

Representation of Numbers from 1 to 20000 in Terms of Palindromic Digits 1357-9-7531

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*During past years author worked with representations of numbers in terms of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. These representations called as **crazy representations**, and are done from 1 to 200000. For details see the references. This work is little different. It brings crazy representations of numbers from 1 to 20000 in terms of **palindromic digits** of 1357-9-7531. For each number 9 digits, 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 7, 5, 3, 1 are used. This we have done by the help of extra operations or functions, such as **factorial** and **square-root**. Similar kind of work for the numbers from 1 to 1729 in terms of digits 1729271 see author's work [18], and for the numbers 1-10000 in terms of 2022-2022 [20].*

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¹ Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijtaneja@gmail.com;

Web-sites: <http://inderjtaneja.com>; <http://numbers-magic.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section, we shall write different ways of writing natural numbers. These representations are divided in four different types.

1.1 Increasing and Decreasing

In 2013-2014, author [21] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 100 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 101 &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 102 &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 103 &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\
 104 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 105 &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 106 &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 107 &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 108 &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 786 &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 56 + 78 \times 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 999 &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321 \\
 2535 &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1 \\
 2607 &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 10483 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 - 7 - 8 + 9 = (9 \times 87 \times 6 + 543) \times 2 + 1 \\
 10549 &:= 1^2 \times 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) \times 1 \\
 10550 &:= 1^2 + 34 \times 5 \times (6 + 7 \times 8) + 9 = 9 + (87 \times 6 + 5) \times 4 \times (3 + 2) + 1 \\
 10553 &:= 1 \times 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (7 + 6 \times 5 \times 43 + 21) \\
 10554 &:= 1 + 23 \times 456 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = -9 + (8 + 7) \times (6 + 5) \times 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 11807 &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that the number 10958 is the only number among 0 to 11111, where we need extra operations, such as **square-root**, **factorial**, etc. to write in increasing case. For more details refer author's web-site link [26]. Extension of numbers from 11112 to 30000 refer [22, 23]. For more studies, comments and suggestions refer author's site link [26]. More details in this directions can be seen in author's work [21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26].

For more studied on crazy representations of numbers by different author's refer [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14]. Youtube videos on number 10958 refer M. Parker [3, 4]. M. Abrahams [1, 2] considered this work as **improbable research**. Recently author [28, 29, 30, 31, 27] wrote the crazy representations of natural numbers using only **factorials** up to 100000. Below are few examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 39915 &:= (1 + 2 \times 3!) \times 4! + 5 - 6! + 7 + 8! - 9 = 9 + 8 \times (7! - 6) + 5 - (4! + 3!)/2 + 1 \\
 39916 &:= 1 + (2 + 3!)! + 4! + 5! + (6! - 7!)/8 - 9 = 9 + 8! - 7 + (6 - 5! + 4! - 3!)/2 - 1 \\
 39917 &:= (1 \times 2 + 3!)! - 4^5 + 6! \times 7/8 - 9 = (9 + 8!/7) \times 6 + 5! + (4! \times 3)^2 - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{39918} &:= 1 + (2 + 3!) - 4^5 + 6! \times 7/8 - 9 &= 9 + 8! + 7!/6 - 5^{4!/3!} \times 2 - 1 \\
 \mathbf{59997} &:= (1 + 2^{3!} \times (4! + 5!) - 6) \times 7 - 8!/9 &= 9 \times 8 \times 7!/6 - 5! - 4 - 3!!/2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{59998} &:= 1 \times 2 \times ((3! - 4) \times (5^6 - 7!/8) + 9) &= 9 + 8! + (7! + 6 - 5!) \times 4 - 3!^2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{59999} &:= 1 + 2 \times ((3! - 4) \times (5^6 - 7!/8) + 9) &= 9 + 8! + (7 \times 6! - 5!) \times 4 - 3^2 - 1 \\
 \mathbf{60000} &:= 1 \times 2 \times (3!! - 4) \times 5!/6 + 7 \times 8!/9 &= 9 \times (8! - 7!)/6 + 5! \times ((4! + 3!) \times 2 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{71051} &:= 1 + 2^{3!} \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7!/8 - 9) &= 9 \times (8! - 7!/6)/5 + 4! - 3!^2 - 1 \\
 \mathbf{71052} &:= 1 + 2 \times (3! + 4 + (5! - 6! + 7!) \times 8) - 9 &= 9 + 8! + 7! \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3!!/2 - 1 \\
 \mathbf{71053} &:= 1 - 2 \times 3! + 4! \times (5 \times 6! - 7!/8 - 9) &= 9 \times (8! - 7!/6)/5 + 4! - 3!^2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{71054} &:= (1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4 + (5! - 6) \times (7!/8 - 9) &= 9 + 8! + 7! \times 6 + 5! + 4 + 3!!/2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{99997} &:= 1 + 2 \times 3! + 4! + (5! + 6!) \times 7 \times (8 + 9) &= 9 - (8 - 7!/6) \times 5! + 4 \times (3!^2 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{99998} &:= 1 - 2 + (3! + 4)^5 - (-6 + 7 + 8 - 9)! &= (9 + 8) \times (7! - 6) + 5 \times 4 \times (3!! + 2 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{99999} &:= 1 \times 2 + (3! + 4)^5 + 6 + (7 - 8) \times 9 &= 9 + 8! - 7! - (6 - 5! + 4!) \times (3!! - 2 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{100000} &:= (1 + (2 \times 3!! - 4! + 5) \times 6) \times 7 + 8! - 9 &= 9 \times 8 - 7 - 6!/5 \times (4! - 3!! + 2) - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

The crazy representations of numbers from 100001 to 200000 is divided in five parts as given below:

- 1 Crazy representations from 100001-120000; [32];
- 2 Crazy representations from 120001-140000; [33];
- 3 Crazy representations from 140001-160000; [34];
- 4 Crazy representations from 160001-180000; [35];
- 5 Crazy representations from 180001-200000; [36].

The whole work is by use of basic operations along with **factorials**. There are few numbers not available by using **factorials**. In order to get the results we used an extra operation of **square-root** or **triangular numbers**. Below are these numbers.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{117059} &:= 1 \times 2 - 3!! - 4! \times (\sqrt{5^6} - 7! + 8) + 9 \\
 \mathbf{153310} &:= 1 + 2 \times ((3! + \sqrt{4})!/5 + 6) \times 7 + 8! + 9 \\
 \mathbf{179618} &:= ((-1 + (2 - 3!!) \times \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{5^6} + 7) \times (8 - 9) \\
 \mathbf{186917} &:= 1 - 2 \times 3! \times (\sqrt{4} - 5^6) - 7! + 8!/9 \\
 \mathbf{194918} &:= (1 + 2^{3!}) \times 4! \times \sqrt{5^6} + 7 - 89 \\
 \mathbf{192398} &:= -1 + T((T(2 - 3 + 4))!) - T(T(5 + 6) + T(7 + 8 + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

This work is little different from others. In this work we shall write numbers from 1 to 20000 using palindromic type digits 1357-9-7531.

2 Numbers in Terms of Digits of 1357-9-7531

Below are numbers from 1 to 20000 written in terms of **palindromic digits** 1357-9-7531. Whole the work is by use **factorials**. There are only few numbers where we used **square-root** also. Below are these numbers:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{17078} &:= (1+3)! + 5! + 7! / (\sqrt{9})!! + (7^5 + (3! - 1)!) \\
 \mathbf{18157} &:= 1357 - \sqrt{9} + 7^5 - 3 - 1 \\
 \mathbf{18253} &:= 1^3 5 + 7! \times \sqrt{9} + 7 + 5^{3!-1} \\
 \mathbf{18281} &:= (1-3) \times 5 + 7 \times \sqrt{9} \times (7 \times 5! + 31) \\
 \mathbf{18282} &:= (1+35) \times 7 \times \sqrt{9} + 7^5 + 3!! - 1 \\
 \mathbf{18303} &:= (1 \times 3!! + 5 + 7!) \times \sqrt{9} + 7! / (5! / (3+1)!) \\
 \mathbf{18401} &:= (1 \times 3!! / 5!)! + 7 \times ((\sqrt{9})! + 7! / (5-3)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{18439} &:= (1+3! - 5)^7 \times \left((\sqrt{9+7})! + 5! \right) + 3! + 1 \\
 \mathbf{18461} &:= 1 + 3!^5 + 7! + \sqrt{9} + 7! - 5! + 3!! + 1 \\
 \mathbf{18463} &:= 1 + 3!! + 5! + \left(7! - (\sqrt{9})! + 7 \times 5! \right) \times 3 \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{18555} &:= \sqrt{1+3} + 57 + (9+7+5!)^{3-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{18587} &:= \sqrt{1+3} + 5 \times \left(7 - (\sqrt{9})! \right) \times 7 \times 531 \\
 \mathbf{18919} &:= 1 + 357 \times (\sqrt{9})! + 7^5 - 31 \\
 \mathbf{18947} &:= 13 \times 5 + 7! + \left(\sqrt{9}^7 + 5! \right) \times 3! \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{19004} &:= (1+3) \times 5 - 7 \times (\sqrt{9})! \times (7-5!) \times (3+1) \\
 \mathbf{19151} &:= (1+3! - 5)^7 \times \left((\sqrt{9+7})! + 5! \right) + 3!! - 1 \\
 \mathbf{19291} &:= 1 - \left((3-5! - 7^{\sqrt{9}}) \times 7 + 5 \right) \times 3! \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{19347} &:= 1 - 3 \times 5 - 79 + 7! + 5!^{\sqrt{3+1}} \\
 \mathbf{19463} &:= 1 \times 3!! / 5 + 7! \times \sqrt{9} + 7! - 5! - 3!! - 1 \\
 \mathbf{19599} &:= 1 \times 3 \times 5 + \sqrt{(7+9)} \times (7! - 5! - (3+1)!) \\
 \mathbf{19979} &:= 1 + (3-5) \times 7^{\sqrt{9}} + 7! + 5^3! - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

In the results given below, there are lot of extra brackets. These can be removed easy by simple calculations.

2.1 Numbers From 1 to 2000

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1} &:= 1^{35797531} & \mathbf{21} &:= ((1^{357}) - 9) - ((7-5) - 31) \\
 \mathbf{2} &:= 1^{3579753} + 1 & \mathbf{22} &:= (13 \times 5) + (7 + ((9-7) - (53-1))) \\
 \mathbf{3} &:= 1^{357975} + 3 - 1 & \mathbf{23} &:= ((1+35) - 79) + ((7 \times 5) + 31) \\
 \mathbf{4} &:= 1^{357975} \times (3+1) & \mathbf{24} &:= (13+5) + ((79 - (75-3)) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{5} &:= 1^{357975} + (3+1) & \mathbf{25} &:= ((1^{357})^9) \times (75 / (3 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{6} &:= (1^{3579} + (7-5+3)) \times 1 & \mathbf{26} &:= 13 + ((57 - (97-53)) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{7} &:= (1^{3579} + (7-5+3)) + 1 & \mathbf{27} &:= 1^{35797} - 5 + 31 \\
 \mathbf{8} &:= (13 - (57 + (9-7))) + (53+1) & \mathbf{28} &:= ((13-5) + (7 \times 9)) - (7 + (5+31)) \\
 \mathbf{9} &:= ((13+57) - 97) + (5+31) & \mathbf{29} &:= ((13 \times 5) - (79-7-5)) + 31 \\
 \mathbf{10} &:= (1-3+57) - ((97-53) + 1) & \mathbf{30} &:= 13 \times 5 - 79 + (75-31) \\
 \mathbf{11} &:= ((1-3+57) - (97-53)) \times 1 & \mathbf{31} &:= 1^{357975} \times 31 \\
 \mathbf{12} &:= 135 - 79 - 75 + 31 & \mathbf{32} &:= 1^{357975} + 31 \\
 \mathbf{13} &:= 13 \times ((57+9 - (7 \times 5)) / 31) & \mathbf{33} &:= (13 \times 5) - ((79+7) - (53+1)) \\
 \mathbf{14} &:= 13 + ((57+9 - (7 \times 5)) / 31) & \mathbf{34} &:= (1^{357}) \times (9 + (75 / (3 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{15} &:= (1 - (((35+7) - 9) + (7-53))) + 1 & \mathbf{35} &:= (1^{357}) + (9 + (75 / (3 \times 1))) \\
 \mathbf{16} &:= (13-5) + (79-75+3+1) & \mathbf{36} &:= 13 + ((57-9) - ((75/3) \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{17} &:= (1 \times 35) - ((79-7-53) - 1) & \mathbf{37} &:= ((13+5) + 79) - ((7+53) \times 1) \\
 \mathbf{18} &:= (1+35) - ((79-7-53) - 1) & \mathbf{38} &:= 13 - ((57-9) - (75 - (3-1))) \\
 \mathbf{19} &:= (13-5) - (((7-9) - 7) - (5-3)) \times 1 & \mathbf{39} &:= ((1-35) + 79) - (7 - (5 - (3+1))) \\
 \mathbf{20} &:= (1 + ((35/7) \times 9)) - ((75/3) + 1) & \mathbf{40} &:= (1-3 \times 5) - ((7 - (97-5)) + 31)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41 &:= (1^3 + (57 - 9)) - (7 + ((5 - 3) - 1)) \\ 42 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 - 7)) - 9) + ((7 + 53) - 1) \\ 43 &:= ((135 - 79) + 7) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 44 &:= (1^{3579} \times 75) - 31 \\ 45 &:= (13 + (((5 + 7) - 9) - 7)) + (5 + 31) \\ 46 &:= (1 \times ((35/7) + 9)) + ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 47 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 57)) - 9) - (7 \times 5)) + 31 \\ 48 &:= (((13 \times 5) + (7 + 9)) - 7) + (5 - 31) \\ 49 &:= (13 + 57) - (((9 - 7) + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 50 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 79) + ((7 - 5) - 31) \\ 51 &:= ((1 - 35) + 79) + (7 - (5 - (3 + 1))) \\ 52 &:= ((13 + 57) - 9) + ((7 - (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\ 53 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((79 - 7 - 53) - 1) \\ 54 &:= 1^{35797} \times (53 + 1) \\ 55 &:= 1^{35797} + 53 + 1 \\ 56 &:= (13 + 57) - ((9 \times (7 - 5)) - (3 + 1)) \\ 57 &:= (((((1 - 3 \times 5) + 79) + 7) - (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 58 &:= (13 - ((5 - 79) - 7)) - (5 + 31) \\ 59 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5)/7) + ((97 - 5) - 31) \\ 60 &:= (((13 \times 5) - (7 + 9))/7) + (53 \times 1) \\ 61 &:= 1^{3579} \times (7 + (53 + 1)) \\ 62 &:= (1^{3579} + 7) + (53 + 1) \\ 63 &:= ((1^{3579} + 7) \times (5 + 3)) - 1 \\ 64 &:= ((1^{3579} + 7) \times (5 + 3)) \times 1 \\ 65 &:= (((13 - 57) - (9 - 75)) \times 3) - 1 \\ 66 &:= (((13 - 57) - (9 - 75)) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 67 &:= (((13 - 57) - (9 - 75)) \times 3) + 1 \\ 68 &:= ((13 + 57) - 9) - ((7 - (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 69 &:= (1^{357}) - (((9 - 75) - 3) + 1) \\ 70 &:= ((13 + 57) - 9) - ((7 - (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\ 71 &:= 13 + ((57 + 9 - ((7 + 5) - 3)) + 1) \\ 72 &:= ((135 - 79) + 7) + (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 73 &:= 13 - ((57 - (9 \times 7)) - (53 + 1)) \\ 74 &:= (1 + ((3 + (5 + 79)) - 7)) - (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 75 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + ((7 - 9) + (75 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 76 &:= 1 \times (((3 - (57 - 97)) - 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 77 &:= ((1 - (35/7)) + (97 - (5 \times 3))) - 1 \\ 78 &:= ((1 - (35/7)) + (97 - (5 \times 3))) \times 1 \\ 79 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 7) - (((9 - 75)/3) - 1) \\ 80 &:= (((1^{357}) \times 9) + (75 - 3)) - 1 \\ 81 &:= ((1^{357} + 9) + (75 - 3)) - 1 \\ 82 &:= ((1^{357} + 9) + (75 - 3)) \times 1 \\ 83 &:= ((1^{357} + 9) + (75 - 3)) + 1 \\ 84 &:= (13 + 57) + ((9 \times (7 - 5)) - (3 + 1)) \\ 85 &:= ((1 + 35) + 7) + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 86 &:= (13 + (57 - 9)) + ((75/3) \times 1) \\ 87 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) + 79) - (7 - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 88 &:= ((1 - 3) \times ((5 \times (7 - 9)) - 7)) + (53 + 1) \\ 89 &:= ((1^3 - (5 \times 7)) + (97 - 5)) + 31 \\ 90 &:= ((1 - 3) - (57 - 97)) + (53 - 1) \\ 91 &:= (1^3) + (5 \times (79 - (7 + (53 + 1)))) \\ 92 &:= ((1 + 35) - 7) + (((9 - 7)^5) + 31) \\ 93 &:= (1 - ((35/7) + (9 - 75))) + 31 \\ 94 &:= 1 - (3 \times ((57 - 97) + (5 + 3 + 1))) \\ 95 &:= 1 + 35 + (7 + ((9 + (7 + 5)) + 31)) \\ 96 &:= 1 + 35 + (79 + ((7 + 5) - 31)) \\ 97 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((79 + 7) - (53 + 1)) \\ 98 &:= (1 \times (35 - (7 - (9 + 7)))) + (53 + 1) \\ 99 &:= ((13 - 5) - 7) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5) + 31) \\ 100 &:= (1^{357}) + ((97 + 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 101 &:= 1 + (((3 - 57)/9) + (75 + 31)) \\ 102 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) \times (7 - 9)) - (7 - ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 103 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 97) - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 104 &:= (1 - 35) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5 - 31)) \\ 105 &:= (1 \times (357 - 97)) - (5 \times 31) \\ 106 &:= (1 - 35) + ((79 + 7) + (53 + 1)) \\ 107 &:= (((13 + 57) - 9) - 7) + (53 \times 1) \\ 108 &:= ((13 + 57) - 9) - (7 - (53 + 1)) \\ 109 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (79 + (7 + 5))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 110 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) - (7 - 97)) + (53 - 1) \\ 111 &:= (1^{357}) \times ((9 \times (7 + 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 112 &:= (1^{357}) + ((9 \times (7 + 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 113 &:= (13 \times 57 - 97) - 531 \\ 114 &:= ((13 - 5) + (7 \times 9)) + (7 + (5 + 31)) \\ 115 &:= ((13 + 5) - 7) + ((9 - 7) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 116 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (79 + 75)) - 31 \\ 117 &:= (((135 - 7) - 9) + (7 - 5)) - 3 - 1 \\ 118 &:= (13 - 5) + ((7 \times 9) - (7 - (53 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

- 119** := ((13 + (5 × 7)) + (97 + 5)) - 31
120 := (1 - ((3 - 5) × 7)) + (((9 - 7) × 53) - 1)
121 := (1 + ((3⁵) - 79)) - (75 - 31)
122 := (((13 + 57) - 9) + 7) + (53 + 1)
123 := ((135 - 7) - 9) + (7 - 5 + 3 - 1)
124 := (13 + (5 - 7)) + ((97 + (5 × 3)) + 1)
125 := (1 + 3) - (5 - ((79 - (7 - 53)) + 1))
126 := (1³) - ((5 - ((7 - 9) + 7)) - ((5³) × 1))
127 := ((13 + (57 + 9)) × (7 - 5)) - 31
128 := ((1 + (3 + (5 × 7))) + (9 × 7)) - (5 - 31)
129 := 1 × 3 + (57 - ((9 - 75) - (3 × 1)))
130 := ((13 - (5 - 7)) + 9) + (75 + 31)
131 := ((13 + (57 + 97)) - 5) - 31
132 := ((13 - 5) + (((7 × 9) + 7) + 53)) + 1
133 := (13 - (5 + 7)) - ((9 - 75) × (3 - 1))
134 := 1 × 3 + (((5 - ((7 - 9)⁷)) - 5) + 3 × 1)
135 := (135 - 7) + (((9 + (7 - 5)) - 3) - 1)
136 := (((1³⁵) + 7) × ((9 × 7) + 5)) / (3 + 1)
137 := ((1 × 35) / 7) - ((9 - 75) × (3 - 1))
138 := (1 + 3) - ((5 - (79 - 7)) × ((5 - 3) × 1))
139 := ((1³⁵) + (79 + (7 + 53))) - 1
140 := ((1³⁵) + (79 + (7 + 53))) × 1
141 := ((1³⁵) + (79 + (7 + 53))) + 1
142 := (135 + 79) - (75 - (3 × 1))
143 := 1 - (((3 - 57) - 9) - (75 + 3 + 1))
144 := (1 × (3 + 5)) × (79 - (7 + (53 + 1)))
145 := ((1 + 35) + ((7 × 9) - 7)) + (53 × 1)
146 := ((1 × 35) - (7 × (9 - 7))) + (5³ × 1)
147 := (13 - 57) + (9 - (7 × (5 - 31)))
148 := ((1 + (35 + 7)) + ((9 - 7) × 53)) - 1
149 := ((1 + (35 + 7)) + ((9 - 7) × 53)) × 1
150 := ((1 + (35 + 7)) + ((9 - 7) × 53)) + 1
151 := (13 × (5 + 7)) - ((9 - (7 × 5)) + 31)
152 := ((1 × 3) - 5) × ((7 - (97 - (5 × 3))) - 1)
153 := (1 × (3 + (5 × 7))) + (9 + (75 + 31))
154 := ((1³ - 5) + 7) + ((97 + 53) + 1)
155 := ((1 × (3⁵)) + 7) - (97 - ((5 - 3) × 1))
156 := 13 - ((5 - (7 × 97)) + 531)
157 := (1 × (35 × 7)) - ((9 + 75) + 3 + 1)
158 := (1 - 3) + (5 × (79 + (7 - (53 + 1))))
159 := (13 + (5 + 79)) + ((7 - 5) × 31)
160 := (1 + ((3 + 5) + (79 + 75))) - (3 × 1)
161 := (1 - (3 - 5)) + (79 + (75 + 3 + 1))
162 := (135 - 79) + (75 + 31)
163 := ((1³)⁵79) + (7 + 5 × 31)
164 := (1³ + 5) + ((79 + 75) + 3 + 1)
165 := 1 × (35 + ((7 + 97) - (5 - 31)))
166 := 1 + (35 + ((7 + 97) - (5 - 31)))
167 := 13 + (((57 - 9) + 75) + 31)
168 := (1 + ((3 - 57) + 97)) + ((5³) - 1)
169 := ((1 + ((3 - 57) + 97)) + (5³)) × 1
170 := ((1 + ((3 - 57) + 97)) + (5³)) + 1
171 := (1 - 3 + 5) × (7 + ((9⁷⁻⁵) - 31))
172 := (1 × (3 × 5)) + (79 + ((75 + 3) × 1))
173 := 1 - (((357 + 9) - 7) - 531)
174 := (13 + (5 + 79)) + (75 + 3 - 1)
175 := (13 + 57 + (97 + (5 + 3))) × 1
176 := (13 + 57 + (97 + (5 + 3))) + 1
177 := (((1 + 3) × (5 × 7)) + (9 × 7)) + (5 - 31)
178 := ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (79 + 75)) + 31
179 := (135 - (7 + 9)) + (7 + (53 × 1))
180 := ((135 + 7) + ((9 - 7) + 5)) + 31
181 := ((13 + (5 × 7)) + (97 + 5)) + 31
182 := 13 × ((57 - 97) + (53 + 1))
183 := (135 × 7) - ((9 + 753) × 1)
184 := (1 - 3 + 5) - (((7 - 9)⁷) - (53 × 1))
185 := (135 - 7) - (9 - ((7 × 5) + 31))
186 := ((13 - 579) + 753) - 1
187 := (13 - 579) + (753 × 1)
188 := (1 + 3) + (((5 × 7) + 97) + (53 - 1))
189 := ((13 + (57 + 9)) × (7 - 5)) + 31
190 := 135 - ((7 + 9) - ((75 - 3) - 1))
191 := (1 × 35) + (((79 × (7 - 5)) - 3) + 1)
192 := ((1 × 3) × (57 - 9)) + ((7⁵⁻³) - 1)
193 := ((13 + (57 + 97)) - 5) + 31
194 := 13 - (((5 - 7) × (97 - 5)) + 3) × 1
195 := (1 - 3) + (((57 + 9) + 7) + ((5³) - 1))
196 := 1 × 3 + (579 / ((7 + 5) / (3 + 1)))

$$\begin{aligned} 197 &:= (1^3) + (((5-7) \times ((9-7) + 5))^{3-1}) \\ 198 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + ((7-97)/((5-3) \times 1)) \\ 199 &:= ((1 \times (35 + (7 \times (9+7)))) + 53) - 1 \\ 200 &:= ((1 \times (35 + (7 \times (9+7)))) + 53) \times 1 \\ 201 &:= (1 + 357) - ((9-7) + 5 \times 31) \\ 202 &:= (1 - 357) + ((9 \times (7-5)) \times 31) \\ 203 &:= (13 + 5) + ((79 + 75) + 31) \\ 204 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 - (7+9)) + (75 + 3 + 1)) \\ 205 &:= (135 + 7) - ((9-75) + 3 \times 1) \\ 206 &:= (1 - (3 - 57)) + ((97 + 53) + 1) \\ 207 &:= 135 - (((7-97)/5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 208 &:= (1 + (357 - 97)) - (53 \times 1) \\ 209 &:= (1 + ((3^5) - 79)) + (75 - 31) \\ 210 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + ((7+9) - (7^{5-3} \times 1)) \\ 211 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 7)) + ((9-7) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 212 &:= ((135 + 7) - 9) + ((75 + 3) + 1) \\ 213 &:= (((1-35) + ((7^{9-7}) \times 5)) + 3) - 1 \\ 214 &:= (((1-35) + ((7^{9-7}) \times 5)) + 3) \times 1 \\ 215 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 + (9-7))) + (53 \times 1) \\ 216 &:= (1^{35}) - (7 - (97 + ((5^3) \times 1))) \\ 217 &:= (135 + (79 - 7)) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 218 &:= (((1+3) \times 57) + (9+7)) + (5 - 31) \\ 219 &:= ((1 + 357) + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times 31) \\ 220 &:= (135 - 7) - ((9 \times 7) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 221 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + (((7-9) + 75) \times 3) - 1 \\ 222 &:= (13 - (5 - (7-9))) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3 - 1) \\ 223 &:= ((13 + (57 - 9)) + 7) + (5 \times 31) \\ 224 &:= ((1 \times (357 - 97)) - 5) - 31 \\ 225 &:= ((135 - 7) - 9) + (75 + 31) \\ 226 &:= ((1 + (35 \times 7)) - (9 \times (7-5))) - (3 - 1) \\ 227 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 7)) - (((9-7) + (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 228 &:= ((1^{35}) - 7) + ((9 + (75 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 229 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7) + (97 + ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 230 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times 7) - ((9 \times (7-5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 231 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((7 \times (9-7)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 232 &:= ((1^{357}) - 9) \times ((7-5) - 31) \\ 233 &:= (1 - (((3+5) + (7 - (97-5))) \times 3)) + 1 \\ 234 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 57) - ((9-75) + 3 \times 1) \\ 235 &:= ((1^{35})^7) \times ((9 + (75 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 236 &:= 135 + 7 + 97 - 5 + 3 - 1 \\ 237 &:= 135 + 7 + 97 - 5 + 3 \times 1 \\ 238 &:= 135 + 7 + 97 - 5 + 3 + 1 \\ 239 &:= (135 + 79) + ((75/3) \times 1) \\ 240 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times 57) - ((9-75) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 241 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 57) - ((9-75) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 242 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) \times 9) - ((7 + (5-3)) + 1) \\ 243 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) - (7 - ((9 + (75 \times 3)) + 1)) \\ 244 &:= (1 + ((3-5) - 7)) + ((9+75) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 245 &:= ((1+3) \times 5) + (((7 \times (9+7)) \times (5-3)) + 1) \\ 246 &:= (1 - (35/7)) + ((9-7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 247 &:= (135 + 7) + (97 + ((5+3) \times 1)) \\ 248 &:= (13 + 5) + ((7 \times (((9+7) - 5) \times 3)) - 1) \\ 249 &:= (((1 \times (3-5)) \times 7)^{9-7}) + (53 \times 1) \\ 250 &:= ((1 + 357) + (9 + 7)) - ((5^3) - 1) \\ 251 &:= ((1+3) \times (5 \times ((7-9) \times 7))) + 531 \\ 252 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + (797 - 531) \\ 253 &:= ((1 + 3^5) - ((7+9) - 75/3)) \times 1 \\ 254 &:= ((1 + 3^5) - ((7+9) - 75/3)) + 1 \\ 255 &:= (((135 - 7) + 9) - 7) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 256 &:= ((1 \times ((35 - 7) \times 9)) + (7 \times 5)) - 31 \\ 257 &:= (1 \times ((35 \times 7) - (9-7))) + ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 258 &:= (135 + (79 + 75)) - 31 \\ 259 &:= ((1-3) \times 57) + (9 + (7 \times (53-1))) \\ 260 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times 7) + ((9 \times (7-5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 261 &:= ((1 + 357) + (9 - 75)) - 31 \\ 262 &:= 1 + ((357 - (97 - 5)) - (3 + 1)) \\ 263 &:= ((1 + 35) \times 7) + ((9 + (7 \times 5))/(3 + 1)) \\ 264 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 - 797) + 531) \\ 265 &:= (1^3) - ((5 \times ((7+9) - 75)) + 31) \\ 266 &:= (1 + (35 \times 7)) + ((9 \times (7-5)) + 3 - 1) \\ 267 &:= (1 - 357) - (9 - (7 + (5^{3+1}))) \\ 268 &:= (13 - (5 - 7)) + (((9 + 75) \times 3) + 1) \\ 269 &:= (1 \times (357 - 9)) - ((75 + 3) + 1) \\ 270 &:= 1 \times (((357 - 9) - (75 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 271 &:= 1 + (((357 - 9) - (75 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 272 &:= (1 - (357 - 97)) + 531 \\ 273 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + (7 \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 274 &:= (13 - (5 - 797)) - 531 \end{aligned}$$

- 275** := $135 + ((7 + 97) + (5 + 31))$
276 := $1 + (35 + 7 + ((9 + (75 \times 3)) - 1))$
277 := $(1 - (3 - 579)) - (75 \times (3 + 1))$
278 := $(1 + (35 + 7)) + ((9 + (75 \times 3)) + 1)$
279 := $135 - ((7 - 9) \times ((75 - 3) \times 1))$
280 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) + (97 + 5 \times 31)$
281 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5) + (797 - 531))$
282 := $1 + ((3 \times 5) + (797 - 531))$
283 := $(135 + (7 \times 97)) - 531$
284 := $((1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7) + 9) - 7) \times 5) + (3 + 1)$
285 := $((1 + 3) \times 57) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) - 31)$
286 := $(135 + 79) + (75 - (3 \times 1))$
287 := $(13 \times 57) - ((97 \times 5) - 31)$
288 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((57 - 9) + (7^{5-3})) - 1)$
289 := $(1 + ((35 \times 7) + 97)) - (53 + 1)$
290 := $(13 + ((57 - (9 - 7)) \times 5)) + (3 - 1)$
291 := $135 + ((79 + 75) + 3 - 1)$
292 := $((135 + 7) + 97) + (53 \times 1)$
293 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 \times 79) - (75 + 31))$
294 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((57 - 9) + (7^{5-3})) + 1)$
295 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 - 79))) + (75 - (3 \times 1))$
296 := $13 + (((57 - 9) \times 7) - 53) \times 1$
297 := $(1 \times ((357 - (9 \times 7)) + 5)) - (3 - 1)$
298 := $(1 + 357) - ((9 \times 7) - ((5 - 3) + 1))$
299 := $(1^3 - (5 + 7)) + (((9 - 7) \times 5) \times 31)$
300 := $((1^3 + (5 - 7)) + 9) + 7 \times (5 \times (3 + 1))$
301 := $1 \times ((35 + 797) - 531)$
302 := $1 + ((35 + 797) - 531)$
303 := $((1 \times 3)^5) + (7 + 9) + (75 - 31)$
304 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) + 97 + (5 + 31)$
305 := $((1^{35}) - (7 - ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) - (3 + 1)$
306 := $(1 + 357) + (9 - (7 + (53 + 1)))$
307 := $1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7) - (((9 - 7) \times 5)^{3-1})))$
308 := $(1 \times (357 - (9 \times (7 - 5)))) - 31$
309 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 - 9)) - (7 - ((5^3) - 1))$
310 := $((135 - 7) - 97) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))$
311 := $13 + ((5 - (79 - (7 \times 53))) + 1)$
312 := $((1^{35})^7) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1))$
313 := $((1^{35}) - (7 - ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) + (3 + 1)$
314 := $(1 + (357 - 97)) + (53 \times 1)$
315 := $((1^{35} \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - ((5^3) + 1)$
316 := $((1^{35} \times 79) \times (7 - 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
317 := $13 - ((5 - (7 \times (97 - 53))) - 1)$
318 := $((1 \times ((35 - 7) \times 9)) + (7 \times 5)) + 31$
319 := $(1^3 + (5 - 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
320 := $(135 + 79) + (75 + 31)$
321 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + 7) + 97 + (5 - 31)$
322 := $(13 + (57 + 97)) + (5 \times 31)$
323 := $((1 + 357) + (9 - 75)) + 31$
324 := $((1^3)^5 \times 7) \times (975/3) - 1$
325 := $((1^3)^5 \times 7) \times (975/3) \times 1$
326 := $(1 + ((35 \times 7) + (9 + 75))) - (3 + 1)$
327 := $((1 - (3 \times (5 - 79))) + (7 \times (5 \times 3))) - 1$
328 := $((1 - (3 \times (5 - 79))) + (7 \times (5 \times 3))) \times 1$
329 := $((1 - (3 \times (5 - 79))) + (7 \times (5 \times 3))) + 1$
330 := $((1 \times 35)/7) + (975/(3 \times 1))$
331 := $(13 \times 5) + (797 - 531)$
332 := $((13 - 5) + 7) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3) - 1$
333 := $(1 \times (35 \times 7)) + ((9 + 75) + 3 + 1)$
334 := $(1 + ((35 \times 7) + (9 + 75))) + (3 + 1)$
335 := $(1^3 \times (5 \times 79)) - ((7 + 53) \times 1)$
336 := $(135 + 7) + (97 \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
337 := $(13 - (5 \times (7 - 97))) - ((5^3) + 1)$
338 := $(1^3 \times ((5 \times 79) - (7 \times (5 + 3)))) - 1$
339 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) - 97 \times 5 - 31$
340 := $((1 \times (357 + 9)) - 75/3) - 1$
341 := $((1 \times (357 + 9)) - 75/3) \times 1$
342 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) - ((7 - (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - 31)$
343 := $1 + ((35 \times 7) - ((9 - 75) - 31))$
344 := $(1 \times 357 + 9) - (7 + ((5 \times 3) \times 1))$
345 := $1 - (((3 \times 57) + 9) + (7 - 531))$
346 := $(13 \times (5 + 7 + 9)) + (75 - (3 - 1))$
347 := $(1 \times (357 - 9)) - (7/(5 + 3 - 1))$
348 := $(1 \times (357 - 9)) \times (7/(5 + 3 - 1))$
349 := $((1 + (357 - 9)) + 7) - (5 + 3 - 1)$
350 := $((13 + 5) + 7) + (975/(3 \times 1))$
351 := $(1357 - 975) - 31$
352 := $(1 \times (35 - 7)) + ((9^{7-5}) \times (3 + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 353 &:= (1 \times 357 + 9) - ((7 \times (5 - 3)) - 1) \\ 354 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 57) - 9) \times 7)) - (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 355 &:= 1 + ((3^5) - ((7 - (9 + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 356 &:= 13 - (((5 + 7) \times (9 - (7 \times 5))) - 31) \\ 357 &:= ((13 - 57) \times 9) + (753 \times 1) \\ 358 &:= 13 + (5 \times (7 - (9 - (75 - (3 + 1)))))) \\ 359 &:= ((1 + (357 + (9 - 7))) - 5) + (3 + 1) \\ 360 &:= ((13 - 5) - (7 + 9)) \times ((7 - 53) + 1) \\ 361 &:= (13 + ((5 \times 79) + 7)) - (53 + 1) \\ 362 &:= (1 \times (357 - 9)) + (7 + (5 + 3 - 1)) \\ 363 &:= ((1 + (357 - 9)) + 7) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 364 &:= (1 \times 357 + (9 + (7 - 5))) - (3 + 1) \\ 365 &:= (13 + (((5 - 7) \times 9) + (7 \times 53))) - 1 \\ 366 &:= (1 \times 357) + ((9 + (7 - 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 367 &:= (13 + (((5 - 7) \times 9) + (7 \times 53))) + 1 \\ 368 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (7 + 9 + 7)) \times (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 369 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 57) - ((9 - 75) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 370 &:= (13 - 57) - ((9 \times (7 - 53)) \times 1) \\ 371 &:= ((13 - 57) - (9 \times (7 - 53))) + 1 \\ 372 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 - 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 373 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) + 7) + 97) - (5 - 31) \\ 374 &:= (13 + 5) + (((79 - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 375 &:= 13 + (((5 \times (79 - 7)) + (5 - 3)) \times 1) \\ 376 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) \times (7 - 9)) + ((7 \times 53) + 1) \\ 377 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times 7) - ((9 - 75) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 378 &:= (1357 - 975) - (3 + 1) \\ 379 &:= (1 - 3 + (57 + (975/3))) - 1 \\ 380 &:= (1 - 3 + (57 + (975/3))) \times 1 \\ 381 &:= (1 - 3 + (57 + (975/3))) + 1 \\ 382 &:= ((13 + 5) + ((79 - 7) \times 5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 383 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5 \times ((7 - (97 - (5 \times 3))) - 1)) \\ 384 &:= (1^3 - 5) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - 53) \times 1) \\ 385 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 \times (7 - 9)) - ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\ 386 &:= (1357 - 975) + (3 + 1) \\ 387 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) - 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 388 &:= ((1^3)^5) \times (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - 53) \times 1) \\ 389 &:= 13 - (((5 - 7) - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 390 &:= ((1 \times (35 - 7)) + (97 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 391 &:= 1 \times (((357 + 9) + (75/3)) \times 1) \\ 392 &:= (1^3 + (57 - 9)) \times (7 + ((5 - 3) - 1)) \\ 393 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) - 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 394 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 5) + 79)) + (75 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 395 &:= ((13 - (5 - 7)) + 9) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1) \\ 396 &:= (13 + 57) + ((975/3) + 1) \\ 397 &:= (1 + ((35 \times 7) + 97)) + (53 + 1) \\ 398 &:= 13 + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) + (7 \times (5 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 399 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5 \times 79))) - ((7 - 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 400 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) - (9 - (7 - (53 \times 1))) \\ 401 &:= 135 + (797 - 531) \\ 402 &:= (1 + (35/7)) + (9 \times (75 - 31)) \\ 403 &:= (1 \times (((35 + 7) \times 9) + (75/3))) \times 1 \\ 404 &:= 135 - (7 - (((97 - 5) \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 405 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times 7) + ((9 - 7) - (53 - 1)) \\ 406 &:= ((1 - 357) + 9) + (753 \times 1) \\ 407 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5 \times 79))) + ((7 + 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 408 &:= (1 - ((3 - 57) \times 9)) - (75 + 3 + 1) \\ 409 &:= 1 \times (357 - ((9 - 7) - (53 + 1))) \\ 410 &:= 13 - (57 - ((97 \times 5) - 31)) \\ 411 &:= (1 + (3 + (57 \times 9))) - (75 + 31) \\ 412 &:= ((135 \times 7) - 9) + (7 - 531) \\ 413 &:= (1357 - 975) + 31 \\ 414 &:= ((1 - 3 + (57 - 9)) \times (7 + (5 - 3))) \times 1 \\ 415 &:= (1 \times (357 - 97)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 416 &:= (13 - 5) \times (7 + ((97 - 53) + 1)) \\ 417 &:= (1 - (35 - (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 418 &:= ((1 + (3 - (5 \times 7))) + 9) \times (7 + (5 - 31)) \\ 419 &:= ((1 + (357 + 97)) - 5) - 31 \\ 420 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) + 7)) - 97) + 531 \\ 421 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5 - (79 \times 7)) + ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 422 &:= (1 + 3^5) + (7 + 9 + (7 + 5 \times 31)) \\ 423 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) - ((7 - 97) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 424 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times ((7 - 9) \times (75 + 31)) \\ 425 &:= ((1 + 35) - 7) + (9 \times (75 - 31)) \\ 426 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (57 + (9 \times 7))) - (53 + 1) \\ 427 &:= (((13 - 5) \times 7) \times 9) - ((75 + 3) - 1) \\ 428 &:= 1 \times ((3^5 + (79 + 75)) + 31) \\ 429 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((79 + 75) + 31) \\ 430 &:= 1 \times (((3 - 57) + 97) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \end{aligned}$$

- 431** := $1 + (((3 - 57) + 97) \times (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
432 := $((((135 + 7) + 9) - 7) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)$
433 := $(1 + (3 \times ((5 \times 7) + 97))) + (5 + 31)$
434 := $((1^{35} \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - ((5 - 3) - 1))$
435 := $((((135 + 7) - 9) + (7 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)$
436 := $13 - (((5 + 7) - 97) \times 5) + 3 - 1$
437 := $1 + 35 + ((797 + 5)/(3 - 1))$
438 := $(1^3 \times 5) + (((7 \times 9) + (7 \times 53)) - 1)$
439 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) + (7 - (97 - 531))$
440 := $((1^{35} \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - (5 - (3 + 1))$
441 := $((1^{35} \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 - (3 + 1))$
442 := $((1^{35} \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + (5 - (3 + 1))$
443 := $(1 - 3) - (5 \times (((7 - 97) + (5 - 3)) - 1))$
444 := $(1 - (3 + (5 - 79))) + ((7 + 5) \times 31)$
445 := $((1^3 + 5) \times 79) + ((7 - 5) - 31)$
446 := $((1 + (357 + (97 - 5))) - 3) - 1$
447 := $(1^3 - 57) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5 + 3)) - 1)$
448 := $1 \times ((35 - 7) \times ((9 \times (7 - 5)) - (3 - 1)))$
449 := $((1^3 - ((5 - 79) - 75)) \times 3) - 1$
450 := $((1^3 - ((5 - 79) - 75)) \times 3) \times 1$
451 := $((1^3 - ((5 - 79) - 75)) \times 3) + 1$
452 := $((1^{35} + 79) + ((7 \times 53) + 1)$
453 := $(13 + (5 \times 79)) - ((7 - 53) + 1)$
454 := $(13 - (((5 \times (7 - 97)) + 5) + 3)) - 1$
455 := $(1^3) - ((5 + (79 - 7)) - 531)$
456 := $((1 + (35 \times 7)) - (9 \times (7 - 5))) \times (3 - 1)$
457 := $((1 + (35/7)) \times 97) - ((5^3) \times 1)$
458 := $((((1 + 3) - 5) - (79 - 7)) + 531)$
459 := $((((1 + (35 + 7)) \times 9) + (75 - 3)) \times 1)$
460 := $(1^{35}) - (79 - 7 - 531)$
461 := $((((1^3 + 57) \times 9) - 7) - (53 + 1)$
462 := $(1 - (35 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 75) + 31)$
463 := $(13 + 5) - (79 + (7 - 531))$
464 := $(((((1 + 3) \times 5) + 79) - 7) \times 5) + (3 + 1)$
465 := $((135 - 7) - 97) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
466 := $((((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 7) + ((975/3) + 1)$
467 := $(135 + 7) + (975/(3 \times 1))$
468 := $(135 + ((7 - 97)/5)) \times (3 + 1)$
469 := $(13 + ((5 \times 79) + 7)) + (53 + 1)$
470 := $((((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7)) \times 97) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
471 := $(1 - 3) + ((579 - 75) - 31)$
472 := $(1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) - (75 - 31)$
473 := $13 - ((5 \times (7 - 97)) - (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
474 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) \times (79 + (75 + 3 + 1))$
475 := $((1^3 + 57) \times 9) + (7 - (53 + 1))$
476 := $(1 \times 3 + (579 - 75)) - 31$
477 := $(1 + (35 + 7)) - (97 - 531)$
478 := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) + ((9 + (75 \times 3)) - 1)$
479 := $((1^{35}) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5))) + (3 - 1)$
480 := $(1 - 3) - (((5 - (7 - 9)) \times 7) - 531)$
481 := $((1 + (357 + 97)) - 5) + 31$
482 := $13 + (((5 \times 7) - 97) + 531)$
483 := $((1^{35}) - 7) + (((97 \times 5) + 3) + 1)$
484 := $(13 - 5) + (7 \times (((9 + 7) + 53) - 1))$
485 := $1 + ((3 - (5 \times (7 - (9 - 7))))^{5-3 \times 1})$
486 := $((13 \times 5) \times 7) + (((9 - 7) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1)$
487 := $((1 - (3 - 57)) \times 9) - (((7 - 5)^3) \times 1)$
488 := $((1 - 3) - (5 \times (7 - 9))) \times (7 + (53 + 1))$
489 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) + (79 + 75))) \times (3 \times 1)$
490 := $(135 - (7 + 9)) + (7 \times (53 \times 1))$
491 := $(1^3 - (57 - (9 + 7))) + 531$
492 := $((1^3 + 57) - 97) + 531$
493 := $(13 + ((57 \times 9) - 7)) + (5 - 31)$
494 := $((1 + ((35 \times 7) \times (9 - 7))) + 5) - (3 - 1)$
495 := $((1^3)^5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7)) + (53 \times 1)$
496 := $(13 - 5) + ((7 + ((97 \times 5) - 3)) - 1)$
497 := $135 + (((79 - 7) \times 5) + 3 - 1)$
498 := $((1 + 357) + (9 + 7)) + ((5^3) - 1)$
499 := $(1 - (35 \times 7)) - ((9 - 753) + 1)$
500 := $(1 - (35/7)) + (9 \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) \times 1))$
501 := $1 + (((35 \times 7) \times (9 - 7)) + (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
502 := $(13 \times (5 \times 7)) + (((9 \times 7) - (5 \times 3)) - 1)$
503 := $(1 \times 3 + (579 - 75)) - (3 + 1)$
504 := $((1 \times (3 + 579)) - 75) - (3 \times 1)$
505 := $(1 \times (3 - (5 \times (7 - 97)))) + (53 - 1)$
506 := $(1 + (3 + 579)) - ((75 + 3) - 1)$
507 := $(1 \times (357 + 97)) + (53 \times 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 508 &:= 1 + ((357 + 97) + (53 \times 1)) \\ 509 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((79 \times (7 - 5)) \times 3) \times 1) \\ 510 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) + (9 - (7 - (53 \times 1))) \\ 511 &:= (1 \times 3 + (579 - 75)) + (3 + 1) \\ 512 &:= ((13 - 5) + ((7 \times 9) - 7)) \times ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 513 &:= (((1 - 3) - (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) - (5^3)) \times 1 \\ 514 &:= (((1 - 3) - (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) - (5^3)) + 1 \\ 515 &:= (1 + 357) + ((9 - 7) + 5 \times 31) \\ 516 &:= (1 - 3 + (579 - 7)) - (53 + 1) \\ 517 &:= (13 + 5) + ((79 \times 7) - (53 + 1)) \\ 518 &:= (1 + 3) + ((57 \times 9) + ((7 - 5)/(3 - 1))) \\ 519 &:= ((13 + 579) - (75 - 3)) - 1 \\ 520 &:= (13 + 579) - ((75 - 3) \times 1) \\ 521 &:= ((13 + 579) - (75 - 3)) + 1 \\ 522 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) + (7 + 9)) + (7 + 531) \\ 523 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5) - 7) - 9) - (7 - 531) \\ 524 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5) - 7) - 9) - (7 - 531) \\ 525 &:= (((13 \times (5 \times 7)) + (9 \times 7)) + 5) + (3 - 1) \\ 526 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 79) - (75 + 31) \\ 527 &:= (1 + (3 + 579)) - (7 \times ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\ 528 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 5) - 7)/(9 - 7)) - 531 \\ 529 &:= ((1 + 357) + (9 + 7)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 530 &:= (1 - 3 + 579) + ((7 - 53) - 1) \\ 531 &:= (1^{35797}) \times 531 \\ 532 &:= (1^{35797}) + 531 \\ 533 &:= ((13 + 579) - 7) - (53 - 1) \\ 534 &:= (1 - 3) + (579 - (7 + (5 + 31))) \\ 535 &:= (1 - (35 + 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 + 31)) \\ 536 &:= (((((1 \times 35) \times 7) + 9) - 75) \times 3) - 1 \\ 537 &:= (((((1 \times 35) \times 7) + 9) - 75) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 538 &:= (1^{3579} \times 7) + 531 \\ 539 &:= (1 + ((35 + (79 - 7)) \times 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 540 &:= (1^{357} + (9 \times (7 + 53))) - 1 \\ 541 &:= (1^{357}) \times ((9 \times (7 + 53)) + 1) \\ 542 &:= (1^{357}) + ((9 \times (7 + 53)) + 1) \\ 543 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times 7) + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 544 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57)) + 9) + (7 \times (53 - 1)) \\ 545 &:= (1 - 3 + (579 - 7)) - (5^{3-1}) \\ 546 &:= (13 + 579) + (7 - (53 \times 1)) \\ 547 &:= (13 + (579 + 7)) - (53 - 1) \\ 548 &:= (((1^{35} + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 549 &:= ((13 + 579) - (7 + 5)) - 31 \\ 550 &:= 1 \times ((3 + ((579 - (7 \times 5)) + 3)) \times 1) \\ 551 &:= (1 \times 357) + (97 \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 552 &:= (13 \times 57) - (9 \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) - 1)) \\ 553 &:= (1^3 \times 579) - ((75/3) + 1) \\ 554 &:= (1^3 + 579) - ((75/3) + 1) \\ 555 &:= (1 - 3 + (57 \times 9)) + (75 - 31) \\ 556 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5) + 7) + ((9 - 7) + 531)) \\ 557 &:= ((13 + (5 - 79)) - 7) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 558 &:= (13 + (5 - 7)) + ((9 + 7) + 531) \\ 559 &:= 13 + ((579 - 7) + (5 - 31)) \\ 560 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) + (75 - 31) \\ 561 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 5) - (((7 - 9) \times 7) - 531)) \\ 562 &:= (135 - 7) - (97 - 531) \\ 563 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + ((797 + 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 564 &:= (1 + ((3 + 579) + (7 + 5))) - 31 \\ 565 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - (79 \times 7))) - (5 - 31) \\ 566 &:= (1 - ((3 - 57) \times 9)) + (75 + 3 + 1) \\ 567 &:= 135 + (((7 \times 9) \times 7) - (5 + 3 + 1)) \\ 568 &:= 13 - (5 - (((79 \times 7) + 5) + 3 - 1)) \\ 569 &:= 1 - ((3 - 579) - ((7 - (5 \times 3)) \times 1)) \\ 570 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) \times 79) - ((7 - 5) \times 31)) \\ 571 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) \times 79) - ((7 - 5) \times 31)) \\ 572 &:= (1^3 \times (57 - (9 + 7))) + 531 \\ 573 &:= 13 + ((579 + 7) + (5 - 31)) \\ 574 &:= (1 \times 3 + (579 + 7)) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 575 &:= (13 + 5) + (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 576 &:= ((135 + 7) - 97) + 531 \\ 577 &:= (1 \times 3 + (579 - (7 - 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 578 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - (79 \times 7)) + (5 - 31)) \\ 579 &:= (1 + 3) + ((579 - 7) + (5 - (3 - 1))) \\ 580 &:= 135 - ((79 + 7) - 531) \\ 581 &:= (((13 - 5) \times 7) \times 9) + ((75 + 3) - 1) \\ 582 &:= ((13 + (57 - 9)) \times 7) + (5 \times 31) \\ 583 &:= ((1 \times ((3 + 579) - 7)) + (5 + 3)) \times 1 \\ 584 &:= (13 - 57) + (97 + 531) \\ 585 &:= 135 + (((7 \times 9) \times 7) + (5 + 3 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 586 &:= (1 \times 35) - (7 - (9 \times ((7 - 5) \times 31))) \\ 587 &:= ((13 - (5 \times (7 - 97))) + (5^3)) - 1 \\ 588 &:= (1 - 357) + (975 - 31) \\ 589 &:= ((13 - (5 \times (7 - 97))) + (5^3)) + 1 \\ 590 &:= (1^3) \times (57 + (9 - (7 - 531))) \\ 591 &:= (1^3) + (57 + (9 - (7 - 531))) \\ 592 &:= (135 + 79) + (7 \times (53 + 1)) \\ 593 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) + (79 - (7 - 531)) \\ 594 &:= 135 - (79 - 7 - 531) \\ 595 &:= (13 - 5) + ((7 \times 9) - (7 - 531)) \\ 596 &:= (1 - 3) + ((579 - 7) - (5 - 31)) \\ 597 &:= 1 \times ((3 + 5) + ((79 \times 7) + (5 + 31))) \\ 598 &:= ((13 + 57) - 97) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 599 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) + ((79 \times 7) + (53 \times 1)) \\ 600 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7 + 9)) \times (75/3)) \times 1 \\ 601 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7 + 9)) \times (75/3)) + 1 \\ 602 &:= (((13 - 5) + 79) \times 7) - 5 - (3 - 1) \\ 603 &:= (((1 - 35) - 7) + (9 \times 75)) - 31 \\ 604 &:= (1 \times 3 + (579 + 7)) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 605 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times 57) - (97 - 531)) \\ 606 &:= (13 - (5 \times 7)) + (97 + 531) \\ 607 &:= (13 + (5^{79-75})) - 31 \\ 608 &:= 1 \times 3 + (579 + ((75/3) + 1)) \\ 609 &:= (13 - 5) + ((7 \times 9) + (7 + 531)) \\ 610 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + 79) + (7 + 531) \\ 611 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + (((79 \times 7) + 53) \times 1) \\ 612 &:= 135 + (((7 + 9) - 7) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 613 &:= (1^3) - ((5 - (79 + 7)) - 531) \\ 614 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) + 7)) + 97) + 531 \\ 615 &:= (1 - ((357 - 975) + 3)) - 1 \\ 616 &:= 1 - (((357 - 975) + 3) \times 1) \\ 617 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 57)) + (9 \times 75)) - (3 + 1) \\ 618 &:= (13 \times 57 - 97) + (5 - 31) \\ 619 &:= 13 + ((5 + (7 \times 9)) + (7 + 531)) \\ 620 &:= (135 - (7 + 97)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 621 &:= (13 + 5) + (79 - (7 - 531)) \\ 622 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times (5 - 7)) + (97 + 531)) \\ 623 &:= 1 - (357 - (975 + 3 + 1)) \\ 624 &:= (1 - 3 + 579) - ((7 - 53) - 1) \\ 625 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 579) + (7 + 5)) + 31) \\ 626 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7 \times 97)) - (53 \times 1) \\ 627 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) \times (7 - 97)) - ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 628 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 + (7 - (975/3))) - 1) \\ 629 &:= (13 - 5) - (7 - (97 + 531)) \\ 630 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 - 7) + 97) + 531) \\ 631 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 + 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 632 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) \times (7 - 97)) + (5 - 3) \times 1 \\ 633 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) \times (7 - 97)) + ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 634 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5) + ((7 \times 97) - 53))) \times 1 \\ 635 &:= 13 + ((579 + 7) + (5 + 31)) \\ 636 &:= (135 + (79 \times 7)) - (53 - 1) \\ 637 &:= ((13 + 579) - 7) + (53 - 1) \\ 638 &:= (13 + 579) - (7 - (53 \times 1)) \\ 639 &:= (1 + (3 + 579)) + (7 \times ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\ 640 &:= (1^3) + ((579 + (7 + 53)) \times 1) \\ 641 &:= 1 + 35 + ((79 \times 7) + (53 - 1)) \\ 642 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 79) + (((7 + 5) - 3) + 1) \\ 643 &:= (135 - (7 + 9 + 7)) + 531 \\ 644 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times 7)) + (9 \times 7)) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 645 &:= (13 \times 57) - (((97 - 5) + 3) + 1) \\ 646 &:= ((1 \times (35 + 7)) / (9 - 7)) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 647 &:= ((13 + 5) \times ((79 - 7) / (5 - 3))) - 1 \\ 648 &:= (1 + 35) \times ((7 + 9) - ((7 - (5 + 3)) - 1)) \\ 649 &:= ((1 - 35) + (7 \times (97 + 5))) - 31 \\ 650 &:= (((1^{35}) + 7) \times 97) - ((5^3) + 1) \\ 651 &:= (13 + (579 + 7)) + (53 - 1) \\ 652 &:= 13 + (579 + (7 + (53 \times 1))) \\ 653 &:= (1 + (3 - 57)) + ((9 \times 75) + 31) \\ 654 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times (((7 - 9) + 75) \times 3) - 1 \\ 655 &:= (13 + (((5 + 79) \times 7) + 53)) + 1 \\ 656 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7)^{9-7}) + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 657 &:= ((1^3 + (579 + 75)) + 3) - 1 \\ 658 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (57 - 9)) + (753 + 1) \\ 659 &:= ((1^3 + (579 + 75)) + 3) + 1 \\ 660 &:= (1 + (3 + 579)) + ((75 + 3) - 1) \\ 661 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + 5 \times 31) \\ 662 &:= (1 + (3 + 579)) + ((75 + 3) + 1) \\ 663 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7 \times 97)) - (53 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 664 &:= (13 + 579) + ((75 - 3) \times 1) \\ 665 &:= (((1 - 35) - 7) + (9 \times 75)) + 31 \\ 666 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 667 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - (7 - ((9 \times 75) + 31)) \\ 668 &:= (1 + 357) + ((9 - 7) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 669 &:= (13 + (5^{79-75})) + 31 \\ 670 &:= (13 \times 57 - 97) - (5 - 31) \\ 671 &:= ((1 - 3) - ((5 \times (7 + 9)) - 753)) \times 1 \\ 672 &:= ((1 - 3) - ((5 \times (7 + 9)) - 753)) + 1 \\ 673 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7 + (9 \times 75))) - (3 - 1) \\ 674 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 57) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 + 3))) - 1) \\ 675 &:= (1^{35}) - (79 - (753 \times 1)) \\ 676 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 79) + (75 - 31) \\ 677 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7 + (9 \times 75))) + (3 - 1) \\ 678 &:= (135 + (79 \times 7)) - (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 679 &:= (1^3 + 5) - (79 - (753 - 1)) \\ 680 &:= (13 \times 57 - (97 - 5)) + 31 \\ 681 &:= 1 + ((3 + 5) \times (((7 + 9 + (7 + 5)) \times 3) + 1)) \\ 682 &:= (1 \times 357) + (975 / (3 \times 1)) \\ 683 &:= (13 \times 57) + (97 - (5 \times 31)) \\ 684 &:= (1 - (3 + 57)) - ((9 - 753) + 1) \\ 685 &:= (1^3 \times 57) + (97 + 531) \\ 686 &:= ((1^3 + 57) + 97) + 531 \\ 687 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + (9 + 7)) + 531 \\ 688 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) - (7 \times (9 - ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) + 1))) \\ 689 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (7 \times ((97 + 5) + 31)) \\ 690 &:= ((13 \times 57) + 9) - ((7 + 53) \times 1) \\ 691 &:= (13 + (5 - 79)) + (753 - 1) \\ 692 &:= ((1 \times 357) - (9 + (7 - 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 693 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) + 797) - ((5^3) - 1) \\ 694 &:= (1 - 3) + (5 - ((7 \times 9) - (753 + 1))) \\ 695 &:= (1^3 - 5) - ((7 - (9 \times 75)) - 31) \\ 696 &:= (1 + (3 - 5)) + ((79 - 7) + (5^{3+1})) \\ 697 &:= (13 - 5) - (((7 \times 9) - 753) + 1) \\ 698 &:= (135 + (79 \times 7)) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 699 &:= (1 - (3 - 57)) + ((9 \times 75) - 31) \\ 700 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5 - 7))) \times (((9 - 7) \times 5)^{3-1}) \\ 701 &:= ((1^{35}) + 7) + (9 \times ((75 + 3) - 1)) \\ 702 &:= ((13 + 57) - 97) \times (5 - 31) \\ 703 &:= ((135 - 79) \times (7 + 5)) + 31 \\ 704 &:= (13 + (5 + 7)) + ((9 \times 75) + 3 + 1) \\ 705 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 \times ((7 + 9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1))) \\ 706 &:= (((1 + (35/7)) \times 97) + (5^3)) - 1 \\ 707 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) - (7 - ((9 \times 75) + 31)) \\ 708 &:= ((1 \times 35) - (79 - 753)) - 1 \\ 709 &:= ((1 \times 35) - (79 - 753)) \times 1 \\ 710 &:= (1 - (35 - 797)) - (53 \times 1) \\ 711 &:= ((1 - 35) + (7 \times (97 + 5))) + 31 \\ 712 &:= (1^3) \times (579 + ((7 + (5^3)) + 1)) \\ 713 &:= (1^3) + (579 + ((7 + (5^3)) + 1)) \\ 714 &:= (135 + ((79 \times 7) - 5)) + 31 \\ 715 &:= ((1 + 3) + 579) + (7 + ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 716 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + (79 + 7))) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 717 &:= (13 - (57 - 9)) + (753 - 1) \\ 718 &:= ((13 - (57 - 9)) + 753) \times 1 \\ 719 &:= (((1 + 357) - 9) + (7 \times 53)) - 1 \\ 720 &:= (((1 + 357) - 9) + (7 \times 53)) \times 1 \\ 721 &:= (((1 + 357) - 9) + (7 \times 53)) + 1 \\ 722 &:= (1 + 3) + (5 + (7 + ((9 \times 75) + 31))) \\ 723 &:= 1 \times (3 + (((((5 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5) - 31)) \\ 724 &:= 1 + (3 + (((((5 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5) - 31)) \\ 725 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) \times (79 + 7)) + (5 + 31)) \\ 726 &:= (1 + 357) + ((97 - 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 727 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 7)) + ((97 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 728 &:= 13 \times ((57 + 9 - ((7 + 5) - 3)) - 1) \\ 729 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) - (7 + 9)) + (753 - 1) \\ 730 &:= 1 + ((3 - 5) + ((7 \times 97) + (53 - 1))) \\ 731 &:= (1 + ((3 - (5 \times 7)) + 9)) + (753 \times 1) \\ 732 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7 \times 97)) + (53 \times 1) \\ 733 &:= (13 + ((5 \times (79 - 7)) \times (5 - 3))) \times 1 \\ 734 &:= (13 + ((5 \times (79 - 7)) \times (5 - 3))) + 1 \\ 735 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) + ((9 \times 75) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 736 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 7) + 97) + (53 - 1)) \\ 737 &:= (1 - 35) + (797 + (5 - 31)) \\ 738 &:= 135 + (79 - (7 - 531)) \\ 739 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 75) / (3 + 1))) \\ 740 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5 + (((7 \times 97) + 53) \times 1)) \\ 741 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 \times (7 - 9)))) + (753 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 742 &:= (1^3 + 579) + (7 + 5 \times 31) \\ 743 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times (79 + 75))) - 31 \\ 744 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((579 + 7) + 5 \times 31) \\ 745 &:= (13 \times 57 - 9) - (7 - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 746 &:= (1 - 3) + (5 + ((797 - 53) - 1)) \\ 747 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 \times (7 - 9)) + (753 \times 1)) \\ 748 &:= (1 \times (35 + (7 + (9 \times 75)))) + 31 \\ 749 &:= (1 - 3) - (5 + (((7 - 9) \times 7) \times (53 + 1))) \\ 750 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 \times (((7 + 97) - 53) - 1)) \\ 751 &:= 1 + 35 + ((7 \times 97) + (5 + 31)) \\ 752 &:= (135 + (79 + 7)) + 531 \\ 753 &:= 1^{3579} \times (753 \times 1) \\ 754 &:= 1^{3579} + (753 \times 1) \\ 755 &:= 1^{3579} + (753 + 1) \\ 756 &:= (135 - 7) + (97 + 531) \\ 757 &:= (1^{35}) - (((7 - 9) - 753) - 1) \\ 758 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) + (7 + 9)) + 753 - 1 \\ 759 &:= (1 - 3 + 579) - (7 \times (5 - 31)) \\ 760 &:= (135 + (7 \times 97)) - (53 + 1) \\ 761 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (797 - 5)) - 31 \\ 762 &:= (13 - ((5 + 7) - 9)) + (753 - 1) \\ 763 &:= 13 + ((5 + 797) - (53 - 1)) \\ 764 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) + (797 + 5)) - 31 \\ 765 &:= (13 \times 57) + (((9 + 7) + 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 766 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 \times (7 - 9)) - (753 - 1)) \\ 767 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7 \times 97)) + (53 - 1) \\ 768 &:= (1 + ((3^5 + ((7 + 97) \times 5)) + 3)) + 1 \\ 769 &:= (((1^{35}) + 7) + 9) + (753 - 1) \\ 770 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) \times ((7 - 97) - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 771 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 79) + 7) + (53 \times 1) \\ 772 &:= (13 + (5 \times 79)) + (7 \times (53 - 1)) \\ 773 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7) \times 9)) + (753 - 1) \\ 774 &:= (1^3) + (((5 + 7) + 9) + (753 - 1)) \\ 775 &:= (1^{35}) + ((79 + 7) \times ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\ 776 &:= 1 - (((3 - (5 \times 7)) + (9 - (7 - 5))) \times 31) \\ 777 &:= (135 + 797) - (5 \times 31) \\ 778 &:= 1 \times ((35 \times 7) + (9 - (7 - 531))) \\ 779 &:= 13 + ((5 + (797 - 5)) - 31) \\ 780 &:= (13 \times (5 + 7)) \times ((9 - (7 \times 5)) + 31) \\ 781 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + (797 - (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\ 782 &:= (1^3) \times (((((5 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5) + 31) \\ 783 &:= (1^3) + (((((5 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5) + 31) \\ 784 &:= ((1 - (3 - (5 - 7))) \times ((9 - 7) + 5))^{3-1} \\ 785 &:= 1 \times (3 + (((((5 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5) + 31)) \\ 786 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times 7) - ((9 - 753) \times 1) \\ 787 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times 7) - ((9 - 753) - 1) \\ 788 &:= (13 \times 57) + (((9 \times 7) - (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\ 789 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 797) - ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 790 &:= ((1^3 - (5 - 797)) - (5 - 3)) - 1 \\ 791 &:= ((1^3 - (5 - 797)) - (5 - 3)) \times 1 \\ 792 &:= (1^3 - (5 - 797)) - ((5 - 3) - 1) \\ 793 &:= (1^3 - (5 - 797)) \times ((5 - 3) - 1) \\ 794 &:= ((13 \times 5) + (7 + 97)) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 795 &:= (1^3) + (((5 + 797) - 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 796 &:= ((13 - 5) + (797 - (5 + 3))) - 1 \\ 797 &:= ((13 - 5) + (797 - (5 + 3))) \times 1 \\ 798 &:= ((13 - 5) + (797 - (5 + 3))) + 1 \\ 799 &:= 1 - (35 - ((797 + 5) + 31)) \\ 800 &:= (1 - 3) + ((57 - 9) + (753 + 1)) \\ 801 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) + 9) + (753 \times 1) \\ 802 &:= (13 \times 57) + ((97 - 5) - 31) \\ 803 &:= 13 - (5 - ((797 - 5) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 804 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7) \times 97) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 805 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 797) + ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 806 &:= (1^{35}) + (797 + ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\ 807 &:= (13 + (5 + (797 - 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 808 &:= (1^3) - ((5 - 797) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 809 &:= (135 - 79) + (753 \times 1) \\ 810 &:= ((13 \times 5) + 797) - (53 - 1) \\ 811 &:= (1^3 + (5 + (797 + 5))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 812 &:= ((13 \times 57) + (97 + 5)) - 31 \\ 813 &:= (13 + (5 + (797 - 5))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 814 &:= (13 + 57) - (9 - (753 \times 1)) \\ 815 &:= 1 \times (3 + ((5 + 797) + (5 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 816 &:= (1 - (35 - 797)) + (53 \times 1) \\ 817 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + 797)) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 818 &:= 1 - ((3 - 57) - ((9 + 753) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 819 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + (79 + 7))) \times (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 820 &:= (((135 + 7) + (9 \times 75)) + 3) \times 1 \\ 821 &:= (((135 + 7) + (9 \times 75)) + 3) + 1 \\ 822 &:= (1 \times 3 + 57) + ((9 + 753) \times 1) \\ 823 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (797 - 5)) + 31 \\ 824 &:= ((1^{35}) + 797) - (5 - 31) \\ 825 &:= 1 \times (357 - ((9 \times 7) - 531)) \\ 826 &:= (1 + 357) - ((9 \times 7) - 531) \\ 827 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 - (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 828 &:= (13 \times 57) + ((9 + (75 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 829 &:= (1^3) + (((5 + 797) - 5) + 31) \\ 830 &:= ((1 + 35) + 797) - (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 831 &:= (13 + 57) + (9 + (753 - 1)) \\ 832 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 - 9) + (((7 \times 5) \times 3) + 1)) \\ 833 &:= ((1^{35}) + 79) + (753 \times 1) \\ 834 &:= (135 - 7) + ((9 \times 75) + 31) \\ 835 &:= 1 \times (((35 + 797) + 5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 836 &:= ((1 + 35) + 797) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 837 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) + 79) + (753 \times 1) \\ 838 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) + (797 + (5^{3-1})) \\ 839 &:= 13 - ((5 - 79) - (753 - 1)) \\ 840 &:= (13 - ((5 - 79) - 753)) \times 1 \\ 841 &:= 13 + ((5 + (797 - 5)) + 31) \\ 842 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + (79 \times 7)) + 531 \\ 843 &:= ((1 + 35) + 797) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 844 &:= ((1 - 35) + ((7^{9-7}) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 845 &:= (1^3 - (5 - (797 + 53))) - 1 \\ 846 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 - (79 \times 7)) + ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 847 &:= (1^3 - (5 - (797 + 53))) + 1 \\ 848 &:= (1 + (3 - 57)) \times ((9 - 75/3) \times 1) \\ 849 &:= (13 + ((5 + 79) + 753)) - 1 \\ 850 &:= (13 + ((5 + 79) + 753)) \times 1 \\ 851 &:= 13 + (((5 + 79) + 753) + 1) \\ 852 &:= 1 - (3 - ((5 + (797 + 53)) - 1)) \\ 853 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 854 &:= (1 + (3 + 57)) \times (((9 - 7) \times 5) + 3) + 1 \\ 855 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 - 9) + ((7 + 53) - 1)) \\ 856 &:= (135 \times 7) - ((9 \times 7) - (5 - 31)) \\ 857 &:= 1 \times (3 + ((5 + (797 + 53)) - 1)) \\ 858 &:= 13 - ((5 - 797) - (53 \times 1)) \\ 859 &:= ((135 \times 7)/9) + (753 + 1) \\ 860 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 + 7) \times 9) + (753 + 1)) \\ 861 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 + (9 \times 7))) \times (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 862 &:= (1 - 35) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times ((5 + 3) - 1)) \\ 863 &:= ((13 - 5) + (7 + ((9 + 7) \times 53))) \times 1 \\ 864 &:= (1 + ((3 - 57) \times (9 - 75/3))) - 1 \\ 865 &:= (1 + ((3 - 57) \times (9 - 75/3))) \times 1 \\ 866 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 79) + (753 - 1) \\ 867 &:= (1 \times ((35 + 79) + 753)) \times 1 \\ 868 &:= (135 + (7 \times 97)) + (53 + 1) \\ 869 &:= (13 + 5) + (797 + (53 + 1)) \\ 870 &:= ((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 - 7) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 871 &:= ((135 - 7) - 9) + (753 - 1) \\ 872 &:= (((1^3 + 5) - 7) - 9) + (7 \times ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 873 &:= (((1 + 357) - 9) - 7) + 531 \\ 874 &:= ((13 \times 57) + (97 + 5)) + 31 \\ 875 &:= ((135 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) - ((5 + 3) - 1) \\ 876 &:= (13 \times 5) + (797 + ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 877 &:= (((135 \times 7) - 9) - 7) - (53 - 1) \\ 878 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7)) + (97 \times ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\ 879 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((57 \times (9 + 7)) - 5) - 31) \\ 880 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - (7 - (53 + 1))) \\ 881 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 + 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 882 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) \times ((7 - 9) \times 7)) \times (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 883 &:= ((1 - 35) + (79 \times (7 + 5))) - 31 \\ 884 &:= (13 \times (5 - 7)) \times (9 - ((7 + 5) + 31)) \\ 885 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 - 9) + ((7 + 53) + 1)) \\ 886 &:= 1 \times (35 + (797 + (53 + 1))) \\ 887 &:= 1 + (35 + (797 + (53 + 1))) \\ 888 &:= ((135 \times 7) + 9) - ((7 \times 5) + 31) \\ 889 &:= ((135 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) + ((5 + 3) - 1) \\ 890 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 57) + (975 - 31) \\ 891 &:= (1 + (357 + 9)) - (7 - 531) \\ 892 &:= (135 \times 7) - ((9 + 75) - 31) \\ 893 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) - ((7 - 97) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 894 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5 - ((7 + 9) \times (7 \times (5 + 3 \times 1)))) \\ 895 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 + 7)) + 9) + ((7 \times (5^3)) - 1) \\ 896 &:= (135 - 7) \times (((9 + (7 - 5)) - 3) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 897** := $((1 + 3^5) + ((7 \times 97) + 5)) - 31$
898 := $(1 \times (3 \times (57 - 9))) + (753 + 1)$
899 := $(1 + (3 \times (57 - 9))) + (753 + 1)$
900 := $13 - (57 - (975 - 31))$
901 := $((1 + (35/7)) \times (97 + 53)) + 1$
902 := $((1^{35} + 7) \times 97) + ((5^3) + 1)$
903 := $(135 + 7) + ((9 + 753) - 1)$
904 := $((1^3 + (5 + 7)) - 9) \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)$
905 := $(135 + 7) + ((9 + 753) + 1)$
906 := $(135 + 797) + (5 - 31)$
907 := $((1 + 35) + 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (53 + 1))$
908 := $1 \times (((3^5) - 7) + (9 \times 75)) - (3 \times 1)$
909 := $(1 + 3) - (5 \times (((7 - 9)^7) - 53) \times 1)$
910 := $(1^3) - ((5 + (7 - ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) \times (3 \times 1))$
911 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) + 9 + ((7 \times (5^3)) - 1)$
912 := $(13 + ((5 \times 7) + 9)) \times (7 + ((5 + 3) + 1))$
913 := $((1 - 3) - (57 - 975)) - (3 \times 1)$
914 := $((13 \times 5) + 797) + (53 - 1)$
915 := $(1 \times 357) + ((9 \times (7 - 5)) \times 31)$
916 := $((135 \times 7) + 9) - (7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)$
917 := $(1^3) - ((57 - (975 - 3)) - 1)$
918 := $(1 - 35) \times (79 - (75 + 31))$
919 := $((1 - 3) - (57 - 975)) + (3 \times 1)$
920 := $(13 \times (57 + 9)) + ((7 - 5) \times 31)$
921 := $((1 + 3) - 5) + (797 + ((5^3) \times 1))$
922 := $(1 \times ((3 + (5 \times 79)) - 7)) + 531$
923 := $(1 - 3 \times 5) - ((7 - 975) + 31)$
924 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 + 797) + (5^3))) - 1$
925 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 + 797) + (5^3))) \times 1$
926 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 + 797) + (5^3))) + 1$
927 := $(1^3 - 5) + (7 \times ((97 + 5) + 31))$
928 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 - 5) \times (3 + 1))$
929 := $(13 \times (57 + (9 + 7))) - (5 \times (3 + 1))$
930 := $(13 \times 57) + (9 \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) - 1))$
931 := $((13 \times 5) - 7) \times (9 + 7) + 5 - (3 - 1)$
932 := $((1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 7))) \times 9) + 7 - (5 \times (3 + 1))$
933 := $((1 - 3)^5) - (7 - (975 - (3 \times 1)))$
934 := $((1 \times (3^5)) - (7 \times 9)) + (753 + 1)$
935 := $((13 + 5) + (79 \times (7 + 5))) - 31$
936 := $(135 \times 7) + ((9 - (7 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
937 := $(13 \times (5 \times 7)) + ((97 \times 5) - (3 \times 1))$
938 := $(1^{35}) - ((7 - 975) + 31)$
939 := $((135 + 797) + (5 + 3)) - 1$
940 := $((135 + 797) + (5 + 3)) \times 1$
941 := $((135 + 797) + (5 + 3)) + 1$
942 := $((1 + 3) + ((57 \times (9 + 7)) - 5)) + 31$
943 := $(13 + 57) + (97 \times ((5 + 3) + 1))$
944 := $(1^{357}) \times (975 - 31)$
945 := $(1^{357}) + (975 - 31)$
946 := $((1^3 + 5) \times (79 \times (7 - 5))) - (3 - 1)$
947 := $((1 \times 3)^5) + ((7 + 9) \times (75 - 31))$
948 := $(1^3 + 5) \times ((79 + 75) + 3 + 1)$
949 := $13 - (((5 \times 7) - 975) + 3) + 1$
950 := $((135 \times 7) + 9) - ((7 \times 5) - 31)$
951 := $(1^3 + 579) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)$
952 := $(1 \times 3) - ((57 - 975) - 31)$
953 := $((135 \times 7) + (9 + 7)) - (5 + 3) \times 1$
954 := $((135 \times 7) + (9 + 7)) - (5 + 3) + 1$
955 := $1 - ((3 - 5) - (797 + 5 \times 31))$
956 := $(1^3) \times (5 + ((7 + 975) - 31))$
957 := $(1^3) + (5 + ((7 + 975) - 31))$
958 := $((135 \times 7) + 9) + ((7 \times 5) - 31)$
959 := $((135 \times 7) - 9) + ((7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1)$
960 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) \times (((7 - (97 \times 5)) - 3) + 1)$
961 := $1 \times (((35 - 79) + 75) \times 31)$
962 := $1 + (((35 - 79) + 75) \times 31)$
963 := $((135 + 7) \times ((9 - 7) + 5)) - 31$
964 := $13 + (579 + ((7 \times 53) + 1))$
965 := $(1^3) + ((57 \times (9 + 7)) + (53 - 1))$
966 := $(135 + 79) + (753 - 1)$
967 := $(135 + 79) + (753 \times 1)$
968 := $((135 - 7) + 9) \times 7 + ((5 + 3) + 1)$
969 := $(1^3 \times 57) \times (9 + (7 + ((5 - 3) - 1)))$
970 := $((1 + 3) - (5 + 7)) + 975 + (3 \times 1)$
971 := $((135 \times 7) + 9) + (7 + (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
972 := $((1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 7))) \times 9) + 7 + (5 \times (3 + 1))$
973 := $1 \times 3 + (5 - (7 - (975 - (3 \times 1))))$
974 := $((1 + 3) + (5 - 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3 - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 975 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 - 7) + (975 - (3 - 1))) \\ 976 &:= (1^3 \times (5 - 7)) + ((975 + 3) \times 1) \\ 977 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) + (((7 + 975) - 3) - 1) \\ 978 &:= 1 - (((3 \times (5 - 7)) - (975 - 3)) + 1) \\ 979 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times (79 \times (7 - 5))) + 31 \\ 980 &:= ((1 - 35) + (7 + 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 981 &:= (((135 \times 7) - 9) - 7) + (53 - 1) \\ 982 &:= 1 + 35 + ((79 \times (7 + 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 983 &:= (((135 + (7 - 9)) \times 7) + 53) - 1 \\ 984 &:= (((135 + (7 - 9)) \times 7) + 53) \times 1 \\ 985 &:= 1 \times (357 + (97 + 531)) \\ 986 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + (797 - 53)) - 1 \\ 987 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + (797 - 53)) \times 1 \\ 988 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + (797 - 53)) + 1 \\ 989 &:= (1 + (35 + 7)) \times ((97 - 5) / (3 + 1)) \\ 990 &:= ((13 - 5) + 7) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 991 &:= ((1^3 + (5 + 7)) \times 9) + ((7 \times (5^3)) - 1) \\ 992 &:= 13 - ((5 - (7 + (975 + 3))) + 1) \\ 993 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 5) + 7)) + (975 - (3 + 1)) \\ 994 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7 + 975)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 995 &:= (((135 \times 7) - (9 - 7)) + 53) - 1 \\ 996 &:= (((135 \times 7) - (9 - 7)) + 53) \times 1 \\ 997 &:= (((135 \times 7) - (9 - 7)) + 53) + 1 \\ 998 &:= (135 \times 7) + ((9 + 75) - 31) \\ 999 &:= ((135 \times 7) + 9) - (7 - (53 - 1)) \\ 1000 &:= (1 \times (35 - 7)) + (975 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 1001 &:= (135 \times 7) + (((9 - 7) + 53) + 1) \\ 1002 &:= ((1^3 + 57) + 975) - 31 \\ 1003 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) - (7 - 9)) \times ((7 + 53) - 1) \\ 1004 &:= 1 \times 3 + (57 + (975 - 31)) \\ 1005 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) - 79) + ((7 + 53) \times 1) \\ 1006 &:= 1 \times ((35 - 7) + (975 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 1007 &:= 1 + ((35 - 7) + (975 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 1008 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) \times ((79 + 7) - (5 - 31)) \\ 1009 &:= 1 - (((3 + 57) - (97 + 5)) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 1010 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (57 - 9)) \times 7)) - (5 - (3! \times 1)) \\ 1011 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5 - 7)) - ((9 - (7!/5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 1012 &:= (1^{3579} + (7!/5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 1013 &:= 1^{3579} \times (7!/5 + 3!) - 1 \\ 1014 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + 97 - (5! - 3! \times 1) \\ 1015 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times (9 + 7)) + (5!/3) - 1 \\ 1016 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) \times (7 - 97)) + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\ 1017 &:= ((13 + 5) - 7) + (975 + 31) \\ 1018 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times 9)/7)) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 1019 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) + (7 + (((9 - 7)^5) \times 31)) \\ 1020 &:= ((13 - 5) + 7) \times (((9 + 7) + 53) - 1) \\ 1021 &:= (13 - 5) + (7 + (975 + 31)) \\ 1022 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7 + ((9 - 7) - 5))^{3! - 1}) \\ 1023 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1))) \\ 1024 &:= ((1 - 3 + 57) + (975 - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 1025 &:= ((1 - 3 + 57) + (975 - 3!)) + 1 \\ 1026 &:= 13 + (((5 \times 7) + (975 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 1027 &:= ((135 \times 7) + 9) + (75 - (3 - 1)) \\ 1028 &:= (1 - (3 - ((5 - 7)^9))) \times (7 - (5 + 3 + 1)) \\ 1029 &:= (1 \times 357) + (((9 \times 75) - 3) \times 1) \\ 1030 &:= 1 \times ((3 - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 - 7) \times 531)) \\ 1031 &:= 1357 - ((975/3) + 1) \\ 1032 &:= (1357 - (975/3)) \times 1 \\ 1033 &:= (1357 - (975/3)) + 1 \\ 1034 &:= ((1 \times 35) - 7) + (975 + 31) \\ 1035 &:= (1 + 3!) + (57 + ((975 - 3) - 1)) \\ 1036 &:= (1 + (3 - (5 - 797))) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 1037 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) - (7 - 9)) \times ((7 + 53) + 1) \\ 1038 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7) \times 97) - 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\ 1039 &:= (135 \times 7) + ((97 - 5) + 3 - 1) \\ 1040 &:= (((1^3 + 5)! / (7 + 9)) + 7) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 1041 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7! / (9 + 7))) + 5 + (3! + 1) \\ 1042 &:= (13 + 579) + (75 \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 1043 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) - 7) - 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 1044 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times 9) - ((7!/5) / (3 - 1)) \\ 1045 &:= 1 - ((357 - 9) \times (7 - (5 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 1046 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 + ((7 + 97) \times 5)))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 1047 &:= (13 + 57) + (975 + 3 - 1) \\ 1048 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times 9)/7)) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 1049 &:= (13 \times (5 + 79)) - (7 + (5 + 31)) \\ 1050 &:= 13 + ((57 + 975) + (3! - 1)) \\ 1051 &:= (1^3) \times (((57 \times 9) + 7) + 531) \\ 1052 &:= (1^3) + (((57 \times 9) + 7) + 531) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1053 &:= (13 \times 57) + (((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - 3) \times 1) \\1054 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 - ((7 - 9)^7))) - 5) \times (3 - 1) \\1055 &:= ((1 - 3!) + 5) + ((7 - 9) + (7 \times (5! + 31))) \\1056 &:= ((1 \times (3 - (5 - 7)))!) + ((97 + (5! + 3!)) - 1) \\1057 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5! + 7)) + ((9 + 75) \times (3 - 1)) \\1058 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) - 7) + (9 + ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1))) \\1059 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5) - (7 - 9)) + (7 \times (5! + 31)) \\1060 &:= ((13 - 5) - (7 - 9)) \times (((7 \times 5) \times 3) + 1) \\1061 &:= 1 + ((357 - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\1062 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7 + 9 + 7)) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\1063 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) - 7) - 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\1064 &:= ((1^3 + 57) + 975) + 31 \\1065 &:= ((1^3 - 5) \times (7 - (9 \times 7))) + (5! + (3!! + 1)) \\1066 &:= 1357 - (97 \times (5 - (3 - 1))) \\1067 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7)) - (5^3)) \times 1 \\1068 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7)) - ((5^3) - 1) \\1069 &:= (((1^3)^5) \times 7) + ((9 - 7) \times 531) \\1070 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5!)) + 7) + ((97 + 5!) + (3!! - 1)) \\1071 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + (7 + (53 - 1)) \\1072 &:= (((1^3 - 5!) \times (7 - (9 + 7))) - 5) + (3! \times 1) \\1073 &:= (((13 \times (5 + 79)) - 7) - 5) - (3! + 1) \\1074 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times ((5 \times ((7 - 9)^7)) - 5))/3 - 1 \\1075 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times ((5 \times ((7 - 9)^7)) - 5))/3 \times 1 \\1076 &:= 13 + ((57 + 975) + 31) \\1077 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7) \times 9)) + 753) \times 1 \\1078 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7 + (975 + 31)) \\1079 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5! \times ((7 - 9) - 7)) + 5) - 3! \times 1) \\1080 &:= (1 + (357 + (9 - 7))) \times ((5 - 3) + 1) \\1081 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) - (5 + ((3! - 1)!)) \\1082 &:= 1 + ((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) - (5 + ((3! - 1)!)) \\1083 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 79)) - 7) + (5 - (3! + 1)) \\1084 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((7!/(9 - 7))/(5 - 3) + 1) \\1085 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\1086 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 - (7 - (9 \times 7))) + 5!) \times 3!) \times 1 \\1087 &:= (135 + 797) + (5 \times 31) \\1088 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 - 79)) + (((7!/5) + 3) - 1) \\1089 &:= (1 + 357) + (((9 - 7) \times 5) + 3!! + 1) \\1090 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5)) - (3! \times 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1091 &:= (13 + (((5! + 7) + 9) \times 7)) + ((5^3) + 1) \\1092 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times ((9 - (7 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\1093 &:= 1 - (((3 \times (5 \times 7)) - (9 \times 7)) \times (5 - 31)) \\1094 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - (7 + (9 \times (7 - (5 + 31)))) \\1095 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + 531 \\1096 &:= (((1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + 753) + 1 \\1097 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 79)) - 7) + (5 + (3! + 1)) \\1098 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - (7! + 531) \\1099 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + (((79 \times 7) - 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\1100 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) - (7^{9-7})) + (5^3 \times 1) \\1101 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! + 7) + (97 - 5)) \times (3! - 1)) \\1102 &:= (13 \times (5 + 79)) + ((7 + 5) - (3 - 1)) \\1103 &:= ((13 + 5) \times 7) + ((975 + 3) - 1) \\1104 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (((7 - 9) + (7 \times 5))^{3-1}) \\1105 &:= (1^3) + ((5! + 7) + ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\1106 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 79)) + (7 + 5)) + (3 - 1) \\1107 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times 79) - ((75 + 3) \times 1) \\1108 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + 97 - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\1109 &:= (13 - 5) + (7 + 9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31))) \\1110 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5)) + 7) + 9) + (7 \times (5 \times 31)) \\1111 &:= (1 + (3!! + (((5 \times 79) + 7) - 5))) - (3! + 1) \\1112 &:= (135 + 7) + (97 \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\1113 &:= (1^{35}) \times (7 \times (9 + (75 \times (3 - 1)))) \\1114 &:= (1^{35}) + (7 \times (9 + (75 \times (3 - 1)))) \\1115 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5 \times 79)) - (75 - (3 + 1)) \\1116 &:= (1^3 - 5) + ((7 + (97 + 5!)) \times (3! - 1)) \\1117 &:= (((1^3)^5) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\1118 &:= (1 \times 357 + 9) + (753 - 1) \\1119 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + 97) - 5) - (3 + 1) \\1120 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 5 \times 79) - ((7 \times 5) + 31)) \\1121 &:= ((1 + 3) + (579 + 7)) + 531 \\1122 &:= (1357 - 9) - ((75 \times 3) + 1) \\1123 &:= ((1^3 \times 57) + 9) + (7 \times (5! + 31)) \\1124 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) - (7 + (53 + 1)) \\1125 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5 \times 79)) - (7 + (53 + 1)) \\1126 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) - 7) - (53 - 1) \\1127 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + 97) - 5) + (3 + 1) \\1128 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((57 + 9) + 75) \times (3 - 1)) \\1129 &:= (1 \times (35 + 7!)) - (9 + ((7 + 5!) \times 31))\end{aligned}$$

- 1130** := (13 + (579 + 7)) + 531
1131 := 13 × ((57 - 9) + ((7 × 5) + 3 + 1))
1132 := ((13 + 5) × ((7 × 9) - 7)) + ((5³) - 1)
1133 := ((1 × (3! + 5!)) - (7 + (9 + 7))) × (5 + 3! × 1)
1134 := ((1³ - (5 - 7)) × (9 × 7)) × ((5 - (3 - 1)))!
1135 := ((1 + 3!) × (5! - 7)) - ((9 + 7) - (5! × (3 × 1)))
1136 := 1357 - (97 + ((5³) - 1))
1137 := 135 + ((7 - 9) + ((7!/5) - (3 + 1)))
1138 := ((1 × (3 × 5 × 79)) + 7) - (53 + 1)
1139 := ((1 × 3)⁵) + ((7 + 9) × (7 × (5 + 3 × 1)))
1140 := (((13 - 5) + 79) × 7) + 531
1141 := ((1 + 3!) × (5! + 79)) - ((7!/5!) × 3! × 1)
1142 := (1 - 3) × (5! + ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5 - (3!! - 1))))
1143 := (1 + (3 + 5)) × (((7 + 9) × 7) + ((5 × 3) × 1))
1144 := (((13 + 5) - 7) × (9 - 7)) × (53 - 1)
1145 := ((1 + 3)! + 5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) + 5!) × (3! + 1))
1146 := (((1 + 3)⁵) + 79) + (7 + (5 + 31))
1147 := 1 × 3! + (5 + ((7 + 9) × (75 - (3 + 1))))
1148 := (135 + 7) + (975 + 31)
1149 := ((1 × 3) × 57) + ((975 + 3) × 1)
1150 := (1³) - (579 - ((7 + 5)³ × 1))
1151 := (1 × 35) + (((7 + 9) - 7) × ((5³) - 1))
1152 := (1 × 3)! × (((5 + 79)/7) × ((5 × 3) + 1))
1153 := (((1 + 3) - 579) + ((7 + 5)³) × 1
1154 := (((1 + 3) - 579) + ((7 + 5)³) + 1
1155 := (135 × (7 + 9)) - ((7!/5) - (3 × 1))
1156 := (1 + 3) × ((5 × 79) - (75 + 31))
1157 := (((1 + 3⁵) + (79 × 7)) + (5! × 3)) × 1
1158 := 1 × (((3 + 5797)/5) - (3 - 1))
1159 := 1 + (((3 + 5797)/5) - (3 - 1))
1160 := (13 + (5 × 79)) + (753 - 1)
1161 := 1 + ((3! + (((5 + 79) - 7) × (5 × 3))) - 1)
1162 := (13 + ((5 + 7) × 97)) - (5 × (3 × 1))
1163 := ((1 + 3)⁵) + (79 + ((7 + 53) × 1))
1164 := ((135 × 7) + 97) + (5! + 3 - 1)
1165 := ((1³⁵) + 79) + ((7 × 5) × 31)
1166 := ((1 + 3)⁵) + (((7 × ((9 + 7) + 5)) - 3!) + 1)
1167 := ((1 + 3!) × (5! - 7)) + ((9 + 7) + (5! × (3 × 1)))
1168 := 1 × ((3 + 5) × ((7 - (9 - 75)) × (3 - 1)))
1169 := ((1 + ((3⁵) × 7)) - 9) + (7 - 531)
1170 := (((1 × 3! + (5 - 7)))! - 9) × ((75 + 3) × 1)
1171 := ((1 + (3!! + 579)) - 7) - ((5! + 3) - 1)
1172 := (((13 × 5) + 7) × 9) - (7 - 531)
1173 := (1 + ((3 + ((5 × 7) × 97)) + 5!))/(3 × 1)
1174 := (((1 × 3)!)! + ((57 × 9) - (7 × 5))) - (3 + 1)!
1175 := (13 × 57 - 97) + 531
1176 := (1 + (3! + 5)) × ((7 + ((9 - 7) + 5!)) - 31)
1177 := (1 + ((3!! + 579) - 7)) - ((5! - 3) - 1)
1178 := ((1 × 3) × (5 × 79)) - (((7 + 5) - 3!) + 1)
1179 := (1 + ((3 × (5 × 79)) - 7)) × ((5 - 3) - 1)
1180 := ((1 + 3!!) + ((579 + 7) - 5!)) - (3! + 1)
1181 := ((1³ × 5) + ((7 + 9) × 75)) - (3 + 1)!
1182 := (((1 + 3) × 5) × (7 × 9)) - (75 + 3 × 1)
1183 := ((1 × (3 + 5)) × ((7 + 9 + 7) + (5³))) - 1
1184 := ((1 × (3 + 5)) × ((7 + 9 + 7) + (5³))) × 1
1185 := ((1 × (3 + 5)) × ((7 + 9 + 7) + (5³))) + 1
1186 := (((1 × (3⁵)) + 7) + 97) + 5! + (3!! - 1)
1187 := (((1 + ((3 - (5 × 7)) × 9)) + 7!) - 5)/(3 + 1)
1188 := ((1 × 3)⁵) + (7 × ((9 × 75)/(3! - 1)))
1189 := (1 + 3!!) + (((579 + 7) - 5!) + 3 - 1)
1190 := (((1 × 3) × 5) + 7) + 97 × (5 × (3 - 1))
1191 := (1 × 3) × (((5 × 7) - 9) + ((7 × 53) × 1))
1192 := (1 × (3 + 5)) × ((7 + 9 + 7) + ((5³) + 1))
1193 := (((1^{3!}) + 5)! - 7) + (97 × 5) - (3! - 1)
1194 := ((1 + 3!!) + ((579 + 7) - 5!)) + (3! + 1)
1195 := ((1 × 3)!)! + (5 × (7 + 9 + (75 + 3 + 1)))
1196 := 1 × ((3 × ((5 × 79) + 7)) - (5 + (3! - 1)))
1197 := 1 + ((3 × ((5 × 79) + 7)) - (5 + (3! - 1)))
1198 := (13 × 5!) + ((7 + 9) - (7 × (53 + 1)))
1199 := (1 × (35 × 7)) + (9 × (75 + 31))
1200 := (((1 × 3)!)! - 5!) × (((7 - 9)⁷⁻⁵) - (3 - 1))
1201 := ((1³ × 5) + ((7 + 9) × 75)) - (3 + 1)
1202 := ((1 × 3) × ((5 × 79) + ((7 + 5) - 3!))) - 1
1203 := ((1 × 3) × ((5 × 79) + ((7 + 5) - 3!))) × 1
1204 := ((1 × 3) × ((5 × 79) + ((7 + 5) - 3!))) + 1
1205 := (((1 + 3)⁵) - 7) + ((9 × 7) + (5³ × 1))
1206 := ((1357 - 97) - 53) - 1
1207 := 1357 - (97 + (53 × 1))

- 1208** := ((1357 - 97) - 53) + 1
1209 := ((1³ × 5) + ((7 + 9) × 75)) + (3 + 1)
1210 := ((1³)⁵!) × ((7 × 97) + 531)
1211 := ((1³)⁵!) + ((7 × 97) + 531)
1212 := ((135 + 7) × 9) - ((7 × 5) + 31)
1213 := 1 × (3! - ((5! - ((7! - 97) + 5)) / (3 + 1)))
1214 := 1 + (3! - ((5! - ((7! - 97) + 5)) / (3 + 1)))
1215 := ((1 + 3) - ((5 - (7 + 9) × 7)) × (5 × (3 × 1)))
1216 := ((1 - 3)⁵) × ((7 - 97) + (53 - 1))
1217 := (((1 + 3!) × (5 × 7)) + 975) - (3 × 1)
1218 := (((1 + 3!) - 5)⁷ × 9) + ((7 × 5) + 31)
1219 := 1 - ((35 + 7) × (9 - ((7 × 5) + 3) × 1))
1220 := ((1 + 3)! × ((5! - 7) - (9 × 7))) + (5 × (3 + 1))
1221 := ((1 - 3) × (5 - (79 × 7))) + ((5³) × 1)
1222 := (((1 × 3)!) + ((57 × 9) - (7 × 5))) + (3 + 1)!
1223 := (1 × (3⁵)) + (7 + (975 - (3 - 1)))
1224 := (1357 - (97 + 5)) - 31
1225 := ((1 × 3)! - (5! - 7)) - (9 × (7 - (5 × 31)))
1226 := (1357 + 9) - (7! / (5 + 31))
1227 := (13 + ((5 - 7) - 9)) + ((7 × 5)³⁻¹)
1228 := (1 × (3⁵ + 7)) + ((975 + 3) × 1)
1229 := ((1³ × 5) + ((7 + 9) × 75)) + (3 + 1)!
1230 := ((1 × (3 × 5 × 79)) - 7) + (53 - 1)
1231 := ((1357 - 97) - 5) - (3 + 1)!
1232 := (1 × (3⁵)) + ((7 + 975) + (3! + 1))
1233 := ((1 + (35/7))!) + (9 × ((7 × (5 + 3)) + 1))
1234 := ((1 - 3!) - 5!) + (((7 × 9) / 7) × (5! + 31))
1235 := ((1357 + 9) - 7) - (5! + 3 + 1)
1236 := (135 + 7) + (9 + ((7 × 5) × 31))
1237 := ((13 + 579) - 75) + ((3! × 1))!
1238 := 13 + (5 × 7)^{97×5/(3!-1)}
1239 := 1 × (((3 × 57) × 9) - (75 × (3 + 1)))
1240 := ((1 + 3⁵) × 7) + ((9 × 7) - 531)
1241 := (((1 × 3) × 5!) + ((7 × ((9 + 7) + 5)) × 3!)) - 1
1242 := (((1 × 3) × 5!) + ((7 × ((9 + 7) + 5)) × 3!)) × 1
1243 := 13 - (5! + ((7 - 97) × ((5 × 3) × 1)))
1244 := (1³ × ((5 + ((7 + 97) × 5)) + 3!)) - 1
1245 := (1³ × ((5 + ((7 + 97) × 5)) + 3!)) × 1
1246 := (1 - 3) × (5! - ((797 - 53) - 1))
1247 := (1 + (3 × 5 × 79)) + (7 + (53 + 1))
1248 := 13 × (((5 × 7) - 9) + (7 × (5 × (3 - 1))))
1249 := 1357 - ((9 - 7) × (53 + 1))
1250 := 1357 - (97 + (5 × (3 - 1)))
1251 := (1 + (3 + 5)) × (7 + (9 + (7 + (5! - (3 + 1))))))
1252 := 1 - ((3!! × 5) - (((7 × (9 × 7)) × (5 + 3!)) × 1))
1253 := (1357 - (97 + 5)) - (3 - 1)
1254 := ((1 + (35 - 7)) + 9) × (7 - 5 + 31)
1255 := (((1 + 3) × (5 × 7)) × 9) - (7 - (5 - (3 × 1)))
1256 := 1 × ((3 × 5 × 79) + (75 - (3 + 1)))
1257 := (1357 - (97 + 5)) + (3 - 1)
1258 := (1 × (((3 × 57) - 9) × 7) + (5³)) - 1
1259 := ((1357 - 97) + 5) - 3! × 1
1260 := (1357 + 9) - (75 + 31)
1261 := (13 × (5 × 7)) - ((9 - (7 × 5)) × 31)
1262 := ((1357 - 97) + 5) - (3 × 1)
1263 := ((1 × (3 × 5)) × 79) + ((75 + 3) × 1)
1264 := (1 - ((3⁵) - ((79 × 7) + 5))) × (3 + 1)
1265 := (1 × (3⁵)) - ((7 × 9) - (7 × (5 × 31)))
1266 := (1 - (3 - 5!)) + ((7 × 9) + (7 × (5 × 31)))
1267 := (1 + ((3! + 5) × ((7 - (9 - 7))!)) - (53 + 1))
1268 := ((1357 - 97) + 5) + (3 × 1)
1269 := ((1 + 3) + 5) + (7! / (9 - (7 - (5 - (3 × 1))))))
1270 := ((1 - 3) × (5 × ((7 - 9)⁷))) - (5 + (3! - 1))
1271 := ((1357 - 97) + 5) + 3! × 1
1272 := (1 + 3)! × (((5 - (7 - 9)) × (7 + 5)) - 31)
1273 := (1 - 3) - (5 + (((7 - 9)⁷) × ((5 + 3!) - 1)))
1274 := ((135 + 7) × 9) - ((7 × 5) - 31)
1275 := (1357 - 9) - ((75 - 3) + 1)
1276 := (1 × (3 - (5! - ((7 × 97) - 5)))) + (3!! - 1)
1277 := (1 + (3 - (5! - ((7 × 97) - 5)))) + (3!! - 1)
1278 := (1 + (3 - ((5 × ((7 - 9)⁷) + 5))) × (3 - 1)
1279 := ((1357 - 97) - 5) + (3 + 1)!
1280 := ((1³⁵) + (7 × 97)) + (5! × (3! - 1))
1281 := (1^{3!}) - ((5 × ((7 - 9)⁷)) × ((5 - 3) × 1))
1282 := ((135 + 7) × 9) + ((7 × 5) - 31)
1283 := (((1 + 3) + 5) + (79 × 7)) + ((5! × 3!) + 1)
1284 := (13 × 5) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) × (53 × 1))

$$\begin{aligned}1285 &:= ((1-3) \times ((5 \times ((7-9)^7) - 5)) - (3! - 1)) \\1286 &:= (1357 - (97 + 5)) + 31 \\1287 &:= 1357 + (9 - (75 + 3 + 1)) \\1288 &:= (13 \times 57) + (9 + (7 + 531)) \\1289 &:= (1 \times 3!)^{(57-9)/(7+5)} - (3! + 1) \\1290 &:= ((1-3) \times (5 \times ((7-9)^7))) + (5 + (3! - 1)) \\1291 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) + 579) - 7 + (5 - 3! \times 1) \\1292 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - 7) \times ((9 \times 75) - 31)) \\1293 &:= 1 \times (3^5 + (7 \times (97 + (53 \times 1)))) \\1294 &:= (1 - 35) + (797 + 531) \\1295 &:= ((1-3) \times ((5 \times ((7-9)^7) - 5)) + (3! - 1)) \\1296 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 57) + 9) - 75))^{3+1} \\1297 &:= (1 + 3)! - ((5! - ((7 \times 97) - 5)) - (3!! - 1)) \\1298 &:= ((13 \times 57 - 97) + 5) \times (3 - 1) \\1299 &:= 1357 + (97 - (5 \times 31)) \\1300 &:= ((1 \times 3)!) + (((579 - 7) + 5) + 3 \times 1) \\1301 &:= ((1 + 3)!) - ((5 + (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5! \times 31)) \\1302 &:= (1 + 357) + (975 - 31) \\1303 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^{(57-9)/(7+5)}) + (3! + 1) \\1304 &:= 1357 - ((9 + 75) - 31) \\1305 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5! + (((7!/(9 + 7)) + 5) - (3! - 1))) \\1306 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 + 79) \times 7)) + (((5 - (3 - 1)))!) \\1307 &:= (((((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97) - 5)/(3 - 1) \\1308 &:= ((135 \times 7) - 9) + ((7 \times 53) + 1) \\1309 &:= (1 + 357) + (975 - (3 + 1)!) \\1310 &:= (((((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) + 7) \times 5)/(3 - 1) \\1311 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 57) + ((9 - (7 \times 5)) - 31) \\1312 &:= 1357 - ((97 - 53) + 1) \\1313 &:= 13 \times ((57 + 97) - (53 \times 1)) \\1314 &:= 1 \times ((3! \times 57) + (975 - (3 \times 1))) \\1315 &:= (1357 - 9) - (7 - 5 + 31) \\1316 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7)) + ((5^3) - 1) \\1317 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + (((((7 \times 9)/7) \times 5!) - 3! \times 1) \\1318 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5 \times 7))) + ((9 \times 75) \times (3 - 1)) \\1319 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) + (5! - 3!)) - 1) \\1320 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5 - 797)) \times 5)/3! \times 1 \\1321 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) - (5 - ((3! - 1)))!) \\1322 &:= 1 + ((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) - (5 - ((3! - 1)))!) \\1323 &:= (1357 + 9) - (7 + (5 + 31))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1324 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) - ((7 - 9) - (7! - (5! \times 31))) \\1325 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! + 7)) + 97) + (5! \times (3! \times 1)) \\1326 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((579 + 753) - 1) \\1327 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + 7) - (9 - (7 \times (5 \times 31))) \\1328 &:= 1 \times (((357 + 975) - 3) - 1) \\1329 &:= 1 + (((357 + 975) - 3) - 1) \\1330 &:= (1 - 3 + 579) + (753 \times 1) \\1331 &:= (1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7))) + (5 + ((3! - 1)))! \\1332 &:= (1^3 + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 - 31)) \\1333 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 + 797) + 531) \\1334 &:= (1^3) + ((5 + 797) + 531) \\1335 &:= (1 \times (3 + 579)) + (753 \times 1) \\1336 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5 + 797))) + 531 \\1337 &:= 1357 + ((9 + 7) - (5 + 31)) \\1338 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (7 \times 9)) + (75 + 3 \times 1) \\1339 &:= ((1357 + 9) - 7) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\1340 &:= (1 + ((3! - 5) + 7)) + (((9 + 7) - 5)^3 \times 1) \\1341 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 79) - (7 \times (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\1342 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times (79 + 7))) + (53 - 1) \\1343 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 75)) - 3!) - 1 \\1344 &:= ((135 + 7) \times 9) + ((7 \times 5) + 31) \\1345 &:= (13 + 579) + (753 \times 1) \\1346 &:= (13 + 579) + (753 + 1) \\1347 &:= ((1 - 3!)^5) + ((79 + 7) \times (53 - 1)) \\1348 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 - (79 \times 7)) - (5^3)) - 1) \\1349 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 57) - ((9 + 7) + ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\1350 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((79 - (7 \times 5)) + 31) \\1351 &:= ((135 + 7) \times 9) + (75 - (3 - 1)) \\1352 &:= ((1357 + 9) - (7 + 5)) - (3 - 1) \\1353 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\1354 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) + (7 - ((97 - (5! \times 3!)) + 1)) \\1355 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 75)) + (3! - 1) \\1356 &:= ((1357 + 9) - (7 + 5)) + (3 - 1) \\1357 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 579) + (753 + 1) \\1358 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5 + ((7 \times 97) \times (5 - 3)))) \times 1 \\1359 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (579 \times 7))/(5 - 3) + 1 \\1360 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - ((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7))) \times (5!/(3 \times 1)) \\1361 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 79) - 7) - (53 + 1) \\1362 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 79) - 7) - (53 \times 1)\end{aligned}$$

- 1363** := $((1 - (3! - 57)) \times (9 + 7)) + 531$
1364 := $(1 + 357) + (975 + 31)$
1365 := $1 \times (35 \times ((7 + ((9 + (7 - 5)) \times 3)) - 1))$
1366 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 - (7 + (9 \times 75)))) - 31$
1367 := $(1 + (3 \times 579)) - ((7 \times 53) \times 1)$
1368 := $((1 + 35) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5 \times 3))) \times 1$
1369 := $(1 + (3! - 5!)) + ((797 - 5) - (3 + 1)!)!$
1370 := $(135 + ((79 + (7 + 5!)) \times 3!)) - 1$
1371 := $135 + ((79 + (7 + 5!)) \times (3! \times 1))$
1372 := $(135 + ((79 + (7 + 5!)) \times 3!)) + 1$
1373 := $(1 \times 3! \times ((5! + 79) + (7 \times 5))) - 31$
1374 := $(1 - ((35 - 7) - (97 \times 5))) \times (3 \times 1)$
1375 := $(1 + 3)! + ((579 \times 7) / ((5 - 3) + 1))$
1376 := $(135 - (79 - 7!)) - (5! \times 31)$
1377 := $1357 - ((9 + 7) - (5 + 31))$
1378 := $((13 + 5) \times 79) - (75 - 31)$
1379 := $((1357 + 9) - 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1))$
1380 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 + 9)) \times 7 - (((5 - 3) + 1)!)!$
1381 := $(1357 - 9) + (7 - 5 + 31)$
1382 := $13 + (((5 - 79)^{7-5}) / (3 + 1))$
1383 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 - (7 - (9 \times 7))) - ((5 + 3!) - 1))$
1384 := $((13 - 5) \times 79) + (753 - 1)$
1385 := $((135 \times 7) - 9) + ((75 \times 3!) - 1)$
1386 := $(13 - ((5 - 7)^9)) + (7 \times (5! + 3 \times 1))$
1387 := $((1 + 3)! \times 57) + ((9 + 7) + ((5 - 3) + 1))$
1388 := $(1357 + (9 + (7 + (5 \times 3)))) \times 1$
1389 := $((13 + 5) \times 79) - 7) + (5 - 31)$
1390 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5 - (7 \times 97)) - (5! / 3!)) - 1)$
1391 := $((1 + (3! + 5!)) \times 7) - (97 + 5!) + (3! - 1)$
1392 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5 - 79 + (7 + 531))$
1393 := $((13 \times 5) + 797) + 531$
1394 := $(1357 + 97) - (5! / (3 - 1))$
1395 := $((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5))) - (3! \times 1)$
1396 := $((13 \times (5 + 7)) \times 9) + (7 - (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
1397 := $(1 + ((3! + 57) \times (9 - 7))) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
1398 := $1357 + (((9 - 7) \times 5) + 31)$
1399 := $135 + (79 \times (7 + (5 + 3 + 1)))$
1400 := $(1357 + 97) - (53 + 1)$
1401 := $(1357 + 97) - (53 \times 1)$
1402 := $1357 + ((97 - 53) + 1)$
1403 := $1 - (((3! \times 5) - (7! + (9 + 7))) + (53 + 1))$
1404 := $((1 - (3! \times 5)) + (7! + (9 + 7))) - (53 \times 1)$
1405 := $13 - ((57 - 9) \times ((7 - 5) - 31))$
1406 := $1 \times (3! + ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times (53 \times 1))))$
1407 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) + (3! \times 1))$
1408 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 \times 79)) + (75 \times (3 + 1)!)!$
1409 := $(1357 + 9) + (7 + (5 + 31))$
1410 := $(1 - 3) \times (57 - (9 + (753 \times 1)))$
1411 := $(13 \times 5!) - (((7 + 9 + 7) + (5^3)) + 1)$
1412 := $(13 \times 5!) - ((79 + 75) - 3! \times 1)$
1413 := $(13 \times ((57 \times (9 - 7)) - 5)) - (3 + 1)$
1414 := $((13 \times 5!) + 7) + (9 - (7 + 5 \times 31))$
1415 := $1357 - (97 - (5 \times 31))$
1416 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5 + 79) / 7) - (((5 - (3 - 1)))!))!$
1417 := $(1 \times (3! - (5 + 7))) - (((9 + 7) - 5) - ((3! \times 1))!)$
1418 := $1357 + (97 - (5 + 31))$
1419 := $((1357 - 9) + 75) - (3 + 1)$
1420 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 + 7) \times (97 + ((5! / 3!) + 1)))$
1421 := $(1357 - 9) + ((75 - 3) + 1)$
1422 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5! - 7)) - (9 - (753 \times 1))$
1423 := $1 - (((3! \times 5!) + (7 - (9 + 7))) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1))$
1424 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) + ((7! / 9) - (7 - (5 \times 31)))$
1425 := $((1 + 3)! \times 57) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) - 31)$
1426 := $((1357 + 9) + 7) + (53 \times 1)$
1427 := $((1357 - 9) + 75) + (3 + 1)$
1428 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 - (7 + (9 \times 75)))) + 31$
1429 := $1 + (((3! - 5) + (7 + (9 \times 75))) + 31)$
1430 := $((1 + 3!) + 579) + (((7 + 5!) + 3) \times 1)$
1431 := $((13 + 5) + (7 + (9 - 7))) \times (53 \times 1)$
1432 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((579 + 7) + 5!) + (3! \times 1))$
1433 := $(13 - (5 \times 7)) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
1434 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7 + 97) + 5! \times (3! \times 1)$
1435 := $1357 + (97 + (5 - (3 + 1)!))$
1436 := $1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7 + 97)) - (5! + (3! - 1)))$
1437 := $((13 - (5 - 7) - 9)! \times (7 - 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
1438 := $13 + ((5 - (7 - 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1))$
1439 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - (79 + (7! / 5!)) + (3! \times 1)$
1440 := $((1 + (35 - (7 + 9))) \times (7 + 5)) \times 3! \times 1$
1441 := $((13 + 5) \times 79) - 7) - (5 - 31)$

$$\begin{aligned} 1442 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5! + 79)) \times ((7!/5!)/3! \times 1) & 1481 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 - 75)) - 31 \\ 1443 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 - 31)) & 1482 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 1444 &:= 1357 + (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1))) & 1483 &:= ((1357 + 9) - 7) + (5! + 3 + 1) \\ 1445 &:= (1357 + 9) + (75 + 3 + 1) & 1484 &:= (1 - (((3 - 5) \times 7) \times ((9 - 7) \times 53))) - 1 \\ 1446 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) + 797) + 531 & 1485 &:= 1 \times (((3!! - ((5 - 7) - 9)) + 753) + 1) \\ 1447 &:= 1357 + (97 - (5 + 3 - 1)) & 1486 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + (5 - (7!/9))) + (7! - (5! \times 31)) \\ 1448 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 79) - 7) + (5 - 31)) & 1487 &:= (1^3 - (57 \times (9 - (7 \times 5)))) + (3 + 1) \\ 1449 &:= (1357 - (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times 31) & 1488 &:= (1 + (3 \times (57 - (9 + 7)))) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1) \\ 1450 &:= (1 \times 3 + 579) + (7 \times (5! + 3 + 1)) & 1489 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5 - 7) - 97) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 1451 &:= (13 \times 5) - (((7 \times (9 - 75)) \times 3) \times 1) & 1490 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (7 + 9 + (75 \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 1452 &:= (1 + (357 + 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times 31) & 1491 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 79) + 7) - (5 \times 31) \\ 1453 &:= ((1^3 + 57) + (9 \times 75)) + 3!! \times 1 & 1492 &:= (135 + 7) + (9 \times (75 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 1454 &:= (13 \times 5!) - ((7 \times 9) + ((7 + 5) + 31)) & 1493 &:= (1 - (3!^5)) + (7 + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1)) \\ 1455 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times (9 + 7))) - (5! \times (3 \times 1)) & 1494 &:= (13 \times 5!) + ((7 - 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 - 1))) \\ 1456 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + ((75 + 3!) + 1)) & 1495 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + (5 + 7)) + ((9 + 753) + 1)) \\ 1457 &:= (1357 + (97 + 5)) - (3 - 1) & 1496 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5)) + 7) \times (97 - 5)) + (3 + 1)! \\ 1458 &:= ((1^{357}) \times 9) \times (7 + 5 \times 31) & 1497 &:= ((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7)))^{9-7}) + (53 \times 1) \\ 1459 &:= (((1^{3!}) - 5) + 7) + (((97 \times 5) \times 3) + 1) & 1498 &:= (135 + 79) \times (7 \times (5/(3! - 1))) \\ 1460 &:= ((135 \times 7) - 9) - (7 - 531) & 1499 &:= 1 + ((35 + (79 - 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 1461 &:= (1357 + (97 + 5)) + (3 - 1) & 1500 &:= ((13 - 5) + (7 + (97 \times 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 1462 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5!) + (7 + 975)) + ((3! \times 1)!) & 1501 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 57)/9) \times (75 + 3 + 1)) \\ 1463 &:= 135 + (797 + 531) & 1502 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 57)/9) \times (75 + 3 + 1)) \\ 1464 &:= 1357 + (97 + (5 \times (3 - 1))) & 1503 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 57)) + (9 + 7)) \times (5 + 3)) - 1 \\ 1465 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 79) + 753) + 1 & 1504 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + ((79 \times 7) \times 5)))/(3 - 1) \\ 1466 &:= ((13 + 5) \times 79) + (75 - 31) & 1505 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 57)) + (9 + 7)) \times (5 + 3)) + 1 \\ 1467 &:= (13 + 579) + ((7 \times (5^3)) \times 1) & 1506 &:= (1 + (((35 - 7) \times 9) - (7 - 5))) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 1468 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 79) - 7) + (53 \times 1) & 1507 &:= (1357 + 97) + (53 \times 1) \\ 1469 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 79) - 7) + (53 + 1) & 1508 &:= (1357 + 97) + (53 + 1) \\ 1470 &:= (13 + 57) \times (((9 - 7) + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) & 1509 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) + (797 - ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\ 1471 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - (5 + 7)) + ((9 + 753) + 1)) & 1510 &:= ((1 - (3!! \times 5)) + (7! + (9 + 7))) + (53 \times 1) \\ 1472 &:= (1357 + 9) + (75 + 31) & 1511 &:= 1 - ((3 - (57 + ((97 \times 5) \times 3))) - 1) \\ 1473 &:= (1357 + ((9 \times 7) + 53)) \times 1 & 1512 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5)) + (7 \times (97 + 5!))) - (3! - 1) \\ 1474 &:= (1357 + ((9 \times 7) + 53)) + 1 & 1513 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5) - 7) \times (((9 \times 7) + (5^3)) + 1)) \\ 1475 &:= ((1357 + 9) - 7) + (5! - (3 + 1)) & 1514 &:= (1357 + 97) + (5!/(3 - 1)) \\ 1476 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (57 - (9 + 7)))) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1) & 1515 &:= ((1 + 35) \times (7 \times 9)) - (753 \times 1) \\ 1477 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) + 7) + (9 \times (7 + 5 \times 31)) & 1516 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + (5 \times 7)) + (9 + (753 - 1))) \\ 1478 &:= (135 \times 7) + ((9 - 7) + 531) & 1517 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! + (7 \times 97)) + (5! \times 3!))) \times 1 \\ 1479 &:= ((1 - (3!! \times 5)) + (7! - ((9 + 7) - 53))) + 1 & 1518 &:= ((1^{35}) + 797) + (((5 - 3) + 1)!)! \\ 1480 &:= 13 + ((5 + 7) + (97 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) & 1519 &:= (13 \times ((5 + 7) \times 9)) - ((7 - 5!) - (3 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 1520** := $(1^3 \times 5) \times (79 + (75 \times (3 \times 1)))$
1521 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 79)) - 7 - (53 - 1)$
1522 := $((1 \times (3 - 5)) + (7 \times (97 + 5!))) + (3! - 1)$
1523 := $((135 - 7) \times 9) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)$
1524 := $((13 \times 5!) + 7) - ((97 - 53) - 1)$
1525 := $1 - ((35 - 797) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1))$
1526 := $(1 - 35) + ((7 + 97) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1))$
1527 := $((1 - 3) \times ((5 - 7) - (9 + 753))) - 1$
1528 := $(1357 - 975) \times (3 + 1)$
1529 := $(1 + 3!) - (5 - ((797 + (5 \times 3)) + 1))$
1530 := $(1^{3!}) \times (((5 \times 7) + (9 + 7)) \times (5 \times 3! \times 1))$
1531 := $((1 + 35) - (7 + 9)) \times 75 + 31$
1532 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) \times 7) + (9 \times 75) + 31$
1533 := $((13 \times 5!) - 7) + (9 + ((7 - 5) - 31))$
1534 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) - 5) + (3!! + 1)$
1535 := $(1 + 3) - (5 - ((7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!))$
1536 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((57 \times 9) + 7) - 5) - (3 \times 1)$
1537 := $(13 - (57 + 9)) \times ((7 - 5) - 31)$
1538 := $(13 \times 5!) + ((7 + (9 - (7 \times 5))) - (3 \times 1))$
1539 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((57 \times 9) + 7) - 5) - 3! \times 1$
1540 := $((1 \times (3^5 + (7 \times 9))) + (7 - 5)) \times (3! - 1)$
1541 := $1 - ((3 - 5) \times 797) + (53 + 1)$
1542 := $1 - ((3 - 5) \times 797) + (53 \times 1)$
1543 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5^{3-1}))$
1544 := $((1 + (35/7))!) - (((9 + 7) - 5!) - 3! \times 1)$
1545 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) - (7 + (9 + 7))) \times 5 \times (3 \times 1)$
1546 := $((1^{35}) + (7! + (9 \times (7 + 5!)))) / (3 + 1)$
1547 := $((1 - (35/7)) - 9) \times ((7 - 5!) - 3! \times 1)$
1548 := $1 \times 3 + (((57 \times 9) + 7) - 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
1549 := $((1 + 3) + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7! - 5!) / (3 + 1))$
1550 := $(1^3 + 5) + ((7! / (9 + 7)) \times 5) - 31$
1551 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 7)) - (97 + (53 \times 1))$
1552 := $((1 \times ((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) - 7)) - 5!) \times (3 + 1)$
1553 := $((1 + 35) \times (79 - (7 \times 5))) - 31$
1554 := $((1^{35}) \times 7) \times (97 + (5^3 \times 1))$
1555 := $((1 + 3)! - 5) + ((7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
1556 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + ((7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
1557 := $135 + (797 + (5^{3+1}))$
1558 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times 9) + 7)) - (5 - (3 \times 1))$
1559 := $(1 \times 3! + 5) + (7! - (97 \times (5 + 3!)))$
1560 := $(1 - 35) + (797 \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
1561 := $((13 \times 5!) - 7!) + (((9 + (7! - 5)) - 3) \times 1)$
1562 := $(13 - 5) + (7 \times (97 + (5^3 \times 1)))$
1563 := $(13 - 5) + ((7 \times (97 + (5^3))) + 1)$
1564 := $(1 + (3 \times 5 \times 79)) + (7 \times (53 + 1))$
1565 := $((13 \times 5!) + (7 - 9)) + (((7 - 5) \times 3) + 1)$
1566 := $(1^3 + ((5 + 7 + 9) + 7)) \times (53 + 1)$
1567 := $(1 + 3!) - (5! \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5^3 \times 1)))$
1568 := $(1 \times (((3^5 + 7) + 9) - (7 \times 5))) \times (3! + 1)$
1569 := $((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times 7) - (9 + 7) + (5 + (3!! - 1))$
1570 := $((1^3 \times 57) \times 9) + (7 \times (5! + 3!))$
1571 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5) + (3!! + 1)$
1572 := $((13 \times 5!) - ((7 - 97) / 5)) - 3! \times 1$
1573 := $(1 + ((35 - 7) \times 9)) + 7! - (5! \times 3!)$
1574 := $(1357 - 9) + ((75 \times 3) + 1)$
1575 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) + (53 + 1))$
1576 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7 \times (((97 + 5!) + 3!) \times 1))$
1577 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times 97) - (5! + 3! \times 1))$
1578 := $1357 + (97 + ((5^3) - 1))$
1579 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + (((7 + 97) \times 5) \times 3) - 1$
1580 := $(1 - 3) + ((579 + ((7! / 5) - 3!)) + 1)$
1581 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 + 97) - 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
1582 := $(1 \times 35) + (7 \times ((97 + (5^3)) - 1))$
1583 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - 797)) + (5 - 3! \times 1)$
1584 := $((13 \times 5!) - ((7 - 97) / 5)) + 3! \times 1$
1585 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - 797)) - (5 - 3! \times 1)$
1586 := $1 \times 3! + ((5! \times 79) / ((7 + 5) / (3 - 1)))$
1587 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + (797 \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
1588 := $((13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) / 3! \times 1$
1589 := $((13 + 5) \times (79 + 7)) + (5! / 3) + 1$
1590 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 + 797) - 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
1591 := $1 - (3! - ((57 \times (9 - 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)))$
1592 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - 797)) + ((5 + 3) \times 1)$
1593 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5 + (7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)))) + (3!! + 1)$
1594 := $((13 + 579) + (7! / 5)) - (3! \times 1)$
1595 := $(1 + (35 - 7)) \times (((9 \times (7 - 5)) \times 3) + 1)$
1596 := $(13 + 579) + ((7! / 5) - (3 + 1))$
1597 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) - 7^9) + (7 \times (5 \times 3!))$

$$\begin{aligned}1598 &:= ((135 + 7) + (97 \times (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\1599 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1))) \\1600 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 79) + (((7 - 5 + 3)!) - 1) \\1601 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5 - 7975)/(3! - 1)) \\1602 &:= ((1 + (3 - (5 - 797))) + 5) \times (3 - 1) \\1603 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) - (79 - (7!/(5 - (3 - 1)))) \\1604 &:= (1 + 3!) + (5 \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5^3 \times 1))) \\1605 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 579)) - (7 + (5^3 \times 1)) \\1606 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 579) - 7)) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\1607 &:= ((1 + ((3 \times 579) - 7)) - (5^3)) + 1 \\1608 &:= (1 + ((35 + (79 - 7) \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\1609 &:= 13 + ((5 + 7975)/(3! - 1)) \\1610 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + 7) + ((97 - 53) - 1) \\1611 &:= (13 \times (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\1612 &:= (1 \times 3! \times ((5! + 7) + 9)) + (75 + (3!! + 1)) \\1613 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + ((79 - 7) + 5)) - (3 + 1)! \\1614 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5 - (797 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\1615 &:= ((1 + 35) \times (79 - (7 \times 5))) + 31 \\1616 &:= ((1 \times ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) \times 7) + (5! \times (3! \times 1)) \\1617 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times 79) - 7) + ((5! \times 3) \times 1) \\1618 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + 79) - (7 + ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\1619 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times 7) - ((97 - (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\1620 &:= (13 + (5 - (7 - 97))) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\1621 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 79) + (7 \times (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\1622 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5!) \times 7) + (((9 + 7) + 5) + (3!! - 1))) \\1623 &:= (((13 + (5! + 7)) + (9 \times 7)) \times (5 + 3)) - 1 \\1624 &:= ((1^{3!} + 57) \times ((9 + 7) + (5 + (3! + 1)))) \\1625 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 79)) - 7) + (53 - 1) \\1626 &:= (1 + (((3 + 57) \times 9)/(7 - 5))) \times 3! \times 1 \\1627 &:= ((1 + 3)! - (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7))))/(5 - 3) + 1 \\1628 &:= (13 - 57) \times (9 + ((7 - 53) \times 1)) \\1629 &:= (((1 - (3! - 57)) \times 9) + 75) \times (3 \times 1) \\1630 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times 79) + (7 + (5! \times 3))) - 1 \\1631 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times 79) + ((7 + (5! \times 3)) \times 1) \\1632 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7 + 5) \times 31) \\1633 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 579) - ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) \times 1)) \\1634 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5!)) + (797 + ((5! - 3) - 1)) \\1635 &:= (1 \times (((3! \times 5) + 79) \times 75))/(3! - 1) \\1636 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) + 5) + 3 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1637 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! - 5) + (797 + ((5^3) \times 1)) \\1638 &:= (13 \times (579 - 75))/(3 + 1) \\1639 &:= (((((1 \times 3)!)! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) - ((7! + 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\1640 &:= 1 \times (((((3^5) \times 7) - (97 - 5)) + 31)) \\1641 &:= 1 + (((((3^5) \times 7) - (97 - 5)) + 31)) \\1642 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 797) + 5) - (3!! \times 1) \\1643 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 7) + 97)) - (5 \times 31) \\1644 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! + 7) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - 31)) \\1645 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5! + 79)) + ((7!/5!) \times 3! \times 1) \\1646 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5!)) + ((7 \times 97) + (5! + 3!))) \times 1 \\1647 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5!)) + ((7 \times 97) + (5! + 3!))) + 1 \\1648 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + (79 + (7 + 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\1649 &:= (13 \times 5!) + (79 + ((7 + (5 - 3)) + 1)) \\1650 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (5! + ((7 - 9) \times (75 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\1651 &:= (((((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times 7) + 9) + (753 \times 1)) \\1652 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 - 9) + (7!/(5 + 3 \times 1))) \\1653 &:= (((1^{3!} + ((5 + 7) + 9)) \times 75) + (3 \times 1)) \\1654 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5))) - (3! - 1) \\1655 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) - ((7 \times 9) - 7)) \times 5) + 3!! \times 1 \\1656 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5! - (7 - (9 - 7)))/5)) \times (3 + 1)! \\1657 &:= ((13 - (5 \times (7 - 9))) \times (75 - 3)) + 1 \\1658 &:= (13 - ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!) \\1659 &:= 1 \times (((((3^5) \times 7) - 9) - (((7 \times 5) - 3) + 1))) \\1660 &:= 1 + (((((3^5) \times 7) - 9) - (((7 \times 5) - 3) + 1))) \\1661 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) + 7) - (9 \times (7 \times (5 - 3))) \\1662 &:= ((1 - 35) - 797) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1) \\1663 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7 + 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \\1664 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5))) + (3! - 1) \\1665 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) \times ((79 + (7 \times (5 \times 3))) + 1) \\1666 &:= (13 \times 5!) + ((7 \times 9) + ((7 + 5) + 31)) \\1667 &:= 1357 + (((9 - 7) \times 5) \times 31) \\1668 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5) - ((7 - 9)^7))) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1) \\1669 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7 + 5!)) + (3 \times 1) \\1670 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times 5!) + (79 + (7 \times 5!)))) + 31 \\1671 &:= (((1 - 35) - 7)^{9-7}) - ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\1672 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) \times ((7 - 9) \times ((7 \times 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\1673 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7 \times 97) - 5!)) - (3 + 1) \\1674 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times ((5 \times 7) + ((9 - 7) \times 5!))) + (3 + 1)! \\1675 &:= (((((1 + 3) - 57) + 9) + ((7! + 5!)/3)) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1676 &:= (((1 + 35) + 797) + 5) \times (3 - 1) & 1715 &:= (13 - (5! + ((7 - 97) \times 5))) \times (3! - 1) \\ 1677 &:= (((((13 \times 5!) + 7) - 9) - 7) + ((5^3) + 1)) & 1716 &:= (1^{3!}) \times ((579 - 7) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\ 1678 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5! - (7 \times ((9 + 7)^{5-3 \times 1})) & 1717 &:= (1^{3!}) + ((579 - 7) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\ 1679 &:= 1 \times (((((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) + (7! + 5)) / (3 \times 1)) & 1718 &:= (1^{357}) - ((9 - (7! + 5!)) / (3 \times 1)) \\ 1680 &:= 1 + (((((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) + (7! + 5)) / (3 \times 1)) & 1719 &:= 135 + ((797 - 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 1681 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7 \times 97) - 5!)) + (3 + 1) & 1720 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + (79 + 75)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 1682 &:= ((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 9)) \times 7) - (5! - 31) & 1721 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - 57) + 97)) \times (5! / 3)) + 1 \\ 1683 &:= 1357 + ((975 / 3) + 1) & 1722 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 579) - (7 + 5))) - (3 + 1) \\ 1684 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (7 + 97)) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) & 1723 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((579 - 7) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\ 1685 &:= (13 \times 57) + (975 - 31) & 1724 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + ((5 - 7) + (975 + 31)) \\ 1686 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5 \times (7 + 9))) \times 7) - (5 - (3 + 1)) & 1725 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 579) + (7 + 5)) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 1687 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5! - 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 + 3 \times 1))) & 1726 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 579) + (7 + 5)) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 1688 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5 \times (7 + 9))) \times 7) + (5 - (3 + 1)) & 1727 &:= ((1 + ((3^5 + 7) \times 9)) + 7) - 531 \\ 1689 &:= (135 \times 7) - (9 - (753 \times 1)) & 1728 &:= ((1 - (3 - 57)) + 9) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 1690 &:= (1 + (3 \times 579)) - ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)) & 1729 &:= 13 \times (((5! + 79) - (7 \times 5)) - 31) \\ 1691 &:= (((1 - 35) - 7)^{9-7}) + ((5 + 3!) - 1) & 1730 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 + 7!)) + (9 \times (753 \times 1)) \\ 1692 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) - ((7 - 9) \times ((7 \times 5!) - (3 + 1))) & 1731 &:= ((1 - 3) - ((5 + 7!) - (9 \times 753))) + 1 \\ 1693 &:= 1 + (3! \times ((57 + (9 \times (75 / 3))) \times 1)) & 1732 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (53 - 1)) \\ 1694 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 79) + 7) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1) & 1733 &:= 1 + (((3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (53 - 1)) \\ 1695 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! - 7) + (9 - 7))) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)) & 1734 &:= ((135 + 79) + 75) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 1696 &:= (1 \times (3!! + (5! \times 7))) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times (3 - 1)) & 1735 &:= ((135 \times 7) \times (9 - 7)) - (5 \times 31) \\ 1697 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) + (((7! - (9 \times 7)) + 5!) / 3)) - 1 & 1736 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7 + 9)) \times (7 \times (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 1698 &:= (13 + 5) + (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) & 1737 &:= ((1 - (3 - 579)) + (7 - 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 1699 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times (97 - 5)) + 31) & 1738 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 + (7 - 5))) - (3! - 1) \\ 1700 &:= (1 \times (3 \times ((579 - 7) + 5))) - 31 & 1739 &:= (((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + 9) + 7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 1701 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 579) - 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1) & 1740 &:= (1 \times 3 + (579 - (7 - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 1702 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) + 79) \times (7 - (53 \times 1)) & 1741 &:= ((13 + 57) - 9) + (7! / (5 - (3 - 1))) \\ 1703 &:= 1 \times (3 - ((5 + (7 - 97)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))) & 1742 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (579 - 7)) - 5)) + 31 \\ 1704 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5! + 7) - ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1))) & 1743 &:= (13 \times ((5! + (7 - 9)) + 7)) + ((5! - 3) + 1) \\ 1705 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) / 7)) + (5^{3+1}) & 1744 &:= ((1^3)^5) \times (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 1706 &:= (13 + 5) - ((7 - 975) - 3!! \times 1) & 1745 &:= ((1^3)^5) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 1707 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + ((5 + 3) + 1)) & 1746 &:= (1 \times 3 + 579) \times ((7 + 5) / (3 + 1)) \\ 1708 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 - (7 \times 975)) / (3 + 1)) & 1747 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) - ((7 - 9) \times (753 - 1)) \\ 1709 &:= (((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + 9) + 7 - (5 \times (3 \times 1)) & 1748 &:= (((1^3)^5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 1710 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times (97 - (53 - 1)) & 1749 &:= (((1 + 3) + 579) \times (7 + 5)) / (3 + 1) \\ 1711 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((5 - (7 \times 975)) / (3 + 1)) & 1750 &:= (1 \times 35) \times ((7 + 97) - (53 + 1)) \\ 1712 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (((7 \times 97) + 5) + 3 + 1) & 1751 &:= 1 - (((3 + 5) \times ((7 - 9)^7)) - (5 + (3!! + 1))) \\ 1713 &:= 1 + (((3^5 + 7) \times 9) - (7 + 531)) & 1752 &:= (13 - (5 - (7 + 9))) \times (75 - (3 - 1)) \\ 1714 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) - 7!) + (9 \times (753 - 1)) & 1753 &:= (1 - (35 / 7)!) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1754 &:= ((1 + (35 \times 79)) - (7!/5)) - (3 + 1) \\1755 &:= ((13 - (5 - 7)) \times 9) \times ((7 \times (5 - 3)) - 1) \\1756 &:= (((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times 7) - (9 + (7 \times 5))) - 3! \times 1 \\1757 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7! - ((9 \times (7 + 5)) \times 31)) \\1758 &:= (13 \times 5!) + ((797 - 5)/(3 + 1)) \\1759 &:= ((1 + ((35 \times 7) + 9)) \times 7) + (5 - 31) \\1760 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 579) - 7) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\1761 &:= 13 - (((5 - 7)^9) + 75) \times (3 + 1) \\1762 &:= (1 \times (3 \times ((579 - 7) + 5))) + 31 \\1763 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times 7)) + ((97 - 5) - 31) \\1764 &:= (1 + 35) \times (7 \times (9 + ((7 - (5 + 3)) - 1))) \\1765 &:= (13 - 5!) - ((79 - 7) \times (5 - 31)) \\1766 &:= (13 \times (5 - (7 - 97))) + 531 \\1767 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((797 - 53) - 1) \\1768 &:= (13 \times (579 - (7 \times 5)))/(3 + 1) \\1769 &:= (1 \times (3! - (5 \times 7))) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5! + 3 + 1)) \\1770 &:= (13 + (579 - (7 - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\1771 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 579) + (7 - 5))) + 31 \\1772 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - (5! + ((3! + 1)!)) \\1773 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 579) + (7 + 5))) + (3 + 1)! \\1774 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 \times ((7 + 9) - 75)) \times 3! \times 1) \\1775 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 579) + ((7 \times 5) + 3)) \times 1 \\1776 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 579) + ((7 \times 5) + 3)) + 1 \\1777 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times 7) + (9 - (753 - 1)) \\1778 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 79)) \times 7) + ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\1779 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + 5!) - (7 \times ((97 \times 5) - 3) + 1)) \\1780 &:= (1 - 3) + ((57 + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) \times (3! \times 1)) \\1781 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 579) + 75)) - 31 \\1782 &:= 1 \times ((3! + (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5) + 31) \\1783 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times 7) + ((97 - (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\1784 &:= 1 - (((3 - (5 + 79)) \times (7 + (5 \times 3))) - 1) \\1785 &:= (((1 \times 35) + (7 \times 97)) \times 5)/(3 - 1) \\1786 &:= (1 + (3 \times 579)) + ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\1787 &:= ((1 + ((3 + 5) \times 7)) \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) - (3! + 1) \\1788 &:= (((1^3)^5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + 5) \times (3 + 1) \\1789 &:= (1 - ((3^5) - 7)) + ((9 \times (75 \times 3)) - 1) \\1790 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) \times (7 - (9 \times 7))) + ((5 - 3!) - 1) \\1791 &:= (((13 + 5) + 7!) + (9 \times (7 \times 5)))/(3 \times 1) \\1792 &:= (((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + 9) \times 7) + (5 \times 3) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1793 &:= (((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + 9) \times 7) + (5 \times 3) \times 1 \\1794 &:= ((1 + (357 + (9 - 7))) \times 5) - 3! \times 1 \\1795 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (((5! - 7) \times (9 + 7)) - 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\1796 &:= 1 \times ((357 + (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\1797 &:= 1 + ((357 + (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\1798 &:= 1 - (((3 - 57) \times 9) + (7 - 5!)) \times 3 \times 1) \\1799 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) \times (79 - ((7!/(5 \times 3)) \times 1)) \\1800 &:= (1 - ((3! \times 5) + (79 - (7!/5)))) \times (3 - 1) \\1801 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 79) + 7) + (5 \times 31) \\1802 &:= (1 \times (3! + (5! + (7! + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)))))/(3 \times 1) \\1803 &:= ((1 + (357 + (9 - 7))) \times 5) + (3 \times 1) \\1804 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 5) \times ((7 + (97 \times 5))/3)) \times 1 \\1805 &:= (13 \times 5!) - (7 - ((9 - 7) \times ((5^3) + 1))) \\1806 &:= (((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7)/(5 - 3)) \times 1 \\1807 &:= (((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7)/(5 - 3)) + 1 \\1808 &:= ((1^3!) \times (579 - (7 + 5!))) \times (3 + 1) \\1809 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + 9) - (((7 - 5) \times 3) \times 1)! \\1810 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) \times (((7 - 9)^7) - (53 \times 1)) \\1811 &:= ((1 + ((35 \times 7) + 9)) \times 7) - (5 - 31) \\1812 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 + 75)/(3! + 1)) \\1813 &:= (1 - (3! + (57 - 9))) + ((7! + 5!)/(3 - 1)) \\1814 &:= (((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - 97) \times 5) + (3 + 1)! \\1815 &:= 1 \times ((35 + (79 + 7)) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\1816 &:= 1 + ((35 + (79 + 7)) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\1817 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (((7 \times 97) + 5!) - 3! \times 1) \\1818 &:= (1^3 + 5) \times ((79 + (75 \times 3)) - 1) \\1819 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 579) + (75 + (3! + 1)) \\1820 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) + (((7 + (9 \times 7)) + 5) \times (3 + 1)! \\1821 &:= 1 + (3! + ((57 - (9 - 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\1822 &:= (((1 - 357) \times 9) + 7!) - ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\1823 &:= 1 \times ((3! + (5! \times 7)) + ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\1824 &:= (135 \times (7 + 9)) - ((7!/5)/(3 \times 1)) \\1825 &:= (13 - (57 \times 9)) + (75 \times 31) \\1826 &:= (13 \times 5!) + (797 - 531) \\1827 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5) - (7 + 9))^7 - (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \\1828 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5))) - (3 + 1)! \\1829 &:= ((13 - (5 - (7 \times 9))) - (7 + 5)) \times 31 \\1830 &:= (1 + (35 + (79 + 7))) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\1831 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + 79)) + (((7! + 5!)/3) + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1832 &:= (13 - 5) \times (7 + (97 + (5^3 \times 1))) \\ 1833 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) - 7) \times 9 + (753 \times 1) \\ 1834 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) - (7 \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 1835 &:= 1 \times ((3 + 5) - (7 \times (9 \times (7 - (5 + 31)))))) \\ 1836 &:= (135 \times (7 \times (9 - 7))) - (53 + 1) \\ 1837 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + (579 + 7)) + 531) \\ 1838 &:= 1357 + ((97 \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 1839 &:= ((135 - 7) - 9) + ((7! + 5!)/(3 \times 1)) \\ 1840 &:= ((1 + 35) + 79) \times ((7 - 5)^{3+1}) \\ 1841 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 579) + (7 \times (5 \times 3))) - 1) \\ 1842 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 579) + (7 \times (5 \times 3))) - 1) \\ 1843 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) - 97) \times (5! - (3! - 1))) \\ 1844 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 + 797) + 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 1845 &:= ((135 + 7) - 97) \times ((5!/3) + 1) \\ 1846 &:= (13 - 5!) + ((7 \times 9) \times (((7 \times 5) - 3) - 1)) \\ 1847 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5 - 79)) \times ((75/3) + 1)) \\ 1848 &:= (1 + ((3 + (5! - 7)) \times (9 + 7))) - ((5 + 3) + 1) \\ 1849 &:= (1 + 35 + 7)^{9-7} \times (5 - 3 - 1) \\ 1850 &:= (1 - ((35/7) - 9)) \times ((7 \times 53) - 1) \\ 1851 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) \times 7)) + (97 + (53 \times 1)) \\ 1852 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5! \times 7) + (975 + 31)) \\ 1853 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! + (9 - 75))/(3! \times 1)) \\ 1854 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5! \times (7 + (9 - 7)))) + (53 \times 1) \\ 1855 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((79 \times 75) - (3 + 1)) \\ 1856 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 579) - 7)) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 1857 &:= 135 - (7 - (9 + ((7! + 5!)/(3 \times 1)))) \\ 1858 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + (97 + (53 \times 1)) \\ 1859 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5 + ((79 - (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 1860 &:= ((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 9)) \times 7) + (5! - 31) \\ 1861 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (5 + ((7 + 9) \times (75 - (3 + 1)))))) \\ 1862 &:= (((1 - 3 + (5 \times 79)) - 7) - 5!) \times (3! + 1) \\ 1863 &:= ((135 + 797) \times (5 - 3)) - 1 \\ 1864 &:= 13 - (((5 - 79) \times (75/3)) - 1) \\ 1865 &:= ((135 + 797) \times (5 - 3)) + 1 \\ 1866 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 1867 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\ 1868 &:= (13 \times (57 + 9)) + ((7!/5) + 3 - 1) \\ 1869 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((5 + 7) - 97)) \times ((5!/3!) + 1) \\ 1870 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7 + (((9 \times 7) - 5) \times 31)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1871 &:= ((135 - 7) \times 9) + (((7 - 5) \times 3)! - 1) \\ 1872 &:= 13 \times ((5 + ((79 + 7) + 53)) \times 1) \\ 1873 &:= 1 \times ((3 + 5!) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1))) \\ 1874 &:= 1 + ((3 + 5!) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1))) \\ 1875 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (5 \times ((7 - 97) + (5 \times 3)))) \times 1 \\ 1876 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (5 \times ((7 - 97) + (5 \times 3)))) + 1 \\ 1877 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7) \times ((97 + 5!) + 3!)) \times 1) \\ 1878 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 - 79)) + (75 \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 1879 &:= (((1 \times 3!)/5!) \times (7!/(9 + 7))) - (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 1880 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5!)) + 7) + (97 + 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 1881 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times ((5 - 7) + (9 \times (7 \times 5)))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 1882 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) + 79) + (75 \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 1883 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 + 7) \times 97) - (5 - 3)) + 1) \\ 1884 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5) + (((7 + 9) \times 75) - 31) \\ 1885 &:= (1357 - 97) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 1886 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5 \times 7) - 975) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 1887 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - 5!) - 3! - 1) \\ 1888 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + 7)) \times (97 + ((5!/3!) + 1)) \\ 1889 &:= (135 \times 7) + (975 - 31) \\ 1890 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 7) + (9 \times 7))) + (5! + 3! \times 1) \\ 1891 &:= ((1 - 35) - ((7 - 97) - 5)) \times 31 \\ 1892 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((579 - (7 + 5!)) + 3! \times 1) \\ 1893 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5 \times 7)^{9-7})) - (53 \times 1) \\ 1894 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5 \times 7)^{9-7})) - (53 - 1) \\ 1895 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! + 7) \times 9)) + (753 - 1) \\ 1896 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) + (7 + 9)) \times (75 + 3 + 1) \\ 1897 &:= ((13 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + (7 \times 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\ 1898 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 7) + (9 + ((7!/5)/(3 \times 1))) \\ 1899 &:= (((1 - 3) - (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) - 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 1900 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((579 - ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) + 1) \\ 1901 &:= (((1 \times 3!)/5!) \times (7!/(9 + 7))) + (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 1902 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5!) - 7!) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1}) \\ 1903 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57)) + (9 - 7)) \times (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 1904 &:= ((135 - 7) \times 9) + (753 - 1) \\ 1905 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1))) \\ 1906 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 79))) + (((7 + 5) - 3!)! + 1) \\ 1907 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (5 - ((7 \times (9 - 75)) - (3! \times 1)))) \\ 1908 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 + (79 + 75)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 1909 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5) - 7) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1910 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + 79)) + (75 \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 1911 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - 5!) \times 3!))) - 1 \\ 1912 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - 5!) \times 3!))) \times 1 \\ 1913 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 \times 97)) - 5!) - (3 + 1) \\ 1914 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5 \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!) \times 3!))) - 1 \\ 1915 &:= (135 \times 7) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 1916 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5 \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!) \times 3!))) + 1 \\ 1917 &:= (135 \times 7) + ((975 - 3) \times 1) \\ 1918 &:= (1 \times (((35/7)! \times (9 + 7)) - 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 1919 &:= (((13 - 5!) \times (7 - 97))/5) - (3! + 1) \\ 1920 &:= (((1 \times 35)/7)!) \times ((9 + (7 - 5)) + (3! - 1)) \\ 1921 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 \times 97)) - 5!) + (3 + 1) \\ 1922 &:= ((13 + 5) + (79 - (7 \times 5))) \times 31 \\ 1923 &:= (13 - 5!) + (((7 \times 9) + 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 1924 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times ((5 \times 7) + (9 - 7))) \times (53 - 1) \\ 1925 &:= (135 \times 7) + (975 + (3! - 1)) \\ 1926 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 - (9 \times (7 - (5!/(3 + 1)))))) \\ 1927 &:= (135 \times 7) + (975 + (3! + 1)) \\ 1928 &:= ((13 - 57)^{9-7}) - ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 1929 &:= ((1 + ((3 \times 5) + 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\ 1930 &:= 1 - (357 - ((9 \times (7 + 5!)) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 1931 &:= (1^3) - ((5 \times 79) - (75 \times 31)) \\ 1932 &:= (((1^3 + (5 \times 79)) \times 7) - 5!) - 3! \times 1 \\ 1933 &:= (((13 - 5!) \times (7 - 97))/5) + (3! + 1) \\ 1934 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 + 79) \times (7 - (5 \times 3!))) + 1) \\ 1935 &:= (1 + (35 + 7)) \times (97 - (53 - 1)) \\ 1936 &:= ((135 \times 7) - (97 - 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 1937 &:= (1 \times 3)! - (((5 + 79) \times (7 - (5 \times 3!))) + 1) \\ 1938 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 79))) + (753 \times 1) \\ 1939 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7) \times (((97 - 5) \times 3) + 1) \\ 1940 &:= (1^3 \times 5) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (53 \times 1)) \\ 1941 &:= 1 \times 3 + (57 \times ((9 + (75/3)) \times 1)) \\ 1942 &:= ((135 \times 7) \times (9 - 7)) + (53 - 1) \\ 1943 &:= (135 + 79) + (((7 + 5)^3) + 1) \\ 1944 &:= ((13 - 57)^{9-7}) + ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 1945 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) - 79) + ((7!/5) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 1946 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 - 7) + (975 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 1947 &:= ((1 + (3! \times (5! + 79))) + 753) - 1 \\ 1948 &:= (1 + (3! \times (5! + 79))) + (753 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1949 &:= ((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) - 7531 \\ 1950 &:= (13 - (5 - 7)) \times ((9 + ((7 - (5 - 3)))!) + 1) \\ 1951 &:= (135 \times 7) + (975 + 31) \\ 1952 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)!)! - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) + 5!)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 1953 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times (7 + ((9 \times 75) - 31)) \\ 1954 &:= (13 + 5) + ((79 - (7 \times 5))^{3-1}) \\ 1955 &:= (1^3 \times ((5 \times 79) + (7 \times 5!))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 1956 &:= ((1 \times 3!)/5) \times ((7!/(9 + 7)) + (5 + (3! \times 1))) \\ 1957 &:= ((1 - ((3 - 579) - 75)) \times 3) + 1 \\ 1958 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) - (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 1959 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) - (7 \times (97 - (5! \times 3)))) \times 1 \\ 1960 &:= ((1 - (3! \times (57 \times 9))) + 7!) - (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 1961 &:= 13 + (((5 \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) - (3! + 1)) \\ 1962 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5 - ((7 + (975 + 3)) + 1)) \\ 1963 &:= ((1 + 35) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) - (53 \times 1) \\ 1964 &:= 135 - (((7 + 9) - 75) \times 31) \\ 1965 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 + 7) - ((5 - (3! - 1)))) \\ 1966 &:= ((1 - (3! \times (57 \times 9))) + 7!) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 1967 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1)) \\ 1968 &:= (1^{357} + (9^{7-5})) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 1969 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 57)^{9-7}) - 531 \\ 1970 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5 + ((7 - 97) \times (5 + (3! \times 1)))) \\ 1971 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (79 - 7)) + 531 \\ 1972 &:= (1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 - (5! \times (3 - 1))) \\ 1973 &:= (1^3 + (5! + (7! - (9 \times 7)))) - (5^{3!-1}) \\ 1974 &:= ((1^3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) - 5!) \times (3! + 1) \\ 1975 &:= (1 - 35) - (7 - (9 \times ((75 \times 3) - 1))) \\ 1976 &:= ((1 - 35) + (79 - 7)) \times (53 - 1) \\ 1977 &:= 1 + ((3 \times (5 + 7)) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 1978 &:= (((1 + 3!)/5) - 7) + (975 + 3 - 1) \\ 1979 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) - ((7 - 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 1980 &:= (1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - ((75 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 1981 &:= (1^3) - (((5 - 7) - 97) \times 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 1982 &:= ((1 + 3^5) - 7!) + ((9 \times 753) + 1) \\ 1983 &:= ((1 - 35) - 7) + ((9 \times (75 \times 3)) - 1) \\ 1984 &:= ((1357 + 9) - 7) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 1985 &:= (1357 + 97) + 531 \\ 1986 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 1987 &:= ((1 - (35 + 7)) \times (9 - 75)) - (3! - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1988 &:= ((135 + 7) \times (9 + (7 - (5 - 3)))) \times 1 \\1989 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 - ((7 - 9)^7))) \times 5) - 3! \times 1 \\1990 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) + ((79 \times (75/3)) - 1) \\1991 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - 7) - (9 \times (7 \times (5 - 31))) \\1992 &:= 13 - (((5! + ((7 - 97) \times 5)) \times 3!) + 1) \\1993 &:= 1 - ((3!! \times (5 - 7)) - ((97 - 5) \times 3! \times 1)) \\1994 &:= ((13 \times 5) + 7) + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) + 3 - 1) \\1995 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + 7975)) / (3 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1996 &:= (((1 + 3) - (57 \times 9)) + (7!/5)) \times (3 + 1) \\1997 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times 5!) + 797)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\1998 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7975) / (3 + 1)) \\1999 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + 7975) / (3 + 1)) \\2000 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) + 7) \times ((97 - 5!) + 31)\end{aligned}$$

2.2 Numbers From 2001 to 4000

$$\begin{aligned}2001 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 + 7975) / (3 + 1)) \\2002 &:= 1^{357} + (9 + 7) \times 5^3 + 1 \\2003 &:= ((1 - 3!)^5) + ((79 + (7! + 5)) + 3 + 1) \\2004 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 \times 7) + (9 - 7)) \times (53 + 1)) \\2005 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times (9 + 7)) - (5! / (3 + 1))) \\2006 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times 5) - (3! + 1) \\2007 &:= (135 \times 7) + ((9 - 7) \times 531) \\2008 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - (((7 - 97) + 5) \times (3 + 1)!) \\2009 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((79 \times (75/3)) - 1) \\2010 &:= ((1^3)^5!) - (7 - ((9 + 7) \times ((5^3) + 1))) \\2011 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) - 753) - 1 \\2012 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) - 753) \times 1 \\2013 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) - 753) + 1 \\2014 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) + (79 \times ((7 + 5) \times (3 - 1))) \\2015 &:= 1 + (((35 - 7) - 9) \times (75 + 31)) \\2016 &:= ((1 + (3 - (5 - 7))) \times (9 + 75)) \times (3 + 1) \\2017 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7! + 975)) / (3 \times 1) \\2018 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5) \times 7)) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\2019 &:= ((1 - 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\2020 &:= (135 + (79 \times 75)) / (3 \times 1) \\2021 &:= (1^3 + (5 \times ((79 \times 7) - 5))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\2022 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - 57) + 9))^{7-5}) - (3 \times 1) \\2023 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - 57) + 9))^{7-5}) - (3 - 1) \\2024 &:= (1^3 \times 5) - (7 - (((9 \times 75) \times 3) + 1)) \\2025 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7 + 9) \times (7 - 5)))^{3-1} \\2026 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) + 7) \times ((9 \times 75) / (3! - 1))) \\2027 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - 57) + 9))^{7-5}) + (3 - 1) \\2028 &:= (1 \times 3 + (579 - 75)) \times (3 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2029 &:= ((135 - 7) \times (9 + 7)) + (5 - (3 + 1)!) \\2030 &:= ((1^3 + 57) \times (9 - (7 - 5))) \times (3! - 1) \\2031 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5)^7) - (((9 - 7) - 5) \times 3!!) - 1 \\2032 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 + 7))) \times ((9 - 7) + (5^3 \times 1)) \\2033 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5)^7) - (((9 - 7) - 5) \times 3!!) + 1 \\2034 &:= (1^{357}) \times (9 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)) \\2035 &:= (1^{357}) + (9 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)) \\2036 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 + (7 + (9 \times (75 \times 3)))) + 1) \\2037 &:= ((1 - ((3 \times (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) - 5!)) - 3) - 1 \\2038 &:= ((1 - ((3 \times (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) - 5!)) - 3) \times 1 \\2039 &:= ((1 - ((3 \times (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) - 5!)) - 3) + 1 \\2040 &:= (1 \times (35 + (7 + 9))) \times (7! / ((5^3) + 1)) \\2041 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5)) \times 7) + ((9 - 7)^{5+3! \times 1}) \\2042 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) + ((7 + (9 \times (75 \times 3))) - 1) \\2043 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7! / (9 - 7))) + (5! - 3! \times 1) \\2044 &:= (1 + (((3! \times 5) + 79) \times 75)) / (3 + 1) \\2045 &:= ((135 + (79 + (7 + 5!))) \times 3!) - 1 \\2046 &:= ((135 + (79 + (7 + 5!))) \times 3!) \times 1 \\2047 &:= ((135 + (79 + (7 + 5!))) \times 3!) + 1 \\2048 &:= (135 - 7) \times (((9 - 7)^5) / (3 - 1)) \\2049 &:= (((1 + (3^5 + 7)) \times 9) - ((7 \times 5) \times 3!)) \times 1 \\2050 &:= (((1 + 3)! - (5 - 7)) + (9 \times (75 \times 3))) - 1 \\2051 &:= (((1 + 3)! - (5 - 7)) + (9 \times (75 \times 3))) \times 1 \\2052 &:= (((1 + 3)! - (5 - 7)) + (9 \times (75 \times 3))) + 1 \\2053 &:= 1 - (((((3^5) - 7!) + 9) / 7) \times (5 - (3 - 1))) \\2054 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5! + ((7 - (9 + (7 \times 5))) \times 31)) \\2055 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times 7) + ((9 - 7)^{5+3! \times 1})\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2056 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 \times (7 + 97)) - ((5 - 3) + 1)!) \\ 2057 &:= (1^3 + 5!) \times (79 - ((7 - 5) \times 31)) \\ 2058 &:= (1 \times 35) + (7 + (9 \times ((75 \times 3) - 1))) \\ 2059 &:= ((1 + 35) - 7) \times (9 + ((7 - 5) \times 31)) \\ 2060 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5!)) - (7 + (9 + 7))) \times (5!/3! \times 1) \\ 2061 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! + (((5 \times 7)^{9-7} + 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\ 2062 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7! + 5!)/(3 \times 1)) \\ 2063 &:= 1 - ((3 \times ((5 - 7) - (9 \times 75))) - 31) \\ 2064 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + (57 - 97)) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 2065 &:= (1 - ((3 \times (5 \times 7) - 9)) + (7! - (5! \times (3 + 1)!))) \\ 2066 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) \times 9) + ((7!/5!)/(3 \times 1)) \\ 2067 &:= (((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5))/3 - 1 \\ 2068 &:= (((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5))/3 \times 1 \\ 2069 &:= (((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5))/3 + 1 \\ 2070 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) + (79 \times ((75/3) + 1)) \\ 2071 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) + ((97 \times (5!/3!)) \times 1) \\ 2072 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) + ((97 \times (5!/3!)) + 1) \\ 2073 &:= ((1 + (3 + 57)) \times (9 + (75/3))) - 1 \\ 2074 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!))/(3 + 1) \\ 2075 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + 5)/(3 + 1) \\ 2076 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5)) + 7) \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) + 31) \\ 2077 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((579 - (7 + 5!)) \times 3) \times 1) \\ 2078 &:= (((1 - 35) \times 7) - 9) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2079 &:= ((13 \times 5) + (7 - 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 2080 &:= ((1 \times ((35/7) \times 9)) + 7) \times (5!/(3 \times 1)) \\ 2081 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7!) - (975 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2082 &:= ((1 - (35 - 7)) \times 9) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2083 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((7 - 9)^{7+5})/(3 - 1)) \\ 2084 &:= (((1^3 + 5!) \times (7 + 9)) - 7) + (5 \times 31) \\ 2085 &:= (1 - 3!) + (5 \times ((79 - ((7 - 5!) \times 3)) \times 1)) \\ 2086 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + (7! + 975))/(3 \times 1) \\ 2087 &:= (((1 + 357) - ((9 - 7) \times 5)) \times 3!) - 1 \\ 2088 &:= ((1 + ((3 \times 57) \times (9 - 7))) + 5) \times (3! \times 1) \\ 2089 &:= (((1 + 357) - ((9 - 7) \times 5)) \times 3!) + 1 \\ 2090 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 - 5!) - 3)) + 1 \\ 2091 &:= (1^{3!}) + (5 \times ((79 - ((7 - 5!) \times 3)) \times 1)) \\ 2092 &:= (1 + 3^5) + (7 \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 2093 &:= (13 \times (5 + (7 + 9 + (7 - 5)))) \times (3! + 1) \\ 2094 &:= (((13 + (5 - 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5) \times (3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2095 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (((7 + 97) \times 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 2096 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5 - (3! - 1))) \\ 2097 &:= 1 + ((3 - (5 - (7 - 9))) \times (7 - 531)) \\ 2098 &:= (1 - (3 \times 57)) + (9 \times (7 \times (5 + 31))) \\ 2099 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5)^7) - ((9 + 75) + 3 + 1) \\ 2100 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times ((7 + 97) + (5 + 31)) \\ 2101 &:= 1357 - (9 - (753 \times 1)) \\ 2102 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)^7) - (9^{7-5})) - (3 + 1) \\ 2103 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) + (79 + ((7!/5) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 2104 &:= (13 - 5) \times (((7 + 9)^{7-5}) + (3! + 1)) \\ 2105 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + (79 \times 7)) - (5 + 3 \times 1) \\ 2106 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 57) \times ((9 + 7) + (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 2107 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (79 - 7)) - (5^3 \times 1) \\ 2108 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 579)) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1) \\ 2109 &:= (1 + (3 \times 579)) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1) \\ 2110 &:= 135 + ((79 \times 75)/(3 \times 1)) \\ 2111 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) - (7 - (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\ 2112 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) + 7) \times (9 + (7 + (5! - (3 + 1)))) \\ 2113 &:= (1^3 + (5! - 7)) + (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) - 1) \\ 2114 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) - 3!))) - 1 \\ 2115 &:= 1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) - 3!) \times 1)) \\ 2116 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 - 7)) \times (9 - (7 + 531)) \\ 2117 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 + 7)) + ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\ 2118 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((579 + 7) - 5!) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 2119 &:= (1357 + 9) + (753 \times 1) \\ 2120 &:= 1357 + ((9 + 753) + 1) \\ 2121 &:= 1 - (((3! \times 5) - ((7 \times 9) + 7)) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 2122 &:= 1 - ((3 \times (5 + (7 \times 9))) - (75 \times 31)) \\ 2123 &:= (1 + 3) - (((57 - 97) \times 53) + 1) \\ 2124 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5) - 7)/(9 - 7)) \times 531 \\ 2125 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5) - 7)/(9 - 7)) \times 531 \\ 2126 &:= (((13 \times 5) \times 7) - 9) + (7!/(5 - (3 - 1))) \\ 2127 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 \times ((7 + 9) \times 7))) - (5! - (3! + 1)) \\ 2128 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5 + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times 531) \\ 2129 &:= (((1^{3!}) + 5)! \times 7) - ((97 \times 5) \times 3!) - 1 \\ 2130 &:= (((1 - (3 - 57)) + 9) + 7) \times (5!/(3 + 1)) \\ 2131 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97 - (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 2132 &:= (((1 \times (35/7)) \times 9) + 7) \times ((5!/3) + 1) \\ 2133 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! + (5 - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5 + 3!)) \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 2134** := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times 7 + (9 + (7! - (5! \times 31)))$
2135 := $(1^3) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 + 7!)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!))$
2136 := $((1 + 3)! \times (((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times 7) - 5!)) / (3 + 1)$
2137 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97) + (5 - (3 - 1))$
2138 := $(13 + (5! - ((7 - (9 \times 75)) \times 3))) + 1$
2139 := $(1 \times 3! + 5) - (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 - (3 + 1)!))$
2140 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5) + ((7 + 97) \times 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
2141 := $((((1 - 3) - (5 \times 79)) \times 7) - 5!) + ((3! + 1)!)$
2142 := $(1 - 35) \times (((7 - 9) - 7) \times ((5 + 3) - 1))$
2143 := $135 - ((7 - 9) \times ((7!/5) - (3 + 1)))$
2144 := $((13 \times 5) \times 7) + (9 + (7! / (5 - (3 - 1))))$
2145 := $13 \times ((5! - (7 + 9)) + (7 + (53 + 1)))$
2146 := $(13 \times (5! + (7 + 9))) + (7 \times (53 + 1))$
2147 := $((1 + 35) + ((7 + 9) \times (7 + (5^3)))) - 1$
2148 := $((1 + 35) + ((7 + 9) \times (7 + (5^3)))) \times 1$
2149 := $((1 + 35) + ((7 + 9) \times (7 + (5^3)))) + 1$
2150 := $((((1 \times 3!))! + 5) \times 7) - (975 \times (3 \times 1))$
2151 := $(1 - (3^5)) + (((7 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3)) - 1)$
2152 := $(1 \times 3 + 5) \times (((((7 + 9) - 7) \times 5) \times 3!) - 1)$
2153 := $135 - (7 - (9 \times ((75 \times 3) \times 1)))$
2154 := $((((1 - 3 + 5))!)! + (7! / 9)) + ((7 \times (5^3)) - 1)$
2155 := $((((1 - 3 + 5))!)! + (7! / 9)) + ((7 \times (5^3)) \times 1)$
2156 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) - 7) \times ((97 + 5) - 3) - 1$
2157 := $1 - (((3 - 57) - (97 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1))$
2158 := $1 - (3 - (5! \times (79 - 7 - (53 + 1))))$
2159 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! \times ((7 - 9) - 7))) + (5 - 3! \times 1)$
2160 := $((1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times 9) / 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1)$
2161 := $(1^{3!}) + (5! \times (79 - 7 - (53 + 1)))$
2162 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5! \times ((7 - 9) - 7)) + 5) - 3! \times 1)$
2163 := $((1^3 - 57) + 9) \times (7 - 53) + 1$
2164 := $(1^3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!)) - (3! + 1)$
2165 := $(13 + ((5! + 7) + ((9 \times 75) \times 3))) \times 1$
2166 := $((1 - 3) \times 57) \times ((9 - 7) - ((5! / 3!) + 1))$
2167 := $(13 + ((5! - 79) \times (7 \times 5))) + (3! - 1)$
2168 := $((13 - 5) \times ((7 + 9)^{7-5})) + ((3! - 1)!)$
2169 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 79) - (7 - 531))$
2170 := $(((((1 \times 3)^5) - 7) \times 9) - 7) + 53) \times 1$
2171 := $(((((1 \times 3)^5) - 7) \times 9) - 7) + 53) + 1$
2172 := $(13 \times (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7! + 5!)) / (3 \times 1))$
2173 := $((13 + 5) \times (79 + 7)) + (5^{3+1})$
2174 := $13 + (((5 + 7) - 9)^7) + (5 - 31)$
2175 := $((1 + 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times (9 + 7))) + (5! \times (3 \times 1))$
2176 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 7) - ((9 \times 7) - 531)$
2177 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 - 31))$
2178 := $(13 \times (57 + 9)) + (7! - (5! \times 31))$
2179 := $((1 \times 3)^5) \times ((7 + 9) - 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1)$
2180 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 - 7) + ((9 + 7) + 531))$
2181 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 7)) + (((97 \times 5) - 3!) + 1)$
2182 := $1 \times 3! + (((((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5) - (3 + 1)!)$
2183 := $(1357 \times (9 - 7)) - 531$
2184 := $((((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7) - 9) \times (7 \times (5 - 31))$
2185 := $((13 \times (579 - 75)) / 3) + 1$
2186 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - ((7 \times 97) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1))$
2187 := $((1 + (35 + 7)) \times 9) + (75 \times (3 + 1)!)$
2188 := $(1 - 3!!) - (5 + (7 \times ((9 + (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))))$
2189 := $(1 - 3) + (((((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5) \times 3!) + 1)$
2190 := $(1 \times (3 \times ((57 + 9) + 7))) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1)$
2191 := $1 + ((3 \times ((57 + 9) + 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1))$
2192 := $(1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times 7)) + (5 - (3 + 1)!)$
2193 := $((1 + 3) + (((((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5) \times 3!)) - 1)$
2194 := $((1 + 3) + (((((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5) \times 3!)) \times 1)$
2195 := $((1 + 3) + (((((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5) \times 3!)) + 1)$
2196 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 + 79) / 7) + (((5 - (3 - 1))!)!))$
2197 := $(1 + (3!! - ((5! \times 7) + 9))) + (75 \times 31)$
2198 := $13 - (((5 - 7)^9) + 75) \times (3! - 1)$
2199 := $(1 \times 3! + (5 + 7!)) - ((97 - 5) \times 31)$
2200 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7) \times (97 + (5 - (3 - 1)))$
2201 := $((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) + (5 - (3 - 1))$
2202 := $((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) + ((5 - 3) + 1)$
2203 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7))) + (5 - 31)$
2204 := $(13 \times 5!) + ((7 \times 97) - (5 \times (3! + 1)))$
2205 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 7))) \times ((9 + 75) / (3 + 1))$
2206 := $((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 - 5)) - (3 - 1)$
2207 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + 7) - (5! / (3 + 1)!)$
2208 := $((13 \times (5 + 79)) + (7 + 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
2209 := $((1 - 3!) \times (5 - (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
2210 := $13 - ((5 - ((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5))) + 3 \times 1)$
2211 := $(13 - 5) + ((7 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - (3 - 1))$

- 2212** := $(1 + ((35 \times (7 \times 9))/7)) \times (5 + 3 - 1)$
2213 := $(13^{5+7-9}) + ((7 + (5 + 3)) + 1)$
2214 := $13 + ((5 \times ((7!/(9 + 7)) + (5^3))) + 1)$
2215 := $((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + 7) + 5 - (3 - 1)$
2216 := $(13 \times ((5 + 7) \times 9)) + (7 \times ((5! - 3) - 1))$
2217 := $((1 + ((3^5) \times 7)) - 9) - (7 - 531)$
2218 := $((13 + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times 7)) + (5 - 3!)) + 1$
2219 := $((1 - (3 + 5)) \times 7) + (9 \times ((7!/5)/(3 + 1)))$
2220 := $1 \times (3 \times 5 \times ((7 \times 97) - 531))$
2221 := $1 + (3 \times 5 \times ((7 \times 97) - 531))$
2222 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 - 797))) - (5 \times 31)$
2223 := $(1^3 - ((5! \times 7) + (9 \times 7))) + (5^{3!-1})$
2224 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) + (7 \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1))$
2225 := $((((1 + 3) - (5 + 7)) + 97) \times 5) \times (3! - 1)$
2226 := $(13 + (((5 + 7) - 9)^7)) - (5 - 31)$
2227 := $((1 \times 3)! - (5! - 7)) + (9 + (75 \times 31))$
2228 := $1 \times 3 + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) \times 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
2229 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7))) - (5 - 31)$
2230 := $(1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times 7)) - (5 - (3 + 1)!)$
2231 := $(13 \times 5!) + (797 - ((5^3) + 1))$
2232 := $(13 - (5 - (7 - 9))) \times ((7 + 5) \times 31)$
2233 := $(1 - 35) + (((7 \times 9) \times (7 + 5)) \times 3) - 1$
2234 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times 9) - (7 - (5 + 31))$
2235 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) + (7 + (9 + 7))) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
2236 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5! - (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
2237 := $((1 + 3^5) - 7) \times 9 + ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) - 1)$
2238 := $((1 + (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
2239 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 - 79))) + ((7!/5) \times (3 - 1))$
2240 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((79 + 7) - (5 - 31))$
2241 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) + ((79 + 7!) - (5! \times (3 + 1)!))$
2242 := $(1357 + 9) + ((7 \times (5^3)) + 1)$
2243 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! - 79)) + (75 \times 31)$
2244 := $1 \times (3 \times (5 + ((797 - 53) - 1)))$
2245 := $(1 + 3) - (5 + (79 - (75 \times 31)))$
2246 := $1 + (((3 + 5) \times (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 5)) + (3! - 1))$
2247 := $(1^{35}) - (79 - (75 \times 31))$
2248 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7 + (5 + 31))$
2249 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5!/3! \times 1))$
2250 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times ((79 + 75) - (3 + 1))$
2251 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 - 7) \times 9) + (7!/5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
2252 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) \times (((7 - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) - 1)$
2253 := $(1 \times 3) - (5 \times ((7 - 9) \times (75 \times (3 \times 1))))$
2254 := $((1 + 3) \times 579) - ((7 - 5) \times 31)$
2255 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7))) - (5 - 31)$
2256 := $(1 \times ((3 \times (5 - 7)) + 9)) \times (753 - 1)$
2257 := $(13 \times ((5 + 7) + 97)) + (5! \times (3! + 1))$
2258 := $(13 - 5) - ((7 - 97) \times (5^{3-1}))$
2259 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 + 79))) \times (7 - ((5 \times 3) + 1))$
2260 := $((1 - (35 \times 79)) + 7!) - ((5 \times 3) + 1)$
2261 := $((1 - (35 \times 79)) + 7!) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
2262 := $(13 - (5 \times ((7 - 9) \times (75 \times 3)))) - 1$
2263 := $13 - ((5 \times ((7 - 9) \times (75 \times 3))) \times 1)$
2264 := $(13 - (5 \times ((7 - 9) \times (75 \times 3)))) + 1$
2265 := $((1^{3!}) + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) - 7)) \times 5 + ((3! \times 1)!)$
2266 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - (79 - (75 \times 31))$
2267 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 797) - (5! + 3 + 1)$
2268 := $((1^{35}) \times 7) \times ((975/3) - 1)$
2269 := $((13 \times (5! + 7)) - 97) - 5 + (3! \times 1)$
2270 := $(1 \times ((35 - 7) \times (9^{7-5}))) + (3 - 1)$
2271 := $((1 - 3) - 5) \times (7 \times 9) - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1)!)$
2272 := $13 - (57 + 9 - (75 \times 31))$
2273 := $(1 - (3^5)) - (7 + (97 \times (5 - 31)))$
2274 := $1 \times (3^5 + ((7 + (9 \times (75 \times 3))) - 1))$
2275 := $((1^{3!})^5) \times ((7 \times 975)/(3 \times 1))$
2276 := $((1^{3!})^5) + ((7 \times 975)/(3 \times 1))$
2277 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7 \times (9 \times (7 + 5)))) \times 3) \times 1$
2278 := $(1 + (3 \times (5! + (7 \times 97)))) - (5 \times (3 + 1)!)$
2279 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) - (((7 - (9 + 7)) \times 5!) - (3! - 1))$
2280 := $1 \times (((3 - 57) + 9) + (75 \times 31))$
2281 := $1 + (((3 - 57) + 9) + (75 \times 31))$
2282 := $(1 - 3) - ((5! - 79) - (75 \times 31))$
2283 := $(((((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - 9) \times 7) - 5!) - 3!) + 1$
2284 := $13 - ((5 - (7 \times (975/3))) - 1)$
2285 := $1 + 3 - 5! + 7^{9+7-5-3!-1}$
2286 := $((1 \times 3!) \times ((5 - 7) - 97)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)$
2287 := $((1 + 3) \times 579) + ((7 - 5) - 31)$
2288 := $((1 + (357 - 9)) \times 7) - (5 \times 31)$
2289 := $(1 - (35 - 7)) - (9 - (75 \times 31))$

- 2290** := (13 - (57 - 9)) + (75 × 31)
2291 := ((1 + ((3! × 5) × 79)) - 75) - (3! - 1)
2292 := (1357 - 975) × (3! × 1)
2293 := (1 + (((3! × 5) × 79) - 75)) - (3 × 1)
2294 := (((1 + (3 + 5)) × 7) × 9) + (((7 + 5)³) - 1)
2295 := (((1 + 3!) + (5 × 7))⁹⁻⁷) + 531
2296 := (1 - 3) + ((5! × (7 + 9)) + (7 × (53 + 1)))
2297 := (((1 × 3) - 5)⁷) + (97 × (5³⁻¹))
2298 := (1 + ((3! × 5) × 79)) - (75 - (3 - 1))
2299 := 1 - (3 × (((57 + 9) + 7) - (5! + 3!!)) + 1))
2300 := 1 + (((3! × 5) × 79) - 75) + 3 + 1)
2301 := ((1 + ((3! × 5) × 79)) - 75) + (3! - 1)
2302 := 1 + (3 × ((57 × 9) + ((7 + 5!) × (3 - 1))))
2303 := (1 × 35) + (7 × ((975/3) - 1))
2304 := ((1 × 3) × ((5 - ((7 - 9)⁷)) - 5)) × 3! × 1
2305 := 1 - ((3 - (5 × 7)) × (9 × (7 + (5 - (3 + 1))))))
2306 := (((1 + 3) × 579) - 7) - ((5 - 3) + 1)
2307 := (1 - (35 - 7)) + (9 + (75 × 31))
2308 := ((1 + 3) × 579) - (((7 + 5) - 3) - 1)
2309 := (1 × 35) + ((7 × (975/3)) - 1)
2310 := ((1 × 35) + (7 × (975/3))) × 1
2311 := 1 + 35 + (7 × (975/(3 × 1)))
2312 := (((1 + 3) × 579) - 7) + (5 - 3) + 1
2313 := (1 + (3 × (5 × (79 + 75)))) + (3 - 1)
2314 := (1 + 3) + ((5 × ((79 + 75) × 3)) × 1)
2315 := (((1 - 3) - 5!) × (((7 - 9) × 7) - 5)) - (3 × 1)
2316 := (1 + 3!) + (((5 × (79 + 75)) × 3) - 1)
2317 := (((135 + 7) - 9) × (7 + 5)) + (3!! + 1)
2318 := (1 - 3) + (((5 × (7 × 9)) × 7) + (5! - (3! - 1)))
2319 := (((1 + 357) - 9) × 7) - (5³) + 1
2320 := ((1^{3!}) - ((5 + (7 - 9))!)) + (75 × 31)
2321 := (((1 - 3) - 5!) × (((7 - 9) × 7) - 5)) + (3 × 1)
2322 := 1 × 3! + (579 × ((7 + 5)/(3 × 1)))
2323 := (1 - (3!! × 5)) + (((79 × 75) - 3) × 1)
2324 := ((1 + 3) × 579) + (((7 + 5) - 3) - 1)
2325 := (((1 × 3) - 5) - 7) + (9 + 75) × 31
2326 := ((1357 + 975) - 3!) × 1
2327 := 1357 + (97 × (5 × (3 - 1)))
2328 := (1³ + 5) × ((7 × (9 × 7)) - (53 × 1))
2329 := (((1 + 3!) - 5) - (7 - 9)) + (75 × 31)
2330 := ((1 + 3) - (5! + (7 × 97))) + (5^{3!-1})
2331 := ((1 - 3) - (5 × 7)) × ((9 - 75) + 3 × 1)
2332 := (1 - 3!) + ((5 - ((7 - 9) × 7)) × ((5! + 3) × 1))
2333 := (13 × (5! + (7 × 9))) + ((7 - 53) × 1)
2334 := (1³ + 5) × (((7 × (9 × 7)) - 53) + 1)
2335 := 1 - (3! + ((5 × (7 - (9 + 7))) × (53 - 1)))
2336 := 1357 + (975 + 3 + 1)
2337 := 1 × ((3 - ((5! - 7!)/(9 - 7))) - (5! + 3! × 1))
2338 := (1357 + 975) + (3! × 1)
2339 := 1357 + ((975 + 3!) + 1)
2340 := (1 × 3) - (57 × ((9 - (7⁵⁻³)) - 1))
2341 := 1 - ((3 × (5 - 797)) + (5 + 31))
2342 := (1 + (3! × (5 × 79))) + ((7 - 5) - 31)
2343 := ((13 - 5) + (7 × 9)) × (7 - 5 + 31)
2344 := (1 + (3! × (5 + (7 - 9)))) + (75 × 31)
2345 := ((1 + 3) × 579) - ((7 - 5) - 31)
2346 := ((1 - (3 - 5)) × (797 - (5 × 3))) × 1
2347 := (1 + (3 × (5 + 797))) - (5!/(3 - 1))
2348 := ((13 × 5!) + 797) - (5 + 3 + 1)
2349 := (((1 + 3) × 579) + (7 - 5)) + 31
2350 := ((1 × ((3 × 5) + 79)) × (75/3)) × 1
2351 := ((13 - 5!) + (7 - 9)) + ((7! - 5!)/(3 - 1))
2352 := 1 × (3! × ((5 + (7 × (9 × 7))) - (53 + 1)))
2353 := ((1 × 3) × (5 + 797)) - (53 × 1)
2354 := (((1 × 3) × 5) + 7) × (97 + (5 × (3 - 1)))
2355 := (1 × (3 × 5)) × (79 + ((75 + 3) × 1))
2356 := 1 × 3 + (((57 - 9) × (7⁵⁻³)) + 1)
2357 := ((1 + (3! × 5)) × (79 - 7)) + (5³ × 1)
2358 := ((1 × 3) × ((5! × 7) - (9 × ((7 - 5) × 3)))) × 1
2359 := 1 × 3! + (((57 - 9) × (7⁵⁻³)) + 1)
2360 := (((1 + 3) × 579) + 75) - 31
2361 := 1 - ((35/7) × (((9 - 7) - 5!) × (3 + 1)))
2362 := ((1 - 3) × 5) - (((7 × 9) × (7 - 5!))/3) + 1)
2363 := 1357 + (975 + 31)
2364 := 135 + (((7 × 9) × (7 × 5)) + (3 + 1)!)
2365 := (((1 × 3!) + 5!) + (7 × (97 + 5!))) + (3!! × 1)
2366 := ((13 × 5!) + 797) + (5 + 3 + 1)
2367 := 1 × 3 + ((579 + (7 + 5)) × (3 + 1))

$$\begin{aligned} 2368 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - 7!) - ((97 - 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 2369 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (79 - 7)) - (5! + 31) \\ 2370 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + 97) \times (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 2371 &:= 135 - ((79 + 7) \times (5 - 31)) \\ 2372 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2373 &:= 1 \times (3 + ((5 \times 79) \times (((7 + 5) - 3!) \times 1))) \\ 2374 &:= 1 + (3 + ((5 \times 79) \times (((7 + 5) - 3!) \times 1))) \\ 2375 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((57 + 9) \times (7 + 5)))) - (3 - 1) \\ 2376 &:= (1 \times (35 + (7 + (9 - 7)))) \times (53 + 1) \\ 2377 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))))/5) + (3!! + 1) \\ 2378 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 579) + ((7 - 5) \times 31) \\ 2379 &:= 13 \times ((5 + 7) - (9 \times ((7 + 5) - 31))) \\ 2380 &:= (1 \times (35 - 7)) \times ((9^{7-5}) + 3 + 1) \\ 2381 &:= ((1 \times ((3!!/5) + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - (5 \times (3! + 1)) \\ 2382 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) - 9) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\ 2383 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 797) - ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 2384 &:= (((1 - ((3^5) - 7)) - 9) + (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 2385 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (((5 + 797) - 5) - (3 - 1))) \\ 2386 &:= (13 + 57) - (9 - (75 \times 31)) \\ 2387 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 797) + (5 \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 2388 &:= (1 + (3 - (5 - 797))) \times (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 2389 &:= (1 - 3) + ((57 + 9) + (75 \times 31)) \\ 2390 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 \times (7 - (97 \times 5)))) - (3 + 1) \\ 2391 &:= (1^3) - ((5 - ((7 + 9) \times 75)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 2392 &:= 1 - (3 + (57 \times ((9 - 75) + (3 + 1)!))) \\ 2393 &:= (13 + (5 + ((797 - 5) \times 3))) - 1 \\ 2394 &:= (13 + (5 + ((797 - 5) \times 3))) \times 1 \\ 2395 &:= (13 + (5 + ((797 - 5) \times 3))) + 1 \\ 2396 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 797) + (5!/3)) - 1 \\ 2397 &:= (135 - (7 \times 9)) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2398 &:= 1 \times ((3! + 5) \times ((7 + (97 + 5!)) - (3! \times 1))) \\ 2399 &:= 1 + ((3! + 5) \times ((7 + (97 + 5!)) - (3! \times 1))) \\ 2400 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((79 + 75) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 2401 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7)/9) \times 7^{5-3 \times 1} \\ 2402 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + (9 - 7))) - 5!) - (3 + 1) \\ 2403 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - 79) - (75 \times 31)) \\ 2404 &:= (13 + 57 + 9) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2405 &:= (1^{35}) + (79 + (75 \times 31)) \\ 2406 &:= (((((1^{3!}) \times 5) + 7!) - ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) - 3!!) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2407 &:= (1 - 3 + ((57^{9-7}) - 5!)) - (3!! \times 1) \\ 2408 &:= (((1 + 3)! - 5!) - (7 + 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2409 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5!) - (79 - (7!/5!))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 2410 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + (9 - 7))) - 5!) + (3 + 1) \\ 2411 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7! + 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\ 2412 &:= 13 - ((5 - 79) - (75 \times 31)) \\ 2413 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) + (79 + (75 \times 31)) \\ 2414 &:= (13 - 5) + ((797 + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2415 &:= (13 + 5!) + (7 \times ((975/3) + 1)) \\ 2416 &:= 1 - (((3! \times (5 \times 7)) \times (97 - 5!))/(3 - 1)) \\ 2417 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) \times 7)) - ((9 - 7) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 2418 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7 + 9)) \times ((75 + 3) \times 1) \\ 2419 &:= 1 + (3! - ((57 - 9) - ((7! - 5!)/(3 - 1)))) \\ 2420 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 + (797 + 5))) \times 3) - 1 \\ 2421 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 7)) - (9 - (75 \times 31)) \\ 2422 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 + (797 + 5))) \times 3) + 1 \\ 2423 &:= ((1^3 + (5 + (797 + 5))) \times 3) - 1 \\ 2424 &:= (1^3 + (5 + (797 + 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 2425 &:= ((1^3 + (5 + (797 + 5))) \times 3) + 1 \\ 2426 &:= (13 \times 5!) - (7 + (9 - (7 \times ((5^3) + 1)))) \\ 2427 &:= (1 - (35 \times 79)) + (7! + (5! + 31)) \\ 2428 &:= (1 + 3) - (((((5 - 7)^9) + 7)/5) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 2429 &:= (1 \times ((357 - 9) \times 7)) - (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 2430 &:= ((13 - 5) + (797 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 2431 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 - 31) \\ 2432 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) \times (((7 - 9)^7) + 53) - 1 \\ 2433 &:= ((1 \times (357 - 9)) \times 7) - (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 2434 &:= (1 + (3! \times ((5 \times 79) + 7))) + ((5!/3!) + 1) \\ 2435 &:= (1 + 3)! + (5 + ((797 + 5) \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 2436 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7)! - ((9 + 75) \times 31)) \\ 2437 &:= 13 + ((57 + (9 + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 2438 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 2439 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5! - 79)) + ((7 \times (5! \times 3)) + 1) \\ 2440 &:= (((1 \times 3 + (57 + 9)) \times 7) + 5) \times (3! - 1) \\ 2441 &:= (13 \times 5) + (((797 - 5) \times 3) \times 1) \\ 2442 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) - (7 - 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) + 31) \\ 2443 &:= (1 \times ((357 - 9) \times 7)) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 2444 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) \times 79)) + (75 - (3 - 1)) \\ 2445 &:= ((1 + ((3 + 579) \times 7))/5) \times (3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2446 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 + 7) \times (97 + 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 2447 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5))/7) + ((97 + 5) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 2448 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 - 9)) \times ((7^{5-3}) - 1) \\ 2449 &:= (1 + 3!!) - (((5 + 7) - (9 + 75)) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 2450 &:= (13 + ((5 - 7) - 9)) \times ((7 \times 5)^{3-1}) \\ 2451 &:= (1357 + 9) + (7 \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 2452 &:= 1 \times (((35 \times (7 \times 9)) + 7) + (5! \times (3 - 1))) \\ 2453 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((7 \times 9) + (75 \times 31)) \\ 2454 &:= 1 + (3 + ((5 \times 7) \times (((9 + 7) + 53) + 1))) \\ 2455 &:= (1 + 357) - (9 \times (7 - (5! \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 2456 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) - (79 - ((7 \times (5! \times 3)) - 1)) \\ 2457 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2458 &:= 135 + (7 - (9 - (75 \times 31))) \\ 2459 &:= ((1 \times 357) \times 9) - (753 + 1) \\ 2460 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5!) - (((7 - 97) \times 5) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 2461 &:= (((1 \times ((3 + 5) \times 7)) \times 9) - 7) \times 5 - (3 + 1)! \\ 2462 &:= (135 - 7) + (9 + (75 \times 31)) \\ 2463 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 797) + 5!)/(3! - 1)) \\ 2464 &:= ((1^{35} + 7) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) - (3! + 1))) \\ 2465 &:= 1 + ((3! + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times ((7 \times (5 - 3)) \times 1))) \\ 2466 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 - 7) \times 9)) + (7 \times (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 2467 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + 797))) + (5!/(3 - 1)) \\ 2468 &:= ((1 + 357) \times 9) - (753 + 1) \\ 2469 &:= (1 + (35 \times (79 - 7))) - (53 - 1) \\ 2470 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + 53)) \times 1 \\ 2471 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((797 + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2472 &:= (1 - 35) - (7 \times ((9 - 7) - (5! \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 2473 &:= ((1 \times (357 + 9)) \times 7) - (5! - 31) \\ 2474 &:= ((13 + (5! + 7)) + 9) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2475 &:= (13 + (5 + 7)) \times (9 \times (((7 - 5) \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 2476 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 - (7 + 9)) + (7!/(5 + 3 \times 1))) \\ 2477 &:= 1 - (35 - ((79 + (7 - 5)) \times 31)) \\ 2478 &:= ((13 \times 579) - 7!) - ((5 + 3) + 1) \\ 2479 &:= ((1^{3!} - ((5! - 79) - (7 \times (5! \times 3)))) - 1) \\ 2480 &:= ((1^{3!} - ((5! - 79) - (7 \times (5! \times 3)))) \times 1) \\ 2481 &:= ((1^{3!} - ((5! - 79) - (7 \times (5! \times 3)))) + 1) \\ 2482 &:= (13 + (5 + 7 + 9)) \times (75 - (3 - 1)) \\ 2483 &:= (1 + (3 - 5!)) + (79 + ((7 \times (5! \times 3)) \times 1)) \\ 2484 &:= (1 + 35) \times (7 - (((9 - 75) + 3) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2485 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5! - 79) - (7 \times (5! \times 3))) \times 1) \\ 2486 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 + ((97 \times 5) \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 2487 &:= ((13 - 5) \times ((7 \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) + 3)) - 1 \\ 2488 &:= ((13 - 5) \times ((7 \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) + 3)) \times 1 \\ 2489 &:= 1 \times ((3^5) - (79 - (75 \times 31))) \\ 2490 &:= 1 + ((3^5) - (79 - (75 \times 31))) \\ 2491 &:= ((13 - 57) - 9) \times ((7 - 53) - 1) \\ 2492 &:= ((1 + (357 - 9)) + 7) \times (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 2493 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97 - ((5^3) + 1) \\ 2494 &:= (((13 \times 579) - 7!) + (5 + 3)) - 1 \\ 2495 &:= (((13 \times 579) - 7!) + (5 + 3)) \times 1 \\ 2496 &:= (135 \times (7 + 9)) + ((7!/5)/(3 \times 1)) \\ 2497 &:= (13 - (5 \times 7)) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5!)/3) - 1) \\ 2498 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 - 9)) \times (7^{5-3})) - 1 \\ 2499 &:= ((1 + 35) + 797) \times (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 2500 &:= ((1^{3!} - ((5 \times 7) + (9 + 7)))^{5-3 \times 1}) \\ 2501 &:= (1 \times (35 \times (79 - 7))) - ((5!/3!) - 1) \\ 2502 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 - 7)) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 2503 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((57 - 9) + ((7! - 5!)/(3 - 1))) \\ 2504 &:= ((13 + 57 + 97) \times (5 \times 3)) - 1 \\ 2505 &:= ((13 + 57 + 97) \times (5 \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 2506 &:= ((13 + 57 + 97) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1 \\ 2507 &:= (((1 \times 35) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5^3))) - 1 \\ 2508 &:= (((1 \times 35) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5^3))) \times 1 \\ 2509 &:= (((1 \times 35) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5^3))) + 1 \\ 2510 &:= (1357 - (97 + 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 2511 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((57 \times (97 - 53)) \times 1) \\ 2512 &:= 1 + (3 + ((57 \times (97 - 53)) \times 1)) \\ 2513 &:= (1 \times (357 + (9 - 7))) \times (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 2514 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((57 \times (97 - 53)) \times 1) \\ 2515 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 797) + (5! + 3 + 1) \\ 2516 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7) + 9) - (7!/(5 - (3 \times 1)))) \\ 2517 &:= (1 + (3!!/5!)) + ((7!/(9 - 7)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 2518 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5! + (7 \times 97)))) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 2519 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5)) + ((7^{9-7}) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 2520 &:= (1 + (35 \times (79 - 7))) - ((5 - 3) - 1) \\ 2521 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 - 7)) - (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 2522 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 - 7)) \times (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 2523 &:= (135 + (7 \times 9)) + (75 \times 31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2524 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 + 79) + ((7! + 5!)/3)) \times 1) \\ 2525 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + (9 - 7))) - (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 2526 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7!) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 2527 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + (9 - 7))) + (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 2528 &:= ((1^{357}) \times (9 + (7!/(5 - 3)))) - 1 \\ 2529 &:= ((1^{357}) \times (9 + (7!/(5 - 3)))) \times 1 \\ 2530 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + (7 \times 9)))) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2531 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (79 - 7))) + (5 + 3!)) \times 1 \\ 2532 &:= (13 \times 57) - (9 - (75 \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 2533 &:= 13 + ((5 - 7) + ((9 + (7! - 5))/(3 - 1))) \\ 2534 &:= 13 + ((5! \times ((7 + 9 + 7) - (5 - 3))) + 1) \\ 2535 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5!) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5))) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 2536 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) - 7)) \times 5) - (3 + 1) \\ 2537 &:= (13 + ((57^{9-7}) - 5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 2538 &:= ((13 + 5!) - (79 + 7)) \times (53 + 1) \\ 2539 &:= ((1 + (((3 \times 57) - (9 - 7)) \times 5)) \times 3) + 1 \\ 2540 &:= (135 + ((797 + 5) \times 3)) - 1 \\ 2541 &:= 135 + ((797 + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2542 &:= (135 + ((797 + 5) \times 3)) + 1 \\ 2543 &:= (1 - ((3 \times ((5! + 7) - 975)) + 3)) + 1 \\ 2544 &:= (13 \times 5!) + ((7 + (975 + 3)) - 1) \\ 2545 &:= ((13 + 57) \times 9) + (7! - (5^{3! - 1})) \\ 2546 &:= (((1^{3!}) + 57) \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 2547 &:= (13 + (57^{9-7})) + ((5 - 3!) \times 1) \\ 2548 &:= ((13 + (5 + 7 + 9)) \times 75) - (3 - 1) \\ 2549 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times 7) - (9 - ((7 \times 5) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 2550 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 2551 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5 + (797 \times 5)) - 3! \times 1) \\ 2552 &:= ((13 + (5 + 7 + 9)) \times 75) + (3 - 1) \\ 2553 &:= (1 \times (3! - 57)) + ((9 + 75) \times 31) \\ 2554 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times 9) + ((7!/5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 2555 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5! \times ((7 - 9) + 7))) + (5 \times 31) \\ 2556 &:= (135 + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 2557 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) + (((7!/(9 - 7)) - 5) + 3!) + 1 \\ 2558 &:= (((1^{3!}) + 57) \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 2559 &:= (((1^{3!}) + 57) \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) + (3! + 1) \\ 2560 &:= (135 - 7) \times (9 + ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1)!)) \\ 2561 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + (5 + (7!/(9 - 7)))) + (5 \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 2562 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 + (797 + 53)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2563 &:= ((135 + 79) \times (7 + 5)) - (3! - 1) \\ 2564 &:= 1 + (35 + ((7 + 9 + 7!)/(5 - (3 \times 1)))) \\ 2565 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5! - 79))) + ((7 \times (5! \times 3)) + 1) \\ 2566 &:= (((1^{35}) \times (7! + 97)) - 5)/(3 - 1) \\ 2567 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5)^7) + (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\ 2568 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + ((57 - 9) + (75 \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 2569 &:= (1 + (3!/5!)) + (((79 + 7!) + 5)/(3 - 1)) \\ 2570 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) - (7 - (9 + (75 \times 31))) \\ 2571 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5!) \times 7) - (9 - 7)) + (53 - 1) \\ 2572 &:= 1 + 35 + (7 + 9 + (7!/(5 - (3 \times 1)))) \\ 2573 &:= 1 + ((35 \times (79 - 7)) + (53 - 1)) \\ 2574 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 \times ((7 - 97) + 5))) \times (3! \times 1) \\ 2575 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (5! - ((7 + 97) + 531)) \\ 2576 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 2577 &:= 1 - ((35 - 7) - ((9 + 75) \times 31)) \\ 2578 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 7) + ((9 + (7! - 5))/(3 - 1)) \\ 2579 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7! + (9 - 7)) + 5 \times 31) \\ 2580 &:= (1 + (3! + (5 \times 7))) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3! \times 1))) \\ 2581 &:= ((1^{3!}) + 5!) + ((7!/(9 - 7)) - (5!/(3 - 1))) \\ 2582 &:= ((13 \times ((5 + 7) \times 9)) + (7 - 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 2583 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 2584 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 + 7) + 53) - 1) \\ 2585 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 2586 &:= (1 \times (((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) + 7) \times 5)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 2587 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (((5 - 7)^9) - 7)) - ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 2588 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5! - 7!)/(9 - 7))) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 2589 &:= (1 \times (3 - ((5! - 7!)/(9 - 7)))) + (5! + 3! \times 1) \\ 2590 &:= (13 + (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7))) \times (5 \times (3! + 1)) \\ 2591 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times 7) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 2592 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times ((7 - (5 \times 3)) - 1)) \\ 2593 &:= (1^3 - 5!) + (7! - (97 \times (5!/(3! - 1)))) \\ 2594 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7)^9) - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1) \\ 2595 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) - (7 - ((9 + 75) \times 31)) \\ 2596 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 79) + (((7 \times 5!) \times 3) - 1) \\ 2597 &:= (1^{35}) \times (((7^{9-7}) \times 53) \times 1) \\ 2598 &:= ((1 + (357 - 9)) \times 7) + (5 \times 31) \\ 2599 &:= ((13 - 5) \times ((7 + (9 \times (7 \times 5))) + 3)) - 1 \\ 2600 &:= (((1 - 3) - (5 \times 7)) - (9 \times 7)) \times (5 - 31) \\ 2601 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (((57 - 9) \times 7) + 531)) \end{aligned}$$

- 2602** := $1 + (3 \times ((57 - 9) \times 7) + 531)$
2603 := $(1 \times (3!! + (5 + 7!))) - ((97 + 5) \times 31)$
2604 := $((((1^{3!}) \times (57 - 9)) + 7!) + 5!)/(3 - 1)$
2605 := $((1 + 3) \times 579) + (7!/5) - (3!! - 1)$
2606 := $((((1 + 35) + (7 + 9)) + 7!) + 5!)/(3 - 1)$
2607 := $(1 + (((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) + 7) \times 5)) - (3 + 1)$
2608 := $(135 - 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31))$
2609 := $1 + ((3 + 5) + ((7 + 97) \times (5^{3-1})))$
2610 := $((1 \times 3)! \times 57) + ((9 \times (7!/5))/(3 + 1))$
2611 := $((1^{35}) \times 7) + ((9 + 75) \times 31)$
2612 := $(((((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97) - 5) - (3 - 1)$
2613 := $((13 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + (75 \times 31)$
2614 := $((1 + 35) + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5) + ((3! - 1))!$
2615 := $1 \times ((3 + 5) + (79 \times (7 - 5 + 31)))$
2616 := $((1 + (35 + 7)) - (9 - 75)) \times (3 + 1)!$
2617 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 \times (79 \times 7)))) - (5! + 31)$
2618 := $((((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) + 7) \times 5) - (3 - 1)$
2619 := $(1 - (35 - 7)) \times (9 - (75 + 31))$
2620 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5 \times (7 - 9)) \times (7 + (5! + 3 + 1)))$
2621 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + ((7 + 9 + (7 \times 5))^{3-1})$
2622 := $(13 \times 5) + ((79 + (7! - 5))/(3 - 1))$
2623 := $(1 - ((3! - 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7)))) + (5 - (3! - 1))$
2624 := $(1 - (35 + 7)) \times ((9 - (75 - 3)) - 1)$
2625 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5!) \times 7)) + ((9 - 7) \times (53 - 1))$
2626 := $((((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97) + (5 + 3 - 1)$
2627 := $(1^{3!}) - ((5 - ((7! + 97) + 5!))/(3 - 1))$
2628 := $(13 + ((5 \times (79 + 7)) - 5)) \times 3! \times 1$
2629 := $13 + ((579 + 75) \times (3 + 1))$
2630 := $(1 + (3!! \times 5)) + (7 - (975 + 3 \times 1))$
2631 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (79 + 7)) \times (5 + 3) - 1$
2632 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (79 + 7)) \times (5 + 3) \times 1$
2633 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (79 + 7)) \times (5 + 3) + 1$
2634 := $(1 \times (((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) + 7) \times 5)) + (3 + 1)!$
2635 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + ((7!/(9 - 7)) - ((5 + 3) + 1))$
2636 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3))) - 1$
2637 := $1 - (((3 - (5 \times (79 \times 7))) + (5^3)) + 1)$
2638 := $(1 \times (3^5)) + (((7 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3)) + 1)$
2639 := $1 - (((3 - (5 \times (79 \times 7))) + (5^3)) - 1)$
2640 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + ((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5!/3! \times 1)$
2641 := $((1 + (3!^5)) - 7!) - ((97 - 5) + 3 + 1)$
2642 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) - ((7 - 9) \times (7! - (5! \times 31)))$
2643 := $((1 + 3^5) + 7!) + (9 - 7)/(5 - (3 \times 1))$
2644 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 + (7 \times 9))) + ((7!/5) + 3 + 1)$
2645 := $((1 \times (3!! + 5)) + 7!) + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) - ((3! + 1))!)$
2646 := $(1 - 3) + (((57^{9-7}) + 5!) - (3!! + 1))$
2647 := $1 + ((3!!/5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!) - ((3! - 1))!))$
2648 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (7! + 97)) + (5 + 3 + 1)$
2649 := $(1 \times ((3!^5) - 7!)) - (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
2650 := $(1 + ((3!^5) - 7!)) - (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
2651 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!) + (3! - 1))$
2652 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) - (7 \times ((9 - (7 \times 53)) \times 1))$
2653 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + (7!/(9 - 7)) + ((5 + 3) + 1)$
2654 := $(1^3 \times 5!) - (7 \times (9 - ((7 \times 53) \times 1)))$
2655 := $((1 + 3) + (5 + (7!/(9 - 7)))) + (5! + (3! \times 1))$
2656 := $(13 - 5) \times ((7 + (975/3)) \times 1)$
2657 := $1 \times (((3!^5) - 79) - (7! \times ((5 - 3) - 1)))$
2658 := $1 + (((3!^5) - 79) - (7! \times ((5 - 3) - 1)))$
2659 := $(13 \times (5! + (7 \times 9))) + (7 \times (5!/(3 \times 1)))$
2660 := $((1 + (35 \times 79)) - 75) - 31$
2661 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times (7 + 9 + 7))) - 5! - (3 \times 1)$
2662 := $((135 + (7!/(9 - 7))) + 5) + (3 - 1)$
2663 := $(1 - 3 + 5) + (7 \times (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)))$
2664 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) - 97 \times (5 + 31)$
2665 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7975/(3 \times 1)$
2666 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 79) - (7!/(5! \times 3)))) - 1$
2667 := $((1^3 \times 5!) + 7) \times ((9 + 75)/(3 + 1))$
2668 := $(13 + (579 + 75)) \times (3 + 1)$
2669 := $1 \times (((35 \times 79) - 7) - 5!) + 31$
2670 := $((1 \times 3)^5 \times (7 - (9 - 7))) + 5! \times (3 - 1)$
2671 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! + 7)) + (975 \times (3 \times 1))$
2672 := $(13 + 57 + 97) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1)$
2673 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7 \times ((97 + (5 - 3)) \times 1)$
2674 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times 7) + (975 - (3 - 1))$
2675 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5) + (7 \times (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1))))$
2676 := $(1 + (357 \times 9)) - 7 - 531$
2677 := $(1 - 3!!) + (((5! + (7!/9)) - 7) \times 5) + 31$
2678 := $(1357 \times (9 - 7)) - (5 + 31)$
2679 := $((1 + 3) - ((5! - (7 \times 97)) \times 5)) - ((3! - 1))!$

- 2680** := $135 + ((7!/(9-7)) + (5^{3-1}))$
2681 := $(1^3 + 5) + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - 3!) \times 1$
2682 := $(1 - (35 \times 7)) + ((975 \times 3) + 1)$
2683 := $1 \times (3 - (5 \times (7 - ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1))))))$
2684 := $1 + (3 - (5 \times (7 - ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1))))))$
2685 := $((((1 + 3)^5) - ((7 \times 9)/7) - 5!) \times (3 \times 1)$
2686 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - ((7! - ((9 - 7) - 53)) \times 1)$
2687 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) + 3! \times 1)$
2688 := $((1 - 3) - ((5 - 7) \times 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
2689 := $(1^{3!}) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!))$
2690 := $((1 + (357 \times 9)) + 7) - 531$
2691 := $(13 \times 57) + (975 \times (3 - 1))$
2692 := $((1 + (3!/5)) + (79 + (7! + 5!)))/(3 - 1)$
2693 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times 7 - (9 + (7 \times (5 - 31)))$
2694 := $1 \times ((35 \times 79) - ((75 - 3) - 1))$
2695 := $1 + ((35 \times 79) - ((75 - 3) - 1))$
2696 := $(1 - 3 + (((5 \times 7) - 9)^{7-5})) \times (3 + 1)$
2697 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - ((79 + (7 \times (5 \times 3))) - 1)$
2698 := $((1 + 3)! - 5) \times (((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) - 3!) + 1)$
2699 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 \times 7) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) - (3 \times 1)))$
2700 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7 \times ((97 + (5 - 3)) + 1)$
2701 := $1 - ((3 \times 5 \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1))$
2702 := $(1 + (35 \times 79)) - (((7 - 5)^{3!}) \times 1)$
2703 := $(1 + (35 \times 79)) - (((7 - 5)^{3!}) - 1)$
2704 := $(1 - (((3 \times 5) - 7) + 97)) \times (5 - 31)$
2705 := $(1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) - (5 + (3! + 1))$
2706 := $((1 \times 35) \times 79) - (7 + (53 - 1))$
2707 := $((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) - 5) - (3! - 1)$
2708 := $((1357 + 9) - (7 + 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
2709 := $(1 - (3^5)) + (((7 + (97 \times 5)) \times 3!) - 1)$
2710 := $(13 + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + (7!/(5 - (3 - 1)))$
2711 := $(1 - (3^5)) + (((7 + (97 \times 5)) \times 3!) + 1)$
2712 := $(1 \times ((3!^5) - (7! - (9 - 7)))) + (5 - 31)$
2713 := $13 - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times (75 \times (3 - 1))))$
2714 := $((1 - 3)^5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5) - 3! \times 1$
2715 := $((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + 5) - (3! + 1)$
2716 := $(1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + (5 - (3! \times 1))$
2717 := $((1 - 3)^5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5) - (3 \times 1)$
2718 := $(1 - 3 + (5 \times 79)) + (75 \times 31)$
2719 := $((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) - 5) + 3! + 1$
2720 := $(1^3) \times ((5! + 79) + ((7 \times (5! \times 3)) + 1))$
2721 := $(1^3) + ((5! + 79) + ((7 \times (5! \times 3)) + 1))$
2722 := $((1 + (35 \times 79)) - 75) + 31$
2723 := $((1 - 3)^5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5) + (3 \times 1)$
2724 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (((7 \times 9) \times 7) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)$
2725 := $((1 - 35) + (79 \times (7 \times 5))) - (3! \times 1)$
2726 := $((1 - 3)^5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5) + 3! \times 1$
2727 := $(1 + (3 - ((5 \times 79) + 7))) + (5^{3!-1})$
2728 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 - ((7 - 9) \times 7)))) \times (5! + 3 + 1)$
2729 := $((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + 5) + (3! + 1)$
2730 := $1 - ((3! - ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) - (53 + 1))$
2731 := $1 - (((3 \times 5) - 7) + 97) \times (5 - 31)$
2732 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5) + 7!)) + 9) - (75 \times 31)$
2733 := $13 + ((5 \times 79) + (75 \times 31))$
2734 := $(1^3) \times (((5 \times ((79 \times 7) - 5)) - 3!) \times 1)$
2735 := $((1^3 \times 5) \times (79 \times 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) \times 1)$
2736 := $((1 + ((3 + 579) - 7)) - 5!) \times 3! \times 1$
2737 := $(1^3) - (5! - ((7 \times (97 + 5)) \times (3 + 1)))$
2738 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - (5^{3-1}))$
2739 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5 - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5!))) + 3 \times 1$
2740 := $(1^3 - 5) - (((7 - 9) - (7 + 5))^3) \times 1$
2741 := $13 - ((5 - 7) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times 31))$
2742 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) - ((7 - (9 + (7 + 5)))^3) \times 1$
2743 := $((13 - 5!) \times 7) + (97 \times (5 + 31))$
2744 := $((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + 7) + 531$
2745 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7 \times 97 + ((5^3) + 1)$
2746 := $(1 + ((3! \times 5) \times 79)) + (75 \times (3! - 1))$
2747 := $(1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + (5 \times (3! \times 1))$
2748 := $((1 - 3) - (57 - 975)) \times (3 \times 1)$
2749 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) + ((7 \times 9) \times 7) \times 5 - 31$
2750 := $(1357 \times (9 - 7)) + (5 + 31)$
2751 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + 7 - ((9 + 7) + (5! \times (3! + 1)))$
2752 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5) - 3! \times 1$
2753 := $1 - (3 - (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5) - 3! + 1)$
2754 := $((13 - (57 + 9)) \times 7) + (5^{3!-1})$
2755 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) + ((7! + 5!)/(3 \times 1)))$
2756 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 5) + ((7 + (9 \times (75 \times 3))) - 1)$
2757 := $(13 \times 57) + ((9 + 75) \times (3 + 1)!)$

$$\begin{aligned} 2758 &:= 1 + (3 \times (5! + (79 + (((7 + 5)/(3 - 1)))))) \\ 2759 &:= (1 + (35 \times 79)) - (((7 - 5) \times 3) + 1) \\ 2760 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 79)) - (((7 - 5) \times 3) - 1) \\ 2761 &:= (1^3 - 5!) - (((7 - (9 + 7)) + 5) \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 2762 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - ((5 + 3) - 1)) \\ 2763 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) \times ((5 - 3) - 1)) \\ 2764 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) - (7! - (9 - 7)))) - (5 - 31) \\ 2765 &:= ((1 + (35 \times 79)) + 7) - ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 2766 &:= (1 - 3 + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5)) - (3 - 1) \\ 2767 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((579 + (7 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 2768 &:= (1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5)) - (3! - 1) \\ 2769 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times 79) - (7 - ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\ 2770 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 79)) + (((7 - 5) \times 3) - 1) \\ 2771 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 79)) + ((7 - 5) \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 2772 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 79)) + ((7 - 5) \times 3)) + 1 \\ 2773 &:= (1 + (35 \times 79)) + (((7 - 5) \times 3) + 1) \\ 2774 &:= (1 + 357) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! + 31)) \\ 2775 &:= 1 - (3 - (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 2776 &:= ((1 - 3!) - 579) + (7 \times (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 2777 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5 - ((7 + 9) \times 7)) \times (5 - 31)) \\ 2778 &:= (13 + ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) \times (5! / ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 2779 &:= (13 + ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + (5! / ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 2780 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 79)) + (7 + ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\ 2781 &:= 135 + ((7^{9-7}) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 2782 &:= (135 + 79) \times (((7 - 5) \times 3!) + 1) \\ 2783 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times 79) + (7 + ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\ 2784 &:= (((13 \times 5) - 7) \times (9 + 7)) \times (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 2785 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times (79 \times 7)) + (5 \times 3))) - 1 \\ 2786 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 - ((7 \times 97) + (5! \times 3!))) + 1) \\ 2787 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 - ((7 \times 97) + (5! \times 3!)))) - 1 \\ 2788 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 - ((7 \times 97) + (5! \times 3!)))) \times 1 \\ 2789 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times (79 \times 7)) - 5) + 31) \\ 2790 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) + ((7 \times 97) - 5)) \times (3! - 1) \\ 2791 &:= (((1^3 + 5) + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 2792 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times 7) + ((9 + (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2793 &:= ((13 + 5!) \times ((7 + 9 + 7) - (5 - 3))) \times 1 \\ 2794 &:= ((13 + (5 \times (7!/9))) + (7 + 5)) - 31 \\ 2795 &:= 13 \times (((5 + 79) + 7) + ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 2796 &:= (1^3 - 5) \times ((7 - (9 \times 75)) - 31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2797 &:= (((1 + (3^5 + 7)) \times 9) + 7) + 531 \\ 2798 &:= (1 \times (3!! \times 5)) - ((7 + (9 \times 75)) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 2799 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) \times 5) - (((7 \times 97) + 5!) + 3 - 1) \\ 2800 &:= (13 + (5 + 7)) \times ((97 + (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 2801 &:= ((1 \times 3! + 5) + (7 - 97)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 2802 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (797 \times (5 - 3!))) - 1 \\ 2803 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7) - 9)!)) - ((75 + 3) - 1) \\ 2804 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (797 \times (5 - 3!))) + 1 \\ 2805 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 \times (79 \times 7)))) + (5 + 31) \\ 2806 &:= (1^3 \times 5!) - (79 \times ((7 - (5!/3)) - 1)) \\ 2807 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5) - 79)) + (7 + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 2808 &:= ((135 - 7) - ((9 + 7) - 5)) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 2809 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 57) - 9) + (7 - 5)))^{3-1} \\ 2810 &:= 1 + (((35 \times 79) + 75) - 31) \\ 2811 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) + ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) \times 5 + 31 \\ 2812 &:= ((1 - 35) \times 7) - ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) \times 3) + 1 \\ 2813 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times 5) \times (7!/9)) - 7) + (5! / (3! \times 1)) \\ 2814 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5!)) + 7) + ((975 \times 3) - 1) \\ 2815 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5!)) + 7) + ((975 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 2816 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7 \times 9)) \times (((7!/5!) + 3) - 1) \\ 2817 &:= 1 \times ((3^{5-7+9}) + (7! / (5 + 3 \times 1))) \\ 2818 &:= 1 + ((3^{5-7+9}) + (7! / (5 + 3 \times 1))) \\ 2819 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) + ((7 \times 9) - 7)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 2820 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((7 \times 9) + (75 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 2821 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5 \times 7)) + (975 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2822 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (7! - ((9 + 7) \times 5))) + (3! - 1) \\ 2823 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) - 7!)) + (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 2824 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) - 7!)) + (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 2825 &:= (1 \times 3579) - (753 + 1) \\ 2826 &:= (1 + 3579) - (753 + 1) \\ 2827 &:= (1 \times 3579) - (753 - 1) \\ 2828 &:= (1 + (3579 - 753)) + 1 \\ 2829 &:= (1 + (35 \times 79)) + (((7 - 5)^{3!}) - 1) \\ 2830 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) + (((79 + 7) + 5) \times 31) \\ 2831 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) - 7) + ((97 - 5) \times 31) \\ 2832 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7 + 97) + (5! + (3!! \times 1))) \\ 2833 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - 7!) + ((97 - 5) + 3 + 1) \\ 2834 &:= 13 \times (((5 + 79) + (7 + 5!)) + (3! + 1)) \\ 2835 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 \times ((7!/9) - ((7 \times 53) \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2836 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + 79) + (7 \times ((5! \times 3) - 1)) \\ 2837 &:= ((1 \times ((35 \times 79) + 75)) - 3) \times 1 \\ 2838 &:= ((1 \times ((35 \times 79) + 75)) - 3) + 1 \\ 2839 &:= (1^3 + (57 \times 9)) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2840 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) - 3!) + 1)) \\ 2841 &:= 1 \times (3 + ((57 \times 9) + (75 \times 31))) \\ 2842 &:= (1 + 3) + ((57 \times 9) + (75 \times 31)) \\ 2843 &:= (1 \times (((35 \times 79) + 75) + 3)) \times 1 \\ 2844 &:= (1 \times (((35 \times 79) + 75) + 3)) + 1 \\ 2845 &:= (1 + (((35 \times 79) + 75) + 3)) + 1 \\ 2846 &:= (((1 + 35) \times 79) - (7 - 5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 2847 &:= (1 + (35 \times 79)) + (75 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 2848 &:= (1 - 3) + ((57 \times (9 - 7)) \times (5^{3-1})) \\ 2849 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (97 + 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 2850 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5! + (7 \times 9)) - (753 \times 1)) \\ 2851 &:= 13 + ((57 \times 9) + (75 \times 31)) \\ 2852 &:= ((1 - (3 - 57)) - 9) \times ((7 - 5) \times 31) \\ 2853 &:= ((1 + (3 \times ((5! + (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times 5))) + 3) - 1 \\ 2854 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) - (7 - ((97 - 5) \times 31)) \\ 2855 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (57 - (97 + 531)) \\ 2856 &:= ((13 + (5 \times (7!/9))) + (7 + 5)) + 31 \\ 2857 &:= (1 \times (35/7)) + ((97 - 5) \times 31) \\ 2858 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - 7) - ((97 - 5) \times 31)) \\ 2859 &:= (135 + 7!) + (9 - (75 \times 31)) \\ 2860 &:= ((135 \times 7) + (97 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 2861 &:= (1 - 3) + (((579 - 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 2862 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! - (7 \times (9 - 7)))) \times (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 2863 &:= ((1 - 3!) - 57) + (975 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2864 &:= (((1 - ((3 + 5) + 7)) - 9) + 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 2865 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7 \times (97 + 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 2866 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times (7!/5!)) + 3 + 1) \\ 2867 &:= (1 + (3579 + 7)) - (5! \times 3! \times 1) \\ 2868 &:= (13 \times 5) - (797 - (5 \times 3!! \times 1)) \\ 2869 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - 7!) - ((9 - 75) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 2870 &:= (1^{357} + 9) \times (7 \times ((5!/3) + 1)) \\ 2871 &:= ((1^{3!}) + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7))) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\ 2872 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5 + (7 + ((9 \times 75) + 31))) \\ 2873 &:= (1 \times 3 + 57) + (97 \times (5 + (3 + 1)!)) \\ 2874 &:= ((1 \times 357 + (9 - 7)) + 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 2875 &:= (1 - (3! + 5!)) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5 - 3! \times 1)) \\ 2876 &:= 1 - (((3 + 5) \times (7 - 9)) - 7) \times ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 2877 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 2878 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) \times (7 - 97)) - ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\ 2879 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times 5) \times (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3))) - 1 \\ 2880 &:= (1 + 357) - (97 \times (5 - 31)) \\ 2881 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3))) \times 1 \\ 2882 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3))) + 1 \\ 2883 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (79 + (7!/5!))) \times 3 \times 1 \\ 2884 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (79 + (7!/5!))) \times 3 + 1 \\ 2885 &:= 1 - ((35 + 7) - ((975 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 2886 &:= (1 \times 357 + 9) + (7!/((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 2887 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 - (3! - 1))) \\ 2888 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (79 + 7))) - 5!) - (3 - 1) \\ 2889 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7! + (9 - 7))) + (5 \times 31) \\ 2890 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) - ((7 - 975) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2891 &:= (1^3 + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\ 2892 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (79 + 7))) - 5!) + (3 - 1) \\ 2893 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5! - 7!)) - ((9 \times (75 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 2894 &:= (1 + (3 - (5 \times 7))) + ((975 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 2895 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((57 + 9) + 7) + 5!) \times (3! - 1) \\ 2896 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 + 7)) \times ((9 - (7 \times 53)) \times 1) \\ 2897 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!) + (3! \times 1) \\ 2898 &:= (1 - (35 - 7)) + (975 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 2899 &:= ((1 - 3!) - 5!) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 2900 &:= (1 + (3!! - 5)) + ((7 + 97) \times ((5!/3!) + 1)) \\ 2901 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5)) - (7 - 975)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 2902 &:= (1 - 3 + 579) + (75 \times 31) \\ 2903 &:= (((135 \times 7) - (97 - 5!)) \times 3) - 1 \\ 2904 &:= (((135 \times 7) - (97 - 5!)) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 2905 &:= (((135 \times 7) - (97 - 5!)) \times 3) + 1 \\ 2906 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) + ((7 + 9 + 7) \times (5^3 + 1)) \\ 2907 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 75)) - 31) \\ 2908 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((579 + (7 - 5)) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 2909 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5 - ((7 + 97) - 5)) \times 31) \\ 2910 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 - (7 - (975 - (3 \times 1)))) \\ 2911 &:= 135 - ((7 + 97) - (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 2912 &:= (((1 \times 3! + 57) - 9)^{7-5}) - (3 + 1) \\ 2913 &:= 1 \times (3! - (5 + (7 \times ((9 + (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)))))) \end{aligned}$$

- 2914** := $13 + ((5797 + 5)/(3 - 1))$
2915 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7)) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3! \times 1))$
2916 := $((1 \times 3! \times (57 \times 9)) - 7) - (5 \times 31)$
2917 := $((1 + (3 - 5)) - 7) + (975 \times (3 \times 1))$
2918 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - ((7 \times (9 \times (7 - 53))) \times 1)$
2919 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 \times (79 \times 7)))) + (5! + 31)$
2920 := $(1^{35}) - (7 - ((975 \times 3) + 1))$
2921 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((57 - 9) + 7) \times (53 \times 1))$
2922 := $(1 + (3!! \times 5)) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
2923 := $((1 \times 3!!) + ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) \times 7)) - (5 - (3 \times 1))$
2924 := $((((1 \times 3!) + 5) \times 797) + 5)/(3 \times 1)$
2925 := $((1^3 + (5 + 7)) \times (9 \times 75))/(3 \times 1)$
2926 := $(1^{357}) \times ((975 \times 3) + 1)$
2927 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5) - ((7 \times (9 + (7 - 5!))) \times (3 + 1)))$
2928 := $((13 - 57) \times (9 - 75)) + (3 + 1)!$
2929 := $((1 + 3) - 5!) + (((7!/(9 + 7)) + 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
2930 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 - (7 + 975)))) - (3 - 1)$
2931 := $((1 \times 35)/7) + ((975 \times 3) + 1)$
2932 := $(1^{35}) \times ((7 + (975 \times 3)) \times 1)$
2933 := $(1^{35}) + ((7 + (975 \times 3)) \times 1)$
2934 := $((1 - 35) \times (7 - 97)) - (5^3) - 1$
2935 := $((1 - 35) \times (7 - 97)) - (5^3) \times 1$
2936 := $((1 - 35) \times (7 - 97)) - (5^3) + 1$
2937 := $(13 + (5 - 7)) + ((975 \times 3) + 1)$
2938 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! - 7)) \times ((9 - 7) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
2939 := $(13 - (5 - 7)) + ((975 \times 3) - 1)$
2940 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 75)/(3 + 1)))$
2941 := $(13 - (5 - 7)) + ((975 \times 3) + 1)$
2942 := $((1 \times (3 - 57))^{9-7} - 5) + 31$
2943 := $((1 + 3) - (5 - (7 + 975))) \times (3 \times 1)$
2944 := $(135 - 7) \times ((9 + 7) + ((5 + 3) - 1))$
2945 := $((1 + 35) - ((7 + 9) - 75)) \times 31$
2946 := $((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 + 975)/(3 \times 1)$
2947 := $1 - ((3! - 5) - (((7 + 975) \times 3) + 1))$
2948 := $1 \times ((3! - 5) + (((7 + 975) \times 3) + 1))$
2949 := $((13 + 5) + 7) + (975 \times 3) - 1$
2950 := $((13 + 5) + 7) + (975 \times 3) \times 1$
2951 := $((13 + 5) + 7) + (975 \times 3) + 1$
2952 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5! - (3 + 1)))$
2953 := $((1 - 3!) - 5!) + (79 - 7) + (5! \times 31)$
2954 := $1 \times (35 - (7 - ((975 \times 3) + 1)))$
2955 := $((13 + 57) \times 9) + (75 \times 31)$
2956 := $((1^3 + 5!) - 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) \times 1))$
2957 := $((1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7) - 9)!!)) + ((75 + 3) - 1)$
2958 := $1 \times 3! + (((57 - 9) + 75) \times (3 + 1)!)!$
2959 := $1 - (3! + (57 \times ((9 + 7) - 5!)/(3 - 1)))$
2960 := $((1 + 35) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) + 3!! - 1$
2961 := $(1 \times 357) + ((9 + 75) \times 31)$
2962 := $((1 + 35) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) + 3!! + 1$
2963 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) + ((975 \times 3) \times 1)$
2964 := $(13 \times ((5! - 79) + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 \times 1)$
2965 := $(1 + ((3 + (5 \times 7)) + (975 \times 3))) + 1$
2966 := $1 \times (35 + ((7 + (975 \times 3)) - 1))$
2967 := $1 + (35 + ((7 + (975 \times 3)) - 1))$
2968 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times (53 \times 1))$
2969 := $((1 - ((35 - 7) + (9 \times (7 - 5!)))) \times 3) - 1$
2970 := $(((((1 + 3!)/5) - (7 + (9 + 7))) + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
2971 := $((1 - ((35 - 7) + (9 \times (7 - 5!)))) \times 3) + 1$
2972 := $(1 - (35/7)) \times ((9 - 753) + 1)$
2973 := $13 - ((5 - 79) \times (7!/(5^3 + 1)))$
2974 := $1 \times (((3 - 57) - 97) + (5^{3!-1}))$
2975 := $(1 - 3!) \times (((5! - 7) + (9 + 7)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1))$
2976 := $(1^3 \times (5! - ((7 - 9)^7))) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1)$
2977 := $(1 - 3!!) + ((5 + 79) \times (75 - 31))$
2978 := $((1 + 3) + (5 + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 53))) + 1$
2979 := $1 \times 3 + ((5! - ((7 - 9)^7)) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
2980 := $(1 - (3 - 57)) + ((975 \times 3) \times 1)$
2981 := $(1 \times 3! + 5!) + (((7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 3!) - 1)$
2982 := $(1 + ((3! \times 5) - 7)) - ((97 + 5) \times (3! \times 1))$
2983 := $13 - ((57 + 9) \times (7 - (53 - 1)))$
2984 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) + (97 \times (5 + (3 + 1)!))$
2985 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + (75 \times (3 + 1)!)!$
2986 := $(1 + 3) + (57 + ((975 \times 3) \times 1))$
2987 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 53) - 1$
2988 := $((1 + 3)^5 - (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
2989 := $13 + ((5! - ((79 - 75)!) \times 31)$
2990 := $(1 + (35 + 79)) \times ((75/3) + 1)$
2991 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5) + (7 + 975))) \times (3 \times 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 2992 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + 7) \times ((97 + (5!/3)) - 1) \\ 2993 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - (7 - ((9 + 7) \times 5!)))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 2994 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times 79) + (7 \times ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 2995 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - 7) \times 9 + (7 \times (5 - 31)) \\ 2996 &:= (1^3 + 5!) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 2997 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) + 7!) + ((9 - 75) \times 31) \\ 2998 &:= (((13 + 579) + 7) \times 5) + (3 \times 1) \\ 2999 &:= (1 - 3) - (5 - (7! - (9 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)))) \\ 3000 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (57 \times ((9 - 7) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 3001 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + 5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times ((3! - 1)!!) \\ 3002 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) \times 7)) + 9) + ((7 + 5!) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 3003 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (57 + (975 - 31)) \\ 3004 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 3005 &:= ((1 - 3!)/5) + (7! - (9 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1))) \\ 3006 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + ((79 \times 7) \times 5))) - (3 - 1) \\ 3007 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5! - 7!) + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\ 3008 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5^{7-9+7} - 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 3009 &:= 1 - ((3 - (5 \times 7)) \times (97 - (5 - (3 - 1)))) \\ 3010 &:= (13 \times 5) - ((7 - (97 + 5)) \times 31) \\ 3011 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 7) + (9 \times (7 + 5 \times 31)) \\ 3012 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 - 7) + (975 + 31)) \\ 3013 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7)))) + (5! - 3! \times 1) \\ 3014 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5! + 7)) - ((9 \times 7) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 3015 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5 + (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5^{3!-1})) \\ 3016 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) - (7 - 97)) \times (53 - 1) \\ 3017 &:= 1 + ((3! + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7))) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 3018 &:= 1 + (((35 \times 7) + 9) \times (7 + 5)) - 31 \\ 3019 &:= (1 - 3) + (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - (5 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 3020 &:= (((1 + 35) \times (7 \times 9)) + 753) - 1 \\ 3021 &:= ((1 + 35) \times (7 \times 9)) + (753 \times 1) \\ 3022 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - ((7 - 97) - (53 - 1)) \\ 3023 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times 7) - (97 - (5! \times (3! - 1))) \\ 3024 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (((5 + 7) + (9 + 75)) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 3025 &:= (1 + (((35 \times (79 - 7))/5) \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 3026 &:= (1 + (((35 \times (79 - 7))/5) \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 3027 &:= (1^{3579} + (7!/5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 3028 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 + 7) - (9 - (753 + 1))) \\ 3029 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times 7) + ((975 \times 3) - 1) \\ 3030 &:= (1^3 \times 5) \times ((79 \times 7) + (53 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3031 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 57)^{9-7}) + 531 \\ 3032 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 57)^{9-7}) + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\ 3033 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 3034 &:= ((13 \times ((5 + 7) \times 9)) - (7 - 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 3035 &:= (1^3 \times 5) \times (((7 + 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3)) - 1) \\ 3036 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (((5 \times 7) + (975 + 3)) - 1)) \\ 3037 &:= 1 + (3 \times (((5 \times 7) + (975 + 3)) - 1)) \\ 3038 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) + ((7! - ((9 + 7) \times (5^3))) \times 1) \\ 3039 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5 - (7 - 9))) + (7!/5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 3040 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7!) - ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 3041 &:= ((1^{35}) + 7!) - ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 3042 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5!) \times ((79 - (7 \times (5 \times 3))) \times 1) \\ 3043 &:= 1 - ((3! + 5!) - ((797 - 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 3044 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times 7)) + 9) + ((7! + 5!)/(3 - 1)) \\ 3045 &:= (1 + (3!! - ((5 + (7 \times (9 + 7))) - 5))) \times (3! - 1) \\ 3046 &:= (13 - 5) - (7 \times (97 - 531)) \\ 3047 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) + 7!) - (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) + 1)) \\ 3048 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - ((5 - 7) \times 9)) + ((7!/5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 3049 &:= (1 + 3) - (5 \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) + (5! - ((3! \times 1)!!))) \\ 3050 &:= (1^3 \times (5 - (7!/(9 \times 7)))) + (5^{3!-1}) \\ 3051 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5! + 7)) + ((975 \times 3) - 1) \\ 3052 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + ((7 + 97) \times 5))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 3053 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7)/(9 - 7) - 531 \\ 3054 &:= (1 - ((3 \times (5! - 7)) \times ((9 - 7) - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 3055 &:= (1 \times 3579) + (7 - 531) \\ 3056 &:= 1 + ((3579 + 7) - 531) \\ 3057 &:= ((1 \times 35) + ((7 - 9) + ((7!/5) \times 3))) \times 1 \\ 3058 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7! - (5 + 3)) + 1) \\ 3059 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! - 7)) \times 9) + (7 - (5 - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 3060 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + (7!/((9 - 7) - 5) + 31)) \\ 3061 &:= (((1 + 35) - (7 - 9)) + ((7!/5) \times 3)) - 1 \\ 3062 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times 57) \times 9) - ((7 + 5) + 3 + 1) \\ 3063 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (5 \times 79)) + (7! - ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 3064 &:= 1 - (((3 \times (5 - 7)) - 9) - ((7 + 5!) \times (3 + 1)!!)) \\ 3065 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5! + 7) - ((9 + 7) + ((5 + 3!) - 1))) \\ 3066 &:= (1 + (3 \times (57 + 975))) - 31 \\ 3067 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5) + (((7 + 975) \times 3) + 1) \\ 3068 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 + (7 + (9 + 7)))) \times (5! - (3 - 1)) \\ 3069 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) \times ((7 + (9 \times 75))/(3 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 3070** := $(1 \times (35 \times (79 + 7))) + (5! / (3 - 1))$
3071 := $((13 + 5) - (79 - 7)) + (5^{3! - 1})$
3072 := $(1 - ((3 \times (5 - 7)) + (9 \times (7 - 5!)))) \times (3 \times 1)$
3073 := $((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 - 7) \times 53) - 1$
3074 := $((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 - 7) \times 53) \times 1$
3075 := $((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 - 7) \times 53) + 1$
3076 := $((1 \times 35) - (7 \times 97)) + (5! \times 31)$
3077 := $(1 \times ((3^5 + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + 5))) - 31$
3078 := $((1^3 \times 57) \times 9) \times (7 - (5 - (3 + 1)))$
3079 := $((1 + 3!) + (5^{7 - 9 + 7})) - (53 \times 1)$
3080 := $(13 - 5) \times (7 \times (9 - ((7 - 53) \times 1)))$
3081 := $135 + (((7 + 975) \times 3) \times 1)$
3082 := $((13 \times 5!) + 797) + 5 + (3! \times 1)$
3083 := $1 \times 3 + (5 \times ((79 + 75) \times (3 + 1)))$
3084 := $((1^3 - 57)^{9 - 7}) - (53 - 1)$
3085 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((5! + 7) + (9 - (753 \times 1)))$
3086 := $(13 \times 5!) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5 \times 31))$
3087 := $1^{35} \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 + 3) - 1))$
3088 := $1^{35} + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 + 3) - 1))$
3089 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + ((79 + 7) \times (5 + 31))$
3090 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) - (7 + (9 + 7))) \times (5 \times 3! \times 1)$
3091 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) - (7 + (5^3)) + 1$
3092 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7) + 9) + (753 - 1))$
3093 := $13 + ((5 \times 7) \times (97 - (5 + 3 + 1)))$
3094 := $((135 - 7) - 9) \times (7 - 5 + (3 + 1)!)$
3095 := $((1^{3!} - 5) \times 7) - (9 - (7 + (5^{3! - 1})))$
3096 := $(1 + 3!) \times ((5 + (7 - 9)) \times ((7 + 5) + 31))$
3097 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5!) - (7 + ((9 + 7) - (5! \times 31)))$
3098 := $(1 - ((3 - (5 \times 7)) \times 97)) - (5 + 3) + 1$
3099 := $((1 - 3)^5) + (((7 - (9 - 7))^5) + 3! \times 1)$
3100 := $((1^{3!} + (5 + (7 \times (9 - 7)))) \times (5 \times 31))$
3101 := $1 + (((35/7)^{9 - 7}) \times (5! + 3 + 1))$
3102 := $((13 + 579) - 75) \times (3! \times 1)$
3103 := $((1 + 35) - 7) \times (((9 - 7) \times 53) + 1)$
3104 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 + 9) \times (7 + (5! + 3 \times 1)))$
3105 := $(1^3 + ((5! + 79) + 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
3106 := $(1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9)) + (7! - (5! \times (3 + 1)!))$
3107 := $(1 - (3^5)) + ((79 \times (7!/5!)) + 31)$
3108 := $(1 \times 3 + (((57 \times 9) + 7) - 5)) \times 3! \times 1$
3109 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 - (7 \times 9))) + ((7 + 5!) \times (3 + 1)!)$
3110 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((5 \times 79) - 7) \times (5 + 3)) \times 1$
3111 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times (79 + 75))) + 31$
3112 := $((1 - ((3 - (5 \times 7)) \times 97)) + (5 + 3)) - 1$
3113 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5) - (7 + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times (3! \times 1))))$
3114 := $(135 \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + ((5 + 3) + 1)$
3115 := $((1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7) \times (9 + 7))) \times (5! - 31)$
3116 := $((1 + (3 - 57)) \times 9) - (7 - (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!))$
3117 := $((1 \times 3)^5) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) - 1$
3118 := $((1 \times 3)^5) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) \times 1$
3119 := $((1 \times 3)^5) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) + 1$
3120 := $(1 \times (3! \times 5)) \times (79 + (75 / (3 \times 1)))$
3121 := $(13 + (5! \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 + 31))$
3122 := $((1^{35}) \times (((7 - 9) + 7)^5)) - (3 \times 1)$
3123 := $(1 + 35) - (7 \times ((9 - (75 \times 3!)) \times 1))$
3124 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 \times (7 + 97)) \times (((5 - 3) + 1)!))$
3125 := $((1 + (3! - 5)) + (7 + (9 + 7))) \times (5^3 \times 1)$
3126 := $(1^{35797}) + (5^{3! - 1})$
3127 := $(1 - (3 \times (5! \times (7 - (9 + 7)))) - (5! - (3! \times 1))$
3128 := $(1 + (3 \times (57 + 975))) + 31$
3129 := $((1^{35}) \times (((7 - 9) + 7)^5)) + 3 + 1$
3130 := $(1 \times 3 + (5^{7 - 9 + 7})) + (5 - (3 \times 1))$
3131 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 \times 79))) + ((7! - (5 + 3!)) \times 1)$
3132 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + ((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 + 31)$
3133 := $(1 + (35 \times (79 + 7))) + ((5! + 3) - 1)$
3134 := $((1 - ((3^5) - 7)) + 9) + ((7 \times 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
3135 := $(1 \times 3! \times 579) + ((7 - 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
3136 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) + 7!) - ((9 \times 7) \times (5 \times (3! \times 1)))$
3137 := $((1 + (3! + 5)) + 7!) - (((9 + 7) \times 5!) - (3! - 1))$
3138 := $13 + 5^{7 / (9 - 7 + 5) + 3 + 1}$
3139 := $(1 \times ((3^5 + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + 5))) + 31$
3140 := $1 - ((3! - (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + 7!) - (5^{3 + 1})$
3141 := $((1^{357}) \times 9) + 7 + (5^{3! - 1})$
3142 := $(1 + 3) - (579 - (7 \times 531))$
3143 := $((1 - 3 + (5 - (7 - 9)))! + (((7!/5) \times 3) - 1)$
3144 := $(1 \times 3!) \times ((5! + 7) - (((9 - 75) \times 3!) - 1))$
3145 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) - ((75 + 3) - 1)$
3146 := $(1^3 + 5!) \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) + (5 \times (3! + 1)))$

- 3147** := $1 \times ((3! \times (5 + ((7 + 97) \times 5))) - (3 \times 1))$
3148 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7 + ((97 + 5) \times 31)$
3149 := $13 + (((5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7)) - 5)^{3-1})$
3150 := $(135 + 7!) - (9 \times ((75 \times 3) \times 1))$
3151 := $((1 \times 357) \times 9) - ((7 - 5) \times 31)$
3152 := $((1^3 - 5) + (797 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)$
3153 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 + 7)) + ((97 + 5) \times 31)$
3154 := $(13 + 5) + (((7!/9) + (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))$
3155 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5 + 7!)) - (((9 \times 7) \times (5 \times 3!)) \times 1)$
3156 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7 + 9 + 7)) + (5^{3!-1})$
3157 := $1 \times ((3! + (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) - (3 \times 1)))$
3158 := $1 + ((3! + (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) - (3 \times 1)))$
3159 := $13 \times (((5! + (7 - 9)) + 7) + ((5! - 3) + 1))$
3160 := $(1 \times ((3 - (5 - 797)) - 5)) \times (3 + 1)$
3161 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) - 7 - (53 + 1)$
3162 := $((1 - 3) \times 57) + (9 \times (7 \times (53 - 1)))$
3163 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) - 7 - 53 + 1$
3164 := $(1 + ((3 - (5 - 797)) - 5)) \times (3 + 1)$
3165 := $(135 \times (7 + 9)) + ((7!/5) - (3 \times 1))$
3166 := $((1 \times 3)^5 \times (7 + 9)) - (7 - 5) - (3!! \times 1)$
3167 := $1 \times ((3! \times (((5 \times 79) + 7) + (5! + 3!))) - 1)$
3168 := $((1 - 3)^5) \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times (5 + (3! \times 1)))$
3169 := $(1 + (357 \times 9)) + ((7 - 53) + 1)$
3170 := $((1 \times 3)^5 \times (7 + 9)) + (7 - 5) - (3!! \times 1)$
3171 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - 9) + 7 \times (5 + 3 - 1)$
3172 := $((1 - (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7) - (5 \times 3))) \times 1$
3173 := $(1^3 + (5 - (79 \times 7))) + (5! \times 31)$
3174 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7))) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)$
3175 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5 \times 7) + 97)) + (5 + 3 - 1)$
3176 := $((13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) / (3 \times 1)$
3177 := $1 \times (((3! \times (57 \times 9)) + 75) + (3 + 1)!)$
3178 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) - (75 - 31)$
3179 := $(1 \times (35 \times ((79 + 7) + 5))) - 3! \times 1$
3180 := $((1 \times 357) \times 9) - (7 - 5) - 31$
3181 := $1 + ((3 + 57) \times ((9 + 75) - 31))$
3182 := $(1 \times (35 \times ((79 + 7) + 5))) - (3 \times 1)$
3183 := $(1 \times 3 + 5) + (((7!/9) + 75) \times (3! - 1))$
3184 := $((1 \times 357) \times 9) + ((7 - 5) - 31)$
3185 := $(13 \times 5) \times (7 + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 - 1)))$
3186 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) - ((7 + 5) \times (3 \times 1)))$
3187 := $(1 \times 3 + (57 + 9)) - (7 - (5^{3!-1}))$
3188 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + 797)) - (5 \times (3 + 1))$
3189 := $(1^3 \times (57^{9-7})) - (5! / (3 - 1))$
3190 := $1 \times (((357 \times 9) - 7) - (5 \times 3)) - 1$
3191 := $1 \times (((357 \times 9) - 7) - (5 \times 3)) \times 1$
3192 := $1 + (((357 \times 9) - 7) - (5 \times 3)) \times 1$
3193 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + 797)) - (5 \times 3) \times 1$
3194 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + 797)) - ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
3195 := $(1 - 3!) \times (((5 + 7) - (9 \times 75)) + (3 + 1)!)$
3196 := $((13 \times 5) \times 7) + 9 \times 7 - (53 - 1)$
3197 := $(1 \times ((357 \times 9) - 7)) - ((5 + 3) + 1)$
3198 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) - 9 \times ((75 + 3!) + 1)$
3199 := $((1 - 35) \times ((7 - 97) - 5)) - 31$
3200 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7!)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 - ((3! - 1)!))$
3201 := $(13 + (5 - 7)) \times (97 \times (5 - (3 - 1)))$
3202 := $(1^3 \times 5) + (79 - 7) + (5^{3!-1})$
3203 := $(1 - 3) - (((5 \times ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5) - (3! - 1))$
3204 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((57 + 9) + 7)) + (5^{3!-1})$
3205 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 - 7) - (9 \times 7))) \times 5 - ((3! \times 1)!)$
3206 := $(1 - 35) - ((7 - 97) \times (5 + 31))$
3207 := $(1 \times (3579 - (7 \times 53))) - 1$
3208 := $(1 \times 3579) - (7 \times (53 \times 1))$
3209 := $(1 \times (3579 - (7 \times 53))) + 1$
3210 := $(1 - 3!) \times (((5 \times ((7 - 9)^7)) - 5) + 3 \times 1)$
3211 := $(1 \times (3^5)) + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times (53 \times 1))$
3212 := $1 + (3^5 + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times (53 \times 1)))$
3213 := $((1 - (3 \times 5!)) - (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5 \times (3!! - 1))$
3214 := $((1 + 35) + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5) + (3!! \times 1)$
3215 := $(1 \times ((357 \times 9) - 7)) + ((5 + 3) + 1)$
3216 := $1 + (((3!! + 5!) + ((797 - 5) \times 3)) - 1)$
3217 := $1 + (((3!! + 5!) + ((797 - 5) \times 3)) \times 1)$
3218 := $((1 \times 357) \times 9) + (7 - 5 + 3 \times 1)$
3219 := $(1^3 \times 57) + ((97 + 5) \times 31)$
3220 := $1 \times (((357 \times 9) + (7 - 5)) + (3! - 1))$
3221 := $1 + (((357 \times 9) + (7 - 5)) + (3! - 1))$
3222 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + 797)) + ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
3223 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + 797)) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
3224 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (79 + (75 / (3 \times 1)))$

- 3225** := $1 \times (3 \times (((5 + 7) \times 97) - (5! - 31)))$
3226 := $1 + (3 \times (((5 + 7) \times 97) - (5! - 31)))$
3227 := $1 - ((3 - (57^{9-7})) + (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
3228 := $((1 \times 3)!) + ((57 \times (97 - 53)) \times 1)$
3229 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) \times 7)) \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) + (3!! + 1)$
3230 := $((1 \times 3)!) + (57 \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) + (3 - 1)$
3231 := $13 + ((57^{9-7}) - ((5 \times 3!) + 1))$
3232 := $(1^3 + (5 + (797 + 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
3233 := $((1^{3!}) \times 57)^{9-7} - ((5 \times 3) + 1)$
3234 := $((13 \times (5 + 7)) - 9) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
3235 := $((1 \times 357) \times 9) + ((7 + (5 \times 3)) \times 1)$
3236 := $1 \times ((357 \times 9) + (7 + ((5 \times 3) + 1)))$
3237 := $((1 - 3) - 5) - (7 - 97) \times ((5!/3) - 1)$
3238 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - 97) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)$
3239 := $1 - ((3^5) - ((7 + (9 - 75))^{3-1}))$
3240 := $(135 \times (79 - 75)) \times 3! \times 1$
3241 := $1 \times 3! + (((57 + 9) \times (7^{5-3})) + 1)$
3242 := $((1 \times 357) \times 9) - (7 - 5) + 31$
3243 := $(1 - ((3! \times 57) + (9 + 7))) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!))$
3244 := $1 \times 3 + (((57^{9-7}) - 5) - (3 \times 1))$
3245 := $(1357 \times (9 - 7)) + 531$
3246 := $(1 + 3)! + ((5! - 7) - ((9 + 7) - (5^{3-1})))$
3247 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) \times ((9 + 75)/3)) - 1$
3248 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) \times ((9 + 75)/3)) \times 1$
3249 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) \times ((9 + 75)/3)) + 1$
3250 := $((1 \times 35) + 7!) - (9 + 7!) \times ((5^3) \times 1)$
3251 := $(1 + (3 + ((57^{9-7}) - 5))) + (3 \times 1)$
3252 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 + 79))) - ((7 - 5!) \times 31)$
3253 := $(13 + (57^{9-7})) - ((5 + 3) + 1)$
3254 := $(13 + (57^{9-7})) - ((5 + 3) \times 1)$
3255 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) \times 7 - ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
3256 := $((1^3 - 5) + ((79 + (7!/5)) \times 3)) - 1$
3257 := $((1^3 - 5) + ((79 + (7!/5)) \times 3)) \times 1$
3258 := $((1^3 - 5) + ((79 + (7!/5)) \times 3)) + 1$
3259 := $(1 + (357 \times 9)) - ((7 - 53) + 1)$
3260 := $(13 + (57^{9-7})) - ((5 - 3) \times 1)$
3261 := $((1 - 35) \times ((7 - 97) - 5)) + 31$
3262 := $(1 \times 3)! - ((5 - 79) \times (75 - 31))$
3263 := $1 + ((3 - 5) \times (7 + (9 \times (7 \times (5 - 31))))))$
3264 := $(13 + (57^{9-7})) + ((5 - 3) \times 1)$
3265 := $(1^{3!}) \times ((57^{9-7}) + ((5 \times 3) + 1))$
3266 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) + (75 - 31)$
3267 := $((1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times (97 + (5 - 3))) \times 1$
3268 := $((1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times (97 + (5 - 3))) + 1$
3269 := $(1 \times ((35 + 79) \times (7 \times 5))) - (3!! + 1)$
3270 := $1 \times (((35 + 79) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!!) \times 1$
3271 := $1 + (((35 + 79) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!!) \times 1$
3272 := $(1 + (((35 + 79) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!!)) + 1$
3273 := $1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) - ((5^3) \times 1))$
3274 := $1 \times 3 + ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - (5! + 3 + 1))$
3275 := $((1 \times 357) \times 9) + ((7 - 5) \times 31)$
3276 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - 7) \times ((9 + 75) \times (3 \times 1))$
3277 := $1 \times 3! + ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - (5! + 3 + 1))$
3278 := $(13 + (5 \times 797)) - ((5! \times 3!) \times 1)$
3279 := $(1 \times 3) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - 3)) \times 1$
3280 := $(1 - 3) - ((57 - ((9 \times 7) \times 53)) \times 1)$
3281 := $(1 \times (35/7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (53 - 1))$
3282 := $(1 - (((3! - 5) - 79) \times (7!/5!))) + (3! - 1)$
3283 := $13 + ((5 \times ((7 + 97) + 5)) \times (3! \times 1))$
3284 := $((1 - 3 + 5)!) - ((7 - 9) \times (((7! - 5!)/3) - 1))$
3285 := $1 \times (((357 \times 9) + (75 - 3)) \times 1)$
3286 := $1 + (((357 \times 9) + (75 - 3)) \times 1)$
3287 := $(13 - 5) - (((7 \times 9) \times 7) - (5! \times 31))$
3288 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times ((79 \times 7) - 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
3289 := $13 \times ((5! + 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))))$
3290 := $(13 + 57) \times ((9 \times 7) - ((5 \times 3) + 1))$
3291 := $(1 + ((3 + (5! + (7 \times 97))) \times 5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)$
3292 := $((1 + (3 + (57^{9-7}))) + (5!/3)) - 1$
3293 := $((1 + (3 + (57^{9-7}))) + (5!/3)) \times 1$
3294 := $((1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) - 5!)) + (3 + 1)!$
3295 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (7975 - ((3! + 1)!))$
3296 := $(1 \times 3)! - (5! - ((7 + (9 \times 75)) \times (3! - 1)))$
3297 := $1357 + ((97 \times 5) \times (3 + 1))$
3298 := $(1 - (35/7)) + ((9 \times (7 + (5! \times 3))) - 1)$
3299 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) + ((75 + 3) - 1)$
3300 := $((13 \times 57) + 9) + 75) \times (3 + 1)$
3301 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + 7) \times 9) + ((7 - 5) - (3 + 1))$

- 3302** := $1 - (((3 + (5 \times 7)) - ((9 \times 7) \times 53)) \times 1)$
3303 := $((1 + (3!! - 57)) - (9 - 7)) \times 5 - (3! + 1)$
3304 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + 7) \times 9) - ((7 - 5) - (3 \times 1))$
3305 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + 7) \times 9) - ((7 - 5) - (3 + 1))$
3306 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7) - (5! - 3)) + 1$
3307 := $(1 + 3) + (((57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - 3) \times 1)$
3308 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times (7 + 5)) \times 31)$
3309 := $(1 - (3 - ((57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3!))) - 1$
3310 := $(1 - (3 - ((57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3!))) \times 1$
3311 := $((1^3 - 5) \times 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (53 \times 1))$
3312 := $((1 \times (3 + (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) + 3) \times 1$
3313 := $((1 \times (3 + (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) + 3) + 1$
3314 := $(1 - ((3! - 5) - (79 \times (7!/5!)))) - (3 + 1)$
3315 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times (7 \times (53 - 1))))$
3316 := $1 - (((3 - 5) - (7 \times 9)) \times (75 - (3 + 1)!))$
3317 := $((13 \times 5) \times (7 + (9 + (7 \times 5)))) + (3 - 1)$
3318 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7) + (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31))))$
3319 := $1 \times ((357 \times 9) + (75 + 31))$
3320 := $((1 + 3!!) + ((57 \times (9 - 7)) - 5)) \times (3 + 1)$
3321 := $((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7!) + (((9 - 7!) - 5!)/(3 \times 1))$
3322 := $(1 - ((3! - 5) - (79 \times (7!/5!)))) + (3 + 1)$
3323 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5! - 7!) + 9) - 7!)/(5 - (3 - 1))$
3324 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31)))$
3325 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) \times ((7 \times 9) - (7 + 531))$
3326 := $((1 - 35) + (7!/(9 - 7))) + (5! \times (3! + 1))$
3327 := $(1 \times 3579) - (7 \times (5 + 31))$
3328 := $((1^3 - (5 + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 53)) \times 1$
3329 := $((1^3 - (5 + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 53)) + 1$
3330 := $((13 - 5) + 7) \times (97 + (5^3 \times 1))$
3331 := $(1 - 3) + ((579 \times 7) - (5! \times 3! \times 1))$
3332 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7 \times ((9 - 7) - (5! \times (3 - 1)))$
3333 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (579 \times 7)) \times (5 - 3! \times 1)$
3334 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) - (7! - ((9 + 7) \times 531))$
3335 := $((1 \times (3^5 + 7)) \times 9) + (7 \times (5 \times 31))$
3336 := $(1 + (3 \times 5 \times (79 - (7!/5!)))) \times (3! \times 1)$
3337 := $(1 - (3 \times 5!)) + ((79 + 75) \times (3 + 1)!)$
3338 := $(1^3 + (5 - 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (53 \times 1))$
3339 := $((1 \times 3!!) - (5 - 7!)) - ((9 + 7) \times (5! + 31))$
3340 := $(1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7!/(9 + 7))) - 5)) - ((3! - 1)!)$
3341 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) - ((7 - (5^3)) - 1)$
3342 := $(1^3) - ((5 - 7) - ((9 \times 7) \times (53 \times 1)))$
3343 := $(1 \times 3! \times 579) - ((7 + (5! + 3)) + 1)$
3344 := $(1 + 3)! + ((5! \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31)))$
3345 := $((1 \times 35)/7) \times (((9 \times 75) - 3!) \times 1)$
3346 := $1 - (((3^5) \times 7) - (9 + 7!)) + ((5 - 3) + 1)$
3347 := $1 - (((3^5) \times 7) - (9 + 7!)) + ((5 - 3) \times 1)$
3348 := $((1 + (35/7)) \times 9) \times ((7 - 5) \times 31)$
3349 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5 + 3! \times 1)$
3350 := $(13 + ((5 - 7) + (9 \times (7 \times 53)))) \times 1$
3351 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((579 + 7) + 531)$
3352 := $((1 - 357) - 9) + (7 \times 531)$
3353 := $((1 + 357) \times 9) + ((7 + (5^3)) - 1)$
3354 := $((1 + 3579) - (75 \times 3)) - 1$
3355 := $((1 + 3579) - (75 \times 3)) \times 1$
3356 := $((1 + 3579) - (75 \times 3)) + 1$
3357 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) - (((7 - (9 - 7)))! + 5!) + 3 \times 1$
3358 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) + (7 \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) \times (3! \times 1)))$
3359 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - 7 \times 9 - (7 \times (5 - 31))$
3360 := $(1 \times (3! \times 5)) \times (7 \times (((97 + 5)/3!) - 1))$
3361 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) + ((7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times (3! + 1))$
3362 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) + (((7 + (9 - 7)) \times 5!) \times 3) - 1$
3363 := $(1 - 35) + ((7 \times 97) \times 5) + 3 - 1$
3364 := $(1^{35}) \times (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - 31)$
3365 := $(1^{35}) + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - 31)$
3366 := $(13 + 5) \times ((79 - 7) + ((5! - 3!) + 1))$
3367 := $(13 \times (5 - (7 - 9))) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3 - 1)$
3368 := $(1^3) + (((57^{9-7}) + 5!) - (3 - 1))$
3369 := $(1 \times ((35 \times (79 + 7)) + (5! \times 3))) - 1$
3370 := $(1 \times ((35 \times (79 + 7)) + (5! \times 3))) \times 1$
3371 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5 + 3! \times 1)$
3372 := $(1 + ((35 \times (79 + 7)) + (5! \times 3))) + 1$
3373 := $(1^3) \times (5 - (7 - ((9 \times 75) \times (3! - 1))))$
3374 := $((1^3 \times 5) \times 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (53 \times 1))$
3375 := $1 \times (((3 + (5 + 7))^{9-7} \times 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
3376 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times (((7 - 9)^{7+5}) - 3!) \times 1$
3377 := $13 + (((57^{9-7}) + (5! - (3! - 1)))$
3378 := $(1 \times (3! \times (579 - 7))) - (53 + 1)$
3379 := $((1^{35}) \times (7 + 97)) + 5 \times 31$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3380 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 \times 7) - 97)) \times (53 - 1) \\
 3381 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 + 9)) \times (7^{5-3} \times 1) \\
 3382 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) - 5) - 3! \times 1 \\
 3383 &:= (1 - (((3 - 57) \times 9) \times 7)) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\
 3384 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7!/9) - ((7 \times 53) + 1)) \\
 3385 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + 7) \times ((9 \times 75) + 3 - 1) \\
 3386 &:= ((1 + 3)! - 5) + (7 \times ((97 \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\
 3387 &:= ((1 - 3!) - 5) + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) + 3 - 1) \\
 3388 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) \times ((7 - 975)/(3 + 1)) \\
 3389 &:= ((1 + 3!!) \times 5) + (((7 - 97) - (5! + 3!)) \times 1) \\
 3390 &:= (1^3) \times (((5! - 7) \times (9 - 7)) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\
 3391 &:= (1^3) + (((5! - 7) \times (9 - 7)) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\
 3392 &:= 1 - (3! - ((5 + (7 \times (97 \times 5)))) - (3 \times 1)) \\
 3393 &:= (1 + (3! + 5)) + (7 \times (((97 \times 5) - 3) + 1)) \\
 3394 &:= (1^3 \times (5 \times (7 \times 97))) + (5 - (3! \times 1)) \\
 3395 &:= (1^3 + (5 \times (7 \times 97))) + (5 - (3! \times 1)) \\
 3396 &:= (1^3 \times (5 \times (7 \times 97))) - (5 - (3! \times 1)) \\
 3397 &:= (1 + (35/7)!) + ((9 \times 7) \times (53 - 1)) \\
 3398 &:= 13 - (((5! - (7 \times 97)) - 5) \times 3!) - 1 \\
 3399 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5+7}) - (97 + (5! \times (3! - 1))) \\
 3400 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - 31) \\
 3401 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) + ((9 \times (7 \times 53)) - 1) \\
 3402 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) \times (((7 + 9) \times 7)/(5 + 3 \times 1)) \\
 3403 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5 \times ((7 + (9 \times 75)) - (3 - 1))) \\
 3404 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times 5) + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) + (3 + 1) \\
 3405 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) + 3 - 1) \\
 3406 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + (5 + 3 - 1)) \\
 3407 &:= (13 + (5 \times (7 \times 97))) - (5/(3! - 1)) \\
 3408 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5 - (7 \times 975))/(3 - 1)) \\
 3409 &:= (13 + (5 \times (7 \times 97))) + (5/(3! - 1)) \\
 3410 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times (97 \times 5)))) + 3 \times 1 \\
 3411 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5 \times (((797 - 5!) + 3) + 1)) \\
 3412 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) - (5! - (3 + 1)) \\
 3413 &:= (1 \times (3! \times ((57 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5))) - (3! + 1) \\
 3414 &:= ((1 \times (3! \times (57 \times (9 - 7)))) \times 5) - (3! \times 1) \\
 3415 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) - 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (53 + 1)) \\
 3416 &:= (1 - (35 \times 7)) \times (((9 - 7) - (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\
 3417 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3)) + 1 \\
 3418 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5! + 7)) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3! \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3419 &:= (1^3 + (5 \times ((7 \times 97) + 5))) - (3 - 1) \\
 3420 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + (5!/(3 + 1))) \\
 3421 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (579 - 7)) - 5) - 3! \times 1 \\
 3422 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) + ((5!/3!) + 1)) \\
 3423 &:= (1 - (((3 - 57) \times 9) \times 7)) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\
 3424 &:= (135 + 79) \times (7 + (5 + 3 + 1)) \\
 3425 &:= ((1 - (35 + 7)) \times (9 - 75)) + (3!! - 1) \\
 3426 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((579 - 7) + 5) - 3! \times 1) \\
 3427 &:= (1^{35}) + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) + 31) \\
 3428 &:= 13 + (5 \times ((7 \times (97 + 5)) - 31)) \\
 3429 &:= 1 + (35 + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - (3 - 1))) \\
 3430 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (579 - 7)) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\
 3431 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (579 - 7)) + (5 - 3! \times 1) \\
 3432 &:= ((1 + 3) + (57 - 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) + 31) \\
 3433 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (579 - 7)) - 5) + 3! \times 1 \\
 3434 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (579 - 7)) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\
 3435 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (((5 + 7) - (9 \times 75)) - (3 + 1)!) \\
 3436 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) + (7 \times ((97 \times 5) + 3 \times 1)) \\
 3437 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 \times (5^{3+1})) \\
 3438 &:= ((1 \times 357) \times 9) + ((75 \times 3) \times 1) \\
 3439 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) + 7) + (9 \times ((7 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))) \\
 3440 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (579 - 7)) + (5 + 3 \times 1) \\
 3441 &:= ((1 + 3!!) \times 5) + (((7! - (9 + 7!)) - (5 \times 31)) \\
 3442 &:= 1 - (35 - (79 \times (75 - 31))) \\
 3443 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + (5! + 3 - 1)) \\
 3444 &:= (((1 \times 3! \times 5) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) \times 5) - 3! \times 1 \\
 3445 &:= (((1 - 3)^{5+7}) - (9 \times 75)) + (3 + 1)! \\
 3446 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + ((5 - 7975)/(3! - 1)) \\
 3447 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 57)) + (9 \times (7 \times (53 - 1))) \\
 3448 &:= 13 - (57 - (97 \times (5 + 31))) \\
 3449 &:= (1^{3!}) - ((5! - (7 + 975)) \times (3 + 1)) \\
 3450 &:= ((1 \times (3!! \times 5)) - ((7 + (9 + 7)) + 5!)) - (3! + 1) \\
 3451 &:= ((1 - 3) - (579 + (7!/5))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\
 3452 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times (7 \times 97))) + (53 + 1) \\
 3453 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7)))! + (9 \times ((7 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))) \\
 3454 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! + (7 - (9 \times 7))) \times (53 + 1)) \\
 3455 &:= (1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7!/(9 + 7))) - 5)) - (3! - 1) \\
 3456 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (5! - ((7! + (9 - 753)) - 1)) \\
 3457 &:= (1 \times (3! \times (((57 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5) + 3!))) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3458 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (579 - 7)) - (5 - 31) \\ 3459 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) + 7!) + (9 - (7! + 5 \times 31)) \\ 3460 &:= (1^3 + 57) + (9 \times (7 \times (53 + 1))) \\ 3461 &:= (1 - (357 - 97)) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3462 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) + 31) \\ 3463 &:= ((1 \times (3! - 5!)) - ((7 + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times 3!))) \times 1 \\ 3464 &:= ((1 \times (3! \times 5)) - ((7 + (9 + 7)) + 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\ 3465 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (((97 + 5) - 3) \times 1) \\ 3466 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 + 7!) - (9 \times 753)) - 1) \\ 3467 &:= 1 \times ((3! \times 579) - (7 \times ((5 - 3) - 1))) \\ 3468 &:= 135 - (7 - ((9 \times (7 \times 53)) + 1)) \\ 3469 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) - ((7 + 9) \times 7)) + (5 - (3 + 1)!) \\ 3470 &:= (1 + (3579 + 7)) - (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\ 3471 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 \times (7 - 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 3472 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (7 \times (((97 + 5)/3!) - 1)) \\ 3473 &:= 1 \times ((3579 - 75) - 31) \\ 3474 &:= (1 + 3579) - (75 + 31) \\ 3475 &:= (1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7!/(9 + 7))) + 5)) + (3! - 1) \\ 3476 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 \times (7 - 5))) + (3 - 1) \\ 3477 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 \times (7 - 5))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 3478 &:= 13 + (((57 \times (9 \times 7)) - 5!) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 3479 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5)^7) + ((9 - 7) + (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\ 3480 &:= (1 \times (357 - 9)) \times (7 + (5 - (3 - 1))) \\ 3481 &:= 1 \times ((3! \times 579) + (7 \times ((5 - 3) - 1))) \\ 3482 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5 - ((7 + (9 - 75))^{3-1})) \\ 3483 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7!/(9 - 7))) + (5! + 3! \times 1) \\ 3484 &:= (1 - 3) + ((579 + (7 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 3485 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (579 - 7)) + (53 \times 1) \\ 3486 &:= (1^3) \times ((579 + (7 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 3487 &:= (1^3) + ((579 + (7 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 3488 &:= (((1 + 3) \times ((5 + 7) + 97)) \times (5 + 3)) \times 1 \\ 3489 &:= (1^{35}) - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 3490 &:= (1 + 3) + ((579 + (7 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 3491 &:= (1 \times 35) - ((7 - 9) \times ((7 + 5)^3 \times 1)) \\ 3492 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) - (7 + ((9 - 7) \times (53 \times 1))) \\ 3493 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 3494 &:= 13 + (5 + (79 \times (75 - 31))) \\ 3495 &:= ((1^3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 97) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 3496 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) - (((7 \times 9) - 7) + (53 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3497 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5!)) - (3! + 1) \\ 3498 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 \times 79) - 7) \times ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\ 3499 &:= (1 \times 3579) - (75 + (3! - 1)) \\ 3500 &:= (1^3 + 5!) + (((7 + 97) + 5) \times 31) \\ 3501 &:= (1 - (3 + 5!)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5 \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 3502 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) \times 7)) - (9 \times ((7 - 5!) + 3 + 1)) \\ 3503 &:= ((1 - 3!) - ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) + 5)) \times 31 \\ 3504 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5! + (7 \times 9)) - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1) \\ 3505 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5)) + ((79 + (7 \times 5)) \times 31) \\ 3506 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times (((97 + 5) - 3) + 1)) \\ 3507 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) - ((7 + 9) \times 7)) - (5 - (3 + 1)!) \\ 3508 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + 5!)) - (3 - 1) \\ 3509 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5)) \times ((7 + ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 3510 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7)) \times 9) \times ((75 + 3) \times 1) \\ 3511 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\ 3512 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + 5!)) + (3 - 1) \\ 3513 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5! \times 7)) - ((9 - 7) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 3514 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7 + 97)) - ((5^3) + 1) \\ 3515 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - ((5! \times 7) \times (9 - 7))) + (5 \times 31) \\ 3516 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 + 79) \times 7)) \times ((5 - (3 - 1)))! \\ 3517 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) + 753) - 1 \\ 3518 &:= 1 \times ((3579 - 7) - (53 + 1)) \\ 3519 &:= 1 + ((3579 - 7) - (53 + 1)) \\ 3520 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 579)) - (7 - 53)) - 1 \\ 3521 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 579)) - (7 - 53)) \times 1 \\ 3522 &:= (1 + (3! \times 579)) - ((7 - 53) - 1) \\ 3523 &:= (1^3 + (579 \times 7)) - 531 \\ 3524 &:= (1 + 3579) - ((7 \times (5 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 3525 &:= (1 - (3 - ((5 \times 79) + 7))) + (5^{3!-1}) \\ 3526 &:= (13 + (5 \times 79)) - (7 - (5^{3!-1})) \\ 3527 &:= (1 + (3 - 5)) + (7 \times ((9 + 75) \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 3528 &:= (13 - 5) \times (7 - (97 - 531)) \\ 3529 &:= (1^3) + (((5 + 79) \times 7) \times ((5 - (3 - 1)))!) \\ 3530 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) - 7) \times ((9 \times 75) + 31) \\ 3531 &:= (13 + (5 - 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 3532 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5! + (7 \times 9)) - (7 \times 531)) \\ 3533 &:= (1 \times 3579) + ((7 - 53) \times 1) \\ 3534 &:= (1 + (3579 + 7)) - (53 \times 1) \\ 3535 &:= (1 \times 3579) - (75 - 31) \end{aligned}$$

- 3536** := $1 + (3579 - (75 - 31))$
3537 := $1 + ((3579 - (7 + 5)) - 31)$
3538 := $(13 + (5 + (7 + 97))) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
3539 := $((1 + (3!! \times 5)) - 7) - ((9 - 7) + (53 \times 1))$
3540 := $((1 - 35) + 79) + (7 \times 5!) \times (3 + 1)$
3541 := $(1^3 + (5! \times 7)) + (9 \times (75 \times (3 + 1)))$
3542 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (579 + (7 + 5))) - (3 + 1)$
3543 := $1 \times (((35 + 7) \times 97) - 531)$
3544 := $1 + (((35 + 7) \times 97) - 531)$
3545 := $((1 \times 3!) - ((5 - 7) + (9 \times 7))) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!!)$
3546 := $(1 \times (3579 + 7)) - (5! / (3 \times 1))$
3547 := $1 + ((3579 + 7) - (5! / (3 \times 1)))$
3548 := $1 + ((3579 - 7) - (5 \times (3! - 1)))$
3549 := $(1 \times 3579) - ((7 \times 5) - (3! - 1))$
3550 := $(13 + (5 + 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + ((5^3) + 1))$
3551 := $(1 \times 3!) - (57 - ((9 - 7) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!!))))$
3552 := $(13 + 579) \times (7 + (5 - 3! \times 1))$
3553 := $((1 + (3!! \times 5)) + 7) - ((9 - 7) + (53 \times 1))$
3554 := $(1^3) \times (((5 \times (7! / 9)) + 753) + 1)$
3555 := $((1^3 \times 57) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 + 31)$
3556 := $((1 + 3) + (5 \times (7! / 9))) + (753 - 1)$
3557 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 \times (7! / 9)) + (753 \times 1))$
3558 := $((1 \times 3!!) + ((579 + 7) - 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)$
3559 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5! - (7 \times (97 + 5))) \times (3! \times 1))$
3560 := $(1 - 357) \times (((9 + 7) + 5) - 31)$
3561 := $(1 \times 3579) + (7 - (5 \times (3! - 1)))$
3562 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) - (7 + ((9 + 7) + (5 \times (3 \times 1))))$
3563 := $(13 - 5) - (79 \times (7 - (53 - 1)))$
3564 := $1 \times ((3579 - (7 + (5 + 3))) \times 1)$
3565 := $1357 + ((97 - 5) \times (3 + 1)!)$
3566 := $(1 + (3!! \times 5)) - ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5 + (3! + 1)))$
3567 := $((1 - 3)^{5+7}) - ((97 - 5!)^{3-1})$
3568 := $((1 \times 35) + (7 \times 97)) \times 5 - (3 - 1)$
3569 := $(1 \times 3579) - ((7 + (5 - 3)) + 1)$
3570 := $((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) - 7 \times (5 + 3 - 1)$
3571 := $(13 \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 - 531)$
3572 := $((1 \times 35) + (7 \times 97)) \times 5 + (3 - 1)$
3573 := $(13 \times ((57 - (9 - 7)) \times 5)) - (3 - 1)$
3574 := $((1 - 3!) - 5) + ((7 + 9) \times ((75 \times 3) - 1))$
3575 := $(13 \times 5) \times (((79 - 75))! + 31)$
3576 := $(1 - (3! \times 5!)) + ((7! + (9 - 753)) - 1)$
3577 := $1 \times (3579 + ((7 - (5 + 3)) - 1))$
3578 := $1 + (3579 + ((7 - (5 + 3)) - 1))$
3579 := $(1 \times (3 + (5! - 7!))) + ((9 + 7) \times 531)$
3580 := $(1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7! / (9 + 7))) - 5)) + ((3! - 1))!$
3581 := $(1 \times ((3!! \times 5) + ((7 - 9) - (7 + 5)))) - (3! - 1)$
3582 := $((1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) + 9) - ((7 \times 5)^{3-1})$
3583 := $((1 \times (3! \times 579)) - 7) + (5! - (3 + 1))$
3584 := $((1 - 3^5) + ((7 + 9) \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)))$
3585 := $((1 + (3!! \times 5)) - (7 - 9)) - (((7 + 5) + 3!) \times 1)$
3586 := $(1 \times (3! + 5)) \times (((7 + (97 + 5)) \times 3) - 1)$
3587 := $(1 \times (((3^5) - 7) - 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
3588 := $((1 + (35 / 7)) + (9 \times 7)) \times (53 - 1)$
3589 := $((1 \times 3^5) + 7) + (9 \times ((7 \times 53) \times 1))$
3590 := $(13 + (57 \times (9 \times 7))) - ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
3591 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) \times ((5 + 3) + 1))$
3592 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 + (7 - 9)))^7 + (5! \times 31)$
3593 := $(1 \times 3579) + ((7 + (5 + 3)) - 1)$
3594 := $1 - (3! - ((57 \times (9 \times 7)) + ((5 + 3) \times 1)))$
3595 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5! + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!)) - (3! - 1))$
3596 := $(1 \times (3!! \times 5)) + (((7^9-7) - (53 \times 1)))$
3597 := $(1 + 3) + ((57 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - (3! + 1)))$
3598 := $1 \times ((3579 - (7 + 5)) + 31)$
3599 := $1 + ((3579 - (7 + 5)) + 31)$
3600 := $1 - ((35 + (79 + 7)) - (5! \times 31))$
3601 := $1 + 35 + ((7 + 9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31))$
3602 := $(1 + ((35 + (7 \times 97)) \times 5)) + 31$
3603 := $((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) - (5 + 3 + 1)$
3604 := $(1 \times (3!! \times 5)) - ((7^9-7) - (53 \times 1))$
3605 := $(1 \times 3! \times 579) + ((7 + (5! + 3)) + 1)$
3606 := $(1^3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!)) + (3!! + 1)$
3607 := $(1 + 3) + (((57 - 9) \times 75) + 3) \times 1$
3608 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
3609 := $(1 \times 3579) + ((7 \times 5) - (3! - 1))$
3610 := $((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) - ((5 - 3) \times 1)$
3611 := $1 \times ((3579 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1))$
3612 := $1 + ((3579 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1))$
3613 := $1 + ((3579 + (7 - 5)) + 31)$

$$\begin{aligned} 3614 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7 + 97)) + (5 - 31) \\ 3615 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) + ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 3616 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) \times 5) + ((7 - (9 - 7)) + (5 + 3! \times 1)) \\ 3617 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((((57 \times 9) \times 7) - 5) + 3!) + 1) \\ 3618 &:= (1^{357} + 9) + ((7 + (5 \times 3!)) + 1) \\ 3619 &:= (1 - 3) + (5 + ((7 + 9) \times ((75 \times 3) + 1))) \\ 3620 &:= ((1 - 35) - (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\ 3621 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) + (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 3622 &:= ((1 \times 3579) + 7) + (5 + 31) \\ 3623 &:= (1 \times 3579) + (75 - 31) \\ 3624 &:= 1 + (3579 + (75 - 31)) \\ 3625 &:= (1 \times 3579) - ((7 - 53) \times 1) \\ 3626 &:= 1 \times ((3579 - 7) + (53 + 1)) \\ 3627 &:= 1 + ((3579 - 7) + (53 + 1)) \\ 3628 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) - (5! / (3! \times 1)) \\ 3629 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) \times 5) - ((7 - 975) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 3630 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 3631 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) - 79) + (7 \times 531) \\ 3632 &:= 1 + ((3! \times 5) + (7 + (((9 + 7) + 5) + 3 \times 1))) \\ 3633 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) + ((7 - 97) + (5! - (3 - 1))) \\ 3634 &:= (13 + 5) - (7 + (97 - (5! \times 31))) \\ 3635 &:= (1 \times (3579 + (7 \times (5 + 3)))) \times 1 \\ 3636 &:= (1 + 3579) + ((7 \times (5 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 3637 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) - (79 \times (7 - (53 \times 1))) \\ 3638 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) \times 5) + (7 + ((9 + 7) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 3639 &:= (((1 + 3^5) + (7 + 9)) \times (7 \times (5 - 3))) - 1 \\ 3640 &:= (1 + (3579 + 7)) + (53 \times 1) \\ 3641 &:= (1 - ((3 - (57 \times (9 \times 7))) - 53)) - 1 \\ 3642 &:= (1 - ((3 - (57 \times (9 \times 7))) - 53)) \times 1 \\ 3643 &:= 1 - (((3 - (57 \times (9 \times 7))) - 53) - 1) \\ 3644 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\ 3645 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) - (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 3646 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times 5) - (7 + (9 \times 7))) + 5!) - (3 + 1) \\ 3647 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) - ((7 \times 9) - (7 \times 531)) \\ 3648 &:= ((13 + 5) + 7) - (97 - (5! \times 31)) \\ 3649 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) - ((79 \times (7 - 53)) + 1) \\ 3650 &:= (1 + (3579 + (75 - 3!))) + 1 \\ 3651 &:= ((1 + 3) - (57 + (9 + 7))) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3652 &:= ((1 + 3)!) - ((5 + (7 \times 9)) + (7! - (5! \times 31))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3653 &:= 13 + ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 \times (7 + 5)) - (3 + 1))) \\ 3654 &:= (((13 \times 5) - 7) / (9 - 7)) \times ((5^3) + 1) \\ 3655 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) \times 5) + ((7 - (9 - 7)) \times (5 + 3! \times 1)) \\ 3656 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5 - 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3657 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) \times 5) + 7 + (975 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 3658 &:= ((1 + 357) - ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) \times 31 \\ 3659 &:= (1 \times 3579) + (75 + (3! - 1)) \\ 3660 &:= ((1 + 3) + 57) \times (((9 \times 7) - 5) + 3 - 1) \\ 3661 &:= 1 - ((3 + (57 - 975)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 3662 &:= (1 \times (3 + 57)) + ((9 - 7) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 3663 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5 \times ((7 \times 97) + (53 \times 1))) \\ 3664 &:= (13 - (57 + 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\ 3665 &:= ((13 \times 57) + (975 \times 3)) - 1 \\ 3666 &:= ((13 \times 57) + (975 \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 3667 &:= ((13 \times 57) + (975 \times 3)) + 1 \\ 3668 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! / (3! \times 1)) \\ 3669 &:= (((1^{357} + 9) \times 7) + (5 \times 3!)) - 1 \\ 3670 &:= (((1^{357} + 9) \times 7) + (5 \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 3671 &:= (((1^{357} + 9) \times 7) + (5 \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 3672 &:= (13 + (57 - (9 - 7))) \times (53 + 1) \\ 3673 &:= 1 - (3! \times ((5 - 79) - (7 + 531))) \\ 3674 &:= ((13 - 5!) + ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) \times (5 + 3! \times 1) \\ 3675 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 79)) - 7) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 3676 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + 7) + ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 3677 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) + 7!) - (((9 + 7) - 5^3) \times 1) \\ 3678 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) + 7!) - (((9 + 7) - 5^3) - 1) \\ 3679 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) - (79 - 7))) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3680 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - 5) + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 3681 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 57) + (((9 \times 7) \times 53) \times 1) \\ 3682 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (579 + (7 \times 5))) - (3 - 1) \\ 3683 &:= ((1 + 3) - 57) + ((9 + 7) + (5! \times 31)) \\ 3684 &:= (((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 - 7) + (5^3))) + 1 \\ 3685 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 + ((7 - 9)^7))) \times 5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 3686 &:= (1 + 3579) + (75 + 31) \\ 3687 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (579 + (7 \times 5))) + 3) \times 1 \\ 3688 &:= ((135 \times 7) + (97 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 3689 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5! - 7)) + ((975 + 3) - 1) \\ 3690 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) + (5 + 3! \times 1)) \\ 3691 &:= (1^3) - ((5! + (7 - 97)) - (5! \times 31)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3692 &:= ((1^{35} \times 7!) / 9) + (7 + (5^{3!-1})) \\
 3693 &:= (1 \times (3!! + 5)) + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times (53 \times 1)) \\
 3694 &:= (1 + 3!!) + (5 + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times (53 \times 1))) \\
 3695 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! + 5) - 3!! \times 1 \\
 3696 &:= (1 + 357) + ((9 \times (7 \times 53)) - 1) \\
 3697 &:= ((1 - (3 + (5 - 7))) + 97) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\
 3698 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 + ((7 - 9)^7))) \times 5)) + (3! + 1) \\
 3699 &:= (13 \times 5) - (79 \times ((7 - 53) \times 1)) \\
 3700 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 \times 3!))) + 1 \\
 3701 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5 + (7 \times ((9 - 7) - 531))) \\
 3702 &:= (((13 \times (5! - 79)) \times 7) - 5) - (3 + 1)! \\
 3703 &:= (1 + (35 + (79 - 7))) + (5 \times (3!! - 1)) \\
 3704 &:= ((1 + (3579 + 7)) + 5!) - (3 \times 1) \\
 3705 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) - ((97 \times (5 + 3)) \times 1)) \\
 3706 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5) + ((7! - (97 \times (5 \times 3))) + 1) \\
 3707 &:= (1^3 + (5 - 7)) - (9 - (7 \times 531)) \\
 3708 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5 + (7 \times (9 - 7))) - (5! \times 31)) \\
 3709 &:= 13 + ((5 + 79) \times (75 - 31)) \\
 3710 &:= (1 + (3579 + 7)) + (5! + 3 \times 1) \\
 3711 &:= (1^3) - ((5 - 7) + (9 - (7 \times 531))) \\
 3712 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7 - (9 - 7))) \times (5 + (3 + 1)!) \\
 3713 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7 - 9) + (7 \times 531)) \\
 3714 &:= (((1 - 35) + 7) / 9) + (7 \times 531) \\
 3715 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (53 \times 1)) \\
 3716 &:= (1 \times (((3 \times 5) - 7) - 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\
 3717 &:= (1^{3579} \times 7) \times 531 \\
 3718 &:= ((1 + 3!!) \times 5) + (7 + ((9 - 7) \times (53 \times 1))) \\
 3719 &:= (1 + 3) + (5 \times ((797 - 53) - 1)) \\
 3720 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7) \times (9 - 7)) \times (5! + 3 + 1) \\
 3721 &:= (((1 + 3) - ((5 \times 7) - 97)) - 5)^{3-1} \\
 3722 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 - 7)) + (9 + (7 \times 531)) \\
 3723 &:= (1 - 3) + (5 \times ((797 - 53) + 1)) \\
 3724 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 - ((7 - 9)^7))) \times (5 + 3 - 1) \\
 3725 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 + (7 - 9))) + 7) + (5! \times 31) \\
 3726 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5!) / (7 + 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\
 3727 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) + ((7 + 9) \times (75 \times (3 \times 1))) \\
 3728 &:= (1 \times (3!! \times 5)) - ((7 - 9)^{7+5-3!+1}) \\
 3729 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5)) \times ((7! / (9 + 7)) + (5! / (3! - 1))) \\
 3730 &:= (1 - 3!) + (5 \times (7 + ((9 + 7) + ((5 + 3!!) - 1))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3731 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5)) \times (7 \times ((9 - 7) + 531)) \\
 3732 &:= 1 \times ((3! - 5) + (7 \times ((9 - 7) + 531))) \\
 3733 &:= 1 + ((3! - 5) + (7 \times ((9 - 7) + 531))) \\
 3734 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 - 79 + (7! / 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\
 3735 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5)! - ((7 - 9) \times 7)) + (5! \times 31) \\
 3736 &:= (1 \times (3!! \times (5 + 7))) + ((9 + 7) + (5! - ((3! + 1)!!)) \\
 3737 &:= 1 \times ((357 \times 9) - (7 - 531)) \\
 3738 &:= 1 + ((357 \times 9) - (7 - 531)) \\
 3739 &:= (((1 \times 3!!) - 5!) \times 7) - ((97 \times 5) - (3 + 1)!) \\
 3740 &:= (1 - (3 \times 57)) \times ((9 - 75) / (3 \times 1)) \\
 3741 &:= ((13 \times (5! - 79)) \times 7) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\
 3742 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7 - ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) \\
 3743 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) + ((79 - 7) \times (53 - 1)) \\
 3744 &:= 13 \times (((5 + 7) + ((97 - 5) \times 3)) \times 1) \\
 3745 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5!) \times 7)) + (975 \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 3746 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5! \times 31)) \\
 3747 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) - ((79 - (7! / 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\
 3748 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (579 - 7!)) + (5 - (3!! + 1)) \\
 3749 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) - 7)) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\
 3750 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) - (5 + 3) - 1 \\
 3751 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) - (5 + 3) \times 1 \\
 3752 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) - (5 + 3) + 1 \\
 3753 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) + (7 + 9 + (7 \times 531)) \\
 3754 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (57 \times (9 - 75))) - (3 \times 1) \\
 3755 &:= (1 + 3579) + (7 \times (5 \times (3! - 1))) \\
 3756 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((579 - 7) + 53) + 1) \\
 3757 &:= 13 \times ((5 + 7) + (((97 - 5) \times 3) + 1)) \\
 3758 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) + ((7 + 97) \times (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\
 3759 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5)) \times (7! - (((9 \times 7) + 5!) \times (3! + 1))) \\
 3760 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) \times ((7! / (9 \times 7)) + 5 \times 31) \\
 3761 &:= (1^3 + 5!) + (((7 + 97) \times 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\
 3762 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times (9 - 7))) \times (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\
 3763 &:= (13 + 5!) + ((7 - 97) + (5! \times 31)) \\
 3764 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + (5! + 7)) + ((9 - 75)^{3-1}) \\
 3765 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - ((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 7))) + 5) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\
 3766 &:= (1^3 \times ((5 - 7) + 9)) \times (7 + 531) \\
 3767 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5 \times (7 - 9))) \times (7 + 531)) \\
 3768 &:= (1 + (((3! \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 + 3))) - 1 \\
 3769 &:= 1 - ((3 \times (5 - 7)) \times (97 + 531))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3770 &:= (1 + (((3! \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 + 3))) + 1 \\ 3771 &:= (1^3) - (5 \times (7 - (9 + (753 - 1)))) \\ 3772 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! - (((57 + 9) + 7) - (5^{3-1})) \\ 3773 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 57) \times (9 - 7))) \times (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 3774 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + ((797 \times 5) + 31) \\ 3775 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) + 5! + (3! + 1) \\ 3776 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) \times (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times 3!)) + 1) \\ 3777 &:= (135 \times (7 + ((9 + 7) + 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 3778 &:= (135 \times (7 + ((9 + 7) + 5))) - (3 - 1) \\ 3779 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 \times (7 - (9 + 753))) \times 1) \\ 3780 &:= ((13 + 57) \times 9) \times (((7 - 5) \times 3) \times 1) \\ 3781 &:= 1 - (35 - (((79 - 7) \times 53) - 1)) \\ 3782 &:= (1 - 35) + (((79 - 7) \times 53) \times 1) \\ 3783 &:= (1^{357}) \times (97 \times ((5!/3) - 1)) \\ 3784 &:= (1^{357}) + (97 \times ((5!/3) - 1)) \\ 3785 &:= 1 + ((35 \times ((7 + 97) + 5)) - 31) \\ 3786 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 57)) + 9) + (7 \times 531) \\ 3787 &:= ((1 - (3!! + (5! - 7!))) + (9 \times (7 - 53))) \times 1 \\ 3788 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) + (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times 531)) \\ 3789 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) + (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times 531)) \\ 3790 &:= (1^{35}) \times (7 + (97 \times ((5!/3) - 1))) \\ 3791 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) - 7) + (97 \times ((5!/3) - 1)) \\ 3792 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + 7)) \times (((9 - 7) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 3793 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 79 + 7)) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3794 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((579 - 7) - (5!/(3 + 1))) \\ 3795 &:= ((1357 - 97) + 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 3796 &:= (13 + (57 + 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\ 3797 &:= ((1 + 3) + (57 + (9 + 7))) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3798 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5+7}) + (((9 \times 7) - (5! \times 3)) - 1) \\ 3799 &:= (1 + 3)! - ((5 \times (7 - (9 + 753))) \times 1) \\ 3800 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 - 7) + 97)) \times (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 3801 &:= (1 - 3!) + (5 + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1)))))) \\ 3802 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (((5 - (7!/9)) + (7! + 5)) + 31) \\ 3803 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times 9) \times 7 - (5!/(3 \times 1)) \\ 3804 &:= ((1 + 3579) + (75 \times 3)) - 1 \\ 3805 &:= ((1 + 3579) + (75 \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 3806 &:= ((1 + 3579) + (75 \times 3)) + 1 \\ 3807 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5 \times 3!! \times 1) \\ 3808 &:= (13 - 5) \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) + 53) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3809 &:= (((1 - 35) + 797) \times 5) - (3! \times 1) \\ 3810 &:= (((1 - 3 \times 5) \times 79) + 7!) - ((5! + 3) + 1) \\ 3811 &:= (((1 - 35) \times 7) + (9 \times (75 \times 3!))) - 1 \\ 3812 &:= (((1 - 35) \times 7) + (9 \times (75 \times 3!))) \times 1 \\ 3813 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 579) - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 3814 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) - 9) - ((7 \times 5)^{3-1}) \\ 3815 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times 79)) - (7! + (5^{3+1})) \\ 3816 &:= ((135 \times 7) + 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - 31) \\ 3817 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + (9 \times ((7 - (5! - 3)) + 1)) \\ 3818 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5!) + 7!) - (975 + (3! + 1)) \\ 3819 &:= 1 \times ((3 + 5!) + ((79 + 75) \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 3820 &:= ((13 - (57 + 9)) + (7!/5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 3821 &:= ((1 + 3!!) \times 5) - (((7 - 97) - (5! + 3!)) \times 1) \\ 3822 &:= 13 \times (((579 + 7)/(5 - 3)) + 1) \\ 3823 &:= ((1 - (3!! - 5)) + (7! + ((97 + 5!) - 3!))) \times 1 \\ 3824 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times ((7 - (97 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 3825 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 7) + ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times 31)) \\ 3826 &:= 13 + (((57 - 9) + 75) \times 31) \\ 3827 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (79 - 7)) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3828 &:= ((13 - 5) + 79) \times (75 - 31) \\ 3829 &:= (1 + 3)! + (5 \times (797 - (5 + 31))) \\ 3830 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5 + 7) + (((9 \times 7) - 5!) - 3!) - 1) \\ 3831 &:= (1 \times 3579) + (7 \times (5 + 31)) \\ 3832 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7!) + (97 \times 5)) + 3!) + 1) \\ 3833 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 + 7) + 97) + (5! \times 31)) \\ 3834 &:= (13 + 5) + (((79 - 7) \times 53) \times 1) \\ 3835 &:= 13 \times (5! - (7 \times ((97 - 5!) - (3 - 1)))) \\ 3836 &:= ((1^3 - 5!) + 7!) - ((97 + 5!) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 3837 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 + 7!) - (97 \times 5)) - 3!) - 1) \\ 3838 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5! + (7 \times 9)) \times 7)) - (5!/(3 + 1)!)) \\ 3839 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times ((79 + 7) \times 5)) - 31 \\ 3840 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7 \times 9)) \times (7 + (53 \times 1)) \\ 3841 &:= ((13 \times 5) - 7) + ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times 31)) \\ 3842 &:= (1 + (35 + (79 + 7))) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3843 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (((7 - (9 - 7)))! + 5!) + 3 \times 1) \\ 3844 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (79 + (7!/5))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 3845 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) - (7 + 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\ 3846 &:= ((1 - 3 + ((57^{9-7}) - 5!)) + 3!) - 1 \\ 3847 &:= (1 - 3 + ((57^{9-7}) - 5!)) + (3! \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3848 &:= ((1 - 3 + ((57^{9-7}) - 5!)) + 3!!) + 1 \\
 3849 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (5! + 7)) + (97 + (5 \times 3!!))) + 1 \\
 3850 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (((7 \times 97) - 5) \times (3! - 1)) \\
 3851 &:= (1 + (35 + ((79 - 7) \times 53))) - 1 \\
 3852 &:= (1 + (35 + ((79 - 7) \times 53))) \times 1 \\
 3853 &:= (1 + (35 + ((79 - 7) \times 53))) + 1 \\
 3854 &:= 1 - (3! + (5! - ((797 \times 5) - 3! \times 1))) \\
 3855 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times 5!) + ((7! + (9 + 7)) + ((5! - 3!!) - 1)) \\
 3856 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5^{7-9+7}) + 5) + 3!! \times 1) \\
 3857 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) + (9 + (7 \times 531)) \\
 3858 &:= (1 \times 3!!) - (((57 + 9) \times 7) - ((5 \times 3!!) \times 1)) \\
 3859 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times (5! + 7)) + ((97 - 5) + 3!!)) - 1 \\
 3860 &:= (1^{31}) - (5! - ((797 \times 5) - 3! \times 1)) \\
 3861 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times 5) - (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\
 3862 &:= 1 + (((3! \times 5) - (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\
 3863 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5 \times 797) - (5! + 3!!))) \times 1 \\
 3864 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5 \times 797) - (5! + 3!!))) + 1 \\
 3865 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5! - ((797 \times 5) - 3! \times 1)) \\
 3866 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) / 5)) - (3! - 1) \\
 3867 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 797) - (5^3)) + 1) \\
 3868 &:= ((1 + 35) \times (7 + 97)) + ((5^3) - 1) \\
 3869 &:= ((135 \times 7) + (975 \times 3)) - 1 \\
 3870 &:= ((135 \times 7) + (975 \times 3)) \times 1 \\
 3871 &:= ((135 \times 7) + (975 \times 3)) + 1 \\
 3872 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5 \times 79))) + ((7! + (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\
 3873 &:= (1^{35}) - ((7 - 975) \times (3 + 1)) \\
 3874 &:= (13 + (5 \times 797)) - ((5^3) - 1) \\
 3875 &:= (1 + ((3!! - ((5 + 7) + 9)) + 75)) \times (3! - 1) \\
 3876 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 797)) - ((5! - 3!) - 1) \\
 3877 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) + (((9 - 7) - 5)^{3+1}) \\
 3878 &:= (1 + 3^5) - (79 \times (7 - (53 \times 1))) \\
 3879 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 579) + ((7! - 5) + 3 - 1) \\
 3880 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times (9 + (7 + 5!))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 3881 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) + ((5! + 3) - 1) \\
 3882 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 + 9)) - ((7 - 5) \times 3) \times 1 \\
 3883 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7 - 5) - (3! + 1)) \\
 3884 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 - 7) + (975 - (3 - 1))) \\
 3885 &:= ((1^3 - 5!) + (7 \times (9 \times 75))) - (3!! + 1) \\
 3886 &:= 1357 + (9 + (7! / ((5 - 3) \times 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3887 &:= ((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7 + (97 \times ((5! / 3) \times 1))) \\
 3888 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 57)) + (97 + 5)) \times (3 + 1)! \\
 3889 &:= ((13 \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)) \times 7) - ((5! - 3!) + 1) \\
 3890 &:= 1 \times ((3!! \times 5) + ((7! / (9 + 7)) - (5 \times (3! - 1)))) \\
 3891 &:= 1 \times (3 \times ((579 - (7 - 5)) + 3!! \times 1)) \\
 3892 &:= 1 + (3 \times ((579 - (7 - 5)) + 3!! \times 1)) \\
 3893 &:= (((1 + 3!!) + (5 - (7! / 9))) + 7) + (5! \times 31) \\
 3894 &:= (1 - 3) - (5! - ((797 \times 5) + 31)) \\
 3895 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 797) - 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\
 3896 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 579) + 7!) + (5 \times 3) - 1 \\
 3897 &:= (1^3) - (5! - ((797 \times 5) + 31)) \\
 3898 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 579) + 7!) + (5 \times 3) + 1 \\
 3899 &:= (1 + (3! + (5 - (79 \times (7 - 5!)))) - ((3! + 1)!) \\
 3900 &:= 1 + 35 + (7 \times ((97 - 5) \times (3! \times 1))) \\
 3901 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times ((79 + 7) \times 5)) + 31 \\
 3902 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 - 7) + (975 \times (3 + 1))) \\
 3903 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7) \times (975 \times (3 - 1))) \\
 3904 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5)) - ((7 \times 9) - ((7 + 5!) \times 31)) \\
 3905 &:= (((1 - 3)^{5+7}) - 9) + (7 \times (5 - 31)) \\
 3906 &:= ((1 + 3) - (57 \times 9)) + (7! - (5^{3+1})) \\
 3907 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 57) \times (9 \times 7))) + (5! + (3! + 1)) \\
 3908 &:= (((1 + 35) \times (7 + 9)) \times 7) - (5^3) + 1 \\
 3909 &:= (((1 - (35 / 7)!) \times 9) + 7!) - (5! / (3 - 1)) \\
 3910 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) + ((7! / 9) \times 7)) + (5 - 31) \\
 3911 &:= (13 + (579 \times 7)) - (5 \times 31) \\
 3912 &:= (1 + ((3 + 57) + (97 + 5))) \times (3 + 1)! \\
 3913 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + 5) - (3! \times 1)) \\
 3914 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7 + 975) \times (3 + 1)) \\
 3915 &:= (13 + (579 \times 7)) - (5! + 31) \\
 3916 &:= ((1 - 35) + (((7! / 9) \times 7) + (5 \times 3!))) \times 1 \\
 3917 &:= (1 - 35) + (((7! / 9) \times 7) + (5 \times 3!)) + 1 \\
 3918 &:= 1 - (3 + (((5 \times 79) - (7! - (5 + 3!))) \times 1)) \\
 3919 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 \times 79) - (7! - (5 + 3!))) - 1) \\
 3920 &:= (1 - 35) + ((797 \times 5) - 31) \\
 3921 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) - ((7 \times (9 \times (7 - 53))) + 1) \\
 3922 &:= (1^3) - (((5 \times 79) - (7! - (5 + 3!))) - 1) \\
 3923 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5+7}) + (9 + (7 \times (5 - 31))) \\
 3924 &:= 1 - (3!! + ((5 \times 79) - (7! - ((5 - 3) \times 1)))) \\
 3925 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) \times (7 - 9)) - (75 \times 31)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3926 &:= (1 - 3) + ((579 \times 7) - (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 3927 &:= 1 + ((3 - (57 + 97)) \times (5 - 31)) \\ 3928 &:= (1^{3!}) + (((579 \times 7) - 5!) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 3929 &:= (((1 \times 357) \times (9 + (7 - 5))) + 3) - 1 \\ 3930 &:= (((1 \times 357) \times (9 + (7 - 5))) + 3) \times 1 \\ 3931 &:= (((1 \times 357) \times (9 + (7 - 5))) + 3) + 1 \\ 3932 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + ((7! + 9) - (7 \times (5^3)))) \times 1 \\ 3933 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 \times 797) - (53 - 1)) \\ 3934 &:= (1^3) + ((5 \times 797) - (53 - 1)) \\ 3935 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5 \times 797))) - (53 \times 1) \\ 3936 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5 \times 797))) - (53 - 1) \\ 3937 &:= 1 - (((3 + 57) \times (9 - 75)) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 3938 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (5 - 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\ 3939 &:= (1^{3!}) \times (((579 \times 7) - 5!) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 3940 &:= 13 + ((579 \times 7) - ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 3941 &:= (13 + (579 \times 7)) - (5^3 \times 1) \\ 3942 &:= (13 - ((5 - 797) \times 5)) - 31 \\ 3943 &:= (13 + 5!) - ((7 - 97) - (5! \times 31)) \\ 3944 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times (9 - 7)) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 3945 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5! - 79) \times (7 - 5!)) - 31) \\ 3946 &:= 13 + (57 \times ((9 + (7 + 53)) \times 1)) \\ 3947 &:= 1 \times (((3! - 5) + 7!) - (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\ 3948 &:= 1 + (((3! - 5) + 7!) - (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\ 3949 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5)) \times (7 + 9 + (7^{5-3+1})) \\ 3950 &:= (1 \times 3579) + (7 \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 3951 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5!) + 7!)) - ((975 - 3) + 1) \\ 3952 &:= (1 + (3579 + (7 \times 53))) + 1 \\ 3953 &:= 1 - (3579 - 7531) \\ 3954 &:= 1 + ((3 + (5 \times 797)) - (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\ 3955 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((5 \times 797) - 53)) - 1 \\ 3956 &:= (1 - (3! - (5 \times 797))) - (5! / (3! - 1)) \\ 3957 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((5 \times 797) - 53)) + 1 \\ 3958 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)))! \times (7 \times 97)) - (5! - (3 + 1)) \\ 3959 &:= (1^3) + (5 - 79 + ((7! / 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 3960 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 7)) + 9) \times (((7 \times 5) - 31)!) \\ 3961 &:= (1 - (3! - (5 \times 797))) - ((5! / 3!) - 1) \\ 3962 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 + (797 \times 5))) - 31 \\ 3963 &:= 13 + (5 \times ((797 - 5) - (3 - 1))) \\ 3964 &:= 1 - (((35/7)! \times 9) - 7!) - ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 3965 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5! + 3 - 1) \\ 3966 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 797)) - ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 3967 &:= ((1 \times 357) \times 9) + (753 + 1) \\ 3968 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5! + 7) - 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 3969 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times (5 - (3 + 1)))) \\ 3970 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 + 975) \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 3971 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 797) - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 3972 &:= (13 + 5) + ((797 \times 5) - 31) \\ 3973 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5! - 7) \times 9) - (7! - (53 + 1))) \\ 3974 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (579 - 7)) - (5! / (3 + 1)) \\ 3975 &:= 1 - (3 + (5 - ((797 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)))) \\ 3976 &:= ((1 + 357) \times 9) + (753 + 1) \\ 3977 &:= (13 + ((57^{9-7} - 5)) + (3!! \times 1)) \\ 3978 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((797 \times 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 3979 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5+7}) - (97 + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 3980 &:= ((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 9)) + 7) + (5! \times 31) \\ 3981 &:= ((1 + (3 - (5 \times 797))) \times (5 - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 3982 &:= (1 - 35) + ((797 \times 5) + 31) \\ 3983 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5 - ((797 \times 5) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 3984 &:= ((1 + (3 - (5 - 797))) \times 5) + (3 + 1) \\ 3985 &:= 1 \times ((3!! + (57^{9-7})) + ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 3986 &:= 1 + ((3!! + (57^{9-7})) + ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 3987 &:= (1 - (3 + (5 \times 797))) \times ((5 - 3!) \times 1) \\ 3988 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 7975)) / (3 - 1) \\ 3989 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - 5!) + (((7 - 97) - 5!) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 3990 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (((9 - 7) \times 53) - 1) \\ 3991 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) / 5)) + ((3! - 1)!) \\ 3992 &:= ((1 \times (35 + 79)) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3 - 1) \\ 3993 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (579 + (753 - 1))) \\ 3994 &:= 1 + (3 \times (579 + (753 - 1))) \\ 3995 &:= (1^3 \times (5 \times 797)) + ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\ 3996 &:= (13 - 5) + ((797 \times 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 3997 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + 5) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 3998 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times ((797 + 5) - 3))) - 1 \\ 3999 &:= (1 - (3! - (5 \times 797))) + ((5! / 3!) - 1) \\ 4000 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times ((797 + 5) - 3))) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Numbers From 4001 to 6000

$$\begin{aligned} 4001 &:= ((1-3!) + (5! - 79)) + (7! - ((5! \times 3) + 1)) & 4039 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5! \times 7) + ((9-7!) + 5 \times 31)) \\ 4002 &:= ((13+579) + 75) \times (3! \times 1) & 4040 &:= ((1+3) - (5! \times 7)) - ((9-7!) + 5 \times 31) \\ 4003 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5+7!)) + ((9 \times (7-5!)) - 31) & 4041 &:= ((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 797))) + 53) \times 1 \\ 4004 &:= (13 - ((5-797) \times 5)) + 31 & 4042 &:= ((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 797))) + 53) + 1 \\ 4005 &:= (((1+3) \times 5) \times (7 \times 9) + 75) \times (3 \times 1) & 4043 &:= ((1^{3!}) + (579 \times 7)) - (5+3! \times 1) \\ 4006 &:= (13+5) + ((797 \times 5) + 3 \times 1) & 4044 &:= (1^3 \times (579 \times 7)) - ((5+3) + 1) \\ 4007 &:= 1 - (((3-579) \times 7) - (5-31)) & 4045 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + 7!) + 9 - (((7!/5) - 3!) \times 1) \\ 4008 &:= (((1+3) - 5) + 7) \times ((9 \times 75) - (3! + 1)) & 4046 &:= (135 \times (7 - (97-5!))) - (3+1) \\ 4009 &:= (1 - (35+7)) + ((9 \times 75) \times (3! \times 1)) & 4047 &:= ((1+3!) \times 579) - (7 - ((5-3) - 1)) \\ 4010 &:= 135 + (((7 - (9-7)) + 5!) \times 31) & 4048 &:= (1+3!) + ((5 \times (797+5)) + 31) \\ 4011 &:= (1+3!) \times (((579-7) + 5) - (3+1)) & 4049 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times ((5+7) - 9) \times 75)) \times 3 - 1 \\ 4012 &:= (1+3) + (((5+797) \times 5) - (3-1)) & 4050 &:= ((1 \times ((3-57) + 9))^{7-5}) \times (3-1) \\ 4013 &:= (1^3) + (((5+797) \times 5) + 3 - 1) & 4051 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times ((5+7) - 9) \times 75)) \times 3 + 1 \\ 4014 &:= 1 \times ((3-5) + ((797 \times 5) + 31)) & 4052 &:= (1+3)! + ((579 \times 7) - (5 \times (3! - 1))) \\ 4015 &:= 1 + ((3-5) + ((797 \times 5) + 31)) & 4053 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((797 \times 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 4016 &:= 1 + (3 + (((5+797) \times 5) + 3 - 1)) & 4054 &:= (135 \times (7 - (97-5!))) + (3+1) \\ 4017 &:= 1 - (((3 - ((5 \times 79) \times (7+5))) + 3!) + 1) & 4055 &:= (1 \times ((3 + (579 \times 7)) - (5-3))) + 1 \\ 4018 &:= 1 - (((3 - ((5 \times 79) \times (7+5))) + 3!) \times 1) & 4056 &:= ((1-3) - (57+97)) \times (5-31) \\ 4019 &:= 1 - ((3-5) - ((797 \times 5) + 31)) & 4057 &:= (13 + (579 \times 7)) - (5+3+1) \\ 4020 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) - ((5 \times ((7-9) \times 7) + 5!)) \times (3! \times 1) & 4058 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) \times 3)) - 1 \\ 4021 &:= ((1-3!) - 5!) + ((7! - ((9 \times 7) + (5! - 3))) \times 1) & 4059 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 4022 &:= (1+3!) + ((5 \times 797) + (5!/(3+1))) & 4060 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) \times 3)) + 1 \\ 4023 &:= 1 \times ((3 + (5 \times 797)) + (5 \times (3! + 1))) & 4061 &:= (1^3 \times (579 \times 7)) + ((5+3) \times 1) \\ 4024 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5 + ((797 \times 5) + 31)) & 4062 &:= (1^3 \times (579 \times 7)) + ((5+3) + 1) \\ 4025 &:= (13 \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) - (7 \times (5 \times (3-1))) & 4063 &:= (1 + (3 \times 579)) + (75 \times 31) \\ 4026 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (((7+97) + 5) + 3!)) + 1 & 4064 &:= 13 + ((579 \times 7) - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 4027 &:= (((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (9-7)) \times 53) - 1 & 4065 &:= ((1^{3!}) + (579 \times 7)) + (5+3! \times 1) \\ 4028 &:= (((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (9-7)) \times 53) \times 1 & 4066 &:= ((1-3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! + (53-1)) \\ 4029 &:= (((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (9-7)) \times 53) + 1 & 4067 &:= ((1^3 + 5) + (7! - 975)) - (3+1) \\ 4030 &:= (13 + ((5+797) \times 5)) + (3! + 1) & 4068 &:= (1 + ((3+579) \times 7)) - ((5+3) - 1) \\ 4031 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((797 \times 5) + 31) & 4069 &:= (13 - (5 - (7! - 975))) - (3+1) \\ 4032 &:= (1+3)! + (((5+797) \times 5) - (3-1)) & 4070 &:= ((1 - (3! + 5!)) + ((7! - (9+7)) + 5)) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 4033 &:= (((1-35) + 7!) - 975) + (3-1) & 4071 &:= (1+3)! + ((579 \times 7) - (((5-3) + 1)!)) \\ 4034 &:= (13+5) + ((797 \times 5) + 31) & 4072 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5)^{79-75}) - (3+1)! \\ 4035 &:= (1-3) + (((5 \times 797) + 53) - 1) & 4073 &:= (1 + ((3+579) \times 7)) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4036 &:= ((1-35) + 7!) - (97 \times (5 \times (3-1))) & 4074 &:= ((1+3)! + (579 \times 7)) - ((5-3) + 1) \\ 4037 &:= (1^3 \times (5 \times 797)) + (53-1) & 4075 &:= (1+3)! - (((5-7) \times (9 \times (75 \times 3))) - 1) \\ 4038 &:= (1 \times ((3+579) \times 7)) - (5+31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4076 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 579) \times 7) + 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 4077 &:= (1 + ((3 + 579) \times 7)) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4078 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! \times 79) - 7!) - (5! \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 4079 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((579 \times 7) + (5 - 3)) \times 1) \\ 4080 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (579 \times 7)) + ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 4081 &:= (1 + (3 + 579)) \times (7 \times (5 - (3 + 1))) \\ 4082 &:= (1 + ((3 + 579) \times 7)) + ((5 + 3) - 1) \\ 4083 &:= (((1 \times (3^5 + 7!)) / 9) \times 7) + (5 - 31) \\ 4084 &:= ((1 + 357) + 9) + (7 \times 531) \\ 4085 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5 \times (79 - (753 - 1))) \\ 4086 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5 \times (79 - (753 - 1))) \\ 4087 &:= 1 - (3 - ((579 \times 7) + (5 + 31))) \\ 4088 &:= (13 - 5) \times (7 - (97 + ((5! - 3!) - 1))) \\ 4089 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 - 7!)) - (975 - 31) \\ 4090 &:= ((1 + 3)^{(5!+7-97)/5}) - (3! \times 1) \\ 4091 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5! \times 7) - ((9 + 7) - (5! - ((3! + 1)!)))) \\ 4092 &:= 13 + (((579 \times 7) - 5) + 31) \\ 4093 &:= (13 + (5 + 7)) - ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4094 &:= 1 - (3 - (((57 - 97) / 5)^{3+1})) \\ 4095 &:= (13 \times ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - 5))) / (3 - 1) \\ 4096 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 79) - 75)^{3! \times 1} \\ 4097 &:= (1 + (35 - 7)) - ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4098 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 7) - (9 - 7)) \times (5! + 3 + 1)) \\ 4099 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((7! - 975) - 31) \\ 4100 &:= (((1 \times 3 + 5)^{7+9-7-5}) + 3) + 1 \\ 4101 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5) + 7!) - (97 + ((5! + 3!) + 1))) \\ 4102 &:= ((1 + 3)^{(5!+7-97)/5}) + (3! \times 1) \\ 4103 &:= (1 \times 3579) - (7 - 531) \\ 4104 &:= (1 + 35) \times (7 + (((9 - 7) \times 53) + 1)) \\ 4105 &:= (135 - 7) + (97 \times ((5! / 3) + 1)) \\ 4106 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7! + (9 \times ((7 - 5!) + 3 - 1))) \\ 4107 &:= (1 + 3!) + (5 + (7 \times (((97 \times 5) - 3) + 1))) \\ 4108 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (((7 - 9)^{7+5}) + 3)) + 1 \\ 4109 &:= (((1 - 3)^{5+7}) + ((9 + 7) - 5)) + (3 - 1) \\ 4110 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 579) \times 7)) + (5 + 31) \\ 4111 &:= (((1^3)^5) \times 79) + ((7! / 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4112 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 \times 797) + 5!) + 3!) + 1 \\ 4113 &:= (1^3) + (((5 \times 797) + 5!) + 3!) + 1 \\ 4114 &:= 1 - (3! - ((5! - (7! - 9753)) \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4115 &:= (1^{3!}) \times (5 \times (797 - (5 - 31))) \\ 4116 &:= (1^{3!}) + (5 \times (797 - (5 - 31))) \\ 4117 &:= (1 \times 3579) + (7 + 531) \\ 4118 &:= ((13 + (579 \times 7)) + 53) - 1 \\ 4119 &:= ((13 + (579 \times 7)) + 53) \times 1 \\ 4120 &:= 13 + ((579 \times 7) + (53 + 1)) \\ 4121 &:= 13 \times (5 + (((79 - 7) + 5!) + ((3! - 1)!))) \\ 4122 &:= (13 + (5 \times 797)) + ((5^3) - 1) \\ 4123 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5!) + 7!)) + (9 \times ((7 - 5!) + (3 + 1)!)) \\ 4124 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! + 7)) + (9 + 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) \times 1) \\ 4125 &:= ((13 + (5 \times 7)) \times 97) - 531 \\ 4126 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) \times 7) - (97 + 5) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 4127 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) + 3! \times 1) \\ 4128 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times 79) - ((7! - 5) / (3! - 1)) \\ 4129 &:= ((1 \times 35) + ((7 - 9)^{7+5})) - (3 - 1) \\ 4130 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) + ((7 + (9 \times 75)) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 4131 &:= ((1 \times 3^5) \times (((7 + 9) - 7) + (5 + 3 \times 1))) \\ 4132 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7 \times 5) + 3 - 1) \\ 4133 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((7 - 9)^{7+5}) + 3 - 1) \\ 4134 &:= (((1^3 + 5) + 79) - 7) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 4135 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 797) + 5!) + (3 + 1)! \\ 4136 &:= (1 + 3) \times (57 + ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\ 4137 &:= (1 + ((3^5) - 7)) + (975 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4138 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5!)) - (7 \times 9)) + (7! - (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 4139 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (57 + (975 + 3))) - 1 \\ 4140 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((7 + 97) \times (5 - 3)) - 1)) \\ 4141 &:= (13 \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) - (7 - (53 \times 1)) \\ 4142 &:= (13 \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) - ((7 - 53) - 1) \\ 4143 &:= ((1 \times (3! + ((5 + 7) + 97))) \times 5) - (3 - 1) \\ 4144 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + ((7 + 9) \times (75 + ((3! - 1)!))) \\ 4145 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5! + (7 \times (97 + 5)))) \times (3! - 1) \\ 4146 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5!) + (((7! - 9) + 75) - 3! \times 1) \\ 4147 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - (7 - (97 - (5! \times 31))) \\ 4148 &:= 1 - (((3! + 5!) \times 7) + (9 - (7! - (5 - (3 \times 1)))))) \\ 4149 &:= (1 + (3^5 + ((7! / 9) \times 7))) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 4150 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5! \times 7) + ((9 - (7! - 5)) + 31)) \\ 4151 &:= (((1 - (3! + (57 - 9))) + 7!) - 5!) - (3 - 1) \\ 4152 &:= (1 - (((3 - 5!) \times 79) + 7!)) - (53 - 1) \\ 4153 &:= 13 + ((5 \times 797) + 5 \times 31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4154 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!/5) + ((797 + 5) \times (3! - 1))) \\ 4155 &:= (((1 - (3!! + (57 - 9))) + 7!) - 5!) + (3 - 1) \\ 4156 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 531)) \\ 4157 &:= ((13 \times ((5! + 7) - (9 \times 7))) \times 5) - (3 \times 1) \\ 4158 &:= (13 + 5) \times (((79 - 7) + 5) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 4159 &:= ((1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) - 9) - (7!/(5 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 4160 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) \times ((7!/9) - (((7 \times 5) + 3!) - 1)) \\ 4161 &:= ((13 \times 5) + (7! - 975)) + 31 \\ 4162 &:= (1 + (3^5 + ((7!/9) \times 7))) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4163 &:= (((1 + 35) + 797) \times 5) - (3 - 1) \\ 4164 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 \times ((97 \times 5) + 31)) \\ 4165 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5! + (7 \times (97 + 5)))) \times (3! - 1) \\ 4166 &:= (1 + (3^5 + ((7!/9) \times 7))) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4167 &:= (((1 + 35) + 797) \times 5) + (3 - 1) \\ 4168 &:= (1 + 3!) + (57 \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 4169 &:= 1 \times ((3!! + ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + (53 + 1)) \\ 4170 &:= 1 + ((3!! + ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + (53 + 1)) \\ 4171 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + ((7! - 9) + 7)) - (5^{3+1}) \\ 4172 &:= (1 \times (35 - 7)) \times (97 + (53 - 1)) \\ 4173 &:= (1 - (3!! + (((5 + 7) + (9 + 7)) + 5!))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 4174 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5 \times 7)) - ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4175 &:= ((13 - (5! \times 7)) - 9) + ((7! - 5) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 4176 &:= (1 + 3)! \times ((57 + (9 \times 7)) + (53 + 1)) \\ 4177 &:= 1 + (((3 - ((5! \times 7) - 9)) + 7!) - (5 + 31)) \\ 4178 &:= (1 - (3! \times (5 + 79))) + (7! - ((5! \times 3) - 1)) \\ 4179 &:= (1 + (3^5 + ((7!/9) \times 7))) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 4180 &:= (1 + (3 - 5!)) + (7! + ((9 - 753) \times 1)) \\ 4181 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5!) + ((7! + (9 - 753)) + 1) \\ 4182 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) + 79) \times (75 - (3 + 1)!) \\ 4183 &:= ((1^3 + (5! + 7!)) - 975) - (3 \times 1) \\ 4184 &:= ((1 + (35 - 7)) - (9 \times (7 - 5!))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 4185 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5!) - (7! - ((975 - 3) + 1))) \\ 4186 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5! + (7! - 975)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4187 &:= (((1 - 3)^{5+7}) + 9) + ((75 + 3!) + 1) \\ 4188 &:= (1^3 \times (5! + 7!)) - (975 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4189 &:= (1^{35}) + (7! - (((9 + (7 \times 5!)) + 3) \times 1)) \\ 4190 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5!))! \times (7 \times 97)) + (5! - (3 + 1))) \\ 4191 &:= 13 + (((579 \times 7) + (5^3)) \times 1) \\ 4192 &:= 13 + ((579 \times 7) + ((5^3) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4193 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - 57) \times 9)) + 7!) - ((5! \times 3) + 1) \\ 4194 &:= ((1 + ((3 - 57) \times 9)) + 7!) - ((5! \times 3) + 1) \\ 4195 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5! + 7) \times (((9 \times 7) - 5!) + (3 + 1)!)) \\ 4196 &:= (((1 - (3!! + 5!)) + ((7! - (9 + 7)) + 5)) + 3!) \times 1 \\ 4197 &:= (((1 - (3!! + 5!)) + ((7! - (9 + 7)) + 5)) + 3!) + 1 \\ 4198 &:= (1 + (3^5 + (797 \times 5))) - 31 \\ 4199 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5 + (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 53) + 1 \\ 4200 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! + 7) - 97) \times 5!)/(3! \times 1) \\ 4201 &:= (((1 - 3!!) - 5!) - ((7 - 9) - 7!)) - ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\ 4202 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (5! - 7!)) + (9 - ((7 - 5 + 3!!) \times 1)) \\ 4203 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + (5 + 7!)) - (97 - (5 - 31)) \\ 4204 &:= ((1 - 3!)^5) - (79 - ((7! - (5 + 3!!)) \times 1)) \\ 4205 &:= ((1 - 3!)^5) - (79 - ((7! - (5 + 3!!)) + 1)) \\ 4206 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - ((5! - 7!) - (9 + 7))) - (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 4207 &:= ((1 - 3!) - 5!) + (7! + ((9 + 7) - ((5 + 3!!) - 1))) \\ 4208 &:= (1 + (((3!! - 5!) + 797) + 5) \times 3) + 1 \\ 4209 &:= (13 + (5 + 7!)) - (((9 + 7) \times 53) + 1) \\ 4210 &:= (1^3 \times 5) \times ((7 - 9) + ((7 \times 5!) + 3 + 1)) \\ 4211 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (((57 + 9) \times 7) + 5!)) + (3!! - 1) \\ 4212 &:= ((13 + 5) + (7! - 9)) - ((7 \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4213 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7! + ((9 - (7 \times 5!)) - (3 + 1))) \\ 4214 &:= (13 - ((5! \times 7) - 9)) + ((7! - 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4215 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 + 7) \times (97 + (5!/3!))) + 1) \\ 4216 &:= (((13 - 5!) + 7) - 9) + (7! + (5 - ((3! \times 1)!))) \\ 4217 &:= (13 + (579 \times 7)) + (5! + 31) \\ 4218 &:= ((1 + (357 \times 9)) + (7!/5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 4219 &:= (1 + (357 \times 9)) + (((7!/5) - 3) \times 1) \\ 4220 &:= (1 + (357 \times 9)) + (((7!/5) - 3) + 1) \\ 4221 &:= (13 + (579 \times 7)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 4222 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 - (9 \times 75)))/(3 - 1) \\ 4223 &:= (1^3 - (5 - 7!)) - (((97 - 5) + 3!!) + 1) \\ 4224 &:= ((1^{3!}) + 5!) + (((7! - (97 + 5!)) - 3!!) \times 1) \\ 4225 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5!))! + 7) \times (975/(3 \times 1))) \\ 4226 &:= ((1 + (357 \times 9)) + (7!/5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 4227 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7!) + ((97 - 5) + 3!!)) - 1) \\ 4228 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - ((5 - 7!) - (9 \times 7))) - (5! + 31) \\ 4229 &:= 1 \times (((((3 + 5) \times 7) + 9)^{7-5}) + 3 + 1) \\ 4230 &:= 1 + (((((3 + 5) \times 7) + 9)^{7-5}) + 3 + 1) \\ 4231 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5!)) + (7! - 97)) - (5! + (3!! - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 4232** := $((1 + 3) \times (5 - 7)) \times ((9 - 7) - 531)$
4233 := $(13 \times 57) + (97 \times (5 + 31))$
4234 := $(1 \times (3 - ((5 + 79) - (7! - (5 + 3!)))) \times 1$
4235 := $(1 - 3 + 57) \times ((9 + (7 - 5)) \times (3! + 1))$
4236 := $(1 - (3^5)) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - (5^{3+1})))$
4237 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + ((7! - 97) - ((5! \times 3!) + 1))$
4238 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79)) - ((7 + 5) - ((3! + 1)!))$
4239 := $(1 \times ((3! \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) \times ((5 + 3) + 1)$
4240 := $((1 + (((3! + 5!) - (7 - (9 + 7))) \times 5)) - 3!) \times 1$
4241 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + 7! - (5 + 3 + 1)$
4242 := $(1 - (35 - (7! - (9 + (7 \times 5)))) - ((3! \times 1)!)$
4243 := $((1 - (3 + (5! \times 7))) + (9 + 7!)) + (5 + 31)$
4244 := $((1 - 35) + 7!) - ((9 + 753) \times 1)$
4245 := $((1 - 35) + 7!) - ((9 + 753) - 1)$
4246 := $1 \times ((3! \times (5! + (7 \times (9 + 75)))) - (3 - 1))$
4247 := $1 + ((3! \times (5! + (7 \times (9 + 75)))) - (3 - 1))$
4248 := $(1 + ((3! \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) \times ((5 + 3) + 1)$
4249 := $1 \times (((((3 + 5) \times 7) + 9)^{7-5}) + (3 + 1)!)$
4250 := $1 + (((((3 + 5) \times 7) + 9)^{7-5}) + (3 + 1)!)$
4251 := $1 + ((3! \times (5! + (7 \times (9 + 75)))) + 3 - 1)$
4252 := $((((1 \times 3) - (57 + 9)) + 7!) - 5) - ((3! \times 1)!)$
4253 := $((((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + 7!) + 5) - (3 - 1)$
4254 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) - (797 - (((5 + 3) - 1)!))$
4255 := $((1 - (3 \times 5!)) \times 7) + (9 \times (753 - 1))$
4256 := $(13 - ((5 + 797) - 5)) + ((3! + 1)!)$
4257 := $((((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + 7!) + 5) + (3 - 1)$
4258 := $(1 + 357) + (975 \times (3 + 1))$
4259 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + 7! + (5 + 3 + 1)$
4260 := $(1 + (3^5 + (797 \times 5))) + 31$
4261 := $((1 \times (3! - 5!)) \times 7) - ((9 \times 7) - (5^3)) - 1$
4262 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 5) - 79) + (7! + 5))) - (3! - 1)$
4263 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) + (7!/9)) + (7 \times 531)$
4264 := $((1 - 3!) - 5!) + (7! + ((9 + 7) + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
4265 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 7!)) - (97 \times ((5 + 3) \times 1))$
4266 := $((1 + 3) + (5 + (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times (53 + 1)$
4267 := $((1^{3!}) \times (((5! - 7) + 9) \times 7)) \times 5 - (3 \times 1)$
4268 := $(1^3) \times (((5 + (7! + (9 \times 7))) - 5!) - (3! \times 1))$
4269 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + (7! - (9 + (7 \times 5))) - 3! \times 1$
4270 := $((1 - 3) - (5 - 7!)) - ((9 + 753) + 1)$
4271 := $((1 - 3) - (5 - 7!)) - ((9 + 753) \times 1)$
4272 := $((13 + 5) + 7!) + ((9 - 75) - (3! \times 1))$
4273 := $((1 - 3) - ((5! - 79) - 7!)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1)$
4274 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7!)) - ((9 + 7) + 5) - 31$
4275 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5! \times 7) - (((9 \times 7) + 5) + ((3! + 1)!))$
4276 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7! - 9) - (753 \times 1))$
4277 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) \times ((7 + 97) + (5 - (3! \times 1)))$
4278 := $(1 + (3 - 5)) + ((7! - 9) - (753 - 1))$
4279 := $((1^{35} \times 7!) - 9) - (753 - 1)$
4280 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) - (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
4281 := $(1 - 3 + (5 + ((7! - 9) - 753))) \times 1$
4282 := $1 - (((3 \times 5) - 7!) - ((9 - 753) \times 1))$
4283 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + 7! - ((9 + 7) - 5) - (3! + 1)$
4284 := $((1 - (35/7)) \times 9) \times ((7 - 5!) - 3! \times 1)$
4285 := $(135 \times 7) + ((9 \times (7 \times 53)) + 1)$
4286 := $(1 - 35) - ((7! - (9 + 7!)) \times (5! \times (3 + 1)))$
4287 := $((1 \times (3! \times 5)) + (7 + (9 \times 75))) + (3! - 1)$
4288 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7!)) - 9 + (7 - (5 + 31))$
4289 := $((1 - (3 + 5)) + 7!) + ((9 - 753) \times 1)$
4290 := $13 \times (5! + (7! / ((9 + (7 + (5 + 3))) \times 1)))$
4291 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 \times 79) - (7! - (5! \times 3))) \times 1)$
4292 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5 + 7!) + (9 - (7 + 5)))) - 31$
4293 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7! - 9)) - (753 \times 1)$
4294 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7! - 9)) - (753 - 1)$
4295 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times ((7! + (9 - 753)) - 1)$
4296 := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) + ((9 \times 75) \times 3!) + 1$
4297 := $((1^{35} + 7!) + (9 - (753 \times 1)))$
4298 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5 + 7!) - ((9 - (7 + 5)) + 31))$
4299 := $((13 - 5) \times 79) \times 7 - ((5^3) \times 1)$
4300 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) + ((7! + (9 - 753)) + 1)$
4301 := $((1 + 3!)! - (((5 - 7) + ((9 + 7) + 5)) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
4302 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + (9 - ((7 \times 5) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
4303 := $((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + 9 - (7! / (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
4304 := $(1^3 + ((5 - 7) + 9)) \times (7 + 531)$
4305 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 7)) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1))$
4306 := $(1 \times 3!) + (5 + ((7! + (9 - 753)) - 1))$
4307 := $(1 + (3579 + 7)) + (5! \times 3! \times 1)$
4308 := $(1 \times (3! \times (5 + (7 \times (97 + 5)))) - (3! \times 1)$
4309 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) + 7!) - (9 + 7) - (5! + (3! + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4310 &:= ((1 - (3!! + 5!)) + ((7! - (9 + 7)) + 5)) + ((3! - 1))! & 4349 &:= ((13 - 579) + (7! - (5^3))) \times 1 \\
 4311 &:= (1 - (35/7)) - (9 - (7! + ((5 - 3!!) - 1))) & 4350 &:= ((13 - 579) + (7! - (5^3))) + 1 \\
 4312 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5) + (7! + (9 - 753))) + 1) & 4351 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7!/9) - 7!)) - (5! + 3 - 1) \\
 4313 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5) + (7! + (9 - 753))) + 1) & 4352 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5!)) + (7! - (97 - 5))) - (3!! \times 1) \\
 4314 &:= (((1 \times (3!!/5)) \times ((7 - 97) + 5!)) - 3!) \times 1 & 4353 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) - (7 \times ((97 - (5! \times 3!)) + 1)) \\
 4315 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7! - ((9 - 7) + 5))) - (3!! - 1) & 4354 &:= 1 + 35 + (7! - (97 + (5^{3+1}))) \\
 4316 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 57) + (9 - 7)) \times (53 - 1) & 4355 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7!/9) - 7!)) - (5! - (3 - 1)) \\
 4317 &:= (1^3) \times (((((5! \times 79) - 7!) - 5!) - 3) \times 1) & 4356 &:= (13 - (5 + 7)) \times ((9 - 75)^{3-1}) \\
 4318 &:= (1^3) + (((((5! \times 79) - 7!) - 5!) - 3) \times 1) & 4357 &:= (13 - (5 + 7)) + ((9 - 75)^{3-1}) \\
 4319 &:= (((1^3)^5 7) \times ((9 - (7 - 5)))!) - (3!! + 1) & 4358 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) \times 7) - (9 \times 75) + ((3! + 1))! \\
 4320 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) - (5 - (3 \times 1))) & 4359 &:= 1 + (((3 - 5) - (7 \times (97 - (5! \times 3!)))) - 1) \\
 4321 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times (97 + 5))) \times (3! \times 1)) & 4360 &:= (1 + (3 - 5)) - (7 \times ((97 - (5! \times 3!)) \times 1)) \\
 4322 &:= ((1^{3!}) - 5) - ((7 \times (97 + 5)) - ((3! + 1))!) & 4361 &:= ((1 \times 35)/7) + ((9 - 75)^{3-1}) \\
 4323 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5!)) + ((7! + (9 - 7)) - (5! \times (3 \times 1))) & 4362 &:= ((1 - 35) \times ((7! - (9 + 7!)) - 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\
 4324 &:= 1 \times (((3! + ((5! \times (7 \times 9))/7)) - 5) \times (3 + 1)) & 4363 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) - (7 \times ((97 - (5! \times 3!)) + 1)) \\
 4325 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5) + ((7! + (9 - 753)) - 1) & 4364 &:= (1^{35}) + (7 + ((9 - 75)^{3-1})) \\
 4326 &:= 135 + (7! - (((9 + 7) \times 53) + 1)) & 4365 &:= ((1 + (3! - (5! - 7))) + 9) \times (7 - (53 - 1)) \\
 4327 &:= (1 - (3!! - 57)) + ((9 + 7!) - (5!/(3 - 1))) & 4366 &:= ((1 \times (3!! \times (5 + 7))) + (97 - 5))/(3 - 1) \\
 4328 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) - (7 \times 5!))) + ((3! + 1))! & 4367 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + ((7! + (9 + (7 \times 5))) - 3!! \times 1) \\
 4329 &:= ((1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) + 7!) - (5! \times (3! + 1)) & 4368 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times (9 + ((75 + 3!) + 1)) \\
 4330 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! + (7!/(9 + 7)))) \times (5 + (3! - 1)) & 4369 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + ((9 \times (7 \times 53)) - 1) \\
 4331 &:= (1 \times 3579) + (753 - 1) & 4370 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (7 + ((9 \times (7 \times 53)) \times 1)) \\
 4332 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((57^{9-7})/(5 - (3 - 1))) & 4371 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (579 - 7!)) - (5! - (3 + 1))! \\
 4333 &:= (1 \times 3579) + (753 + 1) & 4372 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7!) - ((9 \times 75) - (3! + 1)) \\
 4334 &:= 1 + (3579 + (753 + 1)) & 4373 &:= (1 + 3) - (5! - ((79 - (7 + 5))^{3-1})) \\
 4335 &:= (1 + (3!! \times 5)) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) - (5 + ((3! \times 1))!)) & 4374 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) - (((7 - (9 + 7)) - 5!) \times (3! \times 1))) \\
 4336 &:= ((13 - 5!) + 7!) + ((9 - (7 - (5! - 3!!))) + 1) & 4375 &:= ((1^3 - (5 - (7! + (9 \times 7)))) - 5) - (3!! - 1) \\
 4337 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + 7!) - ((9 \times ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) + 1) & 4376 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) + (7! - ((9 \times 75) - (3 \times 1))) \\
 4338 &:= 1 \times (((35/7) + 9) + (7! + (5 - 3!!))) - 1 & 4377 &:= (1357 + (97 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\
 4339 &:= 1 - (((3!! + (57 \times 9)) - 7!) - 531) & 4378 &:= ((1357 + (97 + 5)) \times 3) + 1 \\
 4340 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5!) + (7! - 97)) - (5! \times 3!)) - 1 & 4379 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7) + 975/(3 - 1) \\
 4341 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7! + 5) - 3!! \times 1) & 4380 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5)) \times 3) \times 1 \\
 4342 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7!) + ((9 + 7) + (5 - (3!! - 1))) & 4381 &:= 13 \times (((5 + 79) \times (7 + 5))/3) + 1 \\
 4343 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7 + 9 + ((7! + 5) - 3!!))) + 1 & 4382 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + (7! + (9 \times 7)))) - ((5 + 3!!) + 1) \\
 4344 &:= (((1 + 3) - (5 - 79)) + (7!/5)) \times (3 + 1) & 4383 &:= (1^3 - (5 - (7! + (9 \times 7)))) + ((5 - 3!!) - 1) \\
 4345 &:= 1 - (((3 + (5 + (7 \times 9))) - 7!) + (5^{3+1})) & 4384 &:= (1 \times 35) - (7 - ((9 - 75)^{3-1})) \\
 4346 &:= ((1 + 35) + ((7! - 9) - 7)) + (5 - (3!! - 1)) & 4385 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7 \times 97) + (5! \times 31)) \\
 4347 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5) + 7!) - (((97 - 5) + 3!!) + 1) & 4386 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7!) - ((9 - 75) + ((3! \times 1))!) \\
 4348 &:= ((13 - 579) + (7! - (5^3))) - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4387 &:= (((((1-3)-57) \times 9) + 7!) - 5!) - (3-1) \\ 4388 &:= ((1^{3!} \times 5) + ((7! + (9 \times 7)) - (5! \times (3! \times 1)))) \\ 4389 &:= 1 \times (((3+5) \times 79) \times 7) - (5 \times (3! + 1)) \\ 4390 &:= 1 + (((3+5) \times 79) \times 7) - (5 \times (3! + 1)) \\ 4391 &:= (((1 - (3!! + (57 - 9))) + 7!) + 5!) - (3 - 1) \\ 4392 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5 + 79) + (75 + (3 + 1)!)) \\ 4393 &:= ((1 + ((3 + 5) - 7)) \times 9) + (7 \times (5^{3+1})) \\ 4394 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5+7}) - (((9 \times 7) - (5! \times 3)) - 1) \\ 4395 &:= (((1 - (3!! + (57 - 9))) + 7!) + 5!) + (3 - 1) \\ 4396 &:= 1 - ((3!! + (5! - ((79 + 7!) + (5! - 3)))) + 1) \\ 4397 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 + 79) + (7! - (5 + 3!!)))) \times 1 \\ 4398 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 7) + ((9 - 75)^{3-1}) \\ 4399 &:= ((1^{3!} + 5!) + ((7! - 9) - (753 \times 1))) \\ 4400 &:= ((1 - 3!) + 5!) + (((7 \times (97 + 5)) \times 3!) + 1) \\ 4401 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) - ((5 \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) + 5!)) - 31) \\ 4402 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5 + 79)) + 7!) - (((5 - (3 - 1)))!) \\ 4403 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 + (((7 - 9)^7) \times 5)) + ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 4404 &:= 1 \times ((3! + 5!) + ((7! - 9) - (753 \times 1))) \\ 4405 &:= 1 + ((3! + 5!) + ((7! - 9) - (753 \times 1))) \\ 4406 &:= (1^{35}) + (79 + ((7! + 5) - (3!! - 1))) \\ 4407 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) + ((7! - 9) - (7 + (5^{3+1}))) \\ 4408 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times (9 \times (7 - 5))) - (3 - 1) \\ 4409 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 + 7) + 5) \times 3!)) - 1 \\ 4410 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times (((9 - 7) + (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 4411 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 + 7) + 5) \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 4412 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times (9 \times (7 - 5))) + (3 - 1) \\ 4413 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7!/9) - 7!)) - (5!/(3 - 1)) \\ 4414 &:= (1 - (3 - 5!)) + (7! + ((9 - 753) \times 1)) \\ 4415 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5 + (7 - 97)) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 4416 &:= (1^3 \times (5! + 7!)) + ((9 - 753) \times 1) \\ 4417 &:= ((1 - 35) - (7 \times ((9 + 75) - 3!))) - 1 \\ 4418 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! + (7! + (9 - 753)))) - 1 \\ 4419 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! + (7! + (9 - 753)))) \times 1 \\ 4420 &:= ((13 - 5) + (7! - 97)) - 531 \\ 4421 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) + 7!) + ((97 - 5) - 3!)) + 1 \\ 4422 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) + 7!) + ((97 - 5) - 3!)) + 1 \\ 4423 &:= (1 - (3^5 + ((7 + 9) - 7!))) - ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\ 4424 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5) + 7!) + (97 + ((5 - 3!!) + 1)) \\ 4425 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) \times 79)) + ((7! + (5 \times 3)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4426 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5!)) + ((7! - (9 + 7)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 4427 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 + 7)) \times ((9 + (75 \times 3)) - 1) \\ 4428 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 + 79) - 7!)) - 531 \\ 4429 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times 79) - (7! + ((5 + 3!) \times 1)) \\ 4430 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (((7! - 975) + 3!) - 1) \\ 4431 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 + 7) \times 97) - 531) \\ 4432 &:= (13 - 5) \times (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!) \times 1 \\ 4433 &:= ((13 - 5) \times (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!)) + 1 \\ 4434 &:= (((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + 7) + 5) \times (3 - 1) \\ 4435 &:= (1 \times (3! + ((5! + 7!) - ((9 + 7) - 5)))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 4436 &:= (((1 \times (35/7)) - 9) + (7! + 5!)) - 3!! \times 1 \\ 4437 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) + (5 + (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 4438 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) + (((7! + 97) + 5) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 4439 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5^3))) - 1 \\ 4440 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5^3))) \times 1 \\ 4441 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5^3))) + 1 \\ 4442 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5!) + ((7! - (9 - 7)) - (5! \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 4443 &:= 1 \times ((3 - (5! - 7!)) - (((9 + 7) \times 5) \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 4444 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! / 5!) + (7! - (9 - 7))) + (5! - 3!! \times 1) \\ 4445 &:= (1 \times (35 + 7!)) - ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 4446 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + (7 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 4447 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7 \times 9) + (7 \times (5^{3+1}))) \\ 4448 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 - ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 4449 &:= 1 - (3!! - (5 + (7! + ((97 - 5) + 31)))) \\ 4450 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 579) - ((7 \times (5 - 3!)) \times 1) \\ 4451 &:= 1 - ((3! - ((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7))) - (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 4452 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5!) + (7 + 975)) \times (3! \times 1) \\ 4453 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5! - (7 + 975))) + 3!)) \times 1 \\ 4454 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (((7! + 9) + 7) - (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 4455 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (((5 - 7!) + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 4456 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + 5!) + (7! + ((9 + 7) + (5 - (3! \times 1)))) \\ 4457 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) + ((79 - (7 + 5))^{3-1}) \\ 4458 &:= ((13 - 5) \times ((79 \times 7) + 5)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 4459 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5) \times 79) \times 7)) + (5 \times (3! + 1)) \\ 4460 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (7 - 9)) + (7!/5) \times (3! - 1) \\ 4461 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7 \times (97 + 531)) \\ 4462 &:= ((1 - 35) - (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 - 53) \times 1) \\ 4463 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + 7) + ((9 + 7) + (5! \times (3! + 1))) \\ 4464 &:= (135 + (7 + 9 + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4465 &:= ((13 - 579) + ((7! - 5) - 3)) - 1 \\ 4466 &:= ((13 - 579) + ((7! - 5) - 3)) \times 1 \\ 4467 &:= (1 + 3) - (579 - ((7! + 5) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 4468 &:= (1 + 3!) - (((57 - 9) - 7!) + 531) \\ 4469 &:= 1 - ((3!! - (((5 + 7) + (9 + 7)) + 5!)) - ((3! + 1)!!) \\ 4470 &:= (1^3 + 5) \times ((797 - 53) + 1) \\ 4471 &:= 1 - ((3! + 579) - (7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 4472 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) - (7 \times ((9 + 75) - 3!! \times 1)) \\ 4473 &:= ((1 + 3) - 579) + ((7! + 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 4474 &:= 1 + (((((3 + 5) \times 7) \times 9) - 7) \times (5 + 3 + 1)) \\ 4475 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + 5!) - (79 + (7 - (5! \times 31))) \\ 4476 &:= (((1 \times 35) / 7)!) + ((9 - 75)^{3-1}) \\ 4477 &:= 1 - (3! \times (((5 - 7) + 9) - 753) \times 1) \\ 4478 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((79 + 7!) - (5! \times (3 + 1)!!) \\ 4479 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5))!) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 - (3 + 1))) \\ 4480 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 \times (7 + 97)) + (5! \times (3! - 1))) \\ 4481 &:= 13 - (579 - (7 + (((5 + 3) - 1)!!)) \\ 4482 &:= ((1 - (3!! - 57)) - (9 + (7 - 5!))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 4483 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) + ((79 + 7) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 4484 &:= (1 + (3! + 5)) + ((79 + 7) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 4485 &:= 13 \times ((5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 75)) / (3 - 1)) \\ 4486 &:= (1 + (3! - 57)) + ((9 \times (7! / 5)) / (3 - 1)) \\ 4487 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! + 79)) + (7! - ((5! \times 3) + 1)) \\ 4488 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (5 + 7)) \times ((9 - 75) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4489 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) \times 79) + (7! + 5) - (3 \times 1) \\ 4490 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7!) - (9 \times ((7 + 53) \times 1)) \\ 4491 &:= (13 \times ((57 - 9) \times 7)) + (5! + 3 \times 1) \\ 4492 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + 97) - 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 4493 &:= (13 - 579) + ((7! - 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 4494 &:= 1 \times ((35 + 7) \times ((9 - 7) \times 53) + 1)) \\ 4495 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 57) + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 31) \\ 4496 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 57) + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 31) \\ 4497 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5! \times 79) - (7! - (53 \times 1))) \\ 4498 &:= ((1 + 3)!) - ((579 - 7) - (5! / (3 + 1))) \\ 4499 &:= (1^3 - ((57 \times 9) - 7!)) - (5 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 4500 &:= (1^3 + 5) \times (7 - ((9 - 753) + 1)) \\ 4501 &:= (1 - 35) + (((7 \times 9) \times (75 - 3)) - 1) \\ 4502 &:= ((1^3 \times ((5 - 7) + 9))!) - (7 + 531) \\ 4503 &:= (1^3 - 5) + ((7! - (9 - 7)) - 531) \\ 4504 &:= ((1 + 3)! - 579) + (7! - (5 - (3 + 1)!!) \\ 4505 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) + (79 + 7)) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 4506 &:= (1 - ((3 - 57) \times (9 + 75))) - 31 \\ 4507 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 79) + (7 + 5)) + 3!!)) - 1 \\ 4508 &:= (1 - ((3 + 57) \times 9)) + (7! + ((5 + 3) - 1)) \\ 4509 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 79) + (7 + 5)) + 3!!)) + 1 \\ 4510 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7) \times 9) + (7 \times (5^{3+1})) \\ 4511 &:= (((1 - 3) - (57 \times 9)) + 7!) - ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 4512 &:= 1 \times ((3 - (5 \times 7)) \times (9 - (75 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 4513 &:= 13 - ((5 \times (7 - 97)) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 4514 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 \times 7) + 9) - 7!) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4515 &:= ((1 - 3!) - ((5 \times 79) - (7! - (5^3)))) \times 1 \\ 4516 &:= (1^3 \times 5!) + (7 \times (97 + 531)) \\ 4517 &:= 1 - ((3! + (5 \times 79)) - (((7! - 5!) - 3) \times 1)) \\ 4518 &:= 1 - (((3 - 57) / 9) \times 753) + 1) \\ 4519 &:= ((13 - 57) \times 9) + (7! - ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 4520 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + ((7! - 9) - (7 \times 5))) - 3!! \times 1 \\ 4521 &:= (1 + 3)! - (((57 \times 9) - 7!) + (5 \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 4522 &:= (1 - (3! + (5 \times 79))) + ((7! - 5!) + 3 - 1) \\ 4523 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) \times 79) + (7! + (5 + 31)) \\ 4524 &:= 13 \times (((5 \times 79) + (7 - 53)) - 1) \\ 4525 &:= 13 + (((5 + 7) - 9)! \times (753 - 1)) \\ 4526 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - (5 - 7!)) + ((97 + 5!) - (3! + 1)) \\ 4527 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + 5!) + ((7! + ((9 + 7) \times 5)) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 4528 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (((5 + 79) + (7! + 5!)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 4529 &:= (1 + 3)! - (((5 + 7) - 97) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 4530 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - ((5 - 7!) - (9 \times 7))) + (5! + 31) \\ 4531 &:= (13 - ((57 \times 9) - 7!)) - ((5 + 3) + 1) \\ 4532 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - (57 \times 9)) + 7!) - (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 4533 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7! / 9) - 7!)) + (5! / (3 - 1)) \\ 4534 &:= 1 + (3 \times ((57 + ((97 \times 5) \times 3)) - 1)) \\ 4535 &:= (((13 + 57) \times 9) \times 7) + (5 + ((3! - 1)!!) \\ 4536 &:= ((1 \times 3! + 57) + 9) \times (7 \times (5 + 3 + 1)) \\ 4537 &:= ((1 + 3!) - ((5 \times 79) - 7!)) - ((5! - 3!) + 1) \\ 4538 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) + ((7! - 9) - ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\ 4539 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((57 \times 9) - (7! + (5 + 3 + 1))) \\ 4540 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) \times (((7 - 97) \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 4541 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) + 7!) + 97 - ((5! + 3!!) - 1) \\ 4542 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - (57 \times 9)) + 7!) + 5) + (3 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4543 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5! - (7 \times (9 - (7 + 531)))) \\ 4544 &:= (((((1 \times 3) - 5)^7) - 9) + 7!) - ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\ 4545 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 + 9)) + (7 \times 5!)) \times (3! - 1) \\ 4546 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7!)) - (97 \times 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 4547 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 7!) + (97 - (5^{3+1})) \\ 4548 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5!) + 79)) + (7! - (53 + 1)) \\ 4549 &:= (1 + (((3 + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) + (5^3))) - 1 \\ 4550 &:= 13 - ((57 \times 9) - (7! + ((5 + 3!) - 1))) \\ 4551 &:= (1 + (((3 + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) + (5^3))) + 1 \\ 4552 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((79 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 4553 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) \times 7)) + ((97 - 5) \times 31) \\ 4554 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times 7)) + ((97 - 5) \times 31) \\ 4555 &:= (1^{3!}) - (((5 - (7! - (97 \times 5))) - 3) - 1) \\ 4556 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) + ((79 + 7) \times 53)) - 1 \\ 4557 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (79 + 75)) \times 31 \\ 4558 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) + ((79 + 7) \times 53)) + 1 \\ 4559 &:= (((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) + 97)) \times (5!/3!)) - 1 \\ 4560 &:= (((1 + (35/7))!)/9) \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\ 4561 &:= (((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) + 97)) \times (5!/3!)) + 1 \\ 4562 &:= (1 + 3!) - (((5 - 7!) + (97 \times 5)) - 3! + 1) \\ 4563 &:= 13 \times ((5 \times 79) - (75 - 31)) \\ 4564 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! \times 7) + 9) + (7 \times 531)) \\ 4565 &:= ((13 + 57) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 4566 &:= 13 - (5 - (((79 + 7) \times 53) \times 1)) \\ 4567 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + ((79 + 7) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 4568 &:= ((1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7!) - (97 \times 5))) + 3!) - 1 \\ 4569 &:= ((1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7!) - (97 \times 5))) + 3!) \times 1 \\ 4570 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) + (7! - ((97 \times 5) + 3 + 1)) \\ 4571 &:= (((1 + 3) - 57) \times 9) + (((7! + 5) + 3) \times 1) \\ 4572 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5! - 7!) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 3))) + 1) \\ 4573 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 + 7!) - (97 \times 5)) + (3! + 1)) \\ 4574 &:= ((1 - ((3 \times 5) - 79)) + 7!) - 531 \\ 4575 &:= 13 + ((5 + ((79 + 7) \times 53)) - 1) \\ 4576 &:= (((((1^{35}) \times 7))! + 9) + (7 - (5! \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 4577 &:= 13 + ((5 + ((79 + 7) \times 53)) + 1) \\ 4578 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7) \times ((9 - 75) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 4579 &:= ((1 + 35) + 7) + (9 \times ((7!/5)/(3 - 1))) \\ 4580 &:= (1 - (3! - (5 \times 797))) + (5! \times (3! - 1)) \\ 4581 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + 79) + (7! - 531) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4582 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5!)) + (((7! + (9 + 7)) + (5! - 3!)) \times 1) \\ 4583 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - (((5! - 7) - (9 + 7)) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 4584 &:= (((1 + 3579) + (7!/5)) - 3) - 1 \\ 4585 &:= (((1 + 3579) + (7!/5)) - 3) \times 1 \\ 4586 &:= (((1 + 3579) + (7!/5)) - 3) + 1 \\ 4587 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times (7 + 9)) + 7!) - 531) \\ 4588 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5))^7) - (9 \times (7 - 531)) \\ 4589 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) + 7!) - ((97 \times 5) - 31) \\ 4590 &:= (1 + 3579) + ((7!/5) + 3 - 1) \\ 4591 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7!/9) - 7!)) + (5! - (3 - 1)) \\ 4592 &:= (1 + (((3! \times 5) \times 79) - 75)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 4593 &:= ((13 \times 57 - 9) \times 7) - 531 \\ 4594 &:= (1 + (3! - (57 \times 9))) + (7! + (5!/(3 - 1))) \\ 4595 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7!/9) - 7!)) + (5! + 3 - 1) \\ 4596 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) - (7 \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) - (3! - 1))) \\ 4597 &:= 13 + ((579 \times 7) + 531) \\ 4598 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 - (3 - 1))) \\ 4599 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 - 7!)) - ((97 + 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 4600 &:= (13 - 579) + ((7! + (5^3)) + 1) \\ 4601 &:= 1 + (((3 + 579) - 7) \times (5 + 3)) \times 1 \\ 4602 &:= (13 - (5 \times 7)) + (((9 \times 7) + 5)^{3-1}) \\ 4603 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5!) + (7! - (9 \times (7 \times 5)))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 4604 &:= 1 + ((3! - 5) - ((79 - 7!) + ((5! \times 3) - 1))) \\ 4605 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) + 7!) + (97 - 531) \\ 4606 &:= (((((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 + 9)) - (7 - 5)) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 4607 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5 - 7)) \times 9) + (7! - (5 - (3 + 1))) \\ 4608 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) + 7!) - (9 + (7 + 531)) \\ 4609 &:= (((((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 + 9)) + (7 - 5)) + 3!) - 1 \\ 4610 &:= (((((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 + 9)) + (7 - 5)) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 4611 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5) + (79 - 7)) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 4612 &:= (((1 - (3 \times 5!)) - (7 + 9)) + 7!) - (53 \times 1) \\ 4613 &:= (1 - (((3 \times 5!) + (7 + (9 - 7!)))) + 53)) + 1 \\ 4614 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times (7 \times (9 + (7 \times 5)))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 4615 &:= (13 \times 5) \times ((7 \times 9) + ((7 - 5)^3 \times 1)) \\ 4616 &:= ((1 - 3 + 57) \times (9 + 75)) - (3 + 1) \\ 4617 &:= (1^3 \times 57) \times ((9 + 75) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4618 &:= (1 + ((3 - 57) - 9)) + (7! - ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 4619 &:= (13 \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) - (7 - 531) \\ 4620 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times (5 + (3! \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4621 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! - (5 \times (3 \times 1))) & 4660 &:= ((1 - 357) - 9) + (7! - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 4622 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 \times 79) - 7!) - (5 - 31)) & 4661 &:= ((1 - 357) - 9) + (7! - ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 4623 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5 + 79) - 7) \times (5! / (3 - 1))) & 4662 &:= ((1 \times (3! + ((5 + 7) + 9))) - 75) \times (3! + 1) \\ 4624 &:= (13 + 579) + ((7! / 5) \times (3 + 1)) & 4663 &:= ((1 \times (3 - ((5 \times 79) - 7!))) + (5 \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 4625 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5+7}) + ((97 - 5!)^{3-1}) & 4664 &:= 1 \times ((3 - (5 \times 79)) + ((7! + (5 \times 3)) + 1)) \\ 4626 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times (7 \times (9 + (7 \times 5)))) + 3! \times 1 & 4665 &:= (1 + (3! + 5!)) + ((7! + 97) + (5! - (3! - 1))) \\ 4627 &:= (1 - 35) + (79 \times ((7 + 53) - 1)) & 4666 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) - (97 \times 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 4628 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5! + 7) \times 9) + 7) + ((5 + 3) - 1) & 4667 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times ((7! - 9) - (7 \times (53 - 1))) \\ 4629 &:= (((1 + 3) \times ((5! + 7) \times 9)) + (7 \times (5 + 3))) + 1 & 4668 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5) + ((7! - 9) - (7 \times (53 - 1))) \\ 4630 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! + 7!)) - ((9 - 7) + 531) & 4669 &:= (((1 + (3! - 57)) - (9 - 7)) + 5) \times (3! + 1) \\ 4631 &:= ((1^3)^5) \times (7 + (((9 \times 7) + 5)^{3-1})) & 4670 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5!)) + (7! - (((9 \times 7) - 53) + 1)) \\ 4632 &:= ((1^3)^5) + (7 + (((9 \times 7) + 5)^{3-1})) & 4671 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7) \times (9 + (75 \times 31))) \\ 4633 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) + (79 - (7 - (5! \times 31))) & 4672 &:= (13 - 57) - (9 \times (7 - 531)) \\ 4634 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 57) + (9 + 7!))) - ((5! \times 3) + 1) & 4673 &:= (1^3 - (5 - (7! + 9))) - ((7 + 5) \times 31) \\ 4635 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((57 \times 9) + 7) - 5) \times (3 \times 1) & 4674 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) + 9) \times ((75 + 3!) + 1) \\ 4636 &:= (((1 - 3) - (5 \times 79)) + 7!) - (5 + 3 - 1) & 4675 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7! - (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1))) \\ 4637 &:= ((1^3 - ((5 \times 79) - 7!)) - (5 + 3)) - 1 & 4676 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7! - (9 + ((7 \times 53) - 1))) \\ 4638 &:= ((1^3 - ((5 \times 79) - 7!)) - (5 + 3)) \times 1 & 4677 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5! - 7!))) - ((9 - 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\ 4639 &:= (1 \times (3 - ((5 \times 79) - (7! - 5)))) - (3 + 1) & 4678 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5) + ((7! - 9) - (7 \times (53 - 1))) \\ 4640 &:= ((1 \times 3! + 57) + 97) \times (5 + (3 + 1)!) & 4679 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + ((5 + (797 \times 5)) - 31) \\ 4641 &:= 1 - (3! + (((5 \times 79) - (7! + 5)) + 3 + 1)) & 4680 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5 - 7))) \times ((97 + (5! + 3!)) - 1) \\ 4642 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times 79) - (7! - ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) & 4681 &:= (1^{3579}) + (7! - ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 4643 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + ((7! / 9) + 7!)) + (5 - ((3! \times 1)!) & 4682 &:= (1^{3579}) + (7! - ((5! \times 3) - 1)) \\ 4644 &:= (((1^{3!}) - 5) - (7 - 97)) \times (53 + 1) & 4683 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5!) - 7!)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! - 1))) \\ 4645 &:= (1^{35}) + ((79 + 7) \times (53 + 1)) & 4684 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5! - 7!) + (9 + ((75 \times 3) \times 1))) \\ 4646 &:= 1 + (((3! - ((5 + 7) + 9)) + 75) \times 3! + 1) & 4685 &:= ((1 - 357) - (9 - 7!)) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 4647 &:= (1 \times (3 - ((5 \times 79) - (7! - 5)))) + (3 + 1) & 4686 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + (5^3) + 1) \\ 4648 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - ((7 - 97) \times (53 - 1)) & 4687 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5) + (7! + 9))) - (7 \times (53 + 1)) \\ 4649 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((5 \times 79) - (7! - ((5 - 3) \times 1))) & 4688 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + 7!) + (53 - 1) \\ 4650 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5 \times 79) - (7! - ((5 - 3) \times 1))) & 4689 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 97) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 4651 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7!) + (97 + 5!)) - 3!)) - 1 & 4690 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - 53))) - 1 \\ 4652 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7!) + (97 + 5!)) - 3!)) \times 1 & 4691 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7 \times ((9 \times 75) - (3! + 1))) \\ 4653 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7!) + (97 + 5!)) - 3!)) + 1 & 4692 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - 53))) + 1 \\ 4654 &:= (((1 + 3!) - (5 \times 79)) + 7!) + ((5 - 3) \times 1) & 4693 &:= 13 + (5! \times (79 - (7! / ((5^3) + 1)))) \\ 4655 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5!) \times 79) - (7 + 5)) / (3 - 1) & 4694 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7! - ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) - 31 \\ 4656 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((5 \times 79) - 7!)) + ((5 + 3) - 1) & 4695 &:= ((13 - 5) + 7) \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 4657 &:= (1 - (((3 \times (5! - 7)) - 9) - 7!)) - (53 + 1) & 4696 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - (7 - 531)) \\ 4658 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7!) + 9) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) & 4697 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + (7! - 9)) - (7 \times (53 - 1)) \\ 4659 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) - ((5 \times 79) - ((7! / (5! \times 3)) \times 1)) & 4698 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (((7 + 9 + 7!) - 5!) + 3 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4699 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5!)) + ((797 \times 5) - 3! \times 1) \\ 4700 &:= (1 + (((3!!/5) - (7 - 97))) \times (5!/(3! \times 1))) \\ 4701 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + (9 - ((7 \times 5) \times 3))) - 1 \\ 4702 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5) + ((797 \times 5) + 3)) - 1 \\ 4703 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5! - 7!)) + ((97 + 5!) - (3 - 1))) \\ 4704 &:= ((1^{35}) + 7!) - (97 + (5! + ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 4705 &:= (((1 - 3)^{5+7}) - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 4706 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) - 7!) + (9753 \times 1) \\ 4707 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) + 7) \times (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 4708 &:= (((1 - 3 \times 5) \times (7 - 9)) + 7!) - (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 4709 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((79 + 7) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 4710 &:= (1 \times ((35 + 79) \times (7 \times 5))) + (3!! \times 1) \\ 4711 &:= (1 \times ((35 + 79) \times (7 \times 5))) + (3!! + 1) \\ 4712 &:= 1 \times ((3 + 5) \times (((7 \times (9 - 7)) + 5) \times 31)) \\ 4713 &:= (1^{35}) - ((7! - 9753) + 1) \\ 4714 &:= (1^3 - 5) + (((7 \times (9 \times 75)) - 3!) - 1) \\ 4715 &:= (1 \times 35) - ((7 - 97) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 4716 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5!) \times (7 - 9)) + (7! - (5 + 31)) \\ 4717 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5! + ((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!)))) - (3 + 1)! \\ 4718 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5!)) - ((7 + 9) - (7! + (53 \times 1))) \\ 4719 &:= (1 + 35) - (((7 - 9) - (7! - (5! \times 3))) - 1) \\ 4720 &:= ((1 \times 35)/7) \times (975 - 31) \\ 4721 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - (5! + 79)) + ((7! - 5!) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 4722 &:= (13 - 5) - (7! - (9753 + 1)) \\ 4723 &:= 1 \times ((3! + 5) - ((7! - 9753) + 1)) \\ 4724 &:= 1 + ((3! + 5) - ((7! - 9753) + 1)) \\ 4725 &:= 135 \times (((7 + ((9 + 7) + 5)) + 3!) + 1) \\ 4726 &:= (1 + 3) - (5 - (7! - (((9 \times 7) \times 5) - 3) + 1))) \\ 4727 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (7! - (97 + (5 - 31))) \\ 4728 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - 5) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 75)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 4729 &:= (1 \times 3!)! - (5 - ((7 \times (9 \times 75)) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 4730 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times 797) - (53 - 1) \\ 4731 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) \times ((7 - 9) - ((7!/5)/3))) - 1 \\ 4732 &:= ((13 + 5) - 7!) + (9753 + 1) \\ 4733 &:= ((1 + ((3 - (5 \times 7)) \times 9)) + 7!) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4734 &:= 1 - (((3^5) - (7! - ((9 \times 7) - 5))) + 3! \times 1) \\ 4735 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5!)) + (7! - (9 \times 7))) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 4736 &:= (1 + (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times 3!)))) - 1 \\ 4737 &:= (1 + (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times 3!)))) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4738 &:= (1 + (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times 3!)))) + 1 \\ 4739 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + (79 + 7)) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 4740 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 79)/((7 + 5)/(3 - 1))) \\ 4741 &:= ((1 - (3! + (5 - (7 \times (9 \times 7)))))) \times (5 + 3!) \times 1 \\ 4742 &:= ((1 - (3! + (5 - (7 \times (9 \times 7)))))) \times (5 + 3!) + 1 \\ 4743 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((5 + 7!) - ((975/3) + 1)) \\ 4744 &:= 1 - (((3! \times 57) - (9 + (7! + 5))) - 31) \\ 4745 &:= (1 + 35) - (7 + (9 \times (7 - 531))) \\ 4746 &:= (1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) + ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 4747 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + 7!) - (97 \times (5 - (3 - 1))) \\ 4748 &:= (1 \times 35) - ((7! - 9753) \times 1) \\ 4749 &:= 1 \times (35 - ((7! - 9753) - 1)) \\ 4750 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5!)) + (7 + 9 + (7! + (53 \times 1))) \\ 4751 &:= 1 + 35 + (7! - (975/(3 \times 1))) \\ 4752 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 + 97) - 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 4753 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + 7!) - (9 \times (7 + (53 - 1))) \\ 4754 &:= (1 - 35) + ((7! - 97) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 4755 &:= ((13 - 5) + 7) \times (((9 \times (7 \times 5)) + 3) - 1) \\ 4756 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((7! - ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) + 31) \\ 4757 &:= (1^{35}) + ((7! - ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) + 31) \\ 4758 &:= (1 \times 357 + 9) \times ((7 \times (5 - 3)) - 1) \\ 4759 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) - ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4760 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + (9 + (7 - (53 + 1))) \\ 4761 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + ((5 \times (7 - (9 \times 7))) - ((5 - 3!) \times 1)) \\ 4762 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7 \times (9 \times 75))) + (3 - 1) \\ 4763 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4764 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7! - (97 \times (5 - (3 - 1)))) \\ 4765 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5! + ((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!)))) + (3 + 1)! \\ 4766 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5 - 79))) + ((7! - 53) + 1) \\ 4767 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) + ((79 + 75) \times 31) \\ 4768 &:= ((1 - 35) - 7) + ((9 + 7!) - (5! \times (3 - 1))) \\ 4769 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 4770 &:= ((1 - 35) + 79) \times (75 + 31) \\ 4771 &:= (1 + (357 + 9)) \times (7 + ((5 - (3 - 1)))!) \\ 4772 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - (5! + (7 + (9 + 7)))) - (5^3 \times 1) \\ 4773 &:= (1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) \times ((7 + (5 \times 3!)) \times 1) \\ 4774 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((79 + 75) \times 31) \\ 4775 &:= (1^{35}) + ((79 + 75) \times 31) \\ 4776 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + ((7! + (9 - (7 \times 5))) + 3 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4777 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5! - 7!) - 9) + (75 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 4778 &:= (1 - (35 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7! - 5)) + 3 + 1) \\ 4779 &:= 1 + 35 + (7! - (9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 - 1)))) \\ 4780 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) - 7) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4781 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times 797) - (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 4782 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times 797) \times (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 4783 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times 797) + (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 4784 &:= 13 - (5! - (7! - (97 + (53 - 1)))) \\ 4785 &:= ((13 - 5) + 7) \times (((9 \times (7 \times 5)) + 3) + 1) \\ 4786 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5!) - 7!)) - (9 + ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\ 4787 &:= (1 + (3 - (((5! - 7) - 9) \times (7 - 53)))) - 1 \\ 4788 &:= ((1^{35} + 797) \times ((5 - 3) + 1))! \\ 4789 &:= (1 + (3 - (((5! - 7) - 9) \times (7 - 53)))) + 1 \\ 4790 &:= ((1 - 3!) - 5) + ((7 + 9) \times (75 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 4791 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) - 7) - (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 4792 &:= (1^3) + (((57 \times (9 + 75)) + 3) \times 1) \\ 4793 &:= (((1^{35} + 7!) - 97) - (5! + 31)) \\ 4794 &:= (((1 + 3!)!) - (5 + 7 + 9)) - (75 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 4795 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) + (7! - (9 - 7))) - ((5^3) + 1) \\ 4796 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) + 53) - 1) \\ 4797 &:= (13 + ((5 \times 7) - 9)) \times ((7 + (5! - 3)) - 1) \\ 4798 &:= (1 + ((3! \times (57 - 9)) + 7!)) - 531 \\ 4799 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - ((5! - 7!) + (9 - 7))) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 4800 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5!) \times (((7 - 9)^{7-5}) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 4801 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) + ((5 \times 797) + 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 4802 &:= ((13 + 5) - ((7 + 9)^{7-5})) + ((3! + 1))! \\ 4803 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((579 \times 7) + ((5 + 3!) + 1)) \\ 4804 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (7! + (9 + (7 - (5 \times (3 - 1)))))) \\ 4805 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5 + (7 - (975 - 3))) - 1) \\ 4806 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5!) - 7!)) + ((9 - 7) + (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\ 4807 &:= 1 - (3 + ((5 \times (7 - 975)) + 31)) \\ 4808 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 \times 9) + (7 + 531)) \\ 4809 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) - 7) + (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 4810 &:= 1 + 35 + ((79 + 75) \times 31) \\ 4811 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 57) + 9) + ((7! - (5! + 3)) - 1) \\ 4812 &:= 1 \times (3 - ((5 \times (7 - 975)) + 31)) \\ 4813 &:= 1 + (3 - ((5 \times (7 - 975)) + 31)) \\ 4814 &:= ((((((1 - 3)^5) \times 7) + 9) + 7!) - 5) - 3! \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4815 &:= (1 - ((35 - 7) \times 9)) + ((7! - 5) + 31) \\ 4816 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (((7! - 9) + 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 4817 &:= (1 - (((3^5 + 7) + 9) - (7 \times 5))) + ((3! + 1))! \\ 4818 &:= (((1^{35} \times 7)!) - (97 + ((5^3) \times 1))) \\ 4819 &:= 1 + ((3^5 + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times 5))) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 4820 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) - 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4821 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((5 - 7!) + (9 \times 7))) - (5 \times 31) \\ 4822 &:= ((1 - (3! - 5)) + 7!) - ((9 \times 7) + 5 \times 31) \\ 4823 &:= ((13 - 5!) + (7 + 9)) + (7! - ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 4824 &:= (((((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + 9) + 7) + (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 4825 &:= (1 - ((35 - 7) \times 9)) + ((7! + 5) + 31) \\ 4826 &:= ((135 + 79) - 7!) \times ((5 - 3!) \times 1) \\ 4827 &:= ((1 + 3) - 57) - (((9 - 7!) + 5!) + 31) \\ 4828 &:= (1 + (35 + 7!)) - (97 + (5! + 31)) \\ 4829 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 7)) \times (97 - 5!))) - (3 - 1) \\ 4830 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 + 9)) \times 7) \times (5 + (3! - 1)) \\ 4831 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 \times (7 \times ((97 - 5!) \times 3)))) + 1 \\ 4832 &:= (1^3 + (5! + (79 + (7!/5)))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 4833 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 7)) \times (97 - 5!))) + (3 - 1) \\ 4834 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + 7!)) - (97 + (5! - (3 - 1))) \\ 4835 &:= (((1 - 35) + 7!) - (9 + 7)) - (5 \times 31) \\ 4836 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (7! - (9 + (7 - (53 + 1)))) \\ 4837 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + 7!)) + (((97 \times 5) - 3!) + 1) \\ 4838 &:= ((1 - 35) - 79) + (7! - (5! - 31)) \\ 4839 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5)) + (7! - (97 + 5!))) + (3! - 1) \\ 4840 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + (5! - 7)) - 9) \times (75 - 31) \\ 4841 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) - (((9 - 7) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 4842 &:= ((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7! + ((97 \times 5) + 31)) \\ 4843 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 5!) + 7!)) + (9 + ((7 - 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 4844 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! + 5!)) - (3 + 1) \\ 4845 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - 7!)) - (((9 \times 7) + (5^3)) \times 1) \\ 4846 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (579 - (7 - 5!))) + (3 - 1) \\ 4847 &:= 13 - ((5! - (7! - 97)) - ((5 + 3!) \times 1)) \\ 4848 &:= (135 - 7!) + (9753 \times 1) \\ 4849 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) + ((5 \times 797) + 5!)) + (3 + 1)! \\ 4850 &:= (1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 4851 &:= 1 - (((35/7) - 975) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 4852 &:= (1 + 3) - (((57 - (9 + 7!)) + 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 4853 &:= 135 + (((7 \times 9) \times 75) - 3!) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4854 &:= ((1-3) - (5 \times (7 - (975 + 3)))) + 1 \\ 4855 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) + ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 4856 &:= ((1 + (3 - (5 \times 7))) - 9) + (7! - (5! + (3 + 1)!)) \\ 4857 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) - (7 \times 9)) + (7! - (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 4858 &:= (1^3) - (5! - (7! - (((9 \times 7) - (5 - 3!)) - 1))) \\ 4859 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 7!) + ((9 - (75 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 4860 &:= ((13 - 5) + (797 + 5)) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 4861 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) - ((9 \times 7) + (5! + 3 + 1)) \\ 4862 &:= ((13 - 57) - 9) + (7! - ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 4863 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5! - ((7 - 9) + 7!)) + (53 \times 1)) \\ 4864 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + (9 \times 7)) + ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 4865 &:= (1 - ((3 + (5! + 79)) - (7! - 5))) + 31 \\ 4866 &:= ((1 \times 3!)/5!) \times ((797 + (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\ 4867 &:= ((1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) + (9 + 7)) + (53 \times 1) \\ 4868 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5!) - (((7 \times 9) + 7!) + 5!))) + (3 + 1) \\ 4869 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - (75 \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 4870 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 + 7!)) + (9 + (7 \times (5 - 31))) \\ 4871 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) - ((7 - 97) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 4872 &:= 1 - (((3^5) - 7!) - ((9 \times 7) + (5 + 3! \times 1))) \\ 4873 &:= 1 - ((3! + 5!) - ((7 \times (97 + 5)) \times (3! + 1))) \\ 4874 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! + 7)) - ((9 - 7!) + (53 + 1)) \\ 4875 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5) - (7 - 9))) \times (75 \times (3! - 1)) \\ 4876 &:= ((1 + 35) + ((7 \times 9) - 7)) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 4877 &:= 1^{357} - 9 + 7! - 5 \times 31 \\ 4878 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7)))) - ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 4879 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7)))) - ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\ 4880 &:= ((13 - 57) + 9) + (7! - ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 4881 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 57) - (9 - 7!)) - (5 + 31) \\ 4882 &:= ((1 + ((3 - 57) + 9)) + 7!) - (5! - (3! \times 1)) \\ 4883 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7)))) + ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\ 4884 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! - (7! - (9 \times 7))) - ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\ 4885 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5!)) + (((7! - 9) - (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 4886 &:= ((13 - (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7) + 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 4887 &:= ((135 \times (7 - 9)) + (7! + 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 4888 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - 5) + 7!)) - 97) - (53 \times 1) \\ 4889 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5! - 7!)) + (9 - (75 - 31)) \\ 4890 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times 5) \times 79) + 75) \times (3 - 1) \\ 4891 &:= 1 + (((3! \times 5) \times 79) + 75) \times (3 - 1) \\ 4892 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) + (((7! - 9) - 7) - ((5^3) \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4893 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) - 7) \times 9 - (75 - ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 4894 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) + (7 + 9))) + ((7! - 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 4895 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5! - ((7! + (9 - 753)) - 1)) \\ 4896 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (7! + ((97 - 5) + (3! \times 1))) \\ 4897 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5!) + ((7! - (9 - 75)) + 31) \\ 4898 &:= ((1^{35} + 7!) + (97 - (5! + ((3! - 1)!))) \\ 4899 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + 7!)) - ((97 + 53) \times 1) \\ 4900 &:= 1 \times (((35/7) + 975) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 4901 &:= 1 + (((35/7) + 975) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 4902 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5! - ((7! + (97 - 5!)) + 3 - 1)) \\ 4903 &:= ((1 + ((3 - 5) + 7!)) - 97) - ((5!/3) - 1) \\ 4904 &:= (13 - 5!) + ((7! + 97) - (5! + (3! \times 1))) \\ 4905 &:= (((1 + 3!))! - (5! + 7)) - ((9 + 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 4906 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - (7! - (9 + 7)))) - (5/(3! - 1)) \\ 4907 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - (7! - (9 + 7)))) \times (5/(3! - 1)) \\ 4908 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - (7! - (9 + 7)))) + (5/(3! - 1)) \\ 4909 &:= 135 + ((79 + 75) \times 31) \\ 4910 &:= (1 - 3) + (5 + ((7! - 97) - (5 + 31))) \\ 4911 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) + (7! - 97)) - (53 - 1) \\ 4912 &:= 1 + ((3 + (5 \times (7 + 975))) - (3 - 1)) \\ 4913 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5 + (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 53) + 1) \\ 4914 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times (5 - 31))) \\ 4915 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - 57) \times 9)) + 7!) + ((5! \times 3) + 1) \\ 4916 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 + (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 53) + 1) \\ 4917 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((7! - 97) + (5 - 31)) \\ 4918 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 + (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 53) - 1) \\ 4919 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1))) \\ 4920 &:= (1 + (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times (7 - 5)) + 3 - 1) \\ 4921 &:= (((1 + 3!))! - (5! + 7)) + ((9 + 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 4922 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) + (((7! - 97) - 5!) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 4923 &:= (1 - (3 + (5 - (7! + (9 + 7)))) - ((5^3) + 1) \\ 4924 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5 + (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 53) - 1) \\ 4925 &:= (1 + 3!) - (((5 + (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 53) + 1) \\ 4926 &:= ((1 - (35/7)!) - 9) + (7! + ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 4927 &:= ((1 - ((3! - 5) + 7)) + 9) + (((7! - 5!) + 3!) - 1) \\ 4928 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7!/9)) + (7 \times (5^{3+1})) \\ 4929 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5!)) + 7!) - (((9 - 7) \times 5!) - 3! \times 1) \\ 4930 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + ((7 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5))^{3-1}) \\ 4931 &:= ((1 - 3 + 57) - 9) + (7! - (5 \times 31)) \end{aligned}$$

- 4932** := $1 - (((((35/7)! - 9) - 7!) - 5) + 3 \times 1)$
4933 := $(1 - (((3! - 5) + 7) \times 9)) + ((7! - 5) - 31)$
4934 := $(1 - (35 - (7! - 9))) - (7 \times ((5 + 3) + 1))$
4935 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5 + 7!) - ((9 + 7) + (5! - 31)))$
4936 := $((1 - ((35 - 7!) + 9)) - 7) - 53 - 1$
4937 := $((1 - ((35 - 7!) + 9)) - 7) - 53 \times 1$
4938 := $((1 - ((35 - 7!) + 9)) - 7) - 53 + 1$
4939 := $(13 + (5 - 79)) + (7! - (5! / (3 \times 1)))$
4940 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5) + 7!) - ((9 \times 7) + 53) - 1)$
4941 := $((1^{35} \times 7!) - ((97 - (5 - 3!)) + 1)$
4942 := $(1 - ((35 \times 7) + 9)) + (7! + 5 \times 31)$
4943 := $(1 - 3) + (((5! + 7!) + (9 - (75 \times 3))) + 1)$
4944 := $(1 + (3! + 5)) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
4945 := $1 - (3 + (5! - (79 + ((7! - 53) + 1))))$
4946 := $((1 - 3 + 5) + (7! + (9 - 75))) - 31$
4947 := $((1 \times 3) - (57 + 9)) + 7! - (5 \times (3! \times 1))$
4948 := $((1 \times 3!) / 5! + (7! + (9 + 7))) - (5! - (3! \times 1))$
4949 := $(1 + (3 - 5)) + ((7! - (9 + 75)) - 3! \times 1)$
4950 := $1 - (((35 - 7!) + 9) - (7 - 53)) + 1$
4951 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5) + 7!)) + 9) - (75 + 31)$
4952 := $((1^3)^{57})^9 + (7! - (5! - 31))$
4953 := $((1 - 3) \times 57) - (9 - 7!) + (5 + 31)$
4954 := $135 + ((7! - ((97 + 5!) + 3)) - 1)$
4955 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + 9 + ((7! - (5! / 3)) - 1)$
4956 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 + (7 \times 9))) + ((7! + 53) - 1)$
4957 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + (((7! - (9 \times 7)) - 5!) - (3 + 1)!)$
4958 := $((1 + 3) + 5) - 79 + (7! - ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
4959 := $((1 + 3) - (5! - 7!)) - (9 - (75 - 31))$
4960 := $((1 \times 35) - 79) + (7! - 5) - 31$
4961 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) - (((79 - 7!) + 5) - (3 \times 1))$
4962 := $(1 + (35 \times (7 - 9))) + (7! - ((5 + 3) + 1))$
4963 := $(1 \times ((3 - (5 - 7!)) - 9)) - ((7 \times 5) + 31)$
4964 := $((1 + 3) - (57 + (9 - 7!))) - ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
4965 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + ((9 + 7!) - ((5 \times 3!) + 1))$
4966 := $(1^{3!}) \times (57 - ((9 - 7!) + (5! + 3 - 1)))$
4967 := $(1^{3!}) + (57 - ((9 - 7!) + (5! + 3 - 1)))$
4968 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) - (7 - 97) \times (53 + 1)$
4969 := $((1 + (3! - 5)) + (7 + 9 + 7!)) - (5! - 31)$
4970 := $(1 - 3) - ((5 + 79) - ((7! + (5 \times 3)) + 1))$
4971 := $((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7! + (9 \times 7))) - ((5^3) \times 1)$
4972 := $((1 + 3) + 5) - (79 - 7!) - (5 - 3!) + 1$
4973 := $((1 - 3 + 5) + (7! - 9)) - ((7 + 53) + 1)$
4974 := $(135 + (7! + 9)) - (7 \times (5! / (3 + 1)))$
4975 := $(1 + (3 - 5)) + ((7! + (9 - 75)) + 3 - 1)$
4976 := $((1 \times 35) - (7 \times 9)) + (7! - 5) - 31$
4977 := $1 \times ((3 - (5 - 7!)) - ((97 - 5) - 31))$
4978 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7! + ((9 - (7 + 53)) - 1)$
4979 := $((1 + 3) - 57) - 9 + ((7! + (5 - 3)) - 1)$
4980 := $(13 - 5) + ((7! - 9) - (7 + (53 - 1)))$
4981 := $(1^{3579}) + (7! - (5! / (3 - 1)))$
4982 := $(1 - 3) + ((5 + 7!) - ((97 - 5) - 31))$
4983 := $((1^3 + 5) - (7 \times 9)) + ((7 \times (5 - (3 + 1))))!$
4984 := $((13 - 5) \times 7) \times ((97 - 5) - 3) \times 1$
4985 := $((13 - 5) \times 7) \times ((97 - 5) - 3) + 1$
4986 := $(1 + (((3 \times 5) + (7! - 9)) - (7 + 53))) - 1$
4987 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + 9 + (7! - 5) - (3 + 1)$
4988 := $1 + ((3 + (5 + 7!)) - ((97 - 5) - 31))$
4989 := $((13 - 57) - 9) + 7! - (5 - (3! + 1))$
4990 := $(13 \times 5) - ((79 - 7!) + (5 + 31))$
4991 := $1 + ((3 - 57) + (97 \times (53 - 1)))$
4992 := $((1 \times 3)^5) + (7! - (97 \times (5 - (3 - 1))))$
4993 := $((1 \times (3 - (57 + 9))) + 7!) + (5 \times 3) + 1$
4994 := $(1 \times 3) - ((5 - (7! - 97)) - 53) \times 1$
4995 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + 9 + (7! - 5) + (3 + 1)$
4996 := $(1 + 3) - (579 - 7!) + 531$
4997 := $(1 - 3!) + 5 + (((79 + 7!) - 5!) - (3 - 1))$
4998 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + (9 + 7!) - 5 + (3! + 1)$
4999 := $(1^{35}) \times 7! - ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1))$
5000 := $((1 + 3!)! - 5) - ((7 - 97) + (5! + (3! - 1)))$
5001 := $(13 \times (5 \times ((79 - 7) + 5))) - (3 + 1)$
5002 := $(1^{35}) \times ((7! - (9 + (7 \times 5))) + 3!) \times 1$
5003 := $(1 \times ((3! - 5) + 7)) - ((9 - 7!) + (5 + 31))$
5004 := $(1^{35}) + (7 + 9 + 7!) - (53 \times 1)$
5005 := $13 \times (((5 \times 7) \times 9) + (7 \times (5 \times (3 - 1))))$
5006 := $(1 - 35) + (((79 - (75 - 3)))! \times 1)$
5007 := $((13 - (5 \times 7)) - 9) - ((7 - 5) - ((3! + 1)!))$
5008 := $((1 - 3 + 5) + (7! + (9 - 75))) + 31$
5009 := $(13 \times (5 \times ((79 - 7) + 5))) + (3 + 1)$

- 5010** := $(1 + ((3 + 57) \times (9 + 75))) - 31$
5011 := $((1 + 3)! - 5 + 7!) - (9 + ((7 \times 5) + 3 + 1))$
5012 := $((13 + 57) - 9) + (7! - 5!) + 31$
5013 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) + (7! - (5!/3! \times 1))$
5014 := $(1 - ((3 + 5) + ((7 + 9) - (7! - 5)))) + (3 - 1)$
5015 := $(1 - 3 + (5 - ((7 - 9) - 7!))) - (5!/(3 + 1))$
5016 := $(1 + (3! \times 5!)) + ((7! + (9 - 753)) - 1)$
5017 := $(13 - 57) + ((9 + (7! + (5 + 3!))) + 1)$
5018 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (((5! \times 7) + (9 - 7)) - 5)) - (3 + 1)$
5019 := $(1^3 - ((57 - 9) - 7!)) - (5 - 31)$
5020 := $((1 - 3) - (5 \times 7)) - (9 - (7! - (5 - 31)))$
5021 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7! - 9)) + (7 - (5^{3-1}))$
5022 := $((13 + (57 + 97)) - 5) \times 31$
5023 := $((1 + 3) + (5 - 79)) + (7! + (53 \times 1))$
5024 := $((1 + 3)! + 5 + 7!) - (9 \times (7 - (5 - (3 \times 1))))$
5025 := $(1 - (3! + (5 - 7!))) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) + 31)$
5026 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (((5! \times 7) + (9 - 7)) - 5)) + (3 + 1)$
5027 := $((1^3)^5 \times (7! + (9 - (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1))))))$
5028 := $(1 \times (35 - (7 \times 9))) + ((7! + (5 \times 3)) + 1)$
5029 := $1 - (3 - (5 + (7! - ((9 - 7) \times ((5 + 3) - 1)))))$
5030 := $((1 \times (3 - 5) + 7!) - 9) - (7 - 5) + (3 \times 1)$
5031 := $1 \times (((3 - 57) + 9) + ((7! + 5) + 31))$
5032 := $((1 \times 35) - 79) + ((7! + 5) + 31)$
5033 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) + 7!)) - ((9 + 7) - (5 - (3 + 1)))$
5034 := $1 \times (((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) + (7! + 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
5035 := $1 + (((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) + (7! + 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
5036 := $(1^3) + ((5! + ((7! - (9 - 7)) - 5!)) - (3 \times 1))$
5037 := $((1 \times (3 + 57)) + 9) \times ((75 - 3) + 1)$
5038 := $((1 + 35) + (7! - (9 - 7))) - (5 + 31)$
5039 := $((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) - (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
5040 := $(1^{357975}) \times (3! + 1)!$
5041 := $(1^{357975}) + (3! + 1)!$
5042 := $(1 - (((35 - 7!) + 9) + (7 - 53))) - 1$
5043 := $1 - (((35 - 7!) + 9) + (7 - 53)) \times 1$
5044 := $135 - (79 - ((7! - 53) + 1))$
5045 := $((1^{35}) \times (7 + 9 + (7! - 5))) - (3! \times 1)$
5046 := $(1 + (3 + 5)) - (7 - (97 \times (53 - 1)))$
5047 := $(1^3 - (57 - 9)) + (7! + (53 + 1))$
5048 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5 + 7) + (9 + 7))) + (5 + 31)$
5049 := $1 - (((3 + 5) - (7 + 9 + (7! - 5))) - 3!) + 1$
5050 := $1^{3579} \times (((7! + 5) + 3!) - 1)$
5051 := $1^{3579} + (((7! + 5) + 3!) - 1)$
5052 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) + ((7! \times ((9 + 7) - (5 \times 3))) + 1)$
5053 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) - (7 - 9) + (7! + (5 + 31))$
5054 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (5! \times 7)) + ((9 + (7 - 5)) + 3 \times 1)$
5055 := $(1 \times (3 - (5! - 79))) + (7! + (53 \times 1))$
5056 := $(((((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) + 7) - 5) - (3 \times 1)$
5057 := $(((((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) - 7) + 5) + 3 - 1$
5058 := $(((((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) - 7) + 5) + 3 \times 1$
5059 := $(((((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) - 7) + 5) + 3 + 1$
5060 := $((1 - 3 + 57) - 9) + 7! + (5 - 31)$
5061 := $((1 + 3) + ((5 + 7!) - ((9 - 75)/3!))) + 1$
5062 := $(((((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) + 7) - 5) + (3 \times 1)$
5063 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) + 7!)) + ((9 + 7) - (5 - (3 + 1)))$
5064 := $1 + (((3 + 5) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) - (5 - (3 + 1))))$
5065 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) + (((7 + 9 + (7! - 5)) + 3!) \times 1)$
5066 := $(1^3 + 5) + (7! - 9) - ((7 - 5) - 31)$
5067 := $13 + (((57 + 9) + 7!) - (53 - 1))$
5068 := $((1 - 3) \times 57) - (9 - 7!) + (5! + 31)$
5069 := $((1 + 35) + (7! - 9)) - (7 - ((5 + 3) + 1))$
5070 := $13 \times ((5 \times 79) - ((7 - 5 + 3) \times 1))$
5071 := $(1 + (35 - (7 - 9))) + (7! - ((5 + 3) - 1))$
5072 := $(1 + ((3 + 57) \times (9 + 75))) + 31$
5073 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + 7!) + ((9 - 7) \times ((5 + 3) + 1))$
5074 := $(1 - ((3 - 5) - 7!)) + ((9 + 7) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
5075 := $1 + 35 + (((79 - (75 - 3)))! - 1)$
5076 := $((1 \times ((35/7) \times 9)) + ((7! - 5) - 3)) - 1$
5077 := $((1 \times ((35/7) \times 9)) + ((7! - 5) - 3)) \times 1$
5078 := $13 + (5 \times (7 + (975 + 31)))$
5079 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9 + (7 + (5 \times 3)) \times 1$
5080 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9 + (7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1$
5081 := $(1^{35}) \times 7! + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1))$
5082 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7! - ((9 - (7 + 53)) - 1)$
5083 := $(1 + (3 + (5 \times 7))) + (((9 - (7 - 5)))! + 3 + 1)$
5084 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) + (7! - 9)) + 75 - 31$
5085 := $((1 - 3!) + 5) + ((7! + 97) - (53 - 1))$
5086 := $((1^{35}) \times 7!) + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) + 3) - 1$
5087 := $((1^{35}) \times 7!) + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) + 3) \times 1$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5088 &:= ((1^3 + 5) + 7!) + 9) + (7 - (5 - 31)) \\
 5089 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times 79) + ((7 - 53) \times 1) \\
 5090 &:= (13 + ((57 - 9) + 7!)) - ((5 + 3!) \times 1) \\
 5091 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5 - 7!) - 9) - (7 \times 5)) - 3! \times 1) \\
 5092 &:= ((1 + (3 + 579)) + 7!) - 531 \\
 5093 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5) + (7! - 9)) + (7 + 53)) - 1 \\
 5094 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5!) - (7 + ((9 - 7!) + (53 + 1))) \\
 5095 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) + (7! - 9)) + ((7 + 53) + 1) \\
 5096 &:= 1 \times (((3 - 5) + (7! + 97)) - ((5!/3) - 1)) \\
 5097 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5) + (7! + 97))) - ((5!/3) - 1) \\
 5098 &:= (1^3 + 5!) + (7! - ((9 \times 7) - (5 - 3!)) - 1)) \\
 5099 &:= 1 - ((3 - 57) - (97 \times (53 - 1))) \\
 5100 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (53 - 1)) \\
 5101 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) + (7! + 97)) - ((5!/3) - 1) \\
 5102 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 57)) + 9) + (7! - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\
 5103 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times 5) + ((79 + (7! + 5)) + 3 + 1) \\
 5104 &:= ((13 \times 5) - 7) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\
 5105 &:= (1 + (35 + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) + (3 \times 1) \\
 5106 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7 - 9)) + (7! + (53 \times 1)) \\
 5107 &:= ((13 - 5) + (79 + 7!)) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\
 5108 &:= (13 + 57 + ((9 + 7!) - 5)) - (3! \times 1) \\
 5109 &:= ((13 + 5) + 7) - (9 - (7! + (53 \times 1))) \\
 5110 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (5 + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (53 - 1))) \\
 5111 &:= 13 + (((57 - 9) + 7!) + (5 + 3!)) - 1) \\
 5112 &:= ((135 + 7) \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - 31) \\
 5113 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7! + (9 \times 7)) + 5)) - (3 + 1) \\
 5114 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) + 7!) + (9 \times (7 - (5 - (3 \times 1)))) \\
 5115 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - (5 - 31))) \\
 5116 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! - (7! + (9 \times 7))) - ((5^3) + 1)) \\
 5117 &:= (1 + (3! \times ((5! - 7) + 9) \times 7)) - (5 + 3 \times 1) \\
 5118 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7! - (9 \times 7))) + ((5^3) + 1) \\
 5119 &:= 1 - (((3 - (57 + 9)) - 7!) - (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\
 5120 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) + ((7! - (9 - (75 + 3!))) - 1) \\
 5121 &:= (((1^3)^5 7) - 9) + (7! + (5! - 31)) \\
 5122 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) + (7! - (9 - (75 + 3!)))) + 1 \\
 5123 &:= 1 + ((3! - 5!) + ((79 + 7!) + ((5! - 3) \times 1))) \\
 5124 &:= (((13 + 57) - 9) \times (7 + 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\
 5125 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5! + (7! - (9 + 7))) - (5 \times (3! - 1))) \\
 5126 &:= (1 \times 35) + (7! - ((9 - 7) - 53) \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5127 &:= (1 \times (((3! + 5!) + 79) + 7!)) - ((5! - 3) + 1) \\
 5128 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + (5! + 7)) - ((9 - 7!) + (53 + 1)) \\
 5129 &:= (1^3 - (5 + 7)) + ((97 \times 53) - 1) \\
 5130 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - 5) + (7! - ((9 - (75 + 3!)) + 1)) \\
 5131 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((5 - 7!) + (9 \times 7))) + (5 \times 31) \\
 5132 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7! + (9 - 7))) + (53 + 1) \\
 5133 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 + 7!) + ((9 + 75) + 3 + 1)) \\
 5134 &:= (1^3) + ((5 + 7!) + ((9 + 75) + 3 + 1)) \\
 5135 &:= (1^{3!}) - ((5 - 7!) - ((9 \times 7) + (5 + 31))) \\
 5136 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5!)) - ((79 - 7!) - (53 - 1)) \\
 5137 &:= (1 \times ((35/7)! - (9 - 7!))) - ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\
 5138 &:= (((13 \times 5) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 - 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\
 5139 &:= (((1^{35} \times 7))! + ((97 - (5 - 3!)) + 1) \\
 5140 &:= ((1 - (3 - 57)) + 9) + ((7! + 5) + 31) \\
 5141 &:= (((1^{35})^7) \times 97) \times (53 \times 1) \\
 5142 &:= (1^3 \times (57 - 9)) + (7! + (53 + 1)) \\
 5143 &:= (((1 + (3! \times 5)) + 79) + 7!) - 5) - (3 - 1) \\
 5144 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times 5!) + (((7! - (9 + 7)) - 5) + 3!)) - 1 \\
 5145 &:= (((1 - 35) + 7!) - (9 + 7)) + (5 \times 31) \\
 5146 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5)) + (7! - 9)) + 75) + 31 \\
 5147 &:= ((13 - 5!) \times ((7 - 9) / (7 - 5))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\
 5148 &:= ((13 + 5!) + 7!) + ((97 - 5!) - (3 - 1)) \\
 5149 &:= (1 + (((3! - 5) + 7) \times 9)) + (7! + (5 + 31)) \\
 5150 &:= ((1^{35}) + 79) + (7! + (5! / (3 + 1))) \\
 5151 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times (((7! - (9 + 7)) + 5!) + 3!)) + 1 \\
 5152 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5! - 7!) - (9 + ((75 \times 3) \times 1))) \\
 5153 &:= (((1^{35} \times 7))! + (97 + (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\
 5154 &:= (1 - (((3! - 5)^7 9) - (7! + 5!))) - (3! \times 1) \\
 5155 &:= (13 - (5 - (7! + 97))) + ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\
 5156 &:= (((1 - (3 - 57)) + (9 + 7!)) + 53) - 1 \\
 5157 &:= (((1 - (3 - 57)) + (9 + 7!)) + 53) \times 1 \\
 5158 &:= ((1 - (3 - 57)) + (9 + 7!)) + (53 + 1) \\
 5159 &:= (((1 + (3! + 5!)) + 7) - 97) \times 5! + (3!! - 1) \\
 5160 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + ((79 + (7! + 5)) + 31) \\
 5161 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) + ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\
 5162 &:= (((1 \times (35/7)) - 9) + (7! + 5!)) + 3! \times 1 \\
 5163 &:= ((1 \times ((3 + 5) + 7!)) + 9) + (75 + 31) \\
 5164 &:= (((1 + 3!))! / 5!) + (7! + ((9 + 75) - (3 - 1))) \\
 5165 &:= (1 \times ((35/7)! - (9 - 7!))) + ((5 \times 3) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5166 &:= 1 \times (((35/7)! - ((9-7!) - (5 \times 3))) \times 1) \\ 5167 &:= 1 + (((35/7)! - ((9-7!) - (5 \times 3))) \times 1) \\ 5168 &:= (1 \times (35-7)) + ((97 \times 53) - 1) \\ 5169 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5-79) - (7! + (53-1))) \\ 5170 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) + 53) - 1) \\ 5171 &:= ((1+3)! + 5!) + (7! + (9 - (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))))) \\ 5172 &:= 135 - (7 - (97 \times (53-1))) \\ 5173 &:= ((1 \times 3!)/(57-9)) + (7! + (5! - (3-1))) \\ 5174 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + ((7! + 9) + 7)) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 5175 &:= (1 + ((3-5) + (7! + 97))) + ((5!/3) - 1) \\ 5176 &:= ((135 - (7-9)) + ((7! - 5) + 3)) + 1 \\ 5177 &:= 135 - (((7-9) - 7!) \times ((5-3) - 1)) \\ 5178 &:= (((13 \times 57) + (9-7)) + 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 5179 &:= ((1 - (3-5)) + (7! + 97)) + ((5!/3) - 1) \\ 5180 &:= (1 \times 35) \times ((79 + (75-3!)) \times 1) \\ 5181 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times 79) - ((7-53) \times 1) \\ 5182 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 7!) + (((9-7) \times 53) + 1) \\ 5183 &:= ((1^{35} \times 7!) - (97 - (5! + ((3! - 1)!))) \\ 5184 &:= (((1-3)^5) + (7+97))^{5-3} \times 1 \\ 5185 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) + (((7! - 97) + 5!) + 3 + 1) \\ 5186 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) + 7!) + 9) - ((7 \times 5) \times 3) - 1 \\ 5187 &:= ((13 + (5 \times 7)) \times 97) + 531 \\ 5188 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + 7!)) + (9 - (((7 \times 5) \times 3) - 1)) \\ 5189 &:= (1 \times (3-5)) + (7! + ((97+53) + 1)) \\ 5190 &:= 1 + ((3-5) + (7! + ((97+53) + 1))) \\ 5191 &:= (((13 \times (5+79))/7) - 5) + ((3! + 1)! \\ 5192 &:= (((1+3) + 5) + (7! - 97)) + (5! + ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 5193 &:= (((1 - (3! - 5)) + 7!) - 9) + (7 + 5 \times 31) \\ 5194 &:= 1 - ((3-5) - (7! + ((97+53) + 1))) \\ 5195 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 57) - (9 - (7! - (5+3-1))) \\ 5196 &:= ((1-3!)/5) - ((7-9) - (7! + 5 \times 31)) \\ 5197 &:= ((1-3!)/5) \times ((7-9) - (7! + 5 \times 31)) \\ 5198 &:= ((13+5!) + 7!) - ((97-5!) - (3-1)) \\ 5199 &:= 1 \times (3! + (((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 53) - 1) \\ 5200 &:= 135 + (79 + ((7! - 53) - 1)) \\ 5201 &:= 1 - ((35-7!) - (975/(3! - 1))) \\ 5202 &:= (13 \times 579) - (75 \times 31) \\ 5203 &:= (13 \times (5+7)) + ((9 - (7-5)) + ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 5204 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57)) - (9-7!)) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5205 &:= (((1+3)! + 5!) - (((7-9) - 7) - (5+31))) \\ 5206 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 79) + (7! + (53-1)) \\ 5207 &:= 1 \times (((3-5!) + 7!) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - 31)) \\ 5208 &:= (((1+3)!/(5+7)) \times (9+75)) + ((3! + 1)! \\ 5209 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5)) + 7!) - 9) + (7 + 5 \times 31) \\ 5210 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (57-9)) + 7!) + 5! + (3-1) \\ 5211 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 579) \times ((7+5)/(3+1)) \\ 5212 &:= ((1+3)! - ((5-7) + (9-7!))) + (5 \times 31) \\ 5213 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5)) \times (7+9)) + (7! - ((5-3) + 1)) \\ 5214 &:= (1^3) + ((5! + (79 + (7! + 5))) - 31) \\ 5215 &:= (1 \times 35) \times ((79 + (75-3!)) + 1) \\ 5216 &:= ((1+3) + (5! + 7)) - ((9-7!) - (53+1)) \\ 5217 &:= 135 + (7 + (9 + (7! - (5-31)))) \\ 5218 &:= ((1-3!) \times 5) + ((79+7!) + ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 5219 &:= ((1-3!) \times 5) + (((79+7!) + (5^3)) \times 1) \\ 5220 &:= (((13 \times 5) + (7-9)) + (7! + 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 5221 &:= (1 - ((3+5) - 7!)) + (((9 \times 7) + (5^3)) \times 1) \\ 5222 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((57 \times 9) - ((7! + 5) - 31)) \\ 5223 &:= (((13-5) + (79+7!)) + 5!) - (3+1)! \\ 5224 &:= 1 \times ((3 + (5! + 7!)) + ((97-5) - 31)) \\ 5225 &:= 1 + ((3 + (5! + 7!)) + ((97-5) - 31)) \\ 5226 &:= (1 - ((3-5!) - 7!)) - ((9-75) - (3-1)) \\ 5227 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) + (((7 \times 9) + (7! + 5!)) - (3+1)) \\ 5228 &:= (((((1+3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97) - 5) \times (3-1) \\ 5229 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (79 \times ((7 \times 5) + 31)) \\ 5230 &:= ((135-7) + 9) + (7! + (53 \times 1)) \\ 5231 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + 7!)) - (((9 \times 7) - 5) - 3! \times 1) \\ 5232 &:= 1 - (((3! - 5) - 79) - (7! + 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\ 5233 &:= (((1^{3!}) - (5-79)) + (7! + 5!)) - (3-1) \\ 5234 &:= ((13 + (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7))) + 5!) + ((3! + 1)! \\ 5235 &:= 1 - ((3! - 5) - (((79+7!) + 5!) - (3+1))) \\ 5236 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5)) + (((79+7!) + 5!) - (3+1)) \\ 5237 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) + (((79+7!) + 5!) - (3+1)) \\ 5238 &:= (1 \times (3 + 579)) \times (7 + (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 5239 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) + 7!) - ((97-53) \times 1) \\ 5240 &:= ((1-3) \times (5-79)) + (7! + (53-1)) \\ 5241 &:= 1^{35} \times ((79 + (7! + 5!)) + 3 - 1) \\ 5242 &:= (135 + ((79+7!) - (5+3!))) - 1 \\ 5243 &:= (135 + ((79+7!) - (5+3!))) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

- 5244** := (135 + ((79 + 7!) - (5 + 3!))) + 1
5245 := ((135 + 7) + 9) + (7! + (53 + 1))
5246 := (1 + 3)! + ((5! + (7! - (9 × 7))) + (5³ × 1))
5247 := 13 - (((5 - 7!) + ((9 - 75) × 3)) - 1)
5248 := ((1 - 3) - (5 - 7!)) - (9 - ((75 × 3) - 1))
5249 := (1 + 3!) + (5! + (7! + ((9 + 75) - (3 - 1))))
5250 := (((1 × 3) × 5!) + (7! - 97)) - (53 × 1)
5251 := 1 - (((3 + (5 - 7!)) - (9 × 7)) - (5 × 3!))
5252 := 1 - (((3! - 5!) - ((7! - 9) + 75)) - 31)
5253 := ((1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) + (97 + 5)) + ((3! + 1)!)
5254 := (((1 + 3)! × 5) + 7!) + ((97 - 5) + 3 - 1)
5255 := (((1 + 3!) + (5 + (79 + 7!))) + 5!) + (3 + 1)
5256 := (1 + 3⁵) + ((7! + 9) - (7 + (5 × 3! × 1)))
5257 := (1 + ((3 × 57) - 9)) + ((7! + 53) + 1)
5258 := ((1 - (3! - 5)) + 7!) + ((9 × 7) + 5 × 31)
5259 := (((1³⁵) + 7!) + (9 × 7)) + (5 × 31)
5260 := (1 × (3⁵)) + (((7! + (9 - (7 × 5))) + 3) × 1)
5261 := (((1 + 3!))! - (5 + 7)) + ((9 + (75 × 3)) - 1)
5262 := (((1³⁵) × 7))! + (97 + ((5³) × 1))
5263 := ((1 + 3⁵) + 7!) - ((9 - (7 - 5)) × (3 × 1))
5264 := 1 - ((3 - 5797) + 531)
5265 := ((135 + (79 + 7!)) + (5 + 3!)) × 1
5266 := ((135 + (79 + 7!)) + (5 + 3!)) + 1
5267 := (1³ + 5797) - 531
5268 := (1³ × (5! + 7!)) - ((9 + (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1))
5269 := (135 + 7) - ((9 - (7! + 5!)) + (3 + 1)!)
5270 := (1 + (3 + 5797)) - 531
5271 := (((13 - 5) + (79 + 7!)) + 5!) + (3 + 1)!
5272 := (1 × 3 + (5! + (7! - (9 + 7)))) + (5 + ((3! - 1)!))
5273 := (1 × (3⁵)) + (7! - (9 - (7 - (5 + 3 × 1))))
5274 := ((1 - ((3 - 5)⁷)) - 9) + ((7! + 5!) - 3! × 1)
5275 := ((1³⁵) × (7! - ((97 × 5) - 3!))) × 1
5276 := ((1 × (3⁵)) + (7! + ((9 - 7) - 5))) - (3 + 1)
5277 := ((1 + 3⁵) + 7!) - (((9 - 7) × 5) - (3 × 1))
5278 := (1³ + 57) × ((9 - 7) + (5! - 3!))
5279 := ((1 × 3) × 5) + (7! + ((97 + 5!) + (3! + 1)))
5280 := ((1 + 3) + 5!) + (7! + (((9 × 7) - 5) × (3 - 1)))
5281 := (1 + ((3⁵ + 7!) - 9)) + ((7 - 5) × (3 × 1))
5282 := ((1 × 3!) + (5! + (7! + 97))) - (5 - (3 + 1)!)
5283 := ((13 + 5) + 7!) + (((9 × 75) / 3) × 1)
5284 := (1 - (3! × (57 - 9))) + (7! + 531)
5285 := 1 + (3⁵ + ((7! + ((9 - 7) - 5)) + 3 + 1))
5286 := (((1 + 35) × 7) + 9) + (7! - (5 × 3)) × 1
5287 := (((135 + 7) + 9) + (7! + 5!)) - (3 + 1)!
5288 := (1 × (((3 - 57) + 97) × (5! + 3))) - 1
5289 := (1 + (35 + 7)) × (97 - (5 - 31))
5290 := (1 × (((3 - 57) + 97) × (5! + 3))) + 1
5291 := (1 + (((3 - 57) + 97) × (5! + 3))) + 1
5292 := ((13 × 57 - 9) + 7!) - (5! × (3 + 1))
5293 := 1 - (((3 - 5) × (7⁹⁻⁷)) × (53 + 1))
5294 := 1 + (((35 / 7)! + 9) + (7! + ((5³) - 1)))
5295 := (1 + 3⁵) + (7 + (97 × (53 - 1)))
5296 := (13 - 5!) + ((7! - 9) + ((7 + 5) × 31))
5297 := (1 × (((3⁵ + 7!) + (9 + 7)) - 5)) + (3 × 1)
5298 := (1 × (3 - 5)) × ((7 × 9) + ((7 - 5!) × (3 + 1)!))
5299 := ((135 + 7) - 9) + ((7! + 5!) + 3! × 1)
5300 := ((1 × (3! × 5)) + ((7 × 9) + 7)) × (53 × 1)
5301 := (135 + 7!) + (9 × (7 + ((5 + 3) - 1)))
5302 := (1 - ((3⁵) - 7!)) + (9 × (7 × (5 + 3 × 1)))
5303 := (((1 + 3!))! / 5) + ((7! + (9 - 753)) - 1)
5304 := 13 × ((5! + (7 × 9)) + ((75 × 3) × 1))
5305 := ((1 + 3⁵) + 7!) + ((9 - (7 - 5)) × (3 × 1))
5306 := (((1 + 3!))! + (5! + (7 + (9 + 7)))) + (5! + 3 × 1)
5307 := (1 + (((3⁵ + 7!) + (9 + 7)) + 5)) + (3 - 1)
5308 := (1 + (3! / 5)) + (7! + ((97 - 5) + 31))
5309 := (((1 × 35) + 79) + 7!) + (5 × 31)
5310 := ((1 × ((3 × 5) - 7)) + (9 - 7)) × 531
5311 := (1 × (3 × 57)) + ((97 × 53) - 1)
5312 := (135 + 7!) + (97 + ((5! / 3) × 1))
5313 := ((1 + 3) × (5 × 7)) + (9 + ((7! + 5!) + 3 + 1))
5314 := ((1^{3!}) + (5 × 79)) + (((7! - 5!) - 3) + 1)
5315 := (1 - (3⁵)) + ((7! + 9) + ((7 + 5!) × (3 + 1)))
5316 := ((1 + 3⁵) + ((7! - 9) + (7 × 5))) + 3! × 1
5317 := ((135 + 7) - (9 - (7! + 5!))) + (3 + 1)!
5318 := 1 × ((3! + (5 × 79)) + (((7! - 5!) - 3) × 1))
5319 := 1 + ((3! + (5 × 79)) + (((7! - 5!) - 3) × 1))
5320 := ((1 × (3 × 5!)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) × (5! / (3 × 1)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 5321 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) \times (5! / (3 \times 1))) \\
 5322 &:= ((1 + ((3! - 5) - (79 - 7!))) + (5! \times 3)) - 1 \\
 5323 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + (7! + (9 + (((7 \times 5) - 3) - 1))) \\
 5324 &:= (1 + (35 + 7!)) + (97 + (5! + 31)) \\
 5325 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + 7!) + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\
 5326 &:= (((1^3 - 5!) + (7 \times (9 \times 75))) + 3!) \times 1 \\
 5327 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) + 7!) + ((97 - 53) \times 1) \\
 5328 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (579 - 7)) \times (5 + 31) \\
 5329 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - (7 + (9 - 75))))^{3-1} \\
 5330 &:= (((1^3 - 5!) \times (7 - (9 + 7))) - 5) \times (3! - 1) \\
 5331 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) - (7 + 9)) + (7! - (53 \times 1)) \\
 5332 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 57) + 97)) \times ((5^3) - 1) \\
 5333 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + (7! - 9))) + ((7 \times 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\
 5334 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5! - (7 \times (9 - (753 \times 1)))) \\
 5335 &:= (((135 + 7) + 9) + (7! + 5!)) + (3 + 1)! \\
 5336 &:= ((13 + ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + 7) \times ((5! - 3) - 1) \\
 5337 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57)) + 9) + ((7! + (5! - 3)) \times 1) \\
 5338 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5) - (7 \times (9 + 753))) - 1) \\
 5339 &:= 1 + (3^5 + ((7! + ((9 \times (7 - 5)) \times 3)) + 1)) \\
 5340 &:= ((1 \times (3^5 + 7!)) + (9^{7-5})) - (3 + 1)! \\
 5341 &:= (1 - (3 - (5! + (7 \times 9)))) + (7! + ((5! / (3 + 1)!))!) \\
 5342 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5! + (7! + (9 \times 7))) + (5! - (3! - 1))) \\
 5343 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times (5 - (7 - (9 \times 7)))) + (5! + ((3! + 1)!))!) \\
 5344 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\
 5345 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (7 - 9)) + (7! - (53 \times 1)) \\
 5346 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7! + (97 \times (5 - (3 - 1)))) \\
 5347 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) + ((79 + 7!) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\
 5348 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (7! + ((9 - 7) - (53 + 1))) \\
 5349 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + 57) + ((9 + 75) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 5350 &:= (135 + 79) \times ((75/3) \times 1) \\
 5351 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7! + (9 \times 7))) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\
 5352 &:= (1 - (3! - 5!)) + ((79 + 7!) + ((5! - 3) + 1)) \\
 5353 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 57) - 9) + 7! - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\
 5354 &:= (1^3 - 5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1)) \\
 5355 &:= (1 + (35 + 7!)) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\
 5356 &:= ((1 + ((35 - 79) + 7!)) + (5! \times 3)) - 1 \\
 5357 &:= (1^3 - 5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3! \times 1)) \\
 5358 &:= ((1 + ((35 - 79) + 7!)) + (5! \times 3)) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5359 &:= ((1^3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7! - (5! / (3 + 1)!)) \\
 5360 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57)) + 97) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\
 5361 &:= (1 \times (((3! + 5!) + 79) + 7!) + (5! - 3)) - 1 \\
 5362 &:= (1 \times (((3! + 5!) + 79) + 7!) + (5! - 3)) \times 1 \\
 5363 &:= (1 \times (((3! + 5!) + 79) + 7!) + (5! - 3)) + 1 \\
 5364 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) + (7! + ((975/3) \times 1)) \\
 5365 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times (7 - (9 - 7))) + ((5 + 3) - 1)! \\
 5366 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5)! + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\
 5367 &:= ((1^3 + 57) \times (97 - 5)) + 31 \\
 5368 &:= (13 - 57) \times ((9 - (7 + (5^3))) + 1) \\
 5369 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5) - 7!) - (975/3)) - 1 \\
 5370 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5!)) - 79) + (7! + 531) \\
 5371 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 + (79 + 7!))) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\
 5372 &:= ((1 \times (35 + 7!)) - (9 \times (7 - 5!))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\
 5373 &:= ((1^3 - 5) + (7! + (97 + 5!))) + ((3! - 1)!) \\
 5374 &:= (1^3 \times (57 \times 97)) - (5 \times 31) \\
 5375 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + 7!) + ((975/3) + 1)) \\
 5376 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) + (7 + 9))) + 7!) + ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\
 5377 &:= ((13 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) \times 3!)) - 1 \\
 5378 &:= 1 \times ((3^5 + 7!) - (9 - (((7 \times 5) \times 3) - 1))) \\
 5379 &:= 1 + ((3^5 + 7!) - (9 - (((7 \times 5) \times 3) - 1))) \\
 5380 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + (7! - 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 5381 &:= (1 + (3! \times (57 - 9))) + ((7! + 53) - 1) \\
 5382 &:= ((1 + (3! / 5)) + (79 + (7! + 5!))) - (3 - 1) \\
 5383 &:= (1 + (3 + (5! + 7!))) + ((97 + 5!) + 3 - 1) \\
 5384 &:= 13 + (5! + (((7! + 97) + 5!) - (3! \times 1))) \\
 5385 &:= (((13 \times 5) + 7) / 9) + 7) \times ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\
 5386 &:= ((1 + (3! / 5)) + (79 + (7! + 5!))) + (3 - 1) \\
 5387 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (57 - 9)) + 7!) + (5 \times 31) \\
 5388 &:= (1 + (35 \times 7)) + ((97 \times 53) + 1) \\
 5389 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) + (7! + (((9 - 7) \times 53) \times 1)) \\
 5390 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) \times (7 + 9))) - (7 \times (53 \times 1)) \\
 5391 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5!)) + (7! - (((9 \times 7) - 53) \times 1)) \\
 5392 &:= (1 + (3 - ((5! + (7 \times 9)) - 7!))) + 531 \\
 5393 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 57) - 9) + 7! + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\
 5394 &:= (135 + (7! + 9)) + (7 \times (5! / (3 + 1))) \\
 5395 &:= 1 \times ((357 - 9) + (7! + (5 + 3 - 1))) \\
 5396 &:= 1 + ((357 - 9) + (7! + (5 + 3 - 1))) \\
 5397 &:= (1 + 3^5) + (7! + (9 + (((7 \times 5) \times 3) - 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5398 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + (7 \times 9)) + (7! + (53 - 1)) \\ 5399 &:= (1 + 357) - ((9 - 7!) - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 5400 &:= ((1 + (357 + (9 - 7))) \times 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 5401 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5! + 7!)) - (((9 + 7) \times 5) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 5402 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((7! - 9) + ((7 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 5403 &:= (1 \times (3! + (5! + (7! + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 5404 &:= ((1 - (((3 - 57) \times 9) - 7!)) - 5!) - (3 \times 1) \\ 5405 &:= ((1 + (3 + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)))) \times 53) - 1 \\ 5406 &:= (1 + (3 + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)))) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 5407 &:= ((1 + (3 + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)))) \times 53) + 1 \\ 5408 &:= ((1 + 3) + (57 \times 97)) - (5^3 \times 1) \\ 5409 &:= (1 \times (3! + (5! + (7! + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 5410 &:= ((13 + (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7))) \times 5) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 5411 &:= 1 \times ((3! + ((57 \times 97) - 5!)) - (3 + 1)) \\ 5412 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 \times 97)) - ((5! / (3 + 1)!)!) \\ 5413 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times 57) - ((9 - 7!) - (5! / (3 \times 1))) \\ 5414 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) - (9 - 7!)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 5415 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (7! + (((9 \times (7 - 5)) - 3) \times 1)) \\ 5416 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) \times ((7 + (9 \times 75)) - (3! - 1)) \\ 5417 &:= (1^3 - (5 - (7! + 9))) + ((7 + 5) \times 31) \\ 5418 &:= (((13 \times (5 + 79)) - 7) \times 5) - (3! + 1) \\ 5419 &:= ((1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) - 9) + (7! / (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 5420 &:= 1 - (35 - (7! - (9 \times ((7 - 53) \times 1)))) \\ 5421 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + ((5 \times 79) - ((7! / (5! \times 3)) \times 1)) \\ 5422 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + (((5 \times 79) + 7) - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 5423 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5) + 7!) + (((9 + 7) + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 5424 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5! - 79)) + ((7! + 5!) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 5425 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 5426 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (((79 + 7!) - 53) \times 1) \\ 5427 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5)) - ((7! - 9753) + 1) \\ 5428 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) + 7!) + (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\ 5429 &:= 135 + (7! + (9 + ((7 \times 5) \times (3! + 1)))) \\ 5430 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + ((975 - 3!) + 1)) \\ 5431 &:= (((1 + 3!)!) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 5432 &:= ((1 - 3) \times ((5 - 7) \times 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 5433 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + 7!)) + (97 + (53 \times 1)) \\ 5434 &:= 13 \times ((5 \times 79) + ((7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1)) \\ 5435 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) - (7 + (9 + (75 \times 31)))) \\ 5436 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) - (7 + (9 + (75 \times 31)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5437 &:= (1 \times (35 + 7!)) - (9 - (7 \times (53 \times 1))) \\ 5438 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7! + (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 3 - 1))) \\ 5439 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 - ((7 - 9)^7))) + (((5 + 3) - 1)!) \\ 5440 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) + 797) \times ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 5441 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) + 797) \times (5 + 3) + 1 \\ 5442 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) + (((7 \times 9) + (7! + 5!)) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 5443 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 \times 79)) + ((7! + 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 5444 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 \times 79)) + (7! + ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 5445 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 \times 79) + 7)) + (5 + ((3! + 1)!)!) \\ 5446 &:= (1 - ((3 - 57) + 9)) + ((7! + (5! \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 5447 &:= 13 \times (((5 \times (79 + 7)) - 5) - 3! \times 1) \\ 5448 &:= 1 \times ((3 + 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - (7 - (5^{3+1})))) \\ 5449 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 - (9 + (75 \times 31))) \\ 5450 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) + (7! + ((97 + 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 5451 &:= (((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5^3))) - 1 \\ 5452 &:= (((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5^3))) \times 1 \\ 5453 &:= (((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5^3))) + 1 \\ 5454 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) + (7 + 9 + 7!)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 5455 &:= 1 - (((3^5) - 7!) + (9 \times 7)) - (5! \times 3! \times 1) \\ 5456 &:= (1 + ((3 - 57) + 97)) \times ((5^3) - 1) \\ 5457 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) - 7)) + ((9 + 7!) + (53 + 1)) \\ 5458 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((7! - 97) + (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 5459 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + 7!)) - (9 \times (7 - (53 \times 1))) \\ 5460 &:= (1 \times 35) \times (((79 \times (7 - 5)) - 3) + 1) \\ 5461 &:= 13 + ((5 + 7) \times ((97 \times 5) - 31)) \\ 5462 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5!)) + (7! + ((97 - 5) - 31)) \\ 5463 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (7! + (9 - ((7 \times 5) + 31))) \\ 5464 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! + 7!)) + ((97 + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 5465 &:= ((1^{3!}) + (5 \times 79)) + ((7! + (5 \times 3!)) - 1) \\ 5466 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((57 \times (9 + 7)) + (5 - 3!)) \times 1) \\ 5467 &:= 1 + (3! \times ((57 \times (9 + 7)) + (5 - (3! \times 1)))) \\ 5468 &:= (1 + 3) + (579 + (7! - (5 \times 31))) \\ 5469 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (7 + 9 + (7! + (53 \times 1))) \\ 5470 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5!) + (7 + 9 + 7!)) + (53 \times 1)) \\ 5471 &:= 1 \times ((3^5 + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^3 \times 1))) \\ 5472 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((57 \times (9 + 7)) + (5 - 3!)) + 1) \\ 5473 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) + 7!) - (97 - 531) \\ 5474 &:= ((1 - 3) - (((5 \times 7) + 9) - 7!)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\ 5475 &:= 1 \times 3 + (57 \times ((97 - (5 - 3)) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 5476** := $((1 + 3) - (57 - (9 + 7!))) + (5! \times (3 + 1))$
5477 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) - (79 - 7!) + (5 + 31)$
5478 := $((1^3 \times 5!) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1)$
5479 := $((1 + 3) + ((57 \times 97) - 53)) - 1$
5480 := $((1 + 3) + ((57 \times 97) - 53)) \times 1$
5481 := $(1 + 3) + (((57 \times 97) - 53) + 1)$
5482 := $((13 - 5) + (7! - 97)) + 531$
5483 := $1 \times 3! + ((57 \times 97) - (53 - 1))$
5484 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) \times (((7 - 9) - 7) \times 5) - 3! \times 1$
5485 := $1 - (((3 - 57) \times (97 + 5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
5486 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (7! + ((5!/3) + 1))$
5487 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) + (79 \times ((75 - 3) - 1))$
5488 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) \times ((7 - (9 + (7 + 5)))^3 \times 1)$
5489 := $(1 \times 35) + (7! - (9 \times ((7 - 53) \times 1)))$
5490 := $((1 \times 3) - ((5 + 79) - 7!)) + 531$
5491 := $((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 9)) \times 7) + (5! \times 31)$
5492 := $((((13 \times 5) \times 7) - 9) + 7!) + ((5 - (3 - 1)))!$
5493 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) + (7! + 97)) + 5!) - (3! + 1)$
5494 := $(1 \times (3! \times (5! + 797))) - ((5 + 3) \times 1)$
5495 := $((1 - 3) - (57 - 975)) \times 3! - 1$
5496 := $((1 - 3) - (57 - 975)) \times 3! \times 1$
5497 := $((1 - 3 + 5) + 7!) + ((97 \times 5) - 31)$
5498 := $1 \times (3!! - ((5! - ((7! - (9 + 7)) - 5!)) + (3! \times 1)))$
5499 := $1 + (3!! - ((5! - ((7! - (9 + 7)) - 5!)) + (3! \times 1)))$
5500 := $1 + (((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7!) - ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
5501 := $1 \times (((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7!) - (5 + 3!)) + 1$
5502 := $1 + (((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7!) - (5 + 3!)) + 1$
5503 := $1 - (3 \times (57 - ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 3!) + 1))$
5504 := $(135 - 7) \times ((97 - 53) - 1)$
5505 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) + (7! + 97)) + (5! + 3!)) - 1$
5506 := $13 + ((57 \times 97) - (5 + 31))$
5507 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) + (7! + 97)) + 5!) + (3! + 1)$
5508 := $(1 + (3 + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)))) \times (53 + 1)$
5509 := $((((1 - 3 + 57) \times 9) + 7!) + 5) - 31$
5510 := $(1 \times (3! \times (5! + 797))) + ((5 + 3) \times 1)$
5511 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! - 5!) + (3 + 1)!$
5512 := $((1 - 35) - 79) + (75^{3-1})$
5513 := $1 - (((3 - 57) \times (97 + 5)) - (3 + 1))$
5514 := $((1 \times 3!) - ((57 - 97) \times 5!)) - (3! \times 1)$
5515 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5!) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) + 53) - 1)))$
5516 := $((1 + 3) \times (((5! + 79) - 7) + 5)) \times (3! + 1)$
5517 := $((((1 - 3) \times 57) - 9) + 7!) - ((5! - 3!) \times 1)$
5518 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5) \times (3 - 1)$
5519 := $(13 \times ((5 \times (79 + 7)) - 5)) - 3! \times 1$
5520 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5) - 7) \times (9 + 7) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
5521 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) + ((7! - 9) + (7 \times 53))) + 1$
5522 := $(1^3) \times ((5! + 7!) - ((9 - (7 \times 53)) \times 1))$
5523 := $(1^3) + ((5! + 7!) - ((9 - (7 \times 53)) \times 1))$
5524 := $((1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - 7) \times (9 + 7)) - (5^3)) + 1$
5525 := $13 \times (5 \times (79 + ((7 - 5 + 3) + 1)))$
5526 := $((1 \times 3!) - ((57 - 97) \times 5!)) + (3! \times 1)$
5527 := $((((1 - 3 + 5)))! + ((7! - 9) - (75 \times 3))) + 1$
5528 := $1 \times ((3! \times (5! + 797)) - (5 - 31))$
5529 := $1 + ((3! \times (5! + 797)) - (5 - 31))$
5530 := $(1 + ((3 + 57) + 9)) \times (75 + 3 + 1)$
5531 := $(13 \times ((5 \times (79 + 7)) - 5)) + 3! \times 1$
5532 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (79 + (7! + (53 \times 1)))$
5533 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) - 7))^9 + 7!) + (5 - (3 + 1)!)$
5534 := $1 - ((3 - ((57 \times 97) + 5)) - (3 - 1))$
5535 := $(1 - (35 - 7)) - (9 - (7! + 531))$
5536 := $(1 - 3 + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
5537 := $(1 - 3 + ((57 \times 9) + 7!)) - ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
5538 := $(13 + 5) + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times (5!/(3 + 1))))$
5539 := $(1 \times (357 - 9)) + ((7! + 5!) + 31)$
5540 := $(1 \times 3! + ((57 \times 9) + 7!)) + (5 - (3 + 1)!)$
5541 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) + 5)) + ((3! - 1)!)$
5542 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) + (7! + ((9 + 75) \times 3! \times 1))$
5543 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 79)) \times (7 + (5 \times 3)) - 1$
5544 := $(135 + (7! - 9)) + (7 \times (53 + 1))$
5545 := $(1 + (3^5 + 7!)) - (9 \times ((7 - 5) - 31))$
5546 := $1 - (3! - (5 - 79 + (75^{3-1})))$
5547 := $((13 - 5) \times 79) + ((7! - (5^3)) \times 1)$
5548 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) + (7! + ((97 \times 5) + 3 + 1))$
5549 := $((135 + (7^{9-7})) - 5) \times 31$
5550 := $(1 + 3)! + ((57 \times 97) - (5 - (3 - 1)))$
5551 := $(1 + (3! + (5 + 79))) \times (7 + (53 + 1))$
5552 := $((1 + 35) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
5553 := $((1 + 3) + 5) \times ((79 + 7) + 531)$

$$\begin{aligned} 5554 &:= ((13 \times (5! - 79)) + 7!) + (5 - (3 + 1)!) \\ 5555 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + (5 + ((7 - 97) + (5! \times (3! - 1)))) \\ 5556 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times ((5! \times 7) - (9 - 75))) + ((3! - 1)!) \\ 5557 &:= 1 \times (3! + (5 - 79 + (75^{3-1}))) \\ 5558 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((57 \times 9) + 7!) - 5) + 3 + 1 \\ 5559 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times ((5 - 7) - 9)) + (75^{3-1}) \\ 5560 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((57 \times 9) + 7!) + (5 - (3 + 1))) \\ 5561 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5 + 7)) \times (97 + (5 - 3!))) - 1 \\ 5562 &:= ((1 + (357 \times (9 + 7))) - 5!) - 31 \\ 5563 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5 + 7)) \times (97 + (5 - 3!))) + 1 \\ 5564 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 79) - 7) \times (53 - 1) \\ 5565 &:= (1 \times 35) \times ((79 + 75) + (3! - 1)) \\ 5566 &:= 1 + (35 \times ((79 + 75) + (3! - 1))) \\ 5567 &:= (1^{3!}) + (((579 + 7!) - 53) \times 1) \\ 5568 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + (57 - 9)) + 7!) - (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 5569 &:= (1 + 3) + ((57 \times 97) + (5 + 31)) \\ 5570 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7!) + (9 \times ((7 + 53) \times 1)) \\ 5571 &:= (1^{3579}) \times (7! + 531) \\ 5572 &:= (1^{3579}) + (7! + 531) \\ 5573 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 579) + ((7! - 53) \times 1) \\ 5574 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! - ((97 \times 5) + 3!)) + 1) \\ 5575 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5) - ((7 - 97) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 5576 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7))!) - (((9 \times 7) + 5!) - 3!) - 1 \\ 5577 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7))!) - (((9 \times 7) + 5!) - 3!) \times 1 \\ 5578 &:= ((1^3 \times ((5 - 7) + 9))!) + (7 + 531) \\ 5579 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7!) + (9 \times ((7 + 53) + 1)) \\ 5580 &:= (1 + (3! + (5 + 7))) - (97 + (5! - 31)) \\ 5581 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times 9) + ((7! - 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 5582 &:= (((135 + 7) - 9) \times (7!/5!)) - (3 + 1) \\ 5583 &:= (13 \times 57) + (9 \times (7 + 531)) \\ 5584 &:= (1^3 + ((57 \times 97) + 53)) + 1 \\ 5585 &:= (((1^3 + 5))! - (79 - 7!)) - 5! + (3 + 1)! \\ 5586 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) + ((57 + 9) + 7!)) - (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 5587 &:= (1 \times (357 \times (9 + 7))) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 5588 &:= (((1^3 + 5) + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 5589 &:= (((1 - 35) + (7! - 9)) - (7 + 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\ 5590 &:= (((135 + 7) - 9) \times (7!/5!)) + (3 + 1) \\ 5591 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7!/9)) + (7! - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 5592 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7!/9) + 7!)) - ((5 - 3) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5593 &:= (((1^3 + 5))! + 7!) - (9 + 7) - (5! + 31) \\ 5594 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) + 5) - 7 - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31) \\ 5595 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - 5 + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 5596 &:= (1 + 357) + (97 \times (53 + 1)) \\ 5597 &:= (1 \times 35) - ((7 \times 9) - (75^{3-1})) \\ 5598 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) - 5) + 7 - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31) \\ 5599 &:= 1 - (3! + ((5! - (7 \times 97)) - (5 + ((3! + 1)!))) \\ 5600 &:= (1 - 35) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) + 531)) \\ 5601 &:= (1 - 3 + (579 + 7!)) - ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\ 5602 &:= (((1 + 357) \times (9 + 7)) - (5^3)) - 1 \\ 5603 &:= (((1 + 357) \times (9 + 7)) - (5^3)) \times 1 \\ 5604 &:= (((1 + 357) \times (9 + 7)) - (5^3)) + 1 \\ 5605 &:= 13 + (((5 + 7) + 9) + 7!) + 531 \\ 5606 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times (79 + 7))) + (5 \times 3)) + 1 \\ 5607 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (((7 \times 9) + 7!) + 5!) + (3 + 1)! \\ 5608 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + ((5 + 7) - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31)) \\ 5609 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) - ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) - ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 5610 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) + (79 \times 7)) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 5611 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) + (79 \times 7)) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 5612 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 5613 &:= (1 \times (3 + 579)) + (7! - ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\ 5614 &:= (((1 + 35) \times (7 + 9)) + (7! + 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 5615 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) + ((7!/9) + ((7! + (5 + 3)) - 1)) \\ 5616 &:= (13 \times (5! - ((7 + 9) \times 7))) \times (53 + 1) \\ 5617 &:= (((1 + (3! - (5 - 7!))) + 9) + 7) - (5 \times 31) \\ 5618 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7! + (9 \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) + 1))) \\ 5619 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 5620 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 - 7) - 9) + (75^{3-1})) \\ 5621 &:= (((1 - 3) - 579) - 7!) \times (5 - 3! \times 1) \\ 5622 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) - ((5 + 79) - ((7! - 53) - 1)) \\ 5623 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) - ((5 + 79) - ((7! - 53) \times 1)) \\ 5624 &:= ((1 + (357 \times (9 + 7))) - 5!) + 31 \\ 5625 &:= ((1 + 3) + 579) + ((7! + 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 5626 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (57 - 9)) + (7! + 531) \\ 5627 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 579) + (7! + (5 - 3))) \times 1 \\ 5628 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 \times 79)) \times ((7!/(5! \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 5629 &:= (((1 + 3!) + (5 \times 79)) \times (7!/(5! \times 3))) + 1 \\ 5630 &:= (13 + ((579 + 7!) - 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 5631 &:= ((1 + 3) + 579) + ((7! + 5) + 3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5632 &:= ((1 \times 3)!) - (((5 - 7!) - (9 - 7)) + ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 5633 &:= (1 - 3 + (579 + 7!)) + ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\ 5634 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) + 7!) - ((9 + 7) - (5 + (3!! + 1))) \\ 5635 &:= (1 + (35 + 79)) \times (7 \times (5 + 3 - 1)) \\ 5636 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) + ((97 \times 5) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 5637 &:= 1 + ((3!! + 5) + (7 - ((9 + 7) + (5! - ((3! + 1)!!)))) \\ 5638 &:= (1 - 3!) + (57 \times ((97 + 5) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 5639 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7) - 9)) + (75^{3-1}) \\ 5640 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) + (7! + (97 + (5^{3+1}))) \\ 5641 &:= (1 + (3! + 579)) + (7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 5642 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((57 \times 97) + 5!) - 31) \\ 5643 &:= (1^3 \times 57) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 + 31)) \\ 5644 &:= (((1 \times 3!!) - (5 + 7)) + ((9 + 7) - 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 5645 &:= 1 - (3! + ((5! - 7) \times (9 - (7 + (53 - 1))))) \\ 5646 &:= ((1 + 3!!) - ((5! - 7!) - (9 + 7))) - (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 5647 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) + (7 \times (5 \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 5648 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5797) - (5 \times 31) \\ 5649 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times (7 + 9)) + 7!) + 531) \\ 5650 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9))) + (7! + 531) \\ 5651 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((7 + 97) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 5652 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 \times 97)) + ((5! / (3 + 1)!)! \\ 5653 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5! - (7! - (((9 - 7) - 5!) \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 5654 &:= (1^3 + (57 \times 9)) \times (((7 - 5) \times 3!) - 1) \\ 5655 &:= (13 + 5797) - (5 \times 31) \\ 5656 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 797) - (5! \times 3! \times 1) \\ 5657 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! - 7) \times (9 - (7 + (53 - 1)))) \\ 5658 &:= ((1 + 3) + (57 \times 97)) + (5^3 \times 1) \\ 5659 &:= (13 + (5 + 7 + 9)) + (75^{3-1}) \\ 5660 &:= 1 \times (35 - (((7! - 9) - 7!) \times (5^{3+1}))) \\ 5661 &:= 1 + (35 - (((7! - 9) - 7!) \times (5^{3+1}))) \\ 5662 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + 7!) - (((97 - 5) - 3!) - 1) \\ 5663 &:= (135 + (7! + (97 \times 5))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 5664 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 + 7) \times (97 + ((5! / 3!) + 1))) \\ 5665 &:= (((1 - (3 + 5)) + 7) \times 9) + (7! + (5^{3+1})) \\ 5666 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7! - (97 + (5! - (3!! \times 1)))) \\ 5667 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5!)) + (7! - ((9 - 753) \times 1)) \\ 5668 &:= ((1 + 3!!) - ((5! - 7!) - (9 + 7))) + (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 5669 &:= ((1^{35} + 7) + (9 \times ((7! / (5 + 3)) - 1)) \\ 5670 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) \times (7 - (97 + (5! \times 3! \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5671 &:= (135 + 7) + ((9 + 7!) + (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 5672 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) + (5 \times 7)) - (((9 - 7!) + 5!) - 3! \times 1) \\ 5673 &:= ((1^3 + 5) + 7!) - (((97 - 5) - 3!!) + 1) \\ 5674 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5797)) - ((5^3) + 1) \\ 5675 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5) + 7!) - ((97 - 5) - 3!))) - 1 \\ 5676 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5) + 7!) - ((97 - 5) - 3!))) \times 1 \\ 5677 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5797)) - ((5! + 3) \times 1) \\ 5678 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 + (((7 - 9)^7) \times 5)) - ((3! + 1)!) \\ 5679 &:= ((1 + 3!))! + ((5 \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) + 5!)) - 31) \\ 5680 &:= 1 \times (((3 + (5 + 7!)) + 9) + (7 \times (5! - 31))) \\ 5681 &:= 1 + (((3 + (5 + 7!)) + 9) + (7 \times (5! - 31))) \\ 5682 &:= (1^{35}) - (7 - (9 \times (7 + (5^{3+1})))) \\ 5683 &:= (((1 + 3!))! + (5! + (7! / 9))) - (7 + (5! / (3 + 1))) \\ 5684 &:= (1^3 \times (57 \times 97)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 5685 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5!) + 7!)) + (9 + (753 - 1)) \\ 5686 &:= 13 + (5797 - ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 5687 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7 + (9 \times (7! / (5 + 3)))) + 1) \\ 5688 &:= (1 + 3!!) - (5 - (7! - ((9 + 7) + (53 - 1)))) \\ 5689 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) - (79 - (7! + (5 + 3!)))) \times 1 \\ 5690 &:= (((13 \times 5) + 7) \times 9) + (7! + (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 5691 &:= (1^3 + 5) - (79 - (7! + ((5 + 3!) - 1))) \\ 5692 &:= ((1357 - 9) + 75) \times (3 + 1) \\ 5693 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) + 7!) + ((9 \times 75) - 31) \\ 5694 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5 - 79) - (75^{3-1})) \\ 5695 &:= (1 + (3!! + (5 + 7!))) - (97 + (5 - 31)) \\ 5696 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + 7!) + ((9 - 7) + 531)) \\ 5697 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!) + (7! + (9 \times 7))) - (5! + (3! \times 1)) \\ 5698 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7! - 5)) - 31) \\ 5699 &:= (((((1^3 \times 5!) + 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5) \times 3!) - 1 \\ 5700 &:= (((((1^3 \times 5!) + 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5) \times 3!) \times 1 \\ 5701 &:= (((((1^3 \times 5!) + 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5) \times 3!) + 1 \\ 5702 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) + 7!) + (9 + (7 + 531)) \\ 5703 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) + ((7! + 9) - (75 - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 5704 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 5)^7)) + ((9 \times (7 - 5))^3 \times 1) \\ 5705 &:= 1 \times (3! - ((5 - 79) - (75^{3-1}))) \\ 5706 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 7) + 9) + (7! + 531) \\ 5707 &:= 1 + ((357 \times (9 \times (7 - 5))) - (3!! \times 1)) \\ 5708 &:= (1^3) \times ((5797 - 5!) + 31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5709 &:= (1^3) + ((5797 - 5!) + 31) \\ 5710 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7!) + (9 - ((75 - 3!) - 1)) \\ 5711 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) + (7! - (9 - 7))) - (53 \times 1) \\ 5712 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! \times 7) - (9 + 7)) - (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 5713 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! + 79)) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 5714 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5!)) + ((7! - (9 + (7 \times 5))) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 5715 &:= (1 + (3 - 5)) + ((7! - (9 + (7 \times 5))) + 3! \times 1) \\ 5716 &:= (1^3 \times (5! \times 7)) - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31) \\ 5717 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5) + 7!) - (9 + ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1)) \\ 5718 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((79 + 7!) - ((5! - 3!) + 1)) \\ 5719 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + ((7! - (9 + (7 \times 5))) + 3! \times 1) \\ 5720 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5! \times 7) - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31)) \\ 5721 &:= ((1 + 3)! - (5! - 7!)) + ((97 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\ 5722 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) + 9) + (7! + (5^{3+1})) \\ 5723 &:= (13 + (5 + 79)) \times ((7 + 53) - 1) \\ 5724 &:= (1 + 35) \times ((79 + 75) + (3! - 1)) \\ 5725 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5) + 7!) - ((9 + 7) - 5) + (3! + 1) \\ 5726 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) - (79 - (7! + (5!/3)))) - 1 \\ 5727 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7! - 97)) - (5! + ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 5728 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) + (((7! + 97) - 5!) - (3! - 1)) \\ 5729 &:= ((1^3 \times (5! - 7)) - 9) + (75^{3-1}) \\ 5730 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 + 7!) + ((9 \times 75) + 3 + 1)) \\ 5731 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - (7 - ((9 + 7!) - (5! + 31))) \\ 5732 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - (5! - ((797 + (5 \times 3)) \times 1))) \\ 5733 &:= (((1^3 + 5)! + 7!) - (((9 \times 7) - 5) - 31)) \\ 5734 &:= (1 - (3 + 5!)) \times (((7 + (9 \times 7)) - 5!) + 3) \times 1) \\ 5735 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - 7!) + (5 - (3 + 1)!)) \\ 5736 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + ((57 \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 5737 &:= 135 + (7! - ((9 \times 7) - (5^{3+1}))) \\ 5738 &:= (1 - (3! - 5797)) - (53 + 1) \\ 5739 &:= (1 - (3! - 5797)) - (53 \times 1) \\ 5740 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((57 + 9) + (753 + 1)) \\ 5741 &:= ((1 - 3!) - 5) + (7! + (9 \times ((75 + 3) + 1))) \\ 5742 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - (((5 \times 7) - (9 + 7!)) - 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 5743 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) + 7!)) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 5744 &:= (1^3 + 5797) - (53 + 1) \\ 5745 &:= (1^3 + 5797) - (53 \times 1) \\ 5746 &:= 13 \times (((5 \times 79) - 7) + (53 + 1)) \\ 5747 &:= ((1^3 \times (5! - 7)) + 9) + (75^{3-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5748 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 5) + (7! + 97) - 5!) + (3! \times 1) \\ 5749 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (((7! - 9) - 7) + 5)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 5750 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 5751 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (((5 - 7) + 9)! - (((7 - 5)^3) + 1)) \\ 5752 &:= 1 - ((3 - (5 + 79)) \times (75 - (3 + 1))) \\ 5753 &:= 13 + (((5! - 79) \times 7) \times 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 5754 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7 \times 97)) + ((5 + 3 - 1)! \\ 5755 &:= (1 + 3) + (5 + (7! + ((9 \times 75) + 31))) \\ 5756 &:= (13 + 5797) - (53 + 1) \\ 5757 &:= (13 + 5797) - (53 \times 1) \\ 5758 &:= (13 + 5797) - (53 - 1) \\ 5759 &:= (((1^{3!})^5) + 7!) - (9 - (7 + (5! \times (3! \times 1)))) \\ 5760 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (5! \times (((7 - 9)^{7-5}) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 5761 &:= 1 - ((3 + ((5! - 7) \times (9 - (7 + 53)))) \times 1) \\ 5762 &:= (1^3 \times (5 - 7)) + (9 + (7! - (5 - 3! \times 1))) \\ 5763 &:= (((1 - (3 + 5)) \times 7) + 97) \times 5! + (3 \times 1) \\ 5764 &:= (((1^3 + 5)! - (7 + 9)) + (7! + (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 5765 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5))^7 9) + ((7! + (5 + 3!)) + 1) \\ 5766 &:= (1 - (3! - 5797)) + (5 - 31) \\ 5767 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7!) + ((9 + 753) - 1) \\ 5768 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7!) + ((9 + 753) \times 1) \\ 5769 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5797) - (53 - 1) \\ 5770 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + (7! - ((9 - 753) \times 1)) \\ 5771 &:= (1^3 \times (5797 + 5)) - 31 \\ 5772 &:= (1 - 3!) + (5! + ((7! + (9 + 7)) - ((5! - 3!) - 1))) \\ 5773 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((7! - 9) + (753 - 1)) \\ 5774 &:= 13 + ((5797 - 5) - 31) \\ 5775 &:= 1 \times ((3 - 5!) + ((7 + 975) \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 5776 &:= 1 + ((3 - 5!) + ((7 + 975) \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 5777 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5)) \times (79 - (7 + 5))) + ((3! + 1)! \\ 5778 &:= (1^3) \times ((5797 + 5) - (3 + 1)! \\ 5779 &:= (1^3) + ((5797 + 5) - (3 + 1)! \\ 5780 &:= (((1^3 + 5)! + 7!) - (9 + 7)) + (5 + 31) \\ 5781 &:= (1 + 3) + (5797 - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 5782 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5797 - 5)) - (3! - 1) \\ 5783 &:= (1^3) + ((5797 - (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 5784 &:= (1^3 + (5797 - (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\ 5785 &:= (1^3) \times (5797 - (5 + (3! + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5786 &:= (1^3) + (5797 - (5 + (3! + 1))) \\ 5787 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) - 5) - 31) \\ 5788 &:= (1 - (3 - 5797)) - (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 5789 &:= (1 + 3) + (5797 - (5 + (3! + 1))) \\ 5790 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5797)) - (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 5791 &:= 1 \times ((3! - (5 - 7!)) - ((9 + 7) - (53 - 1))) \\ 5792 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5797 - 5)) + (3! - 1) \\ 5793 &:= 1 \times ((3 + (5797 - 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 5794 &:= 1 + ((3 + (5797 - 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 5795 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 - 7!)) + ((9 + 753) \times 1) \\ 5796 &:= 1 - (3 - ((5797 + 5) - (3 + 1))) \\ 5797 &:= ((1^3) + ((5 \times 79) + (7! + (5! \times 3)))) + 1 \\ 5798 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7! - 9)) + (753 - 1) \\ 5799 &:= ((1^3 + (5797 + 5)) - 3) - 1 \\ 5800 &:= ((1^3 + (5797 + 5)) - 3) \times 1 \\ 5801 &:= ((1^3 + (5797 + 5)) - 3) + 1 \\ 5802 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5797)) + 5) - (3 + 1) \\ 5803 &:= (1 \times (3! + (5797 - 5))) + (3! - 1) \\ 5804 &:= (1 \times (3! + ((5797 + 5) - 3))) - 1 \\ 5805 &:= (1 \times (3! + ((5797 + 5) - 3))) \times 1 \\ 5806 &:= (1 \times (3! + ((5797 + 5) - 3))) + 1 \\ 5807 &:= (13 + 5797) - (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 5808 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5797)) + (5 + 3)) - 1 \\ 5809 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5797)) + (5 + 3)) \times 1 \\ 5810 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5797)) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 5811 &:= 1 + ((3 + 5797) + (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 5812 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) + 5) + 31 \\ 5813 &:= (13 + 5797) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 5814 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (57 \times ((9 + (75/3)) \times 1)) \\ 5815 &:= ((1^3 - (5 - (7! + (9 \times 7)))) - (5 - 3!)) + 1 \\ 5816 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times (7 + 9)) + (7 \times (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 5817 &:= (13 + 5797) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 5818 &:= (1 - (3! - 5797)) - (5 - 31) \\ 5819 &:= (1 - (3!/5!)) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (53 - 1))) \\ 5820 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + ((5! - 7) - 9)) \times 7) + (53 - 1) \\ 5821 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + ((5! - 7) - 9)) \times 7) + (53 \times 1) \\ 5822 &:= ((1 - 3!) + 5797) + (5 \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 5823 &:= 135 + (79 \times (75 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 5824 &:= 13 \times (579 - ((7 + (5^3)) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5825 &:= ((13 + 57) \times 9) + (7! + 5 \times 31) \\ 5826 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - 7) \times (((97 \times 5) \times 3!) + 1)) \\ 5827 &:= (1^3 + (5797 + 5)) + (3 + 1)! \\ 5828 &:= (((13 + 57) - 9) + 7) + 5! \times 31 \\ 5829 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5797 - (5 - 31)) \\ 5830 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79)) - 7!) \times (5 - (3! \times 1)) \\ 5831 &:= (1 - 3 + 5797) + (5 + 31) \\ 5832 &:= (1^{357}) \times (((9 \times (7 - 5))^3) \times 1) \\ 5833 &:= (((((1^3 + 5)!) + 7!) - (9 + 7)) + 5!) - 31 \\ 5834 &:= (13 + 57 + ((9 + 7!) - 5)) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 5835 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + 79) + ((7! - (5! + 3)) - 1) \\ 5836 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5797 + 5) + 31) \\ 5837 &:= (1 \times (357 \times (9 + 7))) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 5838 &:= ((1 \times (357 \times (9 + 7))) + (5^3)) + 1 \\ 5839 &:= (1 + ((357 \times (9 + 7)) + (5^3))) + 1 \\ 5840 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 5841 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5!) + (79 + 7!)) + ((5! + 3) - 1) \\ 5842 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5!) + (7! + ((9 + 75) - (3 - 1))) \\ 5843 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (79 \times ((7 + 53) + 1)) \\ 5844 &:= ((13 + 5) + 7!) - ((9 - 75) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 5845 &:= (1 - (3! - 5797)) + (53 \times 1) \\ 5846 &:= 13 + (5797 + (5 + 31)) \\ 5847 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7 - (9 \times (75 - 3!)))) - 1 \\ 5848 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 + 79) + (7! + ((5 + 3!) - 1))) \\ 5849 &:= (1^3 - (5 - 7!)) + (((97 - 5) + 3!) + 1) \\ 5850 &:= (1^3 \times 5797) + (53 \times 1) \\ 5851 &:= (1^3 + 5797) + (53 \times 1) \\ 5852 &:= (1^3 + 5797) + (53 + 1) \\ 5853 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5 + 7) + ((9 + 7) - 5!)) - ((3! + 1)!) \\ 5854 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 7!)) + (9 \times 7)) + (5 + 31) \\ 5855 &:= ((13 + (5! \times 7)) - 9) + ((7! - 5) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 5856 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) \times ((7 \times 97) + (53 \times 1)) \\ 5857 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5797 + 53) + 1) \\ 5858 &:= (13 + 5) + ((7! - (9 - (7 \times 5!))) - 31) \\ 5859 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + ((7 + 97) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 5860 &:= (1 + ((3! \times (57 - 9)) + 7!)) + 531 \\ 5861 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)!)! - (((7 + 9) - (7! + 5!)) + 3) \times 1) \\ 5862 &:= ((13 + 5797) + 53) - 1 \\ 5863 &:= (13 + 5797) + (53 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 5864** := (13 + 5797) + (53 + 1)
5865 := (1 + ((3!! + 5!) × 7)) + ((9 + 7) × ((5 - 3!) × 1))
5866 := ((1 + 3!!)! + ((57 + (9 - 7)) × ((5 × 3) - 1))
5867 := (((1 + 3) - 5) + 7) × (975 + 3) - 1
5868 := 1 × ((3! × (5! + (7 + ((9 + 7) - 5)))) + ((3! + 1)!))
5869 := 1 + ((3! × (5! + (7 + ((9 + 7) - 5)))) + ((3! + 1)!))
5870 := (((1 × 3!!) - (5 - (7 × 9))) + (7! + 53)) - 1
5871 := (((1 × 3!!) - (5 - (7 × 9))) + (7! + 53)) × 1
5872 := (1 + 3!) - ((5! - 7!) - ((9 × (7 × 5)) × (3 × 1)))
5873 := ((1 + (3 × 5!)) - (7 - (97 × 5))) × (3! + 1)
5874 := 1 - (3 + ((5! - 7) × ((9 - (7 + 53)) - 1)))
5875 := (13 + (5 + 7)) × (9 + ((75 × 3) + 1))
5876 := (((1 × (35/7)) - 9) + (7! + 5!)) + 3!! × 1
5877 := ((1 + 3)⁵) + (((7! - (9 × 7)) - (5³)) + 1)
5878 := ((1 + (3 × 5)) + ((7! + 97) + 5)) + ((3! × 1)!)
5879 := (((1 × 3!!)! + 5!) × ((7 + 9) - ((7 + 5) - 3))) - 1
5880 := ((1 + 3)! × 5) × ((7! / (97 + (5 + 3))) + 1)
5881 := 1 - ((35 × 7) × ((9 - (7 - 5)) - 31))
5882 := ((1 + 3!) × (5! × 7)) + ((9 + 7) / (5 + 3 × 1))
5883 := ((1 × (3 + 5)) + 7!) - ((9 - (7 × 5!)) - (3 + 1))
5884 := (1 - 3 + (5797 + 5!)) - 31
5885 := (1³) × ((5! × (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3!-1}))
5886 := ((1³ × 5797) + 5!) - 31
5887 := ((1 + (3!! + 57)) + (9 + 7!)) + (5! / (3 - 1))
5888 := (((1 + (3 + 5)) + 7) × (97 - 5)) × (3 + 1)
5889 := ((1 - (3! × (57 × 9))) + 7!) × (5 - (3 - 1))
5890 := ((1 + 3!!)! + ((5 + (7 × (97 × 5)))) / (3 + 1))
5891 := ((1 - 3)⁵) + (((79 × 75) - 3) + 1)
5892 := (1 × (35 + 7)) + (975 × 3! × 1)
5893 := 13 + (((5! × 7) + (9 + (7! - 5))) - (3 + 1))
5894 := (1 + 3) - ((5! - 7!) - (97 × (5 × (3 - 1))))
5895 := (((((1³ + 5)! + 7!) - (9 + 7)) + 5!) + 31
5896 := 1 + ((3!! + (5! + 7!)) + (((9 + 7) + 5) - (3! × 1)))
5897 := (1 + ((3 - 5!) + 7!)) + ((975 - 3) + 1)
5898 := (((1^{3!})⁵) + (7! + ((9 + 7) + 5!))) + 3!! + 1
5899 := (1 - 3!) + ((5! + (7! - 9)) + (753 × 1))
5900 := ((1 + 357) - (9 × 7)) × (5! / (3! × 1))
5901 := (((1 + 3) + 5) + ((7 + 975) × 3!)) × 1
5902 := 13 - ((5 - (79 × 75)) + 31)
5903 := (((1 × 3) × 5!) + ((7! - 97) - (5! - 3!))) × 1
5904 := (1³ × (5! + 7!)) - ((9 - 753) × 1)
5905 := ((1 + 3!!) + 5) + (7! - (9 + (7 - (5 × 31))))
5906 := (1 - 3) + ((57 + (975 × 3!)) + 1)
5907 := 13 + ((5 + 7!) + (((9 + 7) × 53) + 1))
5908 := 1 × ((3!! + (((5 + 7) + (9 + 7)) + 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!))
5909 := (((1 × 3) × 5) + (79 × 75)) - 31
5910 := 1 + (3!! + ((5! + 7!) - ((9 - (7 × 5)) - (3 × 1))))
5911 := ((1 + 3) × 5) + (((7 + 975) × 3!) - 1)
5912 := ((1³ + 5)! + (7! + (((9 × 7) + 5!) - 31))
5913 := ((1 + 3!) - (5 - (79 × 75))) - 31
5914 := ((1 + (3!! + 5)) × 7) + ((9 + 7) × (53 - 1))
5915 := ((1 - 3 × 5) + (79 × 75)) + (3 + 1)
5916 := (1 + (3 + 5797)) + ((5! - 3!) + 1)
5917 := (1 + (3 × 5)) + ((79 × 75) - (3 + 1)!)
5918 := 1 × 3 + ((5797 + 5!) - (3 - 1))
5919 := (1 + 3) + (5797 + (5! - (3 - 1)))
5920 := ((1 + 3) - 5) + (((79 × 75) - 3) - 1)
5921 := ((1³)⁵) × (((79 × 75) - 3) - 1)
5922 := ((1³)⁵) + (((79 × 75) - 3) - 1)
5923 := (1 × (3 + 5797)) + ((5! + 3) × 1)
5924 := 1 × (((3 + 5797) + (5³)) - 1)
5925 := 1 + (((3 + 5797) + (5³)) - 1)
5926 := (1 × (3 + 5797)) + ((5³) + 1)
5927 := (((1 + (3!! - (5 - 7!))) + 9) + 7) + (5 × 31)
5928 := 13 × ((5 - ((7 - 9) × (75 × 3))) + 1)
5929 := ((1 × 35) + (79 × 75)) - 31
5930 := (13 - (5 - (79 × 75))) - (3 × 1)
5931 := (1 × (3 + 5)) + (((79 × 75) - 3) + 1)
5932 := (1³ - (57 × (9 - (7 × 5)))) × (3 + 1)
5933 := (1 + (357 - 9)) × (7 + (5 × (3 - 1)))
5934 := 13 + (5797 + ((5³) - 1))
5935 := ((1 - 3 × 5) + (79 × 75)) + (3 + 1)!
5936 := (13 - (5 - (79 × 75))) + (3 × 1)
5937 := (((1 + 3)⁵) + 7!) - (((9 - 7) + 5!) + (3! - 1))
5938 := ((1 × 3!!)! + (5! + ((7! + (97 - (5! / 3))) + 1))
5939 := ((1 × 3!) × 5!) + (((7 × 9) + (7! + 5!)) - (3 + 1))
5940 := (1 × 3) × (((5 - 7) × 9) × ((7 - 5!) + 3 × 1))
5941 := (((((1 × 3!!)! - 57) × 9) - 75 / 3) - 1

$$\begin{aligned}
 5942 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! - 57) \times 9 - ((75/3) \times 1) \\
 5943 &:= (((((1 \times 3)!)! - 57) \times 9) - 75/3) + 1 \\
 5944 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! \times 7) - (9 \times (753 \times 1))) \\
 5945 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (5797 + 5!)) + (3 + 1) \\
 5946 &:= (1 - 3 + (5797 + 5!)) + 31 \\
 5947 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) - 5)) - ((3! - 1))! \\
 5948 &:= ((1^3 \times 5797) + 5!) + 31 \\
 5949 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!)! + (7! + (9 \times 7))) + (5! + (3! \times 1)) \\
 5950 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + (79 \times 75))) - 3! \times 1 \\
 5951 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (57 - 9)) + 7!) + ((5! \times 3!) - 1) \\
 5952 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (57 - 9)) + (7! + (5! \times (3 - 1))) \\
 5953 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + (79 \times 75))) - (3 \times 1) \\
 5954 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5 - ((79 \times 75) + 31)) \\
 5955 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5! \times 7)) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) + ((3! + 1))!) \\
 5956 &:= (((1^3 + (5! + 79)) + 7!) - 5) + (3!! + 1) \\
 5957 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! \times 7) + ((9 + 7) - 5))) \times (3! + 1) \\
 5958 &:= (1 + (((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7) \times 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\
 5959 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + (79 \times 75))) + (3 \times 1) \\
 5960 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 + 7)) \times (9 - (753 + 1)) \\
 5961 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + (7! - 9)) - (7! / ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\
 5962 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + (79 \times 75))) + 3! \times 1 \\
 5963 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + 57) - ((9 - 7!) - (5 \times 31))) \\
 5964 &:= (1 + (((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7) \times 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\
 5965 &:= (13 + 5797) + (5 \times 31) \\
 5966 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - 5) - (((7 - 97) - 5!) - (3!! + 1))) \\
 5967 &:= (1 \times (3! + (5 \times ((7 + 9) - 7)))) \times (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\
 5968 &:= (1 + ((3^5 + 7) \times 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\
 5969 &:= ((13 + (5 + 7)) \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) - 31 \\
 5970 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + 7!) + ((97 + 5!) + 3!! \times 1) \\
 5971 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (79 \times 75)) + 31 \\
 5972 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5) + 7!) + (((97 - 5) + 3!!) \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5973 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5) + 7!) + (((97 - 5) + 3!!) + 1) \\
 5974 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) - (79 - ((7! - 5) - 3!))) \times 1 \\
 5975 &:= ((1 + 3)! - (5 - (79 \times 75))) + 31 \\
 5976 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) - (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times 5)) \times 3! \times 1 \\
 5977 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 - 7!)) + (975 - 31) \\
 5978 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + ((7! + 97) - (5! \times 3!))) + 1 \\
 5979 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (7! - ((5 - (3 - 1))!)) \\
 5980 &:= ((1^{3!}) - (5 + (7 - (9 \times 7)))) \times (5! - (3! - 1)) \\
 5981 &:= ((1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9)) + 7!) - (5! / (3 + 1)!) \\
 5982 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times ((5 - 7) + (975 + (3 + 1)!)) \\
 5983 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - 5!))) - (3 + 1)! \\
 5984 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) - 79) + 7!) + (5 - (3! \times 1))) \\
 5985 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7975) / (3 + 1)) \\
 5986 &:= (((1^3)^5) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 5987 &:= ((13 \times (57 + 9)) + 7!) + (5! - 31) \\
 5988 &:= (1 - 35) + ((7! + (975 + 3!)) + 1) \\
 5989 &:= (1 + (3!! - 5)) + (7! + ((9 + (75 \times 3)) - 1)) \\
 5990 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5! + 7) + 9) \times (75 - 31)) \\
 5991 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (79 \times 75)) + 31 \\
 5992 &:= (((((1 \times 3)!)! - 57) \times 9) + ((75/3) \times 1)) \\
 5993 &:= 1 + ((35 - 7) \times (97 + (5! - (3 \times 1)))) \\
 5994 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 57) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!)) \\
 5995 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 - ((7 + 9) \times 75))) \times (3! - 1) \\
 5996 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) + 5!) + ((7 \times 9) + ((7! + 53) \times 1)) \\
 5997 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - (5 + 7)) + (975 - 3! \times 1)) \\
 5998 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) + (7! - (9 - (7!/5)))) - 31 \\
 5999 &:= 13 - ((5 - (7! + 975)) + (3 + 1)!) \\
 6000 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) + (7^{9-7})) \times (5^3 \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

2.4 Numbers From 6001 to 8000

$$\begin{aligned}
 6001 &:= (1 - 3!!) + ((5 + 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times (3! + 1)))) \\
 6002 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (((7! - (9 \times 7)) + (5 - 3)) - 1) \\
 6003 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! \times (7^{9-7})) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!)) \\
 6004 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - (5! - ((79 \times 7) + 531))) \\
 6005 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) - 79) + (7! + (5! / (3! \times 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6006 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5 + 7)) - 9) \times (7 \times (5 - 31)) \\
 6007 &:= 135 + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times (53 - 1))) \\
 6008 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7!) - (9 - ((7!/5) + 3 \times 1)) \\
 6009 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times 5) - (3! + 1) \\
 6010 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) + ((7! + (975 + 3)) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6011 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 7!)) + (97 \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 6012 &:= (13 + (57 + 97)) \times (5 + 31) \\ 6013 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - ((7^{9-7}) \times (5 + 31)) \\ 6014 &:= (1 + (3!! + (5 + 7!))) + (97 + (5! + 31)) \\ 6015 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! - (9 \times (7 - 5))) - 31) \\ 6016 &:= 1 \times ((3^5 + ((79 \times 7) \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 6017 &:= 1 + ((3^5 + ((79 \times 7) \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 6018 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + 5!) + (7! - ((97 - 5!) \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 6019 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5 - (7 - 975))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 6020 &:= (135 \times 7) + (9 + (7! - (5 - 31))) \\ 6021 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times (5! \times 7)) + 975) + 3!) \times 1 \\ 6022 &:= 1 + (((3! \times (5! \times 7)) + 975) + 3!) \times 1 \\ 6023 &:= 1 + (((3! \times (5! \times 7)) + 975) + 3!) + 1 \\ 6024 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times ((5 - 7) + (975 + 31)) \\ 6025 &:= (13 - 5) + (7! + ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\ 6026 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 5) \times 79) + ((7! + 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 6027 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) - (((9 - 7)^5) + (3! - 1)) \\ 6028 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) + (7! + ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\ 6029 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5 + ((7 + 975) + 3))) - 1 \\ 6030 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + ((7! - 9) + (7 \times 5))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 6031 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - 5!))) + (3 + 1)! \\ 6032 &:= ((1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) + 9) + ((7 \times 5)^{3-1}) \\ 6033 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 579) + (7 \times 531) \\ 6034 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + ((5 \times 79) + ((7! - 5!) - 3))) + 1 \\ 6035 &:= (13 + 5) + (7! + ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\ 6036 &:= ((13 + 5) + (7! + 975)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 6037 &:= (1^{3!}) - ((5 + 7) - ((9 \times 7) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!))) \\ 6038 &:= (((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times 7) \times 9) + ((7! + 53) \times 1) \\ 6039 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 - 7!) - 975) - 31) \\ 6040 &:= (((1 + 3!!) + 5!) \times 7) - ((9 - 7) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 6041 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)! + 7!) - 9) + ((7!/5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 6042 &:= (1 - ((3 - 57) + 9) - 7) \times (5! - (3! \times 1)) \\ 6043 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + 7!) - 9) + (((7!/5) + 3!) \times 1) \\ 6044 &:= (1 + ((3! \times (5! - 7)) \times 9)) - (7 + (53 - 1)) \\ 6045 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7! + 975)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 6046 &:= (13 \times ((5 + 79) - 7)) + (5 + ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 6047 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) - (9 - (7 - (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 6048 &:= 13579 - 7531 \\ 6049 &:= (1 + ((3!! + (57 - 9)) + 7!)) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6050 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + 7!) + 9) + (((7!/5) - 3!) + 1) \\ 6051 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + ((7! + 975) + 31) \\ 6052 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)! + 7!) + (975 + 31)) \\ 6053 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) + ((79 \times 75) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 6054 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7! + 975)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 6055 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + 79) \times ((75 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 6056 &:= (((13 \times 57) + 9) + 7) \times ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 6057 &:= 135 + ((79 \times 75) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 6058 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 + 7))) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!)) \\ 6059 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 7)) - (9 \times (75 - (3!! + 1))) \\ 6060 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) + (7! - (9 - (7!/5)))) + 31 \\ 6061 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7! + 9) + (7!/5))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 6062 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) + (7 + 9 + ((7!/5) \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 6063 &:= 135 + ((79 \times 75) + 3 \times 1) \\ 6064 &:= 13 + ((5! + (79 \times 75)) + 3! \times 1) \\ 6065 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (7! - 5)) - (3! - 1) \\ 6066 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + ((57 + 9) + 7!)) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 6067 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + ((7! + (5 + 3!)) - 1) \\ 6068 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) - ((7 - (9 + 7!)) - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 6069 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (5 - (7 - ((9 \times (75 \times 3)) \times 1)))) \\ 6070 &:= 1 + (3 \times (5 - (7 - ((9 \times (75 \times 3)) \times 1)))) \\ 6071 &:= 1 \times (((3^5 + (7! + (9 \times 7))) + 5) + 3!! \times 1) \\ 6072 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5! + 79)) + (7! - ((5! \times 3) + 1)) \\ 6073 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + ((7!/9) + 7!)) - (5 - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 6074 &:= 1 \times (((35 + 7!) + 975) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 6075 &:= 1 + (((35 + 7!) + 975) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 6076 &:= (1 + (3 + 5!)) \times (7 + ((9 - 7) + (5!/ (3 \times 1)))) \\ 6077 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (7! - 5)) + (3! + 1) \\ 6078 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + (9 + 7!) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 6079 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5) + 7!) + ((9 \times (7 - 5))^{3-1}) \\ 6080 &:= (((1^{35}) - 79)^{7-5}) - (3 + 1) \\ 6081 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7!)) - (5! + (3 + 1)!) \\ 6082 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + (9 + 7!) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 6083 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + (7!/9)) + ((7! + 5) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 6084 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) - 9) \times ((7!/5!) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 6085 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5 + (7!/ (9 + 7)))) + (5 + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 6086 &:= (1 - 35) \times ((7 - 97) - (5! - 31)) \\ 6087 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5 - 7!) + 9) - (7 \times (5! + 31))) \\ 6088 &:= (((1^{35}) - 79)^{7-5}) + (3 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6089 &:= (((((1-3!) \times 5!) \times (7-9)) + 7!) - 5!) - 31 \\ 6090 &:= (13 + ((5! + 7) + (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times 3! \times 1) \\ 6091 &:= 1 + ((3!! + (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 6092 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) - (5! + 79)) + (7! + 531) \\ 6093 &:= (1^{3!}) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) - 31)) \\ 6094 &:= (1^{3!}) + ((5 + 7!) - ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) - 31)) \\ 6095 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - 7!)) + ((9 - 7) \times 531) \\ 6096 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + ((7 \times 53) + 1)) \\ 6097 &:= 13 \times (((5 \times 7) - 97) + 531) \\ 6098 &:= ((1 \times (35 + 7!)) - (9 \times (7 - 5!))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 6099 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7!)) - ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) - 31) \\ 6100 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) \times 5) - (7! - (9 + 7531)) \\ 6101 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) \times 7)) - (9 \times (((7 \times 5) - 3!!) + 1)) \\ 6102 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) + (7 + 97)) \times (53 + 1) \\ 6103 &:= 1 + ((35 + 7 + 975) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 6104 &:= (1 \times ((35/7!) \times 9)) + ((7! - (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\ 6105 &:= (1 \times ((35/7!) \times 9)) + ((7! - (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 6106 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7!) + ((97 \times (5 + 3!)) - 1) \\ 6107 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + (7! + ((9 - 7) \times 531)) \\ 6108 &:= (1^{35}) + (7! + ((97 \times (5 + 3!)) \times 1)) \\ 6109 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7) - ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 6110 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 + 7!)) + ((9 - 7) \times 531) \\ 6111 &:= (1 + (3! \times (5! - 7))) \times (((9 + 7) - (5 + 3)) + 1) \\ 6112 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) - 79) + (7! + 5!)) + (3! + 1)) \\ 6113 &:= (((1 + 3!)!) - (5 + 7)) + ((97 + 5!) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 6114 &:= (((1 - 3!) - (5! \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times 5))) + 3!!) - 1 \\ 6115 &:= (((1 - 3!) - (5! \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times 5))) + 3!!) \times 1 \\ 6116 &:= (13 - 57) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 6117 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + ((79 + 7) \times 53)) - 1 \\ 6118 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + ((79 + 7) \times 53)) \times 1 \\ 6119 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times 9) + (7! - (5 + 3 \times 1))) \\ 6120 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) \times ((7 \times 97) + (5 - (3 + 1))) \\ 6121 &:= ((1 - (3 \times (5 - (7 \times 9)))) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 6122 &:= (((((1 + 3!)!) + (5! - 7!)) \times 9) + ((7! - 5) + (3! + 1))) \\ 6123 &:= (1 \times ((35/7!) \times 9)) + (7! + ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\ 6124 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5 - 7!) - 9) - ((7 \times 5) \times 31)) \\ 6125 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7! - (9 \times 7))) + ((5^3) - 1) \\ 6126 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7! - (9 \times 7))) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 6127 &:= 135 + (7! + (((9 + 7) + 5!) \times (3! + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6128 &:= ((1^3 \times (5! + (7! + 975))) - 3!) - 1 \\ 6129 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) \times ((7 \times 9) - (7 - (5^{3+1}))) \\ 6130 &:= (1 + 3!!) + (((5 \times 79) + (7! + 5)) - 31) \\ 6131 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - (7 + 531) \\ 6132 &:= (1^3 \times (5! + 7!)) + (975 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 6133 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5!)) + (7! + (97 \times (5 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 6134 &:= (1 - (3! - 5)) + (7! + (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\ 6135 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) + (9 + ((7 - 5) \times 31)) \\ 6136 &:= (13 \times (5 - 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 6137 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5!)) \times ((7 + (9 + (7 \times 5)))/(3 \times 1)) \\ 6138 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) + (7! + ((975 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 6139 &:= (1^3) + ((5! + 7!) + (975 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 6140 &:= (1^3 \times (5! + (7! + 975))) + (3! - 1) \\ 6141 &:= (1 + ((3!!/5!) + (7! + 9))) + (7 \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 6142 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times 79) + ((7! - 5)/(3! - 1)) \\ 6143 &:= ((1 - (3!!/(5 + 7))) \times ((9 + 7) - 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\ 6144 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 \times (7 + ((9 \times 7) - 5!)))) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 6145 &:= (((13 + 5) + 7) \times 97) + (5! \times 31) \\ 6146 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (((7 \times 9) + 7!) - 5)) + (3 + 1)! \\ 6147 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! - ((7 \times 9) - 7)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!)) \\ 6148 &:= ((1^{3!}) + (((5! - 7) + 9) - 7)) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 6149 &:= 13 \times ((579 - ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) - 1) \\ 6150 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((7! - 9) + (7 \times (5^3 \times 1))) \\ 6151 &:= (1^{3!}) + ((579 + 7!) + 531) \\ 6152 &:= 1 + (((((3 + 5) \times 7) \times 97) + (5! \times 3!)) - 1) \\ 6153 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 6154 &:= ((1 + (3 + 579)) + 7!) + 531 \\ 6155 &:= (1 - 3 + (57 \times (9 \times ((7 - 5) \times 3!)))) + 1 \\ 6156 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) + 7!) + (((9 - 7)^5) \times 31) \\ 6157 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) + 7!)/(9 - 7)) + (5^{3!-1})) \\ 6158 &:= (1 + (3!! + (((5 \times 79) + 7) - 5))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 6159 &:= (((1 + (3! \times 5)) + 79) + ((7!/5) \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 6160 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5) \times (7!/9)) - (7! - (5 - (3 + 1)))) \\ 6161 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times (5! - 7)) \times 9) + (7 + (53 - 1))) \\ 6162 &:= (1 + ((3! \times (5! - 7)) \times 9)) + (7 + (53 - 1)) \\ 6163 &:= (13 + 579) + (7! + 531) \\ 6164 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 79)) + (7! + ((5 + 3!) \times 1)) \\ 6165 &:= (1 \times ((3! + (5! - 7)) \times 9)) + (7! + (53 + 1)) \\ 6166 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7!/9)) + (7! + 531) \end{aligned}$$

- 6167** := $((1 - (3 + 5)) + 7!) + (((9 \times (7!/5!)) \times 3) \times 1)$
6168 := $((1 + (35 \times 7)) + (9 + 7)) - 5 \times (3 + 1)!$
6169 := $1 \times 3 + ((5! + 7!) + (975 + 31))$
6170 := $(13 - 5) + (79 \times ((75 + 3) \times 1))$
6171 := $(13 - 5) + ((79 \times (75 + 3)) + 1)$
6172 := $((1 + (3 \times 5 \times 79)) + 7!) - (53 + 1)$
6173 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) + (7! - (53 - 1))$
6174 := $((1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) + 1)$
6175 := $13 \times ((579 - ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) + 1)$
6176 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((79 \times (75 + 3)) - 1)$
6177 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (79 \times ((75 + 3) \times 1))$
6178 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((79 \times (75 + 3)) + 1)$
6179 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((79 + 7!) + (5 + 31))$
6180 := $((1 \times (3! - 5)) - 7) \times (9 - ((7!/5) + 31))$
6181 := $((1 + 3)^5 + 7!) + ((9 - 7) - 5) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
6182 := $(1^3 - (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5^{3+1}))$
6183 := $((1 \times 3)!)! - (5! - (7! + ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1))))))$
6184 := $(1 + 3)! + ((5 \times 79) + (7! + ((5 + 3!) \times 1)))$
6185 := $((1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7))) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! - 31)$
6186 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 - (9 - (7! + 5!))) + 3 + 1)$
6187 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! - ((9 - 7) - 5!)) + (3! - 1))$
6188 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) \times ((97 + (5^3)) - 1)$
6189 := $1 \times ((357 + ((9 \times (7 - 5))^3)) \times 1)$
6190 := $1 + ((357 + ((9 \times (7 - 5))^3)) \times 1)$
6191 := $((1 + 3)^5 + 7!) + ((9 - 7) + 5!) + (3! - 1)$
6192 := $(1 + 3)! \times (((5 + (7 - 9)))! \times ((7 + 5) + 31))$
6193 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - ((797 - 5) \times (3 - 1))$
6194 := $((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5)) + 3 - 1$
6195 := $((1^{3!}) - (5 - (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 \times 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
6196 := $((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5)) + 3 + 1$
6197 := $(1 \times (3!! \times 5)) + ((7^{9-7}) \times (53 \times 1))$
6198 := $1 + ((3!! \times 5) + ((7^{9-7}) \times (53 \times 1)))$
6199 := $1357 + (9 \times (7 + 531))$
6200 := $((13 \times (5 + 7)) + (9 + (7 \times 5))) \times 31$
6201 := $1 \times ((3 - 5!) \times ((7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5) + 3)) + 1)$
6202 := $((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5) - (3 - 1)$
6203 := $1 \times (3 - ((57 - 97) \times (5 \times 31)))$
6204 := $(13 \times 5!) + ((79 + 7) \times (53 + 1))$
6205 := $(1 - 357) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31})$
6206 := $((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5) + (3 - 1)$
6207 := $((1 + 3)^5) + (7! - 97) + (5! + ((3! - 1)!)!$
6208 := $(13 - 5) \times (797 - ((5!/3!) + 1))$
6209 := $((1 - 3)^5) + (79 \times (75 + 3 + 1))$
6210 := $(135 + (79 - 7)) \times (5!/(3 + 1))$
6211 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - 7 + ((9 \times 7) \times 53) - 1$
6212 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - 7 + ((9 \times 7) \times 53) \times 1$
6213 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - 7 + ((9 \times 7) \times 53) + 1$
6214 := $(1 - 35) + ((79^{7-5}) + (3! + 1))$
6215 := $(1 \times 35) + (7! + ((9 \times (7 + 5!)) - (3 \times 1)))$
6216 := $(1 + 3)! \times ((5 - 7) + (9 + (7 \times (5 + 31))))$
6217 := $1 + ((35 - 7) \times (97 + ((5^3) \times 1)))$
6218 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + (7! - ((5 + 3) - 1))$
6219 := $((1 \times 3)^5 + 7!) + 97 + ((5! + 3!) - 1)$
6220 := $(1 + (3!! + 5)) + ((7! + (97 \times 5)) - 31)$
6221 := $((1 - ((3 - 5)^7)) \times 9) + 7! + (5!/3! \times 1)$
6222 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) \times (((7 - 9) - 7) \times 5) - 3! \times 1$
6223 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times 9) + 7!) + (5! - (3 + 1)!)!$
6224 := $((1 + 3!)! + 5!) - (7 + (9 \times (7 - (5! + (3! \times 1))))))$
6225 := $((1 \times 3!) - (57 + (9 - 7))) + 531$
6226 := $(1 - 3 + (5! + 7!)) + ((97 \times (5 + 3!)) + 1)$
6227 := $1 \times 3 + (5! + (((7 \times 975) - 3!) - 1))$
6228 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((5! - 7) \times 9) + (7 \times (5 - (3 - 1))))$
6229 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + 7!) + ((9 \times ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) + 1)$
6230 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((7 + 97) \times (5!/(3 - 1)))$
6231 := $1 \times 3 + ((579 \times (7 + 5)) - 3! \times 1)$
6232 := $(1^3 + 57) - (9 \times (((7 \times 5) - 3!) - 1))$
6233 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7!/9)) + (7! + (5^{3+1}))$
6234 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 - 7!)) + (97 \times 5) + (3! - 1)$
6235 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) \times (7 - ((97 + 5!) + (3! - 1)))$
6236 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7 + ((9 - 7) \times (5^{3!-1}))$
6237 := $((1^{35}) \times (79^{7-5})) - 3 - 1$
6238 := $((1^{35}) \times (79^{7-5})) - 3 \times 1$
6239 := $((1^{35}) \times (79^{7-5})) - 3 + 1$
6240 := $((1 \times 3!)!/(5 + 7)) \times ((9 - 7) \times (53 - 1))$
6241 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 79))) + ((7! + (5 \times 3)) + 1)$
6242 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5! + (7 - (9 + 7!)))) - (5! \times 31)$

- 6243** := $((1^{35} \times (79^{7-5})) + 3) - 1$
6244 := $(((((1^{3!}) + 5))! \times 7) + (97 \times 5)) + (3!! - 1)$
6245 := $(13 \times ((5 \times (79 + 7)) - 5)) + 3!! \times 1$
6246 := $1 \times (((3 \times 5) + (7 \times 97)) \times (5 + 3 + 1))$
6247 := $1 + (((3 \times 5) + (7 \times 97)) \times (5 + 3 + 1))$
6248 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) + 9)) \times (75 - 31)$
6249 := $((13 + 5!) + 7!) - (9 - ((7 \times 5) \times 31))$
6250 := $((1 \times (35 \times 79)) \times (7 - 5)) + ((3! \times 1))!$
6251 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - 5!)) - (3 + 1)$
6252 := $((13 \times 57 - 9) + 7!) + (5! \times (3 + 1))$
6253 := $13 + (5! \times ((7 + (97 - 53)) + 1))$
6254 := $(1^3 + 5) + ((79^{7-5}) + (3! + 1))$
6255 := $((1 + 3^5) + (7! + 975)) - (3 + 1)$
6256 := $(1 \times 3 + (5^{7-9+7})) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
6257 := $(13 \times 5!) + (((7! + (9 + 7)) - (5! \times 3)) + 1)$
6258 := $((1 + 3) + (5! + 7!)) + (9 + ((7 \times 5) \times 31))$
6259 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - 5!)) + (3 + 1)$
6260 := $((1 \times (35 \times (79 + 7))) + 5!) \times (3 - 1)$
6261 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (7! + 975)) + (3 \times 1)$
6262 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (797 \times ((5 + 3) \times 1))$
6263 := $((1 + 3^5) + (7! + 975)) + (3 + 1)$
6264 := $((((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) - 9) + ((7 \times 5)^{3-1}))$
6265 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((7 \times 9) - ((7 - 5!) - 3))) \times 1$
6266 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((7 \times 9) - ((7 - 5!) - 3))) + 1$
6267 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3))) - 1$
6268 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3))) \times 1$
6269 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3))) + 1$
6270 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - (3! - 1))$
6271 := $(((((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times 9) + 7!)) + 5!) + (3 + 1))!$
6272 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (((57 \times 9) + 7!) - 5) + 3 + 1)$
6273 := $(1 + 3) + (((5 + 79) \times 75) - 31)$
6274 := $((((1 \times 3!)! + ((57 \times 9) + 7!)) + (5 - (3 + 1)))$
6275 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((57 \times 97) - (5 - 31))$
6276 := $((1 \times (3!! + ((57 \times 9) + 7!))) + 5) - (3 - 1)$
6277 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) + (7! + (53 - 1))$
6278 := $1 + (((3 \times 5 \times 79) + 7!) + (53 - 1))$
6279 := $((1^3 + (5! + 79)) \times 7) \times 5 - (3!! + 1)$
6280 := $((1 + (3 \times 5 \times 79)) + 7!) + (53 + 1)$
6281 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7 \times 97) \times 5) + (3! \times 1)$
6282 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7 \times 97) \times 5) + (3! + 1)$
6283 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 - (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1))!$
6284 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5 - 7!)) + ((97 - 5!)^{3-1})$
6285 := $(1 + 3!!) - ((5 - (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times (53 - 1))$
6286 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5! \times 7) + 9) + (7^{5-3})) \times 1$
6287 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((79^{7-5}) + 31)$
6288 := $((1 - 3!)/5 + 7) \times (9 + ((7!/5) + 31))$
6289 := $1 + (3^5 + ((79 \times 75) + ((3! - 1))!))$
6290 := $((1 + 3!!) + (5! + ((7!/9) + 7!))) - (5! + 31)$
6291 := $((1 \times 3! + 5!) + 7) \times 9 + (7! + (53 + 1))$
6292 := $((1 \times 35) + 79) + 7) \times (53 - 1)$
6293 := $(1 \times (3!! - (5 + 7)) \times 9) - (75 + 3 + 1)$
6294 := $(1 + ((3!! - (5 + 7)) \times 9)) - (75 + 3 + 1)$
6295 := $(13 + 5!) + ((79 \times (75 + 3)) \times 1)$
6296 := $((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) - (5! \times (3 + 1))$
6297 := $(1 \times (3 + 5!)) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
6298 := $(1 \times (3!! + ((57 \times 9) + 7!))) + (5^{3-1})$
6299 := $(1357 - 9) + (7! - (5! - 31))$
6300 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) - (7 - 9))) \times ((7!/(5 + 3)) \times 1)$
6301 := $1 - ((3! + 5!) \times ((7 - 9) - ((7^{5-3}) - 1)))$
6302 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5 - (7! + (9 + 7)))) + 531$
6303 := $(13 \times 57 - 9) + (7! + 531)$
6304 := $(13 - 5) \times ((797 - (5 + 3)) - 1)$
6305 := $(13 \times (57 \times 9)) - (7 \times (53 - 1))$
6306 := $(1 \times ((357 \times 9) \times (7 - 5))) - ((3! - 1))!$
6307 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5! - 7)) \times (9 + (75 - 31))$
6308 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (((7! + (9 \times 75)) - 3!) - 1)$
6309 := $(1 \times 3!) - ((5! - ((7! + (9 \times 75)) - 3!)) \times 1)$
6310 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (((7! + (9 \times 75)) - 3!) + 1)$
6311 := $(1 + ((3!! - 5!) + ((7! + (9 \times 75)) - 3!))) + 1$
6312 := $((13 - 5) \times (797 - (5 + 3))) \times 1$
6313 := $(1 + ((3! \times 57) \times (9 + 7))) + (5! + ((3! \times 1))!)$
6314 := $((1^3 + 5) + (7 + 9)) \times 7 \times ((5!/3) + 1)$
6315 := $((1 + 3)! + ((579 - 7) \times (5 + 3!))) - 1$
6316 := $((1 + 3)! + ((579 - 7) \times (5 + 3!))) \times 1$
6317 := $((1 + 3)! + ((579 - 7) \times (5 + 3!))) + 1$
6318 := $(13 + 5) \times ((7! - 9) - (7! - (5! \times (3 \times 1))))$
6319 := $((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7!)) + ((9 \times 75) + 3!!) + 1$
6320 := $(1 + ((3 - (5 - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times (3 + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}6321 &:= ((1 \times (3! - 5)) \times 7!) + (((9 \times 7) + 5!) \times (3! + 1)) \\6322 &:= ((1 \times (3! - 5)) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) + 5!) \times (3! + 1)) \\6323 &:= (1 - 3!) + (5797 + 531) \\6324 &:= 1 \times ((3!! - ((5 + 7) + 9)) + (75^{3-1})) \\6325 &:= 1 + ((3!! - ((5 + 7) + 9)) + (75^{3-1})) \\6326 &:= (1 - 3) + (5797 + 531) \\6327 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7!/9)) + (((7!/5)/3!) - 1)) \\6328 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5 - (7 + 9)))) \times ((7 - 5!) \times (3! + 1)) \\6329 &:= (1^3 + 5797) + 531 \\6330 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (7! + (5!/(3 + 1))) \\6331 &:= 1 \times ((3 + 5797) + 531) \\6332 &:= 1 + ((3 + 5797) + 531) \\6333 &:= ((1 + 3!))! - (57 - ((9 \times 75) \times (3 - 1))) \\6334 &:= 1357 - (((9 - 7!) + 53) + 1) \\6335 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times (5 + 79)) + 7!) - ((5! \times 3!) + 1) \\6336 &:= (1357 - (9 - 7!)) - (53 - 1) \\6337 &:= (((1 + 3) + 579) + 7!) - (5 - 3!!) - 1 \\6338 &:= (13 \times (5! - (7 + 9))) + (7! - (53 + 1)) \\6339 &:= (((1 + 3) + 579) + 7!) - (5 - 3!!) + 1 \\6340 &:= (((1 + 35) \times (7 + 9)) + (7! + 5)) + (3!! - 1) \\6341 &:= (1 - 35) + ((797 \times (5 + 3)) - 1) \\6342 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! - 7) + 9) \times 7) + 53 - 1 \\6343 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - ((5 - 7!) - ((97 + 5!) \times 3!))) \times 1 \\6344 &:= ((135 + 7) \times 9) + ((7! - 5) + 31) \\6345 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 57) - 9) + (7! - (53 + 1)) \\6346 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 + 7) \times ((97 - 5!)^{3-1})) \\6347 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 57) - ((9 - 7!) + (53 - 1)) \\6348 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) + (7! + 9)) + ((7! + 5!)/(3 + 1))) \\6349 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! - 7) + 9) \times 7) + 53 \times 1 \\6350 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) + (5 + 31)) \\6351 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times 79) + ((7! - 5!) + (3!! \times 1)) \\6352 &:= (1 - 35) + (((79 + 7) + 5!) \times 31) \\6353 &:= ((135 \times 7) + ((9 + 7!) + (5! \times 3))) - 1 \\6354 &:= (135 \times 7) + (((9 + 7!) + (5! \times 3)) \times 1) \\6355 &:= (1 + (3 - 5!)) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times ((5! \times 3!) - 1)) \\6356 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (5! \times (7 + (9 - 7)))) - ((5^3) - 1) \\6357 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) \times (7 + (9 - 7))) - (5! + 3 \times 1) \\6358 &:= ((1 + (357 \times 9)) - (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\6359 &:= (1^{35}) \times (((7 - (9 - 7)))! \times 53) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6360 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5) \times (((7 + 97)/(5 - 3)) + 1) \\6361 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + (5! + 7!)) + (((9 + 7) \times 5) \times (3! \times 1)) \\6362 &:= (1 + (3! + (5! \times (7 + (9 + 7)))))) + (5 \times (3!! - 1)) \\6363 &:= (((13 - 57) + 97) \times 5!) + (3 \times 1) \\6364 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) \times (5! - ((3! \times 1)!))) \\6365 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 797) - (5 + 3! \times 1) \\6366 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) + (797 \times ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\6367 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5!)) + (7! - ((9 - 75) \times 31)) \\6368 &:= (13 - 5) \times (797 - ((5 - 3) - 1)) \\6369 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - (75 \times (3 + 1)) \\6370 &:= ((1357 + 9) + 7!) - (5 + 31) \\6371 &:= 1 - (3!! - (((5! - 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5) - (3 + 1!)) \\6372 &:= (1 + (3! + 5)) + (((7 - (9 - 7)))! \times 53) \times 1 \\6373 &:= ((1 + 357) + 975) + ((3! + 1)! \\6374 &:= (((13 - 5) \times 797) - 5) + (3 \times 1) \\6375 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 57)) \times ((9 - 7) - 5!)) + (3 \times 1) \\6376 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 797) \times ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\6377 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((797 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\6378 &:= (1^{35}) + ((797 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\6379 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + (797 \times ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\6380 &:= (1357 + 9) + ((7! + 5) - 31) \\6381 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 5) - 7)) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 + ((3! \times 1)!))) \\6382 &:= 13 + (579 \times (((7 - 5) \times 3!) - 1)) \\6383 &:= ((13 - 5) + (797 \times (5 + 3))) - 1 \\6384 &:= ((13 - 5) + (797 \times (5 + 3))) \times 1 \\6385 &:= (13 - 5) + ((797 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\6386 &:= (((13 + 57 + 9) + 7) + 5!) \times 31 \\6387 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 797) + (5 + 3! \times 1) \\6388 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) + (((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - 3!)) - 1)) \\6389 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\6390 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) - 9) + ((7!/5) + 31)) \\6391 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5!) \times (7 - 9)) + 7! + 5! + 31 \\6392 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((797 + 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\6393 &:= (((1 \times 3!))! + 57) - (9 - (75^{3-1})) \\6394 &:= (((1^{35}) + 79)^{7-5}) - 3! \times 1 \\6395 &:= ((1 + 35) + (((7 - (9 - 7)))! \times 53)) - 1 \\6396 &:= ((1 \times ((35/7) \times 9)) + 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1) \\6397 &:= 1 - (((3! - (5! - 7)) - 9) - 7) \times (53 - 1) \\6398 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 + ((7 - 97) + 5))^{3-1})\end{aligned}$$

- 6399** := $(1 + 3!) - ((5! + 7) + ((9 \times (75 - 3!)) \times 1))$
6400 := $(1 - (((3 - 5!) \times 7) - 9)) + (7! + 531)$
6401 := $(1 \times (3! + ((5! - 7) \times (9 \times 7)))) - (5 + (3! - 1))$
6402 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97) \times (5 - (3 - 1))$
6403 := $1 \times (3! + (((5 \times (7 + 9))^{7-5}) - (3 \times 1)))$
6404 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 \times (7 + 9))^{7-5}) - (3 \times 1))$
6405 := $((1 + 3) + 57) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!) - 31$
6406 := $((1^{3!}) - 5!) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times (5 + ((3! \times 1)!))$
6407 := $((1 + 3) - 5) + ((79 - 7) \times (5! - 31))$
6408 := $((1 \times 3! \times (5 + 7)) \times (97 - (5 + 3))) \times 1$
6409 := $((13 + 5) \times 79) + (7! - (53 \times 1))$
6410 := $(1 \times 35) + ((797 \times (5 + 3)) - 1)$
6411 := $((((1 + 3)! \times 57) + 9) + 7!) - (((5 - 3) + 1)!)$
6412 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) \times (797 + 5)) - (3 + 1)$
6413 := $((1 + 3) + 579) \times ((7!/5!) - 31)$
6414 := $1357 - (9 - ((7! - 5) + 31))$
6415 := $((((13 \times 57) + 9) + 7!) + (5^{3+1}))$
6416 := $((((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7! + (5! - (3 + 1))))$
6417 := $((((1 \times 3)! - (57 \times 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1)))$
6418 := $((((1 + 3)! \times 57) + 9) + (((7 \times 5!) \times 3!) + 1)$
6419 := $(1 \times ((357 \times (9 \times (7 - 5))) - 3!)) - 1$
6420 := $((13 \times 5) \times (7 \times 9)) + (75 \times 31)$
6421 := $(1 \times ((357 \times (9 \times (7 - 5))) - 3!)) + 1$
6422 := $((13 - 5) \times (797 + 5)) + 3! \times 1$
6423 := $((((1 + (35/7))!) \times 9) - ((7 \times (5 + 3)) + 1)$
6424 := $(1 \times (3! - 5!)) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (53 - 1)))$
6425 := $((((1 \times 3)! + 5) \times 7) + ((9 \times 75) \times (3 - 1))$
6426 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) + (7! + ((9 \times 75) - (3! - 1)))$
6427 := $1 - ((3! + 5!) \times (7 + (97 - (5 \times 31))))$
6428 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5 + (7 \times 9)) + (7! - (5! \times 31))))$
6429 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 - ((7 \times 9) - 7!)) + 5) + (3! + 1))$
6430 := $(1 + 3!) - (57 - (9 \times (7! / (5 + 3 - 1))))$
6431 := $1 \times (((357 \times 9) \times (7 - 5)) + (3! - 1))$
6432 := $1 + (((357 \times 9) \times (7 - 5)) + (3! - 1))$
6433 := $(1 - (3! + 5!)) + ((7 \times (97 + (5! + 3!))) - 1)$
6434 := $(1 - (3! + 5!)) + ((7 \times (97 + (5! + 3!))) \times 1)$
6435 := $((135 + 7) \times 9) + (7! + ((5! - 3) \times 1))$
6436 := $(1 - ((3 - 5!) \times 7)) - (9 - (75^{3-1}))$
6437 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5!) - 7)) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31})$
6438 := $((135 + 7) \times 9) + (7! + (5 \times (3 + 1)!))$
6439 := $((13 - 5) + 797) \times (5 + 3) - 1$
6440 := $(1357 - (9 - 7!)) + (53 - 1)$
6441 := $(1^3 \times 57) \times ((9 + (7 \times (5 \times 3))) - 1)$
6442 := $((1357 + 9) + 7!) + (5 + 31)$
6443 := $((1 + ((3! \times 5!) + (7!/9) + 7)) \times 5) + (3 \times 1)$
6444 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 + 7!) + ((9 \times 75) + 3 + 1))$
6445 := $(1 \times (3! - 5!)) + (7 \times ((97 + 5!) + (3! \times 1)))$
6446 := $(1 - 35) + (((7 - (9 - 7)))! \times (53 + 1))$
6447 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) + (7! + (((9 \times 75) + 3!) + 1))$
6448 := $(1 - (35 - (79 + 7))) \times ((5! + 3) + 1)$
6449 := $(1 \times 3! \times 5) + ((797 + 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
6450 := $((1 - 3) \times ((5 \times ((7 - 9)^7) - 5)) \times (3! - 1)$
6451 := $1 \times (((3! - (5 + 7)) \times 9) + (75 + 3 + 1))$
6452 := $1 + (((3! - (5 + 7)) \times 9) + (75 + 3 + 1))$
6453 := $(1 + ((3 \times (57 \times 9)) - (7 + 5!))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
6454 := $((135 \times 7) + (97 - 5!)) \times (3! + 1)$
6455 := $((1 \times (3! + 579)) + 7!) + ((5! - 3) - 1)$
6456 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (57 \times (9 + (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 - 1)$
6457 := $((13 \times (5! + (7 - 9))) + 7!) - ((5! - 3) \times 1)$
6458 := $(13 \times 5!) + (7! - ((9 + 7) + (5^3 + 1)))$
6459 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (((5 \times 7) - (9 + 7!)) - (5 + 3! \times 1))$
6460 := $((1^3 + 5)! \times ((7 + 9) - 7) - (5 \times (3 + 1))$
6461 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 + 9 - 7)) + (5 + ((3! + 1)!)$
6462 := $((135 + 7) \times 9) + ((7! + 5!) + (3 + 1)!)$
6463 := $((1 - 3)^5) + (7! + ((97 \times 5) \times (3 \times 1)))$
6464 := $((((1 \times 3!)! + 5) + 7!) - (((9 + 7) + 5) - ((3! \times 1)!))$
6465 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times (79 - (7 - ((5! \times 3) - 1)))$
6466 := $((13 + 5) + (7 + 97)) \times (53 \times 1)$
6467 := $(1 - (((35 \times 79) - (7! - 5!)) \times 3)) + 1$
6468 := $1 \times ((3! \times 5!) + (((7! - (9 + 7)) + 5) + 3!) - 1)$
6469 := $1 - (357 - (975 \times (3! + 1)))$
6470 := $1 + ((3! \times 5!) + (7! - ((9 + 7) - 5) - ((3! \times 1)!))$
6471 := $((13 + 57) \times (97 - 5)) + 31$
6472 := $((1 \times (3! - 5!)) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times (53 - 1))$
6473 := $((1 + (3! - 5!)) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times (53 - 1))$
6474 := $13 \times ((579 - 75) - (3! \times 1))$
6475 := $1 \times (35 \times ((79 + 75) + 31))$
6476 := $1 + (35 \times ((79 + 75) + 31))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6477 &:= ((1357 - 9) + (7! + 5!)) - 31 \\
 6478 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times 7) + (((9 \times 7) + 5!) \times 31) \\
 6479 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) \times (7 + (9 - 7))) + (5 - 3! \times 1) \\
 6480 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times (((7 \times (9 - 7)) - 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\
 6481 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) \times (7 + (9 - 7))) - (5 - 3! \times 1) \\
 6482 &:= ((1^3)^5!) - (((7 - (9 + 7)) \times (5! \times 3!)) - 1) \\
 6483 &:= (1 + ((3 + 57) \times (9 \times (7 + 5)))) + (3 - 1) \\
 6484 &:= 1 - ((3 + 57) - (9 \times (7 + (5! \times (3! \times 1)))))) \\
 6485 &:= (((1 + (35/7)))! \times 9) + ((7 + 5)/3) + 1 \\
 6486 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5! \times (7^{9-7})) - (5! - 3! \times 1)) \\
 6487 &:= (((((1 + 3!))! / 5) + 79) + 7!) + ((5! \times 3) \times 1) \\
 6488 &:= (((1 + 3!))! / 5) + 79) + (7! + ((5! \times 3) + 1)) \\
 6489 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) - (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - (5^3))) - 1) \\
 6490 &:= (1 + (((3 + 5) - (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - (5^3)))) - 1 \\
 6491 &:= (1 + (((3 + 5) - (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - (5^3)))) \times 1 \\
 6492 &:= (((((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7)))! \times 9) + (7 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1 \\
 6493 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + (7 + 9)) + (7! - (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\
 6494 &:= ((13 - 5) + 79) \times 75) - 31 \\
 6495 &:= (1^{35}) + (7! + ((97 \times (5 \times 3)) - 1)) \\
 6496 &:= (1 \times ((357 \times 9) + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\
 6497 &:= 1357 + ((97 \times 53) - 1) \\
 6498 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7 + (9 - (7 \times 5)))^{3-1}) \\
 6499 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! - 3!)) \\
 6500 &:= (((1^3 + 5))! \times ((7 + 9) - 7)) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\
 6501 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) \times (79 - (7!/5))) - (3 - 1) \\
 6502 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7!) - ((97 - (5! \times 3!)) + 1)) \\
 6503 &:= (1 \times 3! + (57 \times (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 3)))) - 1 \\
 6504 &:= ((1 - 3 + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) - (7!/5!)) \times (3 + 1)! \\
 6505 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) \times (79 - (7!/5))) + (3 - 1) \\
 6506 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 79) + ((7! - (5! - 3!)) \times 1) \\
 6507 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 79) + ((7! - 5!) + (3! + 1)) \\
 6508 &:= (13 - 5!) + (((7 \times 9) \times 7) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\
 6509 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 57)^{9-7}) - (53 - 1) \\
 6510 &:= ((135 + 7) + ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 31 \\
 6511 &:= ((1 + 3!))! - (((5 - (7! + 9)) - (7 \times 5!)) / (3 + 1)) \\
 6512 &:= (13 + 579) \times (((7 - 5) \times 3!) - 1) \\
 6513 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 79) + (7! - (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\
 6514 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 79) + 7!) + (53 - 1) \\
 6515 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 79) + 7!) + (53 \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6516 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 6517 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) + ((7 \times 5)^{3-1}) \\
 6518 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) + 7!) / 5)) - (3 + 1) \\
 6519 &:= ((13 - 57) + 97) \times (5! + 3 \times 1) \\
 6520 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 57) - (9 + 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\
 6521 &:= (1 + 3) + (5797 + (5! \times (3! \times 1))) \\
 6522 &:= (1 + ((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) - 5!)) \times (3! \times 1) \\
 6523 &:= (((13 \times 5!) - 79) + (7! + 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\
 6524 &:= (13 + (57^{9-7})) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\
 6525 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - ((5 \times 3!) \times 1)) \\
 6526 &:= (1 + (3^5 + 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\
 6527 &:= (13 \times 5!) - (((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5)) + 3!) - 1) \\
 6528 &:= (13 \times (579 - 75)) - (3 + 1)! \\
 6529 &:= (((13 \times 5!) - 79) + (7! + 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\
 6530 &:= 1 - ((3! \times 5) - 7!) - ((97 + 5!) \times (3! + 1)) \\
 6531 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 797) + (5 \times 31) \\
 6532 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\
 6533 &:= (13 + (5 \times (7 \times 97))) + (5^{3!-1}) \\
 6534 &:= ((13 + (5 - 7)) \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 31) \\
 6535 &:= (13 \times (5 - 7)) + (9^{7-5+3-1}) \\
 6536 &:= 1 \times ((3 + 5) \times (((7 \times 9) + 753) + 1)) \\
 6537 &:= (((1 + (35/7)))! \times 9) + ((7 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\
 6538 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (((79 + (7!/5)) \times 3!) + 1) \\
 6539 &:= ((1357 - 9) + (7! + 5!)) + 31 \\
 6540 &:= (((((1 \times 3!))! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) - (7! + 5!)) \times (3 + 1) \\
 6541 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5 \times ((7 - 9) - (7 + 5)))) \times 31 \\
 6542 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 57) + (9 + (7! + (5^3 \times 1))) \\
 6543 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 + (((9 - 7) \times 5!) \times (3 \times 1))) \\
 6544 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) + 3!) \times 1 \\
 6545 &:= (1 \times 35) - ((7 - (97 + 5!)) \times 31) \\
 6546 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + (97 \times 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\
 6547 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5 - 7)) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31}) \\
 6548 &:= (13 \times (579 - 75)) - (3 + 1) \\
 6549 &:= ((13 \times (579 - 75)) - 3) \times 1 \\
 6550 &:= ((13 \times (579 - 75)) - 3) + 1 \\
 6551 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + 7) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\
 6552 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) - 7) \times ((9 + 75) \times 3! \times 1) \\
 6553 &:= (((1 - 35) - (7 - 97)) \times (5! - 3)) + 1 \\
 6554 &:= ((13 \times (579 - 75)) + 3) - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

- 6555** := $((13 \times (579 - 75)) + 3) \times 1$
6556 := $(13 \times (579 - 75)) + (3 + 1)$
6557 := $((1 + (3!! + 5!)) \times 7) + ((9 \times 75) - (3! - 1))$
6558 := $((13 - 5!) \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) - 5)) + 31$
6559 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 + 7) - 9)^{7+5-3-1})$
6560 := $((((1 + 3!))! - (5 + (7 \times (97 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1)$
6561 := $(135 \times (7^{9-7})) - (53 + 1)$
6562 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3) + 1$
6563 := $((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times 9) + (7! - (5^{3-1}))$
6564 := $(1 - 3) \times ((57 - ((9 \times 7) \times 53)) \times 1)$
6565 := $((((13 \times 5!) - 7) - 9) + (7! + 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
6566 := $(1 - 3) \times ((57 - ((9 \times 7) \times 53)) - 1)$
6567 := $((1 \times 3)^{5-7+(9-7) \times 5}) + 3! \times 1$
6568 := $((1 \times 3!!) \times 5) + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times (53 \times 1))$
6569 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) + ((79 + (7 - 5))^{3-1})$
6570 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 - 7) - (9^{7 \times 5 - 31}))$
6571 := $((((1 + 3) + (57 + (9 \times 7))) \times 53) - 1$
6572 := $((((1 + 3) + (57 + (9 \times 7))) \times 53) \times 1$
6573 := $((((1 + 3) + (57 + (9 \times 7))) \times 53) + 1$
6574 := $1 + (3 \times (((((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5) \times 3!) + 1))$
6575 := $((((13 \times 5!) - 7) - 9) + (((7! - 5) - 3) - 1)$
6576 := $(1 + (3 \times (((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5))) \times (3! \times 1)$
6577 := $((((13 \times 5!) - 7) - 9) + ((7! - 5) - (3 - 1))$
6578 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5! + (79 + 75))) + (3 - 1)$
6579 := $(135 \times 7) + (9 + (75^{3-1}))$
6580 := $((((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (7 - 5!)) + (3 + 1)!$
6581 := $((13 \times 5!) - 7) - (((9 - (7! - 5)) - 3) + 1)$
6582 := $((1 + 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (97 + (5^{3!-1}))$
6583 := $((13 \times 5!) + (7! - 9)) + (7 - (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
6584 := $((((1 + 3!))! + (((5 \times 7) + 9) \times 7) \times 5)) + (3 + 1)$
6585 := $((((13 \times 5!) - 7) - 9) + (7! + 5)) - (3 + 1)$
6586 := $1 \times (((3! \times 5) + 7) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5!) - (3! - 1)))$
6587 := $((((13 \times 5!) - 7) - (9 - 7!)) + 5) - (3 - 1)$
6588 := $(1 - (35 \times 7)) \times (9 - ((7 + 5) \times (3 \times 1)))$
6589 := $(1 - (3 - 5!)) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times ((5! \times 3!) - 1))$
6590 := $(1 + 35) - (7 - (9^{(7+5)/3 \times 1}))$
6591 := $((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times 9) + (7! + (5 - (3 - 1)))$
6592 := $((1 - (3 - 57)) + 9) \times (7 + (5! - (3 + 1)!))$
6593 := $(((((13 + 5) \times 7) \times 9) - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!) - 1$
6594 := $(((((13 + 5) \times 7) \times 9) - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!) \times 1$
6595 := $(((((13 + 5) \times 7) \times 9) - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!) + 1$
6596 := $((((1 \times 3!))! + ((5! + ((7! + (9 - 7)) - 5)) + 3!)) - 1$
6597 := $((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)$
6598 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) - (((7 - 9) \times 7) \times (5! \times (3 + 1)))$
6599 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5! \times 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5 + 3 \times 1))$
6600 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
6601 := $(1 - (((3 - 5!) + (7 + 97)) \times 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)$
6602 := $(1^3) + (5! - (((7 - (9 + 7)) \times (5! \times 3!)) - 1))$
6603 := $((1 + 3!) + (5 \times 7)) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31})$
6604 := $1 + 35 + (7 + (9^{(7+5)/3 \times 1}))$
6605 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (7! + (97 \times 5))) + (3!! \times 1)$
6606 := $1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 7) + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
6607 := $((135 \times (7^{9-7})) - 5) - (3 \times 1)$
6608 := $((((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) - 7) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)$
6609 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + 5)) - (3!! + 1)$
6610 := $((13 \times (57 \times 9)) - 7) - (53 - 1)$
6611 := $((((13 \times 5!) - (7 - 9)) + 7!) + ((5 + 3) + 1)$
6612 := $((((1 - 3 + 5))! - (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 - (5! + 3)) \times 1)$
6613 := $((((1 + 3!) + 57)^{9-7}) + (53 - 1)$
6614 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 7) - ((9 - 7!) + (5^3 \times 1))$
6615 := $((1^3)^5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
6616 := $(1 + 3) + (57 \times ((9 \times 7) + 53) \times 1)$
6617 := $13 \times (579 - ((7 \times 5) \times (3 - 1)))$
6618 := $((13 \times 57) \times 9) - 75 + (3 + 1)!$
6619 := $(1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) - (5! + 3 \times 1)$
6620 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) \times 7)) + (5! / (3 + 1)!)$
6621 := $((((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) - ((9 + 7) + 531)$
6622 := $(13 \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 - 53) - 1)$
6623 := $((13 \times 57) \times 9) - (7! / 5!) - (3 + 1)$
6624 := $(13 \times (57 \times 9)) + (7 - (53 - 1))$
6625 := $((13 \times 5!) + (7! + (9 + 7))) + (5 + 3 + 1)$
6626 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)))) - (3 + 1)$
6627 := $((1 - 3) \times 5!) + (7 \times (975 + (3! \times 1)))$
6628 := $((1 - 3) \times 5!) + (7 \times (975 + 3!)) + 1$
6629 := $((1 \times 3! + 5) \times 7) \times 97 - (5! + ((3! \times 1)!))$
6630 := $1 \times (((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) + 5!) \times (3! - 1))$
6631 := $1 + (((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) + 5!) \times (3! - 1))$
6632 := $(((((1 + 3!))! / 5) + 7!) - ((9 + 7) + 5!) - ((3! \times 1)!))$

$$\begin{aligned} 6633 &:= ((1 + (3!! - 57)) \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 6634 &:= ((1 + 3!!)!) - ((5 - 7975)/(3! - 1)) \\ 6635 &:= (1 + ((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) + 5!)) \times (3! - 1) \\ 6636 &:= (1 + (35 \times ((7^{9-7}) + 5!))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 6637 &:= (((1 + (((3^5) \times 7) + 9)) + 7!) - 5!) + (3! \times 1) \\ 6638 &:= (((1 + (((3^5) \times 7) + 9)) + 7!) - 5!) + (3! + 1) \\ 6639 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5 \times 7) + (9 - 7)) - 531 \\ 6640 &:= (1^3) \times (5 \times (797 + 531)) \\ 6641 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - 31)) \\ 6642 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5 - (7 + 97))) \times (53 + 1) \\ 6643 &:= 1 \times (35 + (7 \times (975 - 31))) \\ 6644 &:= ((135 + 7) + 9) \times (75 - 31) \\ 6645 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + ((5 \times 3!) \times 1) \\ 6646 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((79 \times (7!/5!)) + (3! - 1)) \\ 6647 &:= ((1 + (3!! - 57)) \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) + (3! + 1) \\ 6648 &:= ((1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) - (7!/5!))) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 6649 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7!) + (((9 + 7!) - 5!)/3) \times 1 \\ 6650 &:= (13 + 5!) \times ((7 + (9 \times 7)) - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 6651 &:= (((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + 7) + 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 6652 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - (7 + (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 6653 &:= ((13 \times (57 \times 9)) - (7 + (5 + 3))) - 1 \\ 6654 &:= ((13 \times (57 \times 9)) - (7 + (5 + 3))) \times 1 \\ 6655 &:= ((13 \times (57 \times 9)) - (7 + (5 + 3))) + 1 \\ 6656 &:= 13 \times (((5 - 7)^{(9-7) \times 5})/(3 - 1)) \\ 6657 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + ((5!/3) + 1)) \\ 6658 &:= (13 - (((5 - (7 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5!)) + 3!!)) - 1 \\ 6659 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) - 7) - 5) + (3 - 1) \\ 6660 &:= (((1 + 3!!) - (5! - 7!)) + 9) + (7!/5) + (3 - 1) \\ 6661 &:= (((1 + 3!!) - (5! - 7!)) + 9) + (7!/5) + (3 \times 1) \\ 6662 &:= (1^3 + 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 6663 &:= ((13 + 5) + (79 \times 75)) + (3!! \times 1) \\ 6664 &:= ((13 + 5) + (79 \times 75)) + (3!! + 1) \\ 6665 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + 79) + (7! - ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 6666 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - ((7 + 5)/(3 + 1)) \\ 6667 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - ((7 + 5)/(3! \times 1)) \\ 6668 &:= 1 - (3! + (5 - ((7 \times 9) \times (75 + 31)))) \\ 6669 &:= (135 \times (7^{9-7})) + (53 + 1) \\ 6670 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 7)) + (9 \times (753 \times 1)) \\ 6671 &:= (13 \times 5!) + (79 + (7! - (5 + 3 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6672 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) + ((7 + 5)/(3 + 1)) \\ 6673 &:= (1 \times (3!! + 5!)) + ((79 + (7! - 5)) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 6674 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5!) + ((7 \times 97) \times (5 + (3! - 1))) \\ 6675 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 + 79) - 7)) \times (5! - 31) \\ 6676 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + 5!) + ((7! + (9 \times 75)) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 6677 &:= ((135 - (7 + (9 - 7))) \times 53) - 1 \\ 6678 &:= ((135 - (7 + (9 - 7))) \times 53) \times 1 \\ 6679 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + 7) + 5) - (3 - 1) \\ 6680 &:= (((13 - 5!) + ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) \times 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 6681 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 6682 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) - 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 6683 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + 7) + 5) + (3 - 1) \\ 6684 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7! - (5 + 3!!)) - 1) \\ 6685 &:= (((13 - 57) - 9) + (7!/5)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 6686 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (7 + (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 6687 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) - 7) \times (9 - (753 - 1)) \\ 6688 &:= (1357 + ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 6689 &:= (((1 + 3!!) + 5) \times ((7! + 9) - 7!)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 6690 &:= ((13 \times (5! + (7 - 9))) + 7!) + ((5! - 3) - 1) \\ 6691 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! + 7)) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31}) \\ 6692 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! - 7) \times 9) - (7 + 53)) - 1 \\ 6693 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 + (7 \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1))) \\ 6694 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! \times ((7 \times 9) - 7))) - (5!/(3 + 1)) \\ 6695 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + 7!) + ((97 - 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 6696 &:= ((1 + 3) + (57 + (9 \times 7))) \times (53 + 1) \\ 6697 &:= (1 + ((3^5) - (7 \times 9))) \times (((7 \times 5) + 3) - 1) \\ 6698 &:= 1 - (((3^5) \times 7) - (9 + 7!)) \times (5 - 3) - 1 \\ 6699 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5!)) + 7!) + ((97 + 5!) + 3!!) + 1 \\ 6700 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (7! - (9 + (75 - ((3! \times 1)!))) \\ 6701 &:= ((13 + 5!) + 7) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31}) \\ 6702 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times ((579 + 7) + 531) \\ 6703 &:= (135 + 7) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31}) \\ 6704 &:= ((1 + ((3!! + 5) + 7!)) + ((97 + 5!) + 3!!)) + 1 \\ 6705 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((7 \times 975) - ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 6706 &:= (1^{35}) + ((7 \times 975) - ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 6707 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 7) - ((9 - 7!) - (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\ 6708 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7 \times 97) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 6709 &:= (13 \times 5!) + ((7! + (97 + (5 + 3!))) + 1) \\ 6710 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! - 7) + 9)) \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6711 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + 5!) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 6712 &:= (1 - (3!! + 5!)) \times (7 + (((9 + 7) \times (5 - 3!)) + 1)) \\ 6713 &:= (13 \times (57 \times 9)) + (75 - 31) \\ 6714 &:= (13 \times (57 \times 9)) - (7 - (53 - 1)) \\ 6715 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5!)) + ((7 \times 975) + (3! + 1)) \\ 6716 &:= (1 + (3 - 5!)) + ((7 \times 975) + (3! + 1)) \\ 6717 &:= (((1^{3!})^5!) \times (((7!/9) \times (7 + 5)) - 3)) \times 1 \\ 6718 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) + 5) - (3! - 1)) \\ 6719 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 3))) - 1 \\ 6720 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 + 7) + (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 6721 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\ 6722 &:= (((1 + 3!)/ (5 + (7 - 9))) + (7! + ((5 - 3) \times 1))) \\ 6723 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + (7! - (53 + 1)) \\ 6724 &:= (1 + 3) + ((57 - 9) \times (7 \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 6725 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5! \times (7 - (9 \times 7))) + 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 6726 &:= (1^3 + (5 - 7)) + ((97 + 5!) \times 31) \\ 6727 &:= ((1^3 + 57) \times ((9 \times 7) + 53)) - 1 \\ 6728 &:= (((1 + 35) - 7)^{9-7}) \times (5 + 3 \times 1) \\ 6729 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) - (((7 - 9) \times 7) \times (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 6730 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + (5! - (3! \times 1)) \\ 6731 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 579) + (7! - (5^{3+1})) \\ 6732 &:= (13 - 57) \times (9 - (7 + 5 \times 31)) \\ 6733 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) + ((7 \times ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 6734 &:= ((1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) - 5) - (3 \times 1) \\ 6735 &:= ((1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) - 5) - (3 - 1) \\ 6736 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) \times (7 - ((9 - (7 \times 5!)) - (3 + 1))) \\ 6737 &:= (135 \times (7^{9-7})) + ((5! + 3) - 1) \\ 6738 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) + (7 \times ((975 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 6739 &:= (1^3) + (((57^{9-7}) + 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 6740 &:= ((1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) - 5) + (3 \times 1) \\ 6741 &:= 1 - (((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 - (3 + 1))) \\ 6742 &:= (((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + 9) + 7! - (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 6743 &:= (((1 + (3!! + 5!)) \times 7) + (9 + 7)) + (5! + 3!!) \times 1 \\ 6744 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5 \times ((7 - 97) \times (5 \times 3))) + 1) \\ 6745 &:= ((1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) + 5) - (3 - 1) \\ 6746 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (75 + 3)) - 1 \\ 6747 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (75 + 3)) \times 1 \\ 6748 &:= ((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 6749 &:= (((13 \times 5) \times (7 + 97)) - 5) - (3! \times 1) \\ 6750 &:= ((1 \times 35) - (7 - 97)) \times (53 + 1) \\ 6751 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) + ((7 + (9 \times 753)) - 1) \\ 6752 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 + (7 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!))) + 3 \times 1) \\ 6753 &:= (1 + (((3^5) \times 7) + 9)) + ((7! + (5 - 3)) \times 1) \\ 6754 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5! \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) + (5! / (3 + 1))) \\ 6755 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7!) - (((9 - 7!) - 5!) / (3 \times 1)) \\ 6756 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) + (7! + 531) \\ 6757 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) + (5 + 7!)) + (((9 - 7)^5) \times 31) \\ 6758 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - ((7 - 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 6759 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + (((9 + 7!) + 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 6760 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 6761 &:= (((13 \times 5) \times (7 + 97)) - 5) + (3! \times 1) \\ 6762 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((5! - 7) \times (9 - 7)) \times 5) - (3 \times 1) \\ 6763 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) + (7! + 9)) + ((7 + 5)^3 \times 1) \\ 6764 &:= (((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) - 5!) - (3 + 1) \\ 6765 &:= (1^3 + ((5! - 7) + 9)) \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) - 1) \\ 6766 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7! - 9)) + (((7 + 5)^3) - 1) \\ 6767 &:= (13 \times 5!) - ((7 \times (9 - 753)) + 1) \\ 6768 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (((57 + 9) + 75) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 6769 &:= 13 - (5 + (7 - (9 \times (753 - 1)))) \\ 6770 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 - 7)) + ((9 \times 753) + 1) \\ 6771 &:= (((1^{3!}) + 5)! + (7! - (9 \times (7 - 5!)))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 6772 &:= (((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + 9) + 7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 6773 &:= (13 \times 579) - (753 + 1) \\ 6774 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 753)) \times 1) \\ 6775 &:= (1^{35}) \times (7 + (9 \times (753 - 1))) \\ 6776 &:= (1^{357}) \times ((9 \times 753) - 1) \\ 6777 &:= (1^{357}) + ((9 \times 753) - 1) \\ 6778 &:= (((1^{35})^7!) + ((9 \times 753) \times 1)) \\ 6779 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) - (7 \times ((9 - (7!/5)) + 31)) \\ 6780 &:= ((1^{35}) - 7) + (9 \times (753 + 1)) \\ 6781 &:= ((13 + 57) \times 97) - ((5 + 3) + 1) \\ 6782 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - 7) - ((9 \times 753) - 1)) \\ 6783 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times 53)) + 1 \\ 6784 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7 + (9 \times 753))) - 1 \\ 6785 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7 + (9 \times 753))) \times 1 \\ 6786 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7 + (9 \times 753))) + 1 \\ 6787 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (53 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6788 &:= (((13 + 57) \times 97) + 5) - (3! + 1) \\ 6789 &:= (((13 + 57) \times 97) - 5) + (3 + 1) \\ 6790 &:= (1^3 \times 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times 53) - 1 \\ 6791 &:= (((1357 + 9) - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1) \\ 6792 &:= (((13 + 5) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 6793 &:= (13 + 5) + (7 + (9 \times (753 - 1))) \\ 6794 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) + (((9 - 7) - 5)^{3!}) + 1 \\ 6795 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5)) + 7) + (9 \times (753 \times 1)) \\ 6796 &:= ((1 \times 35) - 7) + (9 \times (753 - 1)) \\ 6797 &:= (1 + 35) - (7 - (9 \times (753 - 1))) \\ 6798 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + 7) + (5! + 3 - 1) \\ 6799 &:= ((13 + 57) \times 97) + ((5 + 3) + 1) \\ 6800 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (7 + (5^3))) - 1 \\ 6801 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + 7) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 6802 &:= (13 + (5 + 7)) + (9 \times (753 \times 1)) \\ 6803 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7) + ((9 \times 753) - 1) \\ 6804 &:= (135 - (7 + (9 - 7))) \times (53 + 1) \\ 6805 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) + (9 \times 753)) \times 1 \\ 6806 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) + (9 \times 753)) + 1 \\ 6807 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7 \times 975) - 3)) - 1 \\ 6808 &:= (13 - 5) \times (797 + (53 + 1)) \\ 6809 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7 \times 975) - 3)) + 1 \\ 6810 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9 \times (753 \times 1)) \\ 6811 &:= (13 \times 5!) + (((7! + 97) + 5!) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 6812 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7 + 9)) \times ((7 + (5^3)) - 1) \\ 6813 &:= (((13 \times 57) + 9) + 7) \times ((5 + 3) + 1) \\ 6814 &:= 1 - (3 + ((5 - (7 \times 975)) + 3 + 1)) \\ 6815 &:= ((1 - (35 \times 7)) + 9) \times ((7 - 5) - 31) \\ 6816 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (((5! + 7!) + (97 + 5!)) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 6817 &:= (1^3) - ((5 - (7 \times 975)) + 3 + 1) \\ 6818 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5!)) \times (7 + (9 - (7 \times 5)))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 6819 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 - (7 \times 975)) + 3) + 1) \\ 6820 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5 - (7 \times 975))) - (3 - 1)) \\ 6821 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 - (7 \times 975)) + 3 - 1) \\ 6822 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 - (7 \times 975)) - 3) - 1) \\ 6823 &:= (1^3 - (5 - (7 \times 975))) + (3 - 1) \\ 6824 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5 - (7 \times 975)) + 3 - 1) \\ 6825 &:= ((13 + ((5 \times 7) - 9)) \times 7) \times (5^{3-1}) \\ 6826 &:= 1 - ((35 - (7!/9)) \times ((7 \times (5 - 3)) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6827 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + (9 + (753 + 1))) \\ 6828 &:= (1 \times (35 + 7)) + (9 \times (753 + 1)) \\ 6829 &:= 1 \times ((3! - (5 - (7 \times 975))) + 3 \times 1) \\ 6830 &:= 1 + ((3! - (5 - (7 \times 975))) + 3 \times 1) \\ 6831 &:= (1 - ((3! - 5!) + (7 + 9))) \times (75 - 3! \times 1) \\ 6832 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times 97) + 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 6833 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) - ((7 - 975) \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 6834 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) + (9 \times (753 + 1)) \\ 6835 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - (7 \times 975))) + (3 + 1)! \\ 6836 &:= 1 - (((3!! - (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + 7) - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 6837 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) + ((7!/5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 6838 &:= 13 \times (((5 \times 7) + (97 \times 5)) + 3! \times 1) \\ 6839 &:= ((13 - 5) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) \times 53))) - 1 \\ 6840 &:= ((13 - 5) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) \times 53))) \times 1 \\ 6841 &:= ((13 - 5) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) \times 53))) + 1 \\ 6842 &:= (1 + 3)! - ((5 - (7 \times 975)) + 3 - 1) \\ 6843 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - 7) + (5 + 3 + 1)) \\ 6844 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) + (7 \times (975 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 6845 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((7 \times (975 + 3)) - 1) \\ 6846 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (5 + ((7 + 9) \times (75 - (3 + 1)))) \\ 6847 &:= 13 + (57 + ((9 \times 753) \times 1)) \\ 6848 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5 + (79 - 7)) \times (5! - 31)) \\ 6849 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + (97 \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 6850 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) + (7 \times ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\ 6851 &:= (1^3 + (5 + (7 \times (975 + 3)))) - 1 \\ 6852 &:= (1^3 + (5 + (7 \times (975 + 3)))) \times 1 \\ 6853 &:= (1^3 + (5 + (7 \times (975 + 3)))) + 1 \\ 6854 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (79 - (((7!/5) - 3!) - 1)) \\ 6855 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((57 + 9) \times 7) - 5) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 6856 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((7 \times 975) - (3 + 1)) \\ 6857 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5! \times 7)) + ((975 + 3) - 1) \\ 6858 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 \times 975) - 3) \times 1) \\ 6859 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 75)/3)) - 1 \\ 6860 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 75)/3)) \times 1 \\ 6861 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 75)/3)) + 1 \\ 6862 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5!) + ((7! + 975) + (3!! + 1)) \\ 6863 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) + ((7 \times 975) + 3 \times 1) \\ 6864 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (579 - 7)) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 6865 &:= (1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) + (5! + 3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 6866** := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + ((7 \times (975 + 3)) \times 1)$
6867 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5 + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
6868 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7 \times (975 + 3 + 1))$
6869 := $((1 + 3!)!) - ((5 - 7) - ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
6870 := $((1 - (3! + 5)) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3! - 1)))$
6871 := $(1 + ((3! \times 5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times 5!))) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
6872 := $(1^{3!}) \times ((5 + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
6873 := $(1^{3!}) + ((5 + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
6874 := $(1 + ((35 \times 7) \times (9 - 7))) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
6875 := $(1 - ((35 + (7 - 97)) \times (5^3))) - 1$
6876 := $(1 - ((35 + (7 - 97)) \times (5^3))) \times 1$
6877 := $13 \times ((57 \times 9) + (7 + ((5 + 3) + 1)))$
6878 := $((1 - 3!) + (57 + 9)) + 7531$
6879 := $((1 + 3!) \times 57) + (9 \times (7! / (5 + 3 - 1)))$
6880 := $(1 - 3!) + (5 + (7! - ((9 + 7) \times (5 - ((3! - 1)!)!)))$
6881 := $1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9 + ((7 \times 5!) + 3 + 1)))$
6882 := $((1 \times 3! \times ((5 + 7) \times (9 + 7))) - 5) \times 3! \times 1$
6883 := $1 \times (3! + ((57 \times (9 \times (7 + 5))) + (3! + 1)))$
6884 := $1 + (3! + ((57 \times (9 \times (7 + 5))) + (3! + 1)))$
6885 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 + 7))) \times (9 \times (75 - (3 + 1)!))$
6886 := $(13 \times 5) + ((7 \times 975) - (3 + 1))$
6887 := $1 \times (3! + (5! - (7 - (9 \times (753 - 1)))))$
6888 := $(1 + 3!) + ((579 - 7) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
6889 := $((1 + 3!)!) + (((5! + 7) - (9 + 75))^{3-1})$
6890 := $1 + (((3 - (5 + 79)) - (7 - 5))^{3-1})$
6891 := $(1 \times (3! + 5)) + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3! - 1))))$
6892 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + (7! + (5! + 3! \times 1))$
6893 := $((1 + 3!)!) - (5 + ((79 - (7! / 5)) \times (3 - 1)))$
6894 := $((((1 \times 3!) \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + 7!) - (5 + 31)$
6895 := $((1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 - 3))) \times 1$
6896 := $((13 \times 579) - (7! / (5 + 3))) - 1$
6897 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5! - 7) + (9 \times (753 \times 1)))$
6898 := $((13 \times 579) - (7! / (5 + 3))) + 1$
6899 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 579) + 7!) + 5!) + (3 - 1)$
6900 := $(1 + ((35 / 7) \times 9)) \times (75 \times (3 - 1))$
6901 := $((1 \times 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7! - 5) - (3 + 1)!)!$
6902 := $1 \times ((3! / 5!) + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3 + 1)))))$
6903 := $((13 + (5 - 7)) + (9 - 7)) \times 531$
6904 := $(1 + ((3 \times 579) - (7 + 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
6905 := $1 \times ((3! / 5) - (7 - (9 \times (753 - 1))))$
6906 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7 \times (975 - 3! \times 1))$
6907 := $1 \times (((3!^5) + ((7 - 9) \times 75)) - (3! - 1))$
6908 := $1 + (((3!^5) + ((7 - 9) \times 75)) - (3! - 1))$
6909 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) \times 7 + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
6910 := $(1 \times (((3! \times 5) \times (7 \times 9)) + 7!)) - (5! / 3! \times 1)$
6911 := $(1^3 + 5!) + (7 \times ((975 - 3!) + 1))$
6912 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 - 9)) \times ((7^{5-3}) - 1)$
6913 := $1 + ((3! \times (5! \times 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3 \times 1))))$
6914 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + ((7 \times 97) \times (5 + (3! - 1)))$
6915 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) + ((7! + (9 \times 75)) + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
6916 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 \times (3! \times 1)))$
6917 := $(1^3 \times 5!) + (7 \times (975 - (3 + 1)))$
6918 := $(1^3) + (5! + (7 \times (975 - (3 + 1))))$
6919 := $(1 - 3) - (5! - (7! + (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) + 1)))$
6920 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! + 7)) + (9 \times (753 + 1))$
6921 := $(1^3) - (5! - (7! + (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) \times 1)))$
6922 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + (((7 - 9)^7) - 5)) - (3! + 1)$
6923 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((579 \times (7 + 5)) - 31)$
6924 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((579 \times (7 - 5)) - 3) - 1)$
6925 := $(13 + (5 + 7)) \times (((97 - 5) \times 3) + 1)$
6926 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (((7 + (9 - 7)) + 5!) + 3!)) - 1$
6927 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (((7 + (9 - 7)) + 5!) + 3!)) \times 1$
6928 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (((7 + (9 - 7)) + 5!) + 3!)) + 1$
6929 := $13 \times (579 + ((7 - 53) \times 1))$
6930 := $(1 - (3 - 57)) \times ((97 + 5) + (3 + 1)!)!$
6931 := $(1 \times 3!) - (5 - (7! + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 3! \times 1)))$
6932 := $(1 \times (3 - (5! + 7))) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1})$
6933 := $(1 + (3 - (5! + 7))) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1})$
6934 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 - (7 + 9)) \times (7! / (5 + 3 \times 1)))$
6935 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) - 7 + ((9 + 75)^{3-1})$
6936 := $(1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 79) - (75 + 31))$
6937 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9))) - (7 \times (5! - (3 + 1)))$
6938 := $(135 + (7 \times (975 - 3))) - 1$
6939 := $(135 + (7 \times (975 - 3))) \times 1$
6940 := $(135 + (7 \times (975 - 3))) + 1$
6941 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (((7 - (9 - 7)))! - (5 - 3! \times 1)))$
6942 := $13 \times (579 + ((7 - 53) + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 6943 &:= ((1-3) - (5!-7!)) + ((9 \times (75 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 6944 &:= (13 \times 5!) + (7! - (((9+7) - (5! \times 3)) \times 1)) \\ 6945 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7 \times 975)) + ((3!-1)!) \\ 6946 &:= (13 - ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) \times (7 - ((5 \times 3!) \times 1)) \\ 6947 &:= ((1+3) + (579 \times (7+5))) - (3!-1) \\ 6948 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 \times (7-5))) \times (3-1) \\ 6949 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (7 + ((9+75)^{3-1})) \\ 6950 &:= ((1-3) - 579) + 7531 \\ 6951 &:= 1 \times 3 + (579 \times ((7-5) \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 6952 &:= (1-3) \times (5 - ((7+(9-75))^{3-1})) \\ 6953 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) + (((7 \times 975) + 3!) - 1) \\ 6954 &:= (((1-3) - 5!) \times (((7-9) \times 7) - 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 6955 &:= (1 \times (3 - 579)) + 7531 \\ 6956 &:= 1 + ((3 - 579) + 7531) \\ 6957 &:= ((1+3) + (579 \times (7+5))) + (3!-1) \\ 6958 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (((7 - (9-7)) + 5) \times 3!! \times 1) \\ 6959 &:= (((1+35) - 7) \times ((9+7) \times (5 \times 3))) - 1 \\ 6960 &:= (((1+35) - 7) \times ((9+7) \times (5 \times 3))) \times 1 \\ 6961 &:= (((1+35) - 7) \times ((9+7) \times (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\ 6962 &:= ((13 \times (5+7)) - 97) \times (5! - (3-1)) \\ 6963 &:= (1^3) + ((57 + (9-7)) \times (5! - (3-1))) \\ 6964 &:= (((1+3)^5) \times 7) - (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 6965 &:= (13 - 579) + 7531 \\ 6966 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (((5! - 7) + 9) + 7)) \times (53 + 1) \\ 6967 &:= ((1^3 - 5) - (7!/9)) + 7531 \\ 6968 &:= (1^3 + 5!) + ((7 \times (975 + 3)) + 1) \\ 6969 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (75 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 6970 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) - (7 \times ((9 - ((7!/5) - 3)) \times 1)) \\ 6971 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7 \times 97) + (5! + (3! \times 1))) \\ 6972 &:= 13 + (((5+7)!) + ((9+7) \times 5!)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 6973 &:= (1 + ((3! - 5) - (7!/9))) + 7531 \\ 6974 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5! - (7 - ((9 \times (7+5!)) \times 3! \times 1))) \\ 6975 &:= (((1+3) \times 57) \times 9) + 7! - (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\ 6976 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times (5+7)) \times 97) - ((5+3) \times 1) \\ 6977 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) + 7!) + (((9+7) \times 5!) + (3! - 1)) \\ 6978 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (797 - 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 6979 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (797 - 5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 6980 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) + ((7-9) - (75+3!))) + 1) \\ 6981 &:= 135 + ((7 \times (975 + 3)) \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6982 &:= 135 + ((7 \times (975 + 3)) + 1) \\ 6983 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) - (797 - 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 6984 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) + ((7 \times (975 + 3!)) - 1) \\ 6985 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! + (7 \times (975 + 3!))) \times 1) \\ 6986 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) - (797 - 5))) + (3 - 1) \\ 6987 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (797 - 5)) + (3 - 1) \\ 6988 &:= 13 + (5 \times (((7 \times 9)/7) \times 5) \times 31) \\ 6989 &:= (13 \times 579) - (7 + 531) \\ 6990 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (797 - 5)) + (3! - 1) \\ 6991 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (797 - 5)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 6992 &:= (((1+3) + 579) \times (7+5)) - (3+1) \\ 6993 &:= (1 - (3+5)) \times (7 - (975+31)) \\ 6994 &:= ((1+3) - (57+9)) + ((7!/5) \times (3!+1)) \\ 6995 &:= ((1-3!) + (5!+7!)) - ((9+7) \times (5 - ((3!-1)!))!) \\ 6996 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 579) + (7+5)) \times (3+1)) \\ 6997 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 579) + (7+5)) \times (3+1)) \\ 6998 &:= (((((1+3) \times 5) \times (7+(9 \times 7))) \times 5) - 3) + 1 \\ 6999 &:= (1^3 + 5) + (7 \times (975 + (3+1)!)) \\ 7000 &:= (((1+3) + 579) \times (7+5)) + (3+1) \\ 7001 &:= ((1 + (3! + 579)) \times (7+5)) - 31 \\ 7002 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7 - (9+7)) - 5!) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 7003 &:= (13 \times 579) + (7 - 531) \\ 7004 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + (7 \times 9))) \times ((7+5!) - (3+1)!) \\ 7005 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (57 - ((9+75)^{3-1})) \\ 7006 &:= (1 + 3!) - (57 - ((9+75)^{3-1})) \\ 7007 &:= (((1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5)) - 3!!) + 1 \\ 7008 &:= (((1+3)^5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times 3))) - 1 \\ 7009 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7)) + ((9 + (7!/5)) \times (3! + 1)) \\ 7010 &:= (((1+3)^5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times 3))) + 1 \\ 7011 &:= (1 - (3! - 5!)) + (7! + ((9+7) \times (5! - (3+1)))) \\ 7012 &:= (((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) + 5!) + (3 + 1) \\ 7013 &:= 13 + ((5 \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) \times (5^{3-1})) \\ 7014 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) \times (3! + 1)) \\ 7015 &:= (((1+3)! - 5!) \times (7 - ((9+7) \times 5))) + (3! + 1) \\ 7016 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - (((7 + (9 \times 7)) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 7017 &:= (((1+3!))!/5) + (7! + (975 - 3! \times 1)) \\ 7018 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 + 79) + (7 - (5 \times (3!! \times 1)))) \\ 7019 &:= (1 \times (3!! \times 5)) + ((7 \times (97 \times 5)) + (3 + 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7020 &:= ((1^{3!}) + (((5! - 7) + 9) + 7)) \times (53 + 1) \\7021 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) \times (7 + (((9 + 7) - 5) - 3!))) + 1 \\7022 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) + 7) - 9) - (753 - 1) \\7023 &:= (1 + (((3!^5) + 7) - 9)) - (753 - 1) \\7024 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 7)^{9-7}) + 531) \\7025 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) + ((9 - 7) \times 5!) + (3! + 1) \\7026 &:= ((1 \times (3^5 + 7)) + (9 \times 753)) - 1 \\7027 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) - (9 + 7) - (5^3 \times 1) \\7028 &:= ((1 \times (3^5 + 7)) + (9 \times 753)) + 1 \\7029 &:= ((1 + (3! + 579)) \times (7 + 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\7030 &:= ((1 + (3! + 579)) \times (7 + 5)) - (3 - 1) \\7031 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5!) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3!)) \\7032 &:= (1 - ((3! - 5!) \times (7 \times 9))) - ((7 + 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\7033 &:= (13 \times (57 \times 9)) + (7 \times (53 - 1)) \\7034 &:= 1 - (3 + ((5 - 7!) - (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) + 1))) \\7035 &:= ((1 + (3! + 579)) \times (7 + 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\7036 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + 79)) + ((7! - (5!/3!)) \times 1) \\7037 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + 79)) + ((7! - (5!/3!)) + 1) \\7038 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) + 7) + 9) - (753 + 1) \\7039 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) + 7) + 9) - (753 + 1) \\7040 &:= (1 + (((3!^5) + 7) + 9) - 753) \times 1 \\7041 &:= ((1^{35}) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\7042 &:= (1^{35}) \times (7 \times (975 + 31)) \\7043 &:= (1^{35}) + (7 \times (975 + 31)) \\7044 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) - ((7 \times (9 \times (7 + 5))) - (3 + 1)!) \\7045 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7!)/9) \times 7 + (5^{3!-1}) \\7046 &:= (1 \times 3)! - (5 \times (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5 + 3!)) \times 1) \\7047 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) \times (((7 + 9) \times (7 - 5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\7048 &:= (1^3 + 5) + (7 \times (975 + 31)) \\7049 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5 - 7!) - (9 \times ((75 \times 3) - 1))) \\7050 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (5 - (7!/(9 + 7) + 5))) \times (3! \times 1) \\7051 &:= ((1 \times (3! \times 5)) \times 79) + (7! - ((5! \times 3) - 1)) \\7052 &:= (1 - (35/7)) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1}) \\7053 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 \times (9 + (7 - 5!))) + 3 + 1) \\7054 &:= ((1 + (3 - 57)) \times 9) + 7531 \\7055 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 579) + (7! - (5 - (3! + 1))) \\7056 &:= ((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (97 + 5 \times 31) \\7057 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 + 9) \times ((7 - 53) + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7058 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5) \times (7 - 9)) - ((7 + 5) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\7059 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((57 - 9) \times (7^{5-3})) + 1) \\7060 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + 7!) - (((9 - 7!) - 5!) + (3! \times 1)) \\7061 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + 7!) - (((9 - 7!) - 5!) + (3! - 1)) \\7062 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5) + 7) \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) + 3! \times 1)) \\7063 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) - ((7 + (9 \times 75)) + 31)) \\7064 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) - ((7 + (9 \times 75)) + 31)) \\7065 &:= (13 \times 5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \\7066 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7 + (9 - 7))) - ((5! \times 3!) - 1) \\7067 &:= (1 - 3) - (5 - (7! + (9 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)))) \\7068 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5! + (7 \times 9)) - (7 \times 531)) \\7069 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7 \times (9 - 7))) - (5! \times 3!) - 1 \\7070 &:= (1 \times 35) \times (7 + (975/(3! - 1))) \\7071 &:= ((13 - 5) + 7) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1}) \\7072 &:= 1 \times ((3! \times 5) + (7 \times (975 + 31))) \\7073 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + (7 \times (975 + 31)) \\7074 &:= (((1 \times 3)^{5-7+9}) - (7!/5)) \times 3! \times 1 \\7075 &:= (1 - 3!) - (5! \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) - 5) + 3 - 1)) \\7076 &:= (1 + ((35 - 7) - 9)) + ((7!/5) \times (3! + 1)) \\7077 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + (7! + (9 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1))) \\7078 &:= (((13 \times (5 + 7)) - 97) \times 5!) - (3 - 1) \\7079 &:= 135 + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times (5! + 3 + 1)) \\7080 &:= (1^3 + (57 + (9 - 7))) \times (5! - (3 - 1)) \\7081 &:= ((13 + 5) + 79) \times ((75 - 3) + 1) \\7082 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5)^7) + ((9 - 7) \times (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\7083 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5! \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5! - 3!)) + 1)) \\7084 &:= ((1 + (((35 - 7) - 9) + 7!)/5) \times (3! + 1) \\7085 &:= (1 - 3 + (579 + (7 \times 5!))) \times (3! - 1) \\7086 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5) + (((7 - (9 - 7)))! \times (53 \times 1)) \\7087 &:= (1 + (3 - 5)) + (7! + ((9 - 7)^{5+3! \times 1})) \\7088 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - 5) \times 7)! + ((9 - 7)^{5+3! \times 1}) \\7089 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) + 7!) - ((9 - 75) \times 31) \\7090 &:= (1 - 3) \times (57 - ((9 - 7) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!))) \\7091 &:= (1^{3!}) + (((5! - 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5 - (3 + 1)!) \\7092 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((579 + (7 + 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\7093 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) + (7! + (97 \times ((5!/3!) + 1))) \\7094 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! - (7!/9)) + 7531) \\7095 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + 57) - ((9 - (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))\end{aligned}$$

- 7096** := $((13 - 5) \times 797) + (5! \times 3! \times 1)$
7097 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((797 - 5!) + 3) + 1$
7098 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + (7 \times 97)))) + (5 + ((3! + 1)!))$
7099 := $((1 + 3!) - 5!) + 7! + (9 \times (7 + 5 \times 31))$
7100 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 + 9) - (75 \times (3 + 1)))$
7101 := $1 \times ((3!)^5) - ((7! / (9 + 7)) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
7102 := $1 + ((3!)^5) - ((7! / (9 + 7)) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
7103 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (797 - (5^3) - 1)$
7104 := $(13 + 579) \times ((7 - 5) \times 3! \times 1)$
7105 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 - (9 \times 75)) - (3 \times 1))$
7106 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((7 \times (9 - 7)) + 5!) \times (3! - 1))$
7107 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 + (9 + (7 \times 5))) - 3! \times 1)$
7108 := $((1 + (3 - 5!)) \times 7) + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times (3! \times 1))$
7109 := $((1 \times 35) + 7!) - (9 \times ((7 - 5!) \times (3 - 1)))$
7110 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + 797 \times ((5 + 3) + 1)$
7111 := $13 \times ((5! - 7) - (97 - 531))$
7112 := $(1 + 3!) \times ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1)))$
7113 := $((1 - (35 + 7)) + (9 \times (75 + 3!))) - 1$
7114 := $((1 - (35 + 7)) + (9 \times (75 + 3!))) \times 1$
7115 := $((1 - (35 + 7)) + (9 \times (75 + 3!))) + 1$
7116 := $1^{35} - (((7 \times 9) \times (7 - 5!)) + 3 + 1)$
7117 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times (7 + 9))^{7-5})) - (3 \times 1)$
7118 := $(1 - (3 + (5 \times 7))) + (9 \times (75 + ((3! \times 1)!))$
7119 := $((1 - 357) \times ((97 - 5!) + 3)) - 1$
7120 := $(1 + 3!) + (57 + ((9 + 75)^{3-1}))$
7121 := $((1 - 357) \times ((97 - 5!) + 3)) + 1$
7122 := $(1 + (((3!)^5) + 7) + (9 \times 7)) - (5 + ((3! \times 1)!))$
7123 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times (7 + 9))^{7-5})) + (3 \times 1)$
7124 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 \times (7 + 9))^{7-5}) + 3 \times 1)$
7125 := $(1 \times (3 \times ((5 - 7) + 97))) \times (5^{3-1})$
7126 := $(13 + 57) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1})$
7127 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times 3)) - 1$
7128 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times 3)) \times 1$
7129 := $(1 + (3 - 57)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! - (3! \times 1)))$
7130 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((579 + 7) + 5!)) \times (3! - 1)$
7131 := $((1 + (3!)^5) + (7 + ((9 \times 7) + 5))) - (3! + 1)$
7132 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 + (7 \times (9 \times (7 - 5!)))) + 3! \times 1)$
7133 := $((1 + 3!)! / 5) + (7! + ((97 + 5!) \times (3! - 1)))$
7134 := $1 - ((3 + (5 \times 79)) - 7531)$
7135 := $((1 + (3! \times 5)) - 7) \times (9 - 7) - (53 \times 1)$
7136 := $((1 \times (3!)^5) - (7 \times (97 - 5))) + (3 + 1)$
7137 := $(13 + (5! - (7 + 9))) \times (7 + (53 + 1))$
7138 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) - ((7 \times 9) \times (7 - 5!)) + (3 + 1)$
7139 := $(1 \times ((3!)^5) + 7) - ((97 - 5) \times (3! + 1))$
7140 := $(135 - (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (53 \times 1))$
7141 := $((1 - 3!) - 5!) + ((7975 + 3!) - 1)$
7142 := $((1 - 3579) + 7) \times (5 - (3! + 1))$
7143 := $(1 \times 357) + (9 \times (753 + 1))$
7144 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! + (53 - 1))$
7145 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! + (53 \times 1))$
7146 := $((1 + 3579) - 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
7147 := $(1 \times (35 - (7 \times (9 \times (7 - 5!)))) - (3! + 1))$
7148 := $(1 \times (35 - (7 \times (9 \times (7 - 5!)))) - 3! \times 1$
7149 := $13 - ((5 \times 79) - 7531)$
7150 := $(13 \times ((57 - (9 - 7)) \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
7151 := $1 - ((3! - 5) \times ((7 - ((9 + 7) - 5)) - (3! \times 1)))$
7152 := $((1 + 3!) + (579 - 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1)$
7153 := $13 + ((5 \times (7 \times (97 + 5))) \times (3 - 1))$
7154 := $(1 - (3^5)) + (((79 + 7)^{5-3}) \times 1)$
7155 := $(13 \times 579) - ((7 + 5) \times 31)$
7156 := $(13 \times 579) - (7 \times (53 \times 1))$
7157 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5) + 3) \times 1$
7158 := $(1 \times (35 - (7 \times (9 \times (7 - 5!)))) + (3 + 1))$
7159 := $1 - (3579 \times ((7 - (5 + 3)) - 1))$
7160 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - 97) \times (5 \times (3 + 1))$
7161 := $((1 - 3 + (5! \times 7)) \times 9) - ((7 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
7162 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (7 \times (9 - 7))) - (5! \times (3! - 1))$
7163 := $((1 + (3! \times 5)) + 7) \times (9 - 7) - (53 \times 1)$
7164 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + (7 - (9 - 7)))) - (5 + 31)$
7165 := $(1 \times ((3 \times ((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) + 5!) \times 3) + 1$
7166 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + (797 \times ((5 + 3) + 1))$
7167 := $((1 + 3)^5 \times 7) - (((9 - 7)^5) - 31)$
7168 := $((1 + 3)^5 \times 7) \times (((9 - 7)^5) - 31)$
7169 := $((1 + 3)^5 \times 7) + (((9 - 7)^5) - 31)$
7170 := $(1 \times 3! \times 5) \times (((7 \times (97 + 5)) / 3) + 1)$
7171 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) \times 7 + (5 + (3! - 1))$
7172 := $((1^3 \times (5! \times (7 + 9))) - (7 + 5!)) \times (3 + 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}7173 &:= 1 \times (3 \times ((57 + 9) + (75 \times 31))) \\7174 &:= 1 + (3 \times ((57 + 9) + (75 \times 31))) \\7175 &:= (1 \times 35) \times (7 - (((9 - 75) \times 3) \times 1)) \\7176 &:= (1^3 + 5) \times (((7 + 9) \times 75) - (3 + 1)) \\7177 &:= ((1 + (3 \times ((5 + 797) - 5))) \times 3) + 1 \\7178 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + 5!) + (3 - 1) \\7179 &:= (1 \times (((3!! + 579) + 7!) + 5!)) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\7180 &:= (1 + (3!! + 579)) + (7! + (5! + ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\7181 &:= (1 + (((3!! + 579) + 7!) + 5!)) + (3!! + 1) \\7182 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) \times ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\7183 &:= (1 + 357) + (975 \times (3! + 1)) \\7184 &:= (1 - ((3!! \times 5) \times (7 - 9))) - ((7 + 5) + (3! - 1)) \\7185 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) + (9 \times ((75 + 3!!) - 1)) \\7186 &:= (1 + 3) - ((57 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 - (3! + 1))) \\7187 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 579) - (7 - (5! \times 31)) \\7188 &:= 13 + (((5! - 79) \times 7) \times (5^{3-1})) \\7189 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7!)) + 97) / 5 \times (3! + 1) \\7190 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) - (5! \times (3! - 1))) \\7191 &:= (13 + 5) + (797 \times ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\7192 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! \times (5 + (7 - (9 - 7)))) - (5 + 3 \times 1) \\7193 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9 \times ((75 + 3!!) \times 1)) \\7194 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5 - (((7 + 9) \times 75) \times 3!)) - 1) \\7195 &:= (135 \times (7 + 9)) + (7! - (5! / (3 + 1)!!)) \\7196 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (57 + ((975 - 3) - 1)) \\7197 &:= (135 \times (7 + 9)) + ((7! - 5) + 3 - 1) \\7198 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7! - (9 - 7)) - (5! \times 3! \times 1)) \\7199 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) + (((7 - (9 - 7)) + 5) \times 3!! \times 1) \\7200 &:= (135 + 7!) + (9 \times ((75 \times 3) \times 1)) \\7201 &:= (1^{35}) \times (7! - (((9 - (7 + 5)) \times 3!!) - 1)) \\7202 &:= (1^{35}) + (7! - (((9 - (7 + 5)) \times 3!!) - 1)) \\7203 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7^{9-7+5-3 \times 1}) \\7204 &:= ((1 - ((3! + 5) - (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times 5!) + (3 + 1) \\7205 &:= (135 \times (7 + 9)) + (7! + (5! / (3 + 1)!!)) \\7206 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (5 + (((7 + 9) \times 75) - (3 + 1))) \\7207 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (7 + 531) \\7208 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5 - 7) - (((9 - 7) \times 5) \times 3!! \times 1)) \\7209 &:= (((((1 + 3) \times 57) \times 9) + 7!) + 5!) - (3 \times 1) \\7210 &:= (13 + 57) \times (97 + (((5 - 3) + 1)!!)) \\7211 &:= 1 - (((3 - 57) + 9) + (7 \times 5)) \times (3!! + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7212 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times (75 + 31)) \\7213 &:= (((((1 + 3^5) - 7) \times 9) + 7!) + (5! / (3 \times 1))) \\7214 &:= (1 - (((3! - 5!) \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\7215 &:= (((((1 + 3) \times 57) \times 9) + 7!) + 5!) + (3 \times 1) \\7216 &:= (1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! - ((5 \times 3!) \times 1)) \\7217 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) + ((9 \times (7 - 5)) + 31) \\7218 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5! - 3!) \times 1)) \\7219 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5!)) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5)) + (3!! + 1) \\7220 &:= ((1 + 3)! - 5) + (((7 + 9) \times 75) \times 3!) + 1) \\7221 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + (7! - 9)) + (7! / ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\7222 &:= (1 + (3^5)) - (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5) - (3! - 1)) \\7223 &:= 1 \times (((3! - 5) + (7 \times (9 + 7))) + 5!) \times 31) \\7224 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\7225 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7 + 9) \times ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\7226 &:= (1 + (3^{5-7+9})) + (7! - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\7227 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5))^7) + ((9 - (7 - 5)) \times 3!! \times 1) \\7228 &:= (((1 + (35 \times 7)) \times 9) + 7!) + 5 - 31) \\7229 &:= (13 - ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + 7531) \\7230 &:= (1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\7231 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) + (((7 - 9) \times 7) - 531) \\7232 &:= (((1 \times (3 \times (5 + 797))) + 5) \times 3) - 1) \\7233 &:= (((1 \times (3 \times (5 + 797))) + 5) \times 3) \times 1) \\7234 &:= (((1 \times (3 \times (5 + 797))) + 5) \times 3) + 1) \\7235 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times ((5 \times 7)^{9-7})) - 5!) + (3! - 1) \\7236 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! \times (5 + (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5 + 31) \\7237 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times ((5 \times 7)^{9-7})) - 5!) + (3! + 1) \\7238 &:= 1 - (((3 + 5) - 7!) - (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times (3! + 1))) \\7239 &:= 1 \times (((35 - 7) - 9) \times ((7 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))) \\7240 &:= 1 + (((35 - 7) - 9) \times ((7 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))) \\7241 &:= (((1 + (3!! \times 5)) - 7) \times (9 - 7)) + (53 \times 1) \\7242 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7! - 5) + 3 - 1) \\7243 &:= ((1 + 3)!) + (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\7244 &:= ((1 + 3)!) + (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - (3 + 1))) \\7245 &:= (1 \times (3! + 57)) \times ((9 + 75) + 31) \\7246 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5! + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! - 3))) - 1) \\7247 &:= 1 - (((3!! \times 5) + (7 + (9 + 7))) \times (5 - (3! + 1))) \\7248 &:= (((((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times 7) \times 9) - (753 \times 1)) \\7249 &:= (1 + (3^5)) - (((7 \times 97) - 5!) - 31) \\7250 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! + 5) \times (((7 \times 9) + 7) / 5) - (3 + 1))\end{aligned}$$

- 7251** := $1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5!) + (3 + 1)!)$
7252 := $1 - ((3! \times 5!) - (7975 - (3 + 1)))$
7253 := $(1 \times ((35 \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7! + 5) + 3))) \times 1$
7254 := $(13 + 5) \times (7 + (9 \times (75 - 31)))$
7255 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) + 531)$
7256 := $((1^3 + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7)) + (5! \times (3 + 1))$
7257 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) - (5! \times (3! - 1)))$
7258 := $135 - (((7 \times 9) \times (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1))$
7259 := $1 \times (((35 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! + (5 \times 3))) - 1)$
7260 := $1 + (((35 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! + (5 \times 3))) - 1)$
7261 := $(1^3 \times 5) + (7975 - (3! - 1))$
7262 := $(1 - (3! \times 5!)) + ((7975 + 3!) \times 1)$
7263 := $13 - (5 - (7975 - (3! \times 1)))$
7264 := $(1 + 3)! - ((5 - 7!) - (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times (3! + 1)))$
7265 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7975)) - (3! + 1)$
7266 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7975)) - (3! \times 1)$
7267 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 - 97) + (5! \times (3! - 1)))$
7268 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7 + 9 + 7) - 531)$
7269 := $((1 + (3! \times 5)) + 7) \times (9 - 7) + (53 \times 1)$
7270 := $((13 - (5 - 7)) \times (97 \times 5)) - (3! - 1)$
7271 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) - (((7! / (9 - 7)) + 5) / (3! - 1))$
7272 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (((7 \times 9) \times (7 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)))$
7273 := $13 + ((5 + 7975) - (3! \times 1))$
7274 := $((1 \times ((3!^5) + 7)) - (97 \times 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
7275 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) \times 7 + 5! - (3! \times 1)$
7276 := $1 \times ((3 - 5) \times (79 - (7 \times 531)))$
7277 := $((1 + 3)^5 \times 7) - (9 + 7) + (5^3 \times 1)$
7278 := $(1 - 3) + (((57 \times 9) + 7) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
7279 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5 - 7) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31}))$
7280 := $(13 + 57) \times ((9 - 7) \times (53 - 1))$
7281 := $((1 \times 3 + (5 + 7)) \times (97 \times 5)) + (3! \times 1)$
7282 := $((13 \times 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times 7)) + 5 - (3 \times 1)$
7283 := $1 - (((3! \times (5 \times (7 - 9))) - 75) - 3! - 1)$
7284 := $(1 + 3) \times (5! + ((7! + (9 \times 7)) / ((5 - 3) + 1)))$
7285 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5 \times (7 + 9))) + (75 \times 31)$
7286 := $1 - (((3 - 5!) + (7 \times 9)) + 7) \times (5 \times 31)$
7287 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) \times 7 + 5! + (3! \times 1)$
7288 := $((13 \times 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times 7)) + 5 + (3 \times 1)$
7289 := $(1 + (3! \times (5 \times 79))) + (((7! - 5!) - 3) + 1)$
7290 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) - 7) \times (9 \times (7 + 5 \times 31))$
7291 := $((13 \times 5) \times (7 + 97)) + 531$
7292 := $(1 + 3) \times ((57 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 - 3))) - 1)$
7293 := $((1 - 3!) + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
7294 := $((1 \times ((3!^5) + 7)) - (97 \times 5)) - (3 + 1)$
7295 := $(1 + (3! \times (5 \times 79))) + (((7! - 5!) + 3) + 1)$
7296 := $(1 \times (3 + (57 + (9 + 7)))) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!)$
7297 := $((1 + 3)! - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5! - 3) - 1))$
7298 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) - 5 - (3! - 1)$
7299 := $1 - (((3 - 5!) \times 7) \times 9) + (75 - (3 - 1))$
7300 := $((1 + 3) - (5 + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5! - 3) - 1))$
7301 := $(1 - (3^5)) + (7 + ((9 \times (7 \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)!))$
7302 := $((1 \times ((3!^5) + 7)) - (97 \times 5)) + (3 + 1)$
7303 := $((1^3!) - (5 + (7 \times 9))) \times (7 - (5! - (3 + 1)))$
7304 := $((1 + 3) \times 579) + (7! - (53 - 1))$
7305 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) - 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! - (3 - 1)))$
7306 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
7307 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) + 7) + (9 \times (7 \times (5! - 3! \times 1)))$
7308 := $((1 \times (357 - 9)) \times 7) \times (5 - (3 - 1))$
7309 := $13 + ((57 \times ((9 - 7)^5)) \times (3 + 1))$
7310 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5!) - 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) - 5 + (3! + 1)$
7311 := $((1 \times (3! \times 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 + 5!))) - 3! \times 1$
7312 := $(1 + 3) \times (5! + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times ((5! + 3) - 1)))$
7313 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5! \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) - 5)) + 3 - 1)$
7314 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 + 7) \times 9)) \times (75 - (3! \times 1))$
7315 := $(1 + (35 \times ((79 + 7) + (5! + 3)))) - 1$
7316 := $(1 + (35 \times ((79 + 7) + (5! + 3)))) \times 1$
7317 := $(1 + (35 \times ((79 + 7) + (5! + 3)))) + 1$
7318 := $(1 + (3 \times 5!)) + (7! + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)))$
7319 := $((1 + 3!)! - 5) + 79) \times 75 - 31$
7320 := $(13 \times 5) + (7975 - (3! \times 1))$
7321 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + ((5! / 3) + 1)$
7322 := $((1 \times ((3!^5) + 7)) - (97 \times 5)) + (3 + 1)!$
7323 := $((1 + 3)! \times (5 - 7)) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5! - 3)) \times 1)$
7324 := $((1 + 3) + (5 + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5! - 3) - 1))$
7325 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + ((5 + 3!) \times 1))$
7326 := $((1 \times 3!) \times ((5 \times 7)^{9-7})) - (5! / (3! - 1))$
7327 := $((13 \times 5!) - 7) + 9) + (7! + 5) + 3! \times 1$
7328 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + (((9 - 7)^5) \times 31))$

$$\begin{aligned} 7329 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - ((5! \times (7 - ((9 \times 7) + 5))) - 3)) \times 1 \\ 7330 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (7 - ((97 \times 5) - 31)) \\ 7331 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + ((7! + 9) + (7 - 5))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 7332 &:= (1 + 3!) + (5 \times (7 + (9 \times (7 + 5 \times 31)))) \\ 7333 &:= ((13 - (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + 7531 \\ 7334 &:= (1 - ((3! - 5!) \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7 + 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 7335 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) - 79) + 7531 \\ 7336 &:= (1 + 3) - (5! + (79 - 7531)) \\ 7337 &:= 1 - (((3! \times 5) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 - 531)) \\ 7338 &:= (1^3 + ((5! + 797) \times (5 + 3))) + 1 \\ 7339 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (797 - (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 7340 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5) - 3)) \times 1 \\ 7341 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5) - 3)) + 1 \\ 7342 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7 + (9 - (7 - 5))) \times 31) \\ 7343 &:= 1 - ((35 \times 7) - (9 \times ((7 \times 5!) + 3 \times 1))) \\ 7344 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7 + 9) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 7345 &:= (1 + 3!!) + ((5 + 7) \times ((97 - 5) \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 7346 &:= (1 + 3!!) + ((5 + ((7 - (9 - 7))))!) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 7347 &:= (((1^3 + 5) \times 79) / (7 - 5)) \times 31 \\ 7348 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 579) + 7!) - (5 + 3 \times 1) \\ 7349 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 \times (97 - (5 + 31))) \\ 7350 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 + (7 + (5 \times 3))) - 1) \\ 7351 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times ((5 \times 7)^{9-7})) - (5 - (3! \times 1)) \\ 7352 &:= ((1^3 - 5) + 7!) - (9 - (75 \times 31)) \\ 7353 &:= ((1 - (3! + 5)) - 7) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5! - 3)) - 1) \\ 7354 &:= ((1 - (3! + 5)) - 7) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5! - 3)) \times 1) \\ 7355 &:= (((1 + 3)!)! - ((5 \times 7) \times (9 - 75))) + 3! - 1 \\ 7356 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times (5! / (3 + 1))) \\ 7357 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! + (((57 - 9) \times 7) - 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 7358 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) - ((79 - ((7 - 5!) \times 3)) \times 1)) \\ 7359 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) - ((79 - ((7 - 5!) \times 3)) \times 1)) \\ 7360 &:= ((1 - (3! - 5!)) \times ((7 + 97) - (5! / 3))) \times 1 \\ 7361 &:= ((1 - (3! - 5!)) \times ((7 + 97) - (5! / 3))) + 1 \\ 7362 &:= (((1 + (35 / 7))!) \times 9) + (7 \times ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 7363 &:= 1 + (((3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 97) - 5) \times (3 - 1) \\ 7364 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\ 7365 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 - 7)) + (9 \times (7 \times (5! - (3 \times 1)))) \\ 7366 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7) + 97) \times 53 - 1 \\ 7367 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7) + 97) \times 53 \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7368 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7) + 97) \times 53 + 1 \\ 7369 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7! - (5! / 3)) - 1) \\ 7370 &:= (1 - (3! + 5)) \times (7 + (9 - (753 \times 1))) \\ 7371 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5) - 79)) \times ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\ 7372 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 7373 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 + (53 + 1)) \\ 7374 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times ((5 \times 7)^{9-7})) + (5! / (3! - 1)) \\ 7375 &:= (1^3 \times 5!) + (7975 - (3!! \times 1)) \\ 7376 &:= (1 \times 3! \times ((5 \times 7)^{9-7})) - (5 - 31) \\ 7377 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) - (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 7378 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (7 \times ((9 \times 7) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1))) \\ 7379 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (5 \times 79)) + (7! - ((5 \times 3!) + 1)) \\ 7380 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) \times ((7! - 5!) / 3!)) \times 1 \\ 7381 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (5! + ((7975 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 7382 &:= ((1 \times ((3 + 5) + 7!)) + 9) + (75 \times 31) \\ 7383 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5!) - (7 \times (9 \times (7 - (5! + 3! \times 1)))) \\ 7384 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) - (7 \times ((9 - 7) + (53 + 1)))) \\ 7385 &:= ((13 \times (57 \times (9 - 7))) - 5) \times (3! - 1) \\ 7386 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times 5) + (7! - 9)) + (75 \times 31) \\ 7387 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5!)) \times 7) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31}) \\ 7388 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 + (9 + ((7 \times 53) + 1))) \\ 7389 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) \times (((7! - 5!) / 3!) + 1) \\ 7390 &:= (1 - (3 - (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) - ((7! / 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 7391 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + (7! - ((97 - 5!)^{3-1})) \\ 7392 &:= ((13 - 5) \times (7 \times (9 + (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 7393 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5! + (7 + 9))) + 7531 \\ 7394 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 - 7))) \times (97 + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\ 7395 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5)^7)) - (9 - 7531) \\ 7396 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5!) \times 7) \times 9) - (((7 \times 5) - 31)!) \\ 7397 &:= (1^{35}) + ((79 + 7)^{5-3 \times 1}) \\ 7398 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 7399 &:= (13 \times 579) - ((7 - 5)^{3!+1}) \\ 7400 &:= ((1 - 3!) - ((5 \times 7) - ((9 \times 7) \times 5!))) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 7401 &:= (1^3 + 5) + (((79 + 7)^{5-3}) - 1) \\ 7402 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) - ((7 \times 9) \times ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\ 7403 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 - (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1))) \\ 7404 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) - 7) + (97 + 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 7405 &:= (((1 - 3) - (5 + 7)) \times 9) + 7531 \\ 7406 &:= (13 \times ((57 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7407 &:= ((1-3)-5!) + ((7-9) + 7531) \\ 7408 &:= (((1-3) \times 57) - 9) + 7531 \\ 7409 &:= (1-3!) - ((5!+7) \times ((9-75) + 3-1)) \\ 7410 &:= (((1 \times 3) - ((5 \times 7) - 97)) \times (5! - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 7411 &:= (((1-3) - 5!) - (7-9)) + 7531 \\ 7412 &:= (13 - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! - (3-1))) \\ 7413 &:= (1 + ((3-5)^7)) + (9 + 7531) \\ 7414 &:= (13 \times ((57 \times (9-7)) \times 5)) + (3+1) \\ 7415 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5!)) + ((7-9) + 7531) \\ 7416 &:= ((1+3!) + (5!+79)) \times ((7!/5!) - 3! \times 1) \\ 7417 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7!/((9+(7-5))+3)) - 1) \\ 7418 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5+7) \times (97+(5-3!)))) - 1 \\ 7419 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5+7) \times (97+(5-3!)))) \times 1 \\ 7420 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5+7) \times (97+(5-3!)))) + 1 \\ 7421 &:= ((13 \times 579) - 75) - 31 \\ 7422 &:= (13 \times 579) - (7 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 7423 &:= ((13 \times 579) - ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) + 1 \\ 7424 &:= ((1+35) - 7) \times ((9-7)^{5+3 \times 1}) \\ 7425 &:= ((1+3!)!) + ((5+(7-9)) \times ((75+3!) \times 1)) \\ 7426 &:= (((1-3) \times 57) + 9) + 7531 \\ 7427 &:= (1+3) - (((5+7) \times 9) - 7531) \\ 7428 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) - (5! - (7 \times 975))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 7429 &:= (((1-3+5!) \times 7) \times 9) - (7 - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 7430 &:= (1^3 - 5) - ((7-9) \times (7 \times 531)) \\ 7431 &:= ((1+3) - ((5!+7) - ((9 \times 7) \times 5!))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 7432 &:= ((1+3!) - 5) - (((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) + 3+1) \\ 7433 &:= (((1 \times (3+5!)) - 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5^3 \times 1) \\ 7434 &:= (((1^3)^5) \times 7) \times ((9-7) \times 531) \\ 7435 &:= (1^{35}) - (((7-9) \times 7) \times 531) \\ 7436 &:= (1+3!) + (((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - (7+5!)) - (3+1)) \\ 7437 &:= (((1+3!) \times (((5!+7) + (9 \times 7)) + 5!)) - 3) \times 1 \\ 7438 &:= (((1 - (3-5!)) \times 7) \times 9) + ((7 \times 5) - 31) \\ 7439 &:= (((1-3+5!) \times 7) \times 9) + (7 - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 7440 &:= (((1+35) - 7) + (9-7)) \times (5! \times (3-1)) \\ 7441 &:= (((13 \times 5) - (7+9))^{7-5}) + ((3!+1)!) \\ 7442 &:= ((1+3) - (((5 \times 7) - 97) \times 5!)) - (3-1) \\ 7443 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) - (((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 7444 &:= (1+3^5) + (((7 - (9-7)) + 5) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 7445 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) - 79)) - (7 \times (5+31)) \\ 7446 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) - 7)) - ((975/3) - 1) \\ 7447 &:= (1+3)! - (((5+7) \times 9) - 7531) \\ 7448 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) \times ((7!/9) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\ 7449 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((7 \times (9-7)) \times 531) \\ 7450 &:= (13 \times 579) - (75 + 3 - 1) \\ 7451 &:= (((1+3) \times 5) + 7) \times ((97-5) \times 3) - 1 \\ 7452 &:= (((1+3) \times 5) + 7) \times ((97-5) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 7453 &:= (((1+3) \times 5) + 7) \times ((97-5) \times 3) + 1 \\ 7454 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + 5!) + (3! - 1) \\ 7455 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5+7) \times 9) \times (75-3! \times 1)) \\ 7456 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5!)) - (((7 \times 9) \times (7-5!)) + (3+1)!) \\ 7457 &:= ((1^3 \times (5! \times (7 \times 9))) - (7+5!)) + (3+1)! \\ 7458 &:= (13 \times 579) - ((75-3!) \times 1) \\ 7459 &:= (13 \times (5! + (7 \times 9))) + (7! + (5!/(3 \times 1))) \\ 7460 &:= 13 - (5 + (79 - 7531)) \\ 7461 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((79+7)^{5-3} \times 1) \\ 7462 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times (7 \times ((9-7) + 531)) \\ 7463 &:= ((1-3) - 57) - (9 - 7531) \\ 7464 &:= (((1-3)^5) - ((7 \times 9) \times ((7-5!) - 3!))) - 1 \\ 7465 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7!) + (97 \times (5^{3-1})) \\ 7466 &:= (1^3 - 57) - (9 - 7531) \\ 7467 &:= ((1 + (3! - 5)) + 7!) + (97 \times (5^{3-1})) \\ 7468 &:= 1 \times (3 - (57 + 9 - 7531)) \\ 7469 &:= ((1 + (3 - 57)) - 9) + 7531 \\ 7470 &:= (((1-3!) \times 5) + (7 \times (97+5!))) \times (3! - 1) \\ 7471 &:= 1 \times (3! - (57 + 9 - 7531)) \\ 7472 &:= 1 + (3! - (57 + 9 - 7531)) \\ 7473 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7) - ((9-7) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 7474 &:= (1+3) + ((5+7!) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3! - 1))) \\ 7475 &:= (((13 \times 5) \times (7+97)) - 5) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 7476 &:= ((13-5) - (7 \times 9)) + 7531 \\ 7477 &:= (1 + (3!/5!)) + (((7 \times 97) \times (5+3!)) + 1) \\ 7478 &:= ((13-57) - 9) + 7531 \\ 7479 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! \times 7) \times 9)) - (75 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 7480 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - (7+9 + ((7 \times 5!)/(3 \times 1))) \\ 7481 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 + ((9-7) \times (5! + (3+1)!))) \\ 7482 &:= ((1-3!) - (5 \times 7)) - (9 - 7531) \\ 7483 &:= ((13 \times 579) - 75) + 31 \\ 7484 &:= (13 \times 579) - ((7+5) + 31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7485 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9 - 7531)) \\7486 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31)) \\7487 &:= (1 \times (35 - 79)) + 7531 \\7488 &:= (1 + (35 - 79)) + 7531 \\7489 &:= ((13 + 5!) + 7!) - (9 - (75 \times 31)) \\7490 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times 5) - (7 + (9 - 7531)) \\7491 &:= (135 + 7!) - (9 - (75 \times 31)) \\7492 &:= (1^3 + ((5! \times 7) \times 9)) - (75 - (3! \times 1)) \\7493 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5! - 79) - 7531) \\7494 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! - ((5 + 7) - (9 \times (753 + 1))) \\7495 &:= ((1 - (35/7)) \times 9) + 7531 \\7496 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5! \times (7 + 9)) + (7 - 53))) \times 1 \\7497 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5! \times (7 + 9)) + (7 - 53))) + 1 \\7498 &:= (13 \times 579) + ((7 - 5) - 31) \\7499 &:= (1 \times (3!! - 5)) + (7 + ((9 \times 753) \times 1)) \\7500 &:= (1 - (3 - (5! + 7))) \times ((9 + 75) - (3 + 1)!) \\7501 &:= (1^3 \times (5! \times (7 \times 9))) - ((7 \times 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\7502 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7! + 9)) + ((7! - 5!)/(3 - 1)) \\7503 &:= (13 \times 579) - ((75/3) - 1) \\7504 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5!) + (7 + (9 \times (753 \times 1))) \\7505 &:= (((1 + 3)!)! - 57) - (97 \times (5 - 31)) \\7506 &:= ((13 \times 579) - 7) - ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\7507 &:= ((13 + 5!) + 7!) + (9 + (75 \times 31)) \\7508 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times 5) - ((7 - 9) - 7531) \\7509 &:= ((1 + 3) - 57) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5!)) + 3 - 1) \\7510 &:= (1 \times 3) - (57 - (((9 \times 7) \times 5!) + 3 + 1)) \\7511 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - (797 - 531) \\7512 &:= ((13 \times 579) - (7 \times (5 - 3))) - 1 \\7513 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - ((797 - 5)/(3 \times 1)) \\7514 &:= ((1 - 3!)/5) - (7 + (9 - 7531)) \\7515 &:= ((1 - 3!)/5) \times (7 + (9 - 7531)) \\7516 &:= (13 - 57) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5) \times (3 + 1)!)) \\7517 &:= (13 \times 5) - (79 - 7531) \\7518 &:= (1 - (35/7)) - (9 - 7531) \\7519 &:= ((13 \times 579) + 7) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\7520 &:= (13 - ((5 + 7) - 9)) \times (753 - 1) \\7521 &:= ((13 \times 579) - 7) + (5 - (3 + 1)) \\7522 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 \times 7)) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5!) - 3!) - 1 \\7523 &:= (1^{357}) - (9 - 7531)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7524 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times (97 - 53)) \times 1) \\7525 &:= 1 - ((3! \times 57) \times (9 - ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1)))) \\7526 &:= (135 + 7) \times (9 + (75 - 31)) \\7527 &:= (1 \times ((35/7) - 9)) + 7531 \\7528 &:= (1 + (((3! \times 5) \times 79) + (7! + 5!))) - (3 \times 1) \\7529 &:= (1^3 + ((5! \times 7) \times 9)) - ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\7530 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) - (7 \times ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1)!)) \\7531 &:= 1^{3579} \times 7531 \\7532 &:= 1^{3579} + 7531 \\7533 &:= (13 + (5 - 7)) - (9 - 7531) \\7534 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7! + 5!) + 3 + 1) \\7535 &:= (13 \times 579) + ((7 + 5) - (3 + 1)) \\7536 &:= ((1 - (35/7)) + 9) + 7531 \\7537 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)^5 - (7 + ((9 - 7) \times ((5! - 3) - 1))) \\7538 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! - ((5 - (7 \times 975)) + 3 - 1) \\7539 &:= 1 - (((3! - ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - 7)) + 5) + 3 + 1) \\7540 &:= ((13 - 5) - 7) \times (9 + 7531) \\7541 &:= ((13 - 5) - 7) + (9 + 7531) \\7542 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5!) + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3 - 1 \\7543 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5!) + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3 - 1 \\7544 &:= ((1^3)^5) \times ((7 \times 975) + (3!! - 1)) \\7545 &:= (1 \times ((35/7) + 9)) + 7531 \\7546 &:= (13 \times (579 + (7 - 5))) - (3! + 1) \\7547 &:= (13 - 57) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5!)) + 31) \\7548 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 + (7 \times 975)) + 3!) \times 1) \\7549 &:= ((13 \times 579) + 7) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\7550 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 57)/9) + 7531) \\7551 &:= ((13 + (5 - 7)) + 9) + 7531 \\7552 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - (5 - 7)) \times (975 - 31) \\7553 &:= (((13 + 57) \times 9) \times (7 + 5)) - (3! + 1) \\7554 &:= ((1^3!) \times (5! \times (7 \times 9))) - (((7 + 5)/(3 + 1)))! \\7555 &:= ((1^3!) + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) - (((7 + 5)/(3 + 1)))! \\7556 &:= (13 \times 579) - ((7 - 5) - 31) \\7557 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5!)) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times 531) \\7558 &:= ((1^3!) + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) - ((7 + 5)/(3 + 1)) \\7559 &:= (13 \times 579) + (7 + (5^{3-1})) \\7560 &:= (1 \times (3 + 57)) \times ((97 + 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\7561 &:= 1 + ((3 + 57) \times ((97 + 5) + (3 + 1)!)) \\7562 &:= (((13 + 57) \times 9) \times (7 + 5)) + 3 - 1\end{aligned}$$

- 7563** := (((13 + 57) × 9) × (7 + 5)) + 3) × 1
7564 := ((1^{3!}) + (5! × (7 × 9))) + ((7 + 5)/(3 + 1))
7565 := (1 + ((3!⁵) + 7)) - (9 + ((7 × 5) × 3! × 1))
7566 := ((1^{3!}) × (5! × (7 × 9))) + (((7 + 5)/(3 + 1)))!
7567 := ((1^{3!}) + (5! × (7 × 9))) + (((7 + 5)/(3 + 1)))!
7568 := ((1 - (3 × 5!)) + 7) + (((9 + 7) - 5) × 3!) × 1
7569 := ((1 - (3 × 5!)) + 7) + (((9 + 7) - 5) × 3!) + 1
7570 := (13 × 579) + ((7 + 5) + 31)
7571 := (((1 × 3!)! + 5) + (7 × (975 + 3 × 1)))
7572 := (((1 × 3!)⁵) - (7⁹⁻⁷)) - (5 × 31)
7573 := ((1³ + 5!) - 79) + 7531
7574 := (((1 × 3!) + (5! × (7 × 9))) + (7 + 5)) - (3 + 1)
7575 := 1 × 3 + ((5! - 79) + 7531)
7576 := ((1 - 35) + 79) + 7531
7577 := 1 - (3 - (57 - (9 - 7531)))
7578 := 1 × 3! + ((5! - 79) + 7531)
7579 := (1 × 3!) + (((5! × (7 × 9)) - 7) + (5 × (3 + 1)))
7580 := (((1 - 3 + 5)! × (7!/(9 + 7))) + 5) × (3 + 1)
7581 := (1³) × (57 × ((97 + 5) + 31))
7582 := (1³) + (57 × ((97 + 5) + 31))
7583 := 1 + (3 + (57 - (9 - 7531)))
7584 := (1 - ((3⁵) - ((79 × 7) + 5))) × (3 + 1)!
7585 := ((1 × (3 - 5)) + (7 × (97 + 5!))) × (3! - 1)
7586 := (1 + 3!) + ((57 - 9) + 7531)
7587 := ((1 + (3 × 5!)) × (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5 - (3! + 1))
7588 := (1 × (3!⁵)) - (7 + ((9 × 7) + ((5! - 3) + 1)))
7589 := (((1 × 3!)! × 5) + ((797 × 5) + 3 + 1))
7590 := ((1357 - 97) + 5) × 3! × 1
7591 := (13 × ((5 + 79) × 7)) - (53 × 1)
7592 := (13 × ((5 + 79) × 7)) - (53 - 1)
7593 := (1 × (3 - 5)) + ((7 × (97 + 5!)) × (3! - 1))
7594 := (1 × 3!) + (((5 × 7) × (97 + 5!)) - (3! + 1))
7595 := ((1 × 35) - (7 - (97 + 5!))) × 31
7596 := 1 × ((3! - 5) + ((7⁹⁻⁷) × (5 × 31)))
7597 := 1 + ((3! - 5) + ((7⁹⁻⁷) × (5 × 31)))
7598 := (1³ + (57 + 9)) + 7531
7599 := ((13 × 579) + 75) - (3 × 1)
7600 := ((13 × 579) + 75) - (3 - 1)
7601 := (1 + 3) + ((57 + 9) + 7531)
7602 := (1 + 3!) × (((5 - (7 - (9 × 7))) + 5!) × 3!) × 1
7603 := ((1 × 3) × (5 + 7)) + (((9 × 7) × 5!) + (3! + 1))
7604 := (13 × 579) + (75 + 3 - 1)
7605 := 13 × ((57 × 9) + ((75 - 3) × 1))
7606 := (((1 + 3)! - 5) × ((7!/(9 × 7)) × 5)) + (3! × 1)
7607 := (13 × (5! + 79)) + (7! - (5 × (3 + 1)))
7608 := (1 - 3 + 57) + (((9 × 7) × 5!) - (3! + 1))
7609 := (1 + 3) - (((5 - 7) - (9 × 7)) × ((5! - 3) × 1))
7610 := (1 × ((3!⁵) + 7)) + (9 + (7 × (5 - 31)))
7611 := (1 + ((3 + 5) × (7 + 9))) × ((7 × 5) + (3 + 1)!)
7612 := (((1 × 3!)⁵) - (7 + (9 - 7))) - (5 × 31)
7613 := (1 - (3 - 5)) + (79 + 7531)
7614 := ((1 × 3!) + (5! × (7 × 9))) + ((7 + 5) × (3 + 1))
7615 := ((1 - (3⁵)) - (7 × 9)) + (7! + (5! × (3 + 1)!))
7616 := ((1 - (3 - 5)))! + (79 + 7531)
7617 := (((1 - 3) × 5!) - (7 × 9) + 7!) + (5! × (3 + 1)!)
7618 := 13 × (57 - ((9 - 7) - 531))
7619 := (1³ × (5! × (7 × 9))) + ((7 × 5) + (3 + 1)!)
7620 := 1 - (3! - ((5 - (7 - (9 × 7))) × (5! + (3! - 1))))
7621 := (1³ + (5! × (7 × 9))) + (7 + (53 × 1))
7622 := ((1 × 3!)⁵) - (7 × ((9 - 7) × (5 + 3! × 1)))
7623 := ((1 × 3) - (5 - 79)) × (75 + (3 + 1)!)
7624 := ((1 + 3!) + (5! × 7)) + (9 × (753 × 1))
7625 := ((1 + 3) + 57) + ((9 × (7 × 5!)) + 3 + 1)
7626 := ((1 × (3 + 57)) + (9 - 7)) × (5! + 3 × 1)
7627 := ((1 + ((3 + 5!) × (7 × 9))) - 7) - (5! - (3 + 1))
7628 := (13 + 5) + (79 + 7531)
7629 := ((1 + (3 × 5!)) × 7) + ((9 + 7!) + (53 × 1))
7630 := ((1 - 35) + 797) × ((5 + 3!) - 1)
7631 := 13 × (579 - (7 - (5 × (3 × 1))))
7632 := (13 × 579) + (7 × (5 × (3 × 1)))
7633 := (1 - 3!) + (((5 × 79) + 7) × ((5!/3!) - 1))
7634 := 1 × (((3!⁵) + ((7 - 97) - 53)) + 1)
7635 := 1 + (((3!⁵) + ((7 - 97) - 53)) + 1)
7636 := ((1 × 3!)⁵) - ((7 × ((9 + 7) + 5)) - (3! + 1))
7637 := (((1 × 3!)⁵) - (7 × (9 - 7))) - (5! + (3! - 1))
7638 := ((1 × 3!)⁵) - ((79 + 7) + (53 - 1))
7639 := (1³ × ((5 + 7) × 9)) + 7531
7640 := ((1 × (3!⁵)) - (7 × (9 + 7))) - (5!/(3! - 1))

$$\begin{aligned} 7641 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) + (5!/(3! - 1))) \\ 7642 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times ((5!/3!) - 1)) \\ 7643 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 + 7) \times 9) + 7531) \\ 7644 &:= 1 \times (3! + (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times ((5!/3!) - 1))) \\ 7645 &:= 1 + (3! + (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times ((5!/3!) - 1))) \\ 7646 &:= (1 + (35 + 79)) + 7531 \\ 7647 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 + 7) \times (9 + ((75 - 3!!) - 1))) \\ 7648 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5 + 79) + (7!/5))) + (3 + 1) \\ 7649 &:= ((1 + ((3!^5) + (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - 5!) - ((3! - 1))! \\ 7650 &:= (1 - 35) \times (((7 - 97) \times 5)/(3 - 1)) \\ 7651 &:= 1 - ((3 + 5) - (7 \times (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))))) \\ 7652 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + ((7 - 9)^7))) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 7653 &:= (((1 \times (3!^5)) - 7) - (97 - 5)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 7654 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - 79) - (7 + (5 + 31)) \\ 7655 &:= (13 \times 579) + ((7 - 5)^{3+1}) \\ 7656 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7 - (((9 + 7) - (5 \times 3)) + 1)))! \\ 7657 &:= (1 + 3!!) - (5! - (7! + ((9 + 7) \times (5! + (3! \times 1)))))) \\ 7658 &:= ((1 \times 3!^5) + ((7 + (9 - 75)) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 7659 &:= (1 + ((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times 9)) + (75 - 31) \\ 7660 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5!)) - 7) + (9 + 7531) \\ 7661 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 + (97 + 5))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 7662 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 + (97 + 5))) - (3! - 1) \\ 7663 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - ((5! - 7) - ((9 + 75)^{3-1})) \\ 7664 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7 \times (9 - 7))) - ((5! + 3!) \times 1) \\ 7665 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5! + 7) \times (9 - 75))) - (3!! \times 1) \\ 7666 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 7!) + (97 \times (5 + 3!))) - 1 \\ 7667 &:= (1 + 3) + (5 + (7 \times (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))))) \\ 7668 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 \times 97)) - 5!) \times (3 + 1) \\ 7669 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! + (7 \times 975))) + (3!! + 1) \\ 7670 &:= 13 \times (579 + (((7 - 5) \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 7671 &:= 1 + ((3!! \times (5 + 7)) - (97 \times (5 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 7672 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 + (97 + 5))) + (3! - 1) \\ 7673 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 + (97 + 5))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 7674 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7 \times (9 - 7))) - (5! - (3 + 1)) \\ 7675 &:= ((1^{3!}) - (5 - 7!)) + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 7676 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) + 7) - 97 - (5 + (3! - 1)) \\ 7677 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((579 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3!!) \times 1)) \\ 7678 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times (5 + (3! \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7679 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 - ((9 - 7) \times (53 - 1))) \\ 7680 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5)! \times (((7!/(9 + 7)) + 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 7681 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - 5) + ((7^{9-7}) \times (53 + 1))) \\ 7682 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - (7 - 9)) + 7! - (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 7683 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 \times (7!/9)) + 7!)) - (5 \times 31) \\ 7684 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - ((79 + 7) + (5 + 3 - 1)) \\ 7685 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5 \times (7 + 97))) \times 5) - ((3! - 1))! \\ 7686 &:= (135 + 7!) + ((9^{7-5}) \times 31) \\ 7687 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 - (97 - 5))) - (3 + 1) \\ 7688 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5!/(3! - 1)) \\ 7689 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 - (9 \times 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) + 1)) \\ 7690 &:= (13 + (((5! + 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 7691 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) - ((9 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 7692 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + (7 - (9 \times 7))) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\ 7693 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 7) \times 9) - (7 \times 5) \times (3! + 1) \\ 7694 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (79 - (7 + 5 \times 31)) \\ 7695 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 57)) \times (9 \times ((7 \times 5)/(3! + 1))) \\ 7696 &:= (13 \times ((5 + 79) \times 7)) + (53 - 1) \\ 7697 &:= (13 \times ((5 + 79) \times 7)) + (53 \times 1) \\ 7698 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) + 7)) - ((97 - 5) - (3! + 1)) \\ 7699 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 \times 9)) - ((7 + (5 + 3)) - 1) \\ 7700 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7 - 9)) \times ((7 - 5!) + 3 \times 1) \\ 7701 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) + ((9 - 7) + 531) \\ 7702 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5! - (7 + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) - 1)))) \\ 7703 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (5! \times 7)) \times 9) - ((7 - (5! + 3)) \times 1) \\ 7704 &:= (1 + 3)! + (5 \times ((7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 7705 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) + (9 - ((75 - 3) + 1)) \\ 7706 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) + (9 - (75 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 7707 &:= 13 + (((57 \times 9) \times (7 + (5 + 3))) - 1) \\ 7708 &:= 13 + (((57 \times 9) \times (7 + (5 + 3))) \times 1) \\ 7709 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) + ((7 - (9 \times 7)) - (5 + 3!)))) \times 1 \\ 7710 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5 - 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! + (3! \times 1))) \\ 7711 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 57) + 9)) + 7531 \\ 7712 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 57) + 9)) + 7531 \\ 7713 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5!)) \times 7) - 9) + (7! + 5 \times 31) \\ 7714 &:= (1^3 + 57) \times ((97 + 5) + 31) \\ 7715 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) + ((9 + 7) + 531) \\ 7716 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 579) + 7!) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7717 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) - ((7 + (9 \times 7)) - 5)) + 3! \times 1 \\
 7718 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) - ((7 + (9 \times 7)) - 5)) + 3! + 1 \\
 7719 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7 - 9) + ((7 + 53) - 1)) \\
 7720 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5!)) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 \times 31) \\
 7721 &:= (135 \times 7) + ((9 \times 753) - 1) \\
 7722 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 - 79)) \times (75 + (3 + 1)!) \\
 7723 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7 \times (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\
 7724 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - 7) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5! - 3)) \times 1) \\
 7725 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7)^9)) \times ((7 + (5 + 3)) \times 1) \\
 7726 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + 7)) + (97 - (5 \times 31)) \\
 7727 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5! \times (7 + 9))) - ((7 - 53) - 1) \\
 7728 &:= (1^3) \times ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7!/5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\
 7729 &:= (1^3) + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7!/5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\
 7730 &:= 135 + (((7^{9-7}) \times 5) \times 31) \\
 7731 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7!/5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\
 7732 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) + 7) + (9 - 7)) - (53 \times 1) \\
 7733 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) - (7 - (9 + 7))) - (53 - 1)) \\
 7734 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) - (7 - (9 + 7))) - (53 - 1)) \\
 7735 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\
 7736 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) - 7) - (9 \times 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\
 7737 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 - (9 + 7))) - (5 \times (3! \times 1)) \\
 7738 &:= (1^3 - (5 + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\
 7739 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 - 97)) + (53 \times 1) \\
 7740 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - 79) + (7 + (5 + 31)) \\
 7741 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) / (3 - 1)) \\
 7742 &:= ((1 + 3)! - (5 - 79)) \times ((75 + 3) + 1) \\
 7743 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 - 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\
 7744 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5) \times (7 + ((97 - 5!) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\
 7745 &:= (135 + 79) + 7531 \\
 7746 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) - ((9 \times 7) + (5 - 31)) \\
 7747 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) - (7 + (9 + 7)))) - ((5 + 3) - 1) \\
 7748 &:= (1 \times (((3!^5) - 79) + 75)) - (3 + 1)! \\
 7749 &:= (1 + (3!! + (((57 \times 9) - 7) - 5!))) \times (3! + 1) \\
 7750 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 + ((9 - 75) / (3 - 1))) \\
 7751 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 - 97) + 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\
 7752 &:= (((13 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)! \\
 7753 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) - (7 + (((97 + 5) / 3!) \times 1))) \\
 7754 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7755 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) - (5 + 31)) \\
 7756 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 + 97) - (5! + (3! - 1))) \\
 7757 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (((7 - 9) + 7) - (5^{3-1})) \\
 7758 &:= (1 + (3!! - (5! + 7))) + (9 \times (75 + (3!! + 1))) \\
 7759 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! + 975) + 3!! \times 1) \\
 7760 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 \times (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5 + 3!))) \times 1) \\
 7761 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) - (7 + (9 + 7)))) + ((5 + 3) - 1) \\
 7762 &:= ((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + 5) + ((3! + 1)!) \\
 7763 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 + (((9 - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\
 7764 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) + (5 + 7!)) + (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) - 1) \\
 7765 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 + 7))) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\
 7766 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) + 9 + ((7 + 5) - (3 + 1)!) \\
 7767 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 7)) - (9 - 7531) \\
 7768 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) - 79) + 75) - (3 + 1) \\
 7769 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) - 79) + 75) - (3 + 1) \\
 7770 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - (((7 + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\
 7771 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7 \times (9 - 7)) - (5! / 3!)) + 1) \\
 7772 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 + 9)) \times (7 - 5) - (3 + 1) \\
 7773 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7 - 9)^7) + ((5^3) \times 1)) \\
 7774 &:= ((1 + ((3!^5) + (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + 5) - ((3! - 1)!) \\
 7775 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 - (((9 - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\
 7776 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) \times (7 - (((9 - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\
 7777 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 - (((9 - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\
 7778 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7 - 9)^{7-5}) - (3 - 1)) \\
 7779 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 - 5))) + 3 \times 1) \\
 7780 &:= 1 + (((3^5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 - 5))) + 3 \times 1) \\
 7781 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + 75) \times 31 \\
 7782 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) - (((9 + 7) - (5 \times 3)) - 1)!) \\
 7783 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) + (((9 + 7) - (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\
 7784 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) + (((9 + 7) - (5 \times 3)) - 1)!) \\
 7785 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)!)! + (7! + (9 \times ((75 \times 3) \times 1)))) \\
 7786 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) - ((9 - 7) - ((5! / 3!) - 1)) \\
 7787 &:= ((1 - (3! + 5!)) + (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times (5! - (3!! - 1)) \\
 7788 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7 - 9)^{7-5})! / (3 - 1)) \\
 7789 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 + (((9 - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\
 7790 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) + (9 - 7) + ((5! / 3!) - 1) \\
 7791 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 5) - (79 \times (7 \times 5))) - ((3! + 1)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 7792** := $(1 - 3) \times (5! - ((797 \times 5) + 31))$
7793 := $(1 + (3!! \times 5)) + (7! - ((9 + 7) \times (53 \times 1)))$
7794 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 579) \times (7 + (5 - 3! \times 1))$
7795 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 + 9)) + 7531$
7796 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - ((7 - 97)/5)) + (3 - 1)$
7797 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - (((7 - 9) + 7) - (5^{3-1}))$
7798 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 + 97) - (5! + (3! - 1)))$
7799 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7) + (9 + (7 + 5)) - (3! - 1)$
7800 := $(1 + (3! + (5! - 7))) \times (((9 + 7) - 5) \times 3!) - 1$
7801 := $1 + ((3!^5) + (7 + ((97 + 5)/3!) \times 1))$
7802 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 + ((9 - 75)/(3 - 1)))$
7803 := $1 \times (((3 + 57) - 9)^{7-5} \times (3 \times 1))$
7804 := $1 + (((3 + 57) - 9)^{7-5} \times (3 \times 1))$
7805 := $(13 \times (5 \times ((7 + 97) + 5))) + ((3! \times 1)!)$
7806 := $(1 \times 3) - (((5 - (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1))$
7807 := $(1 + (3 - ((5 - (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times 5!))) + (3 \times 1)$
7808 := $((1 + 3) - ((5 - (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1)$
7809 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 - (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1))$
7810 := $(1 - 3) + ((5 + 7 + 9) \times ((7 + 5) \times 31))$
7811 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + ((7 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5))/(3 - 1))$
7812 := $((1 \times 35) + 7) \times ((97 + 5!) - 31)$
7813 := $((1 \times 35) \times 79) + (7! + ((5 + 3) \times 1))$
7814 := $(1 + (35 \times 79)) + (7! + ((5 + 3) \times 1))$
7815 := $1 + (((35 \times 79) + 7!) + (5 + 3 + 1))$
7816 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) - ((9 - 75)/(3 - 1))$
7817 := $1 + (((3!^5) + 7) - ((9 - 75)/(3 - 1)))$
7818 := $1 + (((3!^5) + 7) + (9 \times 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
7819 := $(1 \times (3!! + (((5 \times 79) + 7) - 5))) \times (3! + 1)$
7820 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) + ((9 \times 7) + (5 - 31))$
7821 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) - (((7 - 9) - 7) - (5 + 31))$
7822 := $(1 \times ((3!^5) - 7)) - (9 - ((7 - 5) \times 31))$
7823 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) - 7) - (97 - (5! + 31))$
7824 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + (((7 - 9)^{7-5})! \times (3 - 1))$
7825 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 - ((9 - 7)^5))) + (3 + 1)!$
7826 := $(1 + (3!! + (((5 \times 79) + 7) - 5))) \times (3! + 1)$
7827 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + (7! - (9 \times 7)) - (5!/(3 + 1))$
7828 := $((1 + 3) - ((5 - (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1)!$
7829 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5!/3) - 1$
7830 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5!/3) \times 1$
7831 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5!/3) + 1$
7832 := $(1 - 3!!) + (((5! \times (79 - 7)) - 5!) + 31)$
7833 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7 - 9) + ((7 + 53) - 1))$
7834 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - (7 + ((9 - 75) + 3 - 1))$
7835 := $((1 \times 35) \times 79) + (7! + (5!/(3 + 1)))$
7836 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5 + 7) \times ((9 + (75 \times 3)) - 1))$
7837 := $(13 - 5!) + (7975 - 31)$
7838 := $(1 + (3! - 5!)) + (7975 - (3 + 1)!)!$
7839 := $13 \times (579 + ((75/3) - 1))$
7840 := $(1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 + (7 + (5 \times 3))) + 1)$
7841 := $((1 \times 35) \times 79) + 7! + (5 + 31)$
7842 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7)) - (97 - (5 \times 31))$
7843 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) - (79 - (7! + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)))$
7844 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + (7 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5))) - (3 - 1)$
7845 := $1 \times (((3!^5) - 79) - (7 - (5 \times 31)))$
7846 := $1 + (((3!^5) - 79) - (7 - (5 \times 31)))$
7847 := $1 \times (((3!^5) + 7) - (9 - 75)) - (3 - 1)$
7848 := $(1 + (((3!^5) + 7) - (9 - 75))) - (3 - 1)$
7849 := $(1 - (3 + 5!)) + (7975 - (3 + 1))$
7850 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (((7! - (9 \times 7)) - (5 + 3)) + 1)$
7851 := $1 \times (((3!^5) + 7) - ((9 - 75) - (3 - 1)))$
7852 := $(1 + (((3!^5) + 7) - (9 - 75))) + (3 - 1)$
7853 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 - (9 \times 7))) + ((5!/3!) + 1)$
7854 := $1 \times ((35 + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5! + 3 + 1)))$
7855 := $(1 - 3) - (5! - (7975 + 3 - 1))$
7856 := $1 \times (3! - (5 - (7975 - ((3! - 1)!)))$
7857 := $((1 \times 35) \times 79) + (7! + (53 - 1))$
7858 := $(1 \times (3!! + (((5! - 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5))) + (3 + 1)!$
7859 := $(13 + ((5! + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) - (5 \times 31)$
7860 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - (79 - (7 + 5 \times 31))$
7861 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 - ((9 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
7862 := $(1^3 \times 5!) + ((79 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
7863 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) + 1))$
7864 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5!/(3! - 1))$
7865 := $((13 - (5 \times 7))/(9 - 7)) \times (5 - 3!! \times 1)$
7866 := $1 \times (3! \times (57 \times (9 + ((7 - 5) \times (3! + 1))))$
7867 := $1 + (3! \times (57 \times (9 + ((7 - 5) \times (3! + 1))))$

$$\begin{aligned}7868 &:= (1 \times ((3!)^5 + 7)) + ((97 - 5) - (3! + 1)) \\7869 &:= (13 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + 7531 \\7870 &:= 1 + (((3!)^5 + (79 + 7)) + (5 + 3 - 1)) \\7871 &:= ((1 \times (3!)^5) + 7) + ((97 - 5) - (3 + 1)) \\7872 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (((5 + (7 + 975))/3) - 1) \\7873 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 - ((9 - 7) \times (53 - 1))) \\7874 &:= 1 \times (((((35 - 7) \times 9) + 7) - 5) \times 31) \\7875 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) \times 7) \times ((9 \times 75)/(3 \times 1)) \\7876 &:= (((1^3)^5)^7) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \\7877 &:= (1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + (5! + ((3! + 1)!)) \\7878 &:= 13 \times ((5 + (7 \times 9)) + (7 + 531)) \\7879 &:= (1 \times 357) - (9 - 7531) \\7880 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 + (975 + 3)) \times 1) \\7881 &:= 1 \times (((3!)^5 + 7) + (((97 - 5) + 3!) \times 1)) \\7882 &:= 13 + ((5! + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 + 5) + 31)) \\7883 &:= (1 \times ((3!)^5 + 7)) + (((97 + 5) - 3) + 1) \\7884 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) + 7) \times (97 + (5! + 3 - 1)) \\7885 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 57)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 3!))) + 1 \\7886 &:= (1 + (3! - 5!)) + (7975 + (3 + 1)!) \\7887 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5! + (3! - 1)) \\7888 &:= (((((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) + (9 - 7)) + ((5! - 3) \times 1)) \\7889 &:= ((1 + ((3!)^5 + (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - 5!) + ((3! - 1)!) \\7890 &:= ((1 + (3!! + 5!)) - 7) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1}) \\7891 &:= 1 \times (((3!)^5 + (7 - (9 + 7))) + ((5^3) - 1)) \\7892 &:= 1 + (((3!)^5 + (7 - (9 + 7))) + ((5^3) - 1)) \\7893 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 + (9 - 7))) + ((5! + 3!) \times 1) \\7894 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 + (9 - 75)) \times (3 - 1)) \\7895 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) + 7)) - (5 \times 31) \\7896 &:= (1 \times (3!)^5) + ((7 - (((9 + 7) - (5 \times 3)) + 1)))! \\7897 &:= (1 + 3!!) + (5! + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times (5! + (3! \times 1)))))) \\7898 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 - 5))) - (3 + 1) \\7899 &:= (13 \times 579) + ((7 + 5) \times 31) \\7900 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) + (7 \times ((9 \times (7 + 5!)) + 3 \times 1)) \\7901 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) + (7! + ((97 - 5) \times 31)) \\7902 &:= (1 \times 35) - (7 - ((9 \times (7 \times (5^3))) - 1)) \\7903 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5 + 7!)) + ((97 - 5) \times 31) \\7904 &:= ((1 + (3!! + 5!)) + 7) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1}) \\7905 &:= ((1 + (((35 - 7) \times 9) + 7)) - 5) \times 31\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7906 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 - 5))) + (3 + 1) \\7907 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\7908 &:= ((1 + (3!)^5) + ((797 - 5)/3!)) - 1 \\7909 &:= ((1 + (3!)^5) + ((797 - 5)/3!)) \times 1 \\7910 &:= (1^3) \times ((5! - 7) \times ((9 + (7 + 53)) + 1)) \\7911 &:= (1^3) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 + (7 + 53)) + 1)) \\7912 &:= ((1 + 357) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) - (3! \times 1) \\7913 &:= (1 + (3!)^5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) + (5!/(3! - 1))) \\7914 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((79 + 7) + (53 - 1)) \\7915 &:= (((((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5! + 3!)) - 1) \\7916 &:= ((1 \times 3! + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 - 5) - (3 + 1)!) \\7917 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) - (3! \times 1)) \\7918 &:= 1 + (((3!)^5) - (7 \times (9 - 7))) + 5 \times 31 \\7919 &:= (1 + (3!)^5) - (((7 - 97) - 53) + 1) \\7920 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (((5 + (7 + 975))/3) + 1) \\7921 &:= 1 + ((3!! + ((5 - (7 - (9 \times 7))) \times 5!)) - ((3! - 1)!) \\7922 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 + (9 - 7))) + (5 \times 31) \\7923 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((((5 - 7) \times 9) + 7) \times (5! \times 3! \times 1)) \\7924 &:= ((1 + 357) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + (3! \times 1) \\7925 &:= ((1 + 357) + (9 \times (7 \times 5!))) + (3! + 1) \\7926 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5 - 797)) \times 5) + 3! \times 1 \\7927 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) + 7!) + (5! + 3 - 1) \\7928 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5) + (7 - ((9 - 75) \times ((3! - 1)!) \\7929 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5))) + (3! \times 1) \\7930 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - 7975)) - 31 \\7931 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7!) + (975 \times (3 \times 1)) \\7932 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5! - (7 - 9))) + (7! - (5 + 31)) \\7933 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5! + 7!) - (9 - (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\7934 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5! + (3 + 1)!) \\7935 &:= (1 \times 3 + 57) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\7936 &:= (1 - (35 - 7975)) - (3! - 1) \\7937 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 - 9)^{(7-5)^3})) + 1 \\7938 &:= ((13 - (5 + 7)) \times 9) \times (7 \times ((5^3) + 1)) \\7939 &:= (1 - ((3^5) - 7)) + ((9 + 7!) + (5^{3!-1})) \\7940 &:= ((1 \times 3! + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7 - 5) - (3 + 1)) \\7941 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7 + 9) \times (7 \times (53 + 1))) \\7942 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5! + (7 + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) - 1)))) \\7943 &:= (1 + 3) - (5 - (7975 - 31))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7944 &:= ((1 + (3!! - 57)) - (9 - 7)) \times (5 + (3! + 1)) \\7945 &:= ((1 - 3^5) + (7975 + 3 - 1)) \\7946 &:= (1 - (35 - 7975)) + (3! - 1) \\7947 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) - (7975 - 31)) \\7948 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + 7!) - (9 - (7 + (5! / (3 + 1)))) \\7949 &:= (((1^{3!} + 5))! \times 7) + (((97 \times 5) \times 3!) - 1) \\7950 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5 - 797))) \times (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\7951 &:= (((1 + (3!^5)) - 7) + (9 \times 7)) + ((5! - 3) + 1) \\7952 &:= (135 + 7) \times (97 - ((5! / 3) + 1)) \\7953 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + (7! - (9 \times 7))) + 5! - (3 + 1)! \\7954 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) + 7) + 9) + (7 + 5 \times 31) \\7955 &:= (1^3 + (5 + 7!)) + (((97 \times 5) \times 3!) - 1) \\7956 &:= 13 \times ((579 + (7 - 5)) + 31) \\7957 &:= ((1 + 3!))! + (5 - (7 \times ((9 + (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)))) \\7958 &:= (((1^3 \times 5!) - 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5! + (3!! - 1) \\7959 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5) + 7975) - 31) \\7960 &:= (1 + (3 - (5 - 797))) \times (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\7961 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) + 7975) - (3! + 1) \\7962 &:= 13 + (5 + (7975 - 31)) \\7963 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times (57 \times 9)) + 7!) - (5 \times 31) \\7964 &:= (1^3 - (5 - 7975)) - (3! + 1) \\7965 &:= 1 \times (((3! - 5) + (7 \times (9 - 7))) \times 531) \\7966 &:= 1 + (((3! - 5) + (7 \times (9 - 7))) \times 531) \\7967 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) \times (7 - ((9 + 7)^{5-3})) - 1) \\7968 &:= ((1^3)^5!) \times (7975 - (3! + 1)) \\7969 &:= ((1^3)^5!) + (7975 - (3! + 1)) \\7970 &:= 1 - ((3! + 5) - (7975 + (3! - 1))) \\7971 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) + (7975 - (3 - 1)) \\7972 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5 - 7975)) - (3! - 1) \\7973 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((5 - 7975) + 3 \times 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7974 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 7975)) - (3 - 1) \\7975 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) + (7975 + 3 - 1) \\7976 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + 7975)) - (3 + 1) \\7977 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) + (7975 - 3!)) - 1 \\7978 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 7975)) + (3 - 1) \\7979 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7975) - (3 + 1)) \\7980 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7975 + 3!)) - 1 \\7981 &:= 1 - ((3 - (5 + 7975)) - (3 \times 1)) \\7982 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7975 + 3!)) + 1 \\7983 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 7975)) + (3! + 1) \\7984 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + 7975)) + (3 + 1) \\7985 &:= ((1 + ((3!^5) + 7)) - 9) + ((7 \times 5) \times 3! \times 1) \\7986 &:= (13 - 5) + (7975 + 3 \times 1) \\7987 &:= 1 + (3! \times ((579 + 753) - 1)) \\7988 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7975 - (3 - 1)) \\7989 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) + 7975) + (3! - 1) \\7990 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + 7) \times ((9 - 7) - (5 + 31)) \\7991 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5)) + (7975 + (3! - 1)) \\7992 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 5) - 7975) - 31) \\7993 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 \times (7! / 9)) + 7!)) + (5 \times 31) \\7994 &:= (((1 \times 3) - ((5 \times 7) - 97)) \times (5! + 3)) - 1 \\7995 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((5 + 7) - ((9 \times 7) \times ((5! + 3!) + 1))) \\7996 &:= (((1 \times 3) - ((5 \times 7) - 97)) \times (5! + 3)) + 1 \\7997 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (79 - ((7 - 5) - ((3! + 1)!))) \\7998 &:= 13 + ((5 + 7975) + (3! - 1)) \\7999 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times ((5! + 3) \times 1)) \\8000 &:= (((1 \times 3!))! + 5) \times 7 + (975 \times (3 \times 1))\end{aligned}$$

2.5 Numbers From 8001 to 10000

$$\begin{aligned}8001 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (5! + 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\8002 &:= (1^3) - (5 - (7975 + 31)) \\8003 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + 7)) + (9 + ((7 \times 5) \times 3! \times 1)) \\8004 &:= (1 - (((3 - 57) - 97) \times 53)) \times 1 \\8005 &:= 1 - (((3 - 57) - 97) \times 53) - 1) \\8006 &:= (1^{35}) \times (7975 + 31)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8007 &:= (1^{35}) + (7975 + 31) \\8008 &:= (1 \times 35) + (7975 - (3 - 1)) \\8009 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7975 - 31) \\8010 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) - 31) \\8011 &:= (1^{35}) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! - 31)) \\8012 &:= (1^3 + 5) + (7975 + 31)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8013 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7 \times (97 + 5))/3)) - 1 \\8014 &:= ((1 + ((3!^5) + (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + 5) + ((3! - 1)!) \\8015 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + 7975) + 31) \\8016 &:= 13 + (((5! + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\8017 &:= 1 \times ((35 + (7975 + 3!)) + 1) \\8018 &:= 1 + ((35 + (7975 + 3!)) + 1) \\8019 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7) \times ((9 \times 75) - (3! + 1))) \\8020 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 + 797) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\8021 &:= (1^3) + ((5 + 797) \times (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\8022 &:= (13 \times 57) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5!) - 31)) \\8023 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((7 + ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3)) - 1 \\8024 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) \times (((7 + ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3) \times 1) \\8025 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((7 + ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3)) + 1 \\8026 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (((5! + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - 5)) + 3! \times 1 \\8027 &:= (135 + 7!) + ((97 - 5) \times 31) \\8028 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) \times 7) + (975 - (3 \times 1)) \\8029 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) \times 7) + (975 - (3 - 1)) \\8030 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5!)) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times 31) \\8031 &:= (((1^3 \times 5!) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times (3! \times 1)) \\8032 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - (7! - (9 + 7)))) + (5^{3! - 1}) \\8033 &:= ((13 \times 5) + 7975) - (3! + 1) \\8034 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 7))) + 9) + (7! + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\8035 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7975 - (3! - 1)) \\8036 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5!) - ((7 \times 9) - 7)) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1) \\8037 &:= (1 + (3 + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - 7))) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\8038 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (79 - (7 \times (5 - 31))) \\8039 &:= (1 - 3) + (((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5!) - (3! - 1) \\8040 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times (7 - ((9 - 7) - 531)) \\8041 &:= (1 \times 35) + (7975 + 31) \\8042 &:= 1 + 35 + (7975 + 31) \\8043 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + 797) - 531 \\8044 &:= 1 \times (3 + (((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5!) - (3! - 1)) \\8045 &:= 1 + (3 + (((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5!) - (3! - 1)) \\8046 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\8047 &:= ((13 \times 5) + 7975) + (3! + 1) \\8048 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + 7) \times (5 \times (3! - 1))) \\8049 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times 3! \times 1) \\8050 &:= (13 + 57) \times (9 + (75 + 31)) \\8051 &:= (13 \times 579) - (7 - 531)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8052 &:= ((1 + 3) + 57) \times (((9 + 7) + 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\8053 &:= (1^3) + ((5! - (7 - 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) + 31)) \\8054 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + 7) \times ((5 + 3) - 1) \\8055 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - (5! + (7 \times 9))) \times (7 + (5 + 3 \times 1))) \\8056 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((5! - 7) + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times 3!))) - 1 \\8057 &:= (13 + (57 \times 9)) + 7531 \\8058 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((5! - 7) + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times 3!))) + 1 \\8059 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + 7)) + (((97 - 5) \times 3) - 1) \\8060 &:= (13 \times 5) \times ((79 - (7 - 53)) - 1) \\8061 &:= 1 - ((35 - 7975) - ((3! - 1)!)) \\8062 &:= (((1 - 35) + 7!) - 975) \times (3 - 1) \\8063 &:= ((13 + 5) \times ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) + ((5! + 3!) - 1) \\8064 &:= (1^3 \times (57 - 9)) \times ((7!/5) / (3! \times 1)) \\8065 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5!) - (3! - 1) \\8066 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5 - (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times (5! + 3 + 1)) \\8067 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) + (((7 - 97)^{5-3}) - 1) \\8068 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (5! - 7)) + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\8069 &:= (1 - (((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) \times (7!/5))) + (3 + 1) \\8070 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 579) + 7!) - (5 - (3! - 1)) \\8071 &:= (13 \times 5) + (7975 + 31) \\8072 &:= (1 + ((3!/5) \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7)^{5-3+1}) \\8073 &:= 13 \times ((5! + (79 \times 7)) - (53 - 1)) \\8074 &:= ((13 - 5!) + 7!) + (9 + (7 + (5^{3! - 1}))) \\8075 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 - 9) + (75 \times (3 + 1))) \\8076 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) + 7)) - (5 - 31) \\8077 &:= 13 + (5! + (7975 - 31)) \\8078 &:= ((1 + (3! - 5)) \times 79) + (7! + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\8079 &:= 135 + (7975 - 31) \\8080 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 7) \times 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\8081 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 + (7! - 9)) + (75 \times 31))) \\8082 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (((5! + 79) \times (7 + (5 \times 3!))) - 1) \\8083 &:= (1 + (3! + (((5 + 7) \times 9) \times 75))) - (3 + 1)! \\8084 &:= (1 + 3^5) + (((7!/9) \times 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\8085 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5) \times ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) \times (3! - 1)) \\8086 &:= 13 \times (579 + ((7 + 5) + 31)) \\8087 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! + 7975)) - 3! \times 1 \\8088 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 5!) + (7975 - 31) \\8089 &:= (1 + 3579) + (7! - 531) \\8090 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5 - 7!)) + (9 + (75 \times 31))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8091 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) \times ((7 \times 9) + ((7 \times 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\8092 &:= ((1^3 + (5! + 7975)) - 3) - 1 \\8093 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7) + ((9 - 7) \times (5 \times 31))) \\8094 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - (5 - (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times (5! - (3! \times 1)) \\8095 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7975)) - (3 + 1) \\8096 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5! + 7975) - 3) \times 1) \\8097 &:= (1^3) + (5 + ((7!/9) + 7531)) \\8098 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) \times 9) + 7531 \\8099 &:= ((1^3 + (5! + 7975)) + 3) \times 1 \\8100 &:= (1 + 35) \times ((7 \times 9) + (7 + 5 \times 31)) \\8101 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + 7975) + 3 \times 1) \\8102 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5! + 7975) + 3 \times 1) \\8103 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7975)) + (3 + 1) \\8104 &:= (13 - 5) \times (7 + (975 + 31)) \\8105 &:= (1 - 3 + ((579 \times 7) \times (5 - 3))) + 1 \\8106 &:= (135 + (7975 - 3)) - 1 \\8107 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 + 7975)) + ((3! - 1))! \\8108 &:= 1 - ((3 - 579) - 7531) \\8109 &:= 1 + (((3! \times (57 \times 9)) + 7!) - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\8110 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((579 \times 7) \times (5 - 3)) + 1) \\8111 &:= (1 + 3) + (((579 \times 7) \times (5 - 3)) + 1) \\8112 &:= 135 + (7975 + 3 - 1) \\8113 &:= (1 \times 3 + 579) + 7531 \\8114 &:= (1 + 3) + (579 + 7531) \\8115 &:= 1 - (((35 - 7!) + (9 + 7)) - (5^{3! - 1})) \\8116 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5! + 7975) - 3) \times 1) \\8117 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5! + 7975) - 3) + 1) \\8118 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times ((5 + 7) - 9))!) \times ((75 \times 3!) + 1) \\8119 &:= 1 + ((3 \times ((5 + 7) - 9))!) \times ((75 \times 3!) + 1) \\8120 &:= (1 - 3!) + (5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)))) \\8121 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7 + 9) \times ((7 + 5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\8122 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5 - ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)))) \\8123 &:= 1 - (((3!! + ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - (7!/5)) \times 31) \\8124 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5 - 7) + (97 - 5))^{3 - 1}) \\8125 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5!) + 7975)) + (3 + 1)! \\8126 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5!) + 7975)) + (3 + 1)! \\8127 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5 - 7) - ((9 - 7) - (5! \times (3 \times 1)))) \\8128 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 - 7))^9) + (7! + (5 \times 3!! \times 1)) \\8129 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((579 \times 7) \times (5 - 3))) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8130 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((579 \times 7) \times (5 - 3))) \times 1 \\8131 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((579 \times 7) \times (5 - 3))) + 1 \\8132 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 - ((9 - 7) + ((5! \times 3) + 1))) \\8133 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5! - 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) \times (3 \times 1) \\8134 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (7 + (9 \times 7))) - ((5^3) + 1) \\8135 &:= ((1 \times (357 \times 9)) + 7!) - (5! - (3 - 1)) \\8136 &:= ((1 \times (357 \times 9)) + 7!) - ((5! - 3) \times 1) \\8137 &:= ((1 \times (357 \times 9)) + 7!) - ((5! - 3) - 1) \\8138 &:= ((1 + (357 \times 9)) + 7!) - (5! - (3 + 1)) \\8139 &:= 13 + (((5! + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5^3 \times 1)) \\8140 &:= (1 - 357) + ((9 + 7) \times 531) \\8141 &:= (135 + 7975) + 31 \\8142 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((7 + 97) - (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\8143 &:= 1357 + (9 \times (753 + 1)) \\8144 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times 79) \times 7 - (5! + 31) \\8145 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) - 7) + ((9 + 7) + (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\8146 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7 - 9) + (7 \times 53)) + 1) \\8147 &:= ((1 \times ((3^5) - (7 + 9))) + 7!) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!) \\8148 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 579) \times 7)) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\8149 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 - (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1))) \\8150 &:= (1 + ((3 + 579) \times 7)) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\8151 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 + ((97 - 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\8152 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 + 5!))) + (3 + 1)! \\8153 &:= ((1 + (3!! \times (5 + 7))) - (97 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\8154 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 79) + ((7 \times (5! \times 3)) - 1)) \\8155 &:= 1 - (((3 - 57) - 97) \times (53 + 1)) \\8156 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 - (97 + 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\8157 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) - (9 + (7 - (5^{3! - 1}))) \\8158 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5!) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) - (5! \times 31)) \\8159 &:= ((1 + (3!! \times (5 + 7))) - (97 \times 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\8160 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\8161 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) + (7! - (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! - 1}) \\8162 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5!) + 7!) + (9 - 7) + (5! \times 31) \\8163 &:= ((1 \times (3!! + (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) + 7) - (5! + 3 + 1) \\8164 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((579 \times 7) + 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\8165 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 5!) - 7) \times 9)) + (7! - (53 \times 1)) \\8166 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 5!) - 7) \times 9)) + (7! - (53 - 1)) \\8167 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) + (((7 + ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3!) + 1)) \\8168 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) + (((7 + ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3!) + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8169 &:= (13 + ((5! + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) + (5 \times 31) \\ 8170 &:= (1 \times (((3! \times 5) + 79) \times 75)) - (3! - 1) \\ 8171 &:= 1 + (((3! \times 5) + 79) \times 75) - (3! - 1) \\ 8172 &:= (1 + (((3! \times 5) + 79) \times 75)) - (3 + 1) \\ 8173 &:= (13 - 5!) + ((79 - 7) \times (5! - (3! - 1))) \\ 8174 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (79 \times 7)) - (5 \times 31) \\ 8175 &:= 13 + ((57 + 97) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 8176 &:= 1 - (3 \times 5 \times (((7 - 9) \times 7) - 531)) \\ 8177 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5 - ((7 - 9)^{7+5}))) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 8178 &:= (1 \times (3! \times (57 \times 9))) + (7! + (5!/(3 - 1))) \\ 8179 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) - (5! - (3 + 1)) \\ 8180 &:= (1 \times (((3! \times 5) + 79) \times 75)) + (3! - 1) \\ 8181 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7!) + 9) + (7 + (5^{3!-1})) \\ 8182 &:= (1 - 3) + (((57 + 9) \times ((7 + 5!) - 3)) \times 1) \\ 8183 &:= (1 - 3) + (((57 + 9) \times ((7 + 5!) - 3)) + 1) \\ 8184 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5) - 7) \times (9 - 75)) \times 31 \\ 8185 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (57 + 9)) + 7531 \\ 8186 &:= (1 + 3!) - (57 + 9 - 7531) \\ 8187 &:= (((1^{3!}) + 5) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!-1})) \\ 8188 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 \times (7!/9)) - (753 \times 1)) \\ 8189 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 8190 &:= (1 + (((3! + 579) \times 7) \times (5 - 3))) - 1 \\ 8191 &:= (1 + (((3! + 579) \times 7) \times (5 - 3))) \times 1 \\ 8192 &:= (135 - 7) \times (((9 - 7)^5) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 8193 &:= ((1 \times (357 \times 9)) + 7!) - (5!/(3 - 1)) \\ 8194 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 - (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times (5! + 3!))) + 1 \\ 8195 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5)) \times 7) - (((9 + 7) \times 5!) - ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 8196 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times (5!/(3 + 1))) \\ 8197 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) + (7 + 9)) + (7! + (5^{3!-1})) \\ 8198 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) - ((75 + 3!) + 1) \\ 8199 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 + 7) + 9) - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 8200 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - 3))) - 1) \\ 8201 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - 3))) \times 1) \\ 8202 &:= 1 + (((3! + 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - 3))) \times 1) \\ 8203 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 \times (97 - (5 + 31))) \\ 8204 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5!)) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 8205 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) + 7)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 8206 &:= ((13 + (5! + 7!)) + 9) + ((7!/5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 8207 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (((7 - 9)^{7+5}) \times (3 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8208 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times ((7 \times (5 - 3!)) - 1) \\ 8209 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + 7!) + (975 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 8210 &:= ((1 + 357) \times 9) + (7! - (53 - 1)) \\ 8211 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) + (7975 - 3!)) - 1 \\ 8212 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) + (7975 - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 8213 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (797 - (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 8214 &:= (((1 - 3)^{5+7}) + ((9 + 7) - 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 8215 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + (7975 - 3)) - 1 \\ 8216 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + (7975 - 3)) \times 1 \\ 8217 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! \times 7) - 97)) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1) \\ 8218 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) + (7! + ((97 + 5) \times 31)) \\ 8219 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + (79 \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) - 1)) \\ 8220 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times 5!) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7!/(5 + 31))) \\ 8221 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) + (7975 + 3 \times 1) \\ 8222 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) + ((7975 + 3) + 1) \\ 8223 &:= (1^3 + (5! + (7! - (9 \times 7)))) + (5^{3!-1}) \\ 8224 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - (7 - ((97 \times 5) - 31)) \\ 8225 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - 7) \times 9 + ((7! + (5 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 8226 &:= ((1 + ((3! \times 5) + 79)) \times 75) - (3 + 1)! \\ 8227 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((79 \times 7) - 5)) + (3! + 1) \\ 8228 &:= 1 \times ((357 \times 9) + (7! - (5^{3!-1}))) \\ 8229 &:= (1 \times (((35 \times 7) - 9) \times 7) \times 5) - 31 \\ 8230 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + 7!) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 8231 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) \times (7 \times ((97 - 5) + 3!))) - 1 \\ 8232 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (79 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 8233 &:= (((1^3 \times 5) + 7!) + (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3!-1}) \\ 8234 &:= ((1 + (357 \times 9)) + 7!) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 8235 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - ((5! - (79 \times (7!/5!))) + 3 \times 1) \\ 8236 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5! \times 7)) - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31) \\ 8237 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) + ((97 \times 5) - 31) \\ 8238 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times (7!/5!))) \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 8239 &:= (((1 - 3!) - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\ 8240 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (5 - (7 + (9 - 7531)))) \\ 8241 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) \times 7) - (53 + 1) \\ 8242 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5 \times ((7 - 9) \times 7))) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\ 8243 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) \times 7) - (53 - 1) \\ 8244 &:= (((1 \times (35 \times 7)) - 9) - 7) \times (5 + 31) \\ 8245 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) \times 9) \times 7 - ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 8246 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (797 - 531) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8247 &:= (1 - 35) + (((79 + 7) + 5)^{3-1}) \\ 8248 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5 \times 79))) + ((7 + 5) \times (3!! \times 1)) \\ 8249 &:= ((1 - 3 + (57 \times 9))/7) \times (5! - (3! + 1)) \\ 8250 &:= (((13 - 5!) + (7 + 9))^{7-5}) - 31 \\ 8251 &:= 1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (((7 - (9 - 7)))! + 5 \times 31)) \\ 8252 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (7 \times 9)) + (7 + 531) \\ 8253 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5!)) - ((7 - 9) - 7531) \\ 8254 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (5 + (7 - (9 - 7531)))) \\ 8255 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (((7 - (9 - 7)))! + ((5 + 3) - 1)) \\ 8256 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + (5 + 3 + 1)) \\ 8257 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (((5! \times (7 \times 9)) + 7) - (5!/(3 + 1)))) \\ 8258 &:= (13 \times (5! + (7 \times 9))) + (((7! + 5!) + 3!!) - 1) \\ 8259 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - ((5 + 3!) + 1)) \\ 8260 &:= ((1 \times (357 \times 9)) + 7!) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 8261 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5! + 7) \times (((9 + 7) - 5) \times 3! - 1)) \\ 8262 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) \times (((7 - 97) + 5!) + 3 + 1) \\ 8263 &:= (13 \times 57) - (9 - 7531) \\ 8264 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) + 7) + (97 \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 8265 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) + 7) + (97 \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 8266 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5 - (79 \times 7))) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1 \\ 8267 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 8268 &:= (1 + (357 \times 9)) + (7! + ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 8269 &:= (1 \times (((3 \times 5!) - 7) \times 9) + 7!) + (53 - 1) \\ 8270 &:= (1 \times (((3 \times 5!) - 7) \times 9) + 7!) + (53 \times 1) \\ 8271 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) \times 7)) - (5^{3-1}) \\ 8272 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) - ((5^3) + 1) \\ 8273 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times (57 \times 9)) + 7!) + (5 \times 31) \\ 8274 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 - 5 + 3 + 1))) \\ 8275 &:= (1 + (3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 8276 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! \times (7 + (9 \times 7))) - (5! + 3 - 1)) \\ 8277 &:= (1^3 + (5! \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) - ((5^3) - 1) \\ 8278 &:= (1 \times (357 \times 9)) + (7! + (5^{3-1})) \\ 8279 &:= ((1 + ((3 \times 5!) - 7)) \times 9) + (7! + (53 \times 1)) \\ 8280 &:= (135 \times (7 \times 9)) - ((75 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 8281 &:= (13 \times 579) + (753 + 1) \\ 8282 &:= (1^{35}) + (((79 + 7) + 5)^{3-1}) \\ 8283 &:= ((1^{3!}) - (((5 - 7) - 9) \times 753)) - 1 \\ 8284 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7 + 9 + 7) - 531) \\ 8285 &:= (1^{3!}) - (((5 - 7) - 9) \times 753) - 1 \\ 8286 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5)) + 3!)) \times 1 \\ 8287 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 - 97) + (5! \times (3! - 1))) \\ 8288 &:= (13 + 579) \times ((7 - 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\ 8289 &:= (1 \times ((35 \times 79) - (7 - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 8290 &:= ((1 \times (3!! + ((5 + 7) + 97))) \times 5) \times (3 - 1) \\ 8291 &:= (1 + 3!) - (((5 - 7) - 9) \times 753) - 1 \\ 8292 &:= (1 + (3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5) - 3!)) - 1 \\ 8293 &:= (1 + (3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5) - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 8294 &:= (1 + (3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5) - 3!)) + 1 \\ 8295 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5))) \times (3! - 1) \\ 8296 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + 5) - (3 + 1) \\ 8297 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\ 8298 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)! + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 8299 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + (79 \times (7 \times (5 \times 3)))) - 1 \\ 8300 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!)) + (3 + 1) \\ 8301 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + (79 \times (7 \times (5 \times 3)))) + 1 \\ 8302 &:= (((1 + (3 \times (5 \times 79))) \times 7) - 5) + (3! - 1) \\ 8303 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 79))) \times 7) + ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 8304 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + 5) + (3 + 1) \\ 8305 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5 - (7 - 9))) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3!)) \times 1 \\ 8306 &:= (((1 - (3!! + (57 - 9))) + 7!) - 5!) \times (3 - 1) \\ 8307 &:= 13 \times (57 + (97 \times (((5 - 3) + 1)!)) \\ 8308 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (((7 \times (9 - 7)) + 5!) \times 31) \\ 8309 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((579 + 7) - 5!)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 8310 &:= ((1 \times ((3! + 5) \times 7)) \times 97) + ((5! + 3!) + 1) \\ 8311 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 8312 &:= (((13 - 5!) + (7 + 9))^{7-5}) + 31 \\ 8313 &:= (1^3 + 5!) + (((7 - 9)^{7+5}) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 8314 &:= ((135 + (7 \times 9)) \times (7!/5!)) - (3 - 1) \\ 8315 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + 7)) - (975/(3 \times 1))) \\ 8316 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) + 31) \\ 8317 &:= (1 + ((3 + (5! + 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 8318 &:= (1 + 3!!) + ((57 + 9) + 7531) \\ 8319 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + (5^3))) \times 1 \\ 8320 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5! \times 7) \times 9) + (753 \times 1)) \\ 8321 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! - 79)) - 7) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 8322 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((57 \times 9) + 7!) - 5)/(3 + 1) \\ 8323 &:= (13 - 5) + (((7 \times 9) \times (7 + (5^3))) - 1) \\ 8324 &:= 13 - ((5 - ((7 \times 9) \times (7 + (5^3)))) \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8325 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + 797) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\8326 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5!)) + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7!/5!) + 3 + 1) \\8327 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (7 + ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1)))) \\8328 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (7975 - (3! + 1)) \\8329 &:= 13 + ((57 + 97) \times (53 + 1)) \\8330 &:= ((1 + 35) + 797) \times (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\8331 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (7 + 9 + (7 + 531)) \\8332 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5) - (3! - 1)) \\8333 &:= 13 + ((5 + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 + (5^3)))) - 1) \\8334 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5!)) + ((7975 - 3) + 1) \\8335 &:= 13 + ((5 + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 + (5^3)))) + 1) \\8336 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1))) \\8337 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1))) \\8338 &:= (1 \times (((3 \times 5!) + 7975) + 3)) \times 1 \\8339 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5!)) + (7975 + 3 \times 1) \\8340 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + 75) \times (3 - 1) \\8341 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + 57) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1) \\8342 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + 7975) + (3! + 1) \\8343 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 - 7) - 97) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\8344 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) + ((7!/9) + (((7 - 5)^3) \times 1)) \\8345 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) + ((79 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1))) \\8346 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) + ((7 - 9) \times 75)) + (3!! - 1)) \\8347 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) \times 7) + (53 - 1) \\8348 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + (((7 - 9) \times 75) + 3!!))) + 1 \\8349 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5 \times 79)) \times 7) + (53 + 1) \\8350 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 - 7)) + (9 \times (7!/5))) - 3!! \times 1 \\8351 &:= (1 + 3) - (5 - ((79 - 7) \times (5! - (3 + 1)))) \\8352 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - ((7 + 9) \times (7 - 531)) \\8353 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (((((7 - 9) + 7)!/5)^{3-1}) \\8354 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7! - 97) + 531) \\8355 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\8356 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + (79 \times 7)) - (5 - 31) \\8357 &:= (135 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7 - (5 \times 31)) \\8358 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)! \times (79 \times 7)) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!)) \\8359 &:= 1 - (3! - ((5 + 7) \times (97 + (5! \times (3! - 1)))))) \\8360 &:= ((13 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 + 5) - 31) \\8361 &:= (1 \times ((3! + ((5! \times 7) \times 9)) + 75)) + ((3! \times 1)! \\8362 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) - ((7 \times (9 - 7)) - (5! \times (3! - 1)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8363 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (((7 - 9)^7) - 5)) + 3!! \times 1 \\8364 &:= (1 - (3 + (5 \times ((7 - 9) \times 7)))) \times (5! + 3 \times 1) \\8365 &:= (1 \times (3!! \times (5 + 7))) - (((97 - 5) \times 3) - 1) \\8366 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 \times 97)) - (5! - 31) \\8367 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) + (79 \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) + 1)) \\8368 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5!) + ((79 + 7!) + (5^{3!-1})) \\8369 &:= ((1 \times (357 \times 9)) + (7! + (5! - 3))) - 1 \\8370 &:= ((1 + (357 \times 9)) + 7!) + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\8371 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + 7) \times (97 + (5! \times (3! - 1)))) \\8372 &:= ((1^3 - 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\8373 &:= (1 - (((3! \times 5) \times 79) - (7! + 5!))) \times (3 \times 1) \\8374 &:= 1 + ((3!! + (579 \times 7)) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\8375 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times 9) + 7) + 5! \times (3! - 1) \\8376 &:= 1 - (((3! \times (5 \times (7 - (9 \times 7)))) + 5) \times (3! - 1)) \\8377 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7^{9-7})) \times (5 \times 31)) \\8378 &:= (1 \times (357 \times 9)) + (7! + (5^3 \times 1)) \\8379 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)))) - (3 + 1)! \\8380 &:= ((1^{35} + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) \times 53) \times 1) \\8381 &:= ((1^{35} + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) \times 53) + 1) \\8382 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + 9) \times (7 - 5 + 31) \\8383 &:= 1 + (((35 \times 7) + 9) \times (7 - 5 + 31)) \\8384 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 - 9) \times (7 - 531)) \\8385 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (((7 \times 9) \times (7 - 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\8386 &:= (((1^{3!} + 5)! - 7) + (97 \times 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\8387 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 - 7!)) + ((9 \times (7 + 5)) \times 31) \\8388 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (579 + (7 \times (5! - (3 \times 1)))) \\8389 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (79 \times (75 + 31)) \\8390 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5! \times ((7 - 9) - (7 + 5))) + 3 - 1) \\8391 &:= (((1 \times 3) - ((5! + 7) \times (9 - 75))) + 3!) \times 1 \\8392 &:= (1 - (3! + (5 - ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)))) + (3 - 1) \\8393 &:= (1 - (3! + (5 - ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)))) + (3 \times 1) \\8394 &:= (1 + (3!! + (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) - (7 - (5 \times (3 + 1)!)) \\8395 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5! \times (((7 - 9) \times 7) \times 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\8396 &:= (1 \times (3!! + (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) - (7 - (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\8397 &:= (1 \times (3!! + (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) - (7 - (5! + 3 + 1)) \\8398 &:= ((13 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7 + 5) - 31) \\8399 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)))) - (3 + 1) \\8400 &:= (1^3) - ((5 - ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)) \\8401 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)))) - (3! + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8402 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 - (3 + 1))) \\8403 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) - (7 \times 97)) - 5! \times (3 \times 1) \\8404 &:= (1 + 3) + (5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!)) - (3! - 1)) \\8405 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1))) \\8406 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5!)) \times (3! \times 1)) \\8407 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!)))) + (3 + 1) \\8408 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!)) - 3)) \times 1 \\8409 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!)) - 3)) + 1 \\8410 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + (3! + 1))) \\8411 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\8412 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + 3 + 1) \\8413 &:= 13 + ((57 - 9) \times (7 \times (5^{3-1}))) \\8414 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!))) + (3! - 1)) \\8415 &:= (1^{35}) \times (7! + ((9 \times 75) \times (3! - 1))) \\8416 &:= (1^{35}) + (7! + ((9 \times 75) \times (3! - 1))) \\8417 &:= ((1 + 3)! - 5) \times (79 + (7 \times (53 - 1))) \\8418 &:= (1 \times 357 + 9) \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\8419 &:= (1 \times 35) - ((7 + 9) \times (7 - 531)) \\8420 &:= ((1^3 - 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1)! \\8421 &:= 13 - (((5! \times 7) - 9) - (7! - 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\8422 &:= (((13 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7 + 5)) + 31 \\8423 &:= 1 + (((3! + 5!) \times 7) + (9 + 7531)) \\8424 &:= (((1 + 35) + 7) + 9) \times (7 + 5 \times 31) \\8425 &:= (13 - 5!) + (7! + (97 \times (5 + 31))) \\8426 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + (5 + (7 \times ((97 \times 5) - 3) + 1))) \\8427 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + (75 \times 31) \\8428 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times 7) + ((97 + 5!) \times 31) \\8429 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + 7)) - (((97 + 5!) - 3!) \times 1) \\8430 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + 7)) - (((97 + 5!) - 3!) - 1) \\8431 &:= 13 - ((5! + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 - 53) \times 1)) \\8432 &:= (1 + (3 + 5!)) \times ((7 + 97) - (5 + 31)) \\8433 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times (7!/9)) + (7 - 5 + 31) \\8434 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 \times ((7 - 9) \times 7)) \times 5!) - 31) \\8435 &:= (1 \times 35) \times (7 + (9 + ((75 \times 3) \times 1))) \\8436 &:= 13 - (((5! - 7!) + 97) - (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\8437 &:= 13 \times (579 + ((7 \times 5) \times (3 - 1))) \\8438 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5!)) + 31) \\8439 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times 579) - 75) + ((3! + 1)! \\8440 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5! \times 7)) / (9 - 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8441 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (((5 \times 79) + (7!/5) \times 3!)) - 1 \\8442 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) - (7 - (9 \times 75))) - (3 - 1) \\8443 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5 + (7 \times (97 \times 5)))) + (3 \times 1) \\8444 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 - (9 \times 7))) + ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\8445 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 + (9 + (7 \times 5))) - 3! \times 1) \\8446 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) - (7 - (9 \times 75))) + (3 - 1) \\8447 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 - (9 \times 75)) - (3 \times 1)) \\8448 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + ((5! - 3!) - 1)) \\8449 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 797) - ((5^3) - 1) \\8450 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - (5 \times 79)) \times (7 - 5 + (3 + 1)! \\8451 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5)) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 + 3!)) \times 1) \\8452 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5)) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 + 3!)) + 1) \\8453 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 + 3!)) + 1) \\8454 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (((5! \times 7) - 9) - 7!)) + (5 + 31) \\8455 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) + (79 + 7)) \times (5! - 31) \\8456 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 7) \times ((97 + 53) + 1) \\8457 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - 7)) + ((97 - 5)^{3-1}) \\8458 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 \times ((7 \times 97) + 5)) + ((3! + 1)! \\8459 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5 \times (7!/9)))) + (7 + (53 - 1)) \\8460 &:= 13 + ((5 + 7!) + (9 \times (7 \times (53 + 1)))) \\8461 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (7975 + 3! \times 1) \\8462 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (7 - (5 + 31))) \\8463 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7! + (9 \times 7)) + (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\8464 &:= (((((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7) \times (9 - 7)) + 5!)^{3-1} \\8465 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5) - 7)) + ((97 - 5)^{3-1}) \\8466 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times 79)) - (((7!/5) + 3!) \times 1) \\8467 &:= (135 \times 7) - (9 - 7531) \\8468 &:= (1 - (3 - ((5 + (7 \times 9)) + 7))) \times (5! - (3 + 1)) \\8469 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (75 \times (3 + 1)! \\8470 &:= (1 + 3^5) + (7! - (9 \times ((7 - (5! \times 3)) - 1))) \\8471 &:= (13 \times (579 + 75)) - 31 \\8472 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (79 \times (7!/5!)))) - 3! \times 1 \\8473 &:= 1 + ((3 - 5) \times (79 - ((7! - (5 + 3!)) \times 1))) \\8474 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) + (7! - 9)) - (7 + 5 \times 31) \\8475 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) + (79 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\8476 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + ((5! + (79 \times (7!/5!))) - (3 - 1)) \\8477 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) \times 7) + ((9 \times 753) - 1)) \\8478 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (5 - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5 + 3!)) \times 1) \\8479 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! \times 79)) - ((7!/5) - (3 + 1))\end{aligned}$$

- 8480** := $((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (79 \times (7!/5!)))) + (3 - 1)$
8481 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (79 \times (7!/5!)))) + (3 \times 1)$
8482 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5! + 79) - 7!) - (5! - (3!! \times 1)))$
8483 := $((1 + 3!) + (5 + 7)) + ((97 - 5)^{3-1})$
8484 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + (79 \times 7)) + (5 \times 31)$
8485 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times (5! + 31))$
8486 := $(1 - (3 + 5!)) + ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 531))$
8487 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times 79) \times 7 - (5! \times 3) - 1$
8488 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times 79) \times 7 - (5! \times 3) \times 1$
8489 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times 79) \times 7 - (5! \times 3) + 1$
8490 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5! \times 7) - 9) - 7!) - (5 + 31)$
8491 := $((1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 7))) \times 5) \times 3 + 1$
8492 := $(1 - (35/7)) + ((9 + 7) \times 531)$
8493 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7! + (9 \times ((7 \times 53) - 1)))$
8494 := $(1 - 3) + (((5! - 7) - 97) \times 531)$
8495 := $(1^{3!}) + (((5! + 79) + 75) \times 31)$
8496 := $(1 \times 3! \times ((57 - 9) \times (7 + 5))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
8497 := $(1 \times 3579) + ((7! - 5!) - (3 - 1))$
8498 := $(13 \times (579 + 75)) - (3 + 1)$
8499 := $(1 + 3)! + (((5 + 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5! - 3!) - 1))$
8500 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((5! + 79) + 75) \times 31)$
8501 := $(1 \times 3579) + ((7! - 5!) + 3 - 1)$
8502 := $(1 + 3579) + ((7! - 5!) + 3 - 1)$
8503 := $1 - (((3!! \times 5) - (7! + 97)) + 5!) \times (3! \times 1)$
8504 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5) - 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times 531)$
8505 := $(1 \times (3^5)) \times (((7 + 9) \times (7 - 5)) + 3 \times 1)$
8506 := $(13 \times (579 + 75)) + (3 + 1)$
8507 := $((135 \times 7) \times 9) - ((7 - (5 + 3)) - 1)$
8508 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times (9 \times (7 + 5))) - (3 + 1)!)$
8509 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 \times (9 - 7)) + (5! \times 3!) - 1$
8510 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79) + 7!) + 5 \times (3 - 1)$
8511 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 \times (9 - 7)) + (5! \times 3!) + 1$
8512 := $(1 + (3!! \times 5)) + (7 - ((9 + 7) + (5! - ((3! + 1)!!)))$
8513 := $1 + (((3!^5) - 7) - (9 - (753 - 1)))$
8514 := $1 \times (3 \times ((57 \times 9) + (75 \times 31)))$
8515 := $1 + (3 \times ((57 \times 9) + (75 \times 31)))$
8516 := $(1 + (3!! - 5)) + (7! - ((97 - 5!) \times ((3! - 1)!!))$
8517 := $1 \times ((3!! \times 5) + (7! - ((97 - 5) + 31)))$
8518 := $1 + ((3!! \times 5) + (7! - ((97 - 5) + 31)))$
8519 := $((1 \times 3! + (57 + 9)) - 7) \times 5! + (3!! - 1)$
8520 := $1 \times (((35 \times 79) + 75) \times 3) \times 1$
8521 := $1 + (((35 \times 79) + 75) \times 3) \times 1$
8522 := $(1 + (((35 \times 79) + 75) \times 3)) + 1$
8523 := $1 \times 3 + ((5! - (7^{9-7})) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)!))$
8524 := $(1 - 3 + (5! \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) + ((5^3) + 1)$
8525 := $(1^3) + ((5! \times (7 + (9 \times 7))) + ((5^3) - 1))$
8526 := $(1 \times ((3!^5) + 7) - 9) + (753 - 1)$
8527 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7) - 9) + (753 - 1)$
8528 := $1 + (((3!^5) + 7) - ((9 - 753) \times 1))$
8529 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7)) - (9 - (753 + 1))$
8530 := $(13 + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + (7 / ((5 + 3) - 1)))$
8531 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 - 9) - (753 - 1))$
8532 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times (53 + 1))$
8533 := $(1^{35}) - (79 \times ((7 - 5!) + (3! - 1)))$
8534 := $(1 - (3 + (5! - (7 + 9 + 7!)))) + (5 \times 3!! \times 1)$
8535 := $((1^{3!}) \times 5!) + (7! + ((9 \times 75) \times (3! - 1)))$
8536 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + (((7 + (9 \times 7)) + 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
8537 := $((1^{3!}) - (5! - 7)) + ((9 + 7!) + (5 \times 3!!)) \times 1$
8538 := $((1 \times 35) + 7) + ((9 + 7) \times 531)$
8539 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 + 7) \times 9) \times (75 + 3 + 1))$
8540 := $((1 + 3)! \times (((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times 7) - 5!)) - (3 + 1)$
8541 := $((1 + 3!)! + 5!) + (7 \times ((97 \times 5) - 3) + 1)$
8542 := $(1 + (3!! \times (5 + 7))) + (((9 + 7) + 5) - ((3! - 1)!!))$
8543 := $((1 \times 35) + 79) \times 75 - (3! + 1)$
8544 := $((1 + (3!! \times 5)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)$
8545 := $(1 + ((35 + 79) \times 75)) - 3! \times 1$
8546 := $(1 \times (3!! \times (5 + 7))) - ((97 - 5) + 3 - 1)$
8547 := $(1 \times ((35 + 79) \times 75)) - (3 \times 1)$
8548 := $((1 + 3)! \times (((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times 7) - 5!)) + (3 + 1)$
8549 := $(1 \times ((3 \times (579 - 7)) \times 5)) - 31$
8550 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((7 - (9 + 7)) - 5!) \times (3! \times 1))$
8551 := $(1 + (3! \times 579)) + (7! + (5 + 31))$
8552 := $((1 - ((3! + 5) + 7)) \times ((97 + 5!) - 3!!)) + 1$
8553 := $(1 - (3 - 5!)) + (7! + ((97 \times 5) \times (3! + 1)))$
8554 := $(1 + ((35 + 79) \times 75)) + (3 \times 1)$
8555 := $((1 + 3!!) \times (5 + 7)) + (((9 + 7) - 5!) + (3! + 1))$
8556 := $((1 \times 3!!) + ((579 + 7) + 5!)) \times (3! \times 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 8557 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - 7) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 8558 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 8559 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) \times ((7! - 9) - (753 - 1))) \\ 8560 &:= (((1 + 3)!) + ((5! + 7) + (9 \times 7))) \times (5!/3) \times 1 \\ 8561 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 \times (5! - (3 + 1))) \\ 8562 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5! + (((79 \times 7) \times 5) - 31)) \\ 8563 &:= (1^3 + (5! + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 8564 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7!/5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 8565 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) - 79) + (7! + (5 \times (3!! - 1))) \\ 8566 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + ((797 - 5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 8567 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5!) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 8568 &:= (1^{3!}) \times ((5 + 7) \times ((97 + 5) \times (3! + 1))) \\ 8569 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((5 + 7) - 9)!!)) \times ((75 \times 3!) + 1) \\ 8570 &:= (1 + ((35 + 7) \times (97 + 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 8571 &:= (1 + (3!! - 5!)) + (7975 - (3! - 1)) \\ 8572 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((797 - 5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 8573 &:= (1 + (3!! - 5!)) + (7975 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 8574 &:= (1 + (3!! - 5!)) + (7975 - (3 - 1)) \\ 8575 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) \times (7 - 9)) + (75 \times 31) \\ 8576 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) + ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 531)) \\ 8577 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times (7 + ((97 - 5) \times 31)) \\ 8578 &:= ((1 + (3 - 57)) - 9) + (7! + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\ 8579 &:= ((1 \times (3! + ((5! + 7) - 9))) \times 75) - (3!! + 1) \\ 8580 &:= 13 \times ((57 + 9) \times (((7 + 5) - 3) + 1)) \\ 8581 &:= 1 - (3!! - (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 8582 &:= ((1 + (3!! - 5!)) + 7975) + 3! \times 1 \\ 8583 &:= (1 \times (3579 - (7 \times (5 - 3!!)))) - 1 \\ 8584 &:= (1 \times 3579) - ((7 \times (5 - 3!!)) \times 1) \\ 8585 &:= (1 + 3579) - ((7 \times (5 - 3!!)) \times 1) \\ 8586 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 + (9 - 7))) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 8587 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7) + ((9 + 75) + 3!! \times 1) \\ 8588 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) - (53 - 1) \\ 8589 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (((579 - 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 8590 &:= 1 + (3 \times (((579 - 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 8591 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5 - 79) \times ((7 - 5!) - 3))) \times 1 \\ 8592 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + ((5! - 3) - 1)) \\ 8593 &:= 13 + ((579 - 7) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 8594 &:= (((1 \times 3!!) \times 5) + (7! - (9 + 7))) - (5 \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 8595 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5) + 7) + (97 - 5)) + 3!! \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8596 &:= (1 + ((3!! \times 5) + (7! + (9 \times 75)))) - (3!! \times 1) \\ 8597 &:= (((1 \times 3!!) - (5 + (7 - 9))) \times (7 + 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 8598 &:= (((1 \times 3!!) - (5 + (7 - 9))) \times (7 + 5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 8599 &:= (((1 - 35) + 7) - 9) + 7! + (5 \times (3!! - 1)) \\ 8600 &:= 1 \times ((3!! \times 5) - ((79 - (7! + (5!/3))) + 1)) \\ 8601 &:= 1 + ((3!! \times 5) - ((79 - (7! + (5!/3))) + 1)) \\ 8602 &:= 1 + ((3!! \times 5) + ((79 + 7!) - ((5! - 3) + 1))) \\ 8603 &:= 1 - ((35 - ((79 - 7) \times 5!)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 8604 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7!/9) - ((75 + 3!) + 1)) \\ 8605 &:= (1^{3!}) + ((5! \times (79 - 7)) - (5 + 31)) \\ 8606 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5) \times 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) - 5) - 3!! \times 1) \\ 8607 &:= 1 \times ((3!! - 5) + (7! + ((97 - 5) \times 31))) \\ 8608 &:= 1 + ((3!! - 5) + (7! + ((97 - 5) \times 31))) \\ 8609 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5! - 31)) \\ 8610 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times ((9 - 7) + (5! - 3))) + 1) \\ 8611 &:= (1 \times 3579) + ((7! - 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 8612 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! + (7 - 9)) \times (75 - (3 - 1))) \\ 8613 &:= ((1 + (35 - 7)) \times 9) \times (7 - 5 + 31) \\ 8614 &:= ((1 \times (357 \times 9)) + (7! + (5! \times 3))) + 1 \\ 8615 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! \times 79)) - (7 \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 8616 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 - 7) - (9 - (7 \times 53))) - 1) \\ 8617 &:= 1 \times ((3!! \times (5 + 7)) - ((97 - 5)/(3 + 1))) \\ 8618 &:= ((1 + (3579 + (7! + 5))) - 3!) - 1 \\ 8619 &:= ((1 + (3579 + (7! + 5))) - 3!) \times 1 \\ 8620 &:= ((1 + (3579 + (7! + 5))) - 3!) + 1 \\ 8621 &:= ((1 \times 3579) + 7!) + ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\ 8622 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5) + 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - 3! \times 1) \\ 8623 &:= 13 + (((5! - 79) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 8624 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 + 7) - (97 \times (5! - 31))) \\ 8625 &:= ((13 \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + 7) \times (5^{3-1}) \\ 8626 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5!) + 7!) - (9 - (7 \times 531)) \\ 8627 &:= 13 + (5 + (((79 - 7) \times 5!) - 31)) \\ 8628 &:= (1 \times 3579) + ((7! + 5) + 3 + 1) \\ 8629 &:= (1^3 \times (5 - 7)) - (9 - (7! + (5 \times 3!! \times 1))) \\ 8630 &:= (1 \times (3!/(5 + (7 - 9)))) + ((7 + 5) \times (3!! - 1)) \\ 8631 &:= 1 \times (3579 + (((7! + 5) + 3!) + 1)) \\ 8632 &:= 1 + (3579 + (((7! + 5) + 3!) + 1)) \\ 8633 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7! + (9 \times (7 + 5)))/3!) - 1) \\ 8634 &:= (1^3 - (5 - ((79 - 7) \times 5!))) - (3 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8635 &:= ((1-3!)^{5+7-9}) + (7! + (5! \times 31)) & 8674 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (5 + ((7! + ((97 \times 5) \times 3!)) - 1)) \\ 8636 &:= (((1+3) \times 5) \times 7) + ((9+7) \times 531) & 8675 &:= (1 \times 35) - (((7 \times 9) - 75) \times (3!! \times 1)) \\ 8637 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!) - (3! \times 1) & 8676 &:= ((1+3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7))) - (5! + (3+1)!) \\ 8638 &:= 1 - (3 - (((5+79)/7) \times (((5 - (3-1))!))) & 8677 &:= (1 \times ((35 + (7! + 9)) - 7)) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 8639 &:= 1^{3579} \times (7+5) \times 3!! - 1 & 8678 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (7! + (9 + ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1))) \\ 8640 &:= (1 - (((3-5) + 7) - (9+7))) \times (5! \times 3! \times 1) & 8679 &:= (13 \times 57) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + (3! \times 1))) \\ 8641 &:= 1 - (((3+5) \times (7-97)) \times ((5+3!) + 1)) & 8680 &:= (((1^3)^5) \times 7) + (9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) - 1) \\ 8642 &:= 1 \times ((3!/(5 + (7-9))) + (((7+5) \times 3!!) \times 1)) & 8681 &:= (1^{35}) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 8643 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5! \times (7+9 + (7 \times (5+3 \times 1)))) & 8682 &:= 1 + (35 + (((79-7) \times 5!) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 8644 &:= ((13+5) - 7) + (97 \times (5! - 31)) & 8683 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5 \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) + 1))) \\ 8645 &:= (1^3) \times (((5! \times 7) \times 9) + ((7 \times 5) \times 31)) & 8684 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + (5 \times 7)) + (9+7!)) + (5! \times (3+1)!) \\ 8646 &:= 1 \times (((((3 \times 579) - 7) \times 5) - 3) - 1) & 8685 &:= (1^3 \times 579) \times ((7+5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 8647 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 579) - 7) \times 5) - 3) - 1 & 8686 &:= (1 \times 3)! - (5 \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) + 1))) \\ 8648 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 579) - 7) \times 5) - 3) \times 1 & 8687 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 - 7975) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 8649 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 579) - 7) \times 5) - 3) + 1 & 8688 &:= (13 - 5) + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 5) \times 31 \\ 8650 &:= (1 \times ((3579 + 7!) + (5 \times 3!))) + 1 & 8689 &:= (1 - (3! + 57)) - ((9 - 7!) - (5! \times 31)) \\ 8651 &:= 1 + (((3579 + 7!) + (5 \times 3!)) + 1) & 8690 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (((5! \times 79) - (75 - 3)) + 1) \\ 8652 &:= (1 + 3!!) \times (((57 - 9) - (7!/5!)) \times (3 - 1)) & 8691 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + 7)) + ((9 + 7) + (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\ 8653 &:= (135 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 - (5 \times 31)) & 8692 &:= (((1+3)! - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) + (53 - 1) \\ 8654 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 579) - 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1 & 8693 &:= 1 \times 3 + (57 + (97 \times (5! - 31))) \\ 8655 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! \times (79 - 7)) + (5 \times 3))) \times 1 & 8694 &:= (1^3 - (5 - (7! + (9 \times 7)))) + (5 \times (3!! - 1)) \\ 8656 &:= (((1-3!) + 5!) \times (((7 \times 9) + 7) + 5)) + 31 & 8695 &:= (1^3) + ((5! \times (79 - 7)) + (53 + 1)) \\ 8657 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7! + (9 + 7))) + ((5 \times 3!!) + 1) & 8696 &:= (1+3) \times (((5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - (5 \times 3!)) - 1) \\ 8658 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5!) + (7! + (97 \times (5 + 31))) & 8697 &:= (1+3) + ((5! \times (79 - 7)) + (53 \times 1)) \\ 8659 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! \times (79 - 7)) + (5 \times 3)) + 1) & 8698 &:= (13+5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 8660 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!)) + 3!)) - 1 & 8699 &:= (1+3!) - ((5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7!)) - (5! \times 31)) \\ 8661 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!)) + 3!)) \times 1 & 8700 &:= (1 + ((357 - 9) \times (75/3))) - 1 \\ 8662 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!)) + 3!)) + 1 & 8701 &:= (1 + ((357 - 9) \times (75/3))) \times 1 \\ 8663 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7!) - (97 - (5! \times 31)) & 8702 &:= (1 + ((357 - 9) \times (75/3))) + 1 \\ 8664 &:= ((1+3)! \times (5! + (7+9))) + (7! + (5! \times (3 \times 1))) & 8703 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) + ((7975 + 3!!) \times 1) \\ 8665 &:= (1 \times (3!! - (5 - (7! + ((97 \times 5) \times 3!)))) \times 1 & 8704 &:= (1+3) \times (((5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - (5 \times 3!)) + 1) \\ 8666 &:= (1 \times (3!! - (5 - (7! + ((97 \times 5) \times 3!)))) + 1 & 8705 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7975)) + (3!! - 1) \\ 8667 &:= (1 - ((3!! + (5 - 7!)) \times (9 - 7))) + (5 + 31) & 8706 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 + 7975) + 3!!) \times 1) \\ 8668 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - ((5! - (7! - 97)) - (5^{3!-1})) & 8707 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7975)) + (3!! + 1) \\ 8669 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((79 - 7) \times 5!) - 3! \times 1) & 8708 &:= (1 \times (3!! \times 5)) + (((7! + (9 + 7)) + 53) - 1) \\ 8670 &:= (1 - (3! + 5)) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! + 3 + 1)) & 8709 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 + 7) - ((9 \times 7) \times ((5! + 3!) + 1))) \\ 8671 &:= ((1 - (((3-5)^7) \times 9)) \times 7) - (5! - 3!! \times 1) & 8710 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (((7+97) + (5 \times 3!)) \times 1) \\ 8672 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((79 - 7) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)) & 8711 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times (3!! \times 1)) \\ 8673 &:= 1 + 35 + (((79 - 7) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)) & 8712 &:= ((1+3)! + ((5+7) \times ((9-7) \times 5!))) \times (3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 8713** := (13 + (5 + 7975)) + (3!! × 1)
8714 := ((1 + ((3 + 5!) × 79)) - (7!/5)) + (3 + 1)
8715 := ((1 × 3) × (579 + (7 - 5))) × (3! - 1)
8716 := 1 + (3 - ((5 - 797) × (5 + 3! × 1)))
8717 := 1 + ((3 × (5 × 79)) + 7531)
8718 := (1 + 3)! + ((5! × (79 - 7)) + (53 + 1))
8719 := (((1 × 3)!)! + ((5! + 7) × (9 × 7))) - ((5 - 3) × 1)
8720 := ((1 - 3) × ((5 - (7 × (9 × 7))) × 5)) × (3 - 1)
8721 := ((1 - (3! - (5! × 79))) - (7 × 5)) - (3!! - 1)
8722 := ((1 - (3 + 5)) - 7) × (97 - (5! × 3! × 1))
8723 := (((1 × 3!) + (5 + 7)) × (97 × 5)) - (3! + 1)
8724 := ((1 × ((3! + 5) + 7)) × (97 × 5)) - 3! × 1
8725 := ((1 × 3! + (5 + 7)) × (97 × 5)) - (3! - 1)
8726 := (1 - 3!!) + ((5! × (7!/(9 × 7))) - (5 × 31))
8727 := ((1^{3!}) + (5! × 79)) - (753 + 1)
8728 := 1 × (((3!! × (5 + 7)) + (97 - 5)) - (3 + 1))
8729 := 1 - ((3! × 57) - ((9 × (7!/5)) - (3 - 1)))
8730 := (((1 + (35/7)) × (97 × 5)) × 3) × 1
8731 := (((1 + (35/7)) × (97 × 5)) × 3) + 1
8732 := (1 - (3 - 5!)) × ((7 + 97) - (5!/(3 + 1)))
8733 := (1 × ((3 + 5!) × (79 - 7))) - (5! + 3 × 1)
8734 := ((1 × (3!! × (5 + 7))) + (97 - 5)) + (3 - 1)
8735 := ((1 × 3! + (5 + 7)) × (97 × 5)) + (3! - 1)
8736 := (1³ + (5 + 7)) × ((9 × 75) - (3 × 1))
8737 := (1^{3!}) - ((5 + 7) × (((9 + 7) - 5!) × (3! + 1)))
8738 := (1 + (3!! × 5)) - (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5!) - ((3! + 1))!)
8739 := (1 × (3!! × 5)) + (((7! - (9 + 7)) + 5!) - (3! - 1))
8740 := (1 + 3) + (((5 × 7) - 9) × (7!/(5 × (3 × 1))))
8741 := (1 × ((3! + 5) × 797)) + (5 - 31)
8742 := ((13 + 5!) + ((79 - 7) × 5!)) - 31
8743 := (1 + 3) - ((5 - (7! - (9 + 7))) - (5! × 31))
8744 := (13 + ((5 - 79) × (7 - (5³)))) - 1
8745 := ((1 × 3) - (5 - 797)) × (5 + 3! × 1)
8746 := (1³) - ((5 - (7 + 9)) × (75 + ((3! × 1))!))
8747 := ((1^{3!}) × (5! × 79)) - (((7 + 5) + 3!!) + 1)
8748 := (1 × 3) × ((5 + (7 + (9 - 75)))³⁻¹)
8749 := ((1^{3!}) × (5! × 79)) - (((7 + 5) + 3!!) - 1)
8750 := ((1 + ((3! - 5) + 7!)) - 9) + (7 × 531)
8751 := (((1 + (3 + (5! × 79))) - 7) - 5) - (3!! + 1)
8752 := (((1 × 3!) + 5) × 797) - (5 × (3 × 1))
8753 := (1 × (3!⁵)) + (((7 + 975) - 3!) + 1)
8754 := (((1 + 3!) + 5!) × 7) × 9) + (753 × 1)
8755 := ((1 × 3!)⁵) + ((7 + (975 - 3)) × 1)
8756 := (((1 × 3!)⁵) + 7) + 975) - (3 - 1)
8757 := ((1 + 3) + 5) × (7 × ((9 × (7 + 5)) + 31))
8758 := ((1 - 3!) + ((5! × 79) + ((7 - 5) - 3!!)) + 1
8759 := ((1 + 3) × (((57 + 9) + 7) × 5) × 3!) - 1
8760 := ((1 + 3) × (((57 + 9) + 7) × 5) × 3!) × 1
8761 := ((1 + 3) × (((57 + 9) + 7) × 5) × 3!) + 1
8762 := ((1 × 3!)⁵) + (7 + (975 + 3 + 1))
8763 := ((1 × 3!)⁵) + ((7 × ((9 + 7) + (5³))) × 1)
8764 := (1 + 3!) - ((5! × (7 - ((9 + 7) × 5))) + 3 × 1)
8765 := (((1 + 3) - 5) + 7!) + 9) + (7 × 531)
8766 := (1 × 3! + (5! × 79)) - (((7 + 5)/(3 - 1))!)
8767 := (1 + (3⁵ + (79 × 7))) × (5 + 3! × 1)
8768 := (((1 + 3) × (5 × 7)) × (9 × 7)) - (53 - 1)
8769 := (((1 × 3!) + 5) × 797) + 5) - (3 × 1)
8770 := 1 - (((3 × (5! + 7)) × (97 - 5!)) - 3! × 1)
8771 := (1 + 3!) × ((57 × (9 - 7)) × (5 + 3!)) - 1
8772 := ((1³ + (5 + 7)) × (9 × 75)) - (3 × 1)
8773 := (1^{3!}) + ((5! × 79) + ((7 + 5) - (3!! × 1)))
8774 := (13 × (5 + (7 × 97))) - (5! - (3 - 1))
8775 := ((1 × 3) × 5) + (((7 - 9) + 75) × ((3! - 1))!)
8776 := (((1 + (3 + (5! × 79))) + 7) + (5 - 3!!)) × 1
8777 := (1 + (3 + (5! × 79))) + ((7 + 5) - (3!! - 1))
8778 := ((1³ + (5 + 7)) × (9 × 75)) + (3 × 1)
8779 := ((1 + 3!)! + ((5 + (7 × (9 - 7))) + (5! × 31))
8780 := (1 × (((3!! + (5 + 7)) + (9 + 7)) × 5)) + ((3! + 1))!
8781 := ((1 × (3! + 5!)) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) + ((5 × 3!!) - 1))
8782 := (((1 × 3!) + 5) × 797) + (5 × (3 × 1))
8783 := (((1 × 3!)! - 5) + 7!) - 97) + (5^{3!-1})
8784 := (1 - (35 × 7)) × (((9 + 7) - 53) + 1)
8785 := (13 × (5! + (79 × 7))) + (5 + 31)
8786 := (((1 - (3!! + (57 - 9))) + 7!) + 5!) × (3 - 1)
8787 := (1 × (3! + (5 + 7!))) + ((9 + 7) + (5! × 31))
8788 := ((1 - 3)⁵) + (((7 × 9) × (7 × 5)) × (3 + 1))
8789 := (1 - 3) + ((5 - 7) + (9 × ((7!/5) - 31)))
8790 := ((1 × (3!! - 5!)) + ((7 - 9) × 7)) × ((5 × 3) × 1)

$$\begin{aligned} 8791 &:= ((135 + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 \times 31) & 8830 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 + 7!)) + ((9 - (7 - 5!)) \times 31) \\ 8792 &:= (1^3 + ((57 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!)) + 31 & 8831 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (75 - 3!))) - 1 \\ 8793 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5) \times 797)) - (5 - 31) & 8832 &:= (135 - 7) \times (9 + (7 + (53 \times 1))) \\ 8794 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7! - (9 - 7))) + (5! \times 31) & 8833 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (75 - 3!))) + 1 \\ 8795 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))))) & 8834 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) + 7!) + (((9 - 7) + 5!) \times 31) \\ 8796 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 57) - (9 - (7 \times 5!))) \times (3 + 1) & 8835 &:= ((13 + (5! + 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 8797 &:= ((1 \times (3!! \times (5 + 7))) + 97) + (5! / (3 - 1)) & 8836 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - (5 - (7 - 97))) - 5)^{3-1} \\ 8798 &:= (((1 + 3!!) \times 5) + (7! - 9)) + (7 + 5 \times 31) & 8837 &:= (13 + 5) + (((7 \times 9) + 7) \times (5! + 3!)) - 1 \\ 8799 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7 - (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 31) & 8838 &:= (1 - (3! + 5)) + ((79 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 8800 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 31)) & 8839 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + ((79 + 7!) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 8801 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) \times (((7 - 9)^7) \times 5) + ((3! + 1)!)) & 8840 &:= ((135 + 79) + 7) \times ((5! / 3) \times 1) \\ 8802 &:= ((1 + 35) + 7!) + (9 + (7 \times 531)) & 8841 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 + 975)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 8803 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5!)) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)) & 8842 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 + 975)) + (3 + 1) \\ 8804 &:= (1 + (3 + 5!)) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)) & 8843 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 + 975)) + (3! - 1) \\ 8805 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!) + (7! / 9)) \times 7 - (5 \times 31) & 8844 &:= ((13 \times 5) - (7 - 9)) \times (7 + (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 8806 &:= (1 + 3!!) - ((5 \times (7 + 9)) - (7! + (5^{3!-1}))) & 8845 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 + 975)) + (3! + 1) \\ 8807 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + 7!)) + ((9 + 7) + (5! \times 31)) & 8846 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - (5! - ((7! / 9) \times 7))) + ((5 - 3) + 1)!) \\ 8808 &:= (13 - 5) \times (7 + 9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31))) & 8847 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) + (7 \times ((9 + (7! - 5)) / (3 + 1))) \\ 8809 &:= ((135 + 7) \times 9) + 7531 & 8848 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 + 3)) - 1 \\ 8810 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - ((5 + 7) - ((9 - 7) + 5!) \times 31)) & 8849 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times 75)) - (3! + 1) \\ 8811 &:= (((((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + 7)) + 9) + 7) + (5 \times 31)) & 8850 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + 7)) + (((97 + 5!) - 3!) - 1) \\ 8812 &:= (1 + (3!! + 5!)) + ((7975 - 3) - 1) & 8851 &:= (13 + (57 + 97)) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 8813 &:= (13 + 5!) + (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 5) \times 31 & 8852 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 8814 &:= 13 \times (5 - 79 + (753 - 1)) & 8853 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 8815 &:= (1 - (3!! / 5!)) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5^3) + 1)) & 8854 &:= (135 + 79) + ((7 + 5) \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 8816 &:= (135 - (79 - 7!)) + (5! \times 31) & 8855 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5 + (3! \times 1))) \\ 8817 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7975 + 3!)) - 1 & 8856 &:= (13 - 5) + ((79 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 8818 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) + ((7975 + 3!) \times 1) & 8857 &:= (1^{35}) \times (7! + (97 + (5! \times 31))) \\ 8819 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7975 + 3!)) + 1 & 8858 &:= (1^{35}) + (7! + (97 + (5! \times 31))) \\ 8820 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times (9 \times (7 - 5))) \times (3 - 1) & 8859 &:= ((13 + (5! + 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + ((5! / 3) - 1) \\ 8821 &:= 1 + ((35 \times 7) \times ((9 \times (7 - 5)) \times (3 - 1))) & 8860 &:= (1 + 3579) + (7! + (5! \times (3 - 1))) \\ 8822 &:= (((135 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) - ((5! + 3) + 1) & 8861 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) + ((79 \times 7) + 531)) \\ 8823 &:= 1 \times (((35 - 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) + 3 \times 1) & 8862 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) + 975 + (3! - 1) \\ 8824 &:= 1 + (((35 - 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) + 3 \times 1) & 8863 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) + 975 + (3! \times 1) \\ 8825 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 75)) + (3! - 1)) & 8864 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5!)) + 7) + ((9 + 7) \times 531) \\ 8826 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 + 79) \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) \times 1)) & 8865 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) \times (((7 + 975) + 3) \times 1) \\ 8827 &:= 13 \times (5 - 79 + (753 \times 1)) & 8866 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9)) + (7! + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\ 8828 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5 + 797) \times (5 + 3! \times 1)) & 8867 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) - 7) - (9 - 7!)) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 8829 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + (((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)) & 8868 &:= 1 + (((3^5) - 7) - (9 - 7!)) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 8869** := $1 \times ((3!^5) + (79 + (((7!/5) + 3!) \times 1)))$
8870 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5! - (7^{9-7})) \times (5^3 \times 1))$
8871 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 79)) + (((7!/5) + 3!) + 1)$
8872 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7) + (53 - 1)$
8873 := $((1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) \times ((9 + 7) \times 5)) - (3! + 1)$
8874 := $((1 + 3)! + 579) - 7! \times (5 - (3! + 1))$
8875 := $(13 + 5) + (7! + 97) + (5! \times 31)$
8876 := $((1^{3!}) - (5 - 7!)) + (((9 - 7)^5) \times ((3! - 1)!))$
8877 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) - 7 + (9 + (7! + (5! \times 31)))$
8878 := $(1 - ((3 - (5 + (79 - 7))) \times 5!)) - (3 \times 1)$
8879 := $1357 - (9 - 7531)$
8880 := $(1 \times 3! + 579) + 7 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
8881 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times 75))) - 3! \times 1$
8882 := $(1 + ((3! - 5) + 7!)) + (((9 - 7)^5) \times ((3! - 1)!))$
8883 := $(1 + (((3 \times 57) - 97) \times 5!)) + (3 - 1)$
8884 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5! - (7 - 9))) + (75 \times ((3! - 1)!))$
8885 := $((1 \times (3! + 5)) + 7!) - (((9 + 7) \times 5!) - ((3! + 1)!))$
8886 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 + (7 + 975)) \times 3) + 1)$
8887 := $(1 - ((3 - (5 + (79 - 7))) \times 5!)) + 3! \times 1$
8888 := $((1 + (3!^5))/7) \times ((9 - 7)^{5-3+1})$
8889 := $((1 + 35) \times (7 + ((9 - 7) \times 5!))) - (3 \times 1)$
8890 := $1 \times ((3! + ((5 + 7) - 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
8891 := $1 + ((3! + ((5 + 7) - 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
8892 := $1 \times ((3!^5) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)))$
8893 := $1 + ((3!^5) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)))$
8894 := $((1 + ((35 \times 7) + 9)) \times 7) \times 5 - 31$
8895 := $(1 - 3!) \times (((5 + 7) + 9) - (75 \times (3 + 1)!))$
8896 := $(1^3 + 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5! + 3!) + 1))$
8897 := $1357 + 9 + 7531$
8898 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5^{3+1}))$
8899 := $(1 + 3!) - (57 \times ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times (3! \times 1)))$
8900 := $((1 \times ((3! \times 5) + 7)) + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - 31)$
8901 := $(135 + 7!) + (9 + (7 \times 531))$
8902 := $((13 - 5!) + 7!) + ((9 \times 7)^{5-3} \times 1)$
8903 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 \times ((97 - 5!) \times (3! + 1)))$
8904 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 - 7)) \times ((9 + 75) - ((3! \times 1)!))$
8905 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7) + (5 + 3! \times 1))$
8906 := $(1 - (3 + 5!)) \times (7 - ((9 - 7) \times (5!/(3 \times 1))))$
8907 := $((1 + 3)^5 + 7) \times 9 - ((7 \times 53) + 1)$
8908 := $(1^3 \times (5 + (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 + 5!) + 3 + 1)$
8909 := $((1^3 \times 57) + 9) - 7 \times (5! + 31)$
8910 := $135 \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) + (53 - 1))$
8911 := $(1 - 3!) - (5 + ((79 \times (7 - 5!)) + (3! \times 1)))$
8912 := $(1 - 3) - ((5! \times 7) - (9753 + 1))$
8913 := $(1 - (3 + (5 - 7!))) + ((97 \times (5!/3)) \times 1)$
8914 := $(1 - (3 + (5 - 7!))) + ((97 \times (5!/3)) + 1)$
8915 := $(1 \times (3! \times (5 + 7))) + (((97 - 5) \times 3) - 1)$
8916 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5 - 7)) \times ((97 - 5!) - (3! \times 1))$
8917 := $1357 + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times (3 + 1)!)$
8918 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5 + 3!) + 1$
8919 := $((1 + (3 - 5)) + 7!) + ((97 \times (5!/3)) \times 1)$
8920 := $((1 + (3 - 5)) + 7!) + ((97 \times (5!/3)) + 1)$
8921 := $(1 \times 3!) - (5 + ((79 \times (7 - 5!)) + (3! + 1)))$
8922 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 + 7) \times ((97 - 5!) - 3!)) \times 1)$
8923 := $(1 \times (3^5)) + (((7!/9)/(7 - 5)) \times 31)$
8924 := $((1^3 + 5)! + (7!/9)) \times 7 - 5 - 31$
8925 := $((1^3 + 5) + 79) \times 7 \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
8926 := $(1^3 \times 5) - (79 - (75 \times ((3! - 1)!)))$
8927 := $(1 \times (3! + (5 + 7!))) + ((97 + 5) \times 31)$
8928 := $(1 + (3 + 5!)) \times ((7 + (9 - 7)) \times (5 + 3 \times 1))$
8929 := $(1^3) - ((5 + 7) \times ((9 - 753) \times 1))$
8930 := $(1 + 3!) - (((579 - 7!) \times (5 - 3)) - 1)$
8931 := $((1 + 3!) + (5 + 7)) \times 9 + (7! + (5! \times 31))$
8932 := $(1^{35}) - ((79 \times (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1))$
8933 := $((1^{35}) - (79 \times (7 - 5!))) + (3! - 1)$
8934 := $(1 + 3!) - (((5 + 7) \times (9 - 753)) + 1)$
8935 := $(13 + 5797) + (5^{3-1})$
8936 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) - (((79 \times (7 - 5!)) - 3!) - 1)$
8937 := $((1357 + 9) \times 7) - (5^{3+1})$
8938 := $(1^{3!}) \times ((5 - (79 \times (7 - 5!))) + (3! \times 1))$
8939 := $(1^{3!}) + ((5 - (79 \times (7 - 5!))) + (3! \times 1))$
8940 := $(13 - ((5 + 7) \times (9 - 753))) - 1$
8941 := $(13 - ((5 + 7) \times (9 - 753))) \times 1$
8942 := $(13 - ((5 + 7) \times (9 - 753))) + 1$
8943 := $((1 + 3!) - 57) \times ((9 - ((7 \times 5!)/3)) \times 1)$
8944 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 + 7) \times (9 - (753 + 1)))$
8945 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + (((7 + 9) \times 75) - 31)$
8946 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 - (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times (5! + (3! \times 1))$

- 8947** := $1 - (((3 - 5) \times (7 \times 9)) \times (75 - (3 + 1)))$
8948 := $((((1 \times 3!))! \times 5) + 7!) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - (3! + 1))$
8949 := $((((1 \times 3!))! \times 5) + 7!) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - 3! \times 1)$
8950 := $((1 - 3!) - 5) - (((7!/9) - 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
8951 := $((((1 \times 3!) - 5!) - 7) + (9 \times (7 \times (5! + (3 + 1)!))))$
8952 := $(1 - 35) + ((7! + 9) + ((7 + 5!) \times 31))$
8953 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 7)^{9-7}) + (53 + 1))$
8954 := $(1 - (3! - 5!)) + (79 + (7! + (5! \times 31)))$
8955 := $135 + (((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1))$
8956 := $(13 \times 5!) + ((79 + 7)^{5-3 \times 1})$
8957 := $(13 \times 5!) + (((79 + 7)^{5-3}) + 1)$
8958 := $1 \times ((3 - 5) \times ((7!/9) - (7! - (5 - (3 + 1))))))$
8959 := $(135 + (79 + 75)) \times 31$
8960 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5! + (79 - (7! - (5! \times 3)))) + 1)$
8961 := $((1 \times (3 + 5!)) \times 79) - ((7 \times 5) + (3! + 1))$
8962 := $(1 \times (3 + (5! + 79))) + (7! + (5! \times 31))$
8963 := $1 \times ((3! \times 5) - ((79 \times (7 - 5!)) - (3! \times 1)))$
8964 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 + 7) \times (9 - (753 + 1)))$
8965 := $((((1 \times 3!))! \times (5 + 7)) + (975 / (3 \times 1)))$
8966 := $((((1 + 3!))! - ((5! - 7!) - 9)) - (((7!/5) - 3!) + 1)$
8967 := $(1 + 35) - ((79 \times (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1))$
8968 := $(1 - 3) \times (5 - ((79 - (7 + 5))^{3-1}))$
8969 := $((((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) + 3!)) + 1)$
8970 := $(1 + (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1)$
8971 := $((((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - (5^{3+1}))$
8972 := $(1 - ((3! \times 5!) \times (7 - 9))) + 7531$
8973 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times 9) \times ((7 + 5) + (3! + 1)))$
8974 := $(1 - 3) \times (579 - (7! - (5 - 31)))$
8975 := $(1 \times (357 + (9 - 7))) \times (5^{3-1})$
8976 := $((1 + (3! + 579)) \times 7) - ((5! + 3) + 1)$
8977 := $((((1 + (3! + 579)) \times 7) - (5! + 3)) \times 1)$
8978 := $(1 + ((3! + 579) \times 7)) - ((5! - 3) - 1)$
8979 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (79 - 7))) + (5! + 3 \times 1)$
8980 := $((1 + 3!) - (579 - (7! + 5))) \times (3 - 1)$
8981 := $((((1 + 3!))! - 5!) + (7! - 975)) - (3 + 1)$
8982 := $(13 + 5) \times ((79 \times 7) - (53 + 1))$
8983 := $13 \times ((5 + 7) + (97 \times (5 + 3 - 1)))$
8984 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) \times (((((7!/9) + 7!)/5) + 3) \times 1)$
8985 := $((((13 + 579) + 7) \times 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
8986 := $(((((1^3 + 5))! + (7!/9)) \times 7) - 5) + 31$
8987 := $(1 \times 357) - (9 - (7! + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
8988 := $(13 + 5) - (((7!/9) - (7! + 5)) \times (3 - 1))$
8989 := $((((1 + 3!))! - 5!) + (7! - 975)) + (3 + 1)$
8990 := $((((1 + 3!))! - 5) + (7! - ((97 + 5!) \times (3! - 1))))$
8991 := $(1 \times (3^5)) \times ((7 - 9) + ((7!/5!) - (3 \times 1)))$
8992 := $(1 \times 3!) - ((5 - 7) - 9) \times (753 - 1)$
8993 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7975) - 3! \times 1)$
8994 := $((((1 + (3 \times 57)) - 97) \times 5!) - (3! \times 1))$
8995 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5 \times (7 - 97)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
8996 := $13 \times ((5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 75)) + 3 - 1)$
8997 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7975) - (3 - 1))$
8998 := $(((((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times (7 - (9 - 7))) \times 5!) - (3 - 1))$
8999 := $(1 + (3 - 5)) + ((79 - 7) \times (5^3 \times 1))$
9000 := $((13 + (57 + 9)) - 7) \times ((5^3) \times 1)$
9001 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7975) + (3 - 1))$
9002 := $((((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
9003 := $1 - ((3 - 5) - ((79 - 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)))$
9004 := $((1 \times 3) - (5! \times (7 - (97 - (5 \times 3)))) + 1)$
9005 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7975) + 3! \times 1)$
9006 := $((((1 + (3 \times 57)) - 97) \times 5!) + (3! \times 1))$
9007 := $(1 - 3) + ((5 + (79 - 7)) \times (5! - (3 \times 1)))$
9008 := $(1 \times (((3^5 + 7) \times 9) + (7 - 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
9009 := $((((1 + 3!))! - 5!) + (7! - 975)) + (3 + 1)!$
9010 := $(13 \times (5 + (7 \times 97))) + (5! - (3 - 1))$
9011 := $((((13 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7! - 5!)) - (3 + 1))$
9012 := $(13 \times 5!) - (79 - 7531)$
9013 := $((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 9)) + 7!) + (5! \times 31)$
9014 := $((((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times 7) + ((9 + 7!) + (5! \times 31)))$
9015 := $((1 + ((35 \times 7) + 9)) + 7!) + (5! \times 31)$
9016 := $((13 - 5!) \times 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 \times 31))$
9017 := $1 - ((35 - (7 \times 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
9018 := $((((1 \times 3) - 5) - 7) \times (9 - ((7!/5) + 3 \times 1)))$
9019 := $1 - ((3 - 5) \times (7! - (9 \times (7 + (53 - 1))))))$
9020 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) \times ((7!/9) - (7! + (5 \times 3! \times 1)))$
9021 := $(1 \times 357 + (9 - 75)) \times 31$
9022 := $(13 \times (5 - 7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) - (3 + 1)!)$
9023 := $(1 \times 3!) - ((5! + 7) \times (9 - (75 + (3! - 1))))$
9024 := $((1 \times 3 + 5) + 7) + (9 + (75 \times ((3! - 1)!)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 9025 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7)) + (9 \times (((7!/5) + 3!) + 1)) \\ 9026 &:= (((1 + (3!/5)) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7 - 5!)) + (3 + 1) \\ 9027 &:= (13 + 5) + (((7 \times 9)^{7-5}) + ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 9028 &:= (1 - (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 7) - (53 \times 1)) \\ 9029 &:= (1 - (35 + 7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 9030 &:= (1^3) \times (((5! \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times (5 + (3! - 1))) \\ 9031 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((79 - 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 9032 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 \times 7) + 9) - 7!) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\ 9033 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5^{7-9+7}) - 5!)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 9034 &:= 1 + (((3 + (5 \times 797)) + 5) + ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 9035 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 \times 79) + (7! + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!))) \\ 9036 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5! - (7 - 9)) \times 75)) - ((3! - 1)! \\ 9037 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 79)) + (((7 + 5) \times 3!) - 1) \\ 9038 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! + 7!)) + (97 \times ((5!/3) \times 1)) \\ 9039 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 579) + (7! - 53)) - 1 \\ 9040 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) + (79 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\ 9041 &:= ((1^3 \times 5)! - (79 - (75 \times ((3! - 1)!))) \\ 9042 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 \times ((7 \times 97) + 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 9043 &:= (1 - 35) + (((7 + (9 \times (7!/5))) - 3) + 1) \\ 9044 &:= (13 + 5!) \times (7 + (97 - (5 + 31))) \\ 9045 &:= 135 \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) + (53 \times 1)) \\ 9046 &:= ((1^3 - 5!) - (79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3))) + 1 \\ 9047 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((57 \times 9) - 7!) + 5) \times (3 - 1) \\ 9048 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (((9 \times 7) - 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 9049 &:= 13 - ((5 - 7) \times ((9 + 7!) - 531)) \\ 9050 &:= (1 - (3! + 5)) \times (79 - ((7!/5) - (3 + 1)!)) \\ 9051 &:= (1 + ((3!/5) \times (7 \times 9))) - (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 9052 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5!) \times (79 - ((7 + 5)/(3 - 1))) \\ 9053 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5)) \times (797 - (5 - 31)) \\ 9054 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + ((7975 + 3!) - 1) \\ 9055 &:= (135 + 7!) + (97 \times ((5!/3) \times 1)) \\ 9056 &:= (((1 + ((3! - 5)^7))^9) - 7!) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1) \\ 9057 &:= 13 - (((5 \times (7 + 9)) \times (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1)) \\ 9058 &:= (1 + 3) - (((57 \times 9) - 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 9059 &:= (1 + (((3^5 + 7) + 9) \times (7 \times 5))) - (3! + 1) \\ 9060 &:= (1 \times 3 + 57) \times (97 + (53 + 1)) \\ 9061 &:= (13 + 5!) + ((79 - 7) \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 9062 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) - (((7 \times 9) - 7!) - (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 9063 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) - 3! \times 1) \\ 9064 &:= ((13 - 5!) \times (7 - (97 - 5))) - 31 \\ 9065 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) \times (97 - (5!/(3 - 1)))) \\ 9066 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (5 - ((7! + 97) + 5!))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 9067 &:= (1 - ((35 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 53))) + 1 \\ 9068 &:= (((135 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) + (5! + 3) - 1 \\ 9069 &:= (((135 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) + ((5! + 3) \times 1) \\ 9070 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) \times (7!/5)) - (3 - 1) \\ 9071 &:= 1^{357} + ((9 \times (7!/5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 9072 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^{(57-9)/(7+5)}) \times (3! + 1) \\ 9073 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - 5) + (79 \times (7!/5!))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 9074 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) \times (7!/5)) + (3 - 1) \\ 9075 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7) + (9 \times (7!/5)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 9076 &:= ((1 - 35) - 7) + (9 \times (((7!/5) + 3!) - 1)) \\ 9077 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5!) + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31) \\ 9078 &:= (1 + 3)! - (((57 \times 9) - 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 9079 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + ((79 + 7!) + ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 9080 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5! - ((7! - 9) - ((7 \times 53) \times 1))) \\ 9081 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5) + 79) + (75 \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 9082 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5! - 7!) + (9 + ((7 \times 53) - 1))) \\ 9083 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + 5) + (((79 \times (7!/5!)) + 3!) \times 1) \\ 9084 &:= (1^3 + 5) \times ((7 \times (97 + 5!)) - (3! - 1)) \\ 9085 &:= (((1^3)^5) - (7!/(9 \times 7))) \times (5 - ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 9086 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5 - ((7! - (97 \times 5)) - (3! + 1))) \\ 9087 &:= 13 \times (5! + ((7!/9) - ((7 + 5) - 31))) \\ 9088 &:= (135 + 7) \times ((9 + (7 \times (5 + 3))) - 1) \\ 9089 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5!) - (7 - ((9 + 7) \times 531))) \\ 9090 &:= (1 \times ((3 + (5! \times 7)) + 975)) \times (3! - 1) \\ 9091 &:= 1 - (3! - (57 + (9753 \times 1))) \\ 9092 &:= (((1^{35}) - 7) + (9 \times ((7!/5) + 3))) - 1 \\ 9093 &:= (((1^{35}) - 7) + (9 \times ((7!/5) + 3))) \times 1 \\ 9094 &:= (((1^{35}) - 7) + (9 \times ((7!/5) + 3))) + 1 \\ 9095 &:= (1 + ((3!/5) \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 9096 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5 - (7 - 9)) + ((7 + 5) \times 31)) \\ 9097 &:= (13 - ((5 - 7!) - (9 \times (75 \times 3!)))) - 1 \\ 9098 &:= 13 + ((5 \times 79) \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1)) \\ 9099 &:= (13 - ((5 - 7!) - (9 \times (75 \times 3!)))) + 1 \\ 9100 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (7 + 9 + 75)) \times (3! - 1) \\ 9101 &:= ((135 + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 9102 &:= (1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) - (7 \times (53 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 9103** := $1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7!) + (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) + 1)))$
9104 := $(13 \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7! - (5 \times 3!)) - 1)$
9105 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + 797) + 531$
9106 := $((1 \times 3) - ((5! + 7) \times (9 - 75))) + (3!! + 1)$
9107 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5 - 7!) - ((9 - (7!/5)) + 31)))$
9108 := $((1 + (3!! - 5)) + (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times (5 + (3! \times 1))$
9109 := $((1 + 3) - 5) + ((7! - (97 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1))$
9110 := $(1 + (((3 - 57) \times 9) + 7!)) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
9111 := $(1 \times (35 + 7 + (9 \times (7!/5)))) - (3 \times 1)$
9112 := $(1^3 \times ((5! \times 79) - 7)) - ((5! \times 3) + 1)$
9113 := $(1^3) + (((5! \times 79) - 7) - ((5! \times 3) + 1))$
9114 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) - 7 - ((5! \times 3) - 1)$
9115 := $1 + (((3 + 579) \times 7) + (((5 + 3) - 1)!))$
9116 := $((1 \times (35 + 7)) + (9 \times (7!/5))) + (3 - 1)$
9117 := $(1 + (35 + 7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) + 3 - 1)$
9118 := $(1 + (35 + 7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) + 3 \times 1)$
9119 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5! \times 79) - (7! + ((5! \times 3) + 1))))$
9120 := $(1 + 3)! \times (((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times 7) - 5!) + (3 + 1)!)$
9121 := $(1 + (3!! + (5! \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!)))) + ((3! \times 1)!)$
9122 := $(1 - (3! - 57)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) - (3 - 1))$
9123 := $(13 - 5!) + (7! - (9 + ((7 \times (5! - 3!)) + 1)))$
9124 := $(1 + 3) - (5! \times ((7 - (97 - (5 \times 3))) - 1))$
9125 := $((13 + 5) + 7) \times ((97 \times 5) - ((3! - 1)!))$
9126 := $(1^3 + (5 + (79 - 7))) \times (5! - (3 \times 1))$
9127 := $(1 \times (3!! + 5)) + (((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) + 3 - 1)$
9128 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) + 7 - ((5! \times 3) - 1)$
9129 := $1 + ((35 - 7) \times ((975/3) + 1))$
9130 := $(1^3 - (5 + 79)) \times ((7 - 5!) + 3 \times 1)$
9131 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 5) + (((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) + (3! \times 1))$
9132 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 5) + (((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) + (3! + 1))$
9133 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7! + 5) - (3! + 1))$
9134 := $1 + ((3! + 57) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) - (3 - 1)))$
9135 := $((1^{3!}) - (5! + 7)) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1)$
9136 := $((1 - 3!)! - ((5! - 7!) - (9 + 7!))) - (5! - 3! \times 1)$
9137 := $((13 \times 5) \times 7) \times 9 + (7! + (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
9138 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 + 7) \times (9 + 753)) - 1)$
9139 := $((1 - ((3 - 5!) \times 79)) - ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) \times 1$
9140 := $((1^{3!}) \times 5) \times (((7 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3!)) + 1)$
9141 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) + (5! + ((3! \times 1)!)))$
9142 := $((1 \times 3!)! / 5) \times (7 \times 9) + (75 - (3! - 1))$
9143 := $((1 + 35) + 7) + ((9 \times ((7!/5) + 3)) + 1)$
9144 := $(1^3 + 5) \times ((7 \times (97 + 5!)) + (3! - 1))$
9145 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5) + ((7 - (97 + 5))^{3-1})$
9146 := $(1 \times 3) - (((5! + 7) \times ((9 - 75) - 3!)) + 1)$
9147 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) + ((7! / (9 + 7)) \times (5 + (3 + 1)!))$
9148 := $13 - (5 \times (7 \times (9 \times ((7 - 5) - 31))))$
9149 := $((1 + 3!)! + 579) + 7 \times ((5 + 3) - 1)$
9150 := $((13 - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) - (5! \times (3 + 1))$
9151 := $((1 + 3579) + 7!) + 531$
9152 := $((1 + ((3!! + 5!) + 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
9153 := $1 \times (3 \times (((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 531))$
9154 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5 \times (7!/9)) + (753 + 1))$
9155 := $1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7!/9)) + (753 + 1))$
9156 := $((1^3 - 5!) \times ((7 - 9) - 75)) - (3! + 1)$
9157 := $((1 - (3! - 5!)) \times 79) + ((75 - 3) \times 1)$
9158 := $(1 \times ((3^5 + 7) - 9)) \times (((7 \times 5) + 3) \times 1)$
9159 := $(1 \times 35) + (7 + (9 \times (((7!/5) + 3!) - 1)))$
9160 := $(1^3) - (5 + ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) \times 1))$
9161 := $(1 \times 3) - (5 + ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) + 1))$
9162 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) - (79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) \times 1$
9163 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) \times (79 + (753 + 1))$
9164 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5) - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) + 1)$
9165 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7! + (5! / (3 + 1)))$
9166 := $(1 - 3 + 5) - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) + 1)$
9167 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) - ((7 - 9)^7) \times (5! - 31)$
9168 := $(1357 - 975) \times (3 + 1)!$
9169 := $((1 - 3 + 5)! - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) + 1))$
9170 := $(13 \times 5!) + (79 + 7531)$
9171 := $(1 \times 3 + 5) - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) + 1)$
9172 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) \times 1)$
9173 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3)) - 1)$
9174 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) - 3) \times 1$
9175 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + (((9 \times (7!/5)) - 3) + 1)$
9176 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) - 97)) \times (5! + 3 + 1)$
9177 := $((1 \times 35) + 7) + (9 \times (((7!/5) + 3!) + 1))$
9178 := $1 - (3!! + ((5! - 7!) + (9 - ((7! - 53) - 1))))$
9179 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) + 3 - 1)$
9180 := $(1 \times 3! \times 5) \times ((7 + (9 + (7 \times 5))) \times 3! \times 1)$

- 9181** := $((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) - 9 + (7! - 531)$
9182 := $(1 + (((3!/5) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 - 5!))) - (3 + 1)$
9183 := $1 \times (((3^5) - 79) \times (7 \times (5 + 3))) - 1$
9184 := $(1 \times ((3^5) - 79)) \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) \times 1)$
9185 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5 + 3! \times 1))$
9186 := $(1 + (3! \times (((5 \times 7) + (9 + 7)) \times 5))) \times 3! \times 1$
9187 := $1 \times (((3!! \times 5) + (7 + 9)) + (7! + 531))$
9188 := $(1 + ((3!! \times 5) + (7 + 9))) + (7! + 531)$
9189 := $((1 + 3) + 5) \times ((7 - (9 \times (7 - 5!))) - (3 \times 1))$
9190 := $(1 + (((3!/5) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 - 5!))) + (3 + 1)$
9191 := $(1 - ((35/7) + 9)) \times ((7 + 5) - (3!! - 1))$
9192 := $((13 + (5! - 79)) \times 7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)!$
9193 := $(1 - 3!!) + (((5 \times 7) + (9 \times (7!/5!))) \times (3 + 1)!)!$
9194 := $(1 + (3!^5)) + (7! + (97 - (5! \times 31)))$
9195 := $(13 + (5! \times (7 - (9 - 7)))) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
9196 := $(1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7) + (5! \times (3 - 1)))$
9197 := $((1 - 35) + (7! - 9)) - (7 \times (5! - ((3! \times 1)!))!$
9198 := $(((((1 \times 3) - 5) + 7)!) + (9 \times (7!/5))) + 3! \times 1$
9199 := $(1 - (3! - (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 3)))) \times 1$
9200 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 3)) + 1$
9201 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times ((7 \times 9)/7) - (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
9202 := $(1 - (3 - (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 3)))) \times 1$
9203 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + 7) \times (5 + 3) - 1$
9204 := $(1^3) \times (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 3)) \times 1$
9205 := $(13 + (5! \times 79)) - ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)!)!$
9206 := $1 + (35 \times (((797 - 5)/3) - 1))$
9207 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 3)) - 1$
9208 := $(1 - (3!! - 5)) - (((79 - 7!) \times (5 - 3)) \times 1)$
9209 := $1 \times (3! + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 3)) - 1))$
9210 := $1 + (3! + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 3)) - 1))$
9211 := $((135 + 7) + 9) \times (7 + (53 + 1))$
9212 := $(1 + 3!) + (5 + ((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times (5! - (3! - 1))))$
9213 := $((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 - (9 \times (7 - 5!))) - (3 \times 1)$
9214 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times ((7 \times 9)/7) - (5 - (3 \times 1))$
9215 := $(1 + ((3 - 57) \times 9)) \times ((7 + 5) - 31)$
9216 := $(13 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)))$
9217 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times ((7 \times 9)/7) - 5 + 3! \times 1$
9218 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times ((7 \times 9)/7) + (5 - (3 \times 1))$
9219 := $((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 - (9 \times (7 - 5!))) + (3 \times 1)$
9220 := $((1 - (3!! - 5)) + (7! + 9)) + (7! - (5 \times 31))$
9221 := $((1 + (35 - 7)) \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) + 3)) - 1$
9222 := $((1 - (3 - (5! + (7 \times 9)))) - 7) \times (53 \times 1)$
9223 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + 7) \times (5 + 3) - 1$
9224 := $((1 + (3!! + 579)) \times 7) + ((5! + 3) + 1)$
9225 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7 + (9 - 7)) \times (5^{3-1})$
9226 := $((1 - 3!!) - (((5! - 7!) + 9) - 7!)) - ((5 - (3 - 1)))!$
9227 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 3)) - 1$
9228 := $(1 + (3! + 5)) \times (7 + (9 + (753 \times 1)))$
9229 := $((1 + 3!)! - 5!) + (7! - ((9 + 7) - 5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)!$
9230 := $(135 + 7) \times ((9 + (7 \times (5 + 3))) \times 1)$
9231 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times ((7 \times 9)/7) + (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
9232 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! \times 79) - ((7!/5)/(3 + 1)))$
9233 := $((1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + 7)) \times (5 + 3) + 1$
9234 := $1 \times ((3! + (5! \times 79)) - ((7!/5)/(3 + 1)))$
9235 := $1 + ((3! + (5! \times 79)) - ((7!/5)/(3 + 1)))$
9236 := $(1 - 3) - ((5! \times (7 - (9 + 75))) + 3 - 1)$
9237 := $((1 + 3) + 57) + (9 + 7) \times 5! - (3 \times 1)$
9238 := $1 - (((3 \times 5!) - 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + (5! + 3 \times 1)$
9239 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) \times (7!/9)) + (7! - 5!) - (3!! + 1)$
9240 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5 \times ((79 + 75) \times (3 + 1)))$
9241 := $1 + (3 \times 5 \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3+1})))$
9242 := $(1 + (3 - (5! \times (7 - (9 + 75)))) - (3 - 1)$
9243 := $(1^3) - ((5! \times (7 - (9 + 75))) - (3 - 1))$
9244 := $((1 + 3) + 57) + (9 + 7) \times 5! + 3 + 1$
9245 := $(1 \times (3 - (5! \times (7 - (9 + 75)))) + (3 - 1)$
9246 := $(1 + 3) - ((5! \times (7 - (9 + 75))) - (3 - 1))$
9247 := $((1 - 3!!) - ((5! - 7!) - 9)) + (((7! - 5) + 3) - 1)$
9248 := $13 + ((5! \times ((79 - 7) + 5)) - (3! - 1))$
9249 := $(13 + (5! \times ((79 - 7) + 5))) - (3 + 1)$
9250 := $(1 + (3 + (5 + 7 + 9))) \times ((7 \times 53) - 1)$
9251 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) + (7! + ((9 - 7)^{5+3!+1}))$
9252 := $(1 + (3! + 5)) \times (797 + (5 - 31))$
9253 := $(1 + (3!! \times (5 + 7))) + ((97 + 5) \times (3! \times 1))$
9254 := $((13 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times ((5^3) \times 1))$
9255 := $((1 \times (3!! + 5!)) + 7!) + ((9 \times 75) \times (3! - 1))$
9256 := $((1 + 3!)! + 5! + ((7!/(9 \times (7 \times 5)))^3 \times 1))$
9257 := $(13 + (5! \times ((79 - 7) + 5))) + (3 + 1)$
9258 := $((1 \times 3) - 57) + (97 \times (5! - (3 + 1)!))$

$$\begin{aligned} 9259 &:= (((1-3+5)!-7) + (((9+7)+5)^3) - 1) & 9297 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - ((7 \times 9) - (75 \times ((3!-1)!))) \\ 9260 &:= (1+3)^{(5+7-9)!} + (7! + (5! + 3 + 1)) & 9298 &:= ((1-3+5!) \times 79) - ((7+5) \times (3-1)) \\ 9261 &:= ((1^{3!})^{5!+7}) \times (((9+7)+5)^3 \times 1) & 9299 &:= (13-5!) + ((7!-9) + (7 \times (5^{3+1}))) \\ 9262 &:= ((1^{3!})^{5!+7}) + (((9+7)+5)^3 \times 1) & 9300 &:= ((13-5!) + 7) \times (((9-7)-5) \times 31) \\ 9263 &:= (1^{357}) + (((9+(7+5))^3) + 1) & 9301 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5)) + (7! - (((9 \times 7) - (5 \times 3!)) + 1)) \\ 9264 &:= (1^3 \times 579) \times (7 + ((5+3) + 1)) & 9302 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - ((5 \times 79) - 7!)) \times ((5-3) \times 1) \\ 9265 &:= (((13 \times (57-9)) + 7!) + (5 \times 3!)) + 1 & 9303 &:= (((1+3!))! - (5! - 7!)) - (9 \times (75 - (3-1))) \\ 9266 &:= ((1+3!) + (5-7)) + (((9+7)+5)^3 \times 1) & 9304 &:= (((1+3!) - (5 \times 79)) + 7!) \times ((5-3) \times 1) \\ 9267 &:= ((1-3!) - ((5-7)^9)) + (7! + (5! \times 31)) & 9305 &:= ((1^{3!})! + (5! \times 7)) + ((97-5)^{3-1}) \\ 9268 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 579)) + 7531 & 9306 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (57+9)) \times ((7!/5!) + (3!-1)) \\ 9269 &:= (1 + (3 \times 579)) + 7531 & 9307 &:= ((1 \times ((3^5) - (7+9))) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3!)) \times 1 \\ 9270 &:= ((1+3!) + (5! + 79)) \times ((7!/5!) + 3 \times 1) & 9308 &:= ((1-3+5!) \times 79) - ((7+5) + 3-1) \\ 9271 &:= (((1+3!) + (5! + 79)) \times ((7!/5!) + 3)) + 1 & 9309 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times (5! - 7)) - (9-7!))) + (5 \times 3! \times 1) \\ 9272 &:= 1 - (3! + (5 + ((79 - (7! - 5)) - ((3! + 1)!))) & 9310 &:= (13 + 57) \times (97 + (5 + 31)) \\ 9273 &:= (1^{3!}) \times (5 + (7 + (((9+7)+5)^3 \times 1))) & 9311 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + (7! + ((9 \times 75) - (3! - 1))) \\ 9274 &:= ((13+5!) \times (7 + (9 \times 7))) - (5 + 31) & 9312 &:= (((1-3+5!) \times 79) - (7+5)) + (3-1) \\ 9275 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7 - (9-7))) \times (53 \times 1) & 9313 &:= (13 \times 5) + (((7!+9) + (7!-5!)) - (3!+1)) \\ 9276 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! - (7-9)) \times 75) + ((3!-1)!)) & 9314 &:= ((1-3+5!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) - ((5^3) + 1) \\ 9277 &:= (13 + (5! \times ((79-7) + 5))) + (3+1)! & 9315 &:= ((13 \times 5) + (7! + 9)) + (7! - (5! + (3! - 1))) \\ 9278 &:= 1 + (3! + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 \times (3-1)))) & 9316 &:= (13 \times (5 + (7 \times (97 + 5)))) - 31 \\ 9279 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5)) + (7 + (((9+7)+5)^3 \times 1)) & 9317 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((579 + 753) - 1) \\ 9280 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (7 + 97)) \times (5!/(3! \times 1)) & 9318 &:= ((1 - (3! \times 5!)) + 7!) + ((9 + (7! - 53)) + 1) \\ 9281 &:= ((1357-9) \times 7) - (5 \times 31) & 9319 &:= (1 \times (3! - (5! - (79 + 7!)))) + (5 \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 9282 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5! + (7 + ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) \times (3 \times 1)) & 9320 &:= (((1-3!) \times 5!) + 7!) - (9-7!) - (5! + 31) \\ 9283 &:= 1 - ((3! - 57) \times ((9-7) - ((5 \times 3) + 1))) & 9321 &:= ((1 - (35/7)) - 9) \times (((7-5) - 3!) + 1) \\ 9284 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5) - 7) + (((9+7)+5)^3 \times 1) & 9322 &:= ((1+3!)! \times (5 \times 79)) - ((7+5!) + 31) \\ 9285 &:= ((1-3!) - (5! - 7!)) - (9 - ((7! + 53) \times 1)) & 9323 &:= ((1-3!)/5) - ((7 \times 9) \times (7 - (5 \times 31))) \\ 9286 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) - ((79 \times ((7-5!) - 3)) + 1) & 9324 &:= 1 \times (((35-7) \times 9) + 7) \times (5 + 31) \\ 9287 &:= ((1-35) - (79 \times (7 - (5^3)))) - 1 & 9325 &:= 1 + (((35-7) \times 9) + 7) \times (5 + 31) \\ 9288 &:= ((1-35) - (79 \times (7 - (5^3)))) \times 1 & 9326 &:= (1-35) + (7! + (((9-7)+5)! - ((3! \times 1)!))) \\ 9289 &:= ((1-35) - (79 \times (7 - (5^3)))) + 1 & 9327 &:= (((1+3!) \times 5) + 7!) + ((9 \times 75) + 3!) + 1 \\ 9290 &:= (((13 \times 5) \times 7) \times 9) + (7! + 5 \times 31) & 9328 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5 \times 7)) \times (((97-5) - 3) - 1) \\ 9291 &:= ((1 - ((3-5!) \times 79)) - 7) + (53 + 1) & 9329 &:= (1 - ((3! + 5) - (7! + 9))) + ((7! - 5) - 31) \\ 9292 &:= ((1+3!) + 5) + ((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times ((5! - 3) - 1)) & 9330 &:= (13-5) - (79 \times (7 - ((5^3) \times 1))) \\ 9293 &:= ((1+3!) \times ((5 \times 79) - 7)) - ((5!/3!) - 1) & 9331 &:= (((1+3!))! - 5) + ((7! + (9 - 753)) \times 1) \\ 9294 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (7! + ((9 - (75 - 3!)) \times 1)) & 9332 &:= ((1-3+5!) \times 79) + ((7+5) - (3-1)) \\ 9295 &:= (((1+3) + 5!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) - (5^{3+1}) & 9333 &:= (((1+3) + 57) \times 9) \times (7 + (5 \times (3-1))) \\ 9296 &:= (((((1 \times 3!)! / 5!))! + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times 3!))) - 1 & 9334 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) + 7 - 9)) \times ((75/3) + 1) \\ & & 9335 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5! \times (79 - 7)) + 5) - 31) \end{aligned}$$

- 9336** := $((1 - 3 + 5!) \times 79) + ((7 + 5) + 3 - 1)$
9337 := $(1^3 + (5! \times 79)) - ((7 + 5)^{3-1})$
9338 := $1 \times (((3! + 5) \times 7) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1))$
9339 := $(1 \times 3 + (5! \times 79)) - ((7 + 5)^{3-1})$
9340 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5! \times 7)) + ((97 \times 53) - 1)$
9341 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5! \times 7)) + ((97 \times 53) \times 1)$
9342 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! \times 7) + 9) \times (((7 - 5) \times 3!) - 1))$
9343 := $((1 \times (3579 + (7! + 5))) + 3!) - 1$
9344 := $1 \times ((35 \times 7) + (9 \times ((7!/5) + 3 \times 1)))$
9345 := $((1 \times 3) - ((5 + 7) \times 9)) \times ((7 - 5!) + (3 + 1)!)$
9346 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) \times 79) + ((7 + 5) \times (3 - 1))$
9347 := $((1 + (35/7) + 9) - (7 - 5)) \times (3! - 1)$
9348 := $(1^3 + ((5 + 7) + (9 \times 7))) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)$
9349 := $(1 + (3! \times (((5 + (7 - 9))!))) - ((7 + 5) - ((3! + 1)!))$
9350 := $(1^3) \times (((5! \times 79) - 7) - (5! + 3 \times 1))$
9351 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5^{7-9+7}) - (5 + 3 \times 1))$
9352 := $((1^3 \times 5!) + 79) \times (7 + (5!/3)) - 1$
9353 := $((1^3 \times 5!) + 79) \times (7 + (5!/3)) \times 1$
9354 := $((1^3 \times 5!) + 79) \times (7 + (5!/3)) + 1$
9355 := $(1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) - (7 + 5!) + (3 - 1)$
9356 := $(1^3) + (((5! \times 79) - (7!/(5!/3))) + 1)$
9357 := $(1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) - ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1))$
9358 := $(1^3) + (((5! \times 79) - ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1)))$
9359 := $1 - ((3 - 5) \times (7! + (9 - ((7 \times 53) - 1))))$
9360 := $((1 \times 35) - (7 + (9 - 7))) \times (5! \times (3 \times 1))$
9361 := $(1 + (3!^5)) + ((797 - 5) \times (3 - 1))$
9362 := $((1 - (3! \times 5!)) + 797) \times 5! + (3 - 1)$
9363 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (7! - ((9 - 7) - (5 + 3! \times 1)))$
9364 := $1 \times (((3 \times (5^{7-9+7})) - 5) - 3! \times 1)$
9365 := $1 + (((3 \times (5^{7-9+7})) - 5) - 3! \times 1)$
9366 := $(1 - (((3 - 5!) + (7 + 97)) \times 5!)) \times (3! \times 1)$
9367 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5^{7-9+7})) - 5 - (3 \times 1)$
9368 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + (((7 - 9) + 7)^5) \times (3 \times 1)$
9369 := $((1 - ((3 - 5) - 7)) \times (97 + (5! + 3!))) - 1$
9370 := $((1 - ((3 - 5) - 7)) \times (97 + (5! + 3!))) \times 1$
9371 := $((1 - ((3 - 5) - 7)) \times (97 + (5! + 3!))) + 1$
9372 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5! - 7!) + (9 + ((75 \times 3) \times 1)))$
9373 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9 + (7! - ((5 + 3!) - 1))$
9374 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! \times 7) + 97) \times (5 + (3! - 1)))$
9375 := $1 \times (3 \times ((5 \times (7 - (9 - 7))) \times (5^3 \times 1)))$
9376 := $1 + (3 \times ((5 \times (7 - (9 - 7))) \times (5^3 \times 1)))$
9377 := $((1 + 3!) - ((5! - 7!) - 9) + 7!) + (5! - 3!) + 1$
9378 := $(13 \times (5 + (7 \times (97 + 5)))) + 31$
9379 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5! + (7 + 9)) \times (75 - 3! \times 1))$
9380 := $((1 + ((3! + 5) + 7)) + 9) \times ((7!/(5 \times 3)) - 1)$
9381 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5^{7-9+7}) + (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
9382 := $((1^3 - (5 + 79)) \times (7 - 5!)) + (3 \times 1)$
9383 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1))))$
9384 := $(13 + (5 \times 79)) \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1)$
9385 := $(1^{3!}) + ((5! + (7 + 9)) \times (75 - 3! \times 1))$
9386 := $(1 + (3 \times 5!)) \times ((7!/(9 \times 7)) - (53 + 1))$
9387 := $(1 + 3!) \times (5 + (7 + 9 + (7! - (5! \times 31))))$
9388 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5! + 7)) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1)$
9389 := $135 - (7 - (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1))$
9390 := $135 - (7 - (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 + 1))$
9391 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) \times (9^{7-5})) - (3! - 1)$
9392 := $(1 \times ((35 + 7!) - 9)) + ((7! + (5 - 3!)) + 1)$
9393 := $((1 - 3) - 5) - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3!)) + 1)$
9394 := $((1 - 3) - 5) - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3!)) \times 1)$
9395 := $((1 - 3) - 5) - ((79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3!)) - 1)$
9396 := $(1 - (357 - 9753)) - 1$
9397 := $(1 - (357 - 9753)) \times 1$
9398 := $(1 - (357 - 9753)) + 1$
9399 := $((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7! - 9)) + (7 \times (5^{3+1}))$
9400 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
9401 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
9402 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5! \times 79) - (75 - 3)) - 1)$
9403 := $(135 + 7) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1)$
9404 := $135 + (7 + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 + 1))$
9405 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) - ((9 \times 75) \times (3 \times 1)))$
9406 := $(1^{35}) \times ((7! - 9) + (7 \times (5^{3+1})))$
9407 := $((1357 + 9) \times 7) - (5 \times 31)$
9408 := $((13 \times 5!) + (797 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)$
9409 := $(135 \times 7) + ((97 - 5)^{3-1})$
9410 := $((13 \times (5! - (7 + 9))) \times 7) - (53 + 1)$
9411 := $(1^{357}) + ((97^{5-3}) + 1)$

- 9412** := $(1 - (3! \times 57)) + (9753 \times 1)$
9413 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 + 7)) + (9 + 753) - 1$
9414 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) + (7! - 9))) + (7 \times (5^{3+1}))$
9415 := $(1 + (3! + (5! \times 79))) - ((75 - 3) \times 1)$
9416 := $((1^{3!} \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 + 7)) \times (5 + (3! \times 1))$
9417 := $((((1 \times 3!)! + 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times 3!))) \times 1$
9418 := $(1 - (3 - (5! \times 79))) - (7 + (53 \times 1))$
9419 := $((1 + 3)! \times (5 \times 79)) - (7 + 53) - 1$
9420 := $((13 - 5) + 7) \times (97 + 531)$
9421 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7) - ((9 \times 7) \times (5 - 31))$
9422 := $((1 + 3!) + (5 + 7975)) + (3! + 1)$
9423 := $(1 \times (((3! \times 5) + (7 \times 9)) + 7!)) + ((5 \times 3!) \times 1)$
9424 := $(13 \times 5) + (((7! / (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - 3)) - 1)$
9425 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (53 - 1))$
9426 := $1 - ((3! - (5 \times 7)) \times (975 / (3 \times 1)))$
9427 := $((1^{3!}) + ((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7))) \times (5 + (3! \times 1))$
9428 := $((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) - 5)^{3-1}))$
9429 := $((1^3 \times (5 + 7)) + 9) \times ((75 \times 3!) - 1)$
9430 := $(1 \times ((3! + 5!) \times 79)) + (7 - 531)$
9431 := $(1 - 3 + ((5! \times 79) + 7)) - (53 + 1)$
9432 := $(1 - 3 + (5! \times 79)) + ((7 - 53) \times 1)$
9433 := $((1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + 7) - (53 + 1)$
9434 := $(1^3 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 - (53 + 1))$
9435 := $((1^3 + (5! \times 79)) + 7) - (53 \times 1)$
9436 := $(1^3) \times (((5! \times 79) - (7! / 5!)) - (3 - 1))$
9437 := $(1^3) + (((5! \times 79) - (7! / 5!)) - (3 - 1))$
9438 := $((1 + 3) + (5! \times 79)) + (7 - (53 \times 1))$
9439 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! \times 79) + 7)) - (53 + 1)$
9440 := $((1 + (3 + (5! \times 79))) - 75) + 31$
9441 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! \times 79) - (7 + (5 + 31)))$
9442 := $((13 + 5!) \times ((79 + 7) - (5 \times 3))) - 1$
9443 := $((13 + 5!) \times ((79 + 7) - (5 \times 3))) \times 1$
9444 := $((13 + 5!) \times ((79 + 7) - (5 \times 3))) + 1$
9445 := $(13 + (5! \times 79)) - ((7 - 5) \times (3 + 1)!)$
9446 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) + ((7 - (5! / 3)) - 1)$
9447 := $(1 - 3 + (((5 + 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! + 3!))) - 1$
9448 := $((1 + 3!)! - 579) + ((7! - 53) \times 1)$
9449 := $((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 75)) / 3)) - 1$
9450 := $((1 \times 3) \times (((57 \times 9) + 7) + 5)) \times 3! \times 1$
9451 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times (7 + 9)) + 7531$
9452 := $(1 \times 3 + (((5 + 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! + 3!))) - 1$
9453 := $((1^{3!}) + (5! + (7 + 9))) \times (75 - 3! \times 1)$
9454 := $((((1 - 3 + 5)! \times (7! / (9 + 7))) \times 5) + (3 + 1))$
9455 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 - 9)) - (7 - 5!) \times 31$
9456 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + ((7 + 97) \times 5)))) \times (3! \times 1)$
9457 := $(1 + 3!) \times (5 + (((79 \times 7) + 5!) \times (3 - 1)))$
9458 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5! - 7) - (9 \times (7 + 531)))$
9459 := $1 \times 3 + ((5! \times 79) - ((7 + 5) \times (3 - 1)))$
9460 := $(1^3 + (5! \times 79)) - ((7! / 5!) / (3 - 1))$
9461 := $((1 + 3)! + (5! + 7)) \times 9 \times 7 - (53 - 1)$
9462 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) \times (7! - ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - 3! \times 1))$
9463 := $(1 - (3 - 57)) + ((97^{5-3}) - 1)$
9464 := $(13 \times (5 - ((7 - 9) - 7))) \times (53 - 1)$
9465 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! \times 79) - 7) - 5) - (3! + 1)$
9466 := $(1 - 3 \times 5) - (79 \times (((7 - 5!) - 3!) - 1))$
9467 := $((13 + (5! \times 79)) - (7 - 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
9468 := $((13 \times 5!) - ((7 - 97) / 5)) \times 3! \times 1$
9469 := $((1 + 3!)! + 5!) + ((7! - ((9 + 7) - 5)) - ((3! \times 1)!))$
9470 := $(1 - (((3^5) - 7!) \times (9 - 7))) - (5^3 \times 1)$
9471 := $(13 + (5! \times 79)) + ((7 - 5) - (3 + 1)!)!$
9472 := $((1 + (3! - 5))^7) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) - 3! \times 1)$
9473 := $(1 \times (3! - ((5 - 7!) + (9 - 7)))) + (5! \times 31)$
9474 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - 797)) - 5 \times 3! \times 1$
9475 := $1 \times 3 + ((5! \times 79) + ((7 - (5 \times 3)) \times 1))$
9476 := $((1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + 7) - (5 + 3! \times 1)$
9477 := $(1 - 3) + (((57 + 9) + 7) \times 5!) + (3! - 1)$
9478 := $(1 - (((3^5) - 7!) \times (9 - 7))) - ((5! - 3) \times 1)$
9479 := $((1 + 3) + (((5! \times 79) - 7) - 5)) + (3! + 1)$
9480 := $(1 \times 3)! \times ((5! \times 79) / ((7 + 5) / (3 - 1)))$
9481 := $13 + (((5! \times 79) + 7) + (5 - (3 + 1)!))$
9482 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 75)))) \times (3 - 1)$
9483 := $13 + ((5! \times 79) - ((7 + (5 - 3)) + 1))$
9484 := $(13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 - ((5 \times 3) + 1))$
9485 := $(13 + (5! \times 79)) + ((7 - (5 \times 3)) \times 1)$
9486 := $(1 - (3 - (5! \times 79))) + (7 + (5 / (3! - 1)))$
9487 := $(1 \times 3 + ((5! \times 79) + (7 - 5))) + (3 - 1)$
9488 := $((1 + 3!) + (((5 + 7!) + 9) - 7)) + (5! \times 31)$
9489 := $(1 \times ((3 + (5! \times 79)) + 7) + 5) - 3! \times 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 9490 &:= 13 \times (57 + ((9 \times 75) - (3 - 1))) \\ 9491 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 7) + (9 \times (7 \times ((5^3) + 1))) \\ 9492 &:= (1 + (((3 + (5! \times 79)) + 7) + 5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 9493 &:= 1 - ((35 - 7) \times ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) / (3 \times 1))) \\ 9494 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3))) - 1 \\ 9495 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3))) \times 1 \\ 9496 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\ 9497 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! \times 79)) + ((7 + 5) + 3 - 1) \\ 9498 &:= ((1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + 7) + (5 + 3! \times 1) \\ 9499 &:= (1 \times (((3 + (5! \times 79)) + 7) + 5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 9500 &:= (13 + ((57 + 9) \times 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 9501 &:= (1 \times (((3 + (5! \times 79)) + 7) + 5)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 9502 &:= (13 + (5! \times 79)) - (7 - ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 9503 &:= (13 + (((5! \times 79) + 7) + 5) - 3) + 1 \\ 9504 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 - 5 + 31)) \\ 9505 &:= 1 + ((3 \times (57 + 9)) \times ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 9506 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 \times 79)) + (7 - 5 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 9507 &:= (1^3) \times (((5! \times 79) + 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 9508 &:= (((1357 + 9) \times 7) - 53) - 1 \\ 9509 &:= (((1357 + 9) \times 7) - 53) \times 1 \\ 9510 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) - (53 - 1) \\ 9511 &:= 1 - (3 \times 5 \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) - (5^{3+1}))) \\ 9512 &:= ((1 - 3!) + 5797) + (5! \times 31) \\ 9513 &:= 1^{357} \times ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 31)) \\ 9514 &:= ((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) - ((7 - (5!/3)) - 1) \\ 9515 &:= (1 - 3) + (5797 + (5! \times 31)) \\ 9516 &:= (1 - (3^5 + 7)) + (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times 31))) \\ 9517 &:= 1 + ((357 + 9) \times ((75/3) + 1)) \\ 9518 &:= ((13 \times (5! - (7 + 9))) \times 7) + (53 + 1) \\ 9519 &:= (1^3 \times 57) \times ((9 + 7) + (5! + 31)) \\ 9520 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7 \times (9 \times 75))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 9521 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5!) + (7 + (9753 + 1)) \\ 9522 &:= ((13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 9523 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5! \times 79) + ((7!/5!) - 3! \times 1)) \\ 9524 &:= (((13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) - 3) - 1 \\ 9525 &:= (((13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) - 3) \times 1 \\ 9526 &:= (((13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) - 3) + 1 \\ 9527 &:= (1 \times ((3 + (5! \times 79)) + 75)) - 31 \\ 9528 &:= (1 + ((3 + (5! \times 79)) + 75)) - 31 \\ 9529 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 + (5! + (3 + 1)!))) \\ 9530 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! \times 79)) - (7 - (53 \times 1)) \\ 9531 &:= ((13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 9532 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5!) + (7! - (9 \times 75)))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 9533 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) - (5 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 9534 &:= ((13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 9535 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7)) \times (5 + 3)) - 1 \\ 9536 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 \times 79) - 7!) - 5!) - (3 \times 1) \\ 9537 &:= (1 - 3 + (((5! \times 79) + 7) + 53)) - 1 \\ 9538 &:= (1 - (3 - (5! \times 79))) + (7 + (53 \times 1)) \\ 9539 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! \times 79) + 7)) + (53 + 1) \\ 9540 &:= (1^3) \times ((5! \times 79) + (7 + (53 \times 1))) \\ 9541 &:= ((1^3 + (5! \times 79)) + 7) + (53 \times 1) \\ 9542 &:= (1^3) + ((5! \times 79) + (7 + (53 + 1))) \\ 9543 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! \times 79) + (7 + (53 \times 1))) \\ 9544 &:= ((1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 9545 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! + 79)) \times (7 + 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 9546 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5! \times 79) + (7 + (53 \times 1))) \\ 9547 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5! \times 79) + (7 + (53 + 1))) \\ 9548 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 7) + (97^{5-3}) - 1 \\ 9549 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 7) + (97^{5-3}) \times 1 \\ 9550 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 7) + (97^{5-3}) + 1 \\ 9551 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) + ((7 - (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 31)) \\ 9552 &:= (1 + (3 \times (57 + 9))) \times ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 9553 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5!)) + ((7! - (9 + 75)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 9554 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1) \\ 9555 &:= (((1 + 3!)!) - (57 \times 9)) + (7! - (5 + (3! + 1))) \\ 9556 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! \times 79) + (75 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 9557 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! \times 79) + (75 + 3)) + 1) \\ 9558 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5! - 7!) - 9) + (75 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 9559 &:= (1 + (3! + (5! \times 79))) + ((75 - 3) \times 1) \\ 9560 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 9561 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) - (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 9562 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 - (3 + 1)) \\ 9563 &:= (((1357 + 9) \times 7) + 5) - (3 + 1) \\ 9564 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 9565 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (5! + 7)) \times 9) \times 7 + (53 - 1) \\ 9566 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (7! / (9 \times 7))) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 9567 &:= (1 - ((3! + (57 \times 9)) - 7!)) + (5 + ((3! + 1)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9568 &:= ((13 - 5) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) \times (53 - 1) & 9606 &:= ((1^3 + (5! \times 79)) + (7!/(5!/3))) - 1 \\ 9569 &:= (1^{35}) \times (((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times 5!) - 31) & 9607 &:= ((1^3 + (5! \times 79)) + (7!/(5!/3))) \times 1 \\ 9570 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) + (5 + 3 \times 1) & 9608 &:= ((1^3 + (5! \times 79)) + (7!/(5!/3))) + 1 \\ 9571 &:= (((1357 + 9) \times 7) + 5) + (3 + 1) & 9609 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (7! + 975)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 9572 &:= (13 + (5! \times 79)) + ((75 + 3) + 1) & 9610 &:= ((1^3)^5) \times (((7!/(9 + 7)) - 5) \times 31) \\ 9573 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times 75) + (3!! - 1) & 9611 &:= ((1^3)^5) + (((7!/(9 + 7)) - 5) \times 31) \\ 9574 &:= ((1 - (3^5 + 7)) - ((9 - 7!) - 5)) \times (3 - 1) & 9612 &:= 1 + ((3!! \times (5 + 7)) + ((975 - 3) - 1)) \\ 9575 &:= (((1^3 + 5) + (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times (5! + 3!)) - 1 & 9613 &:= ((1 + (3!! + (5 \times (7 + 9)))) \times ((7 - 5) \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 9576 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 + 9)) + 7) \times ((5^3) + 1) & 9614 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) + (53 - 1) \\ 9577 &:= (((1^3 + 5) + (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times (5! + 3!)) + 1 & 9615 &:= (((1357 + 9) \times 7) + 53) \times 1 \\ 9578 &:= 1 + ((3! + (((5! + 7) - 9) \times 75)) + (3!! + 1)) & 9616 &:= (((1357 + 9) \times 7) + 53) + 1 \\ 9579 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - ((57 \times 9) - (7! + (5 + (3! + 1)))) & 9617 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times 5!)) + 31 \\ 9580 &:= (((1 + 3) + ((5! \times 79) + 7)) + 5!) - 31 & 9618 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 \times (7 - 975)) + 31) \\ 9581 &:= (((1357 + 9) \times 7) - 5) + (3 + 1)! & 9619 &:= (1357 \times (9 - (7 - 5))) + ((3! - 1)!) \\ 9582 &:= (((1 - ((3^5) - 7!) + 9)) + 7) - 5) \times (3 - 1) & 9620 &:= (1 + 357) + (((9 + (7 + 5))^3) + 1) \\ 9583 &:= (1 \times 35) - ((7 - ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times 31) & 9621 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (7! + 975)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 9584 &:= (((1 - ((3^5) - 7!) + 9)) \times (7 - 5)) + 3! \times 1 & 9622 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5! + 7!) - (9 - 7!)) + (5! + 31) \\ 9585 &:= (13 \times 5) - (((7!/9) - 7!) - ((5 + 3) - 1)!) & 9623 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 9586 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5! \times 7) - (9 - 7))) + (5! \times 31) & 9624 &:= ((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) + ((7 + 5)^{3-1}) \\ 9587 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - 5) - (3 + 1) & 9625 &:= (1^3 + (5! \times 79)) + ((7 + 5)^{3-1}) \\ 9588 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5! \times 79))) + ((7 \times 5) \times (3 \times 1)) & 9626 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + (5!/(3 + 1)) \\ 9589 &:= (1 \times ((3 + (5! \times 79)) + 75)) + 31 & 9627 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! \times 79)) + ((7 + 5)^{3-1}) \\ 9590 &:= (1 + ((3 + (5! \times 79)) + 75)) + 31 & 9628 &:= (((13 - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) + 5) - (3! + 1) \\ 9591 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) + (5 + (3 + 1)!) & 9629 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + (79 - 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 9592 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5!) + (7 + 9)) \times (75 - 3!))) + 1 & 9630 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5! - 7!) + (97 + 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 9593 &:= (1 + (3 \times (57^{9-7}))) - (5 \times 31) & 9631 &:= (1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + ((7 + 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 9594 &:= (1 - ((3! \times 5!) - 797)) \times ((5! + 3) \times 1) & 9632 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5! - 7!) + (97 + 5)) + 3) - 1 \\ 9595 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - (5 - (3 + 1)) & 9633 &:= (1 - ((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) - 7)) \times (5 - (3 + 1)!) \\ 9596 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) \times (5 - (3 + 1)) & 9634 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) \times (((79 - 7!) + 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 9597 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + (5 - (3 + 1)) & 9635 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) + (79 + (7 \times 5!))) \times (3! - 1) \\ 9598 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5! \times (7!/(9 \times 7)))) - ((5 + 3) \times 1) & 9636 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 + 79) + (75 \times 31)) \\ 9599 &:= (((1^3 \times 5)!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) + ((5 - 3!) \times 1) & 9637 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) \times (((7! - 97) - 5!) - (3! - 1))) \\ 9600 &:= ((13 + 579) + (7!/5)) \times (3! \times 1) & 9638 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) + ((7 + 9753) \times 1) \\ 9601 &:= (((1^3 \times 5)!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) - ((5 - 3!) \times 1) & 9639 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) + (7 + (9753 + 1)) \\ 9602 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + (5 + (7! - (((97 \times 5) - 3) + 1)))) & 9640 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) + 3!)) \times 1 \\ 9603 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 \times 7))) \times (97 \times (5 - (3 - 1))) & 9641 &:= 1 \times (((35 \times 7) - 9) + 75) \times 31 \\ 9604 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) - (((7 - 9) \times 7) + 5!))^{3-1} & 9642 &:= 1 + (((35 \times 7) - 9) + 75) \times 31 \\ 9605 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + 5) + (3 + 1) & 9643 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - ((5 \times 79) + (7!/5!))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 9606 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) + 7) + (9753 \times 1) & 9644 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) + 7) + (9753 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 9645** := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times ((7 \times 97) - (5 + 31))$
9646 := $((13 - 57) - 9) \times (7 \times (5 - 31))$
9647 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) + (((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times 5!) + 31)$
9648 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) + 97 \times (5 + 31)$
9649 := $(1 + (3!^5)) - ((79 - 7) \times (5 - 31))$
9650 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) \times (7 - (975 - (3 \times 1)))$
9651 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) \times ((7! - 97) - 5!) + (3! - 1)$
9652 := $13 - (((5! - 7) - 9753) + 1)$
9653 := $(13 - ((5! - 7) - 9753)) \times 1$
9654 := $(13 - ((5! - 7) - 9753)) + 1$
9655 := $((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7)) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 31)$
9656 := $((1 + 3!) - (5 \times (7 - (97 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1)$
9657 := $(1 \times 3! + (5 \times 7)) - ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3!! + 1)))$
9658 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 7)) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 31)$
9659 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 - (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times 3! \times 1))$
9660 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) \times (((7 - 9) + 7) - 5!)) \times (3! \times 1)$
9661 := $(1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times 9) + 7!)) + ((5 \times 3!!) + 1)$
9662 := $(1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 7)) \times (97 - 5!))) \times (3 - 1)$
9663 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times 79 - ((7 + 5!) + (3! \times 1))$
9664 := $((1 + 3!) - 5!) + (7 + (9753 \times 1))$
9665 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5 \times 79)) + (7! - ((5!/3!) \times 1))$
9666 := $((1^3 + 5!) \times 79) - (((7 - 5!) + 3!) \times 1)$
9667 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) \times 7) + (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times 31)))$
9668 := $(1 - (3 + (5! - (7! - (9 + 75)))))) \times (3 - 1)$
9669 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5! \times 79) - (7 \times (5 - 31)))$
9670 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! - (5 + 3!)))) \times 1)$
9671 := $(1 \times (3 + 5!)) + (7 \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times 31))$
9672 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times (((7 + (9 \times 7)) + 5) + 3) \times 1$
9673 := $(1 + (3 + 5)) + 7! + (((9 \times 7) + 5)^{3-1})$
9674 := $(1 - 3 \times 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - (753 + 1))$
9675 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times 79 - ((7 + 5!) - (3! \times 1))$
9676 := $(1 \times ((3^5) - 79)) \times (7 + (53 - 1))$
9677 := $((1^3 + 5!) \times 79) - (((7 - 5!) - 3!) + 1)$
9678 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 \times (7 + ((9 \times 7) \times 5)))) \times 3! \times 1$
9679 := $((1 + 3!)! - 5!) + ((79 + 7!) - ((5! \times 3) \times 1))$
9680 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 + 7!) - 97) - 5!) \times (3 - 1)$
9681 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5! - 7!) - 9) - (7!/5)) + ((3! \times 1))!$
9682 := $(1 - 3) - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times (7 + 531)))$
9683 := $(1 - 3) \times (5 \times 7) + (9753 \times 1)$
9684 := $(1 \times 3!) \times ((5 + (797 + 5)) \times (3 - 1))$
9685 := $(13 \times (57 + (97 - 5))) \times (3! - 1)$
9686 := $((1357 + 9) \times 7) + 5! + (3 + 1)$
9687 := $((135 + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) + 31$
9688 := $((1 + 3!) \times (579 - (7 - 5!))) \times (3 - 1)$
9689 := $((1 + 3) - ((5 \times 79) - 7!)) + (((5 + 3) - 1))!$
9690 := $(1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + ((7 \times 5!)/(3 + 1))$
9691 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5 \times 79) - (7! + (((5 - 3) + 1))))!$
9692 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 - 7) + (97 \times (5^{3-1})))$
9693 := $(1 - (3 + 57)) + (9753 - 1)$
9694 := $(135 \times (79 - 7)) + (5 - 31)$
9695 := $1 - ((3 + 57) - (9753 + 1))$
9696 := $((13 + (5 \times 7)) \times 97) + ((5 + 3 - 1))!$
9697 := $(1^3) - (57 - (9753 \times 1))$
9698 := $(1^3) - (57 - (9753 + 1))$
9699 := $(1 \times (3 + 5!)) + (((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times 5!) - (3 + 1))!$
9700 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + (9753 \times 1)$
9701 := $(1^3 \times ((5 + 7) + 97)) \times (5! - 31)$
9702 := $(1^3) + (((5 + 7) + 97) \times (5! - 31))$
9703 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 31$
9704 := $(1 + ((3 + 5!) \times 79)) - ((7 + 5) + 3 - 1)$
9705 := $((1 + 3!) - 5!) + (((7 + 97) - 5)^{3-1})$
9706 := $((1 - 3) \times ((5! - 7!) + 97)) + (5!/(3 - 1))$
9707 := $((1 + 3!)! + 5) + (7! - (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + (3! + 1))))$
9708 := $13 - (57 - (9753 - 1))$
9709 := $(13 + 5!) \times ((79 - (7 - 5 + 3)) - 1)$
9710 := $13 - ((57 - 9753) - 1)$
9711 := $((1 \times 3) - 5!) \times (7 - ((97 - 5) - (3 - 1)))$
9712 := $(1 - (((3^5) - 7!) \times (9 - 7))) + ((5! - 3) \times 1)$
9713 := $(1 - 35) - (7 - (9753 + 1))$
9714 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7))! \times (9^{7-5}) - 3! \times 1$
9715 := $(135 \times (79 - 7)) - (5!/(3 + 1))!$
9716 := $(1 - 3) \times (5! - ((7! - ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - (3 + 1)))$
9717 := $13 - (((5! + (7 \times 9)) - (7! - 5)) \times (3 - 1))$
9718 := $(1^3 \times (5! - 7)) \times (9 + (75 + 3 - 1))$
9719 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (7 \times ((975 + 3) - 1))$
9720 := $((1 + 3!) - 57) + (9753 \times 1)$
9721 := $(1 \times 3) - ((5 \times 7) - (9753 \times 1))$
9722 := $((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7) + (5! \times (3 \times 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 9723 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((57^{9-7}) - 5) - (3 \times 1)) & 9761 &:= (((1+3)! - (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7)))) \times (5-3)) - 1 \\ 9724 &:= ((1^3 - 5) \times 7) + (9753 - 1) & 9762 &:= (((1+3)! - (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7)))) \times (5-3)) \times 1 \\ 9725 &:= (((1^3 - 5) \times 7) + 9753) \times 1 & 9763 &:= (((1+3)! - (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7)))) \times (5-3)) + 1 \\ 9726 &:= ((13 \times (5-7)) + 9753) - 1 & 9764 &:= ((13 + (5-7)) + 9753) \times 1 \\ 9727 &:= (1 - 35) + (7 + (9753 + 1)) & 9765 &:= ((1^{357}) \times 9) \times (7 \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 9728 &:= ((13 \times (5-7)) + 9753) + 1 & 9766 &:= (1^3) \times (5 + (7 + (9753 + 1))) \\ 9729 &:= ((1-3)^5) + (7 + (9753 + 1)) & 9767 &:= (1^3) \times ((5! \times 79) + (7 \times ((5!/3) + 1))) \\ 9730 &:= (1-3) \times ((5! - ((7-9) + 7!)) + (53 \times 1)) & 9768 &:= (1^3) + ((5! \times 79) + (7 \times ((5!/3) + 1))) \\ 9731 &:= (1 \times ((3+5) \times 79)) + ((7+5) + 3 - 1) & 9769 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5+7) + (9753 + 1)) \\ 9732 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5! - (7-9))) + (75 \times ((3! - 1)!)) & 9770 &:= (1 \times ((3-5) + 7)) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 31) \\ 9733 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - (5 \times 7)) + (9 \times (7!/5))) - (3 + 1)! & 9771 &:= 1 + (((3-5) + 7) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 31)) \\ 9734 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (5+7)) + 9) + (7 \times (5 \times 31)) & 9772 &:= (1+3) + (((5 \times 79) + 7) + 5) \times (3+1)! \\ 9735 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times ((57^{9-7}) - 5)) + 3 \times 1) & 9773 &:= (((1+3)! + 5!) \times (7 \times ((9+7) - 5))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 9736 &:= 1 + ((3 \times ((57^{9-7}) - 5)) + 3 \times 1) & 9774 &:= 1 \times ((3! + ((5! \times (7 \times 9))/7)) \times (5+3+1)) \\ 9737 &:= (13 - 5!) - ((7-9) \times ((7! - 5!) + 3 - 1)) & 9775 &:= (((1+3)! + 5) - 7) + (9753 \times 1) \\ 9738 &:= (13+5) \times (((7!/9) + (7+5)) - 31) & 9776 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 5) + (7 + (9753 \times 1))) \\ 9739 &:= (1 + ((3+5) + 7!)) + ((9+7!) - ((5! \times 3) - 1)) & 9777 &:= ((1+3)! - 5) - (7 - (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\ 9740 &:= ((1+3)! \times 5!) - (((7-9) \times 7) - 5)^3 - 1 & 9778 &:= (13+5) + ((7+9753) \times 1) \\ 9741 &:= (1^3 - (5+7)) + (9753 - 1) & 9779 &:= (1+3)! - (5 - (7 + (9753 \times 1))) \\ 9742 &:= (1^3 - (5+7)) + (9753 \times 1) & 9780 &:= ((1+3) \times 5) \times (((7 + (97 \times 5)) - 3) \times 1) \\ 9743 &:= (1^3 - 5) - (7 - (9753 + 1)) & 9781 &:= (13 + (5! \times 79)) + ((7+5) \times (3+1)!) \\ 9744 &:= (1 + (3 + ((57^{9-7}) - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) & 9782 &:= (1 - ((3-5!) \times 79)) + (7 + 531) \\ 9745 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) - (7 - (9753 + 1)) & 9783 &:= (1+35) - (7 - (9753 + 1)) \\ 9746 &:= 1 + ((3 \times (57^{9-7})) - (5 - (3 \times 1))) & 9784 &:= (1+3) \times (5 - 79 + (7 \times ((5! \times 3) \times 1))) \\ 9747 &:= ((1+35) + (7! - (9+7!))) \times ((5! \times 3) + 1) & 9785 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5!))/7) \times ((97+5) - (3! + 1)) \\ 9748 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (57^{9-7}))) - (5 - (3! \times 1)) & 9786 &:= (1-3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9753 \times 1) \\ 9749 &:= ((1-3) \times 5) + ((7+9753) - 1) & 9787 &:= ((1-3) \times (5! - 7!)) - (9 + (75 - 31)) \\ 9750 &:= 13 \times (5 + ((797 - 53) + 1)) & 9788 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) \times 7) + (9753 \times 1) \\ 9751 &:= ((1+3!) \times (5! + 79)) \times ((7!/5!)/3! \times 1) & 9789 &:= (((1+3)! + 5) + 7) + (9753 \times 1) \\ 9752 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 + (9+7)) \times (53 \times 1)) & 9790 &:= (1^3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9753 + 1) \\ 9753 &:= ((1^3)^5 7) \times (9753 \times 1) & 9791 &:= ((1+3) \times ((5+7) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3))) - 1 \\ 9754 &:= ((1^3)^5 7) + (9753 \times 1) & 9792 &:= (1+3)! + (((5 \times 79) + 7) + 5) \times (3+1)! \\ 9755 &:= ((13 - 5) - (7 - 9753)) + 1 & 9793 &:= ((1+3) \times ((5+7) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3))) + 1 \\ 9756 &:= (((1+3!)/5) + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 531)))) & 9794 &:= (((1+3)! - (5! + (7 + (9+7)))) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 9757 &:= ((1-3) \times (5-7)) + (9753 \times 1) & 9795 &:= 1 + 35 + ((7+9753) - 1) \\ 9758 &:= ((1+3) - 5) \times (7 - (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) & 9796 &:= (1^{357} + (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 31 \\ 9759 &:= (((1^3)^5) \times 7) + (9753 - 1) & 9797 &:= 1 + 35 + (7 + (9753 + 1)) \\ 9760 &:= (1 + (35/7)) + (9753 + 1) & 9798 &:= 1 \times ((3! + (5! + (7+9))) \times (75 - 3! \times 1)) \\ & & 9799 &:= 1 + ((3! + (5! + (7+9))) \times (75 - 3! \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 9800** := $(1 - 3 + (((5 - 7) - 97)^{5-3})) + 1$
9801 := $(1 + (35 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 75) \times (3! + 1))$
9802 := $((1^{3!}) - (5! + ((79 - 7!) \times (5 - 3)))) - 1$
9803 := $((1^{3!}) - (5! + ((79 - 7!) \times (5 - 3)))) \times 1$
9804 := $(1 - 3) \times (5 - ((7! - 97) - (5 + 31)))$
9805 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! - 7!)) - (((97 + 5)/3) + 1)$
9806 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5! - (7! - (9 - 7))) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
9807 := $((1^3 + 5!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) + 5! + (3! + 1)$
9808 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! - 7!)) + (9 - ((7 \times 5) + 3! \times 1))$
9809 := $1 - (3 - ((57 + 9753) + 1))$
9810 := $(1^3 + 57) + (9753 - 1)$
9811 := $(1^3 + 57) + (9753 \times 1)$
9812 := $(1 \times (3 + 57)) + (9753 - 1)$
9813 := $((1 \times (3 + 57)) + 9753) \times 1$
9814 := $1 \times ((3 + 57) + (9753 + 1))$
9815 := $1 + ((3 + 57) + (9753 + 1))$
9816 := $((1 + 3!) + (5 + 7!)) + (((9 \times 75) \times 3!) \times 1)$
9817 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((57 + 9753) + 1)$
9818 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5! - 7!) + (9 + 7))) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1)$
9819 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times 97) - (5! + 3 - 1))$
9820 := $(1^3 \times (5 \times (7 + 975))) \times (3 - 1)$
9821 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! - ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + 53))) + 1$
9822 := $(1^3 + (5 \times (7 + 975))) \times (3 - 1)$
9823 := $((13 \times 5) - 7) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times 31)$
9824 := $((1 - 3!)^5 + 7!) + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times (3! - 1))$
9825 := $((1 + 3!) - (5! - 7!)) + ((9 + 7!) - (5! + 31))$
9826 := $((13 \times 5) + 7) + (9753 + 1)$
9827 := $((1 - (35 \times 7)) - (9 - 7!)) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!)$
9828 := $(1 - (((3! - 5) - 79) \times (7!/5!)) \times 3) - 1$
9829 := $(1 - (((3! - 5) - 79) \times (7!/5!)) \times 3) \times 1$
9830 := $((1 - (3^5)) + (7! - 9)) + (7! + (5 - (3 + 1)))$
9831 := $(1 + (3! - 5!)) \times ((7 \times 9) - (75 \times (3 - 1)))$
9832 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) - 7) + ((5! \times 3) - 1)$
9833 := $((1^3 \times (5! \times 79) - 7)) + (5! \times 3) \times 1$
9834 := $((1^3 \times (5! \times 79) - 7)) + (5! \times 3) + 1$
9835 := $(1 - (((3^5) - 7!) + 9) - 7!) + ((5 - (3 - 1)))!$
9836 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5 + (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 53) + 1)$
9837 := $(13 \times 5) + (7 + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times 31))$
9838 := $((1 \times (3! - (5! - 7!)) - (9 - 7))) - 5) \times (3 - 1)$
9839 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times 79) + ((7 + 5) + 31)$
9840 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5 + (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 53) - 1)$
9841 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7)))) + 5) - (3 + 1)$
9842 := $(13 + 5!) \times ((79 - (7 - 5 + 3)) \times 1)$
9843 := $((1 + 3!) - 5!) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
9844 := $(1 - (((3^5) - 7!) - 9) - 7!) - (5 - (3 - 1))$
9845 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5! + 79) - 7!)) - 5) - 31$
9846 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) + 7) + ((5! \times 3) - 1)$
9847 := $((1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) + 9) + 7!) - 5!) + ((3! - 1))!$
9848 := $((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) - 9) + ((7! - 5) + (3 + 1)!)$
9849 := $(1 - 3!) - (((5! - 7!) - 9) - 7!) + 5!) - (3! - 1))$
9850 := $(1 - (((3^5) - 7!) - 9) - 7!) + (5 - (3 - 1))$
9851 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) + 5)) + 3!) \times 1$
9852 := $(13 \times 579) + (75 \times 31)$
9853 := $13 + (5 \times ((7 + 9) \times ((7 + (5! - 3)) - 1)))$
9854 := $((1 + 35) - 7) \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5) + (3! - 1)$
9855 := $1 \times ((3!/(57 - 9)) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 - 1)))$
9856 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3+1}))$
9857 := $((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + 9) + 7!) + (5 \times (3 - 1))$
9858 := $(1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times (53 + 1))$
9859 := $((1 + 3!) - ((5! - 7!) + 9)) + ((7! - 5!) + 3 + 1)$
9860 := $((1 - 3!)^5 + 7!) - (9 \times 7)) + 5!) \times (3! - 1)$
9861 := $(1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + ((7 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
9862 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (7! + (9 + 7))) - (5! - ((3! + 1)))!$
9863 := $1^{35} \times ((7! - (97 + 5!)) + ((3! + 1)))!$
9864 := $(135 \times (79 - 7)) + (5! + (3 + 1)!)$
9865 := $((1 + 3!) - 5!) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
9866 := $(1 + ((357 \times 9) + 75)) \times 3) - 1$
9867 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times 7) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
9868 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5! - (7 + 9 + (7! - 5))) - (3 \times 1))$
9869 := $(1 \times 3 + (5! + (7 + 9))) \times (75 - (3 + 1))$
9870 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times 7) \times ((97 - 5) + 3 - 1)$
9871 := $((1 - (3! + (5 + 79))) + 7!) - (5! - ((3! + 1)))!$
9872 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (79 + (7 + 531))$
9873 := $(13 - ((5 - 7) \times ((9 + 7!) - 5!))) + (3 - 1)$
9874 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! - 7!)) + (((97 + 5)/3) \times 1)$
9875 := $((1 + 3) + ((5 + 7) + (9 \times 7))) \times ((5! + 3!) - 1)$
9876 := $(1^{3!}) \times ((5 - 7) \times ((97 + 5) - ((3! + 1)))!$
9877 := $(1^{3!}) + ((5 - 7) \times ((97 + 5) - ((3! + 1)))!$

- 9878** := $((13 + 5) \times 7) + (9753 - 1)$
9879 := $(13 + (5! - 7)) + (9753 \times 1)$
9880 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) \times (7! - ((97 + 5) - 3) + 1)$
9881 := $(1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 31)$
9882 := $135 - (7 - (9753 + 1))$
9883 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! + (7! - 9)) - 7!) \times (5! - 31))$
9884 := $(1 \times 3! + (5! - 7)) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 31)$
9885 := $((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (7! - 97)) + (5 - 3! \times 1)$
9886 := $1 \times ((3 - 5) \times ((7! - 97) \times (5 - (3! \times 1))))$
9887 := $1 + ((3 - 5) \times ((7! - 97) \times (5 - (3! \times 1))))$
9888 := $((1 + (3 - 5)) + (7 + 97)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!)$
9889 := $(1^{3!}) - ((5 + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5! \times (3! + 1))))$
9890 := $((1 + ((3! - 5) + 7!)) - 97) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1)$
9891 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times 7) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5! - 3)) \times 1)$
9892 := $((((1 \times 3) - 5) + (7! - (97 - 5))) \times (3 - 1)$
9893 := $(135 - 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 \times 31))$
9894 := $13 + (5! + (7 + (9753 + 1)))$
9895 := $(135 + 7) + (9753 \times 1)$
9896 := $((((1 + 3!))! - 5!) + (7! + ((9 - 75) + 3 - 1)))$
9897 := $((((1 + 3!))! - 5!) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - ((5^3) + 1))))$
9898 := $((1 - 3) \times (((5! + 7) - 9) - 7!)) + (53 + 1)$
9899 := $1 - (((35/7) + 9) \times ((7 + 5) - (3! - 1)))$
9900 := $((13 + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) - (53 + 1)$
9901 := $((((1 + (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) - 9) + (7! - 531))$
9902 := $(1 + 3)! + (5! - (7 - (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times 31))))))$
9903 := $(1 + (3 \times (57^{9-7}))) + (5 \times 31)$
9904 := $((((1 - 3!) - (5! - 7!)) + 9) + 7!) - (5! / (3 - 1))$
9905 := $(1 \times 3)! - (((5! - 7!) + 9) - 7!) + (53 - 1)$
9906 := $((13 \times 5!) + (79 + (7 + 5))) \times 3! \times 1$
9907 := $((((1 + 3!))! - ((5! + 79) - 7!)) - 5) + 31$
9908 := $((((1 + 3!))! - (5 + 7 + 9)) + (7! - 5!)) - 31$
9909 := $1 - (((3 + 5) - 7!) + 9) - (7! - (5 \times 31))$
9910 := $(13 \times (5! + (7 \times 9))) + 7531$
9911 := $((1 \times (3 \times (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) - 3!) - 1$
9912 := $((1 \times (3 \times (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) - 3!) \times 1$
9913 := $((1 \times (3 \times (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) - 3!) + 1$
9914 := $(1 + (3 \times (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) - (3! - 1)$
9915 := $(1 + (3 \times (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) - (3 + 1)$
9916 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5! + 7) + (9 - 7!)) - (53 + 1))$
9917 := $((((1 + 3) + 5!) \times 79) + ((7 + 5!) - (3! \times 1)))$
9918 := $(1 \times 3 + 57) + ((9 + (7! - 5!)) \times (3 - 1))$
9919 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 + (79 - 7!)) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1))$
9920 := $((((1 - (3 \times 5!) - 79)) + 7!) + 5!) + ((3! + 1)!)$
9921 := $(((((1 + 3!)) - 5!) + (7!/9)) + 7!) + (5! \times 31)$
9922 := $((((1 + 3!)! - 5!) + 7!) - (9 - (7! - (53 \times 1))))$
9923 := $1 \times (((3 \times 57) + 9753) - 1)$
9924 := $1 \times (((3 \times 57) + 9753) \times 1)$
9925 := $1 + (((3 \times 57) + 9753) \times 1)$
9926 := $(1 + ((3 \times 57) + 9753)) + 1$
9927 := $1 + (((3 + (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5))) \times 3) - 1)$
9928 := $((((13 + 5) \times 79) \times 7) + (5 - 31))$
9929 := $((((1 + 3) + 5!) \times 79) + ((7 + 5!) + (3! \times 1)))$
9930 := $(1 - 3) \times (5 - (7! - ((9 + 7) + (53 + 1))))$
9931 := $(((((1 - 3)^5) + 7!) + ((9 + 7!) - 5!)) - 3! \times 1$
9932 := $(1^3) \times ((5! \times 79) - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1)))$
9933 := $(1^3) + ((5! \times 79) - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1)))$
9934 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((7 + 9 + 7!) - (5! - 31))$
9935 := $((1 + 3!))! + ((5 + (7! - 97)) - (53 \times 1))$
9936 := $(1 \times 3 + (57 + 9)) \times ((7 + 5)^{3-1})$
9937 := $((13 \times (5 - (7 + 9))) + 7!) + (((5 + 3) - 1)!)$
9938 := $((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7! - 9)) + ((7! - (5^3)) - 1)$
9939 := $((((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (7! - 97)) + (53 \times 1))$
9940 := $((((1 - 3 + 5))! + (7! + 9)) + (7! - (5 \times 31)))$
9941 := $1 + (((3 + (5 + (7 \times 9))) \times 7) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
9942 := $1 \times ((3 \times (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5))) + (3 + 1)!)$
9943 := $((((1 - 3!) - ((5! - 7!) - 9)) + 7!) - ((5! / 3!) + 1)$
9944 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5 + 79) - ((7! + (5 \times 3)) + 1))$
9945 := $13 \times ((5 \times 79) + ((7 \times 53) - 1))$
9946 := $((((1 + 3!) - 5!) + (7! - (9 + 7))) - (5 - ((3! + 1)!))$
9947 := $((1^{35}) \times (7! - 9)) + ((7! - (5^3)) + 1)$
9948 := $((1 + (3! - (5! - 7!))) - 9) + (7! - (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
9949 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7! - ((9 - 7!) + 5!)) + (3! - 1))$
9950 := $(((((1 + 3!))! - 5!) + (7! + (9 - 7))) - ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
9951 := $(1 \times ((35/7)! - 9)) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 - 1))$
9952 := $((1 + (3 \times 5!)) + 7) - ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3! - 1)))$
9953 := $((((1 - (3 + (5! - 7!))) \times (9 - 7)) + 5!) - (3 \times 1))$
9954 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) / 5) \times (3! \times 1)$
9955 := $((1 + 3!)) + 5! + (7 \times ((97 + 5!) \times (3! \times 1)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9956 &:= (1-3) \times ((5-7!) - (9 - ((7 \times 5) + 31))) & 9980 &:= (((13+5) \times 79) \times 7) - (5-31) \\
 9957 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) + (((79 \times (7!/5!)) \times 3) + 1) & 9981 &:= ((1+3) \times 57) + (9753 \times 1) \\
 9958 &:= (((13+57) - 9) - 7!) \times (5 - (3! + 1)) & 9982 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3! \times 1 \\
 9959 &:= (((1+3!))! - (5 - (7 - (9 \times 7)))) \times (5 - 3) + 1 & 9983 &:= (((1+3) \times (5 + 797)) + 5!) \times 3 - 1 \\
 9960 &:= (1 + ((3 + (5 + (7 \times 9))) \times 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)) & 9984 &:= ((1+3) + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9+7)^{5-3 \times 1}) \\
 9961 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) + (7! - 9)) + (7! + ((5+3) - 1)) & 9985 &:= ((1^{3!}) - (5! - 7!)) + (9 + (7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\
 9962 &:= (1-3) \times (5! - (7! + ((97-5) - 31))) & 9986 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9+75) - (3-1))) \\
 9963 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) \times (((7+9) - 7) \times 5) - (3+1) & 9987 &:= ((1+3!) - (((5! - 7!) + (9-7!)) - (5 \times 3!))) - 1 \\
 9964 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - (7! + (5!/(3+1)!))) & 9988 &:= ((1-3!) - ((5! - 7!) - 9)) + (7! + (5!/(3! - 1))) \\
 9965 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5! \times ((7-9) - 75)) - 3!!) + 1) & 9989 &:= (((1+3!))! - 5!) + (((7! - 97) + 5!) + (3! \times 1)) \\
 9966 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5! \times ((7-9) - 75)) - 3!!) \times 1) & 9990 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + (((5! - (7-9)) \times 75) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\
 9967 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + 9)) + 7!) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!) & 9991 &:= ((1-3!) + 5!) + ((7! - (97+5)) \times (3-1)) \\
 9968 &:= (1+3!) \times ((5! - (7+9)) + (7! - (5! \times 31))) & 9992 &:= 1 + (((3+5!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) + (5! + 31)) \\
 9969 &:= ((1-3) - 5) - ((7-9) \times ((7! - 53) + 1)) & 9993 &:= 1 - (((3 + (5 \times (7+9))) - 7!) + (5 - ((3! + 1)!))) \\
 9970 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - 3! \times 1 & 9994 &:= ((1 \times (3 + (5! \times 7))) \times ((9+7) - 5)) + (3!! + 1) \\
 9971 &:= 13 \times ((5 \times 79) + ((7 \times 53) + 1)) & 9995 &:= 1 - ((35 - (7! - 9)) + (7 \times (5 - (3! - 1)))) \\
 9972 &:= ((1+3!) + 5) \times (79 + (753 - 1)) & 9996 &:= ((1+3!) + 5) \times ((797+5) + 31) \\
 9973 &:= 13 + (5! \times ((79 + (7-5+3)) - 1)) & 9997 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + 9753) - 1 \\
 9974 &:= (1 \times (3+5)) + (((7! + (9 \times 7)) - 5!) \times (3-1)) & 9998 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 7)) + (9753 \times 1) \\
 9975 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) + (7! - ((9+7) + 5!))) + ((3! + 1)!) & 9999 &:= 1 + ((35 \times 7) + (9753 \times 1)) \\
 9976 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) \times ((9^{7-5}) + (3! - 1)) & 10000 &:= (1+3!)! - 5! + 7! + 9 + 7 \times 5 - 3 - 1 \\
 9977 &:= ((1 \times (3+5)) + (7! + 9)) + (7! - (5 \times (3+1)!)) \\
 9978 &:= ((1-3+5)!) - ((7-9) \times (7! - (53+1))) \\
 9979 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5-7!) + 97) + (5 - ((3! + 1)!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

2.6 Numbers From 10001 to 12000

$$\begin{aligned}
 10001 &:= (1+3!)! - 5! + 7! + 9 + 7 \times 5 - 3 \times 1 & 10013 &:= 1 - ((3!!/5!) - (((7! - 9) + (7! - 53)) \times 1)) \\
 10002 &:= ((1-35) + 7!) + (9 + (7! - (53 \times 1))) & 10014 &:= 1 - ((3!!/5!) - (((7! - 9) + (7! - 53)) + 1)) \\
 10003 &:= ((1+3!) + 5) - (((7-9) \times 7!) + (5! - 31)) & 10015 &:= 1 \times (((3-5) + (7! - 9)) + (7! - (53+1))) \\
 10004 &:= ((1+3!) - 5) \times (7 - ((9-7!) + (5+31))) & 10016 &:= 1 + (((3-5) + (7! - 9)) + (7! - (53+1))) \\
 10005 &:= (1+3^5) + (7 + (9753+1)) & 10017 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (57+9)) + (7! \times ((5-3) \times 1)) \\
 10006 &:= ((1+35) \times 7) + (9753+1) & 10018 &:= ((1-3!) + (((5+7!) - 9) + 7!)) - (53 \times 1) \\
 10007 &:= ((1^3)^5) \times (7 + ((9+7) \times (5^{3+1}))) & 10019 &:= ((13-5) - 79) + ((7! + 5) \times (3-1)) \\
 10008 &:= ((13+5) \times (79 \times 7)) + (53+1) & 10020 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times ((7 + (9-7!)) + ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\
 10009 &:= ((13 \times 5) + ((7! - 9) + ((7! - 5!) - 3!))) - 1 & 10021 &:= ((1 \times (3! + ((5! + 7) - 9))) \times 75) + (3!! + 1) \\
 10010 &:= (((1-3) - (5-7!)) - (9 - (7! - 53))) - 1 & 10022 &:= ((1^3 \times ((5+7!) - 9)) + 7!) - (53+1) \\
 10011 &:= (((1-3) - (5-7!)) - (9 - (7! - 53))) \times 1 & 10023 &:= (1 \times (3!!/5!)) + (((7! - 9) + (7! - 53)) - 1) \\
 10012 &:= (((1-3) - (5-7!)) - (9 - (7! - 53))) + 1 & 10024 &:= (1 - ((3+5) + ((7+9) - (7! - 5)))) \times (3-1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10025 &:= (1 + (3!!/5!)) + (((7! - 9) + (7! - 53)) \times 1) \\10026 &:= (13 + 5) \times (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\10027 &:= ((13 - 5) + (7! - 9)) + (7! - (53 - 1)) \\10028 &:= (1 + 3) - (57 + (9 - ((7! + 5) \times (3 - 1)))) \\10029 &:= 1 - (((35 - 7!) - 9) - ((7! + 5) - 31)) \\10030 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (57 + 9)) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\10031 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5)^{7+9-7-5}) + 31 \\10032 &:= (13 - ((5 - (79 + 7)) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)! \\10033 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! + ((9 \times 7)^{5-3})) \times 1) \\10034 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) - (7! - 9))) - 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\10035 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7! + 9)) + ((7! - 53) - 1) \\10036 &:= ((13 - 5) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) - 53)) + 1 \\10037 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7! + 9)) + ((7! - 53) + 1) \\10038 &:= (((1 + 3!))! - (5 - (79 + 7!))) - ((5! - 3) - 1) \\10039 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 5) + (7! - 9))) + (7! - (5 \times 3! \times 1)) \\10040 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times 7)) - ((9 - 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\10041 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (7! - 9)) - (7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1 \\10042 &:= (((1^3)^5!) + 7!) \times (9 - 7) - (5!/(3 \times 1)) \\10043 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (((7 \times 9) \times 7) + (5! - 3))) - 1 \\10044 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - 5 - 31 \\10045 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (((7 \times 9) \times 7) + (5! - 3))) + 1 \\10046 &:= (1 - 35) + ((7 + 9) \times (7!/(5 + 3 \times 1))) \\10047 &:= ((1 - (35 - 7!)) + ((9 + 7!) - (5 + 3))) \times 1 \\10048 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 - 7!) + ((9 \times 7) - (53 - 1))) \\10049 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7! - 9)) + ((7! - (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\10050 &:= ((1^{35}) - ((7 + 9) - 7!)) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\10051 &:= 1 + (3! + (((((5 - 7) + 9))! + 7!) - (5 + 31))) \\10052 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) - ((7 - 9) \times (7 \times ((5! \times 3!) - 1))) \\10053 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) + (9 - (7! + (53 - 1))) \\10054 &:= 1 - (((35 - (7! + (9 + 7!))) + 5) - 3) - 1 \\10055 &:= (1 - (3! - ((5 - 7) \times (9 - 7!)))) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\10056 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (((5 \times (7!/(9 \times 7))) - 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\10057 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7! - 9) + (7! \times (5 - (3 + 1)))) \\10058 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) + (7! - 9)) + (7! + (5 - (3 + 1))) \\10059 &:= (((1^{3!}) + (5 + 7!)) + 9) + (7! - (5 + 31)) \\10060 &:= 1 \times 3 + (57 + ((9 + 7) \times (5^{3+1}))) \\10061 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 79) + 7!) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\10062 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + (7! - (9 + 7))) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\10063 &:= ((1 - 357) + 9) \times (7 - (5 + 31))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10064 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) - ((7 - 9) \times ((7! + 53) \times 1)) \\10065 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5) + (7! + (97 - 5!))) \times (3 - 1)) \\10066 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + ((5 - 7) \times (9 - 7!))) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\10067 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5)) + ((7! - 9) + 7!)) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\10068 &:= (((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - (5 + 3 \times 1) \\10069 &:= (1 + 3)! - (((5 - (7! \times (9 - 7))) + (5 \times 3!)) \times 1) \\10070 &:= (((1^3 \times 5))! + (7 + (9 \times 7))) \times (53 \times 1) \\10071 &:= ((1 + ((3 + 5) + 7!)) - 9) + (7! - (5 + 3 + 1)) \\10072 &:= ((1 + 3)! - ((5! - 7!) - (97 - 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\10073 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 - (7 + 9))) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) \times 1) \\10074 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 - 7)) + ((9 + 75) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\10075 &:= (1 + 35) - (((7 - 9) \times 7!) + ((5!/3) + 1)) \\10076 &:= ((1 \times 3! + 5) - (7! + 9)) \times (((7 - 5) - 3) - 1) \\10077 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) + 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\10078 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! + (3 + 1)!)) \\10079 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7! - 9)) + ((7! + (5 + 3)) \times 1) \\10080 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7! - (9 - 7!))) + (5 - 31) \\10081 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \\10082 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times 5! \times 3)) - 1 \\10083 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times 5! \times 3)) \times 1 \\10084 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times 5! \times 3)) + 1 \\10085 &:= (((1 + (3 - 5)) + 7!) - 9) + (7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\10086 &:= ((1 + (((3 + 5) + 7!) \times (9 - 7))) - 5) - (3! \times 1) \\10087 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) - ((7 - 9) \times (7 + ((5 + 3) - 1)!)) \\10088 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) - ((7! \times (9 - 7)) \times (5 - 3!))) - 1 \\10089 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) - ((7! \times (9 - 7)) \times (5 - 3!))) \times 1 \\10090 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) - ((7! \times (9 - 7)) \times (5 - 3!))) + 1 \\10091 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) - (97 \times (53 - 1)) \\10092 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7! + 9)) + (7! + ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\10093 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7! + 9)) + (7! + ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\10094 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 57)) + (9753 - 1) \\10095 &:= 1 + ((3! \times 57) + (9753 - 1)) \\10096 &:= 1 + ((3! \times 57) + (9753 \times 1)) \\10097 &:= (1 \times 35) - ((7! - 9) \times (7 - ((5 + 3) + 1))) \\10098 &:= (1 + 35) - ((7! - 9) \times (7 - ((5 + 3) + 1))) \\10099 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7!) - (9 - (7! + (5 \times 3! \times 1))) \\10100 &:= ((1 - 35) + ((7! + 9) + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\10101 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) - ((7 - 9) \times (7! + 5))) - (3 + 1) \\10102 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - (5 \times 3!))) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10103 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - (7 - (9 + (75 \times 31))) \\ 10104 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7!) + (9 + 7!)) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 10105 &:= (1 + (35 + 7)) \times ((9 + (75 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 10106 &:= (((1^{35} \times 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - 5) + 31 \\ 10107 &:= (1^{35}) + (((7! \times (9 - 7)) - 5) + 31) \\ 10108 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times (7! + ((9 - 7) + ((5 + 3!) + 1))) \\ 10109 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) - ((7 - 9) \times (7! - ((5 - 3) - 1))) \\ 10110 &:= (1 + 357) + (9753 - 1) \\ 10111 &:= (1 \times 357) + (9753 + 1) \\ 10112 &:= (1 + 357) + (9753 + 1) \\ 10113 &:= (((1 + (3! - 5)) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\ 10114 &:= ((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) - ((5! + 3) + 1) \\ 10115 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + ((5! + 7!) - ((97 - 5) - (3! + 1)))) \\ 10116 &:= (((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) - 5!) - (3 - 1) \\ 10117 &:= (((1 + 35) + (7! + (9 + 7!))) - 5) - (3 \times 1) \\ 10118 &:= 1 + ((35 - (((7 - 9) \times 7!) - 5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 10119 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5 + 7!)) \times (9 - 7)) - (5!/3!) + 1 \\ 10120 &:= (((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) - 5!) + (3 - 1) \\ 10121 &:= (((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) - 5!) + (3 \times 1) \\ 10122 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5! + 79) + (7!/5!))) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 10123 &:= (((1 + 35) + (7! + (9 + 7!))) - 5) + (3 \times 1) \\ 10124 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (((5 + 7!) - 9) + 7!)) + (53 \times 1) \\ 10125 &:= (1 \times (3 + ((5 \times 79) + 7))) \times (5 \times (3! - 1)) \\ 10126 &:= (((1 - 3 \times 5) \times (7 - 9)) + (7! - 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 10127 &:= ((1 + 35) + (7! + (9 + 7!))) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 10128 &:= (1 + (3! \times (5 \times 7))) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 10129 &:= (13 \times 5) + (((7! - 9) + ((7! - 5) - 3)) + 1) \\ 10130 &:= ((1^3 \times ((5 + 7!) - 9)) + 7!) + (53 + 1) \\ 10131 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (((7! + (9 + 7!)) + 5) + 3)) - 1 \\ 10132 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (((7! + (9 + 7!)) + 5) + 3)) \times 1 \\ 10133 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (((7! + (9 + 7!)) + 5) + 3)) + 1 \\ 10134 &:= ((1 \times 35) + ((7! + (9 + 7!)) + 5)) + (3! - 1) \\ 10135 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((7! - 9) + (7! + 5)) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 10136 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! - 7) \times (9 + 7)) - (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 10137 &:= ((13 + (5 \times 7)) + 9) + ((7 - 5) \times ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 10138 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)! - ((7 - 9) \times 7!)) + (53 - 1)) \\ 10139 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - ((5 + 3!) \times 1) \\ 10140 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (5 - 7)) \times (9 + ((7!/5) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 10141 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) + (53 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10142 &:= ((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) - (5! - (3 + 1)!) \\ 10143 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - 5) + ((7! + (9 + 7)) + 53)) - 1 \\ 10144 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7!) + (9 + 7!)) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 10145 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - 5) + ((7! + (9 + 7)) + 53)) + 1 \\ 10146 &:= ((1^3 \times 57) \times (9 - 7)) \times (5! - 31) \\ 10147 &:= ((13 \times 5) - (7 - 9)) + ((7 - 5) \times ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 10148 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) - 9) + (7 \times 5) \times (3 - 1) \\ 10149 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7!) + 9)) + (7! + (53 - 1)) \\ 10150 &:= ((1 \times 35) + 7!) + (9 + ((7! - 5) + 31)) \\ 10151 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((7! + 9) + (7! - ((5 - 3) + 1))) \\ 10152 &:= (((1 + 3)^5 + 7) + 97) \times (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 10153 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 57) - (9 - ((7! \times (5 - 3)) + 1)) \\ 10154 &:= (1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 7) - 9) + (7! + 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 10155 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 \times ((7 + (9 \times 75)) - (3! - 1))) \\ 10156 &:= (1 + (35 - ((7 - 9) \times 7!))) + ((5!/3) \times 1) \\ 10157 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 \times (7 + 9)))) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) - 1) \\ 10158 &:= (((1 \times 3 + 5!) + 7!) + 9) + (7! - (53 + 1)) \\ 10159 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5) + (79 + 7!)) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!) \\ 10160 &:= ((1 \times ((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) - 7)) \times 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 10161 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - (5! - (79 + 7!))) + (5! + 3)) - 1 \\ 10162 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - (5! - (79 + 7!))) + (5! + 3)) \times 1 \\ 10163 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 5) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + 53)) - 1 \\ 10164 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 5) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + 53)) \times 1 \\ 10165 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 5) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + 53)) + 1 \\ 10166 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + 5) - (3 + 1)! \\ 10167 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)) + 79) \times (7 + (5! - 3))) - 1 \\ 10168 &:= (((13 \times 5) - 7) - (9 - (7! - 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 10169 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)) + 79) \times (7 + (5! - 3))) + 1 \\ 10170 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5! - 7) \times (9 - 7)) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 10171 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 57) + ((9 + 7) \times (5^{3+1})) \\ 10172 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - ((5 - (7! - 9)) - (75 + 31))) \\ 10173 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5 - 7!) - ((97 - 5) + ((3! + 1)!))) \\ 10174 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((57 - 9) + (7! - 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 10175 &:= (((13 \times 5!) \times 7) + (9 - 753)) - 1 \\ 10176 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5! - (79 - 7))) \times (53 \times 1) \\ 10177 &:= ((13 \times 5!) \times 7) + ((9 - 753) + 1) \\ 10178 &:= (((1 - 3) \times ((5! - 7!) - 97)) + 5!) + (3 + 1)! \\ 10179 &:= (1 - (35 - (7! + 9))) + ((7! + 5!) + 3 + 1) \\ 10180 &:= (1 - (35 - (7! + 9))) + ((7! + (5! + 3!)) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10181 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! - (3! + 1))) \\ 10182 &:= (13 + ((5! \times (79 + 7)) - 5!)) - 31 \\ 10183 &:= (((((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times 7) \times 97) + 5) - (3! + 1) \\ 10184 &:= ((1 + (3 \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97))) - 5) + (3 \times 1) \\ 10185 &:= (((((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times 7) \times 97) + 5) - (3! - 1) \\ 10186 &:= (((13 + 5) - 7) - 9) \times (7! + (53 \times 1)) \\ 10187 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! \times 79) - 7) - (5 - 3!)) + 1) \\ 10188 &:= ((1^{3!}) - 5) + (7 \times (((97 \times 5) \times 3) + 1)) \\ 10189 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5 \times (7 \times 97)) + 5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 10190 &:= (1 - 3!) - (5 + (((7 - 97) + 5) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 10191 &:= (1 + (3 + (5! \times 79))) - ((7 + 5) - (3! - 1)) \\ 10192 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7!) - (((9 - 7!) - 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 10193 &:= (((((1 \times 3!)/5!) + 7!) - 9) + (7! + (5! - (3 + 1)))) \\ 10194 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + 5) + (3 + 1) \\ 10195 &:= (((((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times 7) \times 97) + 5) + (3! - 1) \\ 10196 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 + (7 - 5!)))) + (3 + 1) \\ 10197 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 57) - 9) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 10198 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + (5! - (3 - 1))) \\ 10199 &:= 135 + ((7! - (9 + 7)) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!)) \\ 10200 &:= ((1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) + 9) \times 75) - 3) - 1 \\ 10201 &:= ((1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) + 9) \times 75) - 3) \times 1 \\ 10202 &:= ((1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) + 9) \times 75) - 3) + 1 \\ 10203 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 \times (7 - 9)) - 75) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 10204 &:= (1^3) \times (((5! + (7 + 9)) \times 75) + 3 + 1) \\ 10205 &:= (1^3) + (((5! + (7 + 9)) \times 75) + 3 + 1) \\ 10206 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5! \times 79)) + (((7 + 5)/(3 - 1)))! \\ 10207 &:= (135 \times 7) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 + 1) \\ 10208 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (5 - (79 + (7! - 5)))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 10209 &:= (13 - 5!) + (((7 - 9) + (7! + 5!)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 10210 &:= (((((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times 7) \times 97) + (5 \times (3! - 1)) \\ 10211 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times 79)) + (((7 + 5) + 3!) - 1) \\ 10212 &:= ((135 + (7! + (9 - 7))) - 5) + ((3! + 1)! \\ 10213 &:= (135 + (7 - 9)) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) \times 1) \\ 10214 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + 5) + (3 + 1)! \\ 10215 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 5) + ((7 \times (97 \times (5 \times 3))) + 1) \\ 10216 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 + (7 - 5!)))) + (3 + 1)! \\ 10217 &:= (((1^{3!}) + ((5 + 7!) \times (9 - 7))) + 5!) + (3! \times 1) \\ 10218 &:= (1 - (3! + ((5 \times 79) - 7))) \times (5 - 31) \\ 10219 &:= ((13 + (5! + 7!)) - 9) + (7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10220 &:= 1 \times ((35 \times (7 - (9 - 75))) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 10221 &:= 1 + ((35 \times (7 - (9 - 75))) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 10222 &:= (135 - 7!) - (9 - (((7! + 5) \times 3) + 1)) \\ 10223 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + (9 + 7!)) + (5! + (3! \times 1)) \\ 10224 &:= ((13 \times 5) + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 10225 &:= 135 + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\ 10226 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5! + (7! \times (9 - 7)))) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 10227 &:= 1 + (35 + (((7! - 9) + 7!) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!))) \\ 10228 &:= ((1 + ((3! + 5) - 7))!) + ((9 + (7! + 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 10229 &:= 135 + (((7! + (9 - 7)) + 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 10230 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 \times (7 + (9 \times 75))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 10231 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + (5! + 31) \\ 10232 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5) \times 7!)) + ((97 + 53) + 1) \\ 10233 &:= ((1^{3!}) + (5! \times 79)) + (753 - 1) \\ 10234 &:= ((1 - (((3 - 5) \times 7!) + 9)) + 7) + (5 \times 31) \\ 10235 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5) \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 - 3! \times 1))) \\ 10236 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5 - ((7 - 9)^7))) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1) \\ 10237 &:= (((((1 + 3!)/5) + 7) \times 9) + (7! + (5! - 31))) \\ 10238 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 - (7! + 97))) + (5 - 31) \\ 10239 &:= (((1 + 3!)/5) + (5! + (79 + 7!))) - ((5!/3) \times 1) \\ 10240 &:= (((((1 + 3!)/5) + (5! + (79 + 7!))) - (5!/3)) + 1) \\ 10241 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5)^7) \times ((9 + 75) - (3 + 1))) \\ 10242 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times 9) \times 7)) - 531 \\ 10243 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((57 \times 9) \times 7))) - 531 \\ 10244 &:= (1^{35}) \times (((7! + 9) + 7!) + 5 \times 31) \\ 10245 &:= 1 \times ((35 \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5^{3+1}))) \\ 10246 &:= 1 + ((35 \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5^{3+1}))) \\ 10247 &:= 13 + ((5! \times 79) + (753 + 1)) \\ 10248 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) \times ((7 \times (9 + (7 - 5!))) - (3 + 1)) \\ 10249 &:= (((1 + 3!)/5) + 5!) + ((79 + 7!) - (5!/(3 + 1))) \\ 10250 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)! + (7! + 9)) + (7! + 5 \times 31) \\ 10251 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! - (97 - 5))/(3 - 1)) \\ 10252 &:= (135 + 797) \times (5 + 3! \times 1) \\ 10253 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5) + ((7! + (9^{7-5})) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 10254 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5) \times 7!)) - (9 + (7 \times (5 - 31))) \\ 10255 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 \times 97) + 5)) - (3! - 1) \\ 10256 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 \times 97) + 5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 10257 &:= 1 \times ((35 + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) - (5! + 31))) \\ 10258 &:= 1 + ((35 + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) - (5! + 31))) \end{aligned}$$

- 10259** := $((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times 79 + ((75 \times 3) + 1)$
10260 := $135 \times (7 + (9 + (7 + (53 \times 1))))$
10261 := $((1 + (3 \times 57)) + 9) + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
10262 := $(1 + (3 \times 5 \times (7 + (9 \times 75)))) + 31$
10263 := $(1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1))$
10264 := $((1 \times 3! + 5) + (7! + (9^{7-5}))) \times (3 - 1)$
10265 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + 7! + (9 + (7! + (53 - 1)))$
10266 := $(1 - ((3 \times 5) + (79 + 7!))) \times (5 - (3! + 1))$
10267 := $((1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((7! + 97) - 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
10268 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5! - 7!)) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - (3! + 1))$
10269 := $(1 + ((3 \times 57) - 9)) \times 7 \times (5 + 3 + 1)$
10270 := $(1^3 + ((5! + 7) + 9)) \times 75 - (3! - 1)$
10271 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5 - (79 + 7!))) + ((5! - 3) \times 1)$
10272 := $(135 + 79) \times ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1))$
10273 := $1 + (3! + ((5! \times (79 + 7)) - (53 + 1)))$
10274 := $(1 \times 3!) + (5! + (7! + ((9 \times 7) + 5) + ((3! + 1)!)))$
10275 := $(1 - 3!) \times (5 \times (((7! / (9 + 7)) - 5) - (3!! + 1)))$
10276 := $((1 + 35) + 7!) + (9 + 7!) + 5! + 31$
10277 := $(13 \times (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 - 1))$
10278 := $((1 - (3! - 5!)) + 7!) - (9 + 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
10279 := $((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) + (5! / 3) + 1$
10280 := $(1^3 + ((5! + 7) + 9)) \times 75 + (3! - 1)$
10281 := $((1 + (3^5 \times 7)) \times 9) - ((7! - (5 - 3)) - 1)$
10282 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (7! + ((9 + 75) - (3 - 1))))$
10283 := $13 \times ((5! + 797) - ((5^3) + 1))$
10284 := $((13 \times 5!) + (79 + 75)) \times 3! \times 1$
10285 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5! + 7!)) + ((97 - 5) - (3! + 1))$
10286 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - 9) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 - 1))$
10287 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (7! + (97 \times (53 + 1)))$
10288 := $(1 + 3)! - ((5 - 7) \times (97 - (5 - ((3! + 1)!))))$
10289 := $((13 + 57 + 9) + 7) \times 5! - 31$
10290 := $(1 - 3) \times (5 - (7! + 97)) - (5 - 31)$
10291 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) - 9) \times 75) + (3!! + 1)$
10292 := $1 - ((35 + ((7 - 9) \times ((7! + 5!) + 3))) \times 1)$
10293 := $1 - ((35 + ((7 - 9) \times ((7! + 5!) + 3))) - 1)$
10294 := $(1 + 3)! + ((5 \times 79) \times (7 - 5 + (3 + 1)!))$
10295 := $((1 + 3) - (5 - 79)) \times (7 + (5^3)) - 1$
10296 := $((1 + 3) - (5 - 79)) \times (7 + (5^3)) \times 1$
10297 := $(13 + (5! \times (79 + 7))) - (5 + 31)$
10298 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7! + (97 \times (53 + 1))$
10299 := $(135 + (7! + 9)) + (75 + ((3! + 1)!)$
10300 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times 7 \times 97 - (5 - ((3! - 1)!)$
10301 := $(135 \times 79) - (7 \times (53 - 1))$
10302 := $(1 \times ((3^5 + 7!) + 9)) + (7! - (5 \times 3! \times 1))$
10303 := $1 \times ((3^5 + ((7! - 9) \times (7 - 5))) - (3 - 1))$
10304 := $(1 \times (35 - 7)) \times ((97 - 5) \times (3 + 1))$
10305 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + ((7! + (9 \times (7 - 5)))) / (3 - 1))$
10306 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) + (5^3 \times 1))$
10307 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) + (5! + 3 + 1))$
10308 := $(1 + 3^5) + (((7! - 9) \times (7 - 5)) + 3 - 1)$
10309 := $(1 + 3^5) + (((7! - 9) \times (7 - 5)) + 3 \times 1)$
10310 := $(1 \times (35 \times (7! / (9 + 7)))) + (5 - ((3! \times 1)!)$
10311 := $(1 + ((35 \times (7! / (9 + 7))) + 5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)$
10312 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + ((7! + (97 + 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)$
10313 := $(13 \times (5 + 797)) - (5! - (3! + 1))$
10314 := $(1 + (((3! \times 5) - (7 - (9 \times 7))) \times 5!)) - (3! + 1)$
10315 := $(1 + (((3! \times 5) - (7 - (9 \times 7))) \times 5!)) - (3! \times 1)$
10316 := $((135 + 7!) + (97 \times 53)) \times 1$
10317 := $((135 + 7!) + (97 \times 53)) + 1$
10318 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (79 + 7!))) + (5! / 3) - 1$
10319 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (79 + 7!))) + ((5! / 3) \times 1)$
10320 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (79 + 7!))) + (5! / 3) + 1$
10321 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times (79 + 7))) + (5 - (3 + 1))$
10322 := $((135 + 7!) - 9) + ((7! + 5!) - (3 + 1))$
10323 := $((1 + 3!) \times 57) + (9 - 75) \times 31$
10324 := $((1 \times (3^5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) - (3!! - 1)$
10325 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + ((7! + 9) + (7! - (5! + 3 + 1)))$
10326 := $(13 \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7! + 5!) + 31)$
10327 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5) + 7!) + ((97 + 5!) + ((3! + 1)!)$
10328 := $(1 + (((3! \times 5) - (7 - (9 \times 7))) \times 5!)) + (3! + 1)$
10329 := $(1 - 3 + (5 \times (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 - 1))$
10330 := $(1 - (3! - ((5 - 7) + 9))) \times (7! + (5^3 \times 1))$
10331 := $((1 + (3 + (5! \times 79))) + 7) + 5! + (3!! \times 1)$
10332 := $(1 + (3 + 5)) \times ((7 \times 9) + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))$
10333 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 7) \times 9 - ((7! + 5) - 3! \times 1)$
10334 := $((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) + (5! - (3 + 1)!)$
10335 := $13 \times (5 + ((797 - 5) - (3 - 1)))$
10336 := $(1^3 + 5!) + ((7! - 9) + (7! + (5! + (3 + 1)!)))$

$$\begin{aligned}10337 &:= (13 + ((5! + ((7! + 9) + 7!)) + 5!)) - (3! - 1) \\10338 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 \times (9 - (75 \times (3! - 1)))) \\10339 &:= 1 \times (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 + 7)) + (((5 + 3) - 1)!) \\10340 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7)) \times (((9 - 7) - 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\10341 &:= (135 + 7!) + (((9 + (7! + 5!)) - 3) \times 1) \\10342 &:= (135 + 7!) + (((9 + (7! + 5!)) - 3) + 1) \\10343 &:= 1 + ((3! \times 57) + ((9 + 7) \times (5^{3+1}))) \\10344 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) - 7!) - (9 + 7)) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1) \\10345 &:= 13 + ((5! + (((7! + 9) + 7!) + 5!)) + 3 \times 1) \\10346 &:= (1^3) \times ((5! + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) - (5 - 31) \\10347 &:= (13 + ((5! + ((7! + 9) + 7!)) + 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\10348 &:= (1 + 3^5) + (7! + (9 + (7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))))) \\10349 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((79 + 7) \times 5!) - 3! \times 1) \\10350 &:= (((1 \times 3! \times 5) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) \times 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\10351 &:= (((13 + 57 + 9) + 7) \times 5!) + 31 \\10352 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7 \times (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\10353 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 5) \times ((7 \times (97 + 5)) / (3 - 1)) \\10354 &:= 1 \times (3^5 + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) + 1))) \\10355 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) + 1)) \\10356 &:= (13 \times (5! + (7 \times 97))) - ((5 \times 3!) + 1) \\10357 &:= 1 + (((((3 \times 5!) - 79) + 7!) - 5) + ((3! + 1)!) \\10358 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((79 + 7) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1) \\10359 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5! + 7!)) + (((9 + 7!) + 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\10360 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) + ((79 + 7) \times 5!)) + 31 \\10361 &:= 13 \times ((5 \times 7) + (9 + (753 \times 1))) \\10362 &:= ((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) + ((5! + 3) + 1) \\10363 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) + (7 - 9)) \times ((7 + 5) + 31) \\10364 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times 97) + 5!) - (3! \times 1) \\10365 &:= (1 - 3) - (5! + (7! + (97 - ((5^{3!}) - 1)))) \\10366 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5! - (7! - 97))) + ((5! \times 3!) \times 1) \\10367 &:= (13 + 5) + (79 \times (7 + ((5^3) - 1))) \\10368 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (57 - 9)) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\10369 &:= (13 + (5! \times (79 + 7))) + (5 + 31) \\10370 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) \times ((7 - 97) + (5! / (3 + 1)!) \\10371 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + 5!) + 7!) - (9 \times ((7 + 5) - 31)) \\10372 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 - 7) \times ((9 - 7!) - (5 \times 31))) \\10373 &:= (1^3) + ((5 - 7) \times ((9 - 7!) - (5 \times 31))) \\10374 &:= (((((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + 9) + 7) + 5) \times 3! \times 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10375 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 \times 7)) + ((97 + 5)^{3-1}) \\10376 &:= (1 + (3! - (5 \times 7))) + ((97 + 5)^{3-1}) \\10377 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((57 \times 9) + 7!) - 5) \times (3 - 1) \\10378 &:= ((13 + 5!) + (7! + (9 + 7))) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\10379 &:= (135 + (7! + 9)) + (7! + 5 \times 31) \\10380 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5!)) \times (7 - 97)) - (5! \times (3! - 1)) \\10381 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5) + ((79 + 7) \times 5!)) + 31 \\10382 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times (97 - 5))) + (3! + 1) \\10383 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) \times (7! + ((97 + 53) + 1))) \\10384 &:= (1 - (3 - 5!)) \times (((79 - 7) + (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\10385 &:= ((1 - (3! + 579)) \times (7 - (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\10386 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times ((579 - 7) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\10387 &:= 13 + ((5! \times (79 + 7)) + (53 + 1)) \\10388 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + (79 - 7))) \times (53 \times 1) \\10389 &:= (13 \times 5) - (((7 - 9) - 7!) - 5!) \times (3 - 1) \\10390 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) - 7) + ((97 + 5)^{3-1}) \\10391 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) \times 7) \times 9) - (7! - (5! + 3 - 1)) \\10392 &:= ((135 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\10393 &:= ((135 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) - (3 - 1) \\10394 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (79 + 7!))) - (5 - ((3! - 1)!) \\10395 &:= 135 \times ((79 + 75) / (3 - 1)) \\10396 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + ((5! + (79 + 7!)) + 5!)) - 3) \times 1 \\10397 &:= ((135 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) + (3 - 1) \\10398 &:= ((135 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\10399 &:= (((135 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) + 3) + 1 \\10400 &:= 13 \times ((5 + 797) - ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\10401 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + (((5! + (79 + 7!)) + 5!) + 3 - 1) \\10402 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times (7 \times (9 - (753 - 1))) \\10403 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5!)) \times 79) - (7 \times 5)) + (3! + 1) \\10404 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 - 7)) \times ((97 + 5)^{3-1}) \\10405 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 \times 79)) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\10406 &:= (1 - 35) - ((7 - 97) \times ((5! - 3) - 1)) \\10407 &:= (((13 - 5!) + 7) \times (9 + (7 - 5!))) + 3! + 1 \\10408 &:= ((1 - ((3 - 5) - 7) \times 9) \times (7 + 5!)) - 3! \times 1 \\10409 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7) - ((97 + 5)^{3-1})) \\10410 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - ((7 - 9) \times 7!)) - (5! / (3 + 1)) \\10411 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times ((5! + 7) + 97)) - 5) + ((3! + 1)!) \\10412 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((5 - 7) - ((97 + 5)^{3-1})) \\10413 &:= 135 + (7! + (97 \times (53 + 1)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10414 &:= (13 \times (5 + 797)) - (5 + (3! + 1)) \\
 10415 &:= (13 \times (5 + 797)) - ((5 + 3!) \times 1) \\
 10416 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (57 - 9)) + 7!) + 5! \times (3 - 1) \\
 10417 &:= 1 - (3! - (579 \times (7 + (5 + 3! \times 1)))) \\
 10418 &:= (13 \times (5! + (7 \times 97))) + ((5 \times 3!) + 1) \\
 10419 &:= (1 + 357) - (9 - ((7! - 5) \times (3 - 1))) \\
 10420 &:= (1 - ((3 - (5! + 7)) \times (9 + 75))) + (3 \times 1) \\
 10421 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (579 \times (7 - 5))) \times 3) - 1 \\
 10422 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 \times (7 - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\
 10423 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (579 \times (7 - 5))) \times 3) + 1 \\
 10424 &:= (((1 + 35) + (7 + 9)) + 7!) + 5! \times (3 - 1) \\
 10425 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5 + 7!) + ((97 \times 53) + 1) \\
 10426 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5) - (7 - ((97 + 5)^{3-1})) \\
 10427 &:= (13 \times (5 + 797)) - ((5 - 3!) \times 1) \\
 10428 &:= (13 \times (5 + 797)) - (5 - (3! + 1)) \\
 10429 &:= (1 + 3!) + (579 \times (7 + (5 + 3! \times 1))) \\
 10430 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((79 + 7!) + (5! - (3 + 1)!)) \\
 10431 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (57 \times ((97 - 5) - 31)) \\
 10432 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! + 7!) \times (9 - 7))) + (5! - 3! \times 1) \\
 10433 &:= ((1 - 35) - 7!) + (((9 + 7!) + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 10434 &:= ((1 - 35) - 7!) + (((9 + 7!) + 5!) \times 3) + 1) \\
 10435 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! + 7!) \times (9 - 7))) + (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\
 10436 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 797)) + (5 + 3!)) - 1 \\
 10437 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 797)) + (5 + 3!)) \times 1 \\
 10438 &:= (13 \times (5 + 797)) + (5 + (3! + 1)) \\
 10439 &:= 13 \times ((579 + (75 \times 3)) - 1) \\
 10440 &:= ((13 + 5!) \times 79) - (7 + (5! / (3 - 1))) \\
 10441 &:= (13 \times (5! \times 7)) - ((97 \times 5) - 3! \times 1) \\
 10442 &:= (((1^{35}) + 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 10443 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! \times ((79 - 7) + (5 \times 3))) \times 1) \\
 10444 &:= (1 + (((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) + 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\
 10445 &:= (1 \times 357) + ((9 + (7! - 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\
 10446 &:= (1 \times 357 + 9) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\
 10447 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5! \times (7 + ((9 - 7) - (5! - (3 + 1)!)))) \\
 10448 &:= (1 + ((3^5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + (5^3))) - 1 \\
 10449 &:= (1 + ((3^5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + (5^3))) \times 1 \\
 10450 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7! / 9)) + ((7 \times 53) - 1) \\
 10451 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5!) - ((7! + (9 + 7)) - ((5^{3!}) - 1)) \\
 10452 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5!) - ((7! + (9 + 7)) - ((5^{3!}) \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10453 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! + 7!)) - ((9 + 7) - ((5^{3!}) + 1)) \\
 10454 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5 \times 79)) + (7! - (5! / 3!))) - 1 \\
 10455 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5 \times 79)) + (7! - (5! / 3!))) \times 1 \\
 10456 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + (5 \times 79)) + (7! - (5! / 3!))) + 1 \\
 10457 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (579 + (7 - 5))) \times 3!) - 1 \\
 10458 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (579 + (7 - 5))) \times 3!) \times 1 \\
 10459 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (579 + (7 - 5))) \times 3!) + 1 \\
 10460 &:= (((1 - (3!! + 5)) \times 7) - (97 - (5^{3!}))) \times 1 \\
 10461 &:= (((1 - (3!! + 5)) \times 7) - (97 - (5^{3!}))) + 1 \\
 10462 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5!) - ((7 + 9) \times (75 - (3!! + 1))) \\
 10463 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 \times 7) + ((97 + 5)^{3-1})) \\
 10464 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (5! - ((7 - 9) \times (7 \times (5! - (3 + 1)!)))) \\
 10465 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! / (3! - 1))) \\
 10466 &:= ((1 - (3!! + (5! \times 79))) + 7!) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\
 10467 &:= (1^3 - (((5! + 7!) - (9 - 7)) - (5^{3!}))) - 1 \\
 10468 &:= (1^3 - (((5! + 7!) - (9 - 7)) - (5^{3!}))) \times 1 \\
 10469 &:= (1^3 - (((5! + 7!) - (9 - 7)) - (5^{3!}))) - 1) \\
 10470 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times (((79 + 7!) + 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\
 10471 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) - (7! - (9 - 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\
 10472 &:= (((1 + 3)! - 5!) - (7! + (9 + 7))) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\
 10473 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5!)) \times 79) + ((7 \times 5) + (3!! + 1)) \\
 10474 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5!)) \times (79 + (7 + 5))) - (3!! - 1) \\
 10475 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + (((5 \times 79) + (7! + 5!)) - ((3! - 1)!)) \\
 10476 &:= ((1^3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 97) \times (5 - (3 - 1)) \\
 10477 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5! \times 79) + (7! / 5)) - (3! \times 1)) \\
 10478 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) - (7 - (97 + 5))) \times 31 \\
 10479 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 - (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\
 10480 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5 + 7!) + (97 - ((5^{3!}) - 1))) \\
 10481 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5! - 7!)) + (9 + 7)) + (5^{3+1}) \\
 10482 &:= ((13 + 5!) \times 79) - (((7 + 5) / 3)! + 1) \\
 10483 &:= (((13 + 5!) \times 79) - (((7 + 5) / 3)!)) \times 1 \\
 10484 &:= (((13 + 5!) \times 79) - (((7 + 5) / 3)!)) + 1 \\
 10485 &:= ((1 \times 35) - (7! - 9)) + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) + 1) \\
 10486 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - 5!) + ((7 + 9) - 7!)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\
 10487 &:= (1 \times (3! - ((5! + 7!) - (9 + 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\
 10488 &:= (((1^3)^5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - 5)) \times (3 + 1)! \\
 10489 &:= (((13 + 5!) \times 79) + 7) - (5^{3-1}) \\
 10490 &:= ((13 + 5!) \times 79) - (((7 + 5) + 3!) - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 10491** := $((1 - 3 + 5) - 7!) - 97 + (5^{3 \times 1})$
10492 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) - ((7 + 5) + 3 \times 1)$
10493 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times 79)) + ((7!/5) + 3!) - 1$
10494 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times 79)) + (((7!/5) + 3!) \times 1)$
10495 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times 79)) + ((7!/5) + 3!) + 1$
10496 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5 \times 79)) + ((7! + (5!/3!)) + 1)$
10497 := $(1 - 35) - (((7 - 97) \times (5! - 3)) - 1)$
10498 := $((1 - 3)^5) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! - (3 \times 1)))$
10499 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5 \times 79)) + 7! + (((5 + 3) - 1)!)!$
10500 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) \times (3! - 1))$
10501 := $(1 \times (35 - 7!)) + (((9 + (7! + 5!)) \times 3) - 1)$
10502 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((79 + (7 + 5)) - (3 - 1))$
10503 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) - (((7 + 5)/3) \times 1)$
10504 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) - 7!) - 97 + (5^{3 \times 1})$
10505 := $(13 \times ((5! \times 7) + ((9 - (7 \times 5)) - 3!))) + 1$
10506 := $(1 - ((3! + 5) + 7)) \times (((97 + 5) - 3!) \times 1)$
10507 := $(13 + 57 + 9) \times ((7 + (5^3)) + 1)$
10508 := $1 - (((3 - 5!) - (7 + 9)) \times ((75 + 3) + 1))$
10509 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + ((7 + 5)/(3! \times 1))$
10510 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + (((7 + 5)/3) - 1)$
10511 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + (((7 + 5)/3) \times 1)$
10512 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (5 + 7)) \times (9 - ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1)!))$
10513 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5 - (79 + 7!))) + ((5! \times 3) - 1)$
10514 := $((1^{3!})^5) \times (((7! + 97) + 5!) \times (3 - 1))$
10515 := $(13 - 5) - ((79 + 7!) - ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
10516 := $((1 + 3) + 5) - (79 + 7!) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)$
10517 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + 7 + (5 - (3 - 1))$
10518 := $1 - ((3 + 5!) + ((7!/9) \times ((7 + 5) - 31)))$
10519 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5! + (79 + 7!))) + (5! \times (3 - 1))$
10520 := $(1 \times 3! + ((57 \times 9) + 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1))$
10521 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + 7 + 5 + (3 - 1)$
10522 := $((1 \times ((3 \times 5) - 79)) - 7!) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)$
10523 := $(1 - ((3! + 5) + 7)) \times (((97 + 5) - 3!) - 1)$
10524 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) - (3! + 1))$
10525 := $((13 + 5) - (79 + 7!)) + (5^{3!}) + 1$
10526 := $1 \times ((3! + 5) + (((7 + 97) - 5)^{3-1}))$
10527 := $(1^3 + 5!) \times (79 - (7 - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)))$
10528 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (7 + 9)) + 7! + (5 \times 3! \times 1)$
10529 := $(1 - 3) + ((5! + 7) + ((97 + 5)^{3-1}))$
10530 := $((1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)$
10531 := $((13 - 5) - (7 \times 9)) - 7! + ((5^{3!}) + 1)$
10532 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + (((7 + 5)/3)! + 1)$
10533 := $(13 - 5!) - ((7!/9) \times ((7 + 5) - 31))$
10534 := $(135 \times 79) - (7 + ((5! + 3) + 1))$
10535 := $((1 - 35) - (7 + 9)) - (7! - (5^{3 \times 1}))$
10536 := $(1 - (35 + 7!)) - ((9 + 7) - ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
10537 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 5) - 7!) - (9 \times 7))) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
10538 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) - (7! + ((9 \times 7) - (5^{3 \times 1})))$
10539 := $(13 \times (5 + 797)) + (5! - (3! + 1))$
10540 := $((13 + 57) - 9) + 7 \times (5 \times 31)$
10541 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + (9 - 7!) + (5^{3!}) \times 1$
10542 := $(135 \times 79) - (((7 + 5!) - 3) - 1)$
10543 := $(1 \times ((3!/5) + 79)) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 - 1))$
10544 := $((1 + 3)^5) - ((7!/9) - (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1))))$
10545 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times (7!/(9 \times 7)) + (5^{3+1})$
10546 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + 7!) + (5! + 31)))$
10547 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1))$
10548 := $(135 \times 79) + (7 - ((5! + 3) + 1))$
10549 := $(1 + ((3! - (5! - 7!)) - ((9 - 7!) + 5!))) - (3 \times 1)$
10550 := $(1 + ((3! - (5! - 7!)) - ((9 - 7!) + 5!))) - (3 - 1)$
10551 := $(1 \times 3!) + (57 \times (((9 \times 7) + 5!) + 3 - 1))$
10552 := $((1 + (3^5 + 7!)) \times (9 - 7)) - (5 \times 3) - 1$
10553 := $((1 + (3^5 + 7!)) \times (9 - 7)) - (5 \times 3) \times 1$
10554 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5!) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) - (5! + 3! \times 1))$
10555 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5 - 7!)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 3! \times 1))$
10556 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5! - 79)) - 7 \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
10557 := $(1 + ((3 + ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)$
10558 := $(1 - (3 - 5!)) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! - (3 + 1)))$
10559 := $((1 + (3! - ((5! - 7!) + 9))) + 7) - (5! - ((3! + 1)!))$
10560 := $1 \times ((3 + 57) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)))$
10561 := $1 + ((3 + 57) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)))$
10562 := $((1 + 3!)! - 5!) + ((7! + 9) - (7 - (5! \times (3! - 1))))$
10563 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) \times 7! + (((97 \times 5) - 3) + 1)$
10564 := $1 + ((3 \times 5!) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + (5! + 3 \times 1)))$
10565 := $((1^{3!}) - 5) - (7! + (9 + 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
10566 := $((1 - (35 + 7!)) + (9 + 7)) + (5^{3!}) - 1$

- 10567** := $((1 - (35 + 7!)) + (9 + 7)) + (5^{3!}) \times 1$
10568 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 - 7) + 5! \times (3 + 1)$
10569 := $13 + ((5 - (7 \times 9)) \times (7 \times (5 - 31)))$
10570 := $(13 + 57) \times (97 + (53 + 1))$
10571 := $1 + (((35/7) + 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + (3! \times 1)))$
10572 := $((1 + 3^5) + 7!) + (9 - 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
10573 := $(1 \times 3!) - (5! - (((7! + 9) + 7!) - (5! - (3 + 1))))$
10574 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + (7 + (5! / (3 - 1)))$
10575 := $(1^{3!}) + (5 - ((7! + (9 + 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1})))$
10576 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + (75 - 3! \times 1)$
10577 := $((1^{35}) \times ((79 + 7) \times (5! + 3))) - 1$
10578 := $((1^{35}) \times ((79 + 7) \times (5! + 3))) \times 1$
10579 := $((1^{35}) \times ((79 + 7) \times (5! + 3))) + 1$
10580 := $((1 - 3) - 5) - (7 - 9) - 7! + (5^{3! \times 1})$
10581 := $((1 + 3!)! + (57 \times 9)) + (7! - (5 + (3! + 1)))$
10582 := $((1 + (3^5 + 7!)) \times (9 - 7)) + (5 \times 3) - 1$
10583 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) \times (75 - 3) - 1$
10584 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5 + 79))) \times (7 \times ((5 - (3 - 1)))!)$
10585 := $((1 - 3) - 5) / 7^9 \times (7! - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
10586 := $((1^{35})^{7+9}) - (7! - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
10587 := $(1 \times 3) - ((5! \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 - (3! - 1))))$
10588 := $((1^{35}) - (7! - (9 - 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
10589 := $((1^{35}) - ((7! - 9) + 7)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)$
10590 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5! + ((7 + (9 \times 75)) \times (3! - 1)))$
10591 := $((13 - 5) + 7) - 9 - (7! - ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
10592 := $((1 \times 3!) / 5! - (7! - (9 - 7))) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
10593 := $((1^{3!}) + 5) - (7! - ((9 - 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})))$
10594 := $(1 + (3^5 + 7!)) \times (9 - 7) - (5 - 31)$
10595 := $(1 \times (((3 + 5) - (7! - 9)) - 7)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
10596 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) + ((7! - (97 + 5)) \times (3 - 1))$
10597 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! \times 7) + (9753 \times 1))$
10598 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5! - 7)) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times 31)$
10599 := $1 - ((3^5 + (7 + 9 + 7!)) \times (5 - (3! + 1)))$
10600 := $((13 + (5 + (7 - 9))) - 7!) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
10601 := $((1^{35}) - (7! - 9)) + ((7 + (5^{3!})) - 1)$
10602 := $((1 \times 3)^5 + 7) + 97 - 5 \times 31$
10603 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5) - ((7! - ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!}))) - 1)$
10604 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) + ((7 + 9) - (7! - (5^{3! \times 1})))$
10605 := $(1 + (3 \times 5!)) + (7! + (9 + (7! + 5 \times 31)))$
10606 := $(135 \times 79) - (7 + (53 - 1))$
10607 := $(1^3) - (5 - ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + 531))$
10608 := $(1 \times (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 + 7)) + 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
10609 := $((13 - 5) + 7) + (9 - 7!) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
10610 := $1 \times (((3 + 5) - (7! - 9)) + (7 + (5^{3!}))) + 1$
10611 := $1 + (((3 + 5) - (7! - 9)) + (7 + (5^{3!}))) + 1$
10612 := $((1^3)^5) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + 531)$
10613 := $(1 \times 3!) + (5 - ((7! - ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!}))) - 1))$
10614 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5 \times 7)) + ((97 + 5)^{3-1})$
10615 := $1 - (((3 - 5) \times 7!) - (9 + (75 \times (3! + 1))))$
10616 := $(1 + 3!) + ((57 \times 9) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) - 1))$
10617 := $(1 \times 3!) - ((5! - 7!) + (9 - ((7! - 53) - 1)))$
10618 := $((1 \times (3 \times 57 \times 9)) \times 7) - (5 \times 31)$
10619 := $1 - (((3 \times 5) + 79) \times (7 - 5!)) + 3 + 1$
10620 := $(135 \times 79) + (7 - (53 - 1))$
10621 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) \times (7 - 97) - ((5! \times 3) - 1)$
10622 := $(1 - 3) - (((5 + (7 - 97)) \times (5^3)) + 1)$
10623 := $(1 + (3! / 5)) + ((79 + (7! + 5!)) \times (3 - 1))$
10624 := $1 + ((35 - ((7! - 9) + 7)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
10625 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5 + 7!)) + (9 + (7! + 531))$
10626 := $(1 \times (3! + 5)) \times ((7 + ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
10627 := $1 - (((3 \times 5) + 79) \times (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1)$
10628 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) - (((79 + 7!) - (5^{3!})) + 1)$
10629 := $((1 + 3!)! / 5! - 7!) + ((9 - 7) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
10630 := $(1 \times 3! \times 5) - ((7! - ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!}))) + 1)$
10631 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5) + (7! - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31))$
10632 := $(1 \times 3! \times 5) - ((7! - ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!}))) - 1)$
10633 := $((1 + 3!) + ((5! \times (7 \times (9 - 7))) / 5)) \times 31$
10634 := $((1 - ((3 \times 5) + 7!)) + (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
10635 := $(1 \times 35) - (((7! - 9) - (7 + (5^{3!}))) + 1)$
10636 := $(1 \times 35) - (((7! - 9) - (7 + (5^{3!}))) \times 1)$
10637 := $(1 \times 35) - (((7! - 9) - (7 + (5^{3!}))) - 1)$
10638 := $(1 + 35) - ((7! - 9) - ((7 + (5^{3!})) + 1))$
10639 := $((1 + (35/7)) \times 9) - 7! + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
10640 := $((1 + (3! + 5)) + 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times (3! + 1)))$
10641 := $(1 \times (3! - 5!)) + ((7! + (9 \times 75)) + ((3! + 1)!))$
10642 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times 79) + (7! - 5!))) \times (3 - 1)$

- 10643** := $((1^3 - 5) - 7!) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^{3!})) - 1$
10644 := $((1^3 - 5) - 7!) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^{3!})) \times 1$
10645 := $((1^3 - 5) - 7!) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^{3!})) + 1$
10646 := $(1 - (3 \times 57)) + ((9 + 7) - 5!)^{3-1}$
10647 := $(1 - (((3 \times 5) + 79) \times (7 - 5!))) + (3 + 1)!$
10648 := $(1 \times (((3! - 5)^7) + (9 + 7)) + 5)^3 \times 1$
10649 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + ((7!/9) + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1))))$
10650 := $(1 + (((3!/5) - (79 + 7!)) + (5^{3!}))) - 1$
10651 := $(1 + (((3!/5) - (79 + 7!)) + (5^{3!}))) \times 1$
10652 := $(1 + (((3!/5) - (79 + 7!)) + (5^{3!}))) + 1$
10653 := $1 - (((3! + 5) \times (7 - 975)) - 3) - 1$
10654 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + (7! \times (9 - 7)))) - 5! - 31$
10655 := $((1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) - 5!)) - 31$
10656 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7 - (5! - (3 \times 1))$
10657 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) \times (9 \times 7) - (5! - 3) + 1$
10658 := $((1^3 + 5)!) + (7! + ((9 + (7! - 5!)) - 31))$
10659 := $(1 + ((3^5 + 7) + 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3!) - 1$
10660 := $(1 + ((3^5 + 7) + 9)) \times (((7 \times 5) + 3!) \times 1)$
10661 := $((1 + 35) \times (7 + 9)) + (7! + 5) + ((3! + 1)!)!$
10662 := $((1 - 35) + ((7! - 9) + 7!)) + (5^{3+1})$
10663 := $(1 \times (3! - 57)) + (((9 - 7) \times 5)^{3+1})$
10664 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75)) - 3!) - 1$
10665 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75)) - 3!) \times 1$
10666 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75)) - 3!) + 1$
10667 := $(13 \times 5) + (((7! - 9) + 7!) + 531)$
10668 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75))) - (3! \times 1)$
10669 := $((1 + 3!)! - 5!) + (7! - ((9 + 7) - 5)) + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
10670 := $((135 \times 79) + (7 + 5)) - (3! + 1)$
10671 := $(13 + 579) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) - 1)$
10672 := $(13 + 579) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) \times 1)$
10673 := $(1 - 3) - ((5! \times (7 - 97)) + ((5^3) \times 1))$
10674 := $((135 \times 79) - 7) + ((5 \times 3) + 1)$
10675 := $(13 + (57 - 9)) \times (7 \times (5^{3-1}))$
10676 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75)) + (3! - 1))$
10677 := $(1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75)) + 3!)) \times 1$
10678 := $(1 \times 3) - ((5! \times (7 - 97)) + (5! + (3! - 1)))$
10679 := $((135 \times 79) + (7 + (5 + 3))) - 1$
10680 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75))) + (3! \times 1)$
10681 := $((135 \times 79) + (7 + (5 + 3))) + 1$
10682 := $(1 \times (3! - (5! - (7 + 9)))) \times ((7 - 5!) + 3 + 1)$
10683 := $((135 \times 79) + (7 + 5)) + (3! \times 1)$
10684 := $((135 \times 79) + (7 + 5)) + (3! + 1)$
10685 := $((1 + 3) + (5! \times (79 + 7))) + ((5! \times 3) + 1)$
10686 := $((13 + 5) \times ((7!/9) + (7 \times 5))) - (3 + 1)!$
10687 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5! - 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
10688 := $(1 + 3!) - (((5! - 7!) - 9) - ((7! - 5) + 3 \times 1))$
10689 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) - ((3! - 1)!)!$
10690 := $((1 + 3) + 5) - (7! - 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
10691 := $((13 + 5) - 7) \times (975 - 3) - 1$
10692 := $((13 + 5) - 7) \times (975 - 3) \times 1$
10693 := $((13 + 5) - 7) \times (975 - 3) + 1$
10694 := $((13 + 5) - 7) \times 975 - 31$
10695 := $1 \times (3 \times 5 \times ((7 + (9 \times 75)) + 31))$
10696 := $1 + (3 \times 5 \times ((7 + (9 \times 75)) + 31))$
10697 := $((1 \times 3)!^5 - 7) + (((9 - 7) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)!)!$
10698 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) - 7!) + (97 + (5^{3 \times 1}))$
10699 := $13 \times ((5 + (797 + (5!/3!))) + 1)$
10700 := $((1 - ((3! \times (5! - 7)) \times 9)) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1$
10701 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) - (7 + (97 - (5^{3-1})))$
10702 := $(1 - 3!) + (5! - ((7! - (9 - 7)) - ((5^3) \times 1)))$
10703 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (79 + 7))) + (5^3 \times 1)$
10704 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5 + 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times (53 - 1)))$
10705 := $((1 + (3 \times 5 \times 7))^{9-7}) - 531$
10706 := $(1 + (3 - 57)) \times (9 - (((7 \times 5) \times 3!) + 1))$
10707 := $(1 + ((3 + 5!) - 7!)) - ((9 - 7) - (5^{3 \times 1}))$
10708 := $((1 + ((3^5) \times 7)) + 975) \times (3 + 1)$
10709 := $((1 \times 357) \times ((9 - 7) \times (5 \times 3))) - 1$
10710 := $(135 \times 79) - (7 - (53 - 1))$
10711 := $((1 \times 357) \times ((9 - 7) \times (5 \times 3))) + 1$
10712 := $13 \times (5 + ((7 + ((97 - 5) + 3!)) \times 1))$
10713 := $135 + ((79 + 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1))$
10714 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) \times (7 + 9)) - ((7! - (5^{3!})) - 1)$
10715 := $((1 \times 3!) - ((5 - 7!) - 9)) + (7! - (5! - 31))$
10716 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + (7! \times (9 - 7)))) - (5! - 31)$
10717 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) - 5!) + 31)$
10718 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((79 + (7! + 5!)) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
10719 := $((1 \times ((3 \times 57) + 97)) \times (5!/3)) - 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 10720 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times 9) \times 7)) - (53 \times 1) \\ 10721 &:= (1 + (3!! + 5)) - (7! - ((97 \times 5) \times 31)) \\ 10722 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5! - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - ((5 + 3 - 1)!!) \\ 10723 &:= ((13 + (5 - 7)) \times 975) - (3 - 1) \\ 10724 &:= (135 \times 79) + (7 + (53 - 1)) \\ 10725 &:= ((13 \times (57 - (9 - 7))) \times 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 10726 &:= (1 \times (((357 - 9) - 7) + 5)) \times 31 \\ 10727 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + ((5! - 7!) + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 10728 &:= (1 + (3! + (5! - 7!))) + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 10729 &:= (13 - 5!) + ((79 + 7) \times ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 10730 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 5) \times ((7 - 9) + ((7 + 5) \times 31)) \\ 10731 &:= (((13 + 5) - 7) \times 975) + 3! \times 1 \\ 10732 &:= ((1 + 3^5) - 7!) - (97 - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 10733 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7) - (5! / (3 \times 1)) \\ 10734 &:= ((13 + 5) \times ((7! / 9) + (7 \times 5))) + (3 + 1)! \\ 10735 &:= ((1 - 35) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) - 31 \\ 10736 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (79 + (7 + 5))) - (3 - 1) \\ 10737 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) \times 7) - (5 + 31) \\ 10738 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5!)) \times 7) \times (9 + ((7 \times 5) - 31)) \\ 10739 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7!)) + ((9 \times 75) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 10740 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (79 + (7 + 5))) + (3 - 1) \\ 10741 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5!)) \times (7 + 9)) - 75) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 10742 &:= ((1 \times (3579 + (7 - 5))) \times 3) - 1 \\ 10743 &:= ((1 \times (3579 + (7 - 5))) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 10744 &:= 1 \times ((357 \times 9) + 7531) \\ 10745 &:= 1 + ((357 \times 9) + 7531) \\ 10746 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 7!)) + ((97 \times 5!) / (3 - 1)) \\ 10747 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times (7 + 9)) + (7! - (53 \times 1)) \\ 10748 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57)) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5^{3-1}) \\ 10749 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7!) + (9 + 7!)) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 10750 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) - (5 - 7!)) - (9 - (7! - (5 + 31))) \\ 10751 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5)) + (79 \times (7 + 5!))) + (3!! - 1) \\ 10752 &:= (1 + (3! + (5 \times 7))) \times ((9 + 7)^{5-3 \times 1}) \\ 10753 &:= ((13 \times 5) + (((7! + 9) + (7! - 5!)) + 3!!)) - 1 \\ 10754 &:= ((13 \times 5) + (((7! + 9) + (7! - 5!)) + 3!!)) \times 1 \\ 10755 &:= ((13 \times 5) + (((7! + 9) + (7! - 5!)) + 3!!)) + 1 \\ 10756 &:= (((13 + 5) - 7) \times 975) + 31 \\ 10757 &:= (1 + (((357 - 9) - 7) + 5)) \times 31 \\ 10758 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times 9) \times 7)) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 10759 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5 \times 7) - 9)) \times ((7 \times 53) \times 1) \\ 10760 &:= 1 \times (((3 + (5! + 7!)) + (97 + 5!)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 10761 &:= 1 + (((3 + (5! + 7!)) + (97 + 5!)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 10762 &:= 1 \times (3 - (57 - (((9 + 7) - 5!)^{3-1})) \\ 10763 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 5) \times ((7 + 9) - 7!))) - (5 - 3!! \times 1) \\ 10764 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5) \times ((7 + 9) - 7!))) - (5 - 3!! \times 1) \\ 10765 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1) \\ 10766 &:= (1 - 35) - ((7 - 9) \times (7! + (5! \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 10767 &:= 1 + ((3!! + ((5 - 7) \times ((9 - 7!) + 5))) - 3! \times 1) \\ 10768 &:= ((1 + (3!! / 5)) + (79 + (7! + 5!))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 10769 &:= (1 \times (35 + (79 + 7))) \times (5! - 31) \\ 10770 &:= (1 \times 357 + (9 - 7)) \times (5 \times 3! \times 1) \\ 10771 &:= ((135 \times 79) - (7 - (5! - 3!))) - 1 \\ 10772 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5!) - ((7! - (9 \times 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 10773 &:= (((13 + 5) + (7 \times 9)) \times 7) \times ((5! / 3!) - 1) \\ 10774 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5!) - 7!)) - (9 - (75^{3-1})) \\ 10775 &:= (1 \times (3!! + ((5 - 7) \times ((9 - 7!) + 5)))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 10776 &:= (1 \times (357 + (97 - 5))) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 10777 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) - ((7 - 9) \times (7! - 5))) + (3!! + 1) \\ 10778 &:= (1 \times (3!! + ((5 - 7) \times ((9 - 7!) + 5)))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 10779 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) + (5 + (7! \times (9 - 7)))) + (5 - 31) \\ 10780 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 10781 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7) + (5 + 3 \times 1) \\ 10782 &:= (135 \times 79) - (7 - ((5! + 3) + 1)) \\ 10783 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (((5 - 7) \times (9 - 7!)) - (5 - 3! \times 1)) \\ 10784 &:= (((1 + 3!))! + (5 + 7!)) - ((9 + 7) + (5 - ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\ 10785 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((57 - 9) \times 75)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 10786 &:= 1 + 35 + ((79 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 10787 &:= 1 - ((35 \times (7 - ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 10788 &:= (135 \times 79) + (((7 + 5!) - 3) - 1) \\ 10789 &:= (((((1 + 3!))! + 5) + 79) + 7!) + (5^{3+1}) \\ 10790 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5! + 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 10791 &:= 1 - (((3 - ((57 - 9) \times 75)) \times 3) + 1) \\ 10792 &:= ((1 - ((3 - 5!) - 7!)) + 9) + (75^{3-1}) \\ 10793 &:= 1 \times ((3!! + ((5 - 7) \times (9 - 7!))) + (5 + 3! \times 1)) \\ 10794 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) + (9 + 7!)) + 5! \times (3 - 1) \\ 10795 &:= (1^3 \times (5! + 7)) \times (((97 - 5) - 3!) - 1) \\ 10796 &:= (((13 \times 5) + 79) \times 75) - (3 + 1) \\ 10797 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5! \times (7 - 97)) + 5) - 3) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10798 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) - 9) \times (7 - 5) + ((3! \times 1))! & 10837 &:= ((1 + (35 + 7)) \times ((9 + 75) \times 3)) + 1 \\ 10799 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5! \times (7 - 97)) - (5 - (3 + 1))) & 10838 &:= ((1 + 3!))! + (((5797 + 5) - 3) - 1) \\ 10800 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times (7 - (9 - ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)))) & 10839 &:= (((13 - 5!) + 7)^{9-7}) + (5! + (3!! - 1)) \\ 10801 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5! \times 7) - (97 \times 5!)) + 3 - 1) & 10840 &:= ((1 \times 3!)) - (((5 \times (7 + 9)) - 7!) - 5!) + ((3! + 1))! \\ 10802 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + (((5 - 7) + 9))! + (7! + (5 - (3 \times 1))) & 10841 &:= ((1 \times 3!)) + (5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + (5 + 31) \\ 10803 &:= (((1^{35}) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) + 3) - 1 & 10842 &:= (1 + 3!)) + (((5! - 7) \times 97) - (5! + (3!! \times 1))) \\ 10804 &:= (((13 \times 5) + 79) \times 75) + (3 + 1) & 10843 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + ((5 \times 7) + ((9 + (7! - 5)) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 10805 &:= (((1^{35}) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) + 3) + 1 & 10844 &:= (1 \times ((35 - 7) \times 97) - 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 10806 &:= ((1^{3!})^5) + (7! + ((9 + (7! - 5)) + 3!)) + 1 & 10845 &:= (1 + 35) - (7 - ((9 + (7 - 5!))^{3-1})) \\ 10807 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5!)) + 7!) - (9 - (7! + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) & 10846 &:= ((1 + 3!))! + (((5797 + 5) + 3) + 1) \\ 10808 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + (((5 - 7) + 9))! + (7! + 5) + 3 \times 1 & 10847 &:= (13 \times ((5! \times 7) - 9)) + (75 - 31) \\ 10809 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) \times 7) + (5 + 31) & 10848 &:= ((1 + (3! - 5!)) \times (7 - 9)) \times ((7^{5-3}) - 1) \\ 10810 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times 5!) + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + ((5 + 3!) - 1)) & 10849 &:= (1 + 3!) - (((5! - 7) - ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 10811 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5 + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3 \times 1)))) & 10850 &:= (((13 + 5!)/7) - 9) \times ((7 \times 5) \times 31) \\ 10812 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) + 3 + 1) & 10851 &:= ((1 + (3!! + 5)) + (7! + 9)) + (7! + (5 + 31)) \\ 10813 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((57 \times 9) \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1}) & 10852 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5) \times (7! + 9)) - (753 \times 1)) \\ 10814 &:= 1 + (3!! + (5! + (((7! + 9) + 7!) - (5! - (3 + 1)))))) & 10853 &:= (((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times (7 + 9)) + 7!) + (53 \times 1) \\ 10815 &:= ((1 + 3!)) - ((5! - 7!) - (9 + 7!)) + (5^3 \times 1) & 10854 &:= (13 + 5) \times (79 - (7 - 531)) \\ 10816 &:= 13 \times (((5 \times 7) - 9) \times (7 + (5^{3-1}))) & 10855 &:= 1 \times ((3!! \times 5) + ((7975 - 3!!) \times 1)) \\ 10817 &:= (1^{35}) + ((7 + 97)^{5-3} \times 1) & 10856 &:= 1 + ((3!! \times 5) + ((7975 - 3!!) \times 1)) \\ 10818 &:= ((13 + 5) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) & 10857 &:= ((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) \times (7!/(5! \times (3 - 1))) \\ 10819 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + ((7 + 97)^{5-3} \times 1) & 10858 &:= (1 + 3!)) + ((5! + 7!) - (9 - ((7! - 53) - 1))) \\ 10820 &:= (13 + 5) - (((7 - 97) \times 5!) - (3 - 1)) & 10859 &:= ((1 + 3!)) \times 5 + ((7975 - 3!!) - 1) \\ 10821 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times ((5! \times 7) - 9)) + 7!) - (5 + 31) & 10860 &:= ((1 + 3!)) + (5! + (7! - 9)) + ((7! - 53) + 1) \\ 10822 &:= 1 - (((((3 - 5) \times 7!) - (9 + 7)) - 5) - 3!! \times 1) & 10861 &:= ((1 + 3!)) \times 5 + ((7975 - 3!!) + 1) \\ 10823 &:= (13 \times (5! \times 7)) - ((97 \times 5)/(3! - 1)) & 10862 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) \times (7 \times 97))) \times (5 - (3! + 1)) \\ 10824 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) \times ((7 \times 9) + ((7! + 5!)/(3 + 1))) & 10863 &:= 13 + (5 \times ((7 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) \times 31)) \\ 10825 &:= (1^3) + (5! + (((7 \times 9) \times 7) + 5) \times (3 + 1)!) & 10864 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 - 7)^9) - (7! - (5 \times (3 + 1)!))) \\ 10826 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times 9) \times 7)) + (53 \times 1) & 10865 &:= ((1 + 3!))! - (((5! \times (7 - 9)) + 7) \times (5^{3-1})) \\ 10827 &:= ((13 \times 5!) \times 7) - (9 + (7!/(5!/(3 - 1)))) & 10866 &:= ((1 - (3!! + 579)) + (7! - 5!)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 10828 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) + 5!) \times 31) & 10867 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - 5) - (((7 + 9) \times (7 - 5!)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 10829 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) + (((7! \times (9 - 7)) + 5) + (3 + 1)!) & 10868 &:= ((13 - 5!) + (7 \times 97)) \times ((5!/3!) - 1) \\ 10830 &:= (1 \times 3!)) + ((5! \times 79) + (7!/(5 + 3 \times 1))) & 10869 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) + (5 \times 3!! \times 1))) \\ 10831 &:= ((1 \times 3!)) + (5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) - (5 - 31) & 10870 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) \times (7 - (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\ 10832 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5) - (((7 - 97) \times 5!) - (3 - 1)) & 10871 &:= ((1 + 3!))^{5-1} - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 10833 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - (3 - 1)) & 10872 &:= ((13 \times 5) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\ 10834 &:= ((1 + 35) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) - (3 - 1) & 10873 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + (5 + (7! + (((9 \times 7) + 5) + ((3! + 1)!))) \\ 10835 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5) - (((7 - 97) \times 5!) - (3 + 1)!) & 10874 &:= (((((1 + (35/7)))!)/9) + 7) \times (5^3) - 1 \\ 10836 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) \times ((5 - 3) + 1) & 10875 &:= ((1^{35}) + (79 + 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10876 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) + ((7! + 9) + ((7! - 53) - 1)) \\ 10877 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) + ((7! + 9) + ((7! - 53) \times 1)) \\ 10878 &:= ((13 + 5) + 7!) + ((97 \times 5!) / (3 - 1)) \\ 10879 &:= 1 - (3 \times ((5 - 79) \times (7 \times (5 + 3 - 1)))) \\ 10880 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 10881 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\ 10882 &:= 13 + ((5! + ((79 + 7) \times (5^3))) - 1) \\ 10883 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5! - 7))) \times ((9 - 7)^5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 10884 &:= (((1 + 3!) + (5 \times 79)) + 7!) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\ 10885 &:= (1 + ((3!! + 5!) + (7! \times (9 - 7)))) - (5 + 31) \\ 10886 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times 5))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 10887 &:= (13 \times (((5! \times 7) - 9) + 7)) - ((5 + 3) - 1) \\ 10888 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (79 \times 75)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 10889 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 + 75) + 3!)) - 1) \\ 10890 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5 + ((7!/9)/7) \times 5!)) - 31 \\ 10891 &:= (13 \times (5! \times 7)) + (((9 - (7 \times 5)) - 3) \times 1) \\ 10892 &:= (1 - (3 + (5 + 7))) \times (((9 \times 7) - 5!) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 10893 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5! \times 7) - 9)) + ((7! + 5) + 31) \\ 10894 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5 + (7! \times (9 - 7)))) + (5! - 31) \\ 10895 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + 5!) - 31) \\ 10896 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 10897 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7) + (5! + 3 + 1) \\ 10898 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7) + (5^3 \times 1) \\ 10899 &:= ((13 \times 5!) \times 7) - ((9 + 75) / (3 + 1)) \\ 10900 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + ((5! + (7! \times (9 - 7))) - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 10901 &:= (13 \times (((5! \times 7) - 9) + 7)) + ((5 + 3) - 1) \\ 10902 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5! \times (7 - 97))) + (5! - (3 + 1)!) \\ 10903 &:= ((1^{3!}) + (5! \times 7)) - ((9 - 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 10904 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (7 + 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1) \\ 10905 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) - ((5! - 7!) - ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 10906 &:= (13 + 5!) \times (((7 \times 9) - (7 + 5)) + 31) \\ 10907 &:= ((13 + 5) \times ((79 \times 7) + 53)) - 1 \\ 10908 &:= ((13 + 5) \times ((79 \times 7) + 53)) \times 1 \\ 10909 &:= ((13 + 5) \times ((79 \times 7) + 53)) + 1 \\ 10910 &:= (1^3 - 5) - ((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 10911 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - (((7 - 9) \times 7!) + (5 + 3 + 1)) \\ 10912 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5 - 7) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!) - 1)) \\ 10913 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 + (7 - (97 \times 5!))) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 10914 &:= (1 - (3 - 5!)) - (((7 - 97) \times 5!) + 3 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10915 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5 + 7) - 97) \times 5!) - (3!! \times 1) \\ 10916 &:= (1 - (3! + (5 - 7))) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!) - 1) \\ 10917 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) + (((7 - 9) + 7!) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 10918 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) - (((7 - 97) \times 5!) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 10919 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 - 7)) \times ((97 \times 5!) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 10920 &:= (13 \times (5 + 79)) \times ((7 + 5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 10921 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (5 - 7)) + (97 \times 5!)) - (3!! \times 1) \\ 10922 &:= (1^3) \times ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 75) + 3 - 1)) \\ 10923 &:= (1^3) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 75) + 3 - 1)) \\ 10924 &:= ((1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) + 9) \times 75)) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 10925 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5! - ((7! + (9 \times 7)) + 5!))) + 3!!) - 1 \\ 10926 &:= 1 \times (35 + (7! + ((975 \times 3!) + 1))) \\ 10927 &:= (1 - (((3 - 5!) + (7 + 97)) \times 5!)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 10928 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) \times 7) + (5 \times 31) \\ 10929 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) + ((3! - 1)!) \\ 10930 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 + 7) + (97 \times 5!))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 10931 &:= (((1^{3!}) + ((5 + 7!) \times (9 - 7))) + 5!) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 10932 &:= (((1 \times ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) / 7) \times 5) - (3 \times 1) \\ 10933 &:= 13 + ((5 \times ((79 + 7) + 5)) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 10934 &:= ((1^{3!}) + (5 + 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3!! - 1)) \\ 10935 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 + 97) + (5^{3+1})) \\ 10936 &:= (1 + ((3! + (5! \times 7)) + 9)) + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 10937 &:= ((1 \times (3!!/5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) - (3! + 1) \\ 10938 &:= ((1 \times (3!!/5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 10939 &:= (13 - (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times ((5! - 3!) - 1)) \\ 10940 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5!) - (((7! - 9) - (7^5)) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 10941 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5) + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 10942 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5 - ((7! - 9) + 7!)) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 10943 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5 \times (7! - ((97 - 5) \times 31))) \\ 10944 &:= (1^{3!}) \times ((57 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5 + (3! + 1))) \\ 10945 &:= (1^{3!}) + ((57 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5 + (3! + 1))) \\ 10946 &:= (1^3) + (((5! - 7) \times 97) - ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 10947 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) + 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) - 1) \\ 10948 &:= (13 \times (5! \times 7)) - (((9 - (7 \times 5)) - 3) + 1) \\ 10949 &:= (13 \times (5! \times 7)) - (((9 - (7 \times 5)) - 3) \times 1) \\ 10950 &:= ((1 \times (3!!/5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 10951 &:= ((1 \times (3!!/5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\ 10952 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5 + ((7!/9)/7) \times 5!)) + 31 \\ 10953 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 \times 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))) \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10954 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 \times 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))) + 1 \\ 10955 &:= ((1^3 + 5)!) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + 5 \times 31) \\ 10956 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 + 79)) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 10957 &:= (13 + (5! \times (79 + (7 + 5)))) + (3 + 1)! \\ 10958 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - (79 \times 75))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 10959 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (57 \times (9 + 7))) + 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 10960 &:= (1^3 + ((5! + 7) + 9)) \times (75 + (3! - 1)) \\ 10961 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + 5 \times 31) \\ 10962 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - (((7! - (9 + 7)) - (5^{3!})) - 1) \\ 10963 &:= 1 + ((3579 + 75) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 10964 &:= 1 + (((35 + 7!) + (9 + 7!) + 5!) + (3! - 1)) \\ 10965 &:= ((1 + (35 + 7!)) + (9 + 7!)) + ((5! + 3!) \times 1) \\ 10966 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5! + (7! + (9 + 7!)))) + (5 + 31) \\ 10967 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5!) - 7!) - (97 - ((5^{3!} - 1)) \\ 10968 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! - 7) \times ((9 - 75) - 31)) \\ 10969 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5) + 7) + (97 \times (5! - (3! + 1))) \\ 10970 &:= (((1 + 3!)!) - ((5! - 7!) - 9)) + (7!/5) - (3! + 1) \\ 10971 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (79 \times 7)) - (5! - 31) \\ 10972 &:= (13 \times ((5! \times 7) + (9 - 7))) - (5 - 31) \\ 10973 &:= (1 + ((3! - 57) \times 9)) + (7! - (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\ 10974 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((79 + (7 + 5)) + 3 - 1) \\ 10975 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) - (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 10976 &:= (1^3 - 5) \times (((7 - 9) - (7 + 5))^3 \times 1) \\ 10977 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! - 7) \times 97)) + ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\ 10978 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 - 7!) - (97 \times 5)) + 31) \\ 10979 &:= ((13 \times 5) - (7 - (97 \times 5!))) - (3! - 1) \\ 10980 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 \times ((7 \times 97) + (53 \times 1))) \\ 10981 &:= (1^{35}) - ((7 - 97) \times ((5! + 3) - 1)) \\ 10982 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3! - 1})) \\ 10983 &:= (((1 + 3!)!) - ((5! - 7!) - 9)) + (7!/5) + (3! \times 1) \\ 10984 &:= (((1 + 3!)!) - ((5! - 7!) - 9)) + (7!/5) + (3! + 1) \\ 10985 &:= ((13 \times 5!) \times 7) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 10986 &:= ((13 + 5) + 7) + (97 \times ((5! - 3!) - 1)) \\ 10987 &:= 1 - (3! + (5! - (7! + (9 \times (753 + 1)))))) \\ 10988 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5! \times 7)) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 10989 &:= (1 \times (3! \times (5! - (7 + 97)))) - 531 \\ 10990 &:= (13 + 57) \times (97 + (5! / (3 - 1))) \\ 10991 &:= (((((1 + 3) \times 5!) + 7!) - 9) \times (7 - 5)) - 31 \\ 10992 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5! - 7)) \times (97 + 5)) - (3 + 1)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10993 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (7! + 97)) + (5! \times 3!) - 1 \\ 10994 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (7! + 97)) + (5! \times 3!) \times 1 \\ 10995 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (7! + 97)) + (5! \times 3!) + 1 \\ 10996 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5! - 7) \times 97)) + (5 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 10997 &:= (((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) \times 5) + 3 - 1 \\ 10998 &:= 13 \times (((5 \times 7) - 9) + ((7 \times (5! - 3)) + 1)) \\ 10999 &:= (((13 - 5!) + 7) \times ((9 + (7 - 5!)) - 3!)) - 1 \\ 11000 &:= ((13 - 5!) + 7) \times (((9 + (7 - 5!)) - 3!) \times 1) \\ 11001 &:= ((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + 97) - ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\ 11002 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - ((79 - (7! + 5!)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 11003 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + ((5! - 7) + (975 \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 11004 &:= (1 + 3) + (5 \times (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5) - (3! - 1))) \\ 11005 &:= (13 \times (5! \times 7)) + ((97 - 5) - (3! + 1)) \\ 11006 &:= (1^{3!}) - ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - (5!^{3-1})) \\ 11007 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - ((7! + (9 - (7^5))) + (3! - 1)) \\ 11008 &:= (135 + (79 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\ 11009 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) - 79) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 11010 &:= ((135 \times 79) - (7! + 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 11011 &:= (13 \times (((5 + 79) - 7) \times (5 + 3!))) \times 1 \\ 11012 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times ((5! \times 7) - 9)) + 7!) + (5 \times 31) \\ 11013 &:= 1 - (3! - ((5 \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5)) - (3! + 1))) \\ 11014 &:= 1 - (3! - (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - 3! \times 1)) \\ 11015 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + 5) + 7) \times ((97 + 5) \times 3) - 1 \\ 11016 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + 5) + 7) \times (((97 + 5) \times 3) \times 1) \\ 11017 &:= (((1 + 3!)! + 5) + 7) \times ((97 + 5) \times 3) + 1 \\ 11018 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5) - (3! + 1) \\ 11019 &:= (1^3) + (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5) - (3! + 1) \\ 11020 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5) - (3! - 1) \\ 11021 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) - 7!) + (9 + (7^5)) - 31 \\ 11022 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5! \times 7)) + (97 \times 53)) + 1 \\ 11023 &:= (((1^3 \times 57) + 9) + 7) \times (5! + 31) \\ 11024 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) - 7!) + (9 + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 11025 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) - 7!) + (9 + (((7^5) - 3!) + 1)) \\ 11026 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 \times 7)) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) \times 1) \\ 11027 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5 + (7! + 9)) - (7^5)) + (3! + 1)) \\ 11028 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5! + ((7 - 9) \times (7! + 531))) \\ 11029 &:= (135 \times 79) + (7 \times (53 - 1)) \\ 11030 &:= 1 - (3 + (((5 + (7! + 9)) - (7^5)) + (3! + 1))) \\ 11031 &:= ((1^3 + 5!) \times (79 + 7)) + (5^{3+1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11032 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + ((7 + 97) \times 5)))) \times (3! + 1) \\11033 &:= ((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + 97) + ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\11034 &:= 13 + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1)) \\11035 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5 + 7)) + ((97 - 5) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\11036 &:= (13 + (5 - 7)) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5)^{3-1})) \\11037 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5 + (7! + 9)) - (7^5)) + (3!! \times 1)) \\11038 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! + 7!) \times (9 - 7))) + (5! \times 3! \times 1) \\11039 &:= ((1^3)^5!) - (7! + ((9 - (7^5)) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\11040 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5) - 7) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5) \times 3! \times 1) \\11041 &:= (1 - 3!!) + ((57 - 9) \times ((7 \times 5) \times (3! + 1))) \\11042 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (((5! + 7) + (97 \times 5!)) - (3! \times 1)) \\11043 &:= ((1 - 3!)^5) + (7 \times (((9 \times 75) \times 3) - 1)) \\11044 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)))! - 7!) - ((9 - (7^5)) + 3!! \times 1) \\11045 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - ((5! \times (7 - 9)) - (7! + 5))) + 3!! \times 1) \\11046 &:= (1 \times ((3 + (5! + 7!)) \times (9 - 7))) + (5! \times 3! \times 1) \\11047 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (((5 + 7!) - 9) - ((7^5) - 3!) - 1) \\11048 &:= 1 \times (3 + (5 \times (((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 + 1))) \\11049 &:= 1 + (3 + (5 \times (((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 + 1))) \\11050 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + 7) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!!) \times 1)) \\11051 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (579 + (7 \times 5))) \times 3) - 1 \\11052 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (579 + (7 \times 5))) \times 3) \times 1 \\11053 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (579 + (7 \times 5))) \times 3) + 1 \\11054 &:= 1 \times (3! + ((5! + 7) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!!) + 1))) \\11055 &:= 1 + (3! + ((5! + 7) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!!) + 1))) \\11056 &:= (((13 + 5) - 7!) - 9) + (7^5) - (3!! \times 1) \\11057 &:= ((1^3)^5) - (7! - ((9 + (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\11058 &:= 1 - (((3! - 5)^7) - (97 \times ((5! - 3!) \times 1))) \\11059 &:= 1 - ((3 + 579) \times ((7 + 5) - 31)) \\11060 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + 7) \times (5! / (3 + 1)!) \\11061 &:= (1 \times (35 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7 - 5!))^{3-1}) \\11062 &:= (1 + (35 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7 - 5!))^{3-1}) \\11063 &:= 1 - ((3 - ((57 \times 97) + 5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\11064 &:= 1 \times (3! \times (((5 + 797) + 5!) \times (3 - 1))) \\11065 &:= 1 + (3! \times (((5 + 797) + 5!) \times (3 - 1))) \\11066 &:= ((13 + 5) - 7) \times (975 + 31) \\11067 &:= (1 \times 357) \times (((9 - 7) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\11068 &:= (1 \times ((35 \times 79) + (7 - 5))) \times (3 + 1) \\11069 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times 5) - 7!) - ((9 - ((7^5) - 3!!)) - 1) \\11070 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 + 9)) + 7) \times (53 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11071 &:= (1 + ((3! - (5! - (7 + 9))) \times (7 - 5!))) - (3 + 1) \\11072 &:= (1 + 3) + (((57 \times 97) + 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\11073 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7!) - (9 - ((7^5) - 3!!))) \times 1 \\11074 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) - (((7 - 97) \times 5!) - 31) \\11075 &:= (1 - ((3! + 5) \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) - ((3! + 1)!)) \\11076 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times ((5! \times 7) + (975 + 31)) \\11077 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - (79 \times 7)) \times (5 + 3! \times 1) \\11078 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((579 \times 7) - (5! \times 3))) - 1 \\11079 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((579 \times 7) - (5! \times 3))) \times 1 \\11080 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((579 \times 7) - (5! \times 3))) + 1 \\11081 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! - 7) \times 97)) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!) \\11082 &:= ((13 + 5) + 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) - 1) \\11083 &:= (((1 - 3!!) - 5) - 7!) + (9 + (7^5)) + 31 \\11084 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) - (5! / (3! \times 1))) \\11085 &:= (1 + (3!! + (5! + (7! + 9)))) + (7! + 5 \times 31) \\11086 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 + 79) \times ((7 + (5^3)) \times 1)) \\11087 &:= ((13 + 5) \times 7) + (97 \times ((5! - 3!) - 1)) \\11088 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) \times (7 \times 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\11089 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) \times (7 \times 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\11090 &:= (1 - (3! \times (5 + (79 - (7! / 5)))) \times (3 - 1) \\11091 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - 7!) + (9 + (7 \times 5)) - ((3! \times 1)! \\11092 &:= ((1 \times 3 + ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + 5) \times (3 + 1) \\11093 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 5) + 79) \times ((7 - 5!) - 3!) + 1) \\11094 &:= (13 \times ((5! \times 7) + 9)) + ((7 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\11095 &:= (1 \times 35) + (79 \times (7! / (5 + 31))) \\11096 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 \times 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) \times 1)) \\11097 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) + 1) \\11098 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 - 79) \times 75) \times (3 - 1)) \\11099 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) \times 1)) \\11100 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((57 \times 9) - 7!) + ((5^3) - 1)) \\11101 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 7) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3) - 1) \\11102 &:= ((13 + 5) - 79) \times (7 \times (5 - 31)) \\11103 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 5) + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!)) \\11104 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) - (((7 - 9) \times (7! + 5)) - 3! \times 1) \\11105 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) - (((7 - 9) \times (7! + 5)) - (3! + 1)) \\11106 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + ((5! \times (7 + 9)) - 75)) \times 3! \times 1 \\11107 &:= (1 - 3) + ((579 + (7! / 5)) \times (3! + 1)) \\11108 &:= (((1 + 3!) - (5! + (79 + 7!))) + (5^3)) + 1 \\11109 &:= 1357 + (9753 - 1)\end{aligned}$$

- 11110** := $1 \times (3579 + 7531)$
11111 := $(1 + 3579) + 7531$
11112 := $(1 \times ((3!! + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + 7))) - (5! \times (3! - 1))$
11113 := $((1 - 3!!) + (5 - 7)) + (97 \times (5! + 3 - 1))$
11114 := $(13 \times (5 + (797 + 53))) - 1$
11115 := $(13 \times 57) \times (((9 + 7) + (5 - 3!)) \times 1)$
11116 := $(13 \times (5 + (797 + 53))) + 1$
11117 := $((((1 + 3^5) + 7!) + ((9 \times (7 - 5))^3)) + 1$
11118 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times (7!/9))) - ((75 + 3!) + 1)$
11119 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + ((79 + 7!) + 5!) + ((3! + 1))!$
11120 := $(13 + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 - 1))$
11121 := $((1 + (3579 + 7)) + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)$
11122 := $1357 + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 \times 31))$
11123 := $(1 \times (((3^5) - (7 + 9)) \times (7^{5-3}))) \times 1$
11124 := $(1 \times (((3^5) - (7 + 9)) \times (7^{5-3}))) + 1$
11125 := $((1 + (3 - 5)) - (7 - 97)) \times (5! + (3! - 1))$
11126 := $((1 - (3!! - (5! \times 7))) \times (97 - 5)) - (3! \times 1)$
11127 := $((1 - (3!! - (5! \times 7))) \times (97 - 5)) - (3! - 1)$
11128 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! + (3! - 1)))$
11129 := $(1 + ((3 - 5!) - 7)) + (97 \times (5! - (3 + 1)))$
11130 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! - (7 \times (9 - 7)))) \times (5 \times (3! + 1))$
11131 := $((1^3 + 5!) \times (7 - 9)) \times (7 - 53) - 1$
11132 := $((1^3 + 5!) \times (7 - 9)) \times (7 - 53) \times 1$
11133 := $1 \times 3 + (5 \times (7 \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1)))$
11134 := $((1 - (3!! - (5! \times 7))) \times (97 - 5)) + (3 - 1)$
11135 := $((1 - (3!! - (5! \times 7))) \times (97 - 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
11136 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5) + (3 + 1)!$
11137 := $1 - (3!! + (57 \times ((9 + 7) - 5!) \times (3 - 1)))$
11138 := $(1^{3!}) - ((5 - 7!) + ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) \times (3! \times 1)))$
11139 := $((1 - (3!! - (5! \times 7))) \times (97 - 5)) + 3! + 1$
11140 := $(1 - (3! - 5!)) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) \times (5^{3-1})))$
11141 := $1 \times (((3 - 5) \times 7) + (97 \times (5! - (3! - 1))))$
11142 := $((13 \times (5 + 797)) - 5) + (3!! + 1)$
11143 := $((13 \times (5! - (7 - 9))) \times 7) + ((5!/3) + 1)$
11144 := $((1 \times ((3! + 5!) - 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!)) - ((3! + 1))!$
11145 := $1 \times (3 \times 5 \times ((797 - 53) - 1))$
11146 := $1 + (3 \times 5 \times ((797 - 53) - 1))$
11147 := $((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (7! - 9)) + (7 \times (5 \times 31))$
11148 := $(1^3 - 5) \times (((79 - (7^5))/3!) + 1)$
11149 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (79 \times 7) + (5! - 3!)$
11150 := $((1^{3!}) \times 5) + ((7 \times 9) \times 7) \times 5 \times (3! - 1)$
11151 := $(1^3 \times ((5 + 7) - 9)) \times (7 \times 531)$
11152 := $(1^3) + (((5 + 7) - 9) \times (7 \times 531))$
11153 := $((1 - 3) - 5) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! + 3 + 1))$
11154 := $((1 + (3! + 5!)) + (7 + 9)) \times (75 + 3 \times 1)$
11155 := $(1 - (((3! - 5)^7) - 97)) \times ((5! - 3!) + 1)$
11156 := $1 - (3 - (5! - ((7! + (9 - (7^5)))) + ((3! \times 1))!))$
11157 := $1 \times ((3^5) - ((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + (3!! - 1)))$
11158 := $((1 - 3!) + 5) + (797 \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
11159 := $(1^3 + ((5! - 7!) - (9 - (7^5)))) - ((3! \times 1))!$
11160 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5 \times ((797 - 53) \times 1))$
11161 := $1 \times ((3 + (5! - 7!)) - ((9 - (7^5)) + ((3! \times 1))!))$
11162 := $1 + ((3 + (5! - 7!)) - ((9 - (7^5)) + ((3! \times 1))!))$
11163 := $(1 - 3) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3 + 1)$
11164 := $((1 + 3) - (((5 - 7) - 97) \times 5!)) - 3!! \times 1$
11165 := $((1 + 3) - (((5 - 7) - 97) \times 5!)) - 3!! + 1$
11166 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5! + 7)) \times (9 + 75) - (3! \times 1)$
11167 := $((1 + 3) \times 579) \times 7 - (5 + ((3! + 1))!)$
11168 := $(1 + (357 - 9)) \times (7 + (5^{3-1}))$
11169 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + (7 \times (97 \times 5)))) - (3 \times 1)$
11170 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5!) - 7! + ((9 + (7^5)) - 3!) \times 1$
11171 := $(1 + 3^5) + (7 + ((97 \times 5!) - ((3! \times 1))!))$
11172 := $(13 \times (5! \times 7)) + ((9 - 7) \times ((5^3) + 1))$
11173 := $((1 - 3) \times ((5 - 7!) - 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times 31)$
11174 := $1 \times (((3!^5) + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) + 3 \times 1)$
11175 := $1 + (((3!^5) + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) + 3 \times 1)$
11176 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! + 3 + 1))$
11177 := $(1 \times 35) + (7! + ((9 + (7!/5)) \times 3! \times 1))$
11178 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5! + 7)) \times (9 + 75) + (3! \times 1)$
11179 := $1 + (3! \times (5 - ((79 - (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))))$
11180 := $(13 \times 5) \times ((79 + 7) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1))$
11181 := $((13 \times 5!) \times 7) - (9 \times ((7 - 5) - 31))$
11182 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5^{3-1})))$
11183 := $1 \times 3! + ((5! - 7!) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3!! - 1)))$
11184 := $((1 + (3 \times 5 \times 7))^{9-7}) - (53 - 1)$
11185 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((7 \times 97) - 5!) + (3! - 1)$
11186 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (53 + 1))$

- 11187** := (((1 + 3!!) - (5! + (7! - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3!})) - 1
11188 := (((1 + 3!!) - (5! + (7! - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3!})) × 1
11189 := (((1 + 3!!) - (5! + (7! - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3!})) + 1
11190 := ((1³⁵) × (((7!/9) + 7!) - 5)) × (3 - 1)
11191 := (((135 - 7!) + 9) + (7⁵)) - 3!! × 1
11192 := (((1 + 3) × 5) × (7!/9)) - ((7 + 5) - (3 + 1))
11193 := (13 × (5! - 79)) × (7 + ((5 × 3) - 1))
11194 := (13 × (((57 + 9) + 75) + 3!!)) + 1
11195 := (((13 × 5!) × 7) + ((97 - 5) × 3)) - 1
11196 := (1 + (3!! + (5 × 79))) + (7! × ((5 - 3) × 1))
11197 := (((13 × 5!) × 7) + ((97 - 5) × 3)) + 1
11198 := ((1 - (3 + 5)) + 7!) - ((9 × ((7 × 5) - 3!!)) × 1)
11199 := (((1 + 3) × (5 × 7)) + 9) × 75 + (3 + 1)!
11200 := (((13 + 57) × (9 + 7)) × 5) × (3 - 1)
11201 := 1 - ((3 - 5) × (((7!/9) + 7!) × (5 - (3 + 1))))
11202 := ((1 × 3!)⁵) + ((7 × (97 × 5)) + 31)
11203 := (1 + (3!⁵)) + (((7 × 97) × 5) + 31)
11204 := ((1 + 3) × ((5 × 79) × 7)) + (5! + (3 + 1)!)
11205 := 135 × (((7 + ((9 + 7) + 5)) × 3) - 1)
11206 := (1 + ((3!! + (5! × 79)) + (7!/5))) - (3 × 1)
11207 := ((1 + (3 + (5 + 79))) × (7 + 5!)) + 31
11208 := (1 - 3) × (5 - (79 × ((75 - 3) - 1)))
11209 := (1 × ((3 - 5!) × 7)) + (97 × ((5! + 3) + 1))
11210 := ((1 × (3!! + (5! × 79))) + ((7!/5) + 3)) - 1
11211 := ((1 × (3!! + (5! × 79))) + ((7!/5) + 3)) × 1
11212 := ((1 × (3!! + (5! × 79))) + ((7!/5) + 3)) + 1
11213 := ((1 + 3!!) + ((5 - 7!) - 97)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)
11214 := (((1 + 3) - (5 + 7)) + 97) × ((5³) + 1)
11215 := (1 × 3!!) + ((5! × 79) + ((7!/5) + (3! + 1)))
11216 := ((1 × 3 + 5) × 79) - (7! - ((5^{3!}) - 1))
11217 := ((13 - 5) × 79) - (7! - (5^{3!×1}))
11218 := ((1 × 3 + 5) × 79) - (7! - ((5^{3!}) + 1))
11219 := ((13 + 5) + (((7!/9) + 7!) × (5 - 3))) + 1
11220 := ((13 - 5) + (79 × 7)) × (5 × (3 + 1))
11221 := ((1 × 3!!) - 5) - (79 + (7! - ((5^{3!}) × 1)))
11222 := ((1 × 3!!) - 5) - (79 + (7! - ((5^{3!}) + 1)))
11223 := (13 × (5! - 7)) + (9753 + 1)
11224 := (1 + 3)! + ((5 × ((7 + 9) × 7)) × (5!/3! × 1))
11225 := (1 + ((3 + 5) × ((7 × 9) - 7))) × (5 × (3! - 1))
11226 := (1 × (3 × ((5 + 7!) - (9 × 7)))) - (5! × 31)
11227 := (1 + 3!) - (5! - ((7!/(9 + 7)) × (5 + 31)))
11228 := (((1 × 3)! × 5!) + (79 × ((7 + 5!) + 3!))) + 1
11229 := ((1 + 3)! + ((57⁹⁻⁷) × 5)) - ((3! + 1)!)
11230 := ((1 + 3) - (579 + 7!)) × (5 - (3! + 1))
11231 := (1 × 3!!) + ((5 - 79) - (7! - ((5^{3!}) × 1)))
11232 := (13 + (5 × ((79 + 7) + 5))) × (3 + 1)!
11233 := 1 - ((3 - (5 × (7 × 9))) × (7 + (5 + (3 + 1)!)))
11234 := (1 + 3) - (5 × (79 - (75 × 31)))
11235 := ((1 - 3) - (5! - 7)) + ((97 × (5! - 3)) + 1)
11236 := (((1 - 3) - (5! + 7)) - 97) + 5!³⁻¹
11237 := (((((1 + 3)⁵) + (7! + 9)) + 7!) + 5!) + (3 + 1)
11238 := (((1 - 3!) - 5) × (7!/9)) + ((7⁵) + 31)
11239 := 1 - (3! × ((5! + 7) - ((9 + 7) × ((5³) × 1))))
11240 := ((1 - 3) × 5) - ((7 - 97) × (5! + (3! - 1)))
11241 := ((1 - 3 + (57 × 9)) × (7 + (5 × 3))) - 1
11242 := ((1 - 3 + (57 × 9)) × (7 + (5 × 3))) × 1
11243 := ((1 - 3 + (57 × 9)) × (7 + (5 × 3))) + 1
11244 := ((1 + 3)! × (5 × 7)) + ((97 + 5)³⁻¹)
11245 := ((1^{3!}) + (5! × 7)) + ((97 + 5)³⁻¹)
11246 := (((1 - 3!) × 5) × ((7 - 97) × 5)) - 3 - 1
11247 := ((13 + ((5! + 79) × 7)) × (5 + 3)) - 1
11248 := ((13 + ((5! + 79) × 7)) × (5 + 3)) × 1
11249 := (((1 + 3) × 5) × (7!/9)) + (7^{5-3×1})
11250 := (1 × (3⁵ + 7)) × ((97 - 53) + 1)
11251 := 13 + ((579 + 7!) × (5 - (3 × 1)))
11252 := (1³⁵) - (((7 - 97) × (5³)) - 1)
11253 := ((1³)⁵7) + (97 × (5! - (3 + 1)))
11254 := 13579 - (75 × 31)
11255 := (1³ × 5) - ((7 - 97) × (5! + (3! - 1)))
11256 := (((1 - 3!) + 57) × 9) + (7! + 5!) × (3 - 1)
11257 := (1³ - 5!) + (79 × ((7 + 5)³⁻¹))
11258 := ((1 + ((3⁵) × 7) + 9) × 7) - ((5! × 3!) - 1)
11259 := 1 - (3!! - (((5! - 7) × (9 - 7)) × (53 × 1)))
11260 := ((1 × (3! + 5)) × (7 + (9 + (7!/5)))) - (3 + 1)
11261 := (1 + (3 × (5 × 79))) + (7! - (5 - ((3! + 1)!)))
11262 := (1 + 3)! - ((579 + 7!) × (5 - (3! + 1)))
11263 := ((13 × (((5 × 7) - 9) + (7 × 5!))) + 3!) - 1

$$\begin{aligned} 11264 &:= ((1+3)^5) \times (((7 \times 9)/7) + (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 11265 &:= ((13 \times (((5 \times 7) - 9) + (7 \times 5!))) + 3!) + 1 \\ 11266 &:= (1+3) + (5! - ((7-9) \times (7! + 531))) \\ 11267 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5!) + ((7-9)^7))) \times ((5!/3!) - 1) \\ 11268 &:= (1-3) + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + 7) \times (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\ 11269 &:= 13 + ((5+79) \times ((7+5!) + (3! + 1))) \\ 11270 &:= (((1-3) \times 5) \times (7 \times (97-5!))) \times (3! + 1) \\ 11271 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 57) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5)/(3+1))) \\ 11272 &:= 1 + (3 - ((5-7) \times (9 + (75^{3-1})))) \\ 11273 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5!)) - (7 - (97 \times 5!))) - (3!! + 1) \\ 11274 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) - 1) \\ 11275 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) + 7)) + (97 \times (5 + 31)) \\ 11276 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) + 1) \\ 11277 &:= (((1+3)! - 5) \times 7) \times 9 + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 11278 &:= (1 \times (((3+5!) \times 79) + (7 \times 5!))) + (3!! + 1) \\ 11279 &:= (1 \times 3! \times ((5! \times (7+9)) - (7 \times 5))) - 31 \\ 11280 &:= (((1 + ((3+5) \times (7+9))) + 7) \times 5!) - ((3! + 1)!) \\ 11281 &:= (1 + (((3!! + 5!) + 7!) \times (9-7))) - (5! \times (3+1)) \\ 11282 &:= ((1+3) \times (5 \times (7!/9))) + ((75+3!) + 1) \\ 11283 &:= (1-3 + ((57 \times 9) \times (7 + (5 \times 3)))) - 1 \\ 11284 &:= (1+3) + (5! \times ((7 + ((9+7) \times 5)) + (3! + 1))) \\ 11285 &:= (1-3 + ((57 \times 9) \times (7 + (5 \times 3)))) + 1 \\ 11286 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 57)) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 - (3-1))) \\ 11287 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 5!) + (7 + (97 \times 5!)))) - 3!!) \times 1 \\ 11288 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5 \times 7))^{9-7}) + (53 - 1) \\ 11289 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((57 \times (9-75)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 11290 &:= (1+3) - (57 \times ((9-75) \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 11291 &:= (((1+3!)! - (5! - 7!)) + (((9+7) - 5)^3 \times 1)) \\ 11292 &:= (1 + ((3! - 5) + 7!)) + ((9-7) \times (5^{3!-1})) \\ 11293 &:= 13 + (5! \times ((7 \times 9) + (((7 \times 5) - 3) - 1))) \\ 11294 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + 5) - (7! + (((9+7) - (5^{3!}))) \times 1)) \\ 11295 &:= (1 + (3^5 + 7)) \times ((97-53) + 1) \\ 11296 &:= (1 + (3-57)) + (97 \times (5! - (3 \times 1))) \\ 11297 &:= 13 + (((5+79) + 7) \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 11298 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5-7) + 9) \times (7 + 531)) \\ 11299 &:= (((1-3!)^5) + (((7-9) + 7)!) \times 5!) + (3+1)! \\ 11300 &:= ((1-3!) \times 5) \times ((7-9) \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 11301 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) - (9 \times 7) + (5 \times (3!! - 1)) \\ 11302 &:= ((1 \times (3+5!)) \times (79+7)) + ((5+3!!) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11303 &:= ((1 - ((3! - 5!) - 7)) \times 97) - 531 \\ 11304 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5!)/7)) \times (97 + 531) \\ 11305 &:= (13 + 5!) \times ((79 + (7 - 5 + 3)) + 1) \\ 11306 &:= (1 - 35) - ((7 - 97) \times ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 11307 &:= (13 \times 5!) - (7 - (9753 + 1)) \\ 11308 &:= (1 - 357) + ((9 \times (7 + 5))^{3-1}) \\ 11309 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (7 + 5)))) - 31 \\ 11310 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + (5! - 79)) - 7) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 11311 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - (5! - 7!)) \times (9 - 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\ 11312 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 797)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 11313 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - (5! - 7!)) \times (9 - 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) + 1) \\ 11314 &:= (1 + 3!!) + ((57 \times 9) + ((7 - 5) \times ((3! + 1)!!)) \\ 11315 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) \times (97 + 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 11316 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! / 5) \times 79) - ((7 + 5) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 11317 &:= (13 \times 57) - (9 + (7! - ((5^3) \times 1))) \\ 11318 &:= ((13 \times 5!) - 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 11319 &:= (13 \times 5!) + ((7 + 9753) - 1) \\ 11320 &:= (((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!! \times 1 \\ 11321 &:= (1 - (3!! - (5 + 7))) + (97 \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 11322 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (5! \times 7)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1) \\ 11323 &:= 13 - (5 \times ((7 \times 9) - (75 \times 31))) \\ 11324 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5! \times 7)) + (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1)) \\ 11325 &:= (((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - 9) + 7) \times (5^{3-1}) \\ 11326 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (5 - ((7! - ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!}))) \times 1)) \\ 11327 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((79 + 7!) + ((5! \times 3) + 1)) \\ 11328 &:= (1 - (35/7)) \times (((9 - 7) - 5!) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 11329 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) \times (97 + 5)) + (3! + 1) \\ 11330 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - (5^{3+1}) \\ 11331 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5! \times 7) + (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1)) \\ 11332 &:= 1 - (((3! - (5! \times (7 \times 9)))/(7 - 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 11333 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! + 3! \times 1)) \\ 11334 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! \times 7) + (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1)) \\ 11335 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (((5! - 7) + ((97 - 5!)^3)) \times 1) \\ 11336 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (((5! - 7) + ((97 - 5!)^3)) - 1) \\ 11337 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - (7 - ((97 - 5)^{3-1})) \\ 11338 &:= ((13 + (5! + 7)) \times (9^{7-5})) - (3 - 1) \\ 11339 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) + ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\ 11340 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 - 7)) \times (53 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11341 &:= 1 + (3 \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 - 7)) \times (53 + 1))) \\11342 &:= ((13 + (5! + 7)) \times (9^{7-5})) + (3 - 1) \\11343 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5! \times (7 - (9 - 7)))) \times (5 - (3 + 1)!) \\11344 &:= ((1 - ((3 - 5) + 7)) + (97 \times (5! - 3))) - 1 \\11345 &:= (1357 \times 9) - (7 \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\11346 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((5! + 7) + (9 - 75)) \times 31) \\11347 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) - (79 + 7!)) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\11348 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5))/7) + (97 \times (5! - (3 \times 1))) \\11349 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) + (7 + 97)) \times (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\11350 &:= (1 - (3 \times 57)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! \times 1))) \\11351 &:= ((1 + 3)^{5-7+9}) - ((7! - (5 + 3)) + 1) \\11352 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((57 \times 9) + (75 \times 31)) \\11353 &:= (1357 \times 9) - ((7! + 5!)/3! \times 1) \\11354 &:= (((13 \times 57) + (9 + 7)) \times (5 \times 3)) - 1 \\11355 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + ((7! + (9 \times 75)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\11356 &:= (1 + (3! + 5)) - ((7 + 9) \times ((7 + 5) - (3! + 1))) \\11357 &:= 1 - ((3! + (5 - 79)) \times (((7!/5)/3!) - 1)) \\11358 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 - 7!) - ((9 \times 75) - 31)) \\11359 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5 - 7) - 97) \times (5! + 3 - 1)) \\11360 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 \times ((7 - 9)^7)) - (((5 + 3) - 1)!) \\11361 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + 7)) + (9 - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1)!) \\11362 &:= ((1 + 3)! - 5) \times (((7 - 9)^7) + (5 + (3! + 1))) \\11363 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + 9) - 7) \times (5 + 3! \times 1) \\11364 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5! + ((7 - ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) \times (3! \times 1))) \\11365 &:= 1 - (((3^5) - (79 \times 75)) \times (3 - 1)) \\11366 &:= (((13 + 5!) \times 79) + ((7! + 5!)/3!)) - 1 \\11367 &:= (((13 + 5!) \times 79) + ((7! + 5!)/3!)) \times 1 \\11368 &:= (((1 + 35) \times 79) - (7 - 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\11369 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) + ((5! + 3!) - 1) \\11370 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) + ((5! + 3!) \times 1) \\11371 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) + ((5! + 3!) + 1) \\11372 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times ((79 - (7! + (5 + 3!))) \times 1) \\11373 &:= ((135 \times 79) - (7 + 5)) + (3! \times 1) \\11374 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + (7! + (5! + 31))) \\11375 &:= 13 \times ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + (7 + (5 + 3))) + 1)) \\11376 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times (((9 - 7) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\11377 &:= (135 \times 79) - (7 - ((5! \times 3!) - 1)) \\11378 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (579 + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) - 1)) \\11379 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (579 + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) \times 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11380 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 579) + 7!) + (((5 + 3) - 1)!) \\11381 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5! + 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5! \times 3!) - 1)) \\11382 &:= (((1 + 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75))) - 3!) - 1 \\11383 &:= (((1 + 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75))) - 3!) \times 1 \\11384 &:= (((1 + 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75))) - 3!) + 1 \\11385 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + ((5 \times 79) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\11386 &:= (1 - (3^5)) - (((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3!) - 1) \\11387 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5 \times 7) + (97 \times (5! - 3)))) - 1 \\11388 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 \times ((97 \times 5) + 31)) \\11389 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5 \times 7) + (97 \times (5! - 3)))) + 1 \\11390 &:= 1 \times (3! + ((5 \times 7) + (97 \times ((5! - 3) \times 1)))) \\11391 &:= ((135 \times 79) + (7 + (5! \times 3!))) - 1 \\11392 &:= ((135 \times 79) + (7 + (5! \times 3!))) \times 1 \\11393 &:= ((135 \times 79) + (7 + (5! \times 3!))) + 1 \\11394 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (9 + 75))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\11395 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5! \times (7 - 97))) - (5! + (3! - 1)) \\11396 &:= 1 \times ((3^5 + (7 + 9)) \times (75 - 31)) \\11397 &:= 1 + ((3^5 + (7 + 9)) \times (75 - 31)) \\11398 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - ((7! + (9 - (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\11399 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 5!) - ((7! + (9 - (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\11400 &:= ((1^3 \times (5! + 7)) + (9 \times 7)) \times (5!/(3 - 1)) \\11401 &:= ((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + (97 \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \\11402 &:= (13 - (5 \times 7)) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 - (3! - 1))) \\11403 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5! \times (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3) - 1) \\11404 &:= (1 + 3) + (5! \times (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3) - 1) \\11405 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((975/3) + 1)) \\11406 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5!) - (7! + ((97 - 5!) \times (3! \times 1))) \\11407 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (7 - (97 - (5! \times 31))) \\11408 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times (7 - (9 - 75)))) \times 31 \\11409 &:= (13 \times 5) - (7! - ((9 - 7)^{5 \times 3 - 1})) \\11410 &:= ((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + (97 \times 5)) + (3! - 1) \\11411 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5!) + (7 + (97 \times 5!))) + (3 + 1) \\11412 &:= (13 - (((5 \times 7) - 9) - 7) \times (5! - 3!)) - 1 \\11413 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5! - (7 + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! \times 1)))) \\11414 &:= (13 - (((5 \times 7) - 9) - 7) \times (5! - 3!)) + 1 \\11415 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times (797 - (5 + 31)) \\11416 &:= ((1 + ((3! \times 5!) - 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - (5 + 3 \times 1) \\11417 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) \times (7 + (9 \times (7 \times (5 - 31)))) \\11418 &:= (135 \times 79) + (753 \times 1)\end{aligned}$$

- 11419** := $1357 - ((9 - 7!) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1))$
11420 := $((1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 79))) \times 7) + (5^{3!-1})$
11421 := $(1 \times (3^5)) \times (79 - (7 + (5^{3!-1})))$
11422 := $((((1 \times 3)!)! - ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + (7! - 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
11423 := $(1 \times (3!! + 5!)) - (7! + ((9 - 7) - ((5^{3!}) \times 1)))$
11424 := $(1 - 35) \times (7 - (((9 - 7) + 5)^3 \times 1))$
11425 := $1 + ((3 \times 5 \times 797) - 531)$
11426 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (7! + (9 \times 75)) - (3 + 1)$
11427 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) \times (((7!/9) + 75) \times 3!) - 1$
11428 := $((1 + 3!!) + 5!) - (((7! - (9 - 7)) - (5^{3!})) \times 1)$
11429 := $((1 + 3!!) + 5!) - ((7! - (9 - 7)) - (5^{3!})) + 1$
11430 := $1 \times 3! + (((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times (7!/5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
11431 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7!/9) + 75)) \times 3! + 1$
11432 := $(1 \times ((3! + 5) + 79)) \times (7 + 5!) + (3 - 1)$
11433 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 579) \times 7) - 5)) - 3!! - 1$
11434 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 579) \times 7) - 5)) - 3!! \times 1$
11435 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 579) \times 7) - 5)) - (3!! - 1)$
11436 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 75) + (3! \times 1)))$
11437 := $((13 + 5!) \times (79 + 7)) - (5 - (3 + 1))$
11438 := $(1 - 3) \times (5 - (((7 \times 97) + 5) + ((3! + 1)!!))$
11439 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) \times (79 + ((7 + 5) + 3 - 1))$
11440 := $13 \times (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7 \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)$
11441 := $((13 + 5!) \times (79 + 7)) + (5 - (3 - 1))$
11442 := $1 \times (((3! \times 5!) \times (7 + 9)) - (75 + 3 \times 1))$
11443 := $1 + (((3! \times 5!) \times (7 + 9)) - (75 + 3 \times 1))$
11444 := $((13 + 5!) \times (79 + 7)) + ((5 - (3 - 1))!)$
11445 := $(1 \times 35) \times ((7 + 97) + 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
11446 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5! - 79) - 7!) - ((5 + 3!!) - 1))$
11447 := $(1 + 3!) + ((579 - 7) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
11448 := $((135 \times 7) + 9) \times (7 + (5!/(3 + 1)!))$
11449 := $(1 - ((3 - 5!) \times (7 + 97))) - (5! \times 3! \times 1)$
11450 := $(1 - 3!) \times (5 - (((7!/9) + 7) \times 5) + (3!! \times 1))$
11451 := $((1 - 3) \times 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times (7 + 5!))) \times (3 \times 1))$
11452 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 \times 79) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3!)) - 1)$
11453 := $((13 \times 5!) + 79) \times 7 - (5 \times (3 + 1))$
11454 := $((1^3 + 5)! \times (7 + 9)) - (7!/5!) - (3 + 1)!$
11455 := $(1 - 3!) \times (5 - (((7!/9) + 7) \times 5) + (3!! + 1))$
11456 := $((1 + 3!) \times 57 + 9) + (7! \times (5 - 3)) - 1$
11457 := $((1 + 3!) \times 57 + 9) + (7! \times (5 - 3)) \times 1$
11458 := $((1 + 3!) \times 57 + 9) + (7! \times (5 - 3)) + 1$
11459 := $(1357 \times 9) - (753 + 1)$
11460 := $(1357 \times 9) - (753 \times 1)$
11461 := $(1357 \times 9) - (753 - 1)$
11462 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times ((5! - 3) - 1))$
11463 := $(1 + 3!) - (((5! - (7 + 97)) \times (5 - 3!!)) + 1)$
11464 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5! \times 3!) - 1))$
11465 := $(13 \times 5) - (((7 - 97) - 5) \times ((3! - 1)!!)$
11466 := $1 \times ((3! - (5! - (7 + 9))) \times ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1)))$
11467 := $1 + ((3! - (5! - (7 + 9))) \times ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1)))$
11468 := $((1 - 3!) - 5!) - ((7 - ((9 + 7) \times (5 + 3!!))) \times 1)$
11469 := $((1 - (3^5)) + (7! - 975)) \times (3 \times 1)$
11470 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57 - 97) \times 5 \times 31$
11471 := $((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) - (3!! + 1)$
11472 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - 97 + 5!) \times (3 + 1)!$
11473 := $((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) - (3!! - 1)$
11474 := $((13 + 5!) \times (79 + 7)) + 5 + 31$
11475 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797) - (5! \times (3 + 1))$
11476 := $((1 - 3!) - 5!) + (7! + (9^{7 \times 5 - 3!}))$
11477 := $1 + ((3 - 5) - ((7 - ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) \times 3! \times 1))$
11478 := $((1 + (3!^5)) - (7 + 9)) + (7 \times 531)$
11479 := $(1 - ((3 - 5)^7)) + ((97 \times (5! - 3)) + 1)$
11480 := $((1 + ((3! \times 5) \times 79)) - 75) \times (3! - 1)$
11481 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5) - (7 \times (9 \times (7 \times (5 - 31))))))$
11482 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) - (7 \times (9 \times (7 \times (5 - 31))))$
11483 := $(1 - 3!) - (((5! - 7) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 + 3!!))) - 1)$
11484 := $1 \times 3! + (((5! + 7) \times 97) - 5!) - (3!! + 1)$
11485 := $(135 \times (79 + 7)) - (5^3 \times 1)$
11486 := $((1^3!) - (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) \times (3! \times 1))$
11487 := $(135 \times (79 + 7)) - (5! + 3 \times 1)$
11488 := $(13 \times (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7 \times 5!))) - (3 + 1)$
11489 := $((13 \times (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7 \times 5!))) - 3) \times 1$
11490 := $((13 \times (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7 \times 5!))) - 3) + 1$
11491 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (7 - (9 - 7))) + (5! \times 31)$
11492 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5! - 3!)) - 1)$
11493 := $((13 \times 5!) + 79) \times 7 + (5 \times (3 + 1))$
11494 := $(135 \times (79 + 7)) - ((5! - 3) - 1)$
11495 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5! - 3!))) - 1$
11496 := $(13 \times (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7 \times 5!))) + (3 + 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 11497 &:= ((1+3) \times ((5! \times (7+(9+7))) + (5! - 3!))) + 1 \\ 11498 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times (9 \times 7))) + 5) + ((3! \times 1)! \\ 11499 &:= (135 \times 79) + (((7 \times 5!) - 3!) \times 1) \\ 11500 &:= (13 - (57 \times 9)) \times (7 - (5 \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 11501 &:= 1 + (((3 + 579) - 7) \times (5!/3! \times 1)) \\ 11502 &:= 1 - ((35 - (7 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5))) \times 31) \\ 11503 &:= ((135 \times 79) + (7 \times 5!)) - (3 - 1) \\ 11504 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5)) \times (7 + (97 - 5!))) \times (3!! - 1) \\ 11505 &:= (1^{35}) - ((7 + (97 - 5!)) \times (3!! - 1)) \\ 11506 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) - 7) + (97 \times 5!) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 11507 &:= ((135 \times 79) + (7 \times 5!)) + (3 - 1) \\ 11508 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! - 7) \times (97 + 5)) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 11509 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 + 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\ 11510 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((5! + 7) - ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))) - 1 \\ 11511 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 + 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 11512 &:= 1 \times ((3 - 5!) - ((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3 + 1)) \\ 11513 &:= 1 + ((3 - 5!) - ((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3 + 1)) \\ 11514 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) + 1) \\ 11515 &:= (1 - 3!) + (5! \times (((7 + 97) - (5 + 3)) \times 1)) \\ 11516 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 5!) - 7)) + (97 \times ((5!/(3 + 1)!)!)) \\ 11517 &:= (1^3 - ((5! + 7) - (97 \times 5!))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 11518 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! + (7 - (97 \times 5!)))) + (3 - 1) \\ 11519 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5)/7) + (97 \times 5!) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 11520 &:= 1 - ((3 - ((5! - 7) \times (97 + 5))) + 3 + 1) \\ 11521 &:= ((1^{35}) + 7!) + (9 \times ((7 - (5 - (3 + 1))))!) \\ 11522 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 57) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\ 11523 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! + 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) + (3! + 1)) \\ 11524 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5 - 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! \times 1)))) \\ 11525 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times 5!) + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + 5 + 3!! \times 1 \\ 11526 &:= ((1 \times 3)!) - (((5! - 7) - ((97 \times 5!) - 3!)) + 1) \\ 11527 &:= (1 - 3579) + ((7! - 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 11528 &:= 1 - (3 - (((5! - 7) \times (97 + 5)) + 3 + 1)) \\ 11529 &:= (135 \times (7 \times 9)) + (((7!/5) \times 3) \times 1) \\ 11530 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5! - (7 + (97 \times 5!))) - (3! - 1)) \\ 11531 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! - (7 + (97 \times 5!)))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 11532 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (5 - (7 - 9))) \times ((7 + 5) \times 31) \\ 11533 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5! - (7 + (97 \times 5!)))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 11534 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) + 3)) \times 1 \\ 11535 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 - (((7 + 9) \times 75) - ((3! + 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11536 &:= (1 - (3^5)) - (((7! - 9) - (7^5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 11537 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! - (7 + (97 \times 5!)))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 11538 &:= (13 - ((5! - 7) - (97 \times 5!))) - (3 - 1) \\ 11539 &:= ((1 + 3!) - ((5! - (7 + (97 \times 5!))) - 3!)) - 1 \\ 11540 &:= (13 - 57) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 11541 &:= (13 \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) - (7!/(5 - (3 - 1))) \\ 11542 &:= (13 - ((5! - 7) - (97 \times 5!))) + (3 - 1) \\ 11543 &:= (13 \times (((5! - 7) + (9 \times 7)) + 5! \times 3)) - 1 \\ 11544 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) + 5) + ((7! + 9) - (7 - 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 11545 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5!)) - (((7 - 97) \times 5!) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 11546 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)))) + (3 - 1) \\ 11547 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!) \times (7 + 9)) + 7 + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 11548 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5 \times ((7 + 9) - (75 \times 31))) \\ 11549 &:= (((1 + 3)! - 5!) + (7 + (97 \times 5!))) - (3 - 1) \\ 11550 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5^{7-9+7}) + 5) + 3!! \times 1) \\ 11551 &:= (1^3 + 5!) + ((7! + (9 \times 75)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 11552 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 75) + 3! + 1)) \\ 11553 &:= (13 \times 5) - ((7 + 9) \times (((7 - 5) - 3!) \times 1)) \\ 11554 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! - (3 \times 1))) \\ 11555 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 11556 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! - 7) \times (97 + 5)) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 11557 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5 + 7)) + (97 \times 5!))) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 11558 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) - (5 - 7)) \times 9 + 7! + (5!/3! \times 1) \\ 11559 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 57) \times 9) - (753 \times 1) \\ 11560 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 11561 &:= (1 + (3 - 5)) + ((7 + ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 11562 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 11563 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (79 + (7! + 5!))) - (3! - 1) \\ 11564 &:= (1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times 97) - 5!)) + (3!! \times 1) \\ 11565 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times 97) - (5! - (3!! + 1))) \\ 11566 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - 7!) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 11567 &:= (((1357 \times 9) + 75) - 3!) - 1 \\ 11568 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7 + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 11569 &:= (((1357 \times 9) + 75) - 3!) + 1 \\ 11570 &:= (135 - (7 - (9 - 7))) \times (5! - 31) \\ 11571 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5! - 3) + 1)) \\ 11572 &:= ((1 - 35) + (7!/9)) \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 11573 &:= (1^3 - (579 \times 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 11574 &:= (1^3 - (579 \times 7)) + ((5^3!) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 11575** := $(1 \times 3) - (5! + (79 \times (7 - (5 \times 31))))$
11576 := $(1 - (3^5)) + ((7! + (9 \times 753)) + 1)$
11577 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 797) - (5^3)) - 1)$
11578 := $(1 \times 3)! - (5! + (79 \times (7 - (5 \times 31))))$
11579 := $((((1 \times 3! + 5!) - 7) \times 97) + (5 + 31))$
11580 := $(1 \times (3 + 57)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! \times 1)))$
11581 := $((1 + 3) + 57) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! \times 1)))$
11582 := $1 - (3 - ((5797 - 5) \times (3 - 1)))$
11583 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 797) - (5^3)) + 1)$
11584 := $(1 + ((3!! \times (5 + 7)) + (9 \times 7))) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)!$
11585 := $((13 \times 57) \times 9) + ((7! - 5!) - (3 + 1))$
11586 := $((1 + 35) \times (7 + ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) - (3! \times 1)$
11587 := $1 \times 3 + ((5797 - 5) \times (3 - 1))$
11588 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5 - 7) + (97 \times 5))) - (3 + 1)$
11589 := $((((1 + 3!))! - 5) - 7) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31})$
11590 := $((((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (7 \times 97)) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1))$
11591 := $((1 + ((3 - 57) + (97 \times 5!))) + 3) + 1$
11592 := $((13 - 57) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3)) - 1$
11593 := $((13 - 57) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3)) \times 1$
11594 := $((13 - 57) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3)) + 1$
11595 := $((((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + 7) - ((5 + 3!) - 1))$
11596 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5 - 7!) - ((9 + 753) + 1))$
11597 := $((((1 \times 3!) + 5) \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! \times 1))))$
11598 := $((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times 97)) - (5 + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
11599 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) - (((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3!) - 1)$
11600 := $1 - ((3 \times (5 + 7)) - ((97 \times 5!) - (3! - 1)))$
11601 := $((1 + (3^5)) + 7) + (97 + (5! \times 31))$
11602 := $(135 \times (79 + 7)) - (5 + 3 \times 1)$
11603 := $((1 + 3!))! - ((5 - 7) - (9^{7 \times 5 - 31}))$
11604 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5797 + 5) / (3 - 1))$
11605 := $((13 \times 5!) + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) - (5 - 31))$
11606 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + (7 + ((97 \times 5!) - 31))$
11607 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1))$
11608 := $((1 - 3!) / 5) - (7 - ((9 + 7) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1)))$
11609 := $((1 \times (3 \times 57)) \times 9) + ((7! - 5) \times (3 - 1))$
11610 := $((((1 \times ((3 - 5) + 7)))! \times 97) - (5! / (3 + 1)))$
11611 := $(1 + (((3^5) \times 7) + 9) \times 7) - ((5! \times 3) \times 1)$
11612 := $(135 \times (79 + 7)) + (5 - (3 \times 1))$
11613 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 + 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3 \times 1))$
11614 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 - 9) - 7!) - (5! + 31))$
11615 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times 9)) - 7!) - (5! - 31)$
11616 := $1^{357} \times ((97 \times 5!) - (3 + 1)!)!$
11617 := $13 + ((5797 + 5) \times (3 - 1))$
11618 := $((13 + (((5! + 7) \times 97) + 5)) - 3!) + 1$
11619 := $(13 \times (5! \times 7)) + ((9 \times 75) + (3 + 1)!)!$
11620 := $(1 \times 3 + (5 \times (7 + 9))) \times (7! / (5 + 31))$
11621 := $((((1 - 3) - 5) - 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3! - 1)))$
11622 := $(1^{3!}) \times (((5! - (7! / 9)) - 7) \times (5 - 31))$
11623 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5! + 7) \times 97)) - ((5! \times 3!) \times 1)$
11624 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 - 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5! - 3) - 1))$
11625 := $((((1 \times 3)!)! \times 5) + (((7 \times 9) \times (7 + 5!)) + (3 + 1)!)!$
11626 := $(13 \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + 7531$
11627 := $(1 + (3 - 5)) \times (((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3!) \times 1)$
11628 := $1 \times ((3! \times 57) \times ((97 + 5) / (3 \times 1)))$
11629 := $1 + ((3! \times 57) \times ((97 + 5) / (3 \times 1)))$
11630 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7! - ((97 - 5!) \times 3!)) - 1)$
11631 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) - (((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3!) - 1)$
11632 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) - ((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3 + 1)$
11633 := $((((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) - 3)) - 1)$
11634 := $((((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) - 3)) \times 1)$
11635 := $((((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) - 3)) + 1)$
11636 := $(1 + ((3 - 5!) - 7!)) - ((9 - (7^5)) + (3! \times 1))$
11637 := $(1^{357} + ((97 \times 5!) - 3)) - 1$
11638 := $(1^{357} + ((97 \times 5!) - 3)) \times 1$
11639 := $(1^{357} + ((97 \times 5!) - 3)) + 1$
11640 := $((1 + 3) + (5 + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)))) \times (3 + 1)!$
11641 := $((((1 + 3) - ((5 - 7) - 97)) \times 5!) - (3! - 1))$
11642 := $1 + (((((3 - 5) + 7))! \times 97) - (5 - (3! \times 1)))$
11643 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) - ((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3!)) \times 1$
11644 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) - (7 - (97 \times 5!))) + (3 - 1)$
11645 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5! \times (7 - 97))) + (5! + (3! - 1))$
11646 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5! \times (7 - 97)) - (5! + (3! - 1)))$
11647 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + ((7 + ((97 \times 5!) + 3!)) + 1)$
11648 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) + 3 \times 1)$
11649 := $1 \times (((3 - 5) + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 + 1))$
11650 := $1 + (((3 - 5) + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 + 1))$
11651 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5 - (7 - (97 \times 5!))) + (3! \times 1))$
11652 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! + (7 + 97)) \times (53 - 1))$

- 11653** := $(13 - 5!) + (((7 \times 9) + (7 \times 5)) \times ((3! - 1)!)$
11654 := $(1 - (((3 - 5) - 7) - (97 \times 5!))) + (3 + 1)$
11655 := $(1 - ((3 - (5 + 7)) - (97 \times 5!))) + (3! - 1)$
11656 := $(13 \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! - (53 \times 1))$
11657 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) + (((7 + (97 \times 5!)) + 3) - 1)$
11658 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7! - ((9 + 7) - (5^3 \times 1)))$
11659 := $((((1 \times 3!) + 5) + ((7 - (9 - 7)))) \times (5! - 3!))$
11660 := $(1 - 3) - ((5! + (7! - 9)) - ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
11661 := $1 - ((3 - (5! - 7)) \times ((97 + 5) + 3 + 1))$
11662 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 + (9 + 7!)) + 5!)) + 3!)$
11663 := $((13 \times 5!) \times 7) - ((9 - 753) + 1)$
11664 := $((((1 \times 3! + 57) - 9)^{7-5}) \times (3 + 1))$
11665 := $((((1 \times (35/7)))! \times 97) + (5^{3-1}))$
11666 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5 + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) + (3! + 1)))$
11667 := $((13 + 5) + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 - 1)$
11668 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7! - (9 + 7)) + 5!) - 3! + 1)$
11669 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7! - (9 + 7)) + 5!) - 3! \times 1)$
11670 := $((((1 \times ((3 - 5) + 7)))! \times 97) + (5! / (3 + 1)))$
11671 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7! + ((97 - 5) + 3 + 1))$
11672 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 - 1)$
11673 := $((((1 + 3)^5) - 7!) + ((9 \times 7) + ((5^3) + 1)))$
11674 := $((1 \times (3! \times 5)) + (7 + (97 \times 5!))) - (3 \times 1)$
11675 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) - (3 \times 1))$
11676 := $((1 + (3! - 5)) \times (79 \times (7! / 5!))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
11677 := $(1 + (3! + ((5 \times 7) + (97 \times 5!)))) - (3! - 1)$
11678 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5! - 79) - (7 \times (5! + 3!))) \times 1)$
11679 := $((((1^3)^5) + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3!))$
11680 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5 \times 3!)$
11681 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) + (((97 \times 5!) + 3) \times 1)$
11682 := $(1 + ((3 \times (5 + 7)) + (97 \times 5!))) + (3! - 1)$
11683 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5) + (7 + (97 \times 5!))) + 3! \times 1$
11684 := $(1 + (3^5 + 7!)) + (((9 + 7) \times 5)^{3-1})$
11685 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - (79 + 7!)) - ((5 - 3) + 1))$
11686 := $1 + ((3 + 5!) \times (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3) - 1))$
11687 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) + (3 + 1)!)$
11688 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 79) - (7! - (5^{3 \times 1})))$
11689 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - 79) - 7!) + ((5 - 3) - 1)$
11690 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - (79 + 7!)) + ((5 - 3) \times 1))$
11691 := $((1 - 3 + 57) + (97 \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)$
11692 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) \times 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3 + 1))$
11693 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5) + 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3!)$
11694 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((79 + 7!) - (((5 - 3) + 1)!))$
11695 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times 9)) - (7! + (5 + 3 + 1)))$
11696 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 + 7)) \times ((97 - (5! - 3!)) + 1)$
11697 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 - (79 - (7^5))) - ((3! + 1)!))$
11698 := $(13 \times (5! \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) - (5 - 3! \times 1))$
11699 := $((1 - 3 + 57) + (97 \times 5!)) + (3 + 1)$
11700 := $(13 \times 5) - (7 - ((97 \times 5!) + 3 - 1))$
11701 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! - 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 + (3! - 1))))$
11702 := $((1 + 3) - (5! - 7!)) + ((9 \times 753) + 1)$
11703 := $((((1 + 3!)! - 5!) + (7 \times (975 - 3! \times 1)))$
11704 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5! - 7) - (9 \times (753 \times 1))))$
11705 := $(1 \times (3! + 5)) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! + 3 - 1))$
11706 := $((1 - 3!) + (5! + 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1))$
11707 := $(1 + (3 \times ((5 + 7!) + 97))) - (5! \times 3!)$
11708 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - ((79 - (7^5)) + ((3! + 1)!))$
11709 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5! - (7 - ((9 + 7) \times (5 + 3!)))) + 1)$
11710 := $((13 \times 5) + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3 - 1))$
11711 := $(((((1 \times 3!)! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7! - 5!)) - (3 + 1))$
11712 := $(1 + (3! + 5)) \times (7 + (975 - 3! \times 1))$
11713 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 \times 9) + (7! - (5 + 3 + 1)))$
11714 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 \times 9) - 7!) - (5! - (3 + 1)))$
11715 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5! \times 3!)$
11716 := $((1 - 3!) \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1)$
11717 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7! - (9 - 7)) + (53 - 1))$
11718 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 75) - (3 + 1)!)$
11719 := $(((((1 \times 3!)! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7! - 5!)) + (3 + 1))$
11720 := $((((1^3!) \times (579 + 7)) \times (5! / 3!)) \times 1)$
11721 := $((1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times 97) + 5!)) - 3! - 1)$
11722 := $((1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times 97) + 5!)) - 3! \times 1)$
11723 := $((1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times 97) + 5!)) - 3! + 1)$
11724 := $((((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5 + (3! + 1)))$
11725 := $((13 + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) + 7)) \times 5) \times (3! + 1)$
11726 := $(1 + ((3! - 57) + (9 + (7^5)))) - ((3! + 1)!)$
11727 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) + ((9 \times (7 + 5))^{3-1})$
11728 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - 7!) - ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3! - 1)))$
11729 := $((((1 \times 35) / 7))! + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))$

- 11730** := $((((1 \times 3!)!) + 5!) \times 7) + (975 \times 3! \times 1)$
11731 := $1 - ((35 + 7!) + 9) - ((7^5) + 3!) + 1)$
11732 := $((1 - 3)^5) - (7! + 9) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))$
11733 := $(1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) - 31$
11734 := $1 \times ((3! - ((5! - (7 + 9)) \times (7 - 5!))) - (3 + 1)!)!$
11735 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 + 7!) + (9 + (7^5))) - 31$
11736 := $((1 - 3) \times 57) \times (9 + (7 - 5!)) - ((3! - 1)!)!$
11737 := $(1^3 + 5!) \times (((7 + 9) \times 7) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
11738 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5 + 7) \times 975) + 31$
11739 := $(((((1 \times 3!)!) + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + 7!) - 5! + (3 + 1)!$
11740 := $(1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((7 - 9)^7) - 5) + (3!! \times 1))$
11741 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)!)!$
11742 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) - 7! - ((9 - (7^5)) + (3! \times 1))$
11743 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) - 7 + ((97 \times 5!) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
11744 := $((1^{3!}) + (5! \times 7)) - (9 - 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
11745 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) - (7! - 9) + (7^5) - 3! \times 1$
11746 := $((1 - 3) - 5) - 7 + (97 \times 5!) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
11747 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - 7! + ((9 + 7) - (5 + 31))$
11748 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) - (7! - 9) + (7^5) - (3 \times 1)$
11749 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! - (97 \times (5 + 3!))) \times 1$
11750 := $(1 + 3) - 5 - ((7! + 9) - ((7^5) - (3! + 1)))$
11751 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) - (3 + 1)!$
11752 := $(1 + (35 + 7)) + 9 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)$
11753 := $(1 + 3) - 5 \times ((7! + 9) - ((7^5) - (3! - 1)))$
11754 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) - (7! - 9) + (7^5) + (3 \times 1)$
11755 := $(1 + (3 - 5)) \times (7! + ((9 - (7^5)) + 3 \times 1))$
11756 := $(1 - 3!) \times (5 \times 7) + ((97 \times (5! + 3)) \times 1)$
11757 := $(1^3 \times (5 - (7! + 9))) + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1))$
11758 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7! + (9 + 7)) + (5 + 3 - 1)$
11759 := $(1^3 - 5) - (((7! + 9) - ((7^5) + 3!)) + 1)$
11760 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5! \times (3! + 1)))$
11761 := $1 - (3 \times (((5 \times 79) - (7! - (5 + 3!))) \times 1))$
11762 := $(1 \times (3^5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!) + (3!! - 1)$
11763 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) - (3!! \times 1))$
11764 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5) + 7))! + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 + 1)$
11765 := $((1 - 3!) + 5) - (((7! + 9) - (7^5)) - (3! + 1))$
11766 := $((1 - (3 - 5))!) - (7! + 9) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1)$
11767 := $((1 + (3 \times 5 \times 7))^{9-7}) + 531$
11768 := $((13 + 5) \times 7) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 - 1)$
11769 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 + 7!) - ((9 + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1))$
11770 := $1 \times ((3! + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) + 3 + 1)$
11771 := $((1 \times 3!) - ((5 + 7!) - (9 + (7^5)))) - 3! \times 1$
11772 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - (7! + 9) + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1))$
11773 := $((1^{35}) - 7!) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3 + 1))$
11774 := $((1^{35}) - 7!) + (9 + ((7^5) - 3) \times 1)$
11775 := $((1 \times 3!) - ((5 + 7!) - (9 + (7^5)))) - (3 - 1)$
11776 := $1 \times ((3 - ((5 + 7!) - (9 + (7^5)))) + 3 - 1)$
11777 := $1 + ((3 - ((5 + 7!) - (9 + (7^5)))) + 3 - 1)$
11778 := $((1 + 3) - (5 + 7!)) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 3 \times 1)$
11779 := $((13 + 5) - 7!) - 9 + (7^5) + (3 \times 1)$
11780 := $((13 + 5) - 7!) - 9 + (7^5) + 3 + 1$
11781 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) - (7! - 9))) + (7^5)) - 3 - 1$
11782 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) - (7! - 9))) + (7^5)) - (3 \times 1)$
11783 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) - (7! - 9))) + (7^5)) - 3 + 1$
11784 := $(1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times (7 + 97)) - (5 + (3 + 1)!)!$
11785 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) - (((7! - 9) - (7^5)) + 3!)) \times 1$
11786 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) - (((7! - 9) - (7^5)) + 3!)) + 1$
11787 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) - 7!) + ((9 + ((7^5) + 3)) - 1)$
11788 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) - (7! - 9))) + (7^5)) + (3 \times 1)$
11789 := $((1 - 3 + 5)!) - (7! - 9) + (((7^5) + 3!) + 1)$
11790 := $(1 \times (3! + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1)!$
11791 := $((1 \times 35) / 7)! + ((97 \times 5!) + 31)$
11792 := $((13 + 5) - 7!) + (9 + (((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
11793 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times 9) - 7! + (5! - 31)$
11794 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5 \times 7) - (97 \times ((5! + 3) - 1)))$
11795 := $(1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) + 31$
11796 := $1 - (((3! \times (5 \times (7 - (9 \times 7)))) - 5) \times (3! + 1))$
11797 := $(1 + ((3 \times (5 + 7)) + (97 \times 5!))) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
11798 := $(13 \times 5!) + ((79 + 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
11799 := $((1 + 35) - 7!) - 9 + ((7^5) + (3! - 1))$
11800 := $((1 \times (35 - 7!)) - 9) + ((7^5) + (3! + 1))$
11801 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5) - (7! - 9) + (((7^5) - 3!) + 1)$
11802 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5) - ((7 - 9)^7) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
11803 := $(1 \times (3! \times 5)) - (((7! - 9) - (7^5)) + 3 \times 1)$
11804 := $(1^3 - 5) + (7! + (9 \times (753 - 1)))$
11805 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times 97) + 5!) + (3!! + 1)$

- 11806** := $(1 \times 35) - (7! - ((9 + (7^5)) - (3! - 1)))$
11807 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5!) - 7)) + ((97 \times (5! + 3)) \times 1)$
11808 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5!) - 7)) + ((97 \times (5! + 3)) + 1)$
11809 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) - 7!)) + ((9 + (7^5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
11810 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) + ((7 + (97 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
11811 := $((1 \times 3 + 5!) - 79) + ((7^5) - ((3! + 1)!))$
11812 := $((((1 \times 35) + 7!) - 9) + (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 - 1)$
11813 := $((((1 \times 3!) \times 5) - (7! - 9)) + (((7^5) + 3!) + 1))$
11814 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) + 1)))$
11815 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 7) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3) - 1))$
11816 := $(1 \times (3 \times 579)) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) - 1)$
11817 := $(1 \times (3 \times 579)) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) \times 1)$
11818 := $(1^{35}) + (7! + ((9 \times 753) \times 1))$
11819 := $((1^{35}) + 7!) + ((9 \times 753) + 1)$
11820 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) + 79) \times (7 + (53 \times 1))$
11821 := $(1 - 3 + (5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 753) + 1)$
11822 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - 7!) - 9) + ((7 - 5)^{3 \times 1})$
11823 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((((5! + 7) \times 9) + 7!) - 5!) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
11824 := $(1 \times ((3!^5) + 7!)) - (((9 - 7)^5) \times 31)$
11825 := $((13 + 5) - 7!) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 31)$
11826 := $((13 + 5!) + (79 + 7)) \times (53 + 1)$
11827 := $((1 \times ((3! + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + 7))) + 5!) - (3! - 1)$
11828 := $((1 \times (3 + (5! - 7))) \times (97 + 5)) - (3 + 1)$
11829 := $((1 - (3 + 5!)) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) - 5!))) - (3! - 1)$
11830 := $13 \times ((5! \times 7) - (((9 - 75) - 3) - 1))$
11831 := $1 \times (((3 \times 5) + 7!) + ((9 \times 753) - 1))$
11832 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5) + (7 + 97))) \times (5! - (3 + 1))$
11833 := $1 + (((3 - 5) + (7 + 97)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)))$
11834 := $(1^{357}) \times (97 \times (5! + 3 - 1))$
11835 := $1 - (((3 + 5) - (79 \times 75)) \times (3 - 1))$
11836 := $(1 - 3) \times (5 - (((79 \times 75) - 3) + 1))$
11837 := $((1 \times ((3! + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + 7))) + 5!) + (3! - 1)$
11838 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5! - 7!) - (975 + (3 + 1)!))$
11839 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - (5! - (3 + 1))$
11840 := $((13 \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) - ((5 \times 3) + 1)$
11841 := $(1357 \times 9) - ((7 + 5) \times 31)$
11842 := $(1357 - 975) \times 31$
11843 := $((1 - (3 - 5!)) \times 79) + ((7 \times (5! \times 3)) + 1)$
11844 := $(1 \times (3^5 + (79 + 7))) \times (5 + 31)$
11845 := $1 \times 3! + (((5! + 7) \times 97) - (5! \times (3 + 1)))$
11846 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) + (79 - 7!)) \times ((5 - 3) - 1))$
11847 := $((13 \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) - ((5 + 3) + 1)$
11848 := $((13 \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) - ((5 + 3) \times 1)$
11849 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times ((7 + 97) - 5)) - 31$
11850 := $((((1 - 3) - 5) + 797) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
11851 := $13579 - ((7 + 5)^3 \times 1)$
11852 := $((((13 + 5!) \times 7) + (97 \times 5!)) - (3! - 1))$
11853 := $1 + ((357 \times 9) + (7! + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
11854 := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - 31)$
11855 := $((1 + 3) + (5 + 79)) + ((7^5) - ((3! + 1)!))$
11856 := $((1 \times (3 + (5! - 7))) \times (97 + 5)) + (3 + 1)!$
11857 := $(1^{3!}) - (57 \times (((9 + 7) - 5!) \times (3 - 1)))$
11858 := $(1 - (3^5)) \times (7 - (((9 \times 7) - 5) - 3) + 1))$
11859 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (79 \times (75 \times (3 - 1)))$
11860 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) - ((7! - 9) - ((7^5) - 31))$
11861 := $(1^3) \times (5 + (((7 + 97) \times (5! - 3!)) \times 1))$
11862 := $(1 \times 3!) - (57 \times (((9 + 7) - 5!) \times (3 - 1)))$
11863 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5) + (7 \times 975))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
11864 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times ((5! + 3) - 1))$
11865 := $((((1 \times 3!) - 5) + 7) + 97) \times (5! - (3! + 1))$
11866 := $((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7! + 9) + 7531$
11867 := $1 - (3! - ((5! - (7! + 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) \times 1)))$
11868 := $1 - (3! - ((5! - (7! + 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) + 1)))$
11869 := $1 \times (((3^5) - ((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3!)) - 1)$
11870 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) - ((7! + (9 - (7^5)))) + 3 \times 1$
11871 := $(1^3 + (5 + (7 \times 975))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
11872 := $((13 \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) + ((5 \times 3) + 1)$
11873 := $((1^3 + 5!) - (7! + 9)) + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1))$
11874 := $1 - (((3 \times (5 - 797)) \times 5) + (3! + 1))$
11875 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times (7 + (9 + 7)))) + (5 \times (3! - 1))$
11876 := $1 - (((3 \times (5 - 797)) \times 5) + (3! - 1))$
11877 := $(1 \times (3! - (5 - 7))) + (97 \times (5! - (3! - 1)))$
11878 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5! - (7! + 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) - 1))$
11879 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) - ((7! + (9 - (7^5)))) - 3! \times 1$
11880 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((7 \times 975) + ((3! + 1)!))$
11881 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5) + (7 \times 975))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
11882 := $((1 + 3!) - (5 + (7! / (9 - 7)))) + (5!^{3-1})$

- 11883** := $((1^3 \times 5)!) - (((7! + 9) - (7^5)) - 3!) + 1$
11884 := $((1^3 \times 5)!) - (((7! + 9) - (7^5)) - 3!) \times 1$
11885 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) - (7 - (9 \times (7! - (5! \times 31))))$
11886 := $(1 \times (35 + 7)) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5!)) / (3 \times 1))$
11887 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5! - 7!)) + ((9 - (7 - 5))^{3!-1})$
11888 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) \times ((797 - 53) - 1)$
11889 := $1 \times (((3!!/5) - 7!) + 9) + ((7^5) - 31)$
11890 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times (5! + 3)) - 1$
11891 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 53)) - 1$
11892 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 53)) \times 1$
11893 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 53)) + 1$
11894 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) - (7! - 9) + ((7^5) + ((3! - 1)!!)$
11895 := $(1 - (3! \times (5 \times (7 - 9)))) \times (75 + ((3! - 1)!!)$
11896 := $(1 - (3 - 5!)) - ((7! - 9) - ((7^5) + 3 - 1))$
11897 := $(13 \times 5!) \times 7 + ((975 + 3) - 1)$
11898 := $(1^3 \times 5!) - ((7! - 9) - ((7^5) + 3 - 1))$
11899 := $((1 - 3) - (5! + 7)) + (97 \times ((5! + 3) + 1))$
11900 := $((1 + 3) - (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times (5! + 3 \times 1))$
11901 := $1 - (35 \times ((7 - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)))$
11902 := $1 \times (((3 \times (5 \times 797)) - 53) \times 1)$
11903 := $1 \times (((3 \times (5 \times 797)) - 53) + 1)$
11904 := $1 + (((3 \times (5 \times 797)) - 53) + 1)$
11905 := $((135 - 7!) + 9) + (7^5) - 3! \times 1$
11906 := $((1 + 3) + (5! - 7!)) + (9 + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
11907 := $((13 + 5) + (7 \times 9)) \times 7 \times ((5!/3!) + 1)$
11908 := $((135 - 7!) + 9) + (7^5) - (3 \times 1)$
11909 := $(1 - 3 \times 5) - (7 - ((97 \times (5! + 3)) - 1))$
11910 := $((1 + (3 - 5)) + (7 + 9)) \times ((75 + 3!!) - 1)$
11911 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times ((7 + 97) - 5)) + 31$
11912 := $((1 \times (3 + 5!)) \times (79 + (7 + 5))) + (3!! - 1)$
11913 := $(135 - 7!) + (((9 + (7^5)) + 3) - 1)$
11914 := $((135 - 7!) + 9) + (7^5) + (3 \times 1)$
11915 := $(13 - (5 - (((7 \times 9)^{7-5}) \times 3))) \times 1$
11916 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 - 9) - 7!) + (5! + 31)$
11917 := $((135 - 7!) + 9) + (7^5) + 3! \times 1$
11918 := $(1 \times ((3!!/5) - 7!)) + ((9 + ((7^5) - 3)) + 1)$
11919 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 \times 9) - 7!) + 5!) - 31$
11920 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 - 9) + (7! - (5! + 31)))$
11921 := $1 - (35 - ((797 \times (5 \times 3)) \times 1))$
11922 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) \times (9 \times 7) + 5 \times (3 \times 1)$
11923 := $((1 + 3) - (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5! + 3 \times 1))$
11924 := $((1^{35}) - 7) + ((97 \times (5! + 3)) - 1)$
11925 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - (5! / (3 + 1))$
11926 := $((1^{35}) - 7) + ((97 \times (5! + 3)) + 1)$
11927 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + (7 + (97 \times (5! + 3))) - 1$
11928 := $(1 + 3) \times (57 + ((975 \times 3) \times 1))$
11929 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5 \times 797) + (5 - 31))$
11930 := $1 + ((3 \times 5 \times 797) + (5 - 31))$
11931 := $((1 + 3) - (5! + 7)) \times 97 \times (5 - (3! \times 1))$
11932 := $((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (7 + (97 \times 5)))) + (3 + 1)$
11933 := $(1 \times (((3!!/5) - 7!) - 9)) + ((7^5) + 31)$
11934 := $(1 \times (3 - 5!)) \times (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5!) - (3! - 1))$
11935 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) - 7) + 9 \times (7 \times (5 \times 31))$
11936 := $(1^3) - ((5 - (7 + 9)) \times (7 \times (5 \times 31)))$
11937 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - 7 + ((9 + 7) \times (5 + (3!! - 1)))$
11938 := $((1^{35}) + 7) + ((97 \times (5! + 3)) - 1)$
11939 := $((1^{35}) + 7) + ((97 \times (5! + 3)) \times 1)$
11940 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) + 5! \times (3! - 1)$
11941 := $(1 - 3 + (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5! + 3 \times 1))$
11942 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + (7! + ((9 \times 753) + 1))$
11943 := $1 + 35 + (((7 \times 9)^{7-5}) \times 3) \times 1$
11944 := $((1 + (3! + 5!)) + 7!) + (9 \times (753 \times 1))$
11945 := $((13 + (5! + 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3!-1})$
11946 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - 5 - (3 + 1)$
11947 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (7 + (97 \times (5! + 3 \times 1)))$
11948 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + (797 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
11949 := $(1 + (((3 + (5 \times 797)) - 5) \times 3)) - 1$
11950 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - (5! / (3 + 1)!)$
11951 := $((1 \times 3)!) + (5 \times 7) \times 9 + ((7! + 5!) - (3 + 1))$
11952 := $(13 + (((5 \times 797) - 5) \times 3)) - 1$
11953 := $(13 + (((5 \times 797) - 5) \times 3)) \times 1$
11954 := $(1^{35}) \times ((797 \times (5 \times 3)) - 1)$
11955 := $(1^{35}) + ((797 \times (5 \times 3)) - 1)$
11956 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + 5 - (3 + 1)$
11957 := $(1 - 3 + (5 + (797 \times (5 \times 3)))) - 1$
11958 := $(1 - 3 + (5 + (797 \times (5 \times 3)))) \times 1$
11959 := $(1 - 3 + (5 + (797 \times (5 \times 3)))) + 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 11960 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + (5!/(3+1)!) \\ 11961 &:= (1-3!) + ((5 \times 7) + ((97 \times (5!+3)) \times 1)) \\ 11962 &:= ((1-3!) + (5 \times 7)) + ((97 \times (5!+3)) + 1) \\ 11963 &:= ((1-3!) + 5!) + ((7! - 9) + 7531) \\ 11964 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + 5) + (3+1) \\ 11965 &:= (1-3!) + ((5 - (7-97)) \times (5! + (3! \times 1))) \\ 11966 &:= 1 \times (((3! + (5 \times 7)) \times (9+7)) - (5! - (3! \times 1))) \\ 11967 &:= (1 + ((3! + (5 \times 7)) \times (9+7))) - (5! - (3! \times 1)) \\ 11968 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 \times 797))) + (5 + (3! + 1)) \\ 11969 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + 79) + ((7^5) - ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 11970 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times ((5 + 7975)/(3+1)) \\ 11971 &:= (1-3!) + (5! + ((7+97) \times (5! - (3! \times 1)))) \\ 11972 &:= (((1 \times 3)!/5) - (7-9)) \times (75 + (3! + 1)) \\ 11973 &:= ((1+3!)^5) + (((79-7!) + 5!) + (3! + 1)) \\ 11974 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - 5) + (3+1)! \\ 11975 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + ((7+97) \times (5! - (3! - 1))) \\ 11976 &:= (((1+3) - (57 \times 9)) + (7!/5)) \times (3+1)! \\ 11977 &:= 1 + (3 \times (((5 \times 797) + (5+3)) - 1)) \\ 11978 &:= ((1+3!) - 5!) \times ((7^{9-7}) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 11979 &:= (1 + ((3! - 5) + 7)) \times (((9+7) - 5)^3 \times 1) \\ 11980 &:= 1 - ((3! - (5! + 7)) \times (97 - (5 - (3! + 1)))) \\ 11981 &:= (((1+3!)^5) + (((7 \times 9) - 7!) + 5!)) + 31 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11982 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (7! + ((9+75)^{3-1})) \\ 11983 &:= (((1+3!) + (5 \times 7)) \times (9+7)) - ((5! - 3!) - 1) \\ 11984 &:= ((13-5!) \times (7+9)) \times ((7 - (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 11985 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + (5!/(3+1)) \\ 11986 &:= 1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 797)) + (5!/(3+1))) \\ 11987 &:= 1 \times (((3! + (5 \times 797)) + 5) \times 3) - 1 \\ 11988 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) + (9-7)) \times (53+1)) \\ 11989 &:= ((1-3) \times ((5-7!) - 975)) - 31 \\ 11990 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times 5) \times ((7!/(9-7)) - (5! + 3 - 1)) \\ 11991 &:= (1 \times 357 + (97 \times 5!)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 11992 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5 \times 797) + 5)) + 31 \\ 11993 &:= (13 \times ((5+797) + 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\ 11994 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times (5-7)) \times (9 - (7!/5)))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 11995 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times 5) \times (((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3!)) - 1) \\ 11996 &:= ((1^3 - 5) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) - 5) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 11997 &:= (((1-3) \times (5! \times ((7 + (9 \times 7)) - 5!))) - 3) \times 1 \\ 11998 &:= (1 - 35) + ((7+9) \times (753-1)) \\ 11999 &:= (((1-3 + (5! + 7)) \times 97) - 5!) - 3! \times 1 \\ 12000 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5!) + (7 + (97 \times 5!))) - (3! + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

2.7 Numbers From 12001 to 14000

$$\begin{aligned} 12001 &:= (((1^3 + 5)! + (797^{-5})) + (3! + 1)!) \\ 12002 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - 7) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5)/(3-1)) \\ 12003 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) - ((7! + 9) - (7^5))) + 3)) - 1 \\ 12004 &:= (1 + (((3^5) - ((7! + 9) - (7^5))) + 3)) - 1 \\ 12005 &:= (1 + (((3^5) - ((7! + 9) - (7^5))) + 3)) \times 1 \\ 12006 &:= (13 - (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 12007 &:= (((1-3 + (5! + 7)) \times 97) - 5!) + (3-1) \\ 12008 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5 \times 797))) + 53) - 1 \\ 12009 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5 \times 797))) + 53) \times 1 \\ 12010 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5 \times 797))) + 53) + 1 \\ 12011 &:= (((1-3 + (5! + 7)) \times 97) - 5!) + 3! \times 1 \\ 12012 &:= (1+3!) \times ((579-7) \times ((5-3)+1)) \\ 12013 &:= (((1+3)^5 + 7!) \times (9-7)) - (5! - (3! - 1)) \\ 12014 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) + (7 + (97 \times 5!)))) + (3! \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12015 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5!) + (7 + (97 \times 5!)))) + (3! + 1) \\ 12016 &:= ((1 + ((3^5) - 7!)) + (9 + ((7^5) - 3))) - 1 \\ 12017 &:= (1 - (3 - (5! + 79))) \times (7 + (53 + 1)) \\ 12018 &:= (1-3) + (5 \times (79 + (75 \times 31))) \\ 12019 &:= (1 - (35/7)!) \times ((9+7) - (5! - (3 \times 1))) \\ 12020 &:= (1 + (35 + (7 - (9 \times 7)))) \times ((5! - 3!) - 1) \\ 12021 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5 \times 7))) + (97 \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 12022 &:= (((1+3)! - 5!) - 7) + (97 \times (5^3)) \times 1 \\ 12023 &:= (1 + 3^5) - ((7! - 9) - ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 12024 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times (5+7)) \times 97) + (((5+3) - 1)!) \\ 12025 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (79 + (75 + 31)) \\ 12026 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5 \times (79 + (75 \times 31))) \\ 12027 &:= (1+3!) + (5 \times (79 + (75 \times 31))) \\ 12028 &:= (1-3) + ((5 \times (797+5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12029 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 \times 9) - ((7! - 5) - 3!! \times 1)) \\12030 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7! + 975)) \times (3 - 1) \\12031 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (57 + 9)) + (7^5)) - ((3! + 1)!) \\12032 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((7 + 9) \times (753 - 1)) \\12033 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 5) + 7)) + (97 \times (5! + 3 + 1)) \\12034 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) - 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 531) \\12035 &:= (1 - (3!! \times 5)) + (((7 \times 9)/7) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\12036 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) \times (7 + (97 + (5 - (3! + 1)))) \\12037 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5!) - 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5! - 3!) - 1)) \\12038 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (57 \times (9 \times 7))) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\12039 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5! + (3!! + 1)) \\12040 &:= (1 + (3! \times ((5! - 7) - (9 \times 7)))) \times (5!/(3 \times 1)) \\12041 &:= ((1 - 3579) - 7) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\12042 &:= ((1 - ((3 - 5!) \times (7 + 97))) - 5!) - (3! + 1) \\12043 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5! + 7) + ((97 - 5!)^3 \times 1)) \\12044 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + 7)) + (97 \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\12045 &:= (1 - (3 - 57)) \times (9 + (7 \times (5!/(3 + 1)))) \\12046 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) - (5! + (7! + (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1))) \\12047 &:= ((1 - 3!)/5) + ((7 + 9) \times (753 \times 1)) \\12048 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! + 7)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) - 1) \\12049 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((79 + 7!) - ((5! \times 3) + 1)) \\12050 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5!) - 7) + (97 \times (5! + 3 \times 1))) \\12051 &:= ((1 - 3) \times ((5 - 7!) - 975)) + 31 \\12052 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5!) - 7)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1) \\12053 &:= (((1 - 3579) + 7) + (5^{3!})) - 1 \\12054 &:= (((1 - 3579) + 7) + (5^{3!})) \times 1 \\12055 &:= (((1 - 3579) + 7) + (5^{3!})) + 1 \\12056 &:= 1 + (((3 \times (5 + 797)) + 5) \times (3! - 1)) \\12057 &:= 1 + (((3 - 5!) + 7) - (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1)) \\12058 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) - ((57 \times 9) - 7531) \\12059 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + (7! + (9 \times 753)))) - 1 \\12060 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((79 - 7) + 531) \\12061 &:= 1 + ((3 \times ((5 \times 79) + 7)) \times (5 + (3! - 1))) \\12062 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((7! + (9 \times 753)) + 1) \\12063 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 + ((797 \times 5) + 31)) \\12064 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - (((7 - 9) \times (7!/5)) \times 3! \times 1) \\12065 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 7) - (5 \times 31) \\12066 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times 5)) + (3! \times 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12067 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((7 + 9) \times (753 - 1)) \\12068 &:= 1 + 35 + ((7 + 9) \times (753 - 1)) \\12069 &:= (((1 + (3 \times (5 \times 797))) + 5!) - 3!) - 1 \\12070 &:= 1 - (3 - ((5 + 7) \times (975 + 31))) \\12071 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\12072 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) + (7! - 531) \\12073 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! - 531) \\12074 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) - (9 - (7! - (5^3 \times 1))) \\12075 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) \times (((9 - 75) - 3) \times 1)) \\12076 &:= 13 + ((5 \times 7) + (97 \times ((5^3) - 1))) \\12077 &:= 13 \times (((5 + 797) + 5!) + (3! + 1)) \\12078 &:= (135 + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 + 53) + 1) \\12079 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((7 + 9) \times (753 + 1)) \\12080 &:= 1 + (((3! \times 5) + ((7 + 9) \times 753)) + 1) \\12081 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7) + (975 \times (3 + 1))) \\12082 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 - 7!) - 975) - 31) \\12083 &:= (((1 + (3 \times (5 \times 797))) + 5!) + 3!) + 1 \\12084 &:= ((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3)) \times 1 \\12085 &:= ((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3)) + 1 \\12086 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((97 + 5) + (3! - 1))) \\12087 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times 79) \times (((7 + 5) + 3!) - 1) \\12088 &:= 13 - (5! - (((7! - 975) \times 3) \times 1)) \\12089 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7) + (97 \times (5! - 3! \times 1)) \\12090 &:= ((13 - 5) + ((7 \times 9) + 7)) \times (5 \times 31) \\12091 &:= (135 + ((797 \times 5) \times 3)) + 1 \\12092 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7 + 5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\12093 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) \times 97) + ((5! + 3!!) + 1) \\12094 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\12095 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5!) \times (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3)) - 1) \\12096 &:= (1357 \times 9) + (7 - ((5^3) - 1)) \\12097 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5!) \times (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3))) \times 1 \\12098 &:= ((1 \times (3 - (5! - 7)))^{9-7}) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\12099 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) \times ((97 + 5) + (3! + 1)) \\12100 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 \times 97)) - (5! + 3 - 1) \\12101 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) + (9 + 7!) - (5! - (3 + 1)) \\12102 &:= ((1 \times (3 - (5! - 7)))^{9-7}) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\12103 &:= ((1 + ((3 - (5! - 7))^{9-7})) + 5) - (3 \times 1) \\12104 &:= (((1 + 3!) - (5! \times (7 - 9))) \times (7^{5-3})) + 1 \\12105 &:= ((13 + 5!) \times ((79 + 7) + 5)) + (3 - 1)\end{aligned}$$

- 12106** := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + (5! + 31)$
12107 := $((1357 \times 9) - 75) - 31$
12108 := $((1 \times 3)^5) + ((7 \times 975) + ((3! + 1)!))$
12109 := $1 - (3 \times ((5! \times 7) + ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31)))$
12110 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7! + 9) + (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1)$
12111 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 797) + 53) - 1)$
12112 := $(1 + ((3 - (5! - 7))^{9-7})) + (5 + 3! \times 1)$
12113 := $((1^3 - (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5^3))) - 1$
12114 := $((1^3 - (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5^3))) \times 1$
12115 := $((1^3 - (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5^3))) + 1$
12116 := $(1 + ((3 - (5! - 7))^{9-7})) + (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
12117 := $(((((1 + 3!))! / 5) \times 7) - (9 - 7!)) + (5! / (3 + 1))$
12118 := $((1^{35} - 7) + ((97 \times (5^3)) - 1)$
12119 := $((1^{35} - 7) + (97 \times (5^3) \times 1))$
12120 := $((1 \times 3!!) / 5) \times ((7! / (9 \times 7) + 5)) - ((3! - 1)!)$
12121 := $((1 - ((3 - (5 \times 79)) + 7)) + 5) \times 31$
12122 := $((1 + 3) \times 57) \times 9 + ((7! - 5) \times (3 - 1))$
12123 := $(1 - 3) + ((5! - (7 + (9 + 7))) \times ((5^3) \times 1))$
12124 := $(1^{357}) \times ((97 \times (5^3)) - 1)$
12125 := $(1^{357}) + ((97 \times (5^3)) - 1)$
12126 := $(13 - 5) - (7 - (97 \times (5^3 \times 1)))$
12127 := $((13 - 5) - 7) + ((97 \times (5^3)) + 1)$
12128 := $(13 - 5) \times ((797 + (5! \times 3!)) - 1)$
12129 := $(13 \times 5) + ((7 + 9) \times (753 + 1))$
12130 := $1 \times (((3 \times 5!) - 7!) + 9) + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1))$
12131 := $1 + (((3 \times 5!) - 7!) + 9) + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1))$
12132 := $(1^{35}) \times (7 + (97 \times ((5^3) \times 1)))$
12133 := $(1^{35}) + (7 + (97 \times ((5^3) \times 1)))$
12134 := $((1^{35}) + 7) + ((97 \times (5^3)) + 1)$
12135 := $13 + ((5 - (7 - (97 \times (5^3)))) - 1)$
12136 := $(13 + 5) - ((7 - (97 \times (5^3))) \times 1)$
12137 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times (53 \times 1)$
12138 := $1 + ((357 \times (9 + (75/3))) - 1)$
12139 := $((13 - 5) + (7 + (97 \times (5^3)))) - 1$
12140 := $((13 - 5) + (7 + (97 \times (5^3)))) \times 1$
12141 := $((13 - 5) + (7 + (97 \times (5^3)))) + 1$
12142 := $(1357 \times 9) - (75 - (3 + 1))$
12143 := $((1 + ((3 \times 5!) - 7!)) + 9) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))$
12144 := $((1 - 3 + (5 \times 79)) - (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!$
12145 := $1 + (3 \times ((57 \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 + 3))) + 1))$
12146 := $1 + (35 \times (7 - (((9 \times (7 - 5!)) / 3) - 1)))$
12147 := $1 \times (((3 \times 579) \times 7) - 5) - (3! + 1)$
12148 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5! + 7) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3! \times 1)))$
12149 := $(13 + (5 + 7)) + ((97 \times (5^3)) - 1)$
12150 := $((1 + 3)! - (5 - 7)) + ((97 \times (5^3)) - 1)$
12151 := $(1 + ((3 \times 579) \times 7)) - ((5 + 3) + 1)$
12152 := $((1357 \times 9) - 7) - (53 + 1)$
12153 := $(1357 \times 9) - (7 + (53 \times 1))$
12154 := $(1 - (3 - 5!)) \times ((7 + 97) - ((5 - 3) - 1))$
12155 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times ((5^3) \times 1))$
12156 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5 + (3! - 1))$
12157 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) - ((7 + ((97 - 5!)^3)) + 1)$
12158 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 + 7) + (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1))$
12159 := $((1 + (3! + 5!)) + 7) \times 97 - (5! + (3! - 1))$
12160 := $((1 + 3)^5 + 7) + (9 + 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
12161 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) - ((7 + ((97 - 5!)^3)) + 1)$
12162 := $(1 - (3 - (5 - (7 + ((97 - 5!)^3)))) - 1$
12163 := $(1 - (3 - (5 - (7 + ((97 - 5!)^3)))) \times 1$
12164 := $(1 - (3 - (5 - (7 + ((97 - 5!)^3)))) + 1$
12165 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7)) + (5 - (3! \times 1))$
12166 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 79 - 7! + ((5^3) + 1)$
12167 := $(1 + (((3! - 5)^7) + (9 + 7) + 5))^3 \times 1$
12168 := $((1 \times 3)^5) - (7 + (9 - 7)) \times (53 - 1)$
12169 := $((1357 \times 9) - 75) + 31$
12170 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (79 + (7! - 5)) - (3! \times 1)$
12171 := $(1 - ((3! - 5!) \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! - (53 - 1))$
12172 := $(1 - 3) + (((579 \times 7) + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
12173 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7! + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - (3! + 1)))$
12174 := $((1 + 3)! \times (5 - 7)) + (97 \times ((5^3) + 1))$
12175 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) - (7 + ((97 - 5!)^3))) - 1$
12176 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) - (7 + ((97 - 5!)^3))) \times 1$
12177 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) - (7 + ((97 - 5!)^3))) + 1$
12178 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + 7!) + (9^{7-5}) - 3! \times 1$
12179 := $(1 - ((3 - 5!) \times (7 + 97))) + ((5 + 3!) - 1)$
12180 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
12181 := $((1 - 3)^5) + ((7 + 9 + 7) \times 531)$

$$\begin{aligned}12182 &:= ((13 - 5) \times 7) + ((97 \times (5^3)) + 1) \\12183 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! - ((975 + 3) + 1)) \\12184 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1) \\12185 &:= (1 - (3! + 5)) + ((7! - 975) \times (3 \times 1)) \\12186 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) - (3! \times 1) \\12187 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) - (3! - 1) \\12188 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) - (3 + 1) \\12189 &:= ((1357 \times 9) - 75/3) + 1 \\12190 &:= (1357 \times 9) - ((7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\12191 &:= (13 + (5 + 7)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1) \\12192 &:= (13 - ((5 - (7! - 975)) \times 3)) - 1 \\12193 &:= 13 + ((5 + 7) - (((97 - 5!)^3) - 1)) \\12194 &:= (1357 \times 9) + ((7 + 5) - 31) \\12195 &:= (1 + ((3!! + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7))) + (5! - (3! \times 1)) \\12196 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) + (3 + 1) \\12197 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) + (3! - 1) \\12198 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((797 \times (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\12199 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) + (3! + 1) \\12200 &:= (1 - (35 \times 7)) \times (9 - ((7 + 53) - 1)) \\12201 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + (7 + 5)) - (3 + 1)! \\12202 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - (79 \times (7 - (5^3 \times 1))) \\12203 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) + ((7 + 9 + 7) \times 531) \\12204 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 7) - ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\12205 &:= (1 + (3! \times ((5! + 7) \times (9 + 7)))) + ((5 + 3!) + 1) \\12206 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 7) - ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\12207 &:= (1357 \times 9) - (((7 + 5)/(3 + 1))!) \\12208 &:= (13 - ((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7))) + (5!^{3-1}) \\12209 &:= (1357 \times 9) - ((7 + 5)/(3 \times 1)) \\12210 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (((5 \times 7) \times 9) + ((7! + 5!)/(3 \times 1))) \\12211 &:= (((1357 \times 9) + 7) - 5) - (3 + 1) \\12212 &:= (1357 \times 9) - (((7 - 5) - 3) + 1)! \\12213 &:= (1357 \times 9) + (((7 - 5) - 3) + 1) \\12214 &:= (1357 \times 9) + (((7 - 5) - 3) + 1)! \\12215 &:= (1357 \times 9) + ((7 + 5)/3! \times 1) \\12216 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((((5! + 7) \times 97) - 5!) - 3!) - 1) \\12217 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((((5! + 7) \times 97) - 5!) - 3!) \times 1) \\12218 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + ((7 + 9 + 7) \times 531) \\12219 &:= (1^3 + 5) + ((7 + 9 + 7) \times 531)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12220 &:= 13 \times (((57 + 9) + (7 \times (5^3)))) - 1 \\12221 &:= (1357 \times 9) + ((7 + 5) - (3 + 1)) \\12222 &:= (135 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7 \times 531) \\12223 &:= ((1 + (3!! + 5)) - 7) \times ((97 + 5)/(3! \times 1)) \\12224 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - ((5^3!) - 1)) \\12225 &:= ((1357 \times 9) - (7 + 5)) + (3 + 1)! \\12226 &:= ((1357 \times 9) - 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\12227 &:= 1 - (3 + ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - ((5^3!) - 1))) \\12228 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (((5! + 7) \times 97) - 5!) + 3!) - 1 \\12229 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5! - 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3! \times 1)) \\12230 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (((5! + 7) \times 97) - 5!) + 3!) + 1 \\12231 &:= 1 + 35 + ((7! - 975) \times (3 \times 1)) \\12232 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - ((5^3!) - 1)) \\12233 &:= (13 \times ((57 + 9) + (7 \times (5^3)))) \times 1 \\12234 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 7) + ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\12235 &:= (((1 \times 3!!)/5) \times ((7!/(9 \times 7)) + 5)) - (3! - 1) \\12236 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 7) + ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\12237 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 579) \times 7) + 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\12238 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + (75/3)) \times 1 \\12239 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + (75/3)) + 1 \\12240 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (7! + 531) \\12241 &:= (1 - 3!!) + ((57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) - 3!! \times 1) \\12242 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - (5 - (7 + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! \times 1))))) \\12243 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 579)) + (7 + 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\12244 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5! \times (7 + ((9 - 7) \times 5)))) + (3 + 1) \\12245 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + (7 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\12246 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5! \times ((7^{9-7}) + 53)) \times 1) \\12247 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5! \times ((7^{9-7}) + 53)) + 1) \\12248 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times 5) - (3! + 1) \\12249 &:= (((1^3 + (5! - 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) - 1 \\12250 &:= (((1^3 + (5! - 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) \times 1 \\12251 &:= (((1^3 + (5! - 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) + 1 \\12252 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - (5! - 7)) + (97 \times 5!)) + 3!! - 1 \\12253 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - (5! - 7)) + (97 \times 5!)) + 3!! \times 1 \\12254 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - (5! - 7)) + (97 \times 5!)) + 3!! + 1 \\12255 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (5 + 7)) \times (97 + (5! \times 3!))) \times 1 \\12256 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) + (97 \times (5! + (3! - 1))) \\12257 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 75) - 31 \\12258 &:= (((1 + 3!)!)/5) - ((7 - 97) \times (5! + (3! - 1)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12259 &:= ((1357 \times 9) - 7) + (53 \times 1) \\ 12260 &:= ((1357 \times 9) - 7) + (53 + 1) \\ 12261 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times 5) + (3! \times 1) \\ 12262 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times 5) + (3! + 1) \\ 12263 &:= (((1 \times 3)!) \times 5) + (7! - 97) + (5! \times 31) \\ 12264 &:= (1 - 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times ((75/3) - 1) \\ 12265 &:= ((135 - 7) \times 97) - (5! + 31) \\ 12266 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((79 - (7 + 5))^{3-1}) \\ 12267 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((579 \times 7) + (5 + 31)) \\ 12268 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7! - (5! + (3 + 1)!))) \\ 12269 &:= 1 - (((3! - 5!) - 7) \times 97) - 531 \\ 12270 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) + ((7 + 97) \times ((5! - 3) + 1)) \\ 12271 &:= 1 + (((3!)/5) \times (79 + 7)) - (5! - 3! \times 1) \\ 12272 &:= (13 \times ((5! + (7 - 9)) \times (7 - 5))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 12273 &:= (1357 \times 9) + (7 + (53 \times 1)) \\ 12274 &:= ((1 - (3! - (5! - 7))) - ((97 - 5!)^3)) - 1 \\ 12275 &:= ((1 - (3! - (5! - 7))) - ((97 - 5!)^3)) \times 1 \\ 12276 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 - 7) \times ((9 - 75) \times 31)) \\ 12277 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5!) + 7) + (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1)) \\ 12278 &:= (13 \times (5! \times 7)) + (97 \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 12279 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - ((5! + 7) \times ((9 - (7 \times 5)) - 31))) \\ 12280 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5^3))) - 1 \\ 12281 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) - ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 12282 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5^3))) + 1 \\ 12283 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) - ((7 \times 5) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 12284 &:= (1357 \times 9) + (75 - (3 + 1)) \\ 12285 &:= (13 - ((5! - (7 + 9)) \times (7 - (5^3)))) \times 1 \\ 12286 &:= (13 - ((5! - (7 + 9)) \times (7 - (5^3)))) + 1 \\ 12287 &:= 1 \times ((3! + (5! - 7)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) - 1)) \\ 12288 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5)) + 7) \times ((9 - 7)^{5+3! \times 1}) \\ 12289 &:= 1 - (((3 \times ((5 - 7)^9)) \times (7 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 12290 &:= (1 - (3! \times (5 + 7))) + (((97 \times 5!) + 3!) + 1) \\ 12291 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (7 + 97)) + ((5!/3!) - 1) \\ 12292 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 579)) \times 7) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 12293 &:= (((1 + ((3! - 5) + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + 5) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 12294 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times ((5 + 7) + (97 \times ((5!/3!) + 1))) \\ 12295 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 75) + (3! + 1) \\ 12296 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5!) - 7) \times ((97 + 5) + 3 + 1)) \\ 12297 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5!) - 7) \times ((97 + 5) + 3 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12298 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5!)) + 7) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1) \\ 12299 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5! + (7 - (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1))) \\ 12300 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 797) + 5!) - (3! - 1)) \\ 12301 &:= (1 - (((3 - 5)^7) \times 97)) - ((5! - 3) - 1) \\ 12302 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times 97) - (5!/3! \times 1)) \\ 12303 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5! + (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 12304 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5) + 7) \times 97 - ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 12305 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! + 7) \times 97) - (5!/3! \times 1)) \\ 12306 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (579 + 7)) \times (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 12307 &:= 1 \times ((3^5 + (79 + 75)) \times 31) \\ 12308 &:= 1 + ((3^5 + (79 + 75)) \times 31) \\ 12309 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5) + 7) \times 97 - (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 12310 &:= (((((13 - 5!) + 7) - 9) \times (7 - 5!)) - 3!) - 1 \\ 12311 &:= (((((13 - 5!) + 7) - 9) \times (7 - 5!)) - 3!) \times 1 \\ 12312 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 12313 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5 \times (7!/9))) + (((7! - 5) \times 3) + 1) \\ 12314 &:= ((13 + (5 + 79)) \times (7 + 5!)) - (3! - 1) \\ 12315 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((57 \times 9) \times ((75/3) - 1)) \\ 12316 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 + ((3! - 1)!))) \\ 12317 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) + (7 + 97)) \times ((5! - 3!) - 1) \\ 12318 &:= ((1 \times 3!)/5) \times (7 - ((9 - 75) \times 31)) \\ 12319 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 75) + 31 \\ 12320 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (79 + 75)) \times (3! - 1) \\ 12321 &:= (((1 - 3!)/5) + (7 \times (9 + 7)))^{5-3 \times 1} \\ 12322 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times 7) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 - 3! \times 1)) \\ 12323 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((7 - 9)^{7+5}) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 12324 &:= (1 + ((3^5) - 7)) \times (9 + ((7 + 5) + 31)) \\ 12325 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) - 7! \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1) \\ 12326 &:= 1 - ((3! + 5) \times (7 - ((9 + 7) + 5) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 12327 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5!)) - 31) \\ 12328 &:= ((1 + (3! + (5 + 7))) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! \times (3! - 1)) \\ 12329 &:= 13 + (5! + (((7! - 975) \times 3) + 1)) \\ 12330 &:= (1357 \times 9) - (7 - ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 12331 &:= (1 + (((3^5) \times 7) + 9) \times 7) + ((5! \times 3) \times 1) \\ 12332 &:= (1 + (((3^5) \times 7) + 9) \times 7) + ((5! \times 3) + 1) \\ 12333 &:= 13 + ((5 \times 7) \times (9 + (7^{5-3+1}))) \\ 12334 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times 97)) + (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 12335 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5) + 7) \times 97 + ((5 \times 3) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12336 &:= (1^3 + (57 \times 9)) \times ((75/3) - 1) \\ 12337 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times (7!/9))) + ((7 + 5!) \times 31)) \\ 12338 &:= (1 + (3^5 + (79 + 75))) \times 31 \\ 12339 &:= ((13 \times (5! + (7 \times 9))) + 7!) - (5! - ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 12340 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((79 + 7) + 531) \\ 12341 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 12342 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) - 7! \times ((5 + 3!) + 1) \\ 12343 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 12344 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 \times 97)) + (5! + 3 - 1) \\ 12345 &:= (1 - ((3 + (5 + 7)) - ((97 \times 5!) + 3!))) - 1 \\ 12346 &:= (1 - ((3 + (5 + 7)) - ((97 \times 5!) + 3!))) \times 1 \\ 12347 &:= (1 - ((3 + (5 + 7)) - ((97 \times 5!) + 3!))) + 1 \\ 12348 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 + 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 12349 &:= (((1^{3!} + 5)!) + ((7! + (9 \times ((7 + 5) + 3!)))) + 1) \\ 12350 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5 + (7 - (97 \times 5!)))) + (3! - 1)) \\ 12351 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + (7 \times 5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 12352 &:= ((1 + (3!! + (5 - 7))) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!)) - 1 \\ 12353 &:= ((1 + (3!! + (5 - 7))) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 12354 &:= 13579 - ((7 \times 5)^{3-1}) \\ 12355 &:= (1 \times ((3!! - (5 - 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))) - 1 \\ 12356 &:= (1 + (3!! - (5 - 7))) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!) - 1) \\ 12357 &:= (1 \times ((3!! - (5 - 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))) + 1 \\ 12358 &:= 1 + (((3!! - (5 - 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!)) + 1) \\ 12359 &:= (1^3) - (5! + (7! + ((9 - (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!))) \\ 12360 &:= (1^3 \times ((5 - (7 - (9 \times 7))) \times 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 12361 &:= (1 - 3!!) + ((5! + 7!) + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 12362 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (5 - 7)) + (97 \times 5!)) + (3!! + 1) \\ 12363 &:= 13 \times (579 + ((7 + 5) \times 31)) \\ 12364 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (((5 - 7) + (97 \times 5!)) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 12365 &:= (1^3) - (5! - (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3) + 1) \\ 12366 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! + (5 + (7 + ((97 \times 5!) - (3! \times 1)))) \\ 12367 &:= (1 - 3!!) + ((5! \times (7 + (97 + 5))) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 12368 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + (5! \times (7 + (97 + 5)))) + (3! + 1) \\ 12369 &:= (13 + 5!) \times (((79 + 7) + 5) + 3 - 1) \\ 12370 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 + 7) + (97 \times 5!))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 12371 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + (5 + 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3 - 1)) \\ 12372 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 \times 79)) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}) \\ 12373 &:= (1 + 3) + (57 \times (97 + (5 \times (3 + 1)!))) \\ 12374 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! + ((5 + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 - 1)) \\ 12375 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) + 7) \times (97 - (5 - (3! + 1))) \\ 12376 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7! + (9 - ((75 \times 3!) - 1))) \\ 12377 &:= ((1 - (3! \times 5)) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 12378 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! + (5 + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 12379 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - (7 + 97)) \times (5! + (3! - 1))) \\ 12380 &:= ((135 - 7) \times 97) - (5 + 31) \\ 12381 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5 - (7 + 97)) \times (5! + (3! - 1))) \\ 12382 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - 5) - (((7!/(9 - 7)) - (5^{3!})) - 1) \\ 12383 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\ 12384 &:= (1 + (3 \times 57)) \times (9 \times (7 + (5 - (3 + 1)))) \\ 12385 &:= (135 \times 79) + (((7! + 5!)/3) \times 1) \\ 12386 &:= (135 \times 79) + (((7! + 5!)/3) + 1) \\ 12387 &:= ((1 + 3)! - (5 - 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) + (3! + 1)) \\ 12388 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) + 7) \times ((975/3) + 1) \\ 12389 &:= 1 - (((3 - (5! + 7)) \times 97) - (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 12390 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 12391 &:= ((1 + 3)!)! - ((5 - (7! - 9)) - (75 \times 31)) \\ 12392 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + ((7 + 9) \times (753 - 1)) \\ 12393 &:= (1 - 3) - (5 - ((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 31))) \\ 12394 &:= 1 + ((3^5) \times ((7 + 97) - (53 \times 1))) \\ 12395 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5 + 7))) + ((97 \times 5!) + (3! - 1)) \\ 12396 &:= (13 \times 5!) + ((79 + 7) \times (5^3) + 1) \\ 12397 &:= (1 - ((3 + 57) \times 9)) \times (7 - (5 \times (3! \times 1))) \\ 12398 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5!)) + ((7 + 97) \times (5! - (3 - 1))) \\ 12399 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) + ((7! + (9 \times 7)) - (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 12400 &:= (((1 - (3! - 5)) + 7!)/(9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 31) \\ 12401 &:= ((1 \times 3! + (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times 5!)) + (3!! \times 1) \\ 12402 &:= (1 + ((3 + 5!) - 7)) \times ((97 + 5) + 3 + 1) \\ 12403 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + ((7!/(9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 12404 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5! + 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 - 1) \\ 12405 &:= ((1 - 3!!) \times 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 12406 &:= (1 - ((357 \times 9) + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 12407 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times (97 - 5)) + (3!! \times 1)) \\ 12408 &:= (((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 12409 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (((5 - 7)^9) - (7 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 12410 &:= (((1 - (3! - 5!)) \times (7 \times 9)) + 7!) + (5^3 \times 1) \\ 12411 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) - 3!))) - 1 \\ 12412 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5!) \times (((7 \times 9)/7) - (5! - (3 + 1))) \\ 12413 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5 \times (7! + (9 - 7531))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12414 &:= (1 - (3 - 57)) + ((97 \times 5!) + (3!! - 1)) \\12415 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (((7 + 9) \times ((7 - 5) \times 3!)) - 1) \\12416 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + 7)) \times (97 \times ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\12417 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) \times 1 \\12418 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times 3)) + 1 \\12419 &:= (((13 \times 5) - (7 - (97 \times 5!))) + 3!!) + 1 \\12420 &:= 135 \times ((7 - 9) \times (7 - (53 \times 1))) \\12421 &:= (13 - 5!) + (7! - (9 \times (7 - (5! + (3!! - 1)))))) \\12422 &:= 1 - (((3! - 5!) \times (7 + (97 + 5))) + (3! - 1)) \\12423 &:= (1357 \times 9) + (7 \times (5 \times 3! \times 1)) \\12424 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5^{7-9+7}) + (5 - (3 + 1)!)) \\12425 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - (7! / (5 + 3 + 1))) \\12426 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 57) \times ((9 + (7 - 5!)) - (3! - 1)) \\12427 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - (5 + 7)) \times ((97 - (5! - 3!)) \times 1) \\12428 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) + (7! + ((5! \times 3!) - 1)) \\12429 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - 5!) + (((7 + 9) \times 7)^{5-3}) - 1 \\12430 &:= (1 + 3) + (57 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5 \times 31)) \\12431 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) - (3!! + 1)) \\12432 &:= (13 - 5) \times (7 \times (97 + (5^3 \times 1))) \\12433 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((7 + ((97 \times 5!) + 3!!)) + 1) \\12434 &:= (((13 \times 57) \times 9) + 7!) + (5 + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\12435 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\12436 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7! - 9)) - ((7 \times 53) \times 1) \\12437 &:= (1 \times (((3!! + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + (7 \times 5!))) - (3 \times 1) \\12438 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times (57 \times 9)) - 7!)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\12439 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5! - 3)) - 1) \\12440 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 \times (97 + (5^3))) + 1) \\12441 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) + 7!) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5! - 3)) + 1) \\12442 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7 + 97) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\12443 &:= ((1 + 3!!) - 5) - (7! + (9 - ((7^5) - 31))) \\12444 &:= (1 + 3^5) \times ((7 + 97) - (53 \times 1)) \\12445 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - ((7! + (9 - (7^5))) - (3!! - 1)) \\12446 &:= (((1 + 3!!)! / 5!) + 7) \times ((9 - 7) \times (5! + (3! + 1))) \\12447 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (79 \times 7)) + (5 \times 3!!)) - 1 \\12448 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! - ((97 - 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\12449 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (79 \times 7)) + (5 \times 3!!)) + 1 \\12450 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (57 \times (9 - (7 \times 5)))) + ((3! + 1)! \\12451 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5! \times 7)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 + (3!! + 1))) \\12452 &:= ((135 - 7) \times 97) + (5 + 31)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12453 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 \times ((97 - (5! \times 3!)) + 1)) \\12454 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! \times (7 + 97)) - (5 + (3 + 1)!)) \\12455 &:= (1^3 + (5! \times (7 + 97))) + (5 - 31) \\12456 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + 7!) + ((9 + 75)^{3-1}) \\12457 &:= (((1^{3!}) + 5!) \times (7 + 97)) - (5! + (3! + 1)) \\12458 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! \times (7 + 97)) - (5^{3-1})) \\12459 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! \times (7 + 97)) - (5! / (3! - 1))) \\12460 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5 - 31)) \\12461 &:= (((1 + 3!!) - 5) - 7!) + (9 + ((7^5) - 31)) \\12462 &:= ((1 + (357 + 9)) + (7 \times 5)) \times 31 \\12463 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! \times (7 + 97))) - (5! / (3! \times 1)) \\12464 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) - 7!) + (9 + (7^5)) + (3!! \times 1) \\12465 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5! \times (7 + 97)) - (5 + (3! - 1))) \\12466 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5! \times (7 + 97)) - ((5! / 3!) + 1)) \\12467 &:= ((13 + 5) + ((7 + 97) \times 5!)) - 31 \\12468 &:= (((1 + 3)! + ((5! + 7) \times 97)) + (5! + 3!)) - 1 \\12469 &:= (((1 + 3)! + ((5! + 7) \times 97)) + (5! + 3!)) \times 1 \\12470 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3 + 1) \\12471 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 + (7! + 9)) - (7^5)) - (3!! \times 1)) \\12472 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3! \times 1) \\12473 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5! \times (7 + 97)))) - (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\12474 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) \times (9 \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))) \\12475 &:= (1^3 - 5) - (((7! + 9) - (7^5)) - (3!! + 1)) \\12476 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1) \\12477 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! \times (7 + 97)) + (5 - (3! \times 1))) \\12478 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 \times (7! / (9 - 7))) - 5!) - (3! \times 1)) \\12479 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7!)) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)) \\12480 &:= (13 \times ((5! + 7) - (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\12481 &:= ((1^{3!}) - 5!) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\12482 &:= (1 \times 357) + (97 \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \\12483 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) + (97 \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\12484 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times ((5 \times 7) + (97 \times 5))) + (3 + 1) \\12485 &:= (((1 \times 3)! + ((5! + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3))) + 1 \\12486 &:= (1 - 3 \times 5) + (((7 - 9) + 7^5) \times (3 + 1)) \\12487 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) - ((7! + 9) - (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)! \\12488 &:= (13 - 5) \times (((7 + 97) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\12489 &:= (((1 \times (3! + 5)) - 7!) - 9) + ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1) \\12490 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (5 - (((7! + 9) - (7^5)) - (3! + 1)))\end{aligned}$$

- 12491** := $(1 + (3! \times 5!)) - ((7! - (9 + (7^5))) + 3! \times 1)$
12492 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) + ((7 + 97) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)$
12493 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + (3! - 1))$
12494 := $(1 + 3!!) - (((5 + 7!) - (9 + (7^5))) - (3 - 1))$
12495 := $((1 - 3!)^5) - ((7 - (9 - 7)) - (5^{3 \times 1}))$
12496 := $1 - ((35 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7) - (53 \times 1)))$
12497 := $((((13 + 5) - 7!) - 9) + (7^5)) + (3!! + 1)$
12498 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! - (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3 \times 1))$
12499 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) \times ((7 + (9 \times 7)) + ((5! \times 3) + 1))$
12500 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) + ((7 + 97) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1)$
12501 := $((1 - 35) - 7!) - (((9 - (7 \times 5))^3) + 1)$
12502 := $(13 + 5!) \times ((79 + 7) + (5 + 3 \times 1))$
12503 := $(1 \times 3 + (5! \times (7 + 97))) + (5! / (3! \times 1))$
12504 := $1 - (3! - (((((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - 5!) \times 3!) - 1))$
12505 := $((((1 \times 3!) \times 5) \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 + (3!! \times 1))$
12506 := $(1 + 3!!) + (((5 - 7!) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1))$
12507 := $((1 + (3^5 + ((7!/9) \times 7))) + 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
12508 := $1 \times ((3 + 5) + (((7 - (9 - 7))^5) \times (3 + 1)))$
12509 := $1 + ((3 + 5) + (((7 - (9 - 7))^5) \times (3 + 1)))$
12510 := $((((13 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + 75) \times (3 \times 1))$
12511 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5! \times (7 + 9)) - (7! - (5^{3 \times 1})))$
12512 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1)$
12513 := $(1 \times 35) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) - (3 - 1))$
12514 := $13 - ((5^{7-9+7}) - ((5^3) + 1))$
12515 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (((7 - 9) + 7^5) \times (3 + 1))$
12516 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times (7 + 97)) + (5 + 31)$
12517 := $1 \times (((((3 \times 5!) \times 7) - (9 + 7)) \times 5) - (3 \times 1))$
12518 := $1 + 35 + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3) - 1$
12519 := $1 + 35 + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3) \times 1$
12520 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times (7 + 97) + (5! / (3 \times 1))$
12521 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) \times ((7 \times 97) - (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
12522 := $((1 \times 3!)!) + (((5! - 7) \times 97) + (5! + 3!!)) + 1$
12523 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 79) + 7) + 5!) - (3! - 1)$
12524 := $((1 + 3) + (5! - (7 + 9 + 7))) \times (5! + 3 + 1)$
12525 := $((((1 \times 3!)!) - 5) + ((7 - (9 - 7)))!) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
12526 := $(1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 - 1))$
12527 := $((((1 \times 3!)!) / 5) \times ((79 - 7) + (5 \times 3))) - 1$
12528 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5! - 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5)) - (3!! + 1))$
12529 := $((13 + 5) + ((7 + 97) \times 5!)) + 31$
12530 := $((1 \times 3! \times 57) + (9 + 7)) \times 5 \times (3! + 1)$
12531 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - 7!) + (9 + (7 \times 5))) + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
12532 := $((1 \times (3 \times 57)) + (97 \times 5!)) + (3!! + 1)$
12533 := $((1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) + 7) + 5!)) + (3! - 1)$
12534 := $(1 - (((3 - 5)^7) \times 97)) + ((5! - 3) \times 1)$
12535 := $(1 \times ((3!)^5 + 79)) + ((7! - (5! \times 3)) \times 1)$
12536 := $(1 \times ((3!)^5 + 79)) + ((7! - (5! \times 3)) + 1)$
12537 := $(1 \times (3! \times 5!)) + (7! + (9 \times (753 \times 1)))$
12538 := $(1 + ((3!! + ((57 \times 9) + 7!)) - 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
12539 := $1 - ((3!! / 5!) - ((7 \times (9 + 7))^{5-3 \times 1}))$
12540 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) + (7! + ((9 \times (7 \times 5!)) - 31))$
12541 := $(1 + ((3! + (5! + 7)) \times 97) - (5! \times 3)) - 1$
12542 := $(13 \times 579) + (7! - (5^{3-1}))$
12543 := $1 + (((3! + (5! + 7)) \times 97) - (5! \times 3)) + 1$
12544 := $((1 - ((3 + 5) + (79 \times 7))) / 5)^{3-1}$
12545 := $(13 \times (5! + (7 - (9 - 75)))) \times (3! - 1)$
12546 := $(1 \times 3!) + (5 \times (((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5) - (3! + 1)))$
12547 := $1 + ((3! + (5 \times 7)) \times (((97 + 5) \times 3) \times 1))$
12548 := $1 \times ((3 \times (5! + 7)) - ((97 - 5!)^3 \times 1))$
12549 := $1 + ((3 \times (5! + 7)) - ((97 - 5!)^3 \times 1))$
12550 := $((1 - 3 + 57) \times 9) + 7 \times (5^{3-1})$
12551 := $(1 \times 3!!) + ((5 + 7!) + (9 \times (753 + 1)))$
12552 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7!) - (((9 - 7) \times 5!) + (3 + 1)!)!$
12553 := $((1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) / 5)) - (3!! - 1)$
12554 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((5! \times (7 \times 9)) + 7!) - (53 - 1))$
12555 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) \times 531)$
12556 := $(1 + (3 \times 57)) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
12557 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5 + (((7 + 9) \times 7)^{5-3})) + 1)$
12558 := $((((13 \times 579) + 7!) - 5) - 3) - 1$
12559 := $((((13 \times 579) + 7!) - 5) - 3) \times 1$
12560 := $((((13 \times 579) + 7!) - 5) - 3) + 1$
12561 := $(1 + ((3^5) - 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) - 5) - (3! - 1))$
12562 := $(1 - 3 + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! - (5 + 31))$
12563 := $((1 + 3!!) - ((5 - 7) \times 9)) \times ((7 + 5) + (3! - 1))$
12564 := $(1 \times ((3! + 5!) / 7)) \times (97 - (5! - (3!! + 1)))$
12565 := $((1 + 3) \times (5! \times (7 + 9))) + (7! - (5 \times 31))$
12566 := $1 - ((3! \times 5) - (((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5) - (3! - 1)))$
12567 := $((135 - 7) \times 97) + (5! + 31)$
12568 := $((13 \times 579) + 7!) + (5 - 3) - 1$

- 12569** := $((13 \times 579) + 7!) + (5 - 3) \times 1$
12570 := $((13 \times 579) + 7!) + (5 - 3) + 1$
12571 := $(1^3) - (5! + (79 - ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}))$
12572 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) \times (7 - 9)) \times ((75 \times 3!) - 1)$
12573 := $1 \times (3 \times (5! + (((7! - 975) + 3!) \times 1)))$
12574 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times ((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5)) - (3! + 1))$
12575 := $1 - ((3! - (5 \times ((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5))) - (3! - 1))$
12576 := $(1^3 - (5 - (7! + 9))) + 7531$
12577 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + 7!) - (9 - 7531)$
12578 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7! - ((9 - 7) \times 5!) - 3) - 1)$
12579 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7! - ((9 - 7) \times 5!) - 3) \times 1)$
12580 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + (5^{3+1})$
12581 := $((1^3 \times (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + 7!) + (5 - (3 + 1)!)$
12582 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 75) + (3 + 1)!)$
12583 := $(1 - ((3 - 5) - 7!)) + (9 + 7531)$
12584 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! + 7)) \times 97) + (5 - 31)$
12585 := $(1357 \times 9) + ((7 + 5) \times 31)$
12586 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times ((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5)) + (3! - 1))$
12587 := $13 + (((5! \times 7) \times 9) + (7! + (5 - 31)))$
12588 := $1 - (((3^5 + 7) + 9) \times 7) - (5!^{3-1})$
12589 := $((1^{3!}) + (5 \times (7! / (9 - 7)))) - ((5 + 3!) + 1)$
12590 := $(1 - (3! - (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) + (7! - (5! / (3 + 1)!))$
12591 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5! - (7! + 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) - 1))$
12592 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5) + 7!) - (9 - 7531)$
12593 := $(13 \times (579 + (7 - 5))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
12594 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 - 5 + 3 + 1)))$
12595 := $(1 \times 3 + ((5! \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7! - (5 + 3)) \times 1)$
12596 := $1 \times ((35 \times ((79 - 7) \times 5)) - (3 + 1))$
12597 := $(1 + (35 \times ((79 - 7) \times 5))) - (3 + 1)$
12598 := $(1^3) \times (5! - (7! + ((9 - (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)))$
12599 := $(1^3) + (5! - (7! + ((9 - (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)))$
12600 := $(1 + 3!) \times (5! \times (7 + ((9 + 7) - (5 + 3 \times 1))))$
12601 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - (7! + 9) + (((7^5) + 3) \times 1)$
12602 := $(1^3 \times 5!) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3) - 1$
12603 := $(1^3 \times 5!) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3) \times 1$
12604 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + ((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5))) - (3! + 1)$
12605 := $(1 + (35 \times ((79 - 7) \times 5))) + (3 + 1)$
12606 := $((13 + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! - 5)) - (3 - 1)$
12607 := $(13 \times 5!) + (7 + ((97 - 5) \times ((3! - 1)!))$
12608 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (797 - (5 + 3 + 1))$
12609 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! + 7)) \times 97) - ((5 - (3! - 1)))!$
12610 := $((13 + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! - 5)) + (3 - 1)$
12611 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! + 7)) \times 97) + ((5 - (3! - 1)))!$
12612 := $((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) + (7 + (5^{3-1}))$
12613 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!))) - (3 - 1)$
12614 := $(135 - (7 + 9)) \times (75 + 31)$
12615 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + ((7 + 97) \times 5!) + ((3! - 1)!)$
12616 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7! - ((9 + 7) \times 53) + 1)$
12617 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + ((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5))) + (3! \times 1)$
12618 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + ((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5))) + (3! + 1)$
12619 := $((1^3 \times (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + 7!) - (5 - (3 + 1)!)$
12620 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7! - (5 + 3)) + 1)$
12621 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!))) + 3! \times 1$
12622 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - 7)) + (5 + (3 + 1)!)$
12623 := $((1 + 3!) - (((5 - 7) - 97) \times 5! - 3!)) - 1$
12624 := $1 \times ((3! \times 5) + (((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5) - (3! \times 1)))$
12625 := $1 + ((3! \times 5) + (((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5) - (3! \times 1)))$
12626 := $1 + ((3! \times 5) + (((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5) - (3! - 1)))$
12627 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1))$
12628 := $1 + ((3!^5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1)))$
12629 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!)) + 3 + 1)$
12630 := $((1 + 3) + (5! \times 7) - 9) + 7 \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
12631 := $((1^{35} \times 7!) / (9 - 7)) \times 5 + 31$
12632 := $1 - (((3 + ((5 - 7) \times 9)) \times 7) \times 5!) - 31$
12633 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5! - (7 \times 9)) \times (((7 \times 5) \times 3!) - 1))$
12634 := $(1 - 3 + ((5! \times 7) \times 9)) + (7! + (5 + 31))$
12635 := $(13 + 5!) \times ((79 + 7) + (5 + 3 + 1))$
12636 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) - (9 - 7)) \times (53 - 1)$
12637 := $((1 \times ((3! \times 5) + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)!$
12638 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - (7 - (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times 31))))$
12639 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5! + 7)) - (9 - ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}))$
12640 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) \times (7 - 9) \times (7 + (5^{3+1}))$
12641 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times (97 + 5!))) + ((3! + 1)!)!$
12642 := $(13 \times ((5 - 7) + 975)) - 3! - 1$
12643 := $(13 \times ((5 - 7) + 975)) - 3! \times 1$
12644 := $(1 - ((3! - 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - ((5^3) \times 1)$
12645 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5) - ((7 - 9)^7) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
12646 := $1 + ((3!^5) + ((7! - 9) - (7 + 5 \times 31)))$

- 12647** := $((1 + (3 + (5! + 7))) \times 97) - (5! / (3 - 1))$
12648 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + (7 \times (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)$
12649 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (((7 - 9)^{7+5}) \times 3) + 1$
12650 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5) + ((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5)) \times (3! - 1)$
12651 := $(13 \times 5) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5) \times 31)$
12652 := $((1 + 3!) - (5 - (7! / 9))) \times 7 + (5! \times 31)$
12653 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7 \times (9 - 7)) + 5!) \times 31)$
12654 := $(1^3) + ((57 \times (97 + (5^3))) - 1)$
12655 := $(1^3) + ((57 \times (97 + (5^3))) \times 1)$
12656 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((579 - 7) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)$
12657 := $1^{35} + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3! + 1))))$
12658 := $(13 + ((5! - 7)^{9-7})) - ((5^3) - 1)$
12659 := $(((((1^{3!}) - (5! - 7))^{9-7}) + 5!) - 3!) + 1$
12660 := $(1^{3!}) \times ((5 \times (7! / (9 - 7))) + (5! / (3 - 1)))$
12661 := $(1^{3!}) + ((5 \times (7! / (9 - 7))) + (5! / (3 - 1)))$
12662 := $((1 \times (357 \times 9) + (7! / 5)) \times 3) - 1$
12663 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! + (9 - 7))) - (5 \times 31)$
12664 := $((1 \times (357 \times 9) + (7! / 5)) \times 3) + 1$
12665 := $((1 + (357 \times 9)) + (7! / 5)) \times 3 - 1$
12666 := $((1 + (357 \times 9)) + (7! / 5)) \times 3 \times 1$
12667 := $((1 + (357 \times 9)) + (7! / 5)) \times 3 + 1$
12668 := $(1 + ((3!^5) - (7 - 9))) + (7! - (5! + 31))$
12669 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 - ((797 \times 5) \times 3)) + 1)$
12670 := $((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times (7 + 97)) - ((5! + 3) - 1)$
12671 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 - ((797 \times 5) \times 3)) - 1)$
12672 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - 797)) \times ((5 + 3) \times 1)$
12673 := $1 - ((3! + 5) \times ((79 - 7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1)!))$
12674 := $13 - (((5 + 7) \times 9) - ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}))$
12675 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) + ((7! - 975) \times (3 \times 1))$
12676 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) + (3! - 1))$
12677 := $1 - (((3 - (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - (5 - (3!! + 1)))$
12678 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 + (97 \times 5!)) + (3! + 1))$
12679 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5 - (7! + ((9 + 75) \times 31)))$
12680 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! + 7)) \times (97 - 5)) + (3!! \times 1)$
12681 := $((1 + 3)! + 5!) - (7 \times (9 - (75 \times (3 + 1)!)))$
12682 := $(((((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) - (9 + 7)) - (5! - (3 - 1)))$
12683 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) - 97 - (5 + 31)$
12684 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 - (79 + 7))) \times (5! + 31)$
12685 := $(((((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) - (9 + 7)) - (5! - (3! - 1)))$
12686 := $1 \times ((3!^5) + ((7 + 975) \times (3! - 1)))$
12687 := $1 + ((3!^5) + ((7 + 975) \times (3! - 1)))$
12688 := $((1 + 3)! - (5 - 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3) \times 1$
12689 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - 7)) + (5! - (3 + 1)!)$
12690 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (7 + 9)) \times (7^{5-3}) - 1$
12691 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (7 + 9)) \times (7^{5-3} \times 1)$
12692 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (7 + 9)) \times (7^{5-3}) + 1$
12693 := $(1 + 3)! - (5! - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
12694 := $(1 - 3 + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! + (5! - (3 + 1)!))$
12695 := $((1 - 3!) \times (579 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
12696 := $((13 \times 5) + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!) + 31$
12697 := $((135 + 7!) - 9) + 7531$
12698 := $((1 + ((3^5) \times 7) + 9)) \times 7 + ((5! \times 3!) + 1)$
12699 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 - 7) \times (53 \times 1)))$
12700 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) - ((97 - 5) + (3 + 1)!)$
12701 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7!) - ((9 \times (7 + 5)) + (3! + 1))$
12702 := $1 \times ((3!^5) - ((7 - 9) - (7! - (5! - (3 + 1)!))))$
12703 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7!) - ((9 \times (7 + 5)) + (3! - 1))$
12704 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (75 + (3!! - 1)))$
12705 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + ((7 + (9 - 7)) - 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)$
12706 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) - 79) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1})$
12707 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + ((7! + 9) + ((7 - (5^3)) \times 1)))$
12708 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + ((7 + 97) \times (5! + 3 - 1))$
12709 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - 7)) + (5! - (3 + 1)!)$
12710 := $((1 - 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) - 97)) \times ((5! / 3) + 1)$
12711 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7) \times (9 + (7 \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)!)$
12712 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) \times ((97 \times 5) - 31)$
12713 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + ((7! - (9 \times (7 + 5))) + (3! - 1)))$
12714 := $(((((1 \times 3!)! - (5! - (7 \times (97 + 5!)))) \times 3!) \times 1)$
12715 := $(((((1 \times 3!)! - (5! - (7 \times (97 + 5!)))) \times 3!) + 1)$
12716 := $(((((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! - 97)) - 5) + (3 - 1))$
12717 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + 7! - (((97 + 5) - 3) \times 1)$
12718 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + 7!) - (((97 + 5) - 3) \times 1)$
12719 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + 7!) - (((97 + 5) - 3) - 1)$
12720 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((5! - (7 \times (9 - 7))) \times 5) \times (3 + 1))$
12721 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + 7) \times 5! - (3!! - 1)$
12722 := $(1^{3!}) \times ((5 \times (7! / (9 - 7))) + (5! + 3 - 1))$

- 12723** := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! + (((9 - 7) - 5) \times 31))$
12724 := $1 + (35 + ((7 + 97) \times (5! + 3 - 1)))$
12725 := $(1^{3!}) \times (((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + 5) - ((3! \times 1)!)!$
12726 := $((1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5^3) + 1)$
12727 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + (797 \times ((5 \times 3) + 1))$
12728 := $1 \times (((3 + 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!)) - ((3! \times 1)!)!$
12729 := $1 + (((3 + 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!)) - ((3! \times 1)!)!$
12730 := $(1 \times 3! + ((5! - (7 \times (9 - 7))) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1)$
12731 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5! + ((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5))) + (3! - 1)$
12732 := $((1 \times 35) + 7!) + (9 - (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)$
12733 := $135 + (((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5) - (3 - 1))$
12734 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 79)) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1})$
12735 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7!) - 9 - ((75 - 3) \times 1)$
12736 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! - (5! - (3 + 1)))$
12737 := $135 + (((7! / (9 - 7)) \times 5) + 3 - 1)$
12738 := $((1 - 35) - 79)^{7-5} - 31$
12739 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + 7!) - ((9^{7-5}) - (3 \times 1))$
12740 := $(1 \times (3 + (5! + 7))) \times ((97 - 5) + (3! \times 1))$
12741 := $1 \times 3 + (579 \times (7 + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)))$
12742 := $(1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! - ((9 + 7) \times 5)) + (3! - 1))$
12743 := $((13 + 5) \times ((7 \times (97 + 5)) - 3!)) - 1$
12744 := $1 \times 3! + (579 \times (7 + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)))$
12745 := $((13 + 5) \times ((7 \times (97 + 5)) - 3!)) + 1$
12746 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) - (79 - 7!)) + (5 + 3 + 1)$
12747 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5! - 7)) \times (((9 - 7) - 5) + (3 + 1)!)!$
12748 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7! - (9 + 7)) - (53 - 1))$
12749 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (7 \times 97) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
12750 := $((1 - (3! + 5!)) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
12751 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) - ((9 \times 7) - (5 - 3!)) - 1$
12752 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) / 5 \times (3 + 1)$
12753 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7! + (9 - (75 - 3))) \times 1)$
12754 := $1 - ((3 - 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) + ((7! / 5!) + 3 + 1)))$
12755 := $((1 + 3!)! + 5!) + ((7^{9-7}) \times (5 \times 3!))$
12756 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) - ((9 \times 7) - (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
12757 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5! + 3 \times 1)$
12758 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 \times 7) + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) - 1)$
12759 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
12760 := $((13 + (5! + 7)) \times (97 - 5)) - ((3! - 1)!)!$
12761 := $(1 \times ((3!^5) + (7! - 9))) + ((7 - 53) \times 1)$
12762 := $(1 \times ((3!^5) + (7! - 9))) + ((7 - 53) + 1)$
12763 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - 5)) - (3!! - 1)$
12764 := $1 + ((3!^5) + (((7! - 9) - 75) + 31))$
12765 := $(1 - 3) + (((5! - 7)^{9-7}) - 5) + 3 \times 1$
12766 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + (7! + ((9 - 7) - 53))) \times 1$
12767 := $((1 + (3!^5)) + (7! + ((9 - 7) - 53))) + 1$
12768 := $((13 + 5!) \times (7 + 9)) \times ((7 + 5) / (3 - 1))$
12769 := $(1 - 3 + ((5! - 7)^{9-7})) + (5 - (3 \times 1))$
12770 := $1^{3579} + (7 - 5!)^{3-1}$
12771 := $(135 + 7!) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5!) + 3 + 1))$
12772 := $((1 + (3 - 5)) + (7 + 97)) \times (5! + 3 + 1)$
12773 := $(13 - 5!) - ((7 + 9) \times (7 \times (5 - ((3! - 1)!)!))$
12774 := $((1^{3!}) + 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! - (3! \times 1)))$
12775 := $((1 - 3 + ((5! - 7)^{9-7})) + 5) + (3 \times 1)$
12776 := $((1 + 3!) - ((5! - 7) + ((97 - 5!)^3))) + 1$
12777 := $((1 - (3!! + 5)) + ((7 \times 9) + (7! - 5!))) \times (3 \times 1)$
12778 := $(1 \times ((3!^5) + 7!)) - ((9 - 7) + (5 + 31))$
12779 := $((1 \times (3^5)) - 7!) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1)$
12780 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7!) - (((9 - 7)^5) + 3 + 1)$
12781 := $1 - (((3 \times 5) - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times 3!)) \times 1$
12782 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! + ((9 - 7) - 5)) - 31$
12783 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) + ((9 - 7) - (5 + 31))$
12784 := $((1 + 3)^5 \times 7) - (9 - (75^{3-1}))$
12785 := $((1 + 3)! - 5) \times ((7! / 9) + 75) + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
12786 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) - ((9 + 7) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1))$
12787 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) + (((9 - 7) - (5 \times 3!)) - 1)$
12788 := $((1 + 3) - 5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times (5 + (3 + 1)!)!))$
12789 := $((1^{35}) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
12790 := $(1 \times 3!) - (5 - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)))$
12791 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((5 \times (7! / 9)) + (7! - 5!)) + 31))$
12792 := $(1 + 3!) \times ((5 + (7! / 9)) - ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)))$
12793 := $((1 + ((3!^5) - 7)) + 9) + 7! + (5 - 31)$
12794 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) - ((97 - 5) / (3 + 1))$
12795 := $(1 \times (3!! + 5!)) + (((797 \times 5) \times 3) \times 1)$
12796 := $(1^3) - ((5! - 7!) - ((9 \times 7) \times (5^3) \times 1))$
12797 := $(1 - 3) + (((5! - 7)^{9-7}) + (5 \times 3! \times 1))$
12798 := $(1 \times 3) - ((5! - 7!) - ((9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) \times 1)))$

$$\begin{aligned}12799 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) - (((9 - 7!) - 5) + 3! \times 1) \\12800 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) \times (5 + (3! - 1)) \\12801 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7 + 97) \times ((5! + 3) \times 1)) \\12802 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! - (9 + (7 - 5)))) - (3 \times 1) \\12803 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 - 9) + 7!)) - 5 - 3! \times 1 \\12804 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) + ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\12805 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! + 7) \times 97) + (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\12806 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) - (((9 - 7) \times 5!)/(3 + 1)!) \\12807 &:= (1 + ((357 + 9) \times (7 \times 5))) - (3 + 1) \\12808 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7! - (9 + (7 - 5))) + 3 \times 1) \\12809 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! - 9)) - (((7 - 5) - 3) - 1) \\12810 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) - (((9 - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\12811 &:= (1 \times (((3!^5) + (7! + (9 + 7))) - (5!/3!))) - 1 \\12812 &:= (1 + 3!!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((97 + 5) + (3! - 1))) \\12813 &:= (1 + (((3!^5) + 7!) - (9 - 7))) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\12814 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! - ((9 - 7) - 5))) - (3! - 1) \\12815 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 - 9) + 7!)) - 5 + 3! \times 1 \\12816 &:= (1 - (3! + (5 + 79))) \times (7 - (5! + 31)) \\12817 &:= (1 + (((3!^5) + 7!) - (9 - 7))) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\12818 &:= (((1^{35}) + 7) + 9) \times (753 + 1) \\12819 &:= (((((13 \times 5) + 7) \times 9) - 7) \times (5!/3!)) - 1 \\12820 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5) - 7) - 9) + (7! + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\12821 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 \times (97 + 5))) - 31 \\12822 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) + (((9 - 7) \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\12823 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5)) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 3 + 1))) \\12824 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) - ((9 - 7) - ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\12825 &:= (13579 - 753) - 1 \\12826 &:= 13579 - (753 \times 1) \\12827 &:= 13579 - (753 - 1) \\12828 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) + ((9 - 7) + ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\12829 &:= (13 \times ((5 + 7) + 975)) - (3 - 1) \\12830 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) + ((9 - 7) + ((5 + 3!) + 1)) \\12831 &:= (((((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) + 5)) - (3! \times 1)) \\12832 &:= (((((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) \times 97) + 5!) + 3!) - 1 \\12833 &:= (((((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) \times 97) + 5!) + 3!) \times 1 \\12834 &:= (((((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) \times 97) + 5!) + 3!) + 1 \\12835 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times 79) + ((7! - 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\12836 &:= ((1 \times ((35 + (79 - 7)) \times 5!)) - 3) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12837 &:= ((1 \times ((35 + (79 - 7)) \times 5!)) - 3) \times 1 \\12838 &:= (1 + (3 + (5! + 7))) \times ((97 - 5) + (3! \times 1)) \\12839 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) + 9) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}) \\12840 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) + ((7! - (9 - 7)) - (5 - 31))) \\12841 &:= 1 + ((3!^5) + ((7! - (9 - 7)) - (5 - 31))) \\12842 &:= ((1 \times ((35 + (79 - 7)) \times 5!)) + 3) - 1 \\12843 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) \times (7 + 97)) - (53 \times 1) \\12844 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! + ((9 - 7) - 5))) + 31 \\12845 &:= (((1 + 3)! - 5) + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5! \times (3 \times 1))) \\12846 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7)) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\12847 &:= ((1 + 3!))! - (((57 - (9 \times 7))^5) - 31) \\12848 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) + ((9 + 7) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\12849 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\12850 &:= ((1357 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5) - 3!! \times 1 \\12851 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) - ((9 - 7) - (5 + 31)) \\12852 &:= (((13 + 5) + 7) + 9) \times 7 \times (53 + 1) \\12853 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7! - 9) - (7 - 53))) \times 1 \\12854 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) + 7!)) + ((9 - 7) + (5 + 31)) \\12855 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times 79) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\12856 &:= (1 + ((3! - (5! - 7!)) + 9)) + (7! + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\12857 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + (7! - ((9 + 7) \times 5))) + ((3! - 1)!) \\12858 &:= ((1 - 3) \times ((5! - (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - 5!))) - (3 + 1)! \\12859 &:= (((1 \times (3!^5)) + 79) + 7!) - (5 + 31) \\12860 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (79 + (7! - (5 + 31))) \\12861 &:= (((1 \times ((35 - 7) \times 97)) \times 5) - 3!!) + 1 \\12862 &:= (1 \times (((3!^5) + 7) + (9 + 7!))) + (5!/(3 + 1)) \\12863 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (797 + 5)) + 31 \\12864 &:= (1 + ((3!!/5!) + 797)) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\12865 &:= (((1 - (3!!/5)) \times (7 - (97 + 5))) - 3!!) \times 1 \\12866 &:= (((((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) - (9 \times 7)) + (5! - (3! + 1))) \\12867 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! - ((9 - 7) - 53)) - 1) \\12868 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! - ((9 - 7) - 53)) \times 1) \\12869 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! - ((9 - 7) - 53)) + 1) \\12870 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (79 - ((7 - (5^3)) - 1)) \\12871 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\12872 &:= ((1 \times ((3!^5) + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - (3 - 1) \\12873 &:= (1 \times (((3 \times 579) \times 7) - 5)) + (3!! - 1) \\12874 &:= 1 \times (((((3 \times 579) \times 7) - 5) + 3!!) \times 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12875 &:= 1 + (((((3 \times 579) \times 7) - 5) + 3!!) \times 1) \\12876 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5) + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + (3 - 1) \\12877 &:= 1 - (3 \times (5 - ((7! + (9 - 753)) + 1))) \\12878 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\12879 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 + 9 + (7 + (5!/(3 + 1)))) \\12880 &:= ((1 + (35 + 79)) \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\12881 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7 \times 9) + ((7! - (5 - 3!)) \times 1)) \\12882 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (79 + (7! - ((5 \times 3) - 1))) \\12883 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 \times (97 + 5))) + 31 \\12884 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5!)) - (797 - (5!^{3-1})) \\12885 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) + (7! + ((9 + 7) + (53 \times 1)))) \\12886 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 579)) \times 7) + (5! \times 3! \times 1) \\12887 &:= (((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) + (97 + 5)) - 31 \\12888 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) + 7!) + ((9 - 7) \times (5 + 31))) \\12889 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) + 7!) + ((9 - 7) \times (5 + 31))) \\12890 &:= (13 + ((5 + 7) \times 9)) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}) \\12891 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7! + (9 - 753)) + 1) \\12892 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times 5)))) - (3! - 1) \\12893 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5!) + (7 - (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1)) \\12894 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (79 + 7!)) - ((5 - 3) - 1) \\12895 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (79 + 7!)) \times ((5 - 3) - 1) \\12896 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (79 + 7!)) + ((5 - 3) - 1) \\12897 &:= (((1 \times 3!^5) + 7!) + 9) + ((75 - 3) \times 1) \\12898 &:= (((1 \times 3!^5) + 7!) + 9) + ((75 - 3) + 1) \\12899 &:= 1 - (3 - (((5 \times ((79 + 7) \times 5)) \times 3!) + 1)) \\12900 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5! \times ((7 - 9) - 7)) + 5) \times 3! \times 1) \\12901 &:= (13 + 5!) \times ((7 \times 97)/(5 + 3 - 1)) \\12902 &:= (1 + ((3 + (57 \times 9)) \times (75/3))) + 1 \\12903 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) + (7! + 97)) - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\12904 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) + (7! + 97)) - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\12905 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7 + 97) \times ((5! + 3) + 1)) \\12906 &:= (1 \times (3!! - (5 + (7 - 9)))) \times ((7 + 5) + (3! \times 1)) \\12907 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - 7!)) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5^3)) - 1) \\12908 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \\12909 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - 7!)) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5^3)) + 1) \\12910 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! + ((97 - 5) + 3))) - 1 \\12911 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! + ((97 - 5) + 3))) \times 1 \\12912 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! + ((97 - 5) + 3))) + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12913 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + 5!))) + (3!! + 1) \\12914 &:= (((((1^3)^5) \times 7)!) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5^3))) - 1 \\12915 &:= (((((1^3)^5) \times 7)!) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5^3))) \times 1 \\12916 &:= (((((1^3)^5) \times 7)!) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5^3))) + 1 \\12917 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + 7!) + (((97 + 5) - 3) + 1) \\12918 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) - (9 + 7) + (5! - (3 - 1)) \\12919 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) - ((5! - (79 + 7!)) - (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\12920 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) + (97 + 5) + (3 - 1) \\12921 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! + 7) \times 97) - 5!) + (3!! - 1) \\12922 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5! + 7) \times 97)) + (5! \times (3! - 1)) \\12923 &:= 1 \times (((3!^5) + (7! + 97)) + (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\12924 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5! + 7) \times 97)) - (5! - (3!! - 1)) \\12925 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! + 7)) + 9) \times ((75/3) \times 1) \\12926 &:= 1 - (((3^5) \times (7 + 9)) - (((7^5) + 3!) \times 1)) \\12927 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5! - ((7 + 9) - (7 \times 5)))) \times 31 \\12928 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7! + 97) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\12929 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! + ((9 \times (7 + 5)) + (3! - 1))) \\12930 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\12931 &:= (((1 \times (3!^5)) + 79) + 7!) + (5 + 31) \\12932 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) + ((97 - 5) + (3 + 1)!)) \\12933 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! + (5! + (3 + 1)!)) \\12934 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5) - (7 - 9))) + 7! + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\12935 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (((5 - 7!) + 9) - ((7 + 5) \times (3!! - 1))) \\12936 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 - 79)) \times ((7!/(5 \times 3!)) \times 1) \\12937 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (97 + 5))) - (3 + 1)! \\12938 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\12939 &:= (1 \times (3579 - 7!)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\12940 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + (5 - (7 - (97 \times (5! + 3!)))) - 1 \\12941 &:= (1 + 3!!) + (5 - ((7 - (97 \times (5! + 3!))) \times 1)) \\12942 &:= ((1 - (3! \times 5!)) + ((7! - (9 - 7)) - 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\12943 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! + 7) - (9 + 75))^{3-1}) \\12944 &:= 1 - ((3!! \times ((5 - 7) \times 9)) + ((7 + 5) + (3! - 1))) \\12945 &:= 1 - ((3!! \times ((5 - 7) \times 9)) + ((7 + (5 + 3)) + 1)) \\12946 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) - 7) - 9 + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1) \\12947 &:= (13579 - 7) - (5^{3+1}) \\12948 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) \times (7 + 97)) + (53 - 1) \\12949 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7! + (9 \times (7 \times (5^3)))) - 1 \\12950 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7! + (9 \times (7 \times (5^3)))) \times 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12951 &:= ((1 \times 35) + (7! + (9 \times (7 \times (5^3)))))) + 1 \\12952 &:= ((1 + ((3!! + (5! + 7)) \times (9 + 7))) + 5!) - (3!! + 1) \\12953 &:= ((1 + ((3!! + (5! + 7)) \times (9 + 7))) + 5!) - (3!! \times 1) \\12954 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7)) \times ((9 + (75/3)) \times 1) \\12955 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (7 + ((9 - 7!) - (5 \times 3!))) \\12956 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) - 79)) \times ((75 + 3) + 1) \\12957 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + (57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!))) - (3 + 1) \\12958 &:= ((1 - 3!)/5) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times 3!!) - 1 \\12959 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7 + ((9 + 7) - 5))) \times 3!! - 1 \\12960 &:= ((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7! + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times (3!! \times 1))) \\12961 &:= 13579 + (7 - (5^{3+1})) \\12962 &:= (1 + ((3 + 57) \times (9 \times (7 + 5)))) \times (3 - 1) \\12963 &:= (1 - ((3!! \times ((5 - 7) - 9)) - (7! + 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\12964 &:= (1 - (3!! - (57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)))) + (3 \times 1) \\12965 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 753) - 1 \\12966 &:= ((1357 \times 9) + 753) \times 1 \\12967 &:= (1357 \times 9) + (753 + 1) \\12968 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) - (((5! - 7) - (97 \times 5!)) - (3!! + 1)) \\12969 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((57^{9-7}) - 5)) - (3! + 1) \\12970 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 \times (((9 + 7) + 5) + (3!! + 1))) \\12971 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + 79) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1})) \\12972 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 57)^{9-7}) - (5!/(3! - 1)) \\12973 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7! + (9 - 7)) + 5 \times 31) \\12974 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5) + ((7 + 97) \times (5^3))) - 1 \\12975 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5) + ((7 + 97) \times (5^3))) \times 1 \\12976 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\12977 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 57)^{9-7}) + 5 - (3 + 1)! \\12978 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7 + ((9 + 7) - 5))) \times (3!! + 1) \\12979 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((57^{9-7}) - 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\12980 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) \times (((7 \times 9) - 7) + (53 + 1)) \\12981 &:= ((13 + 5!) + 79) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}) \\12982 &:= 1 - (((3! \times 5!) - (7! + (9 - (7 - 5)))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\12983 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((57^{9-7}) - 5)) + (3! + 1) \\12984 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!) - 3!! - 1 \\12985 &:= (((1 + 3!) - (5 - 7)) + 9) \times ((7 \times 53) \times 1) \\12986 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5) + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times ((5^3) + 1)) \\12987 &:= (1^{3!}) - (5! + (((7!/(9 - 7)) - (5^{3!}) - 1)) \\12988 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5! + 7))) \times ((9 + (75/3)) \times 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12989 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! - 9)) - (7 \times (5 - 3!)) \\12990 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (57^{9-7})) - ((5 - (3 - 1))!) \\12991 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5!) - (((7!/(9 - 7)) - (5^{3!}) \times 1) \\12992 &:= 1 - (((3 + 5) - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times 3!)) - 1 \\12993 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (57^{9-7})) - (5 - (3 - 1)) \\12994 &:= (1 - 3) + ((57 \times (9 - 7))^{5-3} \times 1) \\12995 &:= (1357 + (97 \times 5!)) - (3 - 1) \\12996 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5!)) \times (((7 - 9) + (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\12997 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 57)^{9-7}) + (5!/(3! - 1)!) \\12998 &:= (1 - 3) + (5 \times ((7 + 97) \times (5^{3-1}))) \\12999 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (57^{9-7})) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\13000 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7) + 97) \times ((5^3) \times 1) \\13001 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - (7 + (((97 - 5!)^3) - 1)) \\13002 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! - (7 \times 9))^{7-5}) \times (3 + 1)) \\13003 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5! + 3 \times 1) \\13004 &:= ((1 \times 3! + (5^{7-9+7})) + 5!) \times (3 + 1) \\13005 &:= 1 - (3 - ((5! \times 7) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1))) \\13006 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) \times ((79 - (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\13007 &:= (1^3) \times ((5! \times 7) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1)) \\13008 &:= (1^3) + ((5! \times 7) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1)) \\13009 &:= (1 \times (3 + (5! \times 7))) - (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1) \\13010 &:= (1 + (3 + (5! \times 7))) - (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1) \\13011 &:= 1 + ((3 + (5! \times 7)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1)) \\13012 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! - 7!)) + (9 \times (7 \times (5! - (3 \times 1)))) \\13013 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!/(5 + 7)) \times (97 + 5!)) - (3! + 1) \\13014 &:= 1 \times ((3!! + (5 + (7 - 9))) \times ((7 + 5) + (3! \times 1))) \\13015 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (5! - 79)) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}) \\13016 &:= (1^3) \times (((57^{9-7}) + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\13017 &:= (1^3) + (((57^{9-7}) + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\13018 &:= (((1 \times (3! + 5!)) + 7) \times 97) + (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\13019 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + (((5! + 7) \times 97) - (5!/3! \times 1)) \\13020 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 79)) - 7) \times (5 + (3! + 1)) \\13021 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) \times (7 - (9 \times 7))) - 531 \\13022 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((79 + 7!) + 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\13023 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) + ((9 \times (7 + 5)) \times ((3! - 1)!) \\13024 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5) \times 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)) \\13025 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 57)^{9-7}) + 5 + (3 + 1)! \\13026 &:= 13 \times (57 + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1)))\end{aligned}$$

- 13027** := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times 79) + (7 - 5)) \times 31$
13028 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) - ((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 31$
13029 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + ((7! - 97) - (5! \times 3!)))) \times 1$
13030 := $((1 - 35) + (7! / (9 - 7))) + 5! \times (3! - 1)$
13031 := $(1 + 3) \times (57^{9-7}) + (5 \times (3! + 1))$
13032 := $((1 \times 3)!^5) + ((7! + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)!)$
13033 := $((((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + 7) - (5 - 3!)) - 1$
13034 := $((13 + 5!) \times 7) \times ((9 + 75) / 3! \times 1)$
13035 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5! + ((7 + ((9 \times 7) - 5))^{3-1}))$
13036 := $(1 + 3) \times (57^{9-7}) + ((5! / 3) \times 1)$
13037 := $(1 + 3) \times (57^{9-7}) + ((5! / 3) + 1)$
13038 := $(1 + (3! + ((5! + 7) \times 97) + 5)) - (3! + 1)$
13039 := $((((1 + 3)! \times 5) + 7) \times 97) + (((5 - (3 - 1)))!)$
13040 := $(1 + (3! + ((5! + 7) \times 97) + 5)) - (3! - 1)$
13041 := $13579 - (7 + 531)$
13042 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 - 7) - (97 \times ((5! + 3!) + 1)))$
13043 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9) + 7) + ((5 + 3!) - 1)$
13044 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9) + 7) + ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
13045 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9) + 7) + ((5 + 3!) + 1)$
13046 := $(1 - (3! \times (((5 - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times 5) + 3!))) + 1$
13047 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times 97) + (5 + (3! - 1))$
13048 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times 97) + (5 + ((3! \times 1)!)$
13049 := $(1 - 3 \times 5) \times ((79 - (7! / 5)) - 3) + 1$
13050 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 - 9) \times (75 \times (3 \times 1)))$
13051 := $(1 + 3) - (57 \times 9) - ((7 - 5!) \times ((3! - 1)!)$
13052 := $((((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) - 5) - (3! - 1)$
13053 := $((13 - 5!) \times (7 - (9 + ((7 \times 5!) - 3!)))) - 1$
13054 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 \times (7 - 97)) \times (5 + (3 + 1)!))$
13055 := $(1 \times ((357 + (9 + 7)) \times 5)) \times (3! + 1)$
13056 := $(1 \times 3)! \times (((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times 7) - 5) - (3 + 1)!)$
13057 := $((((1 \times 3)! + 57) \times (9 + 7)) + (5^{3+1}))$
13058 := $((1 - (3 \times 5!)) - 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! + (3! - 1)))$
13059 := $(1 \times (((3!^5) + 7!) - 9)) + (7! / (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
13060 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times (3! - 1))$
13061 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7!)) + ((9 - 7) \times (5! + 3 - 1))$
13062 := $((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times 7) \times (9 + 7) + (5 - (3! - 1))$
13063 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5! + 7) \times 97)) + ((5! \times 3!) \times 1)$
13064 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 + 9)^{7-5})) - (3 + 1)$
13065 := $((1 + 3)! \times 57) \times 9 + (753 \times 1)$
13066 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! + ((9 - 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)))$
13067 := $((((1 - 3 + 5)^7) - 9) \times ((7 - 5) \times 3)) - 1$
13068 := $((1 \times 3)!^5) + ((7 \times (9 \times (7 + 5))) \times (3! + 1))$
13069 := $((((1 - 3 + 5)^7) - 9) \times ((7 - 5) \times 3)) + 1$
13070 := $(1 - 35) - (7! - ((9 \times (7! / 5)) \times (3 - 1)))$
13071 := $((1 - 3!) \times (5 - 7)) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!) - 1)$
13072 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 + 9)^{7-5})) + (3 + 1)$
13073 := $((1 - 3!) \times (5 - 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3! - 1))$
13074 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + (((7 + 5!) \times 3!) \times 1)$
13075 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) + 7! + (((9 + 7) - 5) \times ((3! \times 1)!))$
13076 := $((1 + (3 + (5! \times 79))) - 7) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
13077 := $(1 \times ((3 + (5! \times 79)) - 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) + 1)$
13078 := $((1 - 3) - (5! - 7!)) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times ((3! - 1)!))$
13079 := $((1 + 3) - ((5 - 7) - 97)) \times 5! + (3! - 1)$
13080 := $((1 \times 3)!^5) + 7! + (((9 - 7) \times 5!) + (3 + 1)!)$
13081 := $(1357 \times 9) + (7 \times ((5^3) - 1))$
13082 := $(1 \times 3 + ((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) \times 5)) - (3! + 1)$
13083 := $(1 \times ((3! - 57) + ((9 + 7) \times 5!))) \times (3! + 1)$
13084 := $(1 - (3! - (5 + (797 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1)$
13085 := $(1 + 3!) - (5! - (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + 3) + 1)$
13086 := $(1357 + 97) \times (5 + 3 + 1)$
13087 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times (7 \times 9))) + 7! + (5! \times (3 + 1))$
13088 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5! + 7!) + ((9 + (7 - 5)) \times 3!)) + 1)$
13089 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((57 - 9) + ((7! - 5) - ((3! \times 1)!))$
13090 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + (9 - 7)) \times 53 - 1$
13091 := $(13 \times (5 - ((7 - 9) \times 7))) \times (53 \times 1)$
13092 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + (9 - 7)) \times 53 + 1$
13093 := $((((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97) \times 5 - (3 - 1)$
13094 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5! \times (7 + (97 + 5))) + (3! + 1))$
13095 := $(1 - 3!) - ((579 + 7) - (5!^{3-1}))$
13096 := $1 - (3! + (5 + (((7! / (9 - 7)) - (5^{3!})) - 1)))$
13097 := $((((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7) \times 97) \times 5 + (3 - 1)$
13098 := $(1 + ((3!^5) - 79)) + (7! + ((5! \times 3) \times 1))$
13099 := $1 + (((3 - ((5 - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times 5)) \times 3!) \times 1)$
13100 := $1 + (((3 - ((5 - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times 5)) \times 3!) + 1)$
13101 := $(1^{3!}) - (5 + (((7! / (9 - 7)) - (5^{3!})) \times 1))$
13102 := $(1^{3!}) - (5 + (((7! / (9 - 7)) - (5^{3!})) - 1))$
13103 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 \times (9 + (753 - 1)))$
13104 := $(1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times (((7 \times (9 + 7)) - 5) - (3 \times 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}13105 &:= (1 - ((35 \times (79 - 7)) - (5^{3!}))) - 1 \\13106 &:= (1 - ((35 \times (79 - 7)) - (5^{3!}))) \times 1 \\13107 &:= (1 - ((35 \times (79 - 7)) - (5^{3!}))) + 1 \\13108 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + ((5! \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 + 5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\13109 &:= 1 - (3 - (((5 + 7) + 97) \times 5!) + 31)) \\13110 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 57) \times (((9 - 7) - 5!) + 3) \times 1 \\13111 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5! \times (7 + 9)) + ((7 - 53) - 1)) \\13112 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + 79) \times ((7 - 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\13113 &:= 1 \times (((357 - 9) + 75) \times 31) \\13114 &:= 1 + (((357 - 9) + 75) \times 31) \\13115 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((5! - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3!))) + 1) \\13116 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) - ((5! - 3!) + 1) \\13117 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) - ((5! - 3!) \times 1) \\13118 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) - ((5! - 3!) - 1) \\13119 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! - 3))) \times 1 \\13120 &:= 1 - (((3!! + 5) - (((7 \times 9) + 7!) - 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\13121 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times (((5 + 7) - 9^7)) + 5) - 3! \times 1) \\13122 &:= 1 \times ((3^5) \times (7 + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1))) \\13123 &:= 1 + ((3^5) \times (7 + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1))) \\13124 &:= (13 - 5!) + (((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times (5 \times 3!))) + 1) \\13125 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) / (3 \times 1)) \\13126 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) - (7!/9)) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1) \\13127 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) - (5 + ((7!/9) - ((7 + 5) \times (3!! + 1)))) \\13128 &:= (((1 \times 3! + 5) + 7!) - (9 \times 75)) \times (3 \times 1) \\13129 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5 - 7) \times (9^{7 \times 5 - 31})) \\13130 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5!) + 79)) \times (((7 - 5)^{3!}) + 1) \\13131 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7) \times (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\13132 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) \times (((7 - 9) \times 7) - 5!)) \times (3! + 1) \\13133 &:= (((1 + 3!) + (5 \times ((79 \times 7) - 5!))) \times 3!) - 1 \\13134 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 + 7) \times (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\13135 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5 + 7) + 97) \times 5!) + 31 \\13136 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((57^{9-7}) + (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\13137 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) - (((7!/9) - 7) - (5^{3!}) - 1) \\13138 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - ((7 - 9) \times ((7! + 5!) - 31)) \\13139 &:= (1 \times 35) - (7! - ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))) \\13140 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5!) \times (3! - 1)) \\13141 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5!) \times ((7 - (9 - 7)) - 5!)) + 31 \\13142 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 579) - (753 + 1) \\13143 &:= 13 \times (57 + (9 \times (75 + 31)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13144 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\13145 &:= (((1^{3!}) - (5! - 7))^{9-7}) - ((5! - 3!) - 1) \\13146 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 - 7) + 9) + (7 \times (5^{3+1}))) \\13147 &:= (1 - ((3! - 5!) \times (7 + (97 + 5)))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\13148 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 57) \times 9) + ((7 \times 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\13149 &:= (((13 + 5) + (7! - (9 \times 75))) \times 3) \times 1 \\13150 &:= (((13 + 5) + (7! - (9 \times 75))) \times 3) + 1 \\13151 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 - (9 \times 7)) - (5 \times 3!)) \times 1) \\13152 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (79 - 7)) \times (5 + (3! + 1)) \\13153 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5!)) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7! - 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\13154 &:= (((1 + (3!^5)) + 7!) + 97) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\13155 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((57 + 9) + 7!) - ((5! \times 3!) + 1)) \\13156 &:= 13 \times ((5 \times 7) + ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\13157 &:= (1 \times (3^5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times (7 \times (5^3))) - 1) \\13158 &:= ((1^3 + 5!) \times ((7 + 97) + 5)) - 31 \\13159 &:= (1 + (3^5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\13160 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times 5)) \times (3! + 1)) \\13161 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5! \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 + (3!! \times 1)))) \\13162 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (7! - 9)) + 7531 \\13163 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 579) - (7 + 5)) - (3!! + 1) \\13164 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 579) - (7 + 5)) - (3!! \times 1) \\13165 &:= 13 \times 5^{(7-9)^{7-5}} + (3! + 1)! \\13166 &:= ((1 - 35) + ((7 + 97) \times 5!)) + 3!! \times 1 \\13167 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + (3!! - 1)) \\13168 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! + 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\13169 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5)) \times ((7 + 9) \times 75)) - 31 \\13170 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5 - ((79 + 7) \times 5)) \times 31) \\13171 &:= ((1 - 357) \times (9 + (7 - 53))) - 1 \\13172 &:= ((1 - 357) \times (9 + (7 - 53))) \times 1 \\13173 &:= ((1 - 357) \times (9 + (7 - 53))) + 1 \\13174 &:= 1 - (3 \times (5! + (7 - (9 + (7! - 531)))))) \\13175 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5) + (79 + 7)) \times (5 \times 31) \\13176 &:= ((1 - (3 - 57)) \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\13177 &:= (((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + 5! - (3!! - 1) \\13178 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7! - 9) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\13179 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 \times (79 + 7)) - 5) \times 31) \\13180 &:= ((1 - (3! + (5 + 7!))) + (97 \times 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\13181 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (((79 \times 7) - 5!) \times 31) \\13182 &:= (13 - (5 \times (7 + 97))) \times (5 - 31)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13183 &:= ((1+3)^5) - (7 + (((97-5!)^3) + 1)) \\13184 &:= (135 \times 79) + (((7 \times 5!) \times 3) - 1) \\13185 &:= (((1+3!) + (5! + 79)) \times ((7-5)^{3!}) + 1) \\13186 &:= (1 \times (3-5)) \times (7! - (((97 \times 5!) - 3!) - 1)) \\13187 &:= (((1+3)! \times 579) + (7+5)) - (3!! + 1) \\13188 &:= (((1+3)! \times 579) + (7+5)) - (3!! \times 1) \\13189 &:= ((1^{3!} + 5!) \times (((7+9) \times 7) - ((5-3) + 1)) \\13190 &:= (1^{3!}) \times (5 \times ((7!/(9-7)) + (5! - (3-1)))) \\13191 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5!) + (7+9)) \times (7 \times 5)) + 31) \\13192 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 5!) + (7+9)) \times (7 \times 5)) + 31) \\13193 &:= ((1 - (3+5)) + ((7+97) \times 5!)) + (3!! \times 1) \\13194 &:= (13+5) \times ((7 \times 97) + (53+1)) \\13195 &:= 1 \times (35 \times (((7 \times 9) \times (7-5)) \times 3) - 1)) \\13196 &:= ((1 - (3-57)) \times ((9-7) \times 5!)) - (3+1) \\13197 &:= (1^{3!}) \times ((5! \times 79) + (7 \times 531)) \\13198 &:= (1^{3!}) + ((5! \times 79) + (7 \times 531)) \\13199 &:= ((1 + (((3! + 5!)/7) + 97)) \times 5!) - (3!! + 1) \\13200 &:= (1^3 \times ((5 + (7+97)) \times 5!)) + ((3! - 1)!) \\13201 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\13202 &:= ((135 \times 7) - (9-7)) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\13203 &:= (1 - (3!! \times 5)) + ((7-9) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)) \\13204 &:= ((1 - (3-57)) \times ((9-7) \times 5!)) + (3+1) \\13205 &:= 1 + (((3 + (5! \times (7+97))) + (5! \times 3!)) + 1) \\13206 &:= 1 \times (3! - ((5! - ((7 + (9+7)) \times 5!)) \times (3! - 1))) \\13207 &:= ((1+3!)^5) - ((7+9) \times (75 \times (3 \times 1))) \\13208 &:= ((1-3!!) \times 5) + ((7 - (9 - ((7^5) - 3))) + 1) \\13209 &:= (1^{35}) + ((7+97) \times (5! + (3! + 1))) \\13210 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times 5) \times ((7!/(9-7)) + (5! + 3 - 1)) \\13211 &:= 1 \times (3 + ((5! + 7) \times ((9-7) \times (53-1)))) \\13212 &:= (1+3) \times (((57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - 3) \times 1) \\13213 &:= 13 + (5! \times ((7 \times 9) - ((7-53) - 1))) \\13214 &:= (13 \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) - (7!/(((5 - (3-1))!))!) \\13215 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5+7+9) \times ((7!/(5+3)) - 1)) \\13216 &:= ((1-3+5!) \times (7 \times (9-7))) \times (5+3 \times 1) \\13217 &:= ((1-3!!) \times 5) - ((7-9) - ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)) \\13218 &:= ((1+3!)!) + (((5! \times (7 \times 9)) - 7) + (5^{3+1})) \\13219 &:= (((1+35) + 79)^{7-5}) - 3! \times 1 \\13220 &:= ((1^3 + 5!) \times ((7+97) + 5)) + 31\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13221 &:= (((1+35) + 79)^{7-5}) - (3+1) \\13222 &:= (((1+35) + 79)^{7-5}) - (3 \times 1) \\13223 &:= (((1-3) - (5! - 7))^{9-7}) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\13224 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) + (7 \times 5)) \times (3+1)! \\13225 &:= ((1 \times (3!! + (5! \times 79))) + ((7!/5) \times 3)) + 1 \\13226 &:= (((1+3) \times (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5))) + 3) - 1 \\13227 &:= (((1-3) - (5! - 7))^{9-7}) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\13228 &:= (((1+35) + 79)^{7-5}) + (3 \times 1) \\13229 &:= (((1+35) + 79)^{7-5}) + (3+1) \\13230 &:= ((13+57) \times 9) \times (7 \times (5 - (3-1))) \\13231 &:= 1 - ((35 \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5!)) + 3 \times 1) \\13232 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5+7+9) \times (7!/(5+3)))) - 1 \\13233 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5+7+9) \times (7!/(5+3)))) \times 1 \\13234 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5+7+9) \times (7!/(5+3)))) + 1 \\13235 &:= (1 \times (((3 \times 5) + 7!) \times (9-7))) + (5^{3!-1}) \\13236 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) \times (7-5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\13237 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5) - (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) \times ((5 \times 3!) + 1) \\13238 &:= 1 - (((3 - (5 \times 79)) - (7 \times 5)) \times 31) \\13239 &:= ((1 + (3+5)) + ((7 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 3!)) \times 1 \\13240 &:= (1 + (3 + (57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) \times (3+1) \\13241 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) \times 3!))) - 1 \\13242 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) \times 3!))) \times 1 \\13243 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) \times 3!))) + 1 \\13244 &:= ((1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) - 5!) \times (3-1) \\13245 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times (((7 \times ((9+7) + 5)) \times 3!) + 1) \\13246 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5)) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3!)) \times 1) \\13247 &:= (((1-3!) + (5! \times 7)) \times (9+7)) - (5! - (3! + 1)) \\13248 &:= ((1 \times 3!)/5) - ((7!/(9-7)) - ((5^{3!}) - 1)) \\13249 &:= (((1+3) \times 5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3!))) - 1 \\13250 &:= (((1+3) \times 5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3!))) \times 1 \\13251 &:= (((1+3) \times 5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3!))) + 1 \\13252 &:= (1 - (((3-5) - (7+97)) \times (5^3))) + 1 \\13253 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times 7)) + (9-7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\13254 &:= (1+3) + ((5! - (7 \times (9-7))) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\13255 &:= (1-3!) + ((5 + (7 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5)))) \times 3! \times 1) \\13256 &:= 1 \times ((3! \times 5!) - (7! + ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1))) \\13257 &:= 1 + ((3! \times 5!) - (7! + ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1))) \\13258 &:= 1 + (3!! + ((5! + 79) \times (7 \times (5+3+1)))) \\13259 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13260 &:= ((1 \times ((3! \times 5) - 7!)) + (97 \times 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\
 13261 &:= ((1 \times 3! + (5! + 7)) + (9 + 7)) \times (5! - 3!) \\
 13262 &:= (1 + ((3! + (5! + 7)) \times 97)) + ((5! \times 3) \times 1) \\
 13263 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5! - 7) + (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 3!) \\
 13264 &:= (13 \times ((5! \times 7) - 97)) + (5 \times (3!! + 1)) \\
 13265 &:= ((1 + 35) + ((7 \times ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times 3!)) - 1 \\
 13266 &:= ((1 - (3 - (5! + 7))) + 9) \times (75 + (3 + 1)!) \\
 13267 &:= ((1 + 35) + ((7 \times ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times 3!)) + 1 \\
 13268 &:= (1^{3!}) \times (((5! - 7) + (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 3!) \\
 13269 &:= (1^{3!}) + (((5! - 7) + (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 3!) \\
 13270 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + ((5!/3) \times 1) \\
 13271 &:= ((1 + (3^{5!})) + 7!) + ((97 \times 5) - 3!) \\
 13272 &:= (1 - ((3! - 5) - (79 \times (7!/5!)))) \times (3 + 1) \\
 13273 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times (79 \times (7!/(5 \times 3!)))) + 1 \\
 13274 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((5! - (7 \times (9 - 7))) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\
 13275 &:= (13 - (5 - 7)) \times ((9 + (7 \times (5^3))) + 1) \\
 13276 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^{5!}) + (7! + (9 + ((75 \times 3!) + 1))) \\
 13277 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (79 \times 7))) - ((5! - 3!) + 1) \\
 13278 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5)) + (3! \times 1) \\
 13279 &:= 1 + ((3 + ((5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + 5)) \times (3! \times 1)) \\
 13280 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 3!))) \\
 13281 &:= (((1 - (3!! \times 5)) + 79) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1 \\
 13282 &:= (((1 - (3!! \times 5)) + 79) + (7^5)) - 3! + 1 \\
 13283 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times 797) + 531 \\
 13284 &:= ((13 - 5!) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5 - ((3! - 1)!)) \\
 13285 &:= ((1 - (3!! \times 5)) + 79) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1)) \\
 13286 &:= (1 - (3! + ((5! - 7) \times 9))) \times (7 - (5!/3! \times 1)) \\
 13287 &:= ((1 + 35) + 7) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) - (3! \times 1)) \\
 13288 &:= (((1 + 3!))! + ((5 - 7)^9)) + 7! + (5! \times 3!) \\
 13289 &:= 1 - ((3! - (5 \times ((7!/(9 - 7)) - 5))) - (3!! - 1)) \\
 13290 &:= (((13 + 5!) \times 7) + (97 \times 5!)) + (3!! - 1) \\
 13291 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times 79) + (7! - (5^{3! - 1})) \\
 13292 &:= ((1 + (3! \times (5 \times 7))) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - (3 + 1)) \\
 13293 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + 7!) - (9 + 7) \times (5 + 3 - 1) \\
 13294 &:= ((1 + (3! \times (5 \times 7))) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 - (3 + 1)) \\
 13295 &:= (((1 \times 3!))!/5) + ((7!/(9 - 7)) - 5) \times (3! - 1) \\
 13296 &:= (1 + ((3!! - (5 - 7!)) + 9)) + 7531 \\
 13297 &:= (1 - (3!!/5)) + ((7!/9) \times ((7 + 5) \times (3 - 1))) \\
 13298 &:= ((1 + 3) + 57) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5 \times 3!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13299 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + ((5 \times (7!/(9 - 7))) - ((5!/3!) + 1)) \\
 13300 &:= (1^3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1))) \\
 13301 &:= (1^3) + ((5 \times 7) \times (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1))) \\
 13302 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times 5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times (3!! - 1))) \\
 13303 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times (3!! - 1))) \\
 13304 &:= ((1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7)^9))) + (7^5)) - ((3! + 1)!) \\
 13305 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + ((5 + 7!) + (9 + 7531)) \\
 13306 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + ((7^5) - ((3! + 1)!) \\
 13307 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^{5!}) + (7! + (((97 \times 5) + 3!) \times 1)) \\
 13308 &:= (1 \times (3!^{5!})) + ((7 + (97 \times 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\
 13309 &:= (13 \times ((5 - 7)^{(9-7) \times 5})) - (3 \times 1) \\
 13310 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times 7) \times 97 + (5^{3! - 1}) \\
 13311 &:= 1 - (3! - (((5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5^3)) + 1)) \\
 13312 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5! \times (7 + ((9 - 7) - 5)))) - 3! \times 1 \\
 13313 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5!)) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) - (3! - 1) \\
 13314 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - (5^3)) - 1 \\
 13315 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - (5^3)) \times 1 \\
 13316 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - (5^3)) + 1 \\
 13317 &:= (1 - (3 - 5!)) + (((7 + 97) \times 5!) + (3!! - 1)) \\
 13318 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5 \times (7!/(9 - 7))) - 5) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\
 13319 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5^3)) \times 1) \\
 13320 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - ((5^3) - 1)) \\
 13321 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times 5!)) - ((3! - 1)!) \\
 13322 &:= 1 \times (3! + (((5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5^3)) + 1)) \\
 13323 &:= 1 + (3! + (((5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5^3)) + 1)) \\
 13324 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5! \times (7 + ((9 - 7) - 5)))) + 3! \times 1 \\
 13325 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times 5) + (((7 - (9 + 7)) + 5!) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\
 13326 &:= (((1^3 \times (5 \times (7!/(9 - 7)))) + 5) + 3!!) + 1 \\
 13327 &:= (1^3 + (5 \times (7!/(9 - 7)))) + (5 + (3!! + 1)) \\
 13328 &:= (1 \times (35 - 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\
 13329 &:= ((1 + 3) + (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\
 13330 &:= ((1^{35}) \times ((79 + 7) \times 5)) \times 3! \\
 13331 &:= (1^{35}) + (((79 + 7) \times 5) \times 3!) \\
 13332 &:= (13579 - 7) - (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\
 13333 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 7)) + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) \times (3! + 1)) \\
 13334 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) \times (((7 \times (9 + 7)) + 5) - (3 + 1)) \\
 13335 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7)) \times ((9 + (75/3)) + 1) \\
 13336 &:= ((1^{3!}) + 5) + ((79 + 7) \times (5 \times 3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13337 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! + ((5! - 7!) + 9)) + ((7^5) + (3!! + 1)) & 13376 &:= 1 + ((35 + (79 - 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 13338 &:= 13 \times (((57 + 975) - 3!) \times 1) & 13377 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 13339 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) + (((79 + 7) \times 5) \times 31) & 13378 &:= ((1 + (3!! + 57)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 13340 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - ((5^3) - 1)) & 13379 &:= 1 - (3! + (5! - ((7 + 9) \times ((7 \times 5!) + 3 + 1)))) \\ 13341 &:= ((1 - (3 \times (57 \times (9 - (7 \times 5)))))) \times 3 \times 1 & 13380 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times 5) + ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) \times (5 \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 13342 &:= ((1 - (3 \times (57 \times (9 - (7 \times 5)))))) \times 3 + 1 & 13381 &:= ((1 - 3) - 57) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! + ((3! \times 1)!)!) \\ 13343 &:= 1 + (((((3!!/5) - 7) \times 97) + 53) \times 1) & 13382 &:= ((1 - (3!! + 5)) + (7! + (9 \times (7!/5)))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 13344 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + ((5! - 3!) - 1) & 13383 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5 + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times 3!))) - 1 \\ 13345 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) + ((5! - 3!) \times 1) & 13384 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5 + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times 3!))) \times 1 \\ 13346 &:= (13579 + 7) - (5! \times (3 - 1)) & 13385 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5 + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times 3!))) + 1 \\ 13347 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) - 7!) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))) & 13386 &:= ((1^{3!}) - (579 - 7!)) \times ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 13348 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! \times ((7 + 9) \times 7) - 5!)) + (3 + 1)!) & 13387 &:= ((1 \times ((3! + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - (5 + 3!)) \times 1 \\ 13349 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + 5) + (7! + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!) + (3 + 1)!)!) & 13388 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 \times (97 \times 5)) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 13350 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) & 13389 &:= (1 \times (3! - 57)) + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) \times (3! + 1)) \\ 13351 &:= (1 \times 3 + 579) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}) & 13390 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5! + 79)) \times (((7 - 5)^{3!}) + 1) \\ 13352 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 - 7) + (9 \times (7 \times 53))) + 1) & 13391 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7 + (97 \times 5!))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 13353 &:= 13579 - ((75 \times 3) + 1) & 13392 &:= (1^{35}) \times ((7 + 9) \times ((7 \times 5!) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 13354 &:= 13579 - ((75 \times 3) \times 1) & 13393 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5!)) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 13355 &:= 13579 - ((75 \times 3) - 1) & 13394 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5! \times (7 + 9))) + ((7 - 53) \times 1) \\ 13356 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times (53 \times 1)) & 13395 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times ((79 + 7) + 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\ 13357 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5+7}) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1) & 13396 &:= (1 - 35) \times ((79 + 7) - (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 13358 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7))) - (5! - 31) & 13397 &:= (((1^3 + 5!) \times (7 + 9)) \times 7) - (5 \times 31) \\ 13359 &:= (((13 - 5!) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5!/3)) - 1 & 13398 &:= (((1 - 3!!) + 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3!))) \times 1 \\ 13360 &:= (((13 - 5!) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5!/3)) \times 1 & 13399 &:= 1 - (3! \times (((5 - (7 + 9)) \times 7) \times (5 + (3 + 1)!))) \\ 13361 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1)) & 13400 &:= 1 - ((3! + (5 \times 7)) - (((9 + 7) \times 5!) \times (3! + 1))) \\ 13362 &:= (((((13 \times 57) \times 9) + 7) + 5) \times (3 - 1)) & 13401 &:= (((1 + 3!) + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - (5! + 31) \\ 13363 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((57 \times (9 - 7)) \times (5! - 3)) + 1) & 13402 &:= (1 \times (3!! + 5!)) + ((7! - 9) + 7531) \\ 13364 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - (53 + 1)) & 13403 &:= (((((1 \times 3)!)! / 5) + 7) \times (9 + 75)) + (3!! - 1) \\ 13365 &:= (1 - (3 - 57)) \times ((9^{7-5}) \times (3 \times 1)) & 13404 &:= (((((1 + 3) \times 5!) \times 7) - 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - 31)) \\ 13366 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! - 9)) - ((7 + 5)^3)) + 1 & 13405 &:= (1 - (3! - ((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7)))) - (5 \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 13367 &:= 1 - (((3^5) \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) - (5 - 3!))) - 1) & 13406 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (79 \times 7))) + ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 13368 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((5! \times ((7 + 9) \times 7) - 5!)) + (3 + 1)!) & 13407 &:= (1 + 3)! - ((579 - 7!) \times (5 - (3 - 1))) \\ 13369 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1) & 13408 &:= 1 - ((3^5) - (7 \times (975 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 13370 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5! + 7))) \times ((9 + (75/3)) + 1) & 13409 &:= (1 - 35) + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1) \\ 13371 &:= (1 \times (3!! - 5)) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3! + 1)))) & 13410 &:= (1 + (((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - 5!)) - (3! + 1) \\ 13372 &:= ((13 \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + (7 + 5!)) + (3 + 1)!) & 13411 &:= (13 \times (57 + 975)) - (3! - 1) \\ 13373 &:= 13 - (5 \times ((7 - (9 \times 75)) \times (3 + 1))) & 13412 &:= 1 \times (((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - 5!) - (3 + 1) \\ 13374 &:= ((1 \times ((35 + 79) - 7)) \times (5^3)) - 1 & 13413 &:= ((1 \times (3! + (5! \times 7))) \times (9 + 7)) - (5! + 3 \times 1) \\ 13375 &:= 1 \times ((35 + (79 - 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1)) & 13414 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) + 7) \times ((9 \times 75) + 31) \end{aligned}$$

- 13415** := $1 + (((((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - 5!) - 3) + 1)$
13416 := $(1 + 3)! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) / 5) + (3! \times 1)$
13417 := $1 + ((3 + 5) \times ((7! - 9) / ((7 + 5) / (3 + 1))))$
13418 := $(1 - 3) + ((5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
13419 := $(1 \times 3579) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 - 1))$
13420 := $(1 - (3 - 57)) \times (((9 - 7) \times 5!) + 3 + 1)$
13421 := $13579 - ((7 + 5!) + 31)$
13422 := $(1 + (((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - 5!)) + (3! - 1)$
13423 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (((7 \times 9) + (7 \times 53)) - 1)$
13424 := $(1 + (((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - 5!)) + (3! + 1)$
13425 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! \times ((7 + 9) \times 7)) + (5 - (3 + 1)!))$
13426 := $(1 \times (3! - (5! - (7 + 9)))) \times ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1)!)$
13427 := $1 + (((3 + 5!) - 7)^{9-7} - (5 \times 3! \times 1))$
13428 := $((1 - (3! + 5!)) \times 7) - 97 + (5!^{3-1})$
13429 := $((135 \times (7 \times 9)) + 7!) - (5! - (3 + 1))$
13430 := $((1 - 35) \times 79) \times (((7 - 5) - 3!) - 1)$
13431 := $(13579 + 7) - (5 \times 31)$
13432 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
13433 := $(1 - (3!! - (5 + 7))) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 \times (3! + 1)))$
13434 := $((1^3)^5) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!) - (3! \times 1)$
13435 := $((1^{35}) \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times 5!))) - (3! - 1)$
13436 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!) + 3!) \times 1$
13437 := $(1 - ((3! - 5) - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!))) - (3 \times 1)$
13438 := $((1^{3!}) \times 5)! \times (7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5 - (3 \times 1))$
13439 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) \times (5 + 3)) - 1$
13440 := $(1 + 3)! \times ((579 - 7) - ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
13441 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) \times (5 + 3)) + 1$
13442 := $((1^{3!}) \times 5)! \times (7 \times (9 + 7)) + (5 - (3 \times 1))$
13443 := $(1 - ((3! - 5) - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!))) + (3 \times 1)$
13444 := $((1 + 3!!) + (5! + 7)) \times (9 + 7) - ((5^3) - 1)$
13445 := $((1^{35}) \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times 5!))) + (3! - 1)$
13446 := $((1^3)^5) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!) + (3! \times 1)$
13447 := $1 - (((((3 - 5)^7) + 9) + 7) \times 5!) - 3! \times 1$
13448 := $((1^{3!}) \times 5) + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1)$
13449 := $(1^{3!}) + (5 + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1))$
13450 := $1 + ((3! - (5 - 7!)) + ((9 + (7^5)) / (3 - 1)))$
13451 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((79 - (7! - 5)) - 3!!) + 1)$
13452 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) + (7 \times 97) \times ((5! / 3!) - 1)$
13453 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((79 - (7! - 5)) - 3!!) - 1)$
13454 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times 5!) - 3! \times 1$
13455 := $(1 \times (3 - 5!)) \times ((7 + 9) - ((7 + 5!) + 3 + 1))$
13456 := $(1^3 \times ((5 - (7 \times 9))^{7-5})) \times (3 + 1)$
13457 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)$
13458 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (579 \times (7 + ((5 \times 3) \times 1))))$
13459 := $((1 - ((35 \times (7 \times 9)) - 7!)) \times 5) - (3!! + 1)$
13460 := $((1 - ((35 \times (7 \times 9)) - 7!)) \times 5) - (3!! \times 1)$
13461 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) \times 7 + ((97 \times 5!) + (3! - 1)!)!$
13462 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))$
13463 := $((1 + 3)! + (5! \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - (((5 - 3!) + 1)!)!$
13464 := $((13579 + 7) - 5!) - (3 - 1)$
13465 := $(1 + ((3! \times 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!))) - 3! \times 1$
13466 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times 5!) + 3! \times 1$
13467 := $(1 + (3! - 5!)) + ((7 \times 97) \times ((5! / 3!) \times 1))$
13468 := $((13579 + 7) - 5!) + (3 - 1)$
13469 := $13 + (((5! + (7 - 9)) - (7 - 5))^{3-1})$
13470 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) \times (5! / (3 + 1))$
13471 := $(1 + (((3 + 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 \times 3!))) \times 1$
13472 := $((1 + 3) + (5! \times (7 \times (9 - 7)))) \times (5 + 3 \times 1)$
13473 := $(13579 - 75) - 31$
13474 := $((1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) - 5) \times (3 - 1)$
13475 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5 \times ((7 \times 97) - 5)) \times (3 + 1))$
13476 := $1 + 35 + ((7! / 9) \times (((7 + 5) / (3 \times 1)))!)$
13477 := $(1 - (3! \times ((5 \times (7 - 97)) \times 5))) - (3 + 1)!$
13478 := $(1 + ((3! + 5!) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - 5))) - (3! - 1)$
13479 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
13480 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 + ((3! - 1)!)!)$
13481 := $13 \times ((57 + 975) + (3! - 1))$
13482 := $((13 - 5!) \times (7 - 97)) / 5 \times (3! + 1)$
13483 := $(13579 - 7) - (5! - 31)$
13484 := $(1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
13485 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
13486 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 - (7 \times 97)) \times (5! / 3!)) \times 1)$
13487 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 - (7 \times 97)) \times (5! / 3!)) - 1)$
13488 := $13 - (((5 - 7) - 9) \times ((7 \times 5)^{3-1}))$
13489 := $((1 - 35) \times 7) \times 9 + 7 + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
13490 := $((1 - 3!) - 5) \times (((7 - 97) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1)$
13491 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (79 \times (7! / 5!)) + (3 - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 13492 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7))) - (5! - (3 + 1)) & 13531 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + 7!) + (97 \times 5!) - (3 + 1)! \\ 13493 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5! / (3 \times 1))) & 13532 &:= (13579 + (7 - 53)) - 1 \\ 13494 &:= ((1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) + 5) \times (3 - 1) & 13533 &:= (13579 + (7 - 53)) \times 1 \\ 13495 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (79 \times (7! / 5!))) + 3! \times 1 & 13534 &:= 13579 + ((7 - 53) + 1) \\ 13496 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5!)) - 7)^{9-7}) + (5! / (3 \times 1)) & 13535 &:= (13579 - 75) + 31 \\ 13497 &:= ((13579 + 7) - 5!) + 31 & 13536 &:= 13579 - ((7 + 5) + 31) \\ 13498 &:= ((1 + ((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7))) - (5! / 3)) + 1 & 13537 &:= 1 - ((3 - ((5 + 7) + 9)) \times (753 - 1)) \\ 13499 &:= ((1 + ((3! / 5) - 7)) \times 97) + ((5! - 3!) - 1) & 13538 &:= (135 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! - ((5 + 3) - 1)) \\ 13500 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times ((5 \times 3!) \times 1) & 13539 &:= (1357 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) - 31 \\ 13501 &:= (13579 - (75 + 3)) \times 1 & 13540 &:= (((1 \times ((3! + 5!) + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - (5 + 3!)) - 1 \\ 13502 &:= (13579 - (75 + 3)) + 1 & 13541 &:= (1 \times (3! + 5)) \times (((7 + 9) \times 75) + 31) \\ 13503 &:= ((1 - ((3! \times 5) \times ((7 - 9) \times 75))) \times 3) \times 1 & 13542 &:= 13579 - ((7 \times 5) + 3 - 1) \\ 13504 &:= (((1^{3!})^5) + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3!)) + 1) & 13543 &:= (((13 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! + 5!)) + (3 + 1) \\ 13505 &:= (1 + (3! - (5 - 7!))) + (9 \times (7 \times ((5! + 3) \times 1))) & 13544 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + (7! - (9 + 7))) - (5! - ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 13506 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5 + (79 \times 7))) + ((5! - 3!) \times 1) & 13545 &:= (135 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7! \times (5 - (3 + 1))) \\ 13507 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (79 \times 7))) + ((5! - 3!) + 1) & 13546 &:= (13579 - 7) + (5 - 31) \\ 13508 &:= (1^{3!}) \times ((57 \times (((9 - 7) \times 5!) - 3)) - 1) & 13547 &:= (13579 - (7 \times 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 13509 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (57 \times ((9^{7-5}) - (3 - 1))) & 13548 &:= ((135 \times (7 \times 9)) + 7!) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 13510 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) - (75 \times (3 + 1)!) & 13549 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (97 \times 5)) - 31 \\ 13511 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5! - 3!)) - 1 & 13550 &:= (13579 + 7) - (5 + 31) \\ 13512 &:= (13 - (5 - 7!)) + ((97 - 5)^{3-1}) & 13551 &:= (((13 + (5! + 7)) \times 97) - (5 \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 13513 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5! - 3!)) + 1 & 13552 &:= (1^3 + 5!) \times (7 + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) / (3 \times 1))) \\ 13514 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (7! / 9))) + ((7 - 53) \times 1) & 13553 &:= 1 + (((3! + 5) \times (7 \times (9 + (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 13515 &:= ((13 + 5!) \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7! + 5!) - (3 + 1)!) & 13554 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5 - 7)) \times 9) \times (753 \times 1) \\ 13516 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5)) \times (((7 \times 9) \times 7) - 5) \times 31 & 13555 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) - (5^{3-1}) \\ 13517 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5)) + (((7 \times 9) \times 7) - 5) \times 31 & 13556 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (7 \times 97)) - (5! / (3! - 1)) \\ 13518 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + 5!) \times (7 + 9)) + (75 + 3 \times 1) & 13557 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) + (((9 + 7) + 5) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 13519 &:= 13579 - (7 + (53 \times 1)) & 13558 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5!) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times 5!))) - (3! - 1)) \\ 13520 &:= (13579 - 7) - (53 - 1) & 13559 &:= 13 \times ((5! + 797) + ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 13521 &:= (1^{3!}) - (5 \times ((7 + 97) \times (5 - 31))) & 13560 &:= ((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) - 5) \times (3! - 1) \\ 13522 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5! + 7)) - (9 - ((7 - 5!)^{3-1})) & 13561 &:= ((13 + (5! + 7)) \times (97 + 5)) - (3! - 1) \\ 13523 &:= 1 - (((3! / 5) - ((7! - (97 \times 5)) \times 3)) - 1) & 13562 &:= (((1 \times (3! + 5!) + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5 + 3!) - 1 \\ 13524 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7) \times ((9 \times 75) - 31) & 13563 &:= (1^3 + (5! + (7 + 9))) \times (75 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 13525 &:= (1 - (3! \times ((5 \times (7 - 97)) \times 5))) + (3 + 1)! & 13564 &:= (((1 \times (3! + 5!) + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5 + 3!) + 1 \\ 13526 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! - 7) - 9) \times ((7 + 5!) + 3 \times 1)) & 13565 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) - (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 13527 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5!)) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5! \times 3)) - 1 & 13566 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) + 7) - (9 + 7) \times (5 - (3! - 1)) \\ 13528 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (7! / 9))) - ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) & 13567 &:= (((1 + 3) \times ((5! - (7 \times 9)) + 7)) \times 53) - 1 \\ 13529 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5!)) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5! \times 3)) + 1 & 13568 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 + 7))) \times ((9 + 7) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 13530 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) - ((97 + 5!) \times 3) - 1) & 13569 &:= (13 \times (((5 + 7) \times 97) - 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13570 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) \times 97) - (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\13571 &:= ((13579 - 7) - 5) + (3 + 1) \\13572 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times 97) - 5) + 3 \times 1 \\13573 &:= 13579 - ((7 + 5)/(3 - 1)) \\13574 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) - ((5 - (3 - 1)))! \\13575 &:= ((1 \times ((35 - 7) \times 97)) \times 5) - (3! - 1) \\13576 &:= (1 - 3) + ((57 \times 9) - 75) \times 31 \\13577 &:= (((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) - 5) + (3 - 1) \\13578 &:= (1 + 357) + ((9 + 7) \times 5) \times 31 \\13579 &:= (13579 - (7 - 5)) + (3 - 1) \\13580 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((57 + ((9 \times 7) \times 53)) - 1) \\13581 &:= ((13579 - 7) + 5) + (3 + 1) \\13582 &:= (((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5! - 31) \\13583 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\13584 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (579 - ((7 \times (5 - 3)) - 1)) \\13585 &:= 13579 + ((7 + 5)/(3 - 1)) \\13586 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + ((5 - (3 - 1)))! \\13587 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\13588 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) + (7 \times (97 \times (5!/(3! \times 1)))) \\13589 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7 - ((9 \times (75 - 3!)) - 1)) \\13590 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) \times 97) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\13591 &:= ((1 \times 3!)/5) + (7 + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! + 1)))) \\13592 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (7!/9))) + ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\13593 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7) \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3! \times 1)) \\13594 &:= ((13579 + 7) + (5 + 3)) \times 1 \\13595 &:= ((13579 + 7) + (5 + 3)) + 1 \\13596 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5) - ((79 - (7! - 5)) - ((3! + 1)!)) \\13597 &:= (13579 + (7 + 5)) + 3! \times 1 \\13598 &:= (13579 - 7) - (5 - 31) \\13599 &:= ((1^3 \times ((5 - 7)^9)) + (7! + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\13600 &:= (((1^3!) \times 5) + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1) \\13601 &:= (1357 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) + 31 \\13602 &:= 1 \times (3! \times (5 - ((7 \times 9) - (75 \times 31)))) \\13603 &:= 1 + (3! \times (5 - ((7 \times 9) - (75 \times 31)))) \\13604 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5 + (3! - 1)) \\13605 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + (5^{3-1}) \\13606 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + (7!/9))) - ((7 - 53) \times 1) \\13607 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1)) \\13608 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + (5 + 3 - 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13609 &:= ((1^3 + (57 \times 9)) - 75) \times 31 \\13610 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + (79 + (7! - 5))) + (3! \times 1) \\13611 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (97 \times 5)) + 31 \\13612 &:= (13579 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 - 1) \\13613 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5!)) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 + 5!)) + (3 + 1)! \\13614 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 5) - 797) + (5!^{3-1}) \\13615 &:= 13579 + (7 + (5 + (3 + 1)!)) \\13616 &:= 13579 + ((7 \times 5) + 3 - 1) \\13617 &:= (13579 + (7 \times 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\13618 &:= (((1 + (3!^5)) + 7!) + (9^{7-5})) + 3! \times 1 \\13619 &:= (((((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) - 3!) + 1 \\13620 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5) \times 7) \times 975) + 31 \\13621 &:= 1 - (3! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5) - ((3! + 1)!)) \\13622 &:= (13579 + 7) + (5 + 31) \\13623 &:= 13579 + (75 - 31) \\13624 &:= (13579 - 7) + (53 - 1) \\13625 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5!)) - (7 \times (9 - 7))) \times (5^3 \times 1) \\13626 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 - (7 \times 975)) + (3! + 1)) \\13627 &:= (((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7! + 97)) - ((5 - 3!) + 1) \\13628 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 \times (7 + (9 \times 75))) - (3 \times 1)) \\13629 &:= ((1 + (3! \times (5 \times 7))) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) - (3! - 1) \\13630 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) \times (7 - 5!)) - (3! + 1) \\13631 &:= ((1 - ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) \times (7 - 5!)) - (3! \times 1) \\13632 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 \times (7 + (9 \times 75))) - (3 - 1)) \\13633 &:= (1 + 3!) + (5! + ((7 + 97) \times (5! + 3 \times 1))) \\13634 &:= ((1^3 + 5)! + ((7! + ((9 \times 7) \times (5^3)))) - 1) \\13635 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5 - (7 \times 975))) \times (3 - 1)) \\13636 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 - (7 \times 975))) \times (3 - 1) \\13637 &:= (((1 - 3!) - ((5! - 7) - 9)) \times 7) + (5!^{3-1}) \\13638 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - (7 - ((9 + 7) \times 5!)))) \times 3! \times 1 \\13639 &:= 13579 + (7 + (53 \times 1)) \\13640 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 - ((3! - 1)!)) \\13641 &:= (((135 \times (7 \times 9)) + 7!) + 5!) - (3 + 1)! \\13642 &:= (1^3 - (5 - (7 \times 975))) \times (3 - 1) \\13643 &:= 1 - (((3 - 57) + (9 + 7)) \times ((5! \times 3) - 1)) \\13644 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! - (97 \times 5)) - (3! + 1)) \\13645 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) \times ((7 \times 975) - (3 \times 1))) \\13646 &:= 1 - (35 + (((7 - 9) \times 7!) - (5 \times (3! \times 1)))) \\13647 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! - (97 \times 5)) - (3! \times 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13648 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 - (7 \times 975)) - 3) - 1) \\13649 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 57) \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) - 31 \\13650 &:= (1 \times (35 + 7)) \times (975 / (3 \times 1)) \\13651 &:= (13579 + 75) - (3 \times 1) \\13652 &:= (13579 + 75) - (3 - 1) \\13653 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5! - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3)))) - 1 \\13654 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3)) \times 1) \\13655 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3)) + 1) \\13656 &:= (13579 + 75) + (3 - 1) \\13657 &:= (13579 + 75) + (3 \times 1) \\13658 &:= (1 \times (3579 + (7! \times (5 - 3)))) - 1 \\13659 &:= ((1 \times (3! + (5! \times 7))) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! + 3 \times 1) \\13660 &:= (1 + 3) + (5! + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times 531))) \\13661 &:= (13579 - 7) + (5! - 31) \\13662 &:= (1^3) + (((5 - 7) + 97) / 5) \times (3!! - 1) \\13663 &:= 1 + ((3 \times ((57 \times 9) - 7)) \times (5 + 3 + 1)) \\13664 &:= 1 \times (((35 - 7) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3)) \times 1) \\13665 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5) \times 7!) + ((9 + 7) - (5 \times 3!! \times 1))) \\13666 &:= 1 + (((35 - 7) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3)) + 1) \\13667 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (((5! - 7) - 9) \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\13668 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 57) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! + 1))) \\13669 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) - 3!) \times 1) \\13670 &:= (1 + 3) - (5 - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) + 1))) \\13671 &:= (1 - 3) + (((57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) - 3!) - 1) \\13672 &:= (1^{35}) + ((7! - 9) + ((7 + 5) \times (3!! \times 1))) \\13673 &:= (1^{3!}) \times ((57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) - (3! + 1)) \\13674 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + (7 - (9 - (7^5)))) - 3! \times 1 \\13675 &:= 13579 + (7 + (5! - 31)) \\13676 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) + ((9 - 7) \times ((5 - 3!!) \times 1)) \\13677 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + (7 - (9 - (7^5)))) - (3 \times 1) \\13678 &:= ((1^{3!}) + ((57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) - 3)) \times 1 \\13679 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\13680 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) + 1)) \\13681 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 - 7) + 97) / 5) \times (3!! + 1) \\13682 &:= (1^3) + (((5 - 7) + 97) / 5) \times (3!! + 1) \\13683 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + (7 - (9 - (7^5)))) + (3 \times 1) \\13684 &:= (1 - 3 + ((57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) + 3!)) \times 1 \\13685 &:= (1 - 3 + ((57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) + 3!)) + 1 \\13686 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + (7 - (9 - (7^5)))) + 3! \times 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13687 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! + ((7 - 9) \times 7!)) - (5! \times 31)) \\13688 &:= ((1 + ((3^5) \times 7)) + 9) \times (7 + (5 - (3 + 1))) \\13689 &:= ((135 \times 7) \times 9) + ((7! + 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\13690 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5) - (7! + ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!)))) - 1 \\13691 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) + 1)) \\13692 &:= (((1 + 3!!) + (5! + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + ((5^3) - 1) \\13693 &:= (13 - (5! - (7! \times (9 - 7)))) + (5! \times 31) \\13694 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (7 \times 97)) + (5! - 3! \times 1) \\13695 &:= ((135 + 79) \times ((7 - 5)^{3!})) - 1 \\13696 &:= ((135 + 79) \times ((7 - 5)^{3!})) \times 1 \\13697 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9) + (7! + ((5 \times 3!!) \times 1)) \\13698 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (579 - 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) \times 1) \\13699 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 - 7) + 97) / 5) \times (3!! + 1) \\13700 &:= (1^3) + (((5 - 7) + 97) / 5) \times (3!! + 1) \\13701 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 + 7!) - (97 \times 5)) + (3! + 1)) \\13702 &:= ((1 + (3!! \times (5 + 7))) + ((9 + 7) + 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\13703 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times (7 + 97)) - (5! - (3!! - 1)) \\13704 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + (5 + (3! \times 1))) \\13705 &:= (1 \times 3!!) - (5! + ((7! / (9 - 7)) - ((5^{3!}) \times 1))) \\13706 &:= (1^3 \times (57 + 97)) \times (5! - 31) \\13707 &:= (((1^3 + 5!) \times (7 + 9)) \times 7) + (5 \times 31) \\13708 &:= ((1 + 35) + ((7! - 9) + 7!)) + ((5 \times 3!!) + 1) \\13709 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - ((7! - 5) - (3 + 1)!) \\13710 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times ((797 + 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\13711 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 57) \times ((9 - 7) \times 5)) + 31 \\13712 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((57 + 97) \times (5! - 31)) \\13713 &:= 1 - (((3 + 5!) - 7) \times (9 - (7 + 5!))) - (3 + 1)!) \\13714 &:= 1 - (3 - ((5! + 7) \times (97 + ((5 + 3!) \times 1)))) \\13715 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (79 + ((7 + (5^3)) \times 1)) \\13716 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7)) \times 9) \times ((7 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\13717 &:= 1 - (((3 - (5 \times 79)) \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 + 1) \\13718 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (579 - 7)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\13719 &:= ((1^3 \times (5! + (7 \times 9))) \times 75) - (3! \times 1) \\13720 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (7 \times (97 + ((5 - 3) - 1))) \\13721 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + (5! + (3!! + 1)) \\13722 &:= (((135 + 7) \times 97) - 53) + 1 \\13723 &:= 13579 + ((7 + 5)^{3-1}) \\13724 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7))) + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\13725 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times 9) \times (75 / (3 \times 1))\end{aligned}$$

- 13726** := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 - 7)) + (5 - (3! + 1))$
13727 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5!) \times (7 + (97 + 5)) - (3! + 1)$
13728 := $((1 + (3 \times 5!)) + 7) + ((9 + 7) \times 5!) \times 3! \times 1$
13729 := $(1 + 3!!) + ((57 + (97 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
13730 := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 - 7)) - (5 - (3! + 1))$
13731 := $((1^3 \times (5! + (7 \times 9))) \times 75) + (3! \times 1)$
13732 := $((1 + 3!!)! - (5 + (((7 \times 9) - 7!) - (5! \times 3!))))$
13733 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (((5! \times 7) + 9) + ((7 - 5) \times 3!))) - 1$
13734 := $((1 - (3 - (5! + 7))) - (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) + 1)$
13735 := $1 + (3 \times ((579 + 75) \times (3! + 1)))$
13736 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5!) + 79)) \times (75 - (3! + 1))$
13737 := $13579 + ((7 + 5!) + 31)$
13738 := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 - 7)) + ((5 + 3!) - 1)$
13739 := $(1 \times 3! + 5) + (((7!/9) + (7 + 5)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
13740 := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 - 7)) + ((5 + 3!) + 1)$
13741 := $(13579 + 7) + (5 \times 31)$
13742 := $1 - (35 - (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1))))$
13743 := $1 - (3!! + (((5 + 7) \times 97) - ((5^{3!}) + 1)))$
13744 := $(1^{3!}) - ((579 - (7! + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1))$
13745 := $(1 - ((3 - (5 \times 79)) \times (7 \times 5))) + (3 + 1)!$
13746 := $(1 \times 3 + (5 + 79)) \times (7 + (5! + 31))$
13747 := $((1 + 3)!^{5+7-9}) - ((75 + 3) - 1)$
13748 := $((135 + 7) \times 97) + (5 - 31)$
13749 := $(1 \times 3)! - (((579 - 7!) - 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
13750 := $((1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^{3+1})$
13751 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5! + 3 \times 1)))$
13752 := $(1 + (3 \times (5! + 7))) \times (9 \times ((7 \times 5) - 31))$
13753 := $((1 + 3)!^{5+7-9}) - (75 - (3 + 1))$
13754 := $((1 \times 3!!) + (5! + 7!)) + (((9 \times 7) \times (5^3)) - 1)$
13755 := $((1 - 3 + (5 \times 79)) \times 7) \times (5!/ (3 + 1)!)$
13756 := $13 - (((579 - 7!) - 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
13757 := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 - 7)) + (5 \times 3!) - 1$
13758 := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 - 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) \times 1)$
13759 := $((135 + 7) \times 97) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
13760 := $((135 + 7) \times 97) - ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
13761 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) - (7 \times 9) \times (7 - (5 - 31))$
13762 := $(1 - (3 \times (5! - 7!))) - (975 + (3 + 1)!)$
13763 := $1 + 3! + (((5! + 797) \times 5) \times 3 + 1)$
13764 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times (7 - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)))$
13765 := $((1 + 3)! \times 579) - (7 + 5!) - (3 + 1)$
13766 := $((1 - 3!!) - 5) - (7 - (97 + (5!^{3-1})))$
13767 := $((1 + 3) + ((5! + 797) \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1)$
13768 := $((1 - 3) - (5 - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3)))) - 1$
13769 := $((1 - 3) - (5 - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3)))) \times 1$
13770 := $((1 - 3) - (5 - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3)))) + 1$
13771 := $1 - (((3! \times 5!) + (7 - 97)) - (5!^{3-1}))$
13772 := $((1 + 3) - 5!) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1))$
13773 := $((1 + 3)! \times 579) - (7 + 5!) + (3 + 1)$
13774 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times ((5^3) - 1)))$
13775 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times 7)) - (9 + 7) \times (5 + (3! \times 1))$
13776 := $(13 + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times ((7 \times 5) - 3)) - 1$
13777 := $(1 \times (3!! \times 5)) + (7! + (97 + ((5 + 3 - 1)!))$
13778 := $1 - (((3 + 5) \times (7 - 9)) \times 7) \times (5! + 3) - 1$
13779 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 79) + (7! - 531))$
13780 := $((1 - 3!!) - 5) + 7 + 97 + (5!^{3-1})$
13781 := $(1 - 3!!) + (((5! \times 79) + 7!) - (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
13782 := $((1 \times 3!!) + 5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times (3!! - 1))$
13783 := $((1 + 3!!) - ((5 - (7 - 9)))! / 7) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)$
13784 := $(1 + ((3!! + 5!) \times (7 + 9))) + (7^{5-3+1})$
13785 := $((1 + (3!! \times (5 + 7))) - ((9 + 7) - 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)$
13786 := $((13 + 5) + 7) + 97 \times ((5! - 3!) - 1)$
13787 := $((1 + 3)! \times 579) + (7 - (5! - (3 + 1)))$
13788 := $((135 + 7) \times 97) + ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
13789 := $((135 + 7) \times 97) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
13790 := $((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7 - 5! + (3! + 1)$
13791 := $(1 - (3! - (5! \times 79))) + (((7! - 5) - 3!!) + 1)$
13792 := $(1 - 3) + (((5! - ((7 - 9) + 7)) \times 5!) - 3! \times 1)$
13793 := $(1 - 3) + (((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) \times 5) - (3! - 1))$
13794 := $((1^3 \times 5) \times ((79 \times 7) \times 5)) - 31$
13795 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 7)) - (9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31)$
13796 := $((1 + 3!!) \times (5 + 7)) - (((9 + 7) - 5!) - ((3! + 1)!)$
13797 := $((1 - 3 + 5)! - (7 \times 9)) \times (7 \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
13798 := $(1 + 357) + (((9 + 7) \times 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
13799 := $((1 \times (3 + (5 + 7!))) - 9) + (7! + (5! \times 31))$
13800 := $((1 - 3 + (57 - 9)) \times 75) \times (3 + 1)$
13801 := $(1^3) + (5! + (((7 \times (9 - 7)) + 5) \times 3! \times 1))$
13802 := $((1 \times 3)! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - (7! - (5! + 3 - 1))$
13803 := $13579 + ((75 \times 3) - 1)$

- 13804** := 13579 + ((75 × 3) × 1)
13805 := 13579 + ((75 × 3) + 1)
13806 := (((1^{3!}) - 5!) - (7 - 9)) × ((7 - 5) - ((3! - 1))!)
13807 := (((1 + 3!))! + (5 - 7)) + (9 + 7!) + (5! × 31)
13808 := (1 × 3)! - (((5 - ((7 - (9 - 7))))!) × 5!) - (3 - 1))
13809 := ((1 + 3)!⁵⁺⁷⁻⁹) - ((7 + (5 + 3)) × 1)
13810 := 1 × ((3! + (((5! × 79) + 7!) + 5)) - (3!! + 1))
13811 := 1 × (35 + (7 × ((9 + 7) × (5! + 3 × 1))))
13812 := 13579 - (7 - (5! × (3 - 1)))
13813 := 13 + (5! × (79 + ((7 + 5) + (3 + 1)!))
13814 := ((1 + (3 + (5 × (79 × 7)))) × 5) - 31
13815 := (1 × (3 × 5)) × (((7 + (9 + 7)) × (5!/3)) + 1)
13816 := (1 - 3!!) + (((5! × 79) + (7! + (5 × 3))) × 1)
13817 := ((1 × (3 + (5 + 7!))) + 9) + (7! + (5! × 31))
13818 := (1 - 3) + (((5 × 79) × 7) × 5) - (3! - 1))
13819 := 13 × ((57 + 975) + 31)
13820 := (1 - 3) + (((5 × 79) × 7) × 5) - (3 × 1))
13821 := ((1³ × (5 × 79)) × (7 × 5)) - (3 + 1)
13822 := ((1 - 3 + 5)⁷) + ((97 × 5!) - (3! - 1))
13823 := (((1 + 3)!⁵⁺⁷⁻⁹) + 7) - (5 + 3 × 1)
13824 := (1 + 3)! × ((5 + 7) × (9 + ((7 × 5) + 3 + 1)))
13825 := (1 × (35 × 79)) × (((7 - 5) × 3) - 1)
13826 := (13579 + 7) + (5! × (3 - 1))
13827 := (((135 + 7) × 97) + 53) × 1
13828 := (1 + (3! - 5)) + (((7 × 9) × 7) + 5) × 31)
13829 := ((1³ × (5 × 79)) × (7 × 5)) + (3 + 1)
13830 := (((1 + 3) × 5) + (7 × (9 × 7))) × ((5 × 3!) × 1)
13831 := (((1 + 3!!) × 5) + 7!) - (9 - (7! + 5 × 31))
13832 := (1 + 3!) + (((5 - ((7 - 9) × 7)) + 5)³) + 1)
13833 := ((1 × (35 × 7)) + (9 + 7)) × (53 × 1)
13834 := (1 + (((35 × 7) + (9 + 7)) × 53)) × 1
13835 := (1 + (((35 × 7) + (9 + 7)) × 53)) + 1
13836 := ((1 + 3!) + 5) × (((79 × 7) - 5!) + 3! × 1)
13837 := (((1 + (3! + 5!)) + 7) × 97) + (5! + (3!! - 1))
13838 := 1 + (3! + (((5 × 79) × (7 × 5)) + 3! × 1))
13839 := 1 × (3 × (((5! - 7) - 9) + (7! - 531)))
13840 := (((1 × 3) × 5!) - (7 × (9 - 7))) × (5!/(3 × 1))
13841 := (1 - 3!!) - ((5 × 7) × ((9 + (7 - 5!)) × (3 + 1)))
13842 := ((13 + 5) × (7 + (9 + 753))) × 1
13843 := ((13 + 5) × (7 + (9 + 753))) + 1
13844 := 13 + ((5 × ((79 × 7) × 5)) + 3! × 1)
13845 := ((1 × 3) × 5) × ((797 + 5!) + 3! × 1)
13846 := ((1 × 3)! - (5 × ((7 + 9) × 7))) + (5! × ((3! - 1))!)
13847 := (1 + 3)! + (((5 × 79) × (7 × 5)) - (3 - 1))
13848 := (1 + 3)! × (5! + (79 + (7 × (53 + 1))))
13849 := (1 - (((3 - 5) + 7))!) + (97 × (5! + (3 + 1)!))
13850 := (1 - 3) × ((5 - 7!) - ((9 × 7) × (5!/(3 + 1))))
13851 := (1 × (3⁵)) × (((7 × 9) - 7) - 5) + 3! × 1
13852 := (1 - ((3⁵ - 7!)) + (9 × ((7!/5) - (3 - 1)))
13853 := 13 - (((5 × 7) × (9 + 7)) - (5!³⁻¹))
13854 := (((13 × 5!) - 7) × 9) - ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1))
13855 := (1 + 3!) + (((579 - 7) + 5) × (3 + 1)!)
13856 := ((1³ × 5) × ((79 × 7) × 5)) + 31
13857 := (1 × 3) × ((57 × (9⁷⁻⁵)) + 3 - 1)
13858 := (13 × (5! - 79)) × (7 - (5 - (3 + 1)!))
13859 := 1 × ((3 + ((5 × (79 × 7)) × 5)) + 31)
13860 := (1 × 3) × (((5 + 79) - 7) × (5!/(3 - 1)))
13861 := 1 + 35 + ((79 × (7 × 5)) × (3! - 1))
13862 := ((1 + (3! - (5 × 7))) × (9 × 7)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)
13863 := 1 × ((3!! × 5) + ((7! + (9 × 7)) + (5! + ((3! + 1))!))
13864 := (1 + 3)! - (((5 × 7) × (9 + 7)) - (5! × ((3! - 1))!))
13865 := ((1 - (3!!/(5 + 7))) × ((97 × 5) - 3!!)) × 1
13866 := (1 + (3 × 5 × (79 + 75))) × 3! × 1
13867 := 13579 + ((7 + 5) × (3 + 1)!)
13868 := 1 - ((3 × (579 + 7)) - (5^{3!×1}))
13869 := (1 - (3! - (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) × (5³)))) - 1
13870 := (1 - (3! - (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) × (5³)))) × 1
13871 := (1 - (3! - (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) × (5³)))) + 1
13872 := (1 + 3)! × (5 - ((7 × ((9 + 7) + 5)) - (3!! × 1)))
13873 := (1 - 3) + (5 × ((7 × 9) - ((7 - 5!) × (3 + 1)!))
13874 := ((1^{3!}) × (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) × (5³))) - 1
13875 := ((1^{3!}) × (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) × (5³))) × 1
13876 := ((1^{3!}) × (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) × (5³))) + 1
13877 := ((1 - 3) - 5!) + (((7 × (9 + 7)) × (5³)) - 1)
13878 := ((1 - 3) - 5!) + ((7 × (9 + 7)) × ((5³) × 1))
13879 := ((1 - 3) - 5!) + (((7 × (9 + 7)) × (5³)) + 1)
13880 := 1 × ((3! + (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) × (5³))) - 1)

- 13881** := $(1^{3!}) - (5! - (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1))))$
13882 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) + 1$
13883 := $1 + (3! + (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) + 1)$
13884 := $1 \times (3 \times (5 + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times (3 + 1))))))$
13885 := $1 + (3 \times (5 + (7! + ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times (3 + 1))))))$
13886 := $1 \times ((3! - 5!) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1))))$
13887 := $1 + ((3! - 5!) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1))))$
13888 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) + (5 - (3! - 1))))$
13889 := $(((((1 \times 3!)! + 5!) \times (7 + 9)) + (75 \times 3!)) - 1$
13890 := $((1 + (35 - 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - 3!)) - 1$
13891 := $((1 + (35 - 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - 3!)) \times 1$
13892 := $((1 + (35 - 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - 3!)) + 1$
13893 := $(1 \times (3^5)) + (7 \times (975 \times (3 - 1)))$
13894 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times ((5! - 3!) - 1))$
13895 := $((((1 + 35) \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - (3!! + 1)$
13896 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (579 \times ((7 + 5)/(3 \times 1)))$
13897 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 579) \times ((7 - 5)^3)) + 1$
13898 := $(1 + 3) - (((57 \times 9) - 7) - (5!^{3-1}))$
13899 := $1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (7 + ((97 + 5) + 3 + 1)))$
13900 := $((13 - 5!) + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 \times 31))$
13901 := $(((((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7) + 5) - (3! + 1)$
13902 := $1 \times 3! + (579 \times (((7 + 5)/(3 \times 1)))!)$
13903 := $(1 + 3!) + (579 \times (((7 \times 5) - 31))!)$
13904 := $1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times (75 + 3 + 1))$
13905 := $1 + (((3! + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times (75 + 3 + 1))$
13906 := $(((((1 - 3!) + 5!) + 7!) - (9 - 7!)) + (5! \times 31)$
13907 := $1 \times (((3^5) \times (7 - 9)) - (7 - (5!^{3-1})))$
13908 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times (7 - 9))) - (7 - (5!^{3-1}))$
13909 := $13 + (579 \times ((75/3) - 1))$
13910 := $(135 + 79) \times (((7 - 5)^{3!}) + 1)$
13911 := $((((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (7!/9)) + 7!) - (5! - 31)$
13912 := $(1^3 + ((5! + (7! - 9)) + 7!)) + (5! \times 31)$
13913 := $(((((1 - 3) - (5 \times 79)) + (7! - 5)) \times 3) - 1$
13914 := $((1 + 3!!) + (5! \times 79)) - (7 - (5! \times 31))$
13915 := $(((((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7) + 5) + (3! + 1)$
13916 := $((1 \times 3) \times (((5! + 79) + 7!) + 5!) - 3!!)) - 1$
13917 := $((1 \times 3) \times (((5! + 79) + 7!) + 5!) - 3!!)) \times 1$
13918 := $((1 \times 3) \times (((5! + 79) + 7!) + 5!) - 3!!)) + 1$
13919 := $((1 \times 3 + 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times ((5 \times 3!) + 1)$
13920 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 \times (((7 + 9) \times 7) + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1))$
13921 := $((((1 \times 3!)! - ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5!))) - (3! + 1)$
13922 := $((((1 \times 3!)! - ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5!))) - (3! \times 1)$
13923 := $((((1 \times 3) - 5!) + (((7 - (9 - 7))! \times (5! - 3))) \times 1$
13924 := $(((((1 \times 3)^5) - (7 - (9 - 7))) - 5!)^{3-1}$
13925 := $(1^{357}) + ((9 - (7 + 5!))^{3-1})$
13926 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5!) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5! \times (3! - 1)))$
13927 := $(1 + 3!) + (5! - (((7 - 9) \times 7!) - (5! \times 31)))$
13928 := $((1 \times (3 - ((5 \times 79) - (7! - 5)))) \times 3) - 1$
13929 := $(1 \times (3 - ((5 \times 79) - (7! - 5)))) \times (3 \times 1)$
13930 := $((((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7) \times ((9 - ((7!/5) - 3)) + 1)$
13931 := $1 - (35 \times (7 + (9 \times ((7 - 53) + 1))))$
13932 := $(1 + (35 + 7)) \times ((975/3) - 1)$
13933 := $1 + ((3! + (5 \times (7 + 9))) \times (7 + 5 \times 31))$
13934 := $((((1 \times 3!)! - ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5!))) + (3! \times 1)$
13935 := $(13 + ((5! + (7 - 9))^{7-5})) - (3 - 1)$
13936 := $(1^3) - (5 \times (((79 - (7^5))/3!) + 1))$
13937 := $1^{35} + ((7 + 9) \times ((7 \times 5!) + 31))$
13938 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) \times 5))) \times 3! \times 1$
13939 := $(13 + ((5! + (7 - 9))^{7-5})) + (3 - 1)$
13940 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)$
13941 := $((1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + (5! \times 3!))) + 1$
13942 := $13 + (((5! + (7! + 9)) + 7!) + (5! \times 31))$
13943 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times (7 + 97)) + (5! + (3!! - 1))$
13944 := $(1 + 3) \times ((579 + (7 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1)$
13945 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) - (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + (5!^{3-1})$
13946 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
13947 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! - (7 \times 97))) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
13948 := $((13 \times (5! \times 7)) - 97) + (5^{3!-1})$
13949 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3!)) - 1)$
13950 := $((1 - (((3 \times 5) - 7) - 97)) \times 5) \times 31$
13951 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times ((97 + 5) \times (3 + 1)))$
13952 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1)$
13953 := $((1 - 3!!) - (5! - 7!)) + (9753 - 1)$
13954 := $(((((1 \times 3!) \times 5) \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 + (3!! - 1))$
13955 := $(((((1 \times 3!) \times 5) \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 + (3!! \times 1))$
13956 := $((1 + (3! - (5 \times 79))) + 7!) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)$
13957 := $1 - ((3 \times (((5 \times 79) - 7!) - 5)) - (3! \times 1))$
13958 := $((((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7) \times ((9 - ((7!/5) - 3)) - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13959 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! + (5! \times 7) - 9) \times ((7 + 5) - (3 \times 1)) & 13981 &:= (1^3 + (5 + 7)) + (97 \times (5! + (3 + 1)!)) \\
 13960 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 + 7))) \times ((9 \times 75) + (3!! + 1)) & 13982 &:= (1 + 3!!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times (7!/5!)) + 31 \\
 13961 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times ((5 + 79) \times 7)) - (5! + 31) & 13983 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) + 9) \times (7 + (53 - 1)) \\
 13962 &:= (13 \times (5 - 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times (3! - 1))) & 13984 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7 + 9)) \times ((7 \times (5^3)) - 1) \\
 13963 &:= (13 + (5 \times (7 - 97))) + (5^{3-1}) & 13985 &:= (((1 \times (3! + ((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)))) + 5!) \times 3!) - 1 \\
 13964 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5) + 7) - (97 \times (5! + (3 + 1)!))) & 13986 &:= (1 \times ((35 + 7) \times 9)) \times (((7 \times 5) + 3) - 1) \\
 13965 &:= (1^3 + 5) - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5^{3-1})) & 13987 &:= 1 - ((3 \times 5) - (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times (5^3))) + 1)) \\
 13966 &:= (1 - (3!! \times ((5 - 7) \times 9))) + ((7!/5) - (3 \times 1)) & 13988 &:= (1 - ((3 - (5 - 79)) \times 7)) \times (5 - 31) \\
 13967 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) - 1) & 13989 &:= (1 - ((3 \times ((5! - 7!) + (9 + 7))) + (5 + 3!!!))) + 1 \\
 13968 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5 - 7)) \times (97 \times (5 + 31)) & 13990 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5! + 7) - ((975 \times 3) \times 1)) \\
 13969 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7! \times (5 - 3)) + 1) & 13991 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5)) + (3!! - 1) \\
 13970 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5)) + (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times (5^3))) - 1) & 13992 &:= (1357 + 975) \times (3! \times 1) \\
 13971 &:= (1^{3!}) - ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - ((5^3) + 1))) & 13993 &:= (1 - 3!!) - ((57 \times (9 + 7)) - ((5^{3!}) - 1)) \\
 13972 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - 7!) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3! + 1)) & 13994 &:= (((1 \times 3! + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5! - 3)) - 1 \\
 13973 &:= 1 - (3 + (((5! - (7 \times 97)) \times 5) \times (3! - 1))) & 13995 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 - (7 \times (9 + 75))) \times (3 + 1)!) \\
 13974 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (7!/9)) + (7! + (5 - 31)) & 13996 &:= ((1^{3!}) - 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\
 13975 &:= ((1 + 35) + 7) \times (975/3 \times 1) & 13997 &:= (((1 - 3!!) + 5) + (((7! - 9) - (7 + 5!)) \times 3)) - 1 \\
 13976 &:= (1 - (3 \times ((5 \times 79) - 7!))) + ((5!/3) \times 1) & 13998 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5 - (((7!/9) \times (75/3)) \times 1)) \\
 13977 &:= (1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7 + 9) \times ((7 \times (5^3)) - 1)) & 13999 &:= (1^{35}) \times (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times (5^3))) - 1) \\
 13978 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 5) \times ((7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) + (3! \times 1)) & 14000 &:= ((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1))) \\
 13979 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5! - (7 \times 97)) \times 5) \times (3! - 1)) \\
 13980 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) \times 7) + 5) \times 3! \times 1
 \end{aligned}$$

2.8 Numbers From 14001 to 16000

$$\begin{aligned}
 14001 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 \times 79) + 7)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) & 14014 &:= ((13 \times 5!) \times ((7 \times 9)/7)) + (5 - 31) \\
 14002 &:= (1^{35}) + (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times (5^3))) + 1) & 14015 &:= 1 - (((3 - (5 - 79)) \times 7) \times (5 - 31)) \\
 14003 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) - (7! + 5 \times 31) & 14016 &:= (1 + 3)! \times ((579 - 7) + ((5 + 3!) + 1)) \\
 14004 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! - 7)) - (9 \times 7)) \times (5 + 31) & 14017 &:= 13 - (((5 \times (7!/9)) - (7^5)) + 3) \times 1 \\
 14005 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 - 97)) + (5^{3 \times 1}) & 14018 &:= (1 + (35 + 7)) \times ((975/3) + 1) \\
 14006 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) - 1)) & 14019 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 579) + ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\
 14007 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 5) \times ((7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) + (3! + 1)) & 14020 &:= ((1 + 3)! - (5 - ((7 + 9) \times (7 \times (5^3)))) + 1) \\
 14008 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) + (((7!/9) \times (75/3)) \times 1) & 14021 &:= (13 \times (5 + 797)) + (5 \times (3!! - 1)) \\
 14009 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5) + (((7!/9) \times (75/3)) + 1) & 14022 &:= ((1 \times 3! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3 \times 1) \\
 14010 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (7 - 97)) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)) & 14023 &:= (1 + ((35 + 7) \times 9)) \times (((7 \times 5) + 3) - 1) \\
 14011 &:= ((1 - ((3! - 5!) \times 79)) + 7!) - (5 + 31) & 14024 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5 - 7!)) + (9 - (75 \times ((3! - 1)!)))) \\
 14012 &:= (1 + (3 + 5!)) \times (7 + ((97 + 5) + 3 + 1)) & 14025 &:= 13 - (((5 \times 79) - 7) - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))) \\
 14013 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) + 7) \times ((9 - 7!) + (5! \times (3 \times 1))) & 14026 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (7!/9)) + 7!) - (5 - 31)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14027 &:= (1^3 - (5 - 7!)) - (9 - (75 \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\14028 &:= ((1 + 3!) - ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times (5! - 3!))) - 1 \\14029 &:= ((1 + 3!) - ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times (5! - 3!))) \times 1 \\14030 &:= ((1 + 3!) - ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times (5! - 3!))) + 1 \\14031 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9))/7) \times 5 + 31 \\14032 &:= (135 \times (7 + 97)) - ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\14033 &:= (135 \times (7 + 97)) - ((5 + 3) - 1) \\14034 &:= 1 - (3! - ((5! + (7 - (9 + 7))) \times 5!) + (3!! - 1)) \\14035 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((7 - 9) + 7)!) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\14036 &:= (((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\14037 &:= 1 - (((3 + ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5!)) + 3!!) + 1) \\14038 &:= 1 - (((3 + ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5!)) + 3!!) \times 1) \\14039 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5!) + (3!! - 1)) \\14040 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5 + 79))) + 7) \times (53 + 1) \\14041 &:= 1 - ((3 \times ((5! - 7) - 9)) \times ((7 - 53) + 1)) \\14042 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((79 + (7 \times 5)) + (3! - 1)) \\14043 &:= (1 \times (3 - ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5!))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\14044 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + ((7 + 9) \times 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)!)) \\14045 &:= (1 + ((3!!/5) + ((7 - (9 - 7))!)) \times (53 \times 1) \\14046 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 + ((7 + 9) \times 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)!)) \\14047 &:= (135 \times (7 + 97)) + ((5 + 3) - 1) \\14048 &:= ((13 - (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\14049 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5 \times (7 + 97))) \times (5 + 3 + 1) \\14050 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 + ((7 + 9) \times 7)) \times 5!) + 3! \times 1) \\14051 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + (7! - 9))) - (7 \times (5! + 31)) \\14052 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times 5!)) + 3! \times 1 \\14053 &:= (13 + (((5! - (7! + 9)) + 7!) \times 5!)) + (3!! \times 1) \\14054 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) + (5!^{3-1}) \\14055 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times (79 - 7))) + 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\14056 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + 7) + 9 \times (((7!/5) - 3) - 1) \\14057 &:= ((1 - (((3!^5) - 7!) - 9)) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)! \\14058 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) - ((9 - 7) \times 531) \\14059 &:= ((1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3)) \times 1 \\14060 &:= 1 - (((357 - 9) - 7) - (5!^{3-1})) \\14061 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5!)) - 7) \times (((9 + 7) - 5!) - (3! - 1)) \\14062 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (579 + 7)) + (5 - (3! + 1)) \\14063 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 \times (9 - 7))^{5-3+1}) \\14064 &:= ((1 + (3! + 579)) \times (7 + 5)) \times (3 - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14065 &:= (1 + (3 \times (((5 - 7)^9) + 7!))) + (5! \times (3 + 1)) \\14066 &:= ((13 \times 5!) \times ((7 \times 9)/7)) - (5 - 31) \\14067 &:= ((13 - 5!) + (7 \times ((9 \times 75) \times 3))) - 1 \\14068 &:= ((13 - 5!) + (7 \times ((9 \times 75) \times 3))) \times 1 \\14069 &:= ((13 - 5!) + (7 \times ((9 \times 75) \times 3))) + 1 \\14070 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) + (7 + 9)) \times (((7!/5) - 3) \times 1) \\14071 &:= ((1 + (3!^5))/7) + (9 \times ((7 + 5) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\14072 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\14073 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) - ((9 - 7) \times 531) \\14074 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) + (7! + (9 \times (((7!/5) - 3) - 1))) \\14075 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (5! + (7 \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3)))) - 1 \\14076 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5)) + 7) \times ((97 + 5) \times (3! \times 1)) \\14077 &:= (1 - (((3!^5) - 7!) - (9 + ((7^5) - 3)))) - 1 \\14078 &:= (1 - (((3!^5) - 7!) - (9 + ((7^5) - 3)))) \times 1 \\14079 &:= (1 - (((3!^5) - 7!) - (9 + ((7^5) - 3)))) + 1 \\14080 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (((5! + (7 \times 9)) - 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\14081 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - ((7 \times 97) - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\14082 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + ((7! + 9) + 7)) - 5!) \times (3 \times 1) \\14083 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) \times (7 - (9 \times 7))) + 531 \\14084 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - ((9 \times 75) + (3!! + 1)) \\14085 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (7! - ((9 + 7) \times 5))) \times (3! - 1) \\14086 &:= (((1 + 3!)!/5) \times (7 \times (9 - 7))) + 5 - 31 \\14087 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((5! - 79) \times (7^{5-3+1})) \\14088 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((579 \times 7) - 531) \\14089 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5)) \times (7!/9)) + 7!) + (5! - 31) \\14090 &:= (((1 - 35) \times 79) + (7^5)) - 31 \\14091 &:= (1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 79) + 7) \times 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\14092 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - (5!/3! \times 1)) \\14093 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) - (5!/3! \times 1) \\14094 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 5) \times ((7 + (97 \times 5)) - 3! \times 1) \\14095 &:= 1 + (((35 \times 7) + (9 + 7)) \times (53 + 1)) \\14096 &:= 1 \times ((3! + 5) - ((7!/(9 + 7)) - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)))) \\14097 &:= 1 + ((3! + 5) - ((7!/(9 + 7)) - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)))) \\14098 &:= ((135 + 7) - 9) \times (75 + 31) \\14099 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (5 + (7 \times (9 \times 7)))) \times (5 \times 3!)) - 1 \\14100 &:= ((1 + (3^5 + (7 - 9))) - 7) \times (5!/(3 - 1)) \\14101 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5!)) + 7) + (97 \times (5! + (3 + 1)!)) \\14102 &:= (((1 - (3 \times 57)) \times 9) + 7) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\14103 &:= (((1 - (3 \times 57)) \times 9) + 7) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)\end{aligned}$$

- 14104** := $((1 \times 3)!^5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times (5! - (3! + 1)))$
14105 := $((13 - 5!) + ((7!/9) + (7 - 5))) \times 31$
14106 := $((1 - (3 \times (5! - 7))) + (((9 - 7) + 5)!)) \times (3 \times 1)$
14107 := $(1 - 3!) + (((57 \times 9) + 75) \times (3 + 1)!)$
14108 := $((1^{3!}) - 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3! \times 1))$
14109 := $((1 - ((3 - (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7))) - 5) + (3!! + 1)$
14110 := $((((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + ((5 - 3!) - 1)$
14111 := $((((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + ((5 - 3!) \times 1)$
14112 := $((((1^3)^5!) \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times ((5^3) + 1)))$
14113 := $((((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) - ((5 - 3!) \times 1)$
14114 := $((1 - 35) + 7!) + (9 \times ((7!/5) + 3 + 1))$
14115 := $(1 - (3! - 5!)) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)))$
14116 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times 31)$
14117 := $13579 + (7 + 531)$
14118 := $13 \times (5! - ((7 - (975 - 3)) - 1))$
14119 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) - (7! + ((5!/3) - 1))$
14120 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times ((5^3) + 1))$
14121 := $(1 + 3!!) + (((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) - (5!/(3 \times 1)))$
14122 := $(1 - (3! - 5!)) + (7 \times (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) + 1))$
14123 := $(1 \times (3 + 5!)) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5! + (3! - 1))))$
14124 := $(13 - 5!) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) - (5 \times 31)))$
14125 := $((((1 + (3!! - 5!)) \times (7 + 9)) + 7!) - 531$
14126 := $((1 \times 3) - ((5 - (7! \times (9 - 7)))/5)) \times (3! + 1)$
14127 := $(1 + (3! + 5!)) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)))$
14128 := $((((1 - 3!) - (5 + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14129 := $((((1 - 3!) - 5!) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7 + 5!)^{3-1})$
14130 := $((((1 + 3)^5) - (79 \times 7)) \times (5!/(3 + 1))$
14131 := $1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) - 7!) + (5 - 31)$
14132 := $1 + (((3^5) \times 79) - 7!) + (5 - 31)$
14133 := $13 + (5! + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times ((5^3) \times 1))))$
14134 := $(1 - 35) + (7 \times ((9 \times (75 \times 3)) - 1))$
14135 := $135 + (((7!/9) \times (75/3)) \times 1)$
14136 := $1 + (((((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - 5!) + 3!!) - 1)$
14137 := $1 \times (((((3! + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) - 5!) + 3!!) + 1)$
14138 := $((1 - 3) \times ((5! \times 7) - 97)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
14139 := $13579 + (7!/(5 + 3 + 1))$
14140 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7)))) \times 5) - (3! - 1)$
14141 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) - ((975 + 3) + 1)$
14142 := $((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + 97) + (5^{3!-1})$
14143 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! + 9)) - ((7!/5) - (3 + 1))$
14144 := $((((1 - 3!) \times 5!) + (7 \times 9)) - 7) \times (5 - 31)$
14145 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times ((7 + 97) + (5! + (3!! - 1)))$
14146 := $((((1 \times 3! + 5!) - 7)^{9-7}) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
14147 := $(1 \times 35) + ((7 \times 9) \times ((75 \times 3) - 1))$
14148 := $1 + 35 + ((7 \times 9) \times ((75 \times 3) - 1))$
14149 := $((1 - (3^5 + 7)) - 9) + (7 + (5!^{3-1}))$
14150 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5) \times (7 + (9 + 7)))) \times 5) + (3! - 1)$
14151 := $((1 + 3!))! - ((5! - 7!) + (((9 - 7!) + (5! + 3!)) \times 1))$
14152 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) \times (7 - ((97 - 5) + 31))$
14153 := $(1 - (3^5)) - ((7 - 9) + (7 - (5!^{3-1})))$
14154 := $((13 \times 5!) + ((7 \times 97) + 5!)) \times (3! \times 1)$
14155 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times 7) + (97 \times 5!)) - (3! - 1)$
14156 := $((((1 - 3) \times 5!) \times (7 + (9 - 75))) - (3 + 1)$
14157 := $((1 \times 35) + (79 + 7)) \times (5! - (3 \times 1))$
14158 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) - (5 - (3!! \times 1)))$
14159 := $((((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!) + (3!! - 1)$
14160 := $((13 \times (5 + 7)) - 97) \times (5! \times (3 - 1))$
14161 := $((1 + 3) + (57 + ((9 \times 7) - 5)))^{3-1}$
14162 := $1 \times 3 + (5! + (((7 - (9 - 7))!) \times (5! - 3)) - 1)$
14163 := $((((135 - 7) - 9)^{7-5}) + 3) - 1$
14164 := $((((135 - 7) - 9)^{7-5}) + 3) \times 1$
14165 := $((((135 - 7) - 9)^{7-5}) + 3) + 1$
14166 := $((((1 + 3!) + (5! \times 79)) + 7!) - ((5! \times 3) + 1)$
14167 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5!) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times 5!))) + (3! + 1)$
14168 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times ((7 - 9) - 7))^{5-3}) - 1)$
14169 := $(1 - (((3! - 5!) \times 79) - (7! + (5! + 3)))) - 1$
14170 := $(1 - (((3! - 5!) \times 79) - (7! + (5! + 3)))) \times 1$
14171 := $(1 - (((3! - 5!) \times 79) - (7! + (5! + 3)))) + 1$
14172 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5! \times 7) - (9 + ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1)!)))$
14173 := $(13 + (5! \times ((7 - (9 - 7))!)) - (5! \times (3 - 1))$
14174 := $((((1 - 3) - (5! + 7)) - 97) + (5!^{3-1})$
14175 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times (((7 + 97) + 5!) + (3!! + 1))$
14176 := $((1 \times 3!))! + ((5! - ((7 - 9)^{7-5}))^{3-1})$
14177 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 75)) \times (3 \times 1))$
14178 := $((1 + 3!) \times (579 + (7 + 5))) - (3! \times 1)$
14179 := $(1 \times (35 \times (7 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)))) - 31$
14180 := $1 + ((35 \times (7 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5))) - 31)$
14181 := $(1^3 + (5 + ((7 \times (9 \times 75)) \times 3))) \times 1$

- 14182** := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times ((7 - 9) - 7))^{5-3}) + 1)$
14183 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (((7 \times (9 \times 75)) \times 3) - 1)$
14184 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (579 + (7 + 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
14185 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (((7 \times (9 \times 75)) \times 3) + 1)$
14186 := $((((1 \times 3)! - 5!) + 7) \times (9 - 7)) + (5^{3-1})$
14187 := $(1^3 \times 5) + (7 \times (((9 \times 75) \times 3) + 1))$
14188 := $(1 + 3) \times (((579 + 7) + 5) \times 3!) + 1$
14189 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7))) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
14190 := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 + (7 + 5))) + (3! \times 1)$
14191 := $((13 + 5) \times 797) - (5 \times 31)$
14192 := $((1 - (3!^5)) + (7 \times 97)) \times (5 - (3! + 1))$
14193 := $(1 - (3! - (5! + 7!))) + (9753 - 1)$
14194 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7!) + 9753) \times 1)$
14195 := $((1 \times 35) \times (7 + (9 \times (7!/5!)))) + 3! \times 1$
14196 := $((((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 79)) \times (7 + 5)) - (3 + 1))!$
14197 := $13579 - (7 - (5^{3+1}))$
14198 := $(1 - (3! \times 5!)) + (((7! - ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 3) + 1)$
14199 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (((5 - (7 \times 97)) \times (5!/3!)) + 1))$
14200 := $((((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 - 7)) + (((9 + 7) + (5^3)) - 1))$
14201 := $((((1 + 3!)! - (5! + (79 + 7!))) + (5^{3-1}))$
14202 := $((((1 + 3) + 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 75))) \times (3 \times 1))$
14203 := $((((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - 3!) - 1)$
14204 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - (3! \times 1)$
14205 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - (3! - 1)$
14206 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times 75))) + 31$
14207 := $((((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) - 3) \times 1)$
14208 := $(13 + 579) \times ((75/3) - 1)$
14209 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) \times 79) - ((7! - 53) + 1))$
14210 := $((((1 + 3^5) \times 79) - (7! - 5)) - 31)$
14211 := $((1 + 35) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 \times 3))) \times 1$
14212 := $((1 + 35) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 \times 3))) + 1$
14213 := $(13 \times ((5! + 7) \times 9)) + ((75 - 3!) - 1)$
14214 := $(13 \times ((5! + 7) \times 9)) + ((75 - 3!) \times 1)$
14215 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + (3! - 1)$
14216 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + (3! \times 1)$
14217 := $((((1 + 3!)!/5!) + ((7! - (9 \times (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 \times 1))$
14218 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times (79 \times (7 + 5))) - (3 - 1)$
14219 := $(1 - (35 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^{3-1}))$
14220 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 79) \times (7 + (53 \times 1))$
14221 := $1 + (((3 \times 57) + 9) \times (75 + 3 + 1))$
14222 := $((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times (79 \times (7 + 5))) + (3 - 1)$
14223 := $(1 + (((3 \times (5 \times 79)) \times (7 + 5)) + 3)) - 1$
14224 := $1 \times (((35 \times 7) + 9) \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) \times 1))$
14225 := $1 + (((35 \times 7) + 9) \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) \times 1))$
14226 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times 79) \times (((7!/5!) - 3!) \times 1))$
14227 := $((1 \times 3) - (5! - (7 - (9 \times 7)))) + (5^{3-1})$
14228 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7! - 97)) + (5! - (3! + 1))$
14229 := $(1 + 3) - (5 \times (7 - ((97 - 5) \times 31)))$
14230 := $(13 \times (((5! + 7) \times 9) + 7)) - (((5 - 3) + 1)!)!$
14231 := $(13 + 5!) \times (((7 \times 9) + 75) - 31)$
14232 := $1 - (((3 - 5!) \times 79) - 7!) + (53 - 1)$
14233 := $((1 - ((3 - (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + 7))) + 5!) + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
14234 := $(1357 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
14235 := $(13 \times (57 + (9 + 7))) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
14236 := $(1 \times 3! \times ((5! - 7) \times (9 + (7 + 5)))) - (3 - 1)$
14237 := $(((((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7) - 5!) - 3!) - 1$
14238 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 \times ((9 \times 75) + 3 \times 1))$
14239 := $1 - (((3! + 5!) \times 7) - (((9 + 7) + 5) \times 3!)) \times 1$
14240 := $(1 + ((3! \times 5!) + (7 - (9 + 7)))) \times ((5!/3!) \times 1)$
14241 := $1 \times ((35 \times (7 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5))) + 31)$
14242 := $1 + ((35 \times (7 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5))) + 31)$
14243 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) + ((7!/9) \times (75/3))) \times 1)$
14244 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) + ((7!/9) \times (75/3))) + 1)$
14245 := $((1 + 3)! \times (5! \times ((7 - 9) + 7))) - (5 \times 31)$
14246 := $1 + (((3 \times 5!) \times 7) - (97 \times 5)) \times (3! + 1)$
14247 := $135 + ((7 \times 9) \times ((75 \times 3) - 1))$
14248 := $((1 + 3)! - (5 - 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5!) \times 3) - 1$
14249 := $(1 + 3)! - (5 \times (7 - ((97 - 5) \times 31)))$
14250 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((79 \times (7 + 5)) + 3 - 1)$
14251 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7 - ((5! - 3!) - 1)$
14252 := $((1 + ((3 \times 5!) \times 7)) - (97 \times 5)) \times (3! + 1)$
14253 := $(((((1 - (3 - 5)))!)! - 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) - 3! \times 1$
14254 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5 - 7)^9)) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
14255 := $((1 - 3) - ((5! + 7) + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3-1})$
14256 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) + (((9 - 7) \times (5! \times 3!)) \times 1)$
14257 := $(1^3) - ((5! - (7 \times (97 + 5))) \times (3 + 1)!)!$
14258 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + ((7 \times 9) \times ((75 \times 3) + 1))$
14259 := $(1 - 3 + 5) \times (7 \times ((9 \times 75) + 3 + 1))$

- 14260** := $(1 \times (35/7)) \times ((97 - 5) \times 31)$
14261 := $1 + (((((3! \times 5) + 7) \times 9) + (7 + 5!)) \times 31)$
14262 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 79) - ((7! + 5) - 31)$
14263 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 + 79) \times 7)) + (5! + 31)$
14264 := $((((1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) - (9 - 7)) - 5!) - (3!! \times 1))$
14265 := $((((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 75))) \times (3 \times 1))$
14266 := $((((1 - 3!) - 5!) - (7! + 9)) + (7! + (5!^{3-1})))$
14267 := $((((1^3 + 5!) \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) - ((5 - 3!!) \times 1))$
14268 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! - (9 + (7 \times 5)))) - 3!! \times 1$
14269 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times (((7 - 9) + 7)!)) - (5 \times 31))$
14270 := $((13 - 5!) - 7) - ((9 + 7) - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14271 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) - (((9 + 7) \times 53) + 1)$
14272 := $((((1 + 3^5) \times 79) - (7! - 5)) + 31)$
14273 := $(1 - 3 + (5! \times (((7 - 9) + 7)!)) - ((5^3) \times 1))$
14274 := $(1 - 3 + (5! \times (((7 - 9) + 7)!)) - ((5^3) - 1))$
14275 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5 \times (7 - 97)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
14276 := $1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7 - 97)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
14277 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) \times (97 + 5))) - (3 \times 1)$
14278 := $((1^{3!}) - ((5! - 7) + 9)) \times (7 - (5^3 \times 1))$
14279 := $((((1^{3!}) + (5 + 79)) \times (7! / (5 \times 3!))) - 1)$
14280 := $(1 \times 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (53 - 1)))$
14281 := $((((1^{3!}) + (5 + 79)) \times (7! / (5 \times 3!))) + 1)$
14282 := $(1 + (3!! \times 5)) - (7! - ((97 + (5^{3!}) - 1))$
14283 := $((((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7)))^{9-7}) - (5! - (3 \times 1))$
14284 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (((7 - 9) + 7)!)) + ((5^3) - 1)$
14285 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) \times (((7 - 9) + 7)!)) + ((5^3) \times 1)$
14286 := $(1 \times ((35/7)!^{9-7}) - (5! - 3! \times 1))$
14287 := $13 + ((5! \times ((7 - (9 - 7)!)) - (5! + 3! \times 1))$
14288 := $(13 + (((5 + 7) - 9)!)) \times (753 - 1)$
14289 := $((((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7) - 97) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14290 := $((1 + 3!)! - (((5! \times 7) \times 9) - ((7^5) + 3 \times 1))$
14291 := $((((1 + 3) \times 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times ((5 \times 3!) + 1))$
14292 := $((13 + 5) \times 797) - (53 + 1)$
14293 := $((13 + 5) \times 797) - (53 \times 1)$
14294 := $((((1 \times 3) - 5) - 7) - (97 - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14295 := $1 \times ((3! - (((5! - 7) - 9) + 7)) + (5!^{3-1}))$
14296 := $1 + ((3! - (((5! - 7) - 9) + 7)) + (5!^{3-1}))$
14297 := $((1 \times 3 + (5 \times (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)))) \times 3!) - 1$
14298 := $((1 \times 3 + (5 \times (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)))) \times 3!) \times 1$
14299 := $(1 + ((3 \times 57) + 9)) \times (75 + 3 + 1)$
14300 := $((1^{35}) \times 7!) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3) - 1$
14301 := $((1^{35}) \times 7!) + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3) \times 1$
14302 := $((1^3 \times 5!)! + (7 \times (((9 \times 75) \times 3) + 1))$
14303 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5 - 7) - ((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1))$
14304 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) - (7 + 97)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14305 := $1 \times (((3 - (5 \times 7)) - (9 \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1}))$
14306 := $1 + (((3 - (5 \times 7)) - (9 \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1}))$
14307 := $((1 \times 3) - ((5 + 7) \times 9) \times 7) \times (5 - (3 + 1)!)$
14308 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 \times 7)) - ((9 \times 7) - (5!^{3-1}))$
14309 := $((1 + 3) - (5 - 7)) - 97 + (5!^{3-1})$
14310 := $135 + ((7 \times 9) \times ((75 \times 3) \times 1))$
14311 := $1 + (3 \times ((5 \times 79) + (7 \times (5^{3+1}))))$
14312 := $1 + ((3! \times (5 \times ((7 + (9 - 7)) \times 53))) + 1)$
14313 := $(1 + (3! + 5)) + (7! + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1))$
14314 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 - 7)) + (97 \times (5 \times 31))$
14315 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5 + 7)) - (97 - (5!^{3-1}))$
14316 := $((1 + 3!) - (5 \times 79)) + (7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)$
14317 := $((1 + 3!)^5 - ((7! / (9 - 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) \times 1))$
14318 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5 - 7) - (97 \times (5 \times 31)))$
14319 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) \times 9) + (7! \times (5 - (3 + 1)))$
14320 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) \times 9) + (7! + (5 - (3 + 1)))$
14321 := $((13 \times (5 + 7)) \times (97 - 5)) - 31$
14322 := $1 \times (((35 + 7) \times (9 + (7 - 5))) \times 31)$
14323 := $1 + (((35 + 7) \times (9 + (7 - 5))) \times 31)$
14324 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + 7 + 9)) - (75 + (3!! + 1))$
14325 := $(1 - ((3 \times (5 - (7! - 9))) + 753)) - 1$
14326 := $(1 - ((3 \times (5 - (7! - 9))) + 753)) \times 1$
14327 := $1 - (((3 \times (5 - (7! - 9))) + 753) - 1)$
14328 := $(1 \times ((3 \times (5! + 79)) \times (7 + 5))) \times (3 - 1)$
14329 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times (9 \times 7))) - (5 \times (3! + 1))$
14330 := $((1 \times (3!^5)) - 7) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 31})$
14331 := $13579 + (753 - 1)$
14332 := $13579 + (753 \times 1)$
14333 := $((1 \times 3! + 5!) \times (79 + (7 \times 5))) - 31$
14334 := $((1 - (3 - 5))! - (79 - 7)) + (5!^{3-1})$
14335 := $(1 - 3!) \times (57 - ((975 \times 3) - 1))$

- 14336** := $((1 \times 3)! - 5) \times 7 \times ((9 - 7)^{5+3! \times 1})$
14337 := $((1 \times 35) \times (7 - 9)) + (7 + (5!^{3-1}))$
14338 := $(1^3 \times (5 \times 7)) - (97 - (5!^{3-1}))$
14339 := $13 \times (579 - (7 - 531))$
14340 := $(1 \times (((3! \times 5) + 7) - 97)) + (5!^{3-1})$
14341 := $(1 + (((3! \times 5) + 7) - 97)) + (5!^{3-1})$
14342 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) - ((9 \times 7) - (5 - 3! \times 1))$
14343 := $((1 - 3) \times 57) / (9 - 7) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14344 := $1 - (((3^5 - 7!) + 9) + 7) \times (5 - (3 - 1))$
14345 := $(1 \times (35 + (7 - 97))) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14346 := $(13 + (5 - (79 - 7))) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14347 := $((1^{3!} \times 5)! \times ((7 - (9 - 7)))! - (53 \times 1))$
14348 := $(1 \times (((3 - 5) + 7))!^{9-7}) - (53 - 1)$
14349 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1})$
14350 := $((1 \times 3!)! / 5! + (7 - (9 \times 7))) + (5!^{3-1})$
14351 := $(1 + (3 - (5 + ((7 - 9)^7)))) \times (5! - (3! + 1))$
14352 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5! + ((7 - 9)^7))) + (5!^{3-1})$
14353 := $(1^{3!} - ((5! - (7! - ((9 + 7) + 5!)))) \times (3 \times 1))$
14354 := $((1 - 3!) - 57) + (9 + (7 + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))))$
14355 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7 - 5 - (3 + 1)$
14356 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) - ((9 + (7 \times 5)) + 3! \times 1)$
14357 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7 - 5 - (3 - 1)$
14358 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) - (((9 \times 7) - 5) + 3!) \times 1$
14359 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) - (((9 \times 7) - 5) + 3!) - 1$
14360 := $(1^3 - 57) + ((9 + 7) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)))$
14361 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7 - 5 + (3 - 1)$
14362 := $(1 \times 3) - (57 - 9) + (7 + (5!^{3-1}))$
14363 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7 - 5 + (3 + 1)$
14364 := $((1 \times (35 + 7)) \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3) \times 1$
14365 := $(1^3) \times ((57 \times (9 + 75)) \times 3) + 1$
14366 := $(1^3) + ((57 \times (9 + 75)) \times 3) + 1$
14367 := $(1 - 35) + (((7 - (9 - 7)))!^{5-3}) + 1$
14368 := $(1 + (3 - 5)) + (((7 - 9) + 7)! \times 5!) - 31$
14369 := $(1 + ((3 \times 57) \times (9 + 75))) + (3 + 1)$
14370 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 \times (97 + (5!/3))) - 1)$
14371 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5 + (7 \times 97)) \times ((5!/3!) + 1))$
14372 := $(1 + 3) \times ((57 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - (3! + 1)))$
14373 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5! + ((7! + 9) - (7 \times (53 + 1))))$
14374 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) \times 79) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
14375 := $((13 + 5) + (7 - (9 - 7))) \times (5^{3+1})$
14376 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 - ((9 + 7) - 5)) \times (3! \times 1)$
14377 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5! + 7!)) + (97 + (5!^{3-1}))$
14378 := $13 \times (5 + (7 + 9 + (7 \times (5 \times 31))))$
14379 := $(1 - ((3 \times (5 - 7!)) + (9 - 7))) - (5 + (3! \times 1))$
14380 := $1 \times 3! + ((5 \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3))) - 1)$
14381 := $1 \times 3! + (5 \times (((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) \times 1))$
14382 := $1 \times 3! + ((5 \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3))) + 1)$
14383 := $((13 \times (5 + 7)) \times (97 - 5)) + 31$
14384 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7 + ((5!/3!) \times 1)$
14385 := $(1^{357}) - (9 + (7 - (5!^{3-1})))$
14386 := $1 \times 3! + (5 \times (((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) + 1))$
14387 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 79) - ((7! - 5!) - 31)$
14388 := $(1 - 3!) - (((5! - 7!) + ((9 - 7) + 5!)) \times 3) + 1$
14389 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) - ((9 + 7) - 5) - ((3! \times 1)!)$
14390 := $(1 - 3!) - (((5! - 7!) + ((9 - 7) + 5!)) \times 3) - 1$
14391 := $((1 \times 3! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) \times ((7!/5!) - (3 \times 1))$
14392 := $((1^{3!} - 5) + (((7 - 9) + 7)! \times 5!) - (3 + 1))$
14393 := $((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times 7 - 5 - (3 + 1)$
14394 := $((1^{357})^9) - (7 - (5!^{3-1}))$
14395 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 + ((7 + 9) \times 7)) \times (5! + 3 \times 1))$
14396 := $(1 + (3 \times (5! + (7! + (9 - (7 \times 53)))))) + 1$
14397 := $(1^3 - (5! - ((7! - (9 - 7)) - 5!))) \times (3 \times 1)$
14398 := $1 + (((3 + 57) - (9 \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1}))$
14399 := $((13 + 5) \times 797) + (53 \times 1)$
14400 := $((13 + 5) \times 797) + (53 + 1)$
14401 := $((1^{35}) + (((7 - (9 - 7)))!^{5-3})) \times 1$
14402 := $((1^{35}) + (((7 - (9 - 7)))!^{5-3})) + 1$
14403 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 - (((7 - (9 - 7))! \times 5!))) + (3 - 1))$
14404 := $(13 + ((5! \times ((7 - (9 - 7))! - (5 + 3)))) - 1$
14405 := $(13 + ((5! \times ((7 - (9 - 7))! - (5 + 3)))) \times 1$
14406 := $(13 + ((5! \times ((7 - (9 - 7))! - (5 + 3)))) + 1$
14407 := $(1 + ((3! + (57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!))) + 3!)) \times 1$
14408 := $((1^{357})^9) + 7 + (5!^{3-1})$
14409 := $((13 \times 5) - (7 \times 9)) + (7 + (5!^{3-1}))$
14410 := $(1 \times 3 + 5) + (((7 - (9 - 7))! \times 5!) + 3 - 1)$
14411 := $((1 + 3) + (5! \times 79)) + ((7 - 5!) + ((3! + 1)!))$

$$\begin{aligned}14412 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((57 - 9) \times 75) + 3) \times 1 \\14413 &:= 1 - ((3 \times ((5! - 7!) - (9 - 7)) + 5!) - 3! \times 1) \\14414 &:= (1^{3!}) \times (((5 + 7) + (9 - 7)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\14415 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\14416 &:= (((1 + 3!!) + 5!) + 7) \times (((9 + 7) - (5 - 3!)) \times 1) \\14417 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) - 7!) + (9 + (7! + (5!^{3-1})))) \\14418 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7 \times 97) + (5! + 3 - 1)) \\14419 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5 + 7) + (9 + (7^5))) + (3!! + 1) \\14420 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) \times (7 - 97))) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\14421 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + 5!) + ((7 \times 97) \times (5!/3! \times 1)) \\14422 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + (7! + 9))) - (7 \times (5 \times 31)) \\14423 &:= (1 + 3!) - (((5 + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5 \times 3!!)) + 1) \\14424 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((57 - 9) \times 75)) + (3 + 1)! \\14425 &:= (13 + ((5 + 79)/7)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\14426 &:= ((1 - (3!! - (5! \times 79))) + 7!) + (5^{3+1}) \\14427 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5)/(7 + (9 - 7))) + (5!^{3-1}) \\14428 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + (9 \times (7 - (5! + 3 + 1))) \\14429 &:= (1^3 + 5) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5!^{3-1})) \\14430 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5! + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!))) \times (3! - 1) \\14431 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!) \times (3! - 1) \\14432 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 79)) - (7^5))) - 3! \times 1 \\14433 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 79)) - (7^5))) - (3! - 1) \\14434 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) - (97 - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\14435 &:= 1 \times (3 - ((5! - 79) \times ((7 - (5! \times 3)) + 1))) \\14436 &:= (1 + 35) \times ((797 + 5)/(3 - 1)) \\14437 &:= 1 + (35 + (((7 - (9 - 7)))!^{5-3} + 1)) \\14438 &:= (1 + ((35 \times (7!/9)) - ((7! + 5!) + 3))) \times 1 \\14439 &:= (1 + ((35 \times (7!/9)) - ((7! + 5!) + 3))) + 1 \\14440 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\14441 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 79)) - (7^5))) + (3 \times 1) \\14442 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 79)) - (7^5))) + (3 + 1) \\14443 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 79)) - (7^5))) + (3! - 1) \\14444 &:= ((1 \times 3 + (57 - 9)) - 7) + (5!^{3-1}) \\14445 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 7) \times 9)) - ((7 \times 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\14446 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) + 5) - ((7 \times 97) - (5!^{3-1})) \\14447 &:= (((1 - 3) - ((5! - 7!) + (97 + 5))) \times 3) - 1 \\14448 &:= ((1 \times 35) - 7) \times ((97 \times 5) + 31) \\14449 &:= (((1 - 3) - ((5! - 7!) + (97 + 5))) \times 3) + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14450 &:= ((13 - 5!) - (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - ((3! - 1)!)) \\14451 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5!) - (7 - (9 + 7))) \times 5) + (3! \times 1) \\14452 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5! - 7!) + (97 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\14453 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times 5!) \times ((7 - (9 - 7)))! + (53 \times 1) \\14454 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((57 + 9) \times (75 - (3 - 1))) \\14455 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) - 7) + 9) \times ((7 + 53) - 1) \\14456 &:= ((13 \times 5) - (7 + 9)) + (7 + (5!^{3-1})) \\14457 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times (9 + 75)) + 31) \\14458 &:= 1 + (3 \times ((57 \times (9 + 75)) + 31)) \\14459 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - 3)) - 1 \\14460 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - 3)) \times 1 \\14461 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - 3)) + 1 \\14462 &:= (1 - ((3! \times (5 \times 79)) - (7^5))) + (3 + 1)! \\14463 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((97 + (5! + 3!)) + 1)) \\14464 &:= (1^3 \times (5! + 7)) - ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\14465 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! \times 79) + 7!)) - (53 \times 1) \\14466 &:= (1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + (7! - (53 + 1)) \\14467 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7)) + ((9 \times 7) + (5!^{3-1})) \\14468 &:= (1^3) + ((5! \times 79) + ((7! - 53) \times 1)) \\14469 &:= (1 \times (3! + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 + 3)))) - 1 \\14470 &:= (1 \times (3! + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 + 3)))) \times 1 \\14471 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times 3) - 1 \\14472 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times 3) \times 1 \\14473 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times 3) + 1 \\14474 &:= (1^3) \times ((579 \times (75/3)) - 1) \\14475 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7! - (97 + (5! - (3 - 1)))) \\14476 &:= (1^3) \times ((579 \times (75/3)) + 1) \\14477 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) + (9 + 7)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\14478 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)))! + ((79 - 7) + (5!^{3-1})) \\14479 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((579 \times (75/3)) + 1) \\14480 &:= ((1 - 3!)^5) + (((7!/9 - 7) - 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\14481 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5! - ((7! - 97) + 5)))) - (3 + 1) \\14482 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((579 \times (75/3)) + 1) \\14483 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7) + (97 + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\14484 &:= ((1^3 \times 5!) \times 79) + (7! - (5 + 31)) \\14485 &:= (1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) - (7 \times (5 - 3! \times 1)) \\14486 &:= (((1 + 3!) + ((5! \times 79) + 7!)) - (5!/3)) - 1 \\14487 &:= 13 + ((579 \times (75/3)) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14488 &:= (((1 + 3!) + ((5! \times 79) + 7!)) - (5!/3)) + 1 \\ 14489 &:= 13 + ((579 \times (75/3)) + 1) \\ 14490 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times ((5! + 3!) \times 1) \\ 14491 &:= (((1^{3!} \times 5)!) \times 79) + (7! - ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 14492 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5 - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3 \times 1))) \\ 14493 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5) \times 7)) + ((9 + 7) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 14494 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 \times (7 \times (9 \times (7 - 53)))) + 1 \\ 14495 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (((7 - 9) + (75 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 14496 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) - (9 \times (75 - (3 + 1))) \\ 14497 &:= (13 + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) - ((7 - 53) \times 1)) \\ 14498 &:= ((13 \times (5 + (79 \times 7))) - 5) \times (3 - 1) \\ 14499 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((5! \times 79) + 7!)) - ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\ 14500 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + (7 + (9 \times 7))) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 14501 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) + ((9 \times 7) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 14502 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((57 \times 9) + 7!)) \times (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 14503 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! \times 79) + 7!)) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 14504 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5!) + (((7! - (97 \times 5)) \times 3) - 1) \\ 14505 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5! + (7! - (975/(3 \times 1)))) \\ 14506 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) \times 7) - 97 + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 14507 &:= (1 + (3! + (5! \times 79))) + (7! - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 14508 &:= (13 + 5) \times (797 + ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\ 14509 &:= (1^{3!}) + (((5 + 79) \times 7) - 5!) \times 31 \\ 14510 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5! \times 79)) + (((7! - 5) - 3!) + 1) \\ 14511 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! - (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3) - 1) \\ 14512 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) - (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 31)) \\ 14513 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) - 7) \times 5!) - (3! + 1) \\ 14514 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5 \times ((7 \times (9 \times (7 - 53))) \times 1)) \\ 14515 &:= (1 + 3!) - (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times (7 - 53))) - 1) \\ 14516 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times (7!/5)) + 3 + 1) \\ 14517 &:= (((1 \times 35) + (79 + 7)) \times 5!) - (3 \times 1) \\ 14518 &:= 13 + ((5! \times 79) + (7! - ((5 \times 3) \times 1))) \\ 14519 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times 79) + (7! + (5 - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 14520 &:= ((1 + (3 + (5 + ((7 + 9) \times 7)))) \times 5) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 14521 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times 79) - (7! \times (5 - 3!)) + 1 \\ 14522 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) + (9 - (7 \times (5! - 31))) \\ 14523 &:= (((1 \times 35) + (79 + 7)) \times 5!) + (3 \times 1) \\ 14524 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) \times 5)) + (3! + 1) \\ 14525 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) - 7) \times 5! + (3! - 1) \\ 14526 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5! \times 79)) + (7 - 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14527 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) - 7) \times 5! + (3! + 1) \\ 14528 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5! + (((7 - (9 - 7)))! \times 5!)) + 3 - 1) \\ 14529 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((57 - 9) + (7! - 5))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 14530 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((57 - 9) + (7! - 5)))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 14531 &:= ((13 + (5! \times 79)) + 7!) - (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 14532 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 \times 7)) + 97) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 14533 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! \times 79) + 7!)) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 14534 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! \times 79) + 7!)) + ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\ 14535 &:= ((13 + (5! \times 79)) + 7!) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\ 14536 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + ((7 \times ((9 \times 75) \times 3)) + 1) \\ 14537 &:= 1 \times ((3!^5) - (7 - (9 \times (753 - 1)))) \\ 14538 &:= (13 - 579) + (((7! - 5) \times 3) - 1) \\ 14539 &:= ((13 - 579) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 14540 &:= ((13 - 579) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) + 1 \\ 14541 &:= ((13 + (5! \times 79)) + 7!) + (5 + 3 \times 1) \\ 14542 &:= (13 + 5!) + (7! + ((9 - 7!) + (5!^{3-1}))) \\ 14543 &:= ((1^3 \times 5!) + (7 + 9)) + (7 + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 14544 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7))) \times (5! + (3 + 1)!) \\ 14545 &:= (1 + ((35/7)!^{9-7})) + (5! + (3 + 1)!) \\ 14546 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - 7) + ((9 \times 753) - 1) \\ 14547 &:= ((1^3 + 5!) \times 79) + (7! - (53 - 1)) \\ 14548 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + (((5! \times 79) + (7 \times 5)) - (3! + 1)) \\ 14549 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 57) \times 9) - (7^5)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 14550 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 - 7)) \times ((97 \times 5)/(3 + 1)) \\ 14551 &:= (1 - ((3^5) - 7!)) + (9753 \times 1) \\ 14552 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5 \times (7 - 975)))) + 31 \\ 14553 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 + 3! \times 1) \\ 14554 &:= (135 \times (7 \times 9)) + (((7!/5) \times 3!) + 1) \\ 14555 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5! \times ((7 - 9) + 7))) + (5 \times 31) \\ 14556 &:= 1 + ((3 - (5 - 7)) \times (((97 \times 5) \times 3!) + 1)) \\ 14557 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! \times 79) + 7!) + ((5 \times 3!) + 1)) \\ 14558 &:= (13 \times ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7)^5))) - (3 - 1) \\ 14559 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5! \times 79)) + (7 \times 5)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 14560 &:= ((1 + 3) - 579) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 14561 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) + 7) + (9 \times 753)) \times 1 \\ 14562 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) + 7) + (9 \times 753)) + 1 \\ 14563 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (7! + (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\ 14564 &:= ((13 \times ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7)^5))) + 3) + 1 \\ 14565 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times 97) + (5 \times 3!)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

- 14566** := $1 - (3 \times 5 \times ((7 - (975 + 3)) \times 1))$
14567 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 - 31)))$
14568 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times 79)) + (7! + ((5!/3) + 1))$
14569 := $13 - (((5! + (7 \times 9)) - (7! - 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
14570 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((5 - ((7 + 97) - 5)) \times 31)$
14571 := $(1 - 3 + ((5! \times 79) + 7!)) + (53 \times 1)$
14572 := $(1 - (3 \times 5!)) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) \times (5 - (3 - 1)))$
14573 := $((1^3 + 5!) \times 79) + 7! + (5 - 31)$
14574 := $(1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) + (7! + (53 + 1))$
14575 := $(1 + (3 + 579)) \times (75 / (3 \times 1))$
14576 := $((1 - 3!) \times (5! - 7)) + (((9 + 7) + 5) \times (3! + 1))$
14577 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) \times 7 + (97 \times (5! + 31))$
14578 := $((13 + 5) - (7!/9)) + (7! \times (5 - (3 - 1)))$
14579 := $(1 + ((3!^5) + 7)) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 3! \times 1))$
14580 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) \times (7 - 97) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14581 := $(1 - (3 \times 57)) - (9 - ((7! - 5!) \times (3 \times 1)))$
14582 := $((1 \times 3) \times (((5 - 7) + 9)!)) - (7 + 531)$
14583 := $((1 - (3^5)) + 7!) + (9 \times 7) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)$
14584 := $(13 \times ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7)^5))) + (3 + 1)!$
14585 := $(1^3 - 57) + (((9 + 7) - 5)^{3+1})$
14586 := $((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) - 7! - (5 - 31)$
14587 := $((1 \times (3^5 + 7)) - (9 \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1})$
14588 := $(1 + 3^5) - (((7 \times 9) - 7) - (5!^{3-1}))$
14589 := $((1 + 35) + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! + 31))$
14590 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
14591 := $1 \times (((((3^5) \times (7 \times 9)) + 7) - 5) - 3! \times 1)$
14592 := $1 - ((3 \times ((5! - 7!) + 97)) - (5! + 3 - 1))$
14593 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 - (7!/9))) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))$
14594 := $((1 \times 3!))! + (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) - 1$
14595 := $((1 \times 3!))! + (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) \times 1$
14596 := $((1 \times 3!))! + (((5! + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5^3)) + 1$
14597 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 + 9) + 7!)) - (5! \times 3!) - 1$
14598 := $(1^3 - 5) \times (7!/9) + ((7^5) + 31)$
14599 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 + 9) + 7!)) - (5! \times 3!) + 1$
14600 := $((1 - (3 \times 57)) + 9) + (((7! - 5!) \times 3) + 1)$
14601 := $(1 + (3! - 5!)) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1))$
14602 := $13 - ((5 \times (7 - (975 \times 3))) + 1)$
14603 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times 975) + 3 - 1)$
14604 := $((1 + 3!) \times 579) - (7 + 5) + (3! \times 1)$
14605 := $((1 + 3!) \times 579) - (7 + 5) + (3! + 1)$
14606 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + (9 - 7) - 531$
14607 := $(1 - (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)$
14608 := $1 - (3 \times ((5! - (7! + (9 \times 7))) + (5! - 3! \times 1)))$
14609 := $(1 - ((35 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7^5))) + 3! \times 1$
14610 := $(1 \times 3! \times 5) \times (7 + (((9 + 7) \times 5) \times 3! \times 1))$
14611 := $1 \times (3! + (5 \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5! + (3! + 1))))))$
14612 := $((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) - (7! - (53 - 1))$
14613 := $(1 - ((3! + (5! - 7!)) + (9 + (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 \times 1)$
14614 := $1 + ((35 \times (7!/9)) - (7! - (53 \times 1)))$
14615 := $((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times 7) \times (9 + 7) + 5! + (3! - 1)$
14616 := $((1 \times (357 - 9)) \times 7) \times ((5 - (3 - 1)))!$
14617 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) \times ((7 - 9)^7) + (5^{3-1})$
14618 := $1 \times 3 + ((5 \times 79) \times (7 + ((5 \times 3!) \times 1)))$
14619 := $(1 - (3 \times (5! - (7! + (9 - (7 \times (5 + 3))))))) - 1$
14620 := $(1 + 3) \times (57 - ((9 - 7) - (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)))$
14621 := $((135 + 79) + 7) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14622 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5!) - 7^{9-7} + (5 - (3 + 1)!)$
14623 := $(1^3 \times ((5 - 7)^9)) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
14624 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3! + 1)))$
14625 := $(13 \times 5) \times (((7 \times 9) / 7) \times (5^{3-1}))$
14626 := $1 - (((3 - 57) - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5! + 3!) - 1))$
14627 := $(1 - (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!)$
14628 := $((1 + 3!) \times 579) + (7 + 5) + (3! \times 1)$
14629 := $((1 + 3!) \times 579) + (7 + 5) + (3! + 1)$
14630 := $((1 \times 35) / 7) \times ((975 \times 3) + 1)$
14631 := $(1 \times (35 \times (79 - ((7 - 5!) \times 3)))) + 1$
14632 := $((1 - (3! + 57)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5^3) - 1$
14633 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5!) \times 79 + ((7! - (5! \times 3)) - 1)$
14634 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 \times 7) + (9 - 7!)) + 5!) \times 3 \times 1$
14635 := $((1 + 3^5) + ((7 - 9) - 7)) + (5!^{3-1})$
14636 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5! + (7! / ((9 - (7 - 5))))))^{3-1}$
14637 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 - 9) \times ((7 \times 5) \times 31))$
14638 := $((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times ((7 - (9 - 7)))!) - (5! + 3 - 1)$
14639 := $((1 + (3 - 5)) \times ((7 - 9)^7) \times 5!) - (3! + 1)$
14640 := $(1 - (3 + 5!)) \times ((7 - (9 - 7)) - (5^3 \times 1))$
14641 := $(1 \times (3! + 5))^{(7+9)/(7-5+3-1)}$

- 14642** := $((((1 \times 3) - 5)^7) + 9) + (((7! - 5!) \times 3) + 1)$
14643 := $((1 + 3)! - (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7)))) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)$
14644 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) - (97 + 5))^{3+1})$
14645 := $((1^3 - 5 + 7)^9) - ((7! - 5) + 3 \times 1)$
14646 := $((((1 \times 3)! - (5 \times 7)) - (9 - (7! - 5!))) \times (3 \times 1))$
14647 := $1 \times 3! + (((5! - 7) - (97 + 5))^{3+1})$
14648 := $(1 + 3) - (((5! \times ((7 - 9)^7)) - (5 - 3!)) + 1)$
14649 := $(1 + 3) - (((5! \times ((7 - 9)^7)) - (5 - 3!)) \times 1)$
14650 := $((1 + 3)! \times 579) + (753 + 1)$
14651 := $((((1 \times 3!))! - 5) + ((7 + 9) \times ((7 \times 5!) + 31)))$
14652 := $((1 - 35) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 + 31)$
14653 := $(13 + (5! \times 79)) + (7! + (5 \times (3 + 1)!))$
14654 := $13 + ((5 - ((7 \times 9) \times (7 - 5)))^{3-1})$
14655 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) + 7)) \times ((975 + 3) - 1)$
14656 := $1 + (((3 + 5) + 7) \times ((975 + 3) - 1))$
14657 := $((((1 + 3)! - 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + 5)) \times 3) - 1$
14658 := $((((1 + 3)! - 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + 5)) \times 3) \times 1$
14659 := $((((1 + 3)! - 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + 5)) \times 3) + 1$
14660 := $(((((1 \times 3)! - 5!) - 7)^{9-7}) - 5) + (3 + 1)!$
14661 := $((((1 - 35) \times 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)$
14662 := $(13 - 5) + (7 + (97 \times (5! + 31)))$
14663 := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 + (7 - 5))) + (3! - 1)$
14664 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7) - ((9 - 7!) + 5 \times 31))$
14665 := $1 \times (35 \times ((79 - ((7 - 5!) \times 3)) + 1))$
14666 := $1 + (35 \times ((79 - ((7 - 5!) \times 3)) + 1))$
14667 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7! - (97 + 53)) - 1)$
14668 := $13 + (5 \times ((7 + (975 \times 3)) - 1))$
14669 := $((((1 - 35) \times 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) + (3 + 1)$
14670 := $((135 \times (7 - 9)) + (7! + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)$
14671 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5) + (7 + ((97 \times (5! - 3!)) + 1))$
14672 := $(13 + 5) + (7 + (97 \times (5! + 31)))$
14673 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7! - (97 + 53)) + 1)$
14674 := $1 - ((3 \times (5! - 7!)) + (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1))))$
14675 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) + (97 \times (5! + 31))$
14676 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 + ((7! - 9) + 7)) - (5! + 31))$
14677 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5 + 79) - (((7! + 5!) \times 3) \times 1))$
14678 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5 + 79) - (((7! + 5!) \times 3) + 1))$
14679 := $(1 - 357) + (97 \times (5 \times 31))$
14680 := $((13 \times ((5! + 7) + 97)) \times 5) + ((3! - 1)!)$
14681 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5! \times 79)) + (7! + 5 \times 31)$
14682 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5! + 7) + (97 \times 5))) - (3! \times 1)$
14683 := $((((1 + 3)! + (5! + 7)) \times (97 + 5)) - (3! - 1))$
14684 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - (97 + 53))) - 1$
14685 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 + 975) - (3 \times 1))$
14686 := $1 + (3 \times 5 \times ((7 + 975) - (3 \times 1)))$
14687 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5! \times 7))) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1)$
14688 := $(13 + 5) \times ((797 + (5!/3!)) - 1)$
14689 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! - (97 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
14690 := $(1 + (3! - 5!)) \times (((7 - 97) - (5!/3)) \times 1)$
14691 := $(1 + 3) - ((5! \times 7) + (97 - ((5^3!) - 1)))$
14692 := $((1 + 3) - ((5! \times 7) + 97)) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
14693 := $((1 \times 3)! - (5! \times 7)) - (97 - ((5^3!) - 1))$
14694 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5! + 7) + (97 \times 5))) + (3! \times 1)$
14695 := $(1 \times 3)! - (((5! \times 7) + (97 - (5^3!))) - 1)$
14696 := $(1 - (3 \times (5! - (7! - (9 \times 7)))) + ((5^3) - 1)$
14697 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5! + ((7 + (9 - 7)) \times 531))$
14698 := $(1 - 3) \times (5! - ((7 \times 97) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1)))$
14699 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + ((7 \times 9) + 7!))) - (5^{3+1})$
14700 := $((((1 \times 3)! - 5!) \times (7 - ((9 + 7) + 5!))) - (3! \times 1))$
14701 := $((13 - ((5! \times 7) + 97)) + (5^3!)) \times 1$
14702 := $((13 - ((5! \times 7) + 97)) + (5^3!)) + 1$
14703 := $1 \times 3 + (((5 + 79) \times 7) \times (5^{3-1}))$
14704 := $((1 \times 3)! - (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 \times 1))$
14705 := $((((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7) \times (9 - (7!/5))) + (3! - 1)$
14706 := $(13 + 5) \times ((797 + (5!/3!)) \times 1)$
14707 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5!/(3 + 1)))$
14708 := $1 + ((((((3! \times 5) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5!) \times 3!) + 1)$
14709 := $((1 + 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (97 \times ((5! - 3) \times 1))$
14710 := $1 - ((3! \times (57 + 9)) - ((7! - 5) \times (3 \times 1)))$
14711 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((9 + 7) + (5^3)))) - 1$
14712 := $((((1 \times 3)! - 5!) \times (7 - ((9 + 7) + 5!))) + (3! \times 1))$
14713 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((9 + 7) + (5^3)))) + 1$
14714 := $(1 + 3!) \times (5 - (((7 \times 9) - 7!) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!)))$
14715 := $((1^{3!} + 5!) \times ((7!/9)/7)) - (5 - ((3! + 1)!))$
14716 := $(((((1 \times 3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) + 7) + 5!) - 3! \times 1$
14717 := $((1 \times ((3! \times (5! - 7)) - 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times 3))) - 1$
14718 := $((1 \times ((3! \times (5! - 7)) - 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times 3))) \times 1$

- 14719** := $((1 \times ((3! \times (5! - 7)) - 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times 3))) + 1$
14720 := $(1 \times (3! \times 5!)) + (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5^3 \times 1)))$
14721 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) + (((7!/9) \times (75/3)) + 1)$
14722 := $((1 - 3 + (57 - 9)) \times 7) + (5!^{3-1})$
14723 := $(1 - 3) + (5 \times (((7 + 975) \times 3) - 1))$
14724 := $1 - ((3! - (5 \times ((7 + 975) \times 3))) + 1)$
14725 := $((1 \times (3!! + 57)) - (9 - 7)) \times ((5!/3!) - 1)$
14726 := $(1 - 3) - (5! + (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5! - (3 + 1))))$
14727 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5 \times (7 + 975)) - (3 \times 1))$
14728 := $1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7 + 975)) - (3 \times 1))$
14729 := $1 + ((3 \times (5 \times (7 + 975))) - (3 - 1))$
14730 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7 + 975) \times (3! - 1))$
14731 := $(1^3 \times ((5! + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 53))) - 1$
14732 := $(1 + (3! - (5 \times 79))) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
14733 := $(1^3 \times ((5! + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 53))) + 1$
14734 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + (((9 + 7!) - 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
14735 := $(1 \times 35) \times ((7 - (9 \times (7 - 53))) \times 1)$
14736 := $1 \times 3! + ((5 \times (7 + 975)) \times (3 \times 1))$
14737 := $1 + (3 \times ((5 \times (7 + 975)) + 3 - 1))$
14738 := $1 - (((3 + 5) + (7 + 9)) - (((7! - 5!) \times 3) + 1))$
14739 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5 + ((7! - 97) - (5 \times (3! + 1))))$
14740 := $1 + (((3! - 5) - 7) + 9) \times ((7! - 5!) - (3! + 1))$
14741 := $(1 \times 3!) + (5 \times (((7 + 975) \times 3) + 1))$
14742 := $(1 + ((357 - 9) - 7)) + (5!^{3-1})$
14743 := $1 + ((3! + 57) \times (9 \times ((75/3) + 1)))$
14744 := $((1 \times ((3! \times 57) + 9)) \times (7!/5!)) + (3 - 1)$
14745 := $(1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times (5! - (3 \times 1))))))$
14746 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 \times (7 + (9 + 7)))) + (5!^{3-1})$
14747 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7!/9) - 7531)$
14748 := $(1 \times 3!) \times ((5! \times (7 + 9)) + (7 + 531))$
14749 := $((1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + 7 + (5!^{3-1})$
14750 := $((1 + 3!)! - 5!) - ((7 - 9) \times (7! - (5^3 \times 1)))$
14751 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + ((9 - 7) - 5))) - 3!! \times 1$
14752 := $(1 - 3) - (((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5!) + 3!) \times 1$
14753 := $(1 - 3) - (((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5!) + 3!) - 1$
14754 := $((1 - (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) - 7!)) + 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
14755 := $((1 \times (35/7)) - 9) + (((7! - 5!) \times 3) - 1)$
14756 := $(1 \times (35/7)) - (9 - ((7! - 5!) \times (3 \times 1)))$
14757 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) + 9 - ((7 + 5) \times 31)$
14758 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) + (((7 - 9) + 7!) \times ((5^3) - 1))$
14759 := $(1 - (3 \times (5! - (7! + 9)))) - ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1)$
14760 := $((1^{3!}) + ((5 + 7) - (9 + 7))) \times (5! - ((3! + 1)!))$
14761 := $(1^3) + (5! \times ((7 \times 9) + (7 + (53 \times 1))))$
14762 := $((1 - 3!!) - 5!) - (((7 + (9 + 7)) - (5^3!)) + 1)$
14763 := $(1 \times (3 + ((5 + (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times 5!))) + ((3! \times 1)!)$
14764 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! + 7!) + (((9 + 7) \times 5) \times ((3! - 1)!))$
14765 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) + ((7! + 9753) + 1)$
14766 := $((1^3 - 5 + 7)^9) - 7! + (5! + 3 \times 1)$
14767 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + ((7! + 9753) - 1)$
14768 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + ((7! + 9753) \times 1)$
14769 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) + 79) \times 75 - (3! \times 1)$
14770 := $(1 - ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) + (((7! - 5!) \times 3) + 1)$
14771 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5!) - (3! - 1))$
14772 := $(1 + 3) - (((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7)) - (5^3!)) + 1$
14773 := $(1 - 3!!) + ((5! + (((79 + 7!) + 5) \times 3)) \times 1)$
14774 := $(1 + 3) - (((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7)) - (5^3!)) - 1$
14775 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5!^{3-1})$
14776 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7! + 9)) - ((7 \times 53) \times 1)$
14777 := $((1 + (3 - 57)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
14778 := $((1 - 3!!) - 5!) + (7 - (9 + 7)) + ((5^3!) + 1)$
14779 := $((13 - 5!) \times 7) - 97 + (5^{3! \times 1})$
14780 := $1 \times (((3!! + (5 \times 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times (5!/(3! \times 1)))$
14781 := $1 + (((3!! + (5 \times 7)) - (9 + 7)) \times (5!/(3! \times 1)))$
14782 := $(1 - 3!) - (5 - ((7! + 9753) - 1))$
14783 := $(1 - 3!) - (5 - ((7! + 9753) \times 1))$
14784 := $(1 \times (3! + 5)) \times ((7 + (97 + 5!)) \times (3! \times 1))$
14785 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) + (7 + 9))) + (((7! - 5!) \times 3) + 1)$
14786 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) + (7 + 9))) + (((7! - 5!) \times 3) + 1)$
14787 := $((1 - (3 - 57)) - ((9 - 7!) + 5!) \times 3) - 1$
14788 := $(1^3 - (5! \times 7)) + (9 - 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
14789 := $((1 - (3 - 57)) - ((9 - 7!) + 5!) \times 3) + 1$
14790 := $((1 + 3)! \times (579 + 7)) + ((5 + 3!!) + 1)$
14791 := $(1 \times 3) - (5 - (7! + (9753 \times 1)))$
14792 := $(1 - 3!) + (5 + ((7! + 9753) - 1))$
14793 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! + (9 + 7)) - (5^3))) \times 1$
14794 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! + (9 + 7)) - (5^3))) + 1$
14795 := $(1 - (((3!! + 5!) + 7) - (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$

$$\begin{aligned}14796 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (((5! \times 7) \times 9) - (7! + (53 + 1))) \\14797 &:= ((13 + (5 - 7)) + (((9 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3)) - 1 \\14798 &:= ((13 + (5 - 7)) + (((9 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3)) \times 1 \\14799 &:= ((13 + (5 - 7)) + (((9 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3)) + 1 \\14800 &:= (((13 - 5!) + 7!) \times (9 - ((7 - 5) \times 3))) + 1 \\14801 &:= 13 - ((5 - (7! + 9753)) \times 1) \\14802 &:= (((1 + 3) - (5! - 7!)) / (9 - 7)) + 5 \times 3! \times 1 \\14803 &:= (1 + (3! - 5!)) \times (((7 - 97) - (5! / 3)) - 1) \\14804 &:= 13579 + ((7 \times 5)^{3-1}) \\14805 &:= (1 \times (35 \times ((7! / 9) + 7))) - (((5 + 3) - 1)!) \\14806 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5) + 7!)) + (9753 + 1) \\14807 &:= (((1^{3!}) - 5!) \times 7) + (((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) - 1) \\14808 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - 97)) - (5 + 31) \\14809 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) \times 7) + (((9 - 7) + (5^{3!})) + 1) \\14810 &:= 13 + ((5 + (7! + 9753)) - 1) \\14811 &:= 13 + ((5 + (7! + 9753)) \times 1) \\14812 &:= (1 + (3! - (5 \times 7))) \times ((9 - 7) - 531) \\14813 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 + 7!)) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5) \times 31)) \\14814 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 - 97)) + (5^{3!}) - 1 \\14815 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 - 97)) + (5^{3!}) \times 1 \\14816 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times (7 - 97)) + (5^{3!}) + 1 \\14817 &:= 1 \times (3! - ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5! + (3! + 1)))))) \\14818 &:= 1 + (3! - ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5! + (3! + 1)))))) \\14819 &:= ((1 + 3)! + 5) \times (((7 - 9) + 75) \times (3! + 1)) \\14820 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (57 \times (((9 + 7) - 5!) / (3 - 1))) \\14821 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) \times 9) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}) \\14822 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((5 + 7!) + (9753 \times 1)) \\14823 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) - (((7 \times 97) - (5^{3!})) + 1) \\14824 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) - ((7 \times 97) - ((5^{3!}) \times 1)) \\14825 &:= 1 + ((3! \times 5) + ((7! + 9753) + 1)) \\14826 &:= (((1^{3!}) - 5!) + 7!) + (9 + 7) + 5 \times (3 \times 1) \\14827 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5 + 797)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\14828 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times ((7 \times 9) - (7 - 5))) + (3! - 1) \\14829 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 + 797)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\14830 &:= 1 - ((3^5 + (79 \times 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\14831 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5! + (7 \times 97)) - ((5^{3!}) - 1)) \\14832 &:= (1 + 35) \times (7 - (9 \times ((7 - 53) + 1))) \\14833 &:= (1 + (3!! + 5)) + ((7! + (9 \times (7! / 5))) - (3! - 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14834 &:= ((135 \times (7 - 9)) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) - 1 \\14835 &:= ((135 \times (7 - 9)) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) \times 1 \\14836 &:= ((135 \times (7 - 9)) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) + 1 \\14837 &:= ((1 \times ((3! + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + (5 + 3!)) \times 1 \\14838 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 + ((7! - (97 - 5)) - 3!)) - 1) \\14839 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) - ((9 + 7) - (5^{3-1})) \\14840 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) \times (7 - (97 \times (5 + 3!)))) \times 1 \\14841 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! + (7! - 97)) - (5! - (3 + 1))) \\14842 &:= 1 - (3 \times (5! - (79 + ((7! - 53) + 1)))) \\14843 &:= (1 - 3!!) - ((5! + 7) - (((9 \times 7) + (5^{3!})) + 1)) \\14844 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (5 - (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3!})) - 1)) \\14845 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (5 - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}))) \\14846 &:= ((1^{3!}) - (579 - 7)) \times (5 - 31) \\14847 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5! - (3 + 1))) \\14848 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5! - 7!))) + (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1))) \\14849 &:= ((1^{35}) - (7 - (97 \times 5))) \times 31 \\14850 &:= ((1 - (3! - 5!)) - (7 + 9)) \times (75 \times (3 - 1)) \\14851 &:= 1 + (((35 + 7) - 9) \times ((75 \times 3!) \times 1)) \\14852 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 + 9)) \times 75) + (3 - 1) \\14853 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + (5 - 31)) \\14854 &:= 1 \times ((3! - ((5! \times 7) - (9 \times 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\14855 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + 5) + ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\14856 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((57 + 9) \times 75) + 3 - 1) \\14857 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5! - (3 + 1))) \\14858 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - ((5! - 7!) - ((9 + 7!) - (5! + 31)))) \\14859 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((7! + 9753) + 1) \\14860 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5 \times ((797 - 53) - 1)) \\14861 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - (5 \times ((7 + 9) - 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\14862 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) - (7 + 9)) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\14863 &:= 13 + ((57 + 9) \times (75 \times (3 \times 1))) \\14864 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - (5! - (7! - (97 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1) \\14865 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (5 \times (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 53))) + 1 \\14866 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + (7! - (97 - 5)))) + (3! + 1) \\14867 &:= 1 - (3! + ((579 - 7) \times (5 - 31))) \\14868 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times 531) \\14869 &:= ((1^{3!}) - 5!) + ((7! - (9 + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\14870 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7) + (((9 - 7) + 5!)^{3-1}) \\14871 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - (5! - (79 - (7! / 5!)))) \times (3 \times 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14872 &:= (((1-3) \times 5!) - 7) + (((9+7) + 5) \times 3!!) - 1 \\14873 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5-79 + (7! - 5)) - 3)) - 1 \\14874 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5-79 + (7! - 5)) - 3)) \times 1 \\14875 &:= (1-3!) \times (5 \times (((7-(9-7)) + 5!) - 3!! \times 1)) \\14876 &:= (((1+3!))! - 5) + (((7!/9)/7) \times (5! + 3)) + 1 \\14877 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5-79 + (7! - 5)) - 3) + 1) \\14878 &:= 1 - ((3 \times 57) \times (9 - (7 + (5! - 31)))) \\14879 &:= (1+3!) - ((579-7) \times (5-31)) \\14880 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5+7!) - 97)) + (5+31) \\14881 &:= 1 + (3 \times ((5! + 7!) - ((9+7) \times 5) + ((3! - 1)!!)) \\14882 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5-79+7!)) - ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\14883 &:= 1 \times (((35+7) - 9) \times ((75 \times 3!) + 1)) \\14884 &:= ((1 \times 3! + 5!) - ((7-9)^{7-5})^{3-1}) \\14885 &:= 1 + ((3! + ((5 \times ((7-9)^7)/5))^{3-1}) \\14886 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times (5 + ((7-9)^7))) + (5^{3!})) - 1) \\14887 &:= ((1 + (3! \times (5 + ((7-9)^7)))) + (5^{3!})) - 1 \\14888 &:= (((1+3!) + (5! \times 79)) + 7!) + ((5! \times 3) + 1) \\14889 &:= ((1 + (3! \times (5 + ((7-9)^7)))) + (5^{3!})) + 1 \\14890 &:= (1 + (35/7)) + (((9-7) + 5!)^{3-1}) \\14891 &:= (((1+3^5) - 7) \times 9) \times 7 - (5!/(3 \times 1)) \\14892 &:= ((13 \times (5+7)) \times 97) - (5! \times (3-1)) \\14893 &:= (1 - (3!! + (5-7))) - (((9+7) - (5^{3!})) - 1) \\14894 &:= ((1+3!) - (((5 \times 7) - 97) \times 5!)) \times (3-1) \\14895 &:= ((1+3^5) \times ((7-(9 \times 7)) + 5!)) - (3!! + 1) \\14896 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5-79+7!)) - (5-3)) \times 1 \\14897 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5-79+7!)) - (5-3)) + 1 \\14898 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (((57-9) + 7!) - 5!) - (3-1)) \\14899 &:= 1 + (3 \times (((57-9) + 7!) - 5!) - (3-1)) \\14900 &:= (1 \times ((3 + (5 \times 797)) \times 5)) - ((3! + 1)!) \\14901 &:= (13 \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + (7!/(5 - (3-1))) \\14902 &:= ((1-3+5) \times 7!) - ((9 \times 7) + 5 \times 31) \\14903 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) - 97) - (5! \times (3+1)) \\14904 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times (79 - 7531) \\14905 &:= (1 + ((35 \times (7 \times 9)) \times 7)) - 531 \\14906 &:= (1+3!) - (((5! \times 7) - 97) - (5^{3!} \times 1)) \\14907 &:= (1+3!) - (((5! \times 7) - 97) - (5^{3!} + 1)) \\14908 &:= (1+3) + ((57 - ((9-7!) + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\14909 &:= ((1^{3!} - 5!) - (7 - (97 \times (5 \times 31)))) \\14910 &:= (1 - ((3!! + 5) - ((7+9) - 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14911 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 31 \\14912 &:= (1 \times ((3+5!) \times 79)) + (7! + 5 \times 31) \\14913 &:= ((1 - (3-5)) \times 7!) + (9 \times (7 - (5!/(3+1)))) \\14914 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5-79+7!)) + ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\14915 &:= (((1+3!) \times 5!) + 7) + (97 \times ((5^3) - 1)) \\14916 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! + 7!)) + (9753 \times 1) \\14917 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + 7!) + (9753 + 1) \\14918 &:= 1 \times (35 - ((79-7!) \times (5 - (3-1)))) \\14919 &:= 1 + (35 - ((79-7!) \times (5 - (3-1)))) \\14920 &:= (1+3) - ((57+9) \times ((7-5!) \times (3-1))) \\14921 &:= ((1-3) \times 57) + (97 \times (5 \times 31)) \\14922 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) + (((9-7) + 5!)^{3-1}) \\14923 &:= (1^{3!}) - ((5! - 7) - (97 \times (5 \times 31))) \\14924 &:= (1-3) - (5 + (((7 \times 9) - 7!) \times ((5-3) + 1))) \\14925 &:= (1 \times 3) - (5! - (7 + ((97 \times 5) \times 31))) \\14926 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - (5! - 7!)) + (((9-7) \times 5)^{3+1}) \\14927 &:= 135 + ((7! + 9753) - 1) \\14928 &:= ((135 + 7!) + 9753) \times 1 \\14929 &:= ((135 + 7!) + 9753) + 1 \\14930 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (((7! - ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 3) - 1) \\14931 &:= ((1-3+5) \times (7! - 9)) - (7 + 5 \times 31) \\14932 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (((7! - ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 3) + 1) \\14933 &:= (1^3) - (((5 - (7! - ((9 \times 7) - 5))) \times 3) - 1) \\14934 &:= (1 - (3-5)) \times ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + ((5-3) - 1)) \\14935 &:= ((13-5!) + 7) + ((97 \times 5) \times 31) \\14936 &:= ((1-35) \times (7+9)) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\14937 &:= (1-3+5) \times (7 - (((9 \times 7) + 5) - ((3! + 1)!!)) \\14938 &:= (1 - ((3+5) \times (79+7))) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\14939 &:= (1 - ((3 \times (5-7!)) + (9+7))) - (5! + 31) \\14940 &:= (1-3) - (5! + ((7-9) \times 7531)) \\14941 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) - ((7 - (97 \times 5)) \times 31) \\14942 &:= (((1+3) \times 5!) - (7-9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3+1)) \\14943 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + (7! - (9-7)))) - 531 \\14944 &:= 1 + (3 \times (5 - (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!) - ((3! + 1)!!))) \\14945 &:= (((1-3!) \times 5) \times 7) + (((9+7) + 5) \times (3!! \times 1)) \\14946 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - 5) - (7 \times 97)) + (5^{3!}) - 1 \\14947 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - 5) - (7 \times 97)) + (5^{3!}) \times 1 \\14948 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7)) + 9) \times (7 - (5 \times 31)) \\14949 &:= ((1^3 - 5) + (79 \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1})\end{aligned}$$

- 14950** := $(1 + (3! - (5 + ((7 - 9)^7)))) \times ((5! - 3!) + 1)$
14951 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + ((9 - 7) - 531)$
14952 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((97 - 5) - 31))$
14953 := $(1 \times 3 + 5) - ((7 \times 97) - (5^{3!} - 1))$
14954 := $((1 \times (3^5)) - (((7 + 9) - 7!) + 5!) \times 3) - 1$
14955 := $(1 - (3^5)) + (((7! - (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 3) - 1)$
14956 := $((1 \times (3^5)) - (((7 + 9) - 7!) + 5!) \times 3) + 1$
14957 := $((1 - (((3 - 5) \times 7!) + 9)) + 7!) - (5 \times 31)$
14958 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (7! - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)$
14959 := $1 - ((3 + (5 \times (7 - (9 \times 7)))) \times (53 + 1))$
14960 := $((1 - (3! + 5)) \times (7 + 9)) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
14961 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5) + (7 + (97 \times (5! - (3 \times 1))))$
14962 := $((1 + 3!)! - (((5! - 7!) + 9) - 7!) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
14963 := $(1 - 3 + (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 7!)) - (5 \times 31)$
14964 := $((1 + 35) + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5) \times 3! \times 1$
14965 := $((1 + 35) + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5) \times 3! + 1$
14966 := $(1^3 + (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 7!)) - (5 \times 31)$
14967 := $1 \times ((3! + (5 - 7!)) \times ((9 - 7) - 5) - ((3! - 1)!))$
14968 := $(1 \times 3 + (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 7!)) - (5 \times 31)$
14969 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) - ((97 + 53) + 1)$
14970 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (5 - (7 - 97))) + (5^{3-1})$
14971 := $((1 + 3^5) - 7) \times 9 \times 7 + (5! / (3 \times 1))$
14972 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + 9 + (7! - 5) \times 3 - 1$
14973 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + 9 + (7! - 5) \times 3 \times 1$
14974 := $1 \times ((35 \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}))$
14975 := $1 + ((35 \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 - 5!)^{3-1}))$
14976 := $1 \times (((3! / 5) \times (7 + (97 - 5))) + 3! \times 1)$
14977 := $1 + (((3! / 5) \times (7 + (97 - 5))) + 3! \times 1)$
14978 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) \times 7! + (9 + (7! - (5! + 31)))$
14979 := $1 \times (3 \times ((5! + (7! - 9)) - ((7 + 5!) + 31)))$
14980 := $(1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7) \times (97 + (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
14981 := $(1 + (3! \times ((5 + 7) + 9))) - (7! / (5 + 31))$
14982 := $(1 \times (3 \times ((5! + 79) + (7! - 5)))) - (3! \times 1)$
14983 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) - ((9 - (7 - 5!)) + 31)$
14984 := $((1 \times (35 - 7!)) \times ((9 - 7) - 5)) - 31$
14985 := $(1 \times (3! - 5!)) + (((7! - (9 - 7)) - 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
14986 := $(1 \times (35 \times 7) + 9) \times ((7 + 53) - 1)$
14987 := $(1^3 + (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) + (5^{3!}) + 1$
14988 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) - ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
14989 := $(1^3 + 5!) - (((79 - 7!) + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
14990 := $1 \times (((3 \times 5) + 7!) - ((9 \times 7) - 5) \times 3) - 1$
14991 := $(13 - 57) + (97 \times (5 \times 31))$
14992 := $(1 - 3) \times (57 - (((9 \times 7) \times 5!) - (3! + 1)))$
14993 := $((1 + 3!) - 5!) - ((7! \times ((9 - 7) - 5)) + 31)$
14994 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5!) \times ((7 \times (97 + 5)) / (3! \times 1))$
14995 := $(1 + 3) - (5! - ((7! - 9) + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1))))))$
14996 := $((1 \times (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) - 5! \times 3 - 1$
14997 := $((1 \times (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) - 5! \times 3 \times 1$
14998 := $((1 \times (3! - 5)) \times (79 + 7!)) - 5! \times 3 + 1$
14999 := $((13 + (5! + 7)) \times (97 + 5)) + (3! - 1)$
15000 := $(1 + (3! + 5)) + (((7! - 9) - (7 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15001 := $(1^3 - 5!) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + (((5 + 3) - 1)!))$
15002 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5! \times (((7 - 9) + 7) + 5!))) - (3 + 1)$
15003 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (7! - (9 \times 7)) - 5 \times 3 \times 1$
15004 := $(1 + 3) + (5! \times (79 - (7 - (53 \times 1))))$
15005 := $((13 + ((5 + 7) + 97)) \times (5! + 3)) - 1$
15006 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((97 - 53) - 1))$
15007 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 \times 7) - (97 \times (5 \times 31)))$
15008 := $(1^3 - (5! - 7)) + (((9 - 7) + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
15009 := $((1 \times 3 + (5 + 79)) \times 7) + (5^{3-1})$
15010 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79)) \times (7 + (5 - 31))$
15011 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + (9 + 7) - 5! - (3! - 1)$
15012 := $1 - ((3! - (((5 + 79) + (7! + 5!)) \times 3)) + 1)$
15013 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 + 79) + (7! + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15014 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) - 7) + (97 \times (5 \times 31))$
15015 := $(1 + 3!) - (5! - ((7! - 9) + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1))))))$
15016 := $(1 + ((3! - (5! - 7!)) + 9)) + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
15017 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) + (7 - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
15018 := $((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) - 5) - ((3! - 1)!)$
15019 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) - ((97 \times 5) - (3 + 1)!)$
15020 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 7!) - (5! + 3 + 1))$
15021 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) \times 7 + ((97 \times 5) \times 31)$
15022 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + (9 + 7) - 5! + (3! \times 1)$
15023 := $((1 - ((3 - 5) \times 7!)) - (9 - 7!)) - (5! - 31)$
15024 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 57) \times (9 + (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
15025 := $(1 + 3) - 57 - ((9 - (7! - 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15026 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5 + 7!)) + ((9 + (7 + 5))^3 \times 1)$
15027 := $((1 \times 3! \times (5 - 7)) \times 9) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$

- 15028** := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + (((9 + 7) - 5!) - (3 \times 1))$
15029 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + (((9 + 7) - 5!) - (3 - 1))$
15030 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5 + 7!))) - ((9 + 7) + (5! - 31))$
15031 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) - ((9 + 7) + (5! - 31))$
15032 := $(1 + 3) \times (5! - (79 - (7 \times 531)))$
15033 := $(((((1 + 3)! + 5) + 7!) - (9 \times 7)) + 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
15034 := $((1 + (35 \times 7)) + (((9 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3)) + 1$
15035 := $((1 - ((3 + 5) + ((7 + 9) - (7! - 5)))) \times 3) - 1$
15036 := $((1 \times 3)^5) + (7! + (9753 \times 1))$
15037 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + 7!) + (9753 + 1)$
15038 := $1 \times ((3! \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) - ((75 + 3!) + 1))$
15039 := $1 + ((3! \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) - ((75 + 3!) + 1))$
15040 := $((1 + ((3! \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) - 75)) - 3!) \times 1$
15041 := $((1 + ((3! \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) - 75)) - 3!) + 1$
15042 := $1 \times (3! \times ((57 \times (97 - 53)) - 1))$
15043 := $1 \times (((3 \times 5) - 7) + ((97 \times 5) \times 31))$
15044 := $1 + (((3 \times 5) - 7) + ((97 \times 5) \times 31))$
15045 := $((((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) - 9) - ((75 + 3!) \times 1))$
15046 := $(1 + (3! - (579 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15047 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7!)) - (9 - ((7! - 53) - 1))$
15048 := $(1 \times 3)! \times ((57 \times (97 - 53)) \times 1)$
15049 := $((((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7!)) - (9 - (7! - 53))) + 1)$
15050 := $1 \times (((3! \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) - 75) + 3!) - 1$
15051 := $((((1 + 3!))! - ((5! + (7 + (9 + 7))) - 5!)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15052 := $((1 - 3!) - 5) - ((7 - 9) \times 7531)$
15053 := $(((((1 \times 3!))! / 5!) \times (((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5) - 3!)) - 1)$
15054 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5 - 79 + (7! + (53 - 1)))$
15055 := $((1 + 3)! - 5!) - ((7! \times ((9 - 7) - 5)) - 31)$
15056 := $((((1 - 3)^5) + ((7! - ((9 + 7) - 5)) \times 3)) + 1)$
15057 := $(1 - (3! / 5!)) - ((7 - 9) \times 7531)$
15058 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) \times (7 - (9 - 7531))$
15059 := $(((((1 \times 3)! \times 5) + 7)^{9-7}) \times (5 + 3! \times 1))$
15060 := $(((((1 + 3) - 57) + 9) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) - 1)$
15061 := $(((((1 + 3) - 57) + 9) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) \times 1)$
15062 := $(((((1 + 3) - 57) + 9) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) + 1)$
15063 := $(((((1 + 3!))! - 5) - (7 \times (9 - 7))) \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
15064 := $(1 \times ((3^{5-7+9}) - (7 \times 5))) \times (3! + 1)$
15065 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7!)) + (9 + ((7! - 53) - 1))$
15066 := $(1 + (3 + 5)) - (((7 + 9) - (7! - 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15067 := $(((((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) - 9) - 7) - (53 - 1))$
15068 := $(1 \times 3 + (5! - (7 \times 97))) + ((5^3!) - 1)$
15069 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + (9 - ((7 + 53) \times 1))$
15070 := $(13 - 5) - ((7 - 9) \times 7531)$
15071 := $1 \times 3! + (5! - ((7 \times 97) - ((5^3!) - 1)))$
15072 := $((((1 \times 3)! \times 57) \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) + (3 + 1)!)$
15073 := $((135 - 7!) / 9) - (7 - ((5^3!) \times 1))$
15074 := $((1^3 \times 5) \times (7! - ((9 \times 75) \times 3))) - 1$
15075 := $(1 - (3 \times 579)) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)$
15076 := $1 - (3 \times (((5! - 79) - (7! - 5)) - 31))$
15077 := $(1 \times 35) - (((7 \times 9) - ((7! - 5) \times 3)) \times 1)$
15078 := $(13 + (5! - (7 \times 97))) + ((5^3!) - 1)$
15079 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 7!) - (5 + 31))$
15080 := $(1 - (3 \times (((5 - 7) + 9) - 7!))) - (5! / 3! \times 1)$
15081 := $(((((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7!) - 9) - (7 - 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15082 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - ((7 - 9) \times 7531)$
15083 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) - ((7 - ((9 + 7) + 5) \times 3!)) + 1$
15084 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5! + ((7! - 97) - (5 \times (3! + 1))))$
15085 := $((((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 + 97)) + (5^{3! - 1}))$
15086 := $((((1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7 - 9) + (7! + 5))) \times 3) - 1)$
15087 := $((((1 - 3 \times 5) + ((7 - 9) + (7! + 5))) \times 3) \times 1)$
15088 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 7!) - (5! / (3 + 1)))$
15089 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) - ((9 + 7) + (5 - (3 + 1)))$
15090 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 - (3 + 1)))$
15091 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) - ((9 + 7) - (5 - (3 + 1)))$
15092 := $((1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7) + 9) - 7!)) - 5) - (3 \times 1)$
15093 := $(1^3 + 57) + (97 \times (5 \times 31))$
15094 := $(1 - (35 - (((7! - 9) + (7 + 5)) \times 3))) - 1$
15095 := $(1 - (35 - (((7! - 9) + (7 + 5)) \times 3))) \times 1$
15096 := $(1 - (35 - (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 \times 1)$
15097 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + (97 - (5! \times (3 + 1)))$
15098 := $(1 \times (3! + 57)) + (97 \times (5 \times 31))$
15099 := $((1 \times 3)! - ((5 + 7) - 9)) \times (7! - ((5 + 3) - 1))$
15100 := $((1 + 3) - 5!) + ((7! + ((9 - 7)^5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15101 := $((((1 + 3) - 5) + 7!) - ((9 - 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))))$
15102 := $((((1 \times 3!) + (5 - 7)))! - ((9 - (7! - 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15103 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! + 9)) - (75 - 31)$
15104 := $(1 - ((3! + 5!) / (7 \times 9))) + ((7! - 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
15105 := $(1 \times 3)! - (((5 - 7!) + (9 - 7)) \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$

- 15106** := $(1 + (3! - (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) \times ((7 - 5) - (3 + 1))$
15107 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (5 + 7)) + ((97 \times 5) \times 31)$
15108 := $(1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7) + 9) - 7!)) + (5 + 3 \times 1)$
15109 := $((1 + 3!)! - (((5 - 7!) \times (9 - 7)) + (((5 - 3!) + 1))!)$
15110 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) + (9 + ((7 + 5) - 31))$
15111 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) + (7! + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)$
15112 := $(1 + (3 - (5! \times (7 \times 9)))) \times (7 - (5 + 3 + 1))$
15113 := $((1 + (((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) + 7!) + 5)) \times 3 - 1$
15114 := $((1 + (((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) + 7!) + 5)) \times 3 \times 1$
15115 := $((1 + (((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) + 7!) + 5)) \times 3 + 1$
15116 := $((1^{3!}) - 5) + ((7! \times ((9 - 7) - (5 - 3!))) \times 1)$
15117 := $(1 + (3! - (5 - 7))) - ((9 - (7! + 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15118 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5 - 7) \times ((9 + 7!) - (5 \times (3 - 1))))$
15119 := $((1 \times 3 + (5 + 7 + 9)) \times (7! / (5 + 3))) - 1$
15120 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times (5 + ((7 - (9 - 7)) + (5 + 3! \times 1)))$
15121 := $((1 - 35) - 7) + ((9 + (7! + 5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15122 := $((1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) + (9 + 7)) \times (5 - (3 + 1))$
15123 := $(1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) + ((9 + 7) + (5 - (3 + 1)))$
15124 := $(1 - 3) - ((5 - 7) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1))$
15125 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + 9 - (7 \times (53 - 1))$
15126 := $(1 - (3 + ((5 - 7) + 9))) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
15127 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
15128 := $((1 + (35 + 79)) + 7) \times ((5^3) - 1)$
15129 := $(1 - ((3 - 5) - 7!)) \times ((9 - 7) - (5 - 3! \times 1))$
15130 := $(13 + 5) + (7! - (9 - ((7! \times (5 - 3)) + 1)))$
15131 := $(1^3) + (((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 7!) + (5 \times (3 - 1)))$
15132 := $((1^{357}) \times ((9 + 7!) - 5)) \times (3 \times 1)$
15133 := $13 - (5! \times ((7 \times 9) \times (((7 - 5) - 3) - 1)))$
15134 := $(1^{35}) + ((7 - 9) + (((7! + 5) \times 3) \times 1))$
15135 := $((1^{35})^{7+9}) + (((7! + 5) \times 3) - 1)$
15136 := $((1^{35})^{7+9}) \times (((7! + 5) \times 3) + 1)$
15137 := $(1 \times (35/7)) + (((9 + 7!) - 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
15138 := $((1^{35}) - (7 - 9)) + (((7! + 5) \times 3) \times 1)$
15139 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + ((9 + ((7^5) + 3)) \times 1)$
15140 := $1 \times ((3 \times ((5 + 7!) - (9 + 7))) + (53 \times 1))$
15141 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times 3! \times 1))$
15142 := $(1^3 + (5 + 7 + 9)) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
15143 := $1 + (((3! \times 5) - (7 - ((9 + 7) + 5) \times 3!)) - 1)$
15144 := $1 + (((3! \times 5) - (7 - ((9 + 7) + 5) \times 3!)) \times 1)$
15145 := $(1^3 + 5!) + ((7! - ((9 - 7)^5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15146 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) + ((9 \times 7) - (53 \times 1))$
15147 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5) + (((7 - 9) + ((7! + 5) \times 3)) - 1))$
15148 := $(1 + ((3! + 5) + (7 + 9))) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
15149 := $(1 - 35) - (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5^{3!})) + 1)$
15150 := $(1 - ((35/7) - (9 + (7! + 5)))) \times (3 \times 1)$
15151 := $1 \times (((35/7) \times 9) + (((7! - 5) \times 3) + 1))$
15152 := $1 + (((35/7) \times 9) + (((7! - 5) \times 3) + 1))$
15153 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (7! + 9753) \times 1$
15154 := $(1 \times 3! + 5!) - (7 - ((97 \times 5) \times 31))$
15155 := $(1 \times 35) \times (((79 + 7) \times 5) + 3) \times 1$
15156 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
15157 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) - (((9 - 75)/3) \times 1)$
15158 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5!) - 31)$
15159 := $((1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) - ((9 \times 7) \times 5) - 3!) \times 1$
15160 := $((1 + 35) + (7! + 9)) + 7! - 5 + ((3! + 1))!$
15161 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + (7! + ((9 - 7) + 5)))) + (3 + 1))$
15162 := $(1 \times 3! + ((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) + (5! \times ((3! - 1))!)$
15163 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) + (((9 \times 7) - 5) - 31)$
15164 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + ((7 + 9 + 7!) - 5)))) - (3! - 1)$
15165 := $1 \times 3 + (5! + (7 + ((97 \times 5) \times 31)))$
15166 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7 + 9 + 7!) \times (5 - (3 - 1)))$
15167 := $13 + (((5 \times 7) + (((9 + 7) + 5) \times 3!)) - 1)$
15168 := $(1 \times 3! + 5!) + (7 + ((97 \times 5) \times 31))$
15169 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 + 9 + 7!)) + 5 - (3 + 1)$
15170 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) - (9 - ((7 + 53) - 1))$
15171 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) - 9 - (7 - (53 - 1))$
15172 := $((135 \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + 53 - 1$
15173 := $((135 \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + 53 \times 1$
15174 := $((135 \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + 53 + 1$
15175 := $((13 + 5!) - (7 \times 9)) + (((7! - 5) \times 3) \times 1)$
15176 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5! - 7) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
15177 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) + 9 + 7 - 5 \times (3 \times 1)$
15178 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + (97 - 53) - 1$
15179 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + (97 - 53) \times 1$
15180 := $((13 \times (5 + 7)) + 97) \times (5! / (3 - 1))$
15181 := $(13 + (57 - 9)) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
15182 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + (((9 \times 7) + 5!) / 3) + 1$
15183 := $((1^{35}) \times (7! + ((9 + 7) + 5))) \times (3 \times 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}15184 &:= (13 \times (57 + (9 + 7))) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\15185 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) - ((7 + 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\15186 &:= ((13 \times (5 + 7)) \times 97) + (53 + 1) \\15187 &:= (((1 + (3!! - 5!)) \times (7 + 9)) + 7!) + 531 \\15188 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + (9 + ((7 + 53) - 1)) \\15189 &:= (1 - (3^5 + 7)) \times (9 - ((7 \times 5) \times (3 - 1))) \\15190 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times ((7^{9-7}) \times (5 \times 31)) \\15191 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! + 9)) + (75 - 31) \\15192 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)))!) + (79 - 7) + (5!^{3-1}) \\15193 &:= 1 - ((3 \times (5 - 7!)) - (97 - (5 \times (3 - 1)))) \\15194 &:= 1 - ((3 \times (5 - 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) - (5! + 31))) \\15195 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 5!) + 79) - (7 + ((5^{3!}) + 1))) \\15196 &:= (1 + (3 - (5 - 797))) + (5!^{3-1}) \\15197 &:= ((1 \times 3!!) \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) + (75 + 3 - 1) \\15198 &:= ((1 \times (35 + 79)) \times (7 + 5!)) + (3!! \times 1) \\15199 &:= (((1^{35}) + (7 \times 9)) + ((7! + 5) \times 3)) \times 1 \\15200 &:= (13 + ((5! \times 7) + 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) + 1) \\15201 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 \times 1) \\15202 &:= (1 \times (3!! \times ((5 + 7) + 9))) + ((75 + 3!) + 1) \\15203 &:= (1 + (3!! \times ((5 + 7) + 9))) + ((75 + 3!) + 1) \\15204 &:= ((13 \times 579) + 75) \times (3 - 1) \\15205 &:= 1 - ((35 + 7) \times (9 - (7 \times (53 \times 1)))) \\15206 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + 79) - (7! / ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\15207 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) \times (97 + ((5! / 3) \times 1)) \\15208 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) - 9) + ((75 + 3!) + 1) \\15209 &:= (1^3 \times ((5 + (7 - 9)) \times 7!)) + (5! - 31) \\15210 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (5 + ((7 + 9) \times 7))) \times (5 - 31) \\15211 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) + (5 + (79 + 7))) + (5!^{3-1}) \\15212 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) + 79) + (((7! - 5) \times 3) - 1) \\15213 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5 + 7) - 9) \times (7! + (5! / (3 + 1)))) \\15214 &:= (1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7) + 9) - 7!)) + (5! - 3! \times 1) \\15215 &:= ((1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7!) + (9 - 7)))) + 5!) - (3! - 1) \\15216 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) - (79 \times 7)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\15217 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) - (79 \times 7)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\15218 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) + 79) \times (7! / ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) \\15219 &:= ((1 + 35) - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5^{3!}))) - 1 \\15220 &:= ((1 + 35) - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5^{3!}))) \times 1 \\15221 &:= ((1 + 35) - ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5^{3!}))) + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15222 &:= (1 - (3 + (5! - 79))) \times ((7 - (5! \times 3)) - 1) \\15223 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^{3-1})) \\15224 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times (5 + 7!)) + (((9 \times 7) - 5) + 31)) \\15225 &:= ((1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7!) + (9 - 7)))) + 5!) + (3! - 1) \\15226 &:= ((1 \times (3 - (5 \times 79))) - 7) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15227 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) + (9 + 7!))) - (5 \times (3! - 1)) \\15228 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1)) \\15229 &:= ((1 \times (3!! + (5! \times 79))) + (7! - 5)) - (3! \times 1) \\15230 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5 \times (7 \times 97))) + (5 + ((3! + 1)!)) \\15231 &:= (1 \times 3! + (((5 \times 7) - 9) + (7! + 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\15232 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) \times (7 + 97)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\15233 &:= ((1 + 35) + 797) + (5!^{3-1}) \\15234 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! + (9 + (7 \times 5))) - 3! \times 1) \\15235 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5!) + (((7! - 9) + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))) \\15236 &:= 1 - ((3!! + (5! \times 7)) + (9 - (((7^5) - 3) \times 1))) \\15237 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) - ((7 + 5) \times 3! \times 1) \\15238 &:= 1 + ((3 \times ((5! - (7 \times 9)) + 7!)) - (53 + 1)) \\15239 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 + 3!)))) - 1 \\15240 &:= (1 \times ((3 - ((5 - 7)^9) - 7)) \times (5! / (3 + 1))) \\15241 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5 + 3!)))) + 1 \\15242 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 7) \times 9)) - (7 + (5! / (3 - 1))) \\15243 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((57 - 9) + (7! - 5))) - (3! \times 1) \\15244 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + (5! - (((7 - 9) - 7!) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1))) \\15245 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7 - 5)^{3! \times 1}) \\15246 &:= (1 \times (3! + 57)) \times (((9 - 7) \times 5!) + 3 - 1) \\15247 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + ((5 + 7!) + (97 \times 5!))) - (3!! - 1) \\15248 &:= (1 \times (3!! + (5! \times 79))) + (7! + (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\15249 &:= 13 - ((579 + 7) \times (5 - 31)) \\15250 &:= ((13 + (5 + 7)) + 97) \times (5^3 \times 1) \\15251 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + (9 \times 7)) + 53 \times 1 \\15252 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15253 &:= 13 + (((5 \times 7) + (97 - 5)) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\15254 &:= (13 \times ((5 + 7) \times 97)) + ((5! + 3) - 1) \\15255 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((57 - 9) + (7! - 5))) + (3! \times 1) \\15256 &:= (135 + (7 + 9)) + ((7! - 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15257 &:= (13 \times ((5 + 7) \times 97)) + (5^3 \times 1) \\15258 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5 - 79 + (7! + 5!))) \times (3 \times 1) \\15259 &:= ((1^{3!}) + ((5 - 79 + (7! + 5!)) \times 3)) \times 1 \\15260 &:= 13 + ((5! + 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! \times (3 - 1))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15261 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) - (9 - (7! - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\15262 &:= 1 + (((3 \times (5! + 7!)) - 97) - (5! + 3 - 1)) \\15263 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5! - (7 - 9))) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15264 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 - 53) + 1) \\15265 &:= (1 + ((3 \times ((5 - 7)^9)) + (7^5))) - (3! + 1) \\15266 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + (97 - 53))) - 1 \\15267 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + (97 - 53))) \times 1 \\15268 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + (97 - 53))) + 1 \\15269 &:= (1 \times (3 \times ((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times 75))) - 31 \\15270 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! + (9 + (7 \times 5))) + 3! \times 1) \\15271 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) + ((97 + 53) + 1) \\15272 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 \times 5)) - (3 - 1) \\15273 &:= 1 - ((3 - ((5 + 7) - 9) \times 7!)) - (5 \times 31) \\15274 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times ((5 - 7)^9))) + ((7^5) + 3)) \times 1 \\15275 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 7!) + 5 \times 31 \\15276 &:= (1^3) + (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 7!) + 5 \times 31 \\15277 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 + (7 - 9)) \times ((7! + 53) \times 1)) \\15278 &:= (1 \times 3 + (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 7!)) + (5 \times 31) \\15279 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times (((7! + 9) + 75) - 31) \\15280 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - (((9 + 7) \times 5) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\15281 &:= (1 \times 3! + (((5 + 7) - 9) \times 7!)) + (5 \times 31) \\15282 &:= (((13 \times 5) - 7) - (9 - (7! + 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\15283 &:= (1 \times ((357 + 9) + (7 + 5!))) \times 31 \\15284 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 57) \times (9 - 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15285 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + (((7! + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 3) \times 1) \\15286 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + (((7! + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 3) + 1) \\15287 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) - (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\15288 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) - (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\15289 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) + ((9 - (7 - 5!)) + 31) \\15290 &:= (1 - (3 \times ((5 - 79) - 7!))) - (53 \times 1) \\15291 &:= ((1 \times ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) - (7 + 5)) - 3! \times 1 \\15292 &:= (((1 + ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) - 5) - 3! \times 1 \\15293 &:= (((13 \times 5) + ((7! - 9) + (7 - 5))) \times 3) - 1 \\15294 &:= (((13 \times 5) + ((7! - 9) + (7 - 5))) \times 3) \times 1 \\15295 &:= (((13 \times 5) + ((7! - 9) + (7 - 5))) \times 3) + 1 \\15296 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 31))) \\15297 &:= (13 + (5! - (79 - (7! + 5)))) \times (3 \times 1) \\15298 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) + ((7 - 9)^7))) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15299 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (797 + 53)) - 1 \\15300 &:= 1 \times (3! \times (5 \times ((7 - 97) + (5! \times (3! - 1)))) \\15301 &:= 1 + (3! \times (5 \times ((7 - 97) + (5! \times (3! - 1)))) \\15302 &:= (1 + (((3^5) \times 7) \times 9)) - (7 + (5 - (3 + 1))) \\15303 &:= 1 \times ((35 + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15304 &:= 1 + ((35 + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15305 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((7! - ((9 \times 7) - 5!)) \times 3)) - 1 \\15306 &:= (1 + (35 + (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 \times 1) \\15307 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) + ((7! - ((9 \times 7) - 5!)) \times 3)) + 1 \\15308 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 79) + 7) + (5^3))) \times 1 \\15309 &:= (1 + (3 \times (57 + (9 + 7!)))) - (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\15310 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) \times 7) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\15311 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) \times 7) - ((5^3) - 1) \\15312 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((579 + 7) + (53 - 1)) \\15313 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7 - 5) - 3! \times 1) \\15314 &:= (((1 + ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) + 5) + 3! \times 1 \\15315 &:= 1 \times (3!! - ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times (3 + 1)))) \\15316 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 \times (5 - 3! \times 1)) \\15317 &:= (13 \times 5) + ((7 + (97 \times 5)) \times 31) \\15318 &:= (13 + 5) \times (797 + (53 + 1)) \\15319 &:= ((1 + ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) + 7) + (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\15320 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 + (3! - 1))) \\15321 &:= (((13 \times 5) - (7 - 9)) + 7!) \times ((5 - 3) + 1) \\15322 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^3))) - 1 \\15323 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^3))) \times 1 \\15324 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5! + 7!)) - 97)) - (5! / (3 - 1)) \\15325 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times ((5 \times 79) - (7! / 5))) \times (3! - 1) \\15326 &:= ((13 + 5) + 79) \times ((7 + 5!) + 31) \\15327 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) - (9 \times (7 - (5! / (3 + 1)))) \\15328 &:= (1 \times (3! - (5 - 7))) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\15329 &:= (1 + (3 \times (57 + (9 + 7!)))) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\15330 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! - 7) + ((9 + (7! - 53)) + 1)) \\15331 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5)) + ((3! + 1)! \\15332 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) + (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\15333 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7) \times ((97 - 5!) + 3!) - 1 \\15334 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7! / 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\15335 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 79) \times ((7! / 5!) - (3! - 1))) \\15336 &:= (((1 + 35) \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + (3!! \times 1) \\15337 &:= (((1 + 35) \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + (3!! + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15338 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + 97)) - (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 15339 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7 + 5!)^{3-1}) \\ 15340 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) + (((7 \times 5) - 3) - 1) \\ 15341 &:= (((((1 - 3!) - 5) + (7! + 9)) + 75) \times 3) - 1 \\ 15342 &:= (((((1 - 3!) - 5) + (7! + 9)) + 75) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 15343 &:= (((((1 - 3!) - 5) + (7! + 9)) + 75) \times 3) + 1 \\ 15344 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + ((7! - ((9 - 7!) \times (5 - 3))) - 1) \\ 15345 &:= (1 \times (3!! \times ((5 + 7) + 9))) + (75 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 15346 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + 7!) - (((9 - 7!) \times (5 - 3)) - 1) \\ 15347 &:= (1 - 3) - ((5! \times ((7 - 9)^7)) + ((5 + 3!) \times 1)) \\ 15348 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((5! + (7 + 9)) \times (7 - 5!))) - (3 + 1)! \\ 15349 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - (9 + 7)) + (5 - ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 15350 &:= (((1 + ((3^5) \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7 \times 5) - 3)) \times 1 \\ 15351 &:= (1^{3!}) - ((5! \times ((7 - 9)^7)) + ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 15352 &:= 1 + (357 \times (97 - (53 + 1))) \\ 15353 &:= (1 \times (35 + ((7! - (9 - 75)) \times 3))) \times 1 \\ 15354 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7 - 53) + 1) \\ 15355 &:= ((1 \times (3!! + (5! \times 79))) + (7! - 5)) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 15356 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + 7) - (9 \times (7 + 5 \times 31)) \\ 15357 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + (9 - 7)) - (5! + 3! \times 1) \\ 15358 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5! - 79) + 7!)) - (5 - ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 15359 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) + ((79 + 7!) \times ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\ 15360 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5! - 7)) \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 + 3 \times 1)) \\ 15361 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times (7 \times 9))) + (75 - (3 + 1)!) \\ 15362 &:= ((1 - 3!)/5) + ((7! + (9^{7-5})) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 15363 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7! + (9 + 75)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 15364 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) - 7) \times ((9 \times 75) - (3! + 1)) \\ 15365 &:= (1 \times 35) \times (((7 - (9 - 75)) \times 3!) + 1) \\ 15366 &:= (((1 + 3^5) \times 7) \times 9) - ((7 + 5)/(3 - 1)) \\ 15367 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 9)^7)) \times (5! + (3! + 1)) \\ 15368 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 15369 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5! \times ((7 - 9)^7))) + ((5 + 3!) \times 1) \\ 15370 &:= (((13^{5+7-9}) \times 7) - (5 + 3)) - 1 \\ 15371 &:= ((1^{3!}) - (5! \times ((7 - 9)^7))) + ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\ 15372 &:= ((1^3 + 5!) - 79) \times (7 + ((5! \times 3) - 1)) \\ 15373 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5!) \times (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 15374 &:= (((1 - (35/7)) \times 9) \times 7) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\ 15375 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5!)) \times (((7 \times 9)/7) + (5! - (3 + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15376 &:= (1^3) - ((5 + ((7 - 9)^7)) \times ((5! + 3!) - 1)) \\ 15377 &:= ((13 \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) + ((7! - 5) \times 3)) - 1 \\ 15378 &:= (((1 + 3^5) \times 7) \times 9) + ((7 + 5)/(3 - 1)) \\ 15379 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 79) + 7!)) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 15380 &:= 13 + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + (7 - 5))^{3-1})) \\ 15381 &:= (((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times 9) \times 7) - (53 + 1) \\ 15382 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) - ((97 + 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 15383 &:= (((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times 9) \times 7) - (53 - 1) \\ 15384 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5!)) + ((7 + 9 + (7^5)) - 3!! \times 1) \\ 15385 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (57 - 97)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 15386 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (57 - 97)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\ 15387 &:= (1^3 + (5! + (7! - ((9 - 7)^5)))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 15388 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) + (75 + 3 + 1) \\ 15389 &:= 13 + (((5! - (7 - 9)) + (7 - 5))^{3-1}) \\ 15390 &:= (1 + ((3! \times (((5! - 7) + 9) \times 7)) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 15391 &:= (1 - (3^5)) - ((7 - ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!}))) + 1) \\ 15392 &:= (1 \times (3! - (5 - 7))) \times (((9 + 7) \times 5!) + 3 + 1) \\ 15393 &:= ((1 + 3!!) + (5 + 7)) \times ((9 + 75)/(3 + 1)) \\ 15394 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) - ((7! \times (9 - (7 + 5))) - 31) \\ 15395 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 15396 &:= (1 - (3!! + 5)) + ((7 + 97) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 15397 &:= ((1 - 3) - ((5! - 7) \times (9 - 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 15398 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5! + 7) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 15399 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - (((9 - 7) - 5)^{3+1}) \\ 15400 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) \times 7) - (5!/(3 + 1)!)) \\ 15401 &:= 1 + ((3!! - (5! - (7 + 9))) \times (75/(3 \times 1))) \\ 15402 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5! + (7! - (9 + 7))) - 5) - (3! - 1)) \\ 15403 &:= 1^{35} - (79 - (((7! + 5!) \times 3) + 1)) \\ 15404 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5!) - (7 + (97 - ((5^{3!}) - 1))) \\ 15405 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + (97 - (5 + 3 - 1))) \\ 15406 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5! + 7)) - (97 - ((5^{3!}) - 1)) \\ 15407 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) + (((7 + 9) \times (7!/5)) - 3!! \times 1) \\ 15408 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)))! \times (((7 + 9) \times 7) - 5)) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 15409 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7! + 97) \times (5 - (3 - 1))) \\ 15410 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7!/5!) - (3 + 1)) \\ 15411 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! - (9 - 75)) + 31) \\ 15412 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5 - 79 + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 15413 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5 - 79 + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15414 &:= (13 + 5) + ((7! + (97 - 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15415 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (5! \times ((7 - 9)^7))) + (5! / (3 - 1)) \\15416 &:= (1 + (35 \times ((7 \times 9) \times 7))) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\15417 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) - (9 - (7! - 5!))) \times (3 \times 1) \\15418 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5!) + (((7 - 97) + (5^{3!})) - 1) \\15419 &:= 1 + ((3 \times (5 + (79 + (7! + 5)))) + 31) \\15420 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - (5 \times 7)) + 9) + (7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1) \\15421 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) + (((7! + (9 \times 7)) - 5) \times 3) \times 1 \\15422 &:= (1 + 3!) + (5! + (((7! + (9 \times 7)) - 5) \times 3)) + 1 \\15423 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + 9) - ((7 \times 5) + 31) \\15424 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times 9)) - 7! + (5! \times 31) \\15425 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\15426 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) + ((7! + 97) \times (5 - (3 - 1))) \\15427 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times (7 \times 9)) - (7 - 5))) + ((3! - 1)!) \\15428 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + (9 - 7)) - (53 + 1) \\15429 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) \times 7) - ((5 - (3 - 1)))! \\15430 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + (9 - 7)) - (53 - 1) \\15431 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7 + 53) - 1) \\15432 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times 5) - 79)) + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) + 1) \\15433 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1)) \\15434 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - (3 + 1)) \\15435 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 - (3 + 1)) \\15436 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 - (3 + 1)) \\15437 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5!)) \times (7 + ((9 - 7) - (53 - 1))) \\15438 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) \times 7) + (5 - (3 - 1)) \\15439 &:= (1 - 3!!) - ((5! + (7! / 9)) - ((7^5) + 31)) \\15440 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 \times 79) - 7)) \times (5! / (3 \times 1)) \\15441 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times (7 \times 9))) \times 7) + ((5 - (3 - 1)))! \\15442 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 79) \times ((7 - 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\15443 &:= (((((1 - 3) \times 5) - 7) - 9) \times 7) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15444 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5! + 7!)) - 97)) + (5! / (3 - 1)) \\15445 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\15446 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) - 7) + (5! + (3 + 1)!) \\15447 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + 9)) - (7 + (53 \times 1)) \\15448 &:= (((1 - 3!)^5) + 7!) + (9 + 7) \times (5 + 3 \times 1) \\15449 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\15450 &:= (1 + ((35 \times ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) + (5 \times 3))) - 1 \\15451 &:= (1 + ((35 \times ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) + (5 \times 3))) \times 1 \\15452 &:= (1 + ((35 \times ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) + (5 \times 3))) + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15453 &:= (((1 + 3^5) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - (5! \times 3) \times 1 \\15454 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - (9 + 7)) - 5 - (3! - 1) \\15455 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + 97) - (5! + 3 - 1)) \\15456 &:= 1 + (((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + 97) - (5! + 3 - 1)) \\15457 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + ((9 - (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\15458 &:= 13 + (5 \times (7! - ((9 + 7) \times 5!) + 31)) \\15459 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5!) - ((7^{9-7}) - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15460 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + ((9 - (7 \times 5)) + 3! \times 1) \\15461 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7 - 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\15462 &:= ((1 - 35) + (7 + 9)) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15463 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5!) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7)) + 5))) + (3!! \times 1) \\15464 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - (9 + 7)) - 5 + (3! - 1) \\15465 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\15466 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + 97)) + (5! / 3)) \times 1 \\15467 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - 9) - ((7 \times 5) - 31) \\15468 &:= ((13 - 5!) - (7! + 9)) \times ((7 - (5 + 3!)) + 1) \\15469 &:= (((1^{35}) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) - 5 \times 31 \\15470 &:= (13 \times 5) \times ((7! / (9 + (7 + 5))) - (3 - 1)) \\15471 &:= 1 - (35 \times ((7 \times ((9 - 75) + 3)) - 1)) \\15472 &:= (1^{357}) - (9 - ((7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))) \\15473 &:= ((1 - ((3^5 + 7) - 97)) + (5^{3!})) \times 1 \\15474 &:= ((1 - ((3^5 + 7) - 97)) + (5^{3!})) + 1 \\15475 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - 9) + ((7 \times 5) - 31) \\15476 &:= (((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5)) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\15477 &:= ((1 + 35) \times ((79 + 7) \times 5)) - (3 \times 1) \\15478 &:= (1 - 3!!) - ((579 - (7^5)) + 31) \\15479 &:= ((1 \times (3!! \times (5 + 7))) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5!) - 3!!)) - 1 \\15480 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5!) - (7! / (9 \times 7)))) \times (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \\15481 &:= 13 + ((5 + (7 - 9)) \times ((7! + (5! - 3)) - 1)) \\15482 &:= ((1 + 35) \times ((79 + 7) \times 5)) + (3 - 1) \\15483 &:= ((1 + 35) \times ((79 + 7) \times 5)) + (3 \times 1) \\15484 &:= (1 + 3) + (5! \times (((7 \times 9) / 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!))) \\15485 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + 9) - ((7 \times 5) - 31) \\15486 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) - 7) - ((9 + 7) - ((5^{3!} \times 1)) \\15487 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + (7 + 97)) + ((5^{3!} \times 1) \\15488 &:= (135 - 7) \times (((9 + 7) - 5)^{3-1}) \\15489 &:= (((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times 9) \times 7) + (53 + 1) \\15490 &:= (1^{357} + 9) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15491 &:= (((((1 \times 3) - 5!) - 7)^{9-7}) + 5!) - (3! - 1)\end{aligned}$$

- 15492** := $(1 + (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + ((9 \times 7) - (53 - 1))$
15493 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + 9 + ((7 \times 5) - 31)$
15494 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) + 97 \times ((5! + 3) - 1)$
15495 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7 \times 9) / 7) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
15496 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + (9 + 7) + (5 - (3! - 1))$
15497 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + (9 + 7) + (5! / ((3! - 1)!))$
15498 := $(1 - ((3 + 5) \times 7)) + ((9 \times ((7 + 5)^3)) + 1)$
15499 := $((1 + 3) - 5!) + 7 - (((9 + 7) - (5^{3!})) + 1)$
15500 := $((1 + 3) - 5!) + 7 - ((9 + 7) - ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
15501 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) + 9 + ((7 + 5) \times 31)$
15502 := $((1 \times 3) - 5!) - 7 + (9 - 7) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
15503 := $(1 \times 3!) - 5! + ((7 - ((9 + 7) - (5^{3!}))) + 1)$
15504 := $(1 + 3) \times 57 \times (9 + (7 + (53 - 1)))$
15505 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) + ((7 - 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1))$
15506 := $(1 - ((3 + 5) \times 7)) - (9 \times 7) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
15507 := $(1 - 3 \times 5) - ((7 + 97) - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
15508 := $(1 - 3) - (5! - 7) - ((9 - 7) - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
15509 := $(1^3 - (5 + (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15510 := $((1 - 3)^5 \times 7 \times 9) + (((7^5) + 3!!) - 1)$
15511 := $((1 - 3)^5 \times 7 \times 9) + (((7^5) + 3!!) \times 1)$
15512 := $((1 - 3)^5 \times 7 \times 9) + ((7^5) + (3!! + 1))$
15513 := $(1 + ((3!)^5 + 7) \times (9 - 7)) - (53 + 1)$
15514 := $((1 + 3!) - 579) + (7^5) - (3!! + 1)$
15515 := $((1 + 3!) - 579) + (7^5) - (3!! \times 1)$
15516 := $(1 \times 3!)^5 + (7! + ((9 \times 75) \times (3 + 1)))$
15517 := $(1 \times 3) - (5! + 7) + (((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) \times 1)$
15518 := $(1 + 3) - ((5! + (7 - (9 + 7))) - ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
15519 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 + (7 + 97))) + (5^{3!}) \times 1$
15520 := $(1 + 3) \times (5 - 7) - (97 - ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
15521 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5) - 7 - ((97 - (5^{3!})) + 1)$
15522 := $(1 + 3) + 5 - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
15523 := $(1^{35}) - ((7 + 97) - ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
15524 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + (7 - 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
15525 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) + 7 \times ((5! - 3!) + 1)$
15526 := $(1^3 + 5) - 7 - ((97 - (5^{3!})) + 1)$
15527 := $(1^3 + 5) - 7 \times ((97 - (5^{3!})) + 1)$
15528 := $((13 + 5) + ((7! - 9) + (7 + 5!))) \times (3 \times 1)$
15529 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) + (79 + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) - 1))$
15530 := $(1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
15531 := $1 - (((3! \times 5) - 79) - (((7! + 5!) \times 3) + 1))$
15532 := $((1 \times 3) - 5!) + (7 + ((9 + 7) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)))$
15533 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
15534 := $((1 + 3) - 5) + (((7 - 97) + (5^{3!})) \times 1)$
15535 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) - (7 + 5) + ((3! + 1)!)$
15536 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5) - ((7 + 97) - (5^{3! \times 1})))$
15537 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) - ((7 + 97) - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
15538 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + (7! + (9 + 7)))) + 5 + (3! - 1)$
15539 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) + 7 - ((9 \times 7) - ((5^{3!}) - 1))$
15540 := $(1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) \times (((9 + 7) + (5^3)) - 1)$
15541 := $(1 - (3! \times 5)) + 7 - ((9 \times 7) - ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
15542 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + 7) - 5!) \times 3) \times 1$
15543 := $(13 - (5 - 7)) - (97 - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
15544 := $((1 + 3) + 5) + (7 - 97) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
15545 := $(1^3) + ((5 - 79) - (7 - (5^{3! \times 1})))$
15546 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) - (((7! / 9) / 7) - ((5^{3!}) - 1))$
15547 := $(1^{35}) - (7 - ((9 \times ((7 + 5)^3)) + 1))$
15548 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5) \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15549 := $(1 + ((3 - 5) \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15550 := $1 \times (((3! \times 5) - 7) - 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
15551 := $1 + (((3! \times 5) - 7) - 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
15552 := $(1 + 35) \times (((79 + 7) \times 5) + 3) - 1$
15553 := $1 - (3 \times ((5 - 7) + (9 - (7 + (5! + 31))))))$
15554 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) - ((7 - (9 \times ((7 + 5)^3))) - 1)$
15555 := $((13 + 5!) \times 79) + ((7! + 5) + 3 \times 1)$
15556 := $((1 + (35 - (7 + 97))) + (5^{3!})) - 1$
15557 := $((1 + (35 - (7 + 97))) + (5^{3!})) \times 1$
15558 := $((1 + (35 - (7 + 97))) + (5^{3!})) + 1$
15559 := $((1^3 + (5 - 79)) + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15560 := $1^{35} \times (79 + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) + 1))$
15561 := $1^{35} + (79 + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) + 1))$
15562 := $1 + ((3 \times ((5! + 7!) - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) + 3 \times 1)$
15563 := $1 \times ((3 + (5 - 7)) - ((9 \times 7) - (5^{3! \times 1})))$
15564 := $1 + ((3 + (5 - 7)) - ((9 \times 7) - (5^{3! \times 1})))$
15565 := $(1 + (3 \times ((5! + 7!) - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) + 3! \times 1$

$$\begin{aligned} 15566 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) \times 7) + ((5^3) - 1) \\ 15567 &:= (1 + ((3 + 5) + 7)) + ((9 \times ((7 + 5)^3)) - 1) \\ 15568 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) \times 7) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 15569 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + 97)) - (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 15570 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) + 79) + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) - 1) \\ 15571 &:= ((13 + 5) - (79 - 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15572 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 57) - ((9 - 7) - (5^{3 \times 1})) \\ 15573 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times 5!) + (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - (5 + 31)) \\ 15574 &:= ((1 + (3! - 57)) - (9 - 7)) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 15575 &:= ((1^3) + 5) - (((7 \times 9) - 7) - ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 15576 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5)!) + (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5^3)) + 1) \\ 15577 &:= 1 - ((3 + (5! - 79)) \times ((7 - (5! \times 3)) - 1)) \\ 15578 &:= 1 - (((3! + 57) - (9 + 7)) - ((5^3) - 1)) \\ 15579 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - (9 + 7)) - (5 - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 15580 &:= ((1 + (3! - 5)) + (7 + 97)) \times ((5!/3!) - 1) \\ 15581 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5! - 79)) - 7) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 15582 &:= ((1 + 35) - 7) + ((9 \times ((7 + 5)^3)) + 1) \\ 15583 &:= ((135 \times 79) + 7!) - ((5! + 3) - 1) \\ 15584 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5! - 79) + (7 - ((5^3) + 1))) \\ 15585 &:= ((1^3) + (57 - 97)) + ((5^3) - 1) \\ 15586 &:= ((1^3) + (57 - 97)) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 15587 &:= (1 + ((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + 97)) + (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 15588 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + ((9 - 7) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 15589 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((79 + ((7! + 5!) \times 3)) - 1) \\ 15590 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((79 + ((7! + 5!) \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 15591 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) - (7 + (((9 \times 7) - (5^3)) - 1)) \\ 15592 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5 - 7) + (975 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 15593 &:= ((1 + ((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + (9 + 7))) + 5!) - (3 + 1)! \\ 15594 &:= (((1 + (3! - 5)) \times 79) + 7!) \times (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 15595 &:= (1 - 3) - (((5 + 7) + 9) + 7) - (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15596 &:= 1 + 35 + (7 + ((9 \times ((7 + 5)^3)) + 1)) \\ 15597 &:= 13 - (57 - (9 + (7 + ((5^3) \times 1)))) \\ 15598 &:= (1 \times (3 - (5! + 7))) + (97 + (5^{3 \times 1})) \\ 15599 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5!) - (((7 - 97) - (5^3)) \times 1) \\ 15600 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5!) - (((7 - 97) - (5^3)) - 1) \\ 15601 &:= ((1 - 3!)^{(5+7-9)!}) - ((75/3) - 1) \\ 15602 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) + (7 - 9)) - (7 - ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 15603 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 + (7! - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3! \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15604 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5! \times ((7 - 97) - (5!/3))) \times 1) \\ 15605 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 + (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15606 &:= ((1 - 3) \times ((5 + (7 - 9)) + 7)) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 15607 &:= 1 - ((3! - 57) \times ((97 + 5) \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 15608 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5) \times 7)) + ((9 \times ((7 + 5)^3)) \times 1) \\ 15609 &:= ((1 - 3) - ((5 - 7) + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15610 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5! - 79) + 7!) + 5!) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 15611 &:= (((1 + 3) - 57) \times 9) + ((7^5) - (3! - 1)) \\ 15612 &:= (((1 - 3)^5 \times 7) / (9 + 7)) + ((5^3) + 1) \\ 15613 &:= (1 + 3) - (5! - ((7 + (97 + (5^3))) \times 1)) \\ 15614 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5! - (7 + (97 + (5^3)))) + 1) \\ 15615 &:= ((1 + (35 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\ 15616 &:= 1 + (3 \times ((5 + 7 + 9) + (7! + (5! + (3 + 1)!))) \\ 15617 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) - 7) + (9 - 7)) + ((5^3) - 1) \\ 15618 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5) - 7) + (9 - 7)) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 15619 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 + (7 - (9 - 7))) - (5^{3 \times 1})) \\ 15620 &:= (((1^3) \times (5 + (7 - (9 + 7)))) + (5^3)) - 1 \\ 15621 &:= (((1^3) \times (5 + (7 - (9 + 7)))) + (5^3)) \times 1 \\ 15622 &:= (13 - 5!) \times (((7 + 9) - 7) - (5 \times 31)) \\ 15623 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 - (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15624 &:= (1 + (35 - (7 - 97))) \times ((5^3) - 1) \\ 15625 &:= (1 \times 3 - 5 + 7)^{9 \times (7-5)/3 \times 1} \\ 15626 &:= 1^{35797} + 5^3 \times 1 \\ 15627 &:= (1 + ((35 - (7 - 97)) \times (5^3))) + 1 \\ 15628 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5))^{7!}) + ((9 - 7) + (5^{3 \times 1})) \\ 15629 &:= (((1^3 \times 5)^{7-9+7}) \times 5) + (3 + 1) \\ 15630 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5! \times 7))) + (9 + 75)) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 15631 &:= ((1^{35}) + (7 - (9 - 7))) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15632 &:= (((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7) + (9 - 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15633 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 + (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15634 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (((5! + 7!) - (9 - 7)) + 53)) + 1 \\ 15635 &:= (((((1 - 3!)/5) \times 7) + (9 + 7)) + (5^3)) + 1 \\ 15636 &:= (((1 - 35) + (7!/(9 - 7))) + 5!) \times (3! \times 1) \\ 15637 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + 97)) + (5!/(3 - 1)) \\ 15638 &:= 13 + 5^{79-75+3-1} \\ 15639 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 + (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 15640 &:= (1 + (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + 7)) \times ((5! - 3!) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 15641** := $(1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}))$
15642 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7 + 9 + 7) + ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
15643 := $(1 - (3! - 5!)) + ((7! + ((9 + 7) + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1))$
15644 := $((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times 7)) - 9) - (7 - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
15645 := $((13 + (5! + (7 + 9))) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1)$
15646 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5) + (7 - (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15647 := $(((((1^{3!}) - 5) + 7))! + (9 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15648 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times ((975/3) + 1)$
15649 := $((1 - 3!)^{(5+7-9)!}) + ((75/3) - 1)$
15650 := $((1 - 3!)^{(5+7-9)!}) + ((75/3) \times 1)$
15651 := $(135 \times 79) + ((7! - 53) - 1)$
15652 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) \times ((79 + 7) \times (5 - 31))$
15653 := $((1^{3!}) \times ((5 + 7) + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15654 := $((1^{3!}) + (5 + 7)) + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) \times 1$
15655 := $((1^{3!}) + (5 + 7)) + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) + 1$
15656 := $(13 - 5) \times (7 + (975 \times (3 - 1)))$
15657 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 79) + (7! - (5 \times (3 + 1))))$
15658 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) + (7 + 9))) + ((7 + (5^{3!})) + 1)$
15659 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + (9 \times 7))) - (5 \times (3 - 1))$
15660 := $1 \times 3! + ((5! + 7) - (97 - ((5^{3!}) - 1)))$
15661 := $1 + ((3 \times (5! + (7! + (9 \times 7)))) - (5 + 3 + 1))$
15662 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! - 79)) - (7 - (5^{3!}))) \times 1$
15663 := $(1 - 3)^{5-(7-9) \times 7-5} - 3!! - 1$
15664 := $(1 - 3)^{5-(7-9) \times 7-5} - 3!! \times 1$
15665 := $(1 - 3)^{5-(7-9) \times 7-5} - 3!! + 1$
15666 := $((13 \times 5) - (7 + 9)) - ((7 - (5^{3!})) + 1)$
15667 := $1 \times (((3 - 57) + 97) + (5^{3!})) - 1$
15668 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + (9 - 7) + 531$
15669 := $((((1 + 3) + 57) - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3!})) - 1$
15670 := $((((1 + 3) + 57) - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3!})) \times 1$
15671 := $((((1 + 3) + 57) - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3!})) + 1$
15672 := $((1 - 3) - 5) \times 7 + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1))$
15673 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5 - 79 + 7) + (5! \times 3!))) + 1$
15674 := $((1^3 \times (5! - (7 + (9 \times 7)))) + (5^{3!})) - 1$
15675 := $((1^3 \times (5! - (7 + (9 \times 7)))) + (5^{3!})) \times 1$
15676 := $((1^3 \times (5! - (7 + (9 \times 7)))) + (5^{3!})) + 1$
15677 := $(1^3 + (5! - (7 + (9 \times 7)))) + (5^{3!}) + 1$
15678 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + (9 \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1))))$
15679 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!) + 3!))) - 1$
15680 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!) + 3!))) \times 1$
15681 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!) + 3!))) + 1$
15682 := $(1 + ((35 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7)^5))) \times (3 - 1)$
15683 := $(1^3 \times ((5! + ((7! + (9 \times 7)) + 5)) \times 3)) - 1$
15684 := $((((1 + 3!))! + (5! - 7!)) / (9 - 7)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
15685 := $(1^3 \times ((5! + ((7! + (9 \times 7)) + 5)) \times 3)) + 1$
15686 := $(13 - (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 - 7) + 5) - ((3! \times 1)!))$
15687 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 + (97 + 5!)) \times (3! - 1))$
15688 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + ((7 \times 9) + 7) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
15689 := $((1^3 \times 5!) + (7 - (9 \times 7))) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
15690 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 \times 7) - (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1)))$
15691 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7!/9) \times (7 - 5)) - (3 + 1))$
15692 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + (7 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5))) \times (3 - 1)$
15693 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7!/9) \times (7 - 5)) - 3! \times 1)$
15694 := $((13 + 57) - (9 - 7)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)$
15695 := $((1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + 97) + (5! - (3 - 1))$
15696 := $13 + (((57 + 9 - 7) + (5^{3!})) - 1)$
15697 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) \times ((7 + 9) - 7)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
15698 := $(1 - 3) + ((5 + 7) + ((9 \times 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})))$
15699 := $(13 + (5 + ((7 \times 9) - 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15700 := $1 - ((3 \times (5 - 7!)) - (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 31)))$
15701 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) \times (97 - 5) - 31$
15702 := $(1 - 3!)^{(5+7-9)!} + 75 + 3 - 1$
15703 := $(1 - 3!)^{(5+7-9)!} + 75 + 3 \times 1$
15704 := $(1 - 3!)^{(5+7-9)!} + 75 + 3 + 1$
15705 := $((1 + 3)^5) + (7 + 9 + 7) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
15706 := $(1 + (3! + 579)) + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
15707 := $((1 - 3) - 5) - 7 + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1))$
15708 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! - (9 + (7 \times 5)))) + 3!! \times 1$
15709 := $13 + ((579 + 75) \times (3 + 1)!)$
15710 := $(135 - (7^9-7)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
15711 := $((13 + (57 + 9)) + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
15712 := $1 \times ((3 - (5 + 7)) + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1)))$
15713 := $(1 + (3 - (5 + 7))) + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1))$
15714 := $(1 - 3) \times (5! - (7975 + 3 - 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}15715 &:= (((((1 \times 3)! - 5) - 7) + 97) + (5^{3!})) - 1 \\15716 &:= (((((1 \times 3)! - 5) - 7) + 97) + (5^{3!})) \times 1 \\15717 &:= (1 \times 3 + (579 - 75)) \times 31 \\15718 &:= 13 - ((5 - 79) - (7 + ((5^{3!}) - 1))) \\15719 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) + (((79 + (7! + 5!)) \times 3) \times 1) \\15720 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 - 9)) - ((7 \times 5) \times 31) \\15721 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) + (7 + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1))) \\15722 &:= ((1^{357}) \times 97) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15723 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) - (7 - 97)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\15724 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 - 9)) - ((7 \times 5) \times 31) \\15725 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) - (7 - 97)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\15726 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times (5! + (7! + ((9 + 7) \times 5)))) + (3! \times 1)) \\15727 &:= 1 \times 3! + (5 - (((7 - 97) - (5^{3!})) - 1)) \\15728 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 5!)) - (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15729 &:= (1 + (3! + 5!)) - ((7 + (9 + 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15730 &:= (1 + (3! + 5!)) - ((7 + ((9 + 7) - (5^{3!}))) - 1) \\15731 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) + 7) + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1)) \\15732 &:= (13 - (5! + 7)) \times ((97 - 5!) \times (3! \times 1)) \\15733 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) - ((97 - 5) - (3!! - 1)) \\15734 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5+7}) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3 - 1)) \\15735 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + ((97 - 5) - (3! + 1))) \\15736 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 + 7) + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1))) \\15737 &:= (13 - (5 - 7)) + (97 + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15738 &:= 1 \times (3 \times ((5! + 7!) + ((9 + 75) + 3 - 1))) \\15739 &:= 1 + (3 \times ((5! + 7!) + ((9 + 75) + 3 - 1))) \\15740 &:= (1 \times (3! + (5 + 7))) + (97 + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15741 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7! - (9 \times (7 - (5! / (3 + 1)))))) \\15742 &:= (((1 + 3!))! + (5! - 7!)) - ((9 - 7) - ((5^{3!}) - 1)) \\15743 &:= (((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7))! - ((9 - 7) - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15744 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + ((7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15745 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times 5) - 7) + 97) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\15746 &:= (1 + (((3! \times 5) - 7) + 97)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\15747 &:= ((1 + 3)! - 5) + ((7 + 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)) \\15748 &:= (((((1 + 3) \times 5) + 7) + 97) + (5^{3!})) - 1 \\15749 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 + (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15750 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) - (9 - (7 \times (5! - 31))) \\15751 &:= ((13 + (57 \times (9 - 7))) + (5^{3!})) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15752 &:= (((((1 + 3!) + (5 + (79 + 7!))) + 5!) \times 3) - 1 \\15753 &:= (((((1 + 3!) + (5 + (79 + 7!))) + 5!) \times 3) \times 1 \\15754 &:= (((((1 + 3!) + (5 + (79 + 7!))) + 5!) \times 3) + 1 \\15755 &:= (1 + (3 - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15756 &:= ((1 - ((35 \times (7 - 97)) \times 5)) + 3!) - 1 \\15757 &:= ((135 \times 79) + (7! + 53)) - 1 \\15758 &:= ((1 + 3!))! + (((5! + (79 + 7!)) + 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\15759 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! + (79 + 7!)) + ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\15760 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15761 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15762 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) - (((7 - 9)^7) - ((5^{3!}) \times 1)) \\15763 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 57) \times (97 - 5)) + 31 \\15764 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - 31 \\15765 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7! + (97 + (5! - (3 - 1)))) \\15766 &:= (((1 - 3) - (5! - 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) - 3!) \times 1 \\15767 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times ((5! + 7) + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})))) - 1 \\15768 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5) + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) + (5^{3!})) + 1) \\15769 &:= (135 - 7) + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15770 &:= (1 \times (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 3)) - 1 \\15771 &:= (1 \times (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 3)) \times 1 \\15772 &:= (1 \times (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 3)) + 1 \\15773 &:= 1 + (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 - (7 \times 5))) \times 3) + 1) \\15774 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5!) + (7 + (9 + 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15775 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times 5) + ((7 - (9 - 7))^5))) \times (3! - 1) \\15776 &:= (((1 - 3!) - (5! - 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 31) \\15777 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! - (((5 \times 7) - (9 + 7!)) - 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\15778 &:= (1 - (((3 - 57) - 97) - (5^{3!}))) + 1 \\15779 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (((7! / (9 - 7)) / 5) + (3! - 1)) \\15780 &:= (1 + (3^5 + 7)) - (97 - ((5^{3!}) + 1)) \\15781 &:= 1 - ((((((3^5) - 7!) / 9) + 7) \times (5 \times 3!)) \times 1) \\15782 &:= ((1 - (3^5 + (7 \times 9))) + (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1))! \\15783 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! + 7!) + (97 + 5)) \times 3) - 1) \\15784 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5) \times 7) + 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\15785 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 797) - (5 \times 31) \\15786 &:= (1 \times 3!!) - ((5 \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) - ((5^{3!}) + 1)) \\15787 &:= (1 + 3!!) + (5! - (((7 \times 9) - 7!) - 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15788 &:= (((1 \times 3!))! - 5!) + (((7! - 97) + 5!) \times 3) - 1) \\15789 &:= (((1^{3!}) \times 5!) \times 7) - 9) \times ((7 + 5) + (3! + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15790 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + ((9 \times 75) - (3! - 1)) \\15791 &:= ((1 + 3!) - ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1) \\15792 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7) \times 9)) \times (753 - 1) \\15793 &:= 13 - ((5! - (7! - 975)) \times (3 + 1)) \\15794 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 + 9 + (7^{5-3}))) - 1 \\15795 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 + 9 + (7^{5-3}))) \times 1 \\15796 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 + 9 + (7^{5-3}))) + 1 \\15797 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) - (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\15798 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times 79) + (7! + ((5 + 3!) \times 1)) \\15799 &:= ((13 - 5) \times ((79 \times 75)/3)) - 1 \\15800 &:= (((1 + 3!)/5) + ((7! + 9753) - 1)) \\15801 &:= (((1 + 3!)/5) + ((7! + 9753) \times 1)) \\15802 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) \times 97) - (5 - ((3! + 1)!)) \\15803 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5) + 3!)) + 1 \\15804 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) + ((7 \times 97) + (5^{3-1})) \\15805 &:= (((1 \times 3!)/5) - 5) + (((7!/(9 - 7)) - 5) \times 3!) \times 1 \\15806 &:= (((1 \times 3!)/5) - 5) + (((7!/(9 - 7)) - 5) \times 3!) + 1 \\15807 &:= (1 \times ((3! - 57) \times 9)) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\15808 &:= (1 + ((3! - 57) \times 9)) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\15809 &:= ((1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9 + 7))) + (5^{3!})) - 1 \\15810 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (((7!/(9 - 7))/5) + (3! \times 1)) \\15811 &:= (1 + (3! \times ((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) - 5))) - 3!! \times 1 \\15812 &:= (((1 \times 3!)/5) + 57) + ((97 \times 5) \times 31) \\15813 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5 + (7 - 9)) \times (753 \times 1)) \\15814 &:= 1 - (3 - ((5! + ((79 - 7) + (5^{3!}))) - 1)) \\15815 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - ((5! + 3!) - 1) \\15816 &:= ((1 - 3!) - ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 31) \\15817 &:= 1 - ((3! - ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)!) \\15818 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5^3)) - 1) \\15819 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + ((79 - 7) + (5^{3!}))) - 1) \\15820 &:= (((1 - 3 \times 5) \times ((7 - 9) \times 7)) + (5^{3!})) - 1 \\15821 &:= (135 \times 79) + (((7! + 5!) - 3) - 1) \\15822 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) \times ((7 - 9) \times 7)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\15823 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5! + (7! - 9)) - (7 - 5!))) + 31 \\15824 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) + (7!/(9 + 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15825 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - ((5! - 3!) + 1) \\15826 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - ((5! - 3!) \times 1) \\15827 &:= (1 + (3! - 5!)) + (797 \times (5!/(3! \times 1)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15828 &:= ((135 \times 79) + 7!) + ((5! + 3) \times 1) \\15829 &:= 1 - (((3! \times 5) \times (7 - 9)) - ((7 + 5) \times (3! - 1))) \\15830 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5! + ((7!/(9 + 7)) - (5 \times 3!))) - 1) \\15831 &:= (135 + (79 - 7)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\15832 &:= (135 + (79 - 7)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\15833 &:= (135 + (79 - 7)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\15834 &:= (1^3 + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times 5!)) - (3! + 1) \\15835 &:= 1 - (((3 + (5 + 79)) \times 7) \times (5 - 31)) \\15836 &:= (1^3 + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times 5!)) - (3! - 1) \\15837 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 - ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\15838 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 + 7) + 9) \times (753 + 1)) \\15839 &:= ((1 + 3!)/5) + (((57 - 9) \times (75 \times 3)) - 1) \\15840 &:= ((1 \times 3!)/5) \times (((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!) - ((3! - 1)!)) \\15841 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (((7!/(9 - 7))/5) + (3! + 1)) \\15842 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - 9) + (7 \times (53 \times 1)) \\15843 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5 - 7) \times (9 - 75)) \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\15844 &:= (1 + 3) - ((5 - 797) \times (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\15845 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5!) + (7 - 9)) + (7^5) - 3!! \times 1 \\15846 &:= (1^3 + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\15847 &:= (1^3 + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times 5!)) + (3! \times 1) \\15848 &:= (1^3 + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times 5!)) + (3! + 1) \\15849 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! - 7) \times (9 - 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15850 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\15851 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5) \times 7) + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15852 &:= 13 + (((5! \times (79 - (7 \times 5))) \times 3) - 1) \\15853 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5!) + ((7 + (97 + (5^{3!}))) \times 1) \\15854 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) + ((97 + (5^{3!}) + 1)) \\15855 &:= (((1 - 3!) - ((5 - 7) - 9))!) + ((7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15856 &:= (135 \times 79) + (7! + (5! + 31)) \\15857 &:= (13 + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1) \\15858 &:= (((1 - 35) \times 7) + (9 + (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\15859 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) - ((7 \times 9)/7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15860 &:= (((1 \times 3!)/5) + (57 + 9)) + 7 \times (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\15861 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) + 7) \times 9 + (((7^5) - 3!) - 1) \\15862 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) + 7) \times 9 + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1)) \\15863 &:= ((1 \times 3!)/5) + (((5 + ((7! - 9) + 7)) + 5) \times 3) - 1 \\15864 &:= (((1 + 3!)/5) + (5! - 7!)) \times (9 - 7) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\15865 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5 + (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1})\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15866 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (5 + ((7! + (9 - (7 - 5))) \times (3 \times 1))) \\15867 &:= (1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) \times ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1)) \\15868 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! + 5!) - (7 - ((97 \times 5) \times 31)) \\15869 &:= (((13 + 5) \times 7)^{9-7}) - ((5 + 3) - 1) \\15870 &:= (1 \times (3!!/5!)) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5! - (3! - 1))) \\15871 &:= (((((1 - 3)^5) \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) - (3!! + 1) \\15872 &:= (((((1 - 3)^5) \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) - (3!! \times 1) \\15873 &:= (((((1 - 3)^5) \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) - (3!! - 1) \\15874 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5! + (7 + (9 - 7))) \times (5! + 3))) + 1 \\15875 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5!) - ((7 - 9) - 7)) \times (5^3 \times 1) \\15876 &:= ((1 - (3! - 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) \times (5 + 31) \\15877 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + (((7 \times 9)/7) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15878 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + ((7 + 97) \times (5 \times 31)) \\15879 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! + (79 + 7!)) + (53 + 1)) \\15880 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - (7 + (97 - ((5^3!) - 1))) \\15881 &:= (1 \times (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times 3) - 1 \\15882 &:= (1 \times (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times 3) \times 1 \\15883 &:= (1 \times (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times 3) + 1 \\15884 &:= (1 + (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 + 7)) - 5) \times 3) + 1 \\15885 &:= (1 \times ((3 - 57) + 9)) \times (7 - ((5! \times 3) \times 1)) \\15886 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 79) \times ((7!/(5 \times 3!)) + 1) \\15887 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! + (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7! - 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15888 &:= (1 + 3!) + (5 + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 + 31))) \\15889 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((5 + 7!) + ((9 + 7) - 5)))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\15890 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times ((7!/9) - (75 + 31)) \\15891 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((5! + 79) - (7^5))) - (3!! + 1) \\15892 &:= (1 + (3 - 5!)) \times (((7 - 9) \times 7) - (5! + 3 \times 1)) \\15893 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + ((7! + (97 + 5!)) \times 3)) - 1 \\15894 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! + ((5 \times (7 - 97)) + ((5^3!) - 1)) \\15895 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) + ((7! + (97 + 5!)) \times 3)) + 1 \\15896 &:= (((1 \times 3! + 57) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5) \times (3 + 1) \\15897 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\15898 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times 5) \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) + ((5^3!) \times 1) \\15899 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5!)) \times (((7 - 9) + 7) + 5!)) + (3 + 1)! \\15900 &:= 1 + (((3! \times 5) \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) + ((5^3!) + 1) \\15901 &:= 13 + (((5! + (7! + (9 + 7))) + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15902 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) - ((7 \times 9) - ((7^5) - (3! \times 1)!!)) \\15903 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times ((5! + 7) \times 9) - 7)) \times (5 - 3)) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15904 &:= 13579 + (75 \times 31) \\15905 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (((5! + 7) \times 9) - 7)) \times (5 - 3)) + 1 \\15906 &:= (1 - 35) + (797 \times (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\15907 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5 + 7) - (9 \times 75)) \times (3 + 1)!) \\15908 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7! + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\15909 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5!) - (7 \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!!) - 1) \\15910 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((57 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\15911 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - (5 + (3 + 1)!) \\15912 &:= (((1^3 + (5 \times 79)) \times 7) - 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\15913 &:= (1 + 3!) - (((5 \times (7 - (9 \times 7))) - (5^3!)) - 1) \\15914 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! \times (5 + 7 + 9)) + (75 + (3!! - 1)) \\15915 &:= (1 + (((3^5 + 7!) + (9 + 7)) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\15916 &:= (1 - 35) + (7975 \times (3 - 1)) \\15917 &:= 1 - (((3 \times (5 - 7!)) - (97 - 5)) - 3!!) + 1 \\15918 &:= 1 - (((3 \times (5 - 7!)) - (97 - 5)) - 3!!) \times 1 \\15919 &:= ((1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) + (97 - 5)) + (3!! + 1) \\15920 &:= ((1 + (3 - (5 - 797))) \times 5) \times (3 + 1) \\15921 &:= 1 - (((3! + 5!) \times 7) + ((9 - (7^5)) - (3 + 1))) \\15922 &:= 1 - ((3! - (5 \times 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) + 5!) \times 3) \times 1) \\15923 &:= (1 + (3 + ((5! + 7) \times 97))) + ((5 \times 3!) \times 1) \\15924 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((7!/9) \times (7 + ((5!/3!) + 1))) \\15925 &:= 13 \times (5 \times 7)^{97 \times 5 / (3! - 1)} \\15926 &:= (1 \times 3! \times ((5! - 7) - (9 \times 7))) + ((5^3!) + 1) \\15927 &:= ((1 - (3! \times 5!)) + (7!/9)) + ((7^5) - (3!! + 1)) \\15928 &:= (((1 - 3!)/5) + (7 + (9 + 7))) \times ((5 + 3!!) - 1) \\15929 &:= ((1 + ((3^5 + 7!) - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times 3) - 1 \\15930 &:= (((1 + 3!!) + 5!) - (7! \times (9 - (7 + 5)))) - 31 \\15931 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times (5 \times 7)) + (97 + ((5^3!) - 1)) \\15932 &:= (1 + (3! \times ((5 \times 7) + (9 + 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\15933 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - (5 + 3)) + 1 \\15934 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times 9) - (7 \times 5) \times 31 \\15935 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!) \times (7 + 9)) + 7! - (5^{3+1}) \\15936 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5) \times (797 + 531) \\15937 &:= (((1 + 3^5) + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + ((5! + 3) + 1) \\15938 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) + 9) + ((7 \times 5!) - 31) \\15939 &:= (1 + 3^5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\15940 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5) + (7975 \times (3 - 1)) \\15941 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + ((97 \times 5) - (3 + 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15942 &:= (1 \times (3!! - (5! - 7!))) - (((9 - 7!) - 5!) \times (3 - 1)) & 15973 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times 97)) - (5 \times 31) \\
 15943 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) + (9 + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) - 1)) & 15974 &:= (((1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + 7) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\
 15944 &:= (1 \times 3!!) - (((5 \times 79) + 7) - ((5^{3!}) + 1)) & 15975 &:= (((1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + 7) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\
 15945 &:= (1 - 3!) - (((5! + 7) + (9 - (7^5))) + (3!! + 1)) & 15976 &:= (13 - ((5! + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 - (3! + 1)) \\
 15946 &:= (1 - 3!!) - ((5! + ((7 + 9) - (7^5))) + 3! \times 1) & 15977 &:= (1 - (((((3 - 5) + 7)! - 9) - (7^5))) - 3!! \times 1) \\
 15947 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + 5) + (3 - 1) & 15978 &:= (((1 + ((3 + 5!) - 7)) + 9) \times (7 + 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\
 15948 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + 5) + (3 \times 1) & 15979 &:= (1 + (3!! + 5!)) \times (79 - 7 - (53 \times 1)) \\
 15949 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + 5) + (3 + 1) & 15980 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (5! - ((7 + (9 + ((7^5) - 3))) - 1)) \\
 15950 &:= ((1 - 3) - (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) \times (5 \times (3! - 1)) & 15981 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 \times ((797 + 5) - 3))) + 1 \\
 15951 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 57) - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) & 15982 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) \times ((7 - 9) - ((7 + 5!) + 3 - 1)) \\
 15952 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 7975)) \times (3 - 1) & 15983 &:= ((13 - (5! \times 7)) + (9 + ((7^5) - 3!))) \times 1 \\
 15953 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) + (7975 \times (3 - 1)) & 15984 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (5! \times (7 + 9 + 7))) - 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\
 15954 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! / 5) + ((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5)) \times (3! \times 1) & 15985 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((7 \times 97) + 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\
 15955 &:= 1 - ((3 - 5) \times (7975 + 3 - 1)) & 15986 &:= ((1 + 357) + 9) - (7 - ((5^{3!}) + 1)) \\
 15956 &:= (1^3) - ((5! \times 7) + (9 - (((7^5) - 3) \times 1))) & 15987 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + (((5 \times 7) + ((9 + 7!) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 15957 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (5! \times 7)) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3 + 1)) & 15988 &:= ((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + 9) + ((7! - 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\
 15958 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times 797) + 5) \times (3 + 1)) & 15989 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 57) \times 9) - (7^5)) - (3!! \times 1) \\
 15959 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) - 5) + (3 + 1)! & 15990 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! + 7)) \times (97 - (5 - 31)) \\
 15960 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((797 + 5) - 3) - 1)) & 15991 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) - (7 \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!!) - 1) \\
 15961 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (((5 + 7!) + (97 \times 5!)) - (3! - 1)) & 15992 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - ((7 \times 9) - ((7^5) - (3!! \times 1))) \\
 15962 &:= ((1 - 357) + 9) \times ((7 - 53) \times 1) & 15993 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - ((7 \times 9) - (((7^5) - 3!!) + 1)) \\
 15963 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - 5!) + ((7 - 9) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)) & 15994 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - (797 + ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\
 15964 &:= (1 - 3!!) - (5! - ((7 - (9 - ((7^5) - 3))) + 1)) & 15995 &:= 13 - (((5! \times 7) - 9) - (7^5)) - (3! \times 1) \\
 15965 &:= (((1 - 3) \times 5!) \times (7 - 9)) + (7 \times 5) \times 31 & 15996 &:= 13 - (((5! \times 7) - 9) - (7^5)) - (3! + 1) \\
 15966 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times (9 - 7))) + (5^{3!})) - 1 & 15997 &:= (((13 - 5!) + 7) + 9) + (7^5) - (3!! - 1) \\
 15967 &:= (1 + ((35 \times (7 \times 9)) \times 7)) + 531 & 15998 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5 \times (7 + (9 \times 7))) + (5^{3!})) - 1) \\
 15968 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 797) + (5 + 3)) - 1) & 15999 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7 \times (9 + 753)) - 1) \\
 15969 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + (((9 + 7) \times 53) + 1) & 16000 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((797 + 5) - 3) + 1)) \\
 15970 &:= (((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + 9) + (7! - 5)) + 3! \times 1 \\
 15971 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) - (7 \times (9 - 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\
 15972 &:= (1 + (3!! + 5)) \times ((7 + (9 \times 75)) / 31)
 \end{aligned}$$

2.9 Numbers From 16001 to 18000

$$\begin{aligned}
 16001 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5-7+9}) + ((7 + 5!)^{3-1}) & 16006 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) + (((79 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3) + 1) \\
 16002 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5! + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) - ((5^3) + 1)) & 16007 &:= (((((1 - 3) \times 5) \times 7) - 9) + (7^5)) - (3!! + 1) \\
 16003 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) - (7! / 9)) + (7^5)) - (3 - 1) & 16008 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5! + 7) + ((9 \times (7 + 53)) \times 1)) \\
 16004 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) + (((79 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3)) - 1 & 16009 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - ((9 - 7) - 531) \\
 16005 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) + (((79 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3)) \times 1 & 16010 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5 - 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) - (3!! \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 16011** := $((1 - 3 + (5 \times 79)) - 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
16012 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times (7 + 9) - ((7 \times 53) + 1)$
16013 := $(1^3 + 5) - (((79 - (7^5)) + 3!!) + 1)$
16014 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) + 7 - ((97 - (5^{3!})) + 1)$
16015 := $((13 - 5) - (79 - ((7^5) - 3!!))) - 1$
16016 := $((13 - 5) - (79 - (7^5))) - (3!! \times 1)$
16017 := $((13 - 5) - (79 - ((7^5) - 3!!))) + 1$
16018 := $((1 - (3!! - (5 - 79))) + ((7^5) + 3)) + 1$
16019 := $((135 + 79) \times 75) - 31$
16020 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) + 3 \times 1)$
16021 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (5 - (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!))$
16022 := $((1 - 3!)/5) - ((7 \times 9) - ((7^5) - (3!! + 1)))$
16023 := $((1 + 3) - 5) - ((7 \times 9) - ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!)))$
16024 := $((1 + 3) - 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!)))$
16025 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 \times 79) + 7) + (5^{3!}) \times 1)$
16026 := $((1 + 3) - 57) - 9 + ((7^5) - (3!! - 1))$
16027 := $((13 + 579) - 75) \times 31$
16028 := $(13 + ((5! + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
16029 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) - 531$
16030 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times ((5^3) \times 1))$
16031 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times (7 \times 9)) + 7 - (5 - 3!! \times 1)$
16032 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 + 797) \times 5) - (3 - 1))$
16033 := $(1 - 3!) - (((57 - (9 + (7^5))) + 3!!) + 1)$
16034 := $(1 - 3!) - (((57 - (9 + (7^5))) + 3!!) \times 1)$
16035 := $((1 \times 3! + 5) - ((7 \times 9) - (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)!)$
16036 := $((1 - 3!!) \times 5) + ((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5)) + 31$
16037 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 + 9) + 7!)) + (5! \times 3!) - 1$
16038 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 + 9) + 7!)) + (5! \times 3!) \times 1$
16039 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 + 9) + 7!)) + (5! \times 3!) + 1$
16040 := $((1 - 3!!) - (((5 \times 7) + 9) - (7^5))) - (3 + 1)$
16041 := $((1 - 3) - ((5 \times 7) + (9 - (7^5)))) - (3!! \times 1)$
16042 := $(1^3 \times 5) + ((79 \times 7) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
16043 := $((1 + (3 - (57 - 9))) + (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)$
16044 := $((1 + 3) - 57) + (9 + ((7^5) - (3!! - 1)))$
16045 := $((1 \times 3!) - (57 - (9 + (7^5)))) - (3!! \times 1)$
16046 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5 + 797) \times (5 \times (3 + 1)))$
16047 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times 9) + (7! - ((5 - (3 - 1))))!)$
16048 := $((1 - 3!!) - (((5 \times 7) + 9) - (7^5))) + (3 + 1)$
16049 := $((1^3 + 5) \times (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - 3!!)) - 1$
16050 := $((1^3 + 5) \times (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - 3!!)) \times 1$
16051 := $((1^3 + 5) \times (((7 \times 97) \times 5) - 3!!)) + 1$
16052 := $((1 + 3)^5) - 7 + (97 \times (5 \times 31))$
16053 := $((1 - 3)^5) + 7 - (9 - ((7^5) - (3!! \times 1)))$
16054 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + ((5! - 3!) \times 1)$
16055 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + ((5! - 3!) + 1)$
16056 := $((1 - 3)^5) - (7 - ((9 + ((7^5) - 3!!)) - 1))$
16057 := $((1 + 3) \times 579) \times 7 - (5 \times 31)$
16058 := $((1 - 3)^5) - 7 + 9 + (((7^5) - 3!!) + 1)$
16059 := $((1 - 3) - ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + (7^5) - (3!! \times 1)$
16060 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + (7 - (9 - (7^5))) - 3!! \times 1$
16061 := $((1 + 3!))! + (((5! + 7!) - 9) \times (7 - 5) + 3!!) - 1$
16062 := $((13 - 5!) \times 7) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3! - 1))$
16063 := $(1 - (3!! + (5 + 7))) - (9 - ((7^5) - 3)) + 1$
16064 := $((135 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7) + (5 \times 3))) - 1$
16065 := $(1 \times 357) \times ((97 - 53) + 1)$
16066 := $((135 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7) + (5 \times 3))) + 1$
16067 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 797)) + ((5! + 3!) + 1)$
16068 := $((1 - (3! \times 5!)) - (7 + (9 - (7^5)))) - (3 + 1)$
16069 := $((1 - 3!)/5) - 7 - ((9 - (7^5)) + 3!!) + 1$
16070 := $((1 - 3)^5) + 7 + 9 + (((7^5) - 3!!) - 1)$
16071 := $((1 - 3)^5) + 7 + (9 + ((7^5) - (3!! \times 1)))$
16072 := $((13 - 5) \times 7) \times ((9 \times ((7 \times 5) - 3)) - 1)$
16073 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) + (7! + ((97 - 5) \times ((3! - 1)!)))$
16074 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + (9 \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1)))))$
16075 := $(1 - 3!) + (5! \times ((7 + (9 - 7)) + (5^3 \times 1)))$
16076 := $((1 - 3!)/5)^7 - (9 - (7^5)) - (3!! + 1)$
16077 := $(13 \times (5 \times 7)) - (9 - (7 + (5^{3!}) - 1))$
16078 := $(1 \times ((3!! - (579 + 7)) \times 5!)) - (3 - 1)$
16079 := $(1 - 3!!) - (5 - ((7 - (9 - (7^5) - 3))) + 1)$
16080 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)$
16081 := $((135 + 79) \times 75) + 31$
16082 := $(1 \times ((3!! - (579 + 7)) \times 5!)) + (3 - 1)$
16083 := $1 \times (((3!! - (579 + 7)) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1)$
16084 := $1 + (((3!! - (579 + 7)) \times 5!) + 3 \times 1)$
16085 := $(1^3 - 5) - ((7 - (9 + (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
16086 := $(1 - (3!! - 5)) + (7! + ((97 \times 5!) + ((3! - 1)!)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 16087 &:= ((1 - 3!) - (5 - (7 - 9))) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 16088 &:= ((1^{3579}) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 16089 &:= (1 - (3! - 5)) + ((7 - (9 - ((7^5) - 3))) + 1) \\ 16090 &:= (1^3) \times (5 + ((7 - (9 - (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 16091 &:= (1^3) + (5 + ((7 - (9 - (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 16092 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (5! - (7 \times (9 - (75 \times (3! - 1)))) \\ 16093 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) + ((7 - (9 - (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 16094 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7 - (9 - (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 16095 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 797) + (5 \times 31) \\ 16096 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times (5! + (7 + 9))) + (7^5)) - 31 \\ 16097 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) - (7 - (9 + (7^5)))) - ((3! \times 1)! \\ 16098 &:= ((13 - 5!) \times 7) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 31) \\ 16099 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times 57) + ((9 - 7)^{5 \times 3 - 1}) \\ 16100 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((5 - 7) + (9 + (7^5)))) + (3! - 1) \\ 16101 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3!})) - 1) \\ 16102 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3!})) \times 1) \\ 16103 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3!})) + 1) \\ 16104 &:= (((1 - 3!) - ((5 - 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3!)) - 1 \\ 16105 &:= (1 - 3!) - (5 - ((7 + 9 + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 16106 &:= (1 - (3! \times (5! + (7 - 9)))) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 16107 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7 + (9 + ((7^5) - 3)))) + 1 \\ 16108 &:= ((1 + 35) - (7 + (9 - (7^5)))) - (3! - 1) \\ 16109 &:= (((1 + (3! - 5)) \times 7) + (9 + (7^5))) - 3! - 1 \\ 16110 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! \times 7)) - (9 \times 75)) \times (3! \times 1) \\ 16111 &:= (13 - (((5 - 7) - 9) - (7^5))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 16112 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) - (9 - ((7^5) - (3! - 1))) \\ 16113 &:= 1 - (((3! + 5) - (7! / (9 + 7))) \times 53) \times 1 \\ 16114 &:= 1 - (((3! + 5) - (7! / (9 + 7))) \times 53) - 1 \\ 16115 &:= 1 \times (35 + ((7 + 9) \times ((7! / 5) - (3 \times 1)))) \\ 16116 &:= (13 - ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + ((7 + 5!)^{3-1}) \\ 16117 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) + (7 \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) - 1) \\ 16118 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7) + ((9 + (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 16119 &:= (((13 + 5) + 7!) + (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 16120 &:= (((1 \times 3)! - (5! + 7)) - (97 - ((5^{3!}) - 1))) \\ 16121 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (5! + 7)) \times (97 + 5)) + (3! - 1) \\ 16122 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5 - ((7 + 97) \times (5 \times 31))) \\ 16123 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16124 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((797 - 5!) + 3! \times 1) \\ 16125 &:= (1 - (3! + 5!)) \times (7 - (97 + ((5! / 3) - 1))) \\ 16126 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5! + (7! / 9)) - (((7^5) - 3) - 1)) \\ 16127 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5! + (7! / 9))) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1) \\ 16128 &:= (135 - 7) \times (9 \times (7 + ((5 + 3) - 1))) \\ 16129 &:= (1 + (3 - 5!)) - ((7! / 9) - (((7^5) - 3) + 1)) \\ 16130 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) - 3!)) - 1 \\ 16131 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 16132 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5) + ((7 + 97) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 16133 &:= (13 - 5!) - ((7! / 9) \times ((7 - 5) - 31)) \\ 16134 &:= (1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)! \\ 16135 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)! \\ 16136 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1)) \\ 16137 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5!) - 7!)) - ((9 + 7) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1)) \\ 16138 &:= (13 + 5) + (((7 + 97) \times 5) \times 31) \\ 16139 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 16140 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5)) \times ((79 \times 7) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 16141 &:= (((1 \times 3)! + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (((7! - 5) \times 3) + 1) \\ 16142 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((57 - 9) + (7^5))) - ((3! \times 1)! \\ 16143 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) + ((7 \times 9) + ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 16144 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + (7! \times ((9 - 7) - ((5 - 3!) \times 1))) \\ 16145 &:= ((1 - (3! \times (5! - 7))) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 16146 &:= (1 \times (3 - 57)) + ((9 \times 75) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 16147 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((57 + 9) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1))) \\ 16148 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times (7 + 97))) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\ 16149 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) - ((7! \times ((9 - 7) - 5)) - (3! - 1)) \\ 16150 &:= (1^{35}) \times (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1) \\ 16151 &:= (1^{35}) + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1) \\ 16152 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 797) + 53) \times 1) \\ 16153 &:= (((1 + 3!) / 5) \times (7 + 9)) + (75 / (3 \times 1)) \\ 16154 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) + 5! - (3 \times 1) \\ 16155 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) + ((7 + 97) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 16156 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((579 - 7) + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 16157 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) + (79 + (7^5))) - (3! - 1) \\ 16158 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times (5! + (7 + 9))) + (7^5)) + 31 \\ 16159 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) + 5! + (3 - 1) \\ 16160 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) + 5! + (3 \times 1) \\ 16161 &:= 1 \times (3! + (5 + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16162 &:= 1 + (3! + (5 + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) - 3!! \times 1))) \\ 16163 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) \times (79 \times 7) + 5!) + 3! \times 1 \\ 16164 &:= (1 + 35) \times ((7 - 9) + ((75 \times 3!) + 1)) \\ 16165 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\ 16166 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 - ((7 - 9)^7)))) \times (5! - (3 - 1)) \\ 16167 &:= (((1 - 3!!) - 5) + (79 + (7^5))) + (3! - 1) \\ 16168 &:= (1 - 3) + (((57 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 \times (3! + 1))) \\ 16169 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 + 9) \times (7!/5)) + 3!) - 1 \\ 16170 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 + 9) \times (7!/5)) + 3!) \times 1 \\ 16171 &:= 1 + 35 + (((7 + 9) \times (7!/5)) + 3!) + 1 \\ 16172 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (79 + 75))) \times 3) - 1 \\ 16173 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7 \times 5!) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 16174 &:= ((1 + (35 \times (79 + 75))) \times 3) + 1 \\ 16175 &:= ((1 - 3!) \times (5! + 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 16176 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times (5! \times (3! - 1))) \\ 16177 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - (7!/(((9 + (7 - 5)) - 3) \times 1)) \\ 16178 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - 7) + ((97 - (5! \times 3!)) + 1) \\ 16179 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5!) + 7) \times (9 + (7 \times 5))) + 31 \\ 16180 &:= (((((1 - 3!) - 5) \times 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) + (3 \times 1) \\ 16181 &:= ((1 + 3!!) \times (5 + 7)) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5!) - 31) \\ 16182 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) + (79 \times 7)) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\ 16183 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times ((97 - 5) - 3))) - 1 \\ 16184 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times ((97 - 5) - 3))) \times 1 \\ 16185 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times ((97 - 5) - 3))) + 1 \\ 16186 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (579 \times 7)) + (5 - 31) \\ 16187 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5!) + ((7 \times 97) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 16188 &:= ((1 - 3 + ((5! + 7!)/(9 - 7))) + 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 16189 &:= (1 \times ((3! - 5!) + (7 \times 97))) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\ 16190 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5 \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\ 16191 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + ((9 - 7) - 5))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 16192 &:= ((1^3 \times (579 \times 7)) - 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 16193 &:= 1 - ((3! - 5) - ((7!/9) + ((7 + (5^{3!}) + 1))) \\ 16194 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) + ((7!/9) + ((7 + (5^{3!}) \times 1)) \\ 16195 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) + ((7!/9) + ((7 + (5^{3!}) + 1)) \\ 16196 &:= (13 + 5) + ((79 \times 7) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)) \\ 16197 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + ((9 - 7) \times 531) \\ 16198 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! + 7975)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 16199 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5! + 7)) - (9 - (7^5))) - (3!! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16200 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5 - 7) \times (9 - 75))) \times ((3! - 1)!) \\ 16201 &:= (((1^{3!}) + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5^{3!}) \times 1 \\ 16202 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + 97) + (5^{3+1})) \\ 16203 &:= 1 + (((3 \times (5! + 7!)) + 97) + (5^{3+1})) \\ 16204 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5! \times ((7 - (9 + 7)) - 5!))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 16205 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7!/9)) - (((7 \times 5) + 3!) + 1) \\ 16206 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7!/9)) - (((7 \times 5) + 3!) \times 1) \\ 16207 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5!) + ((7 \times 97) + (5^{3!}))) - 1 \\ 16208 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5!) + ((7 \times 97) + (5^{3!}))) \times 1 \\ 16209 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5!) + ((7 \times 97) + (5^{3!}))) + 1 \\ 16210 &:= (13 + 579) - (7 - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 16211 &:= ((1 - 3 + (57^{9-7})) \times 5) - (3 + 1)! \\ 16212 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5! + 7!))) + (((9 - 7) + 5!) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 16213 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (57^{9-7})) \times 5) - (3! + 1) \\ 16214 &:= (1 + 3!!) + (5! + (((79 + 7!) + 5) \times 3) + 1) \\ 16215 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 5!) - 7) + (9 + (7^5)) - 3!! \times 1 \\ 16216 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 16217 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (579 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 16218 &:= 1 \times ((3! + (5! + (7! + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 16219 &:= 1 + ((3! + (5! + (7! + ((9 - 7) \times 5!)))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 16220 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5) + 79)) + ((7 + 5!)^{3-1}) \\ 16221 &:= ((1 - ((3 - 57) \times 9) - 7!) - 5!) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 16222 &:= 1 - ((3 + (579 - (7^5))) + 3 + 1) \\ 16223 &:= ((1 + (3! - 5))^7) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 16224 &:= 13 \times ((5! \times 7) + (((9 \times 7) + 5) \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 16225 &:= (1 - 3!!) + ((5 \times (7 \times (97 \times 5))) - 31) \\ 16226 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) + 7) + 97 \times (5! + 3 - 1) \\ 16227 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) - (5! \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 16228 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) - ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\ 16229 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5! + (7 + 9 + ((7^5) - 3!! \times 1))) \\ 16230 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) - (5^{3! - 1}) \\ 16231 &:= 1 + (3! - ((579 - (7^5)) + 3 + 1)) \\ 16232 &:= (1^3) - (579 - (((7^5) + 3) \times 1)) \\ 16233 &:= (1^3) - (579 - ((7^5) + 3 + 1)) \\ 16234 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 16235 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((579 + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 16236 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 579) + (((7^5) + 3) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 16237** := $((1 - 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
16238 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
16239 := $(1 + 3!) - ((579 - (7^5)) - (3 + 1))$
16240 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5!) - (7 - (9 + ((7^5) + 31)))$
16241 := $((13 \times (57 - 9)) - (7 - (5^{3!}))) - 1$
16242 := $((1 - 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) + (3 - 1)$
16243 := $((1 - 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
16244 := $((1 + 3) - 5) - ((7!/9) - (((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
16245 := $((1 + 3) - 5) \times ((7!/9) - (((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
16246 := $((1 + 3) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
16247 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) - (3 + 1)$
16248 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7!/9) + ((7 - 5) - (3 \times 1)))$
16249 := $((1 + 3!) - 579) + (7^5) - (3 \times 1)$
16250 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) - (7!/9)) + (7^{5!/(3+1)!})$
16251 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) - ((7!/9) - ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
16252 := $13 + (((57^{9-7}) \times 5) - 3! \times 1)$
16253 := $1 + (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times (7 + 5!)) - (3 + 1)$
16254 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) + 7) - (9 - 7) \times (5! + 3! \times 1)$
16255 := $(13 + (((57^{9-7}) \times 5) - 3)) \times 1$
16256 := $(13 \times (57 - 9)) + (7 + ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
16257 := $((((1 - 3) - 5) \times 79) + ((7^5) + 3)) \times 1$
16258 := $((((1 - 3) - 5) \times 79) + ((7^5) + 3)) + 1$
16259 := $((1 - 3 + (57^{9-7})) \times 5) + (3 + 1)!$
16260 := $((1 + ((3 \times 5) + 797)) \times 5) \times (3 + 1)$
16261 := $(1 + 3) + (57 + ((9 \times 75) \times (3 + 1)!))$
16262 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7! + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1))$
16263 := $((13 + 5) - (7!/9)) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1)$
16264 := $((1 + 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) - (3! - 1)$
16265 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - ((7!/9) - (((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
16266 := $(1 \times 3!) \times ((5 + (7! - 9)) - (75 \times 31))$
16267 := $((((1 \times 3!) + 5!) - 7!/9) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1))$
16268 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) - ((7!/9) - ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
16269 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 79) - 7) - (5 - ((3! + 1)!)))$
16270 := $(1 \times 3! \times 5) + ((7!/9) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1))$
16271 := $(1 - 3!) + (5 \times (((7 \times (97 \times 5)) + 3) \times 1))$
16272 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 + 797) - (5^3)) + 1)$
16273 := $((1 + 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) + (3 + 1)$
16274 := $((1 + 3!) + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) + (3! - 1)$
16275 := $((1^{35}) + (7 + 97)) \times (5 \times 31)$
16276 := $((1 + 3!) - 579) + (7^5) + (3 + 1)!$
16277 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) \times (79 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 - 1))$
16278 := $(13 + 5) + ((7! - 975) \times (3 + 1))$
16279 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5! + ((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)))) + (3 + 1)$
16280 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times (97 \times 5))) + (3 + 1)!$
16281 := $(1 + 3!) + (57 + ((9 \times 75) \times (3 + 1)!))$
16282 := $((1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5!)) + (3! + 1)$
16283 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 \times 97) + (5 \times 31)$
16284 := $((1^3 + 5) + (7! - 975)) \times (3 + 1)$
16285 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 + 9)) + (7^5) - (3! \times 1)$
16286 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 57) - ((9 - 7) - (5^{3! \times 1}))$
16287 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7!/9) + (((7 \times 5) + 3!) - 1)$
16288 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 - 7)^9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) + 1)$
16289 := $((1 - 3 + 5!)! + (((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5^{3!}) \times 1))$
16290 := $(1 \times 3) - ((5! + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 - 5!) + (3 + 1)!))$
16291 := $(1 \times 3 + (((5 - 7)^9) + (7^5))) - (3! + 1)$
16292 := $(13 - (5 - (7! - 975))) \times (3 + 1)$
16293 := $((1 \times 3) - (57 \times 9)) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1))$
16294 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7!) + (9 \times (7 + 5!)) + 31$
16295 := $((1 + 3!)! + (5 - ((7 - 97) \times (5! + (3! - 1))))$
16296 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7 - 97) - 5!) + (3! + 1))$
16297 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 - 97) + (5! \times (3! - 1)))$
16298 := $((1^{3!}) \times ((5 - 7)^9)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
16299 := $((1^{3!}) + ((5 - 7)^9)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
16300 := $((1 + 3) - (57 \times 9)) + (7^5) + (3 - 1)$
16301 := $13 - (((57 \times 9) - ((7^5) - 3!)) \times 1)$
16302 := $13 - (((57 \times 9) - ((7^5) - 3!)) - 1)$
16303 := $((1 + 3) + (((5 - 7)^9) + (7^5))) + (3 + 1)$
16304 := $((13 + 5) + 79) \times 7 + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
16305 := $(1 + (3 + 5)) + (7 \times (97 \times (5!/(3! - 1))))$
16306 := $((1 - 3 + 5) + (7 \times 97)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
16307 := $((1 + 3!) - (5 + 7)) \times ((97 - 5)/(3 + 1))$
16308 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5 + 31)$
16309 := $((1 - 357) + 9) \times ((7 - 53) - 1)$
16310 := $1 + ((3 \times (5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times (7 + 5!)) + 31))$
16311 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 + (97 \times 5)) + 3 + 1)$

- 16312** := $((13 + (57^{9-7})) \times 5) + (3 - 1)$
16313 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) + 7) \times 5! - (3! + 1)$
16314 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5! + 7)) + ((97 + (5^3)) - 1)$
16315 := $((13 + (57^{9-7})) \times 5) + (3! - 1)$
16316 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) + ((7 \times 97) \times (5! / (3! - 1)))$
16317 := $((1 \times ((3^5 + 7) + 9)) \times 7) \times (5 + 3 + 1)$
16318 := $((1 + 3!)! - (5 + 7)) - (9 + 7) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
16319 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + (7! + (97 \times (5! - (3! - 1))))$
16320 := $((1 - 3)^5) \times ((7 - 97) + 5) \times 3! \times 1$
16321 := $1 + ((3! \times 5) \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) - 5!) + 3!) \times 1)$
16322 := $1 \times ((3! \times 5!) - ((7 + ((9 + 7) - (5^3))) \times 1))$
16323 := $1 + ((3! \times 5!) - ((7 + ((9 + 7) - (5^3))) \times 1))$
16324 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5!) + (3! + 1)$
16325 := $((1 \times 3) - 57) \times 9 + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)$
16326 := $((1 \times ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + 5) \times 3! \times 1$
16327 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) + 7) \times 5! + (3! + 1)$
16328 := $1 + ((3! + ((5 - 7) - ((9 + 7) - (5^3)))) \times 1)$
16329 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! + 7)) - ((97 - 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
16330 := $(1 \times (3 - 57)) + ((9 - 7)^{5 \times 3 - 1})$
16331 := $1 - (((3 - (5^{7-9+7})) \times 5) - 3! \times 1)$
16332 := $((1 + 3!)! - 5) + ((7 - (9 + 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1}))$
16333 := $1 \times 3! + ((5! + 7) + ((9 \times 75) \times (3 + 1)!))$
16334 := $((1 + (3 - 57)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)$
16335 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times (((7 - 9) + (7 \times 5))^{3-1})$
16336 := $((1 - 3 + 5)!)! + (((7 - 9) - 7) + (5^3)) \times 1$
16337 := $((1 + 3^5) \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + 5!)) + (3! + 1)$
16338 := $((1^{35}) \times 7) \times (9 + (75 \times 31))$
16339 := $(1 \times ((3 + 5!) - (7! / 9))) + ((7^5) - 31)$
16340 := $(13 - 57) + ((9 - 7)^{5 \times 3 - 1})$
16341 := $((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times (97 - (5 - 3))) + 1$
16342 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7 + (((9 + 7) + 5!) \times ((3! - 1)!))$
16343 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! + 7)) \times (9 - (7 - 5!)) - (3! - 1)$
16344 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 - 7) + (9 - 7)))! + (5^{3 \times 1})$
16345 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5 - 7)) + ((9 - 7) + (5^{3 \times 1}))$
16346 := $(13 - (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 - 753) + 1)$
16347 := $135 - (7 \times (9 - (75 \times 31)))$
16348 := $((135 - 7)^{9-7}) - (5 + 31)$
16349 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5 - 7)) + (9 - 7) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
16350 := $(1 \times (3! \times 5)) \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) - 5!) + 3!) + 1$
16351 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((5 - (7 - 9)))! / 7) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
16352 := $(1 - 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + (5^{3-1}))$
16353 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5! + (7! + (97 \times (5 - (3 - 1)))))$
16354 := $(1 \times ((3! - 5) \times 7)) + (97 \times (5! - (3 \times 1)))$
16355 := $((135 - 7)^{9-7} - 5) - (3 + 1)!$
16356 := $((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (((7 \times 9)^{7-5}) \times (3 + 1))$
16357 := $((1 - 35) + 7) + ((9 - 7)^{5 \times 3 - 1})$
16358 := $(1 \times 3 + (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + 7) + 5!) \times ((3! - 1)!))$
16359 := $((1 \times (3! + 5)) + ((7 + 9) - 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
16360 := $(1 + (3! + 5)) + (((7 + 9) - 7) + (5^{3 \times 1}))$
16361 := $1 - (((3! - (5! \times 7)) + (9 + 7)) \times (5! / 3! \times 1))$
16362 := $((1 - 3 + (5! - 7)) \times (97 + 5)) + ((3! + 1)!)$
16363 := $(1 - ((3! \times 57) \times 9)) + (7! + (5^{3-1}))$
16364 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5) + 7 + (((9 + 7) + (5^3)) + 1)$
16365 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) - (7! / 9) + (((7^5) + 3) \times 1)$
16366 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) - (7! / 9) + (((7^5) + 3) + 1)$
16367 := $((1 + 3) \times 579) \times 7 + (5 \times 31)$
16368 := $(13 - (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 - 753) \times 1)$
16369 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5! / (7 - (9 - 7))) + (5^{3 \times 1}))$
16370 := $((1 + 3)^5) + 7 \times (9 + 7) - (5! + 3! \times 1)$
16371 := $((1 + 3)^5) + 7 \times (9 + 7) - (5^3 \times 1)$
16372 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! - (7! / 9))) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1)$
16373 := $((1 + 3) + (5! \times 7)) - 97 + ((5^3) + 1)$
16374 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5! + 7)) - (97 - ((5^3) - 1))$
16375 := $1 \times ((3! \times (5! + (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3 \times 1}))$
16376 := $(1 - 357) \times ((97 - 5!) \times (3 - 1))$
16377 := $1 \times ((3! - ((5! + 7) \times 9)) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1)))$
16378 := $1 + ((3! - ((5! + 7) \times 9)) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1)))$
16379 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5! - 79)) - (7 - ((5^3) \times 1))$
16380 := $(1 \times (35 / 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) \times (53 - 1))$
16381 := $1 + ((35 / 7) \times ((9 \times 7) \times (53 - 1)))$
16382 := $(1 - ((35 - (79 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 3!)) + 1$
16383 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) \times (7 + 9) + (7^5) - (3 + 1)!$
16384 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5) + 7 \times ((9 - 7)^{5+3 \times 1})$
16385 := $(1 - ((3! - 5) - 79) \times (7! / 5!)) \times (3! - 1)$
16386 := $(1 - 3) + (5 + (((7 - 9)^7)^{5-3} - 1))$
16387 := $(1 - 3 + 5) + (((7 - 9)^7)^{5-3} \times 1)$

- 16388** := $(1 + 3) + ((5 - 7)^{(9+75)/3!} \times 1)$
16389 := $(1 - 3)^{5-7 \times (7-9)^{-5}} + 3! - 1$
16390 := $(1 - 3)^{5-7 \times (7-9)^{-5}} + 3! \times 1$
16391 := $(1 - 3)^{5-7 \times (7-9)^{-5}} + 3! + 1$
16392 := $((1 + 3!) - 5) + ((7 - 9)^{7+5}) \times (3 + 1)$
16393 := $((1 - (3 \times (5! + (7 + 9)))) + (7^5)) - 3! - 1$
16394 := $((1357 + 9) \times (7 + 5)) + 3 - 1$
16395 := $((1357 + 9) \times (7 + 5)) + 3 \times 1$
16396 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times 7 - ((97 - (5^{3!})) \times 1)$
16397 := $(1 + ((3 - 57) \times (9 + 7))) \times (5 - (3 + 1)!)!$
16398 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times (7 + 9) + (7 \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
16399 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7) \times 5)) - 3!$
16400 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 797) + 5!) - (3! - 1)$
16401 := $(1 - 3) \times (5! - 7!) + (9^{7 \times 5 - 3!})$
16402 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) + (5^3 \times 1))$
16403 := $((135 - 7)^{9-7} - 5) + (3 + 1)!$
16404 := $(1^3 + 5) \times (((79 \times 7) \times 5) - 3!)$
16405 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 \times (7 \times 9)))) + ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!)!$
16406 := $((1 \times 3)!)! - ((5 \times 7) - (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1)))$
16407 := $(1 + 35) \times ((7 \times 9) \times 7) + 531$
16408 := $(1^3 - (5 \times 79)) + ((7^5) - (3! - 1))$
16409 := $(1^3 - ((5 \times 79) - (7^5))) - (3 + 1)$
16410 := $(1 \times 3 + (5 + 7)) \times (9 + (7 \times (5 \times 3!)))$
16411 := $(1 - (357 + 9)) + ((7^5) - 3!)$
16412 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 \times 79) - (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)$
16413 := $(1 + (3 - (5 \times 79))) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)$
16414 := $(1 \times (3! - (5 \times 79))) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1))$
16415 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 797) + 5!) - (3! - 1)$
16416 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 \times 79) - ((7^5) - (3 \times 1)))$
16417 := $(1^3 - ((5 \times 79) - (7^5))) + (3 + 1)$
16418 := $(1 \times 3) - (((5 \times 79) - (7^5)) - (3 \times 1))$
16419 := $((1 \times (3 - (5 \times 79))) + (7^5)) + (3 + 1)$
16420 := $((135 - 7)^{9-7} + (5 + 3!))$
16421 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) + (((7 \times 97) + (5^{3!})) - 1)$
16422 := $((1 \times (3! - (5 \times 79))) + (7^5)) + (3 + 1)$
16423 := $((1 \times (3! - (5 \times 79))) + (7^5)) + (3! - 1)$
16424 := $((1 \times 3!) - ((5 \times 79) - (7^5))) + 3! \times 1$
16425 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 797) + 5!)) + (3! - 1)$
16426 := $1 + (3 \times (((57 \times 97) - 53) - 1))$
16427 := $1 \times ((3 \times ((57 \times 97) - 53)) - 1)$
16428 := $(1 + 3) \times ((579 \times 7) + (53 + 1))$
16429 := $(1 - ((357 - 9) - (7^5))) - 3!$
16430 := $((13 + (57^{9-7})) \times 5) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
16431 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) \times (7 + 9) + (7^5) + (3 + 1)!$
16432 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) + ((7 - 9)^{7+5}) \times (3 + 1)$
16433 := $((1 \times ((3!! - (5! - 7!)) + 9)) / 7) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)$
16434 := $((1 \times 3579) - (7 \times 5!)) \times 3! \times 1$
16435 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7)) - ((5^3) \times 1)$
16436 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7)) - ((5^3) - 1)$
16437 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5) + 797) + (5^{3!})) - 1$
16438 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5) + 797) + (5^{3!})) \times 1$
16439 := $((1 \times 3)!)! + (5 - ((7 - 97) - ((5^{3!}) - 1)))$
16440 := $((1 + 3)! + 5!) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5) - ((3! - 1)!)!$
16441 := $13 + ((5 + 797) + ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
16442 := $(13 \times 5) - (7 - ((9 - 7)^{5 \times 3 - 1}))$
16443 := $1 \times (((3 \times 57) \times 97) - 5!) - (3 + 1)!$
16444 := $1 + (((3 \times 57) \times 97) - 5!) - (3 + 1)!$
16445 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times (7 + 9 + ((7 + 5) - (3! - 1)))$
16446 := $(1 + ((3!! - 5) \times 7)) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 - ((3! \times 1)!)!))$
16447 := $((1 + 3) - (5 \times 79)) + (7^5) + 3!$
16448 := $(1 - (3 \times 5!)) + (7^{9-7 \times 5 + 3!})$
16449 := $(13 \times 5) + ((7 - 9)^{(7!/5!)/(3 \times 1)})$
16450 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1))$
16451 := $((1 - 3!)^5) + (((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1)!)!$
16452 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 7)) - ((97 - 5!) \times 3!) - 1$
16453 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 7)) - ((97 - 5!) \times 3!) \times 1$
16454 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 7)) - ((97 - 5!) \times 3!) + 1$
16455 := $1 \times ((3!! + (5 + 7)) + (97 + ((5^{3!}) + 1)))$
16456 := $(13 \times 5) + (7 + ((9 - 7)^{5 \times 3 - 1}))$
16457 := $1 - (((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9)) - (((7^5) - 3!) - 1))$
16458 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((7 - 9) + 7!) - 5) \times 3! \times 1$
16459 := $((1 + 3)!)! - ((5! - (7! + (9 \times (7 - 5 + 3!)))) - 1)$
16460 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (((7 + 97) + (5! \times 3!)) - 1)$
16461 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 79) + ((7! + 53) - 1))$
16462 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) - (5^3 \times 1)$

- 16463** := $(1 + 3) + (((5 + 7) + 97) \times (5! + 31))$
16464 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 + 9)) \times (7^{5-3+1})$
16465 := $(1 - 3!!) - (5! - (((79 - 75)! \times (3!! + 1)))$
16466 := $(((((1 - 3!)^5) - 7)/9) + (7^5)) + (3! + 1)$
16467 := $((1 - 357) + 9) + (7^5) + (3! + 1)$
16468 := $1 - (((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9)) - ((7^5) + 3) + 1)$
16469 := $(1^3) - (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
16470 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5! + (7 - (9 - 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
16471 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) - (5! - (3 + 1))$
16472 := $(1 + 3) - (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
16473 := $135 + (7 \times (9 + (75 \times 31)))$
16474 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5! \times 7) - ((9 + 7) - (5^{3!})))) + 1$
16475 := $(1 + 3!) - (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
16476 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) \times (9 + 7)) - (5!/3! \times 1)$
16477 := $((13 - 5!) \times (((7 - 9) \times 7) \times (5 + 3!))) - 1$
16478 := $((13 + 5!) \times (79 + 7)) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!)$
16479 := $(1 - (3 + (5 - 7!))) + (97 \times (5! - (3 - 1)))$
16480 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5!) + 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
16481 := $((((1 - 3!) + 5)! \times 7!) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 - 3!))) - 1$
16482 := $((13 + 5) + 7!) - ((9 + 7) \times ((5 - 3!) + 1))$
16483 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 + 7) + (9 \times 75)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
16484 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7)) + ((5^{3!} - 1)))$
16485 := $(1 + 3) + (((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7)) + ((5^{3!} \times 1)))$
16486 := $(1 - 3) - (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)) + 3 + 1)$
16487 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) + 7!) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 - 3!)) - 1$
16488 := $(1 + 3)! \times (((5 \times 7) \times 9) + ((7 + 5) \times 31))$
16489 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 - (975/(3 \times 1)))$
16490 := $(((((1 - 3!)^5) - 7)/9) + ((7^5) + 31))$
16491 := $(1 - ((357 - 9) - (7^5))) + 31$
16492 := $(1 + 3) - (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)) + 3 + 1)$
16493 := $(1 \times ((3^5) - (7!/9))) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
16494 := $(((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) \times (9 + 7)) - 5) + (3 \times 1)$
16495 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times (5^3)) \times 1$
16496 := $(1 + 3) - (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7^{5!/(3+1)!}))$
16497 := $(1 - 3) - (((5 \times 7) \times 9) - (7^5)) - (3! + 1)$
16498 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 \times 9) - ((7 \times 53) + 1)$
16499 := $((1 - 3!)^5) + (((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
16500 := $((1 \times 3!)/(5 + 7)) \times (((97 - 5) \times 3) - 1)$
16501 := $(1 - 3) + (5! + (((7 - 9)^7)^{5-3} - 1))$
16502 := $1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times (5^3)) - 1$
16503 := $(1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times (5^3)) - 1$
16504 := $((1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times (5^3))) \times 1$
16505 := $((1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times (5^3))) + 1$
16506 := $(135 \times (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) - 31)$
16507 := $((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) \times (5 - 3)) + 1$
16508 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times 7 + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) - 1$
16509 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times 7 + ((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) \times 1$
16510 := $(13 \times ((5 + 7) \times 9)) + (((7! - 5) \times 3) + 1)$
16511 := $((1 + 3)! \times 57) + (9 + (((7! + 5) \times 3) - 1))$
16512 := $(1 \times (3 + 5)) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + ((5! + 3) - 1)))$
16513 := $((13 \times 5!) + ((7 \times 97) + 5!)) \times (3! + 1)$
16514 := $(1 - 3) - (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)) - (3 + 1)!)$
16515 := $((1 + 3)! \times 57) + ((9 + 7!) \times (5 - (3 - 1)))$
16516 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7) \times (9 + 7)) + (5!/3! \times 1)$
16517 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times (7 + 9) + ((7 + 5!) + 3! \times 1)$
16518 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
16519 := $(1 - (3! \times (5 - 7))) - ((9 - 7!) + 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
16520 := $((1 \times (3^5)) - 7) \times ((9 + (7 + 53)) + 1)$
16521 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 - 9) + (7!/5)) + (3! \times 1)$
16522 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 \times 7)) \times 9 + (((7^5) + 3) \times 1)$
16523 := $((1 \times (3 - 5)) \times 7) - ((97 - 5!) \times (3! - 1))$
16524 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5 - 7) \times 9 + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)$
16525 := $((1 \times 3!)! / 5) \times (7 - 9) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)$
16526 := $((1 - (3^5)) - (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!)$
16527 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 - 9) \times 7!) / (5 + 31))$
16528 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7! / (9 + 7)) - (5 + 31))$
16529 := $1 + ((3! / 5) - (((7 - (9 + 7)) + 5)^{3!+1}))$
16530 := $(13 + ((5 \times 7) + 97)) \times ((5! - 3!) \times 1)$
16531 := $(1 - (3! - (5! \times 79))) + ((7! / 5) \times (3! + 1))$
16532 := $((1 - (3! / 5)) + (7! + (97 \times 5!))) - (3! - 1)$
16533 := $13 - ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 - (7 + 5!)) \times (3 + 1)))$
16534 := $(1 + (3 \times (5! + 7!))) - (9 \times (7 - (5! + 3 + 1)))$
16535 := $((1 - 3!) \times (5 - ((79 \times (7! / 5!)) - 3!))) \times 1$
16536 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (5 + ((797 + 5!) \times (3 \times 1)))$
16537 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((5 + ((7 + 9) - 75)) + 31)$
16538 := $((1 - (3! \times 5)) + 7) - (((97 - 5!) \times 3!) \times 1)$

- 16539** := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (((79 \times 7) + (5^{3!})) + 1)$
16540 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 797) + 5!)) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
16541 := $(1 + 3!!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 + 7) + ((5^3) - 1)))$
16542 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5! \times 79) + ((7!/5) \times (3! + 1)))$
16543 := $((135 \times (7 - 9)) + (7^5)) + (3! \times 1)$
16544 := $(1^3 + ((5 + 7) + 9)) \times (753 - 1)$
16545 := $((((1 - 3) \times 5!) - ((7 - 9) - (7^5))) - (3 + 1)!)!$
16546 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 - (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
16547 := $1 \times ((3^5 + (7 \times 97)) + (5^{3! \times 1}))$
16548 := $(1 \times (3! \times (5 - 7))) - (((97 - 5!) \times 3!!) \times 1)$
16549 := $1 - (((35 \times 7) + 9) - ((7^5) - 3!)) - 1$
16550 := $1 + (((3!! + 5) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) - (5! + (3! \times 1)))$
16551 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 57) \times 97) - (5 + 31))$
16552 := $(1 - (3^5 + 7)) - ((9 - ((7^5) + 3)) \times 1)$
16553 := $((1 - 35) \times 7) - (9 - ((7^5) - (3! + 1)))$
16554 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 - 7)) - ((97 - 5!) \times (3!! \times 1))$
16555 := $(1 \times 35) \times (((79 \times (7 - 5)) \times 3) - 1)$
16556 := $(1 - 35) + ((79 \times 7) \times (5! / (3 + 1)))$
16557 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 - 9)) - (7 \times (5 + 31)))$
16558 := $((1 + 3)^5) + (((7 - 97) + (5^{3!})) - 1)$
16559 := $(1 - 3) + ((5! \times 7) + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1)))$
16560 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times (5! - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - (5 \times (3 \times 1))))$
16561 := $((((1 \times 3) \times 57) \times 97) + (5 - 31))$
16562 := $((((1 + 3!)! / 5) - (7 + (((9 \times 7) - (5^{3!})) + 1)))$
16563 := $(1 - (3 \times 5 \times (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) - (3! - 1))$
16564 := $((13 \times (5 - 79)) + (7^5)) + (3!! - 1)$
16565 := $((1 + 3) + (5! \times 7)) + (97 + ((5^{3!}) - 1))$
16566 := $(1^3 + ((5 + 7) + 9)) \times (753 \times 1)$
16567 := $((1 \times (3 \times 57)) \times 97) - (5 \times (3 + 1))$
16568 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5! - 7!) - (97 \times 5!)) - (3 - 1))$
16569 := $((((1 - 3)^5) \times 7) - (9 - (((7^5) - 3!) + 1)))$
16570 := $((1 + (3! - (5 - 7))) - ((97 - 5!) \times 3!!)) + 1$
16571 := $((((1 - 35) \times 7) + (9 + (7^5))) - (3! + 1))$
16572 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) - (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
16573 := $1 \times (((3 \times 57) \times 97) - ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
16574 := $(1^{35}) \times (((7! + (97 \times 5)) \times 3) - 1)$
16575 := $((1 - 35) \times 7) + (9 + ((7^5) - (3 \times 1)))$
16576 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) + ((79 \times 7) \times (5 \times 3!))) \times 1$
16577 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) + ((79 \times 7) \times (5 \times 3!))) + 1$
16578 := $((((1 - 3) \times (5! - 7)) - 9) + (((7^5) + 3!) \times 1))$
16579 := $((((1 - 3) \times (5! - 7)) - 9) + (((7^5) + 3!) + 1))$
16580 := $((1 - 35) \times 7) + (((9 + (7^5)) + 3) - 1)$
16581 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((57 \times 97) - 5) + 3 \times 1)$
16582 := $((((1 - 35) \times 7) + (9 + (7^5))) + (3 + 1))$
16583 := $(1 + 3!!) \times ((5 + 79) - (7 + (53 + 1)))$
16584 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((57 \times 97) + 5) - 3! \times 1)$
16585 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) - (5 - (3 \times 1))$
16586 := $((1 + (3! \times 5!)) \times (7 + 9 + 7)) + ((5 - 3) + 1)$
16587 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((57 \times 97) + 5) - (3! - 1))$
16588 := $(1^3 + ((5 + 7) + 9)) \times (753 + 1)$
16589 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((79 \times (7 - 5)) \times 3)) - 1$
16590 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((79 \times (7 - 5)) \times 3)) \times 1$
16591 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((79 \times (7 - 5)) \times 3)) + 1$
16592 := $1 + ((3 + 5!) - ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1)))$
16593 := $1 + (((3 \times 57) \times 97) + (5! / (3 + 1)!))$
16594 := $1 \times (((3 \times 57) \times 97) + ((5 + 3) - 1))$
16595 := $1 \times (((3 \times 57) \times 97) + ((5 + 3) \times 1))$
16596 := $(1^3 \times 5) + (((79 \times 7) \times (5 \times 3!)) + 1)$
16597 := $1 + (((3 \times 57) \times 97) + (5 + 3)) + 1$
16598 := $(13 - 5) + (((79 \times 7) \times 5) \times 3! \times 1)$
16599 := $((((1 - (3! \times 5)) \times 7) - 9) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1))$
16600 := $13 + ((57 \times 97) \times ((5 - 3) + 1))$
16601 := $(13 \times 5!) - (((7 \times 9) - ((7! - 5) \times 3)) + 1)$
16602 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) + (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
16603 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) - (7^{9-7})) - (5 \times 31))$
16604 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((5 \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times ((5! - 3) + 1)))$
16605 := $(1 + (3 \times 5)) + (((79 \times 7) \times (5 \times 3!)) - 1)$
16606 := $((((1 \times 35) - 7) - 9) \times ((7 \times (5^3)) - 1))$
16607 := $((1 \times (3 \times 57)) \times 97) + (5 \times (3 + 1))$
16608 := $1 \times (((3! + 5) + (7! + (97 \times 5))) \times 3) \times 1$
16609 := $1 + (((3! + 5) + (7! + (97 \times 5))) \times 3) \times 1$
16610 := $1 \times (((35/7)! + 9)^{7-5}) - 31$
16611 := $((1 + 3!) - 5!) \times (79 - ((75 \times 3) + 1))$
16612 := $((((1 \times 3!)! - 579) \times 7) + (5^{3! \times 1}))$
16613 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) \times 97 - (5 - 31)$
16614 := $1 + ((3 \times (57 \times 97)) - (5 - 31))$
16615 := $(1 \times (3! \times ((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5)) - (3! - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 16616 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (57 \times 97)) + (5 \times 3!))) - 1 \\ 16617 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times (57 \times 97)) + (5 \times 3!))) \times 1 \\ 16618 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5! + 79) - ((7^5) + (3! + 1))) \\ 16619 &:= (13 - (5! + 79)) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1) \\ 16620 &:= (((1^{3!}) - 5) - (7 \times 9)) + (7^5) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 16621 &:= 1 - (((3 \times 57) + 9) - (((7^5) - 3!) - 1)) \\ 16622 &:= (((1 - (3 \times 57)) + 9) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 16623 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 57) \times 97) + (5 + 31) \\ 16624 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 57)) - 9) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 16625 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((79 \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 16626 &:= ((1 \times (3! \times (5 \times 79))) \times 7) + (5 + 31) \\ 16627 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) \times (5^3)) - 1) \\ 16628 &:= 1 \times ((3 + ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) \times (5^3))) \times 1) \\ 16629 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5 - (7 \times 9)))) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 16630 &:= (1 - (3 \times 57)) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3 - 1)) \\ 16631 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 57) + ((9 - (7^5)) - 3))) \times 1 \\ 16632 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 57) + ((9 - (7^5)) - 3))) + 1 \\ 16633 &:= 1 - ((35 - 79) \times (7 \times (53 + 1))) \\ 16634 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + ((7 \times 9) + (7^5))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 16635 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5! + (7 + 9)) - ((7^5) - 31)) \\ 16636 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) - ((5! - 3!) + 1) \\ 16637 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5) \times (79 \times 7)) - ((5! - 3!) \times 1) \\ 16638 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5!)) - 7) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 16639 &:= 13 - (((5! + (7 \times 9)) - ((7^5) + 3)) + 1) \\ 16640 &:= (1 + ((3! - 5) \times 7)) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 16641 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5 - (7 \times 9))) - 75)^{3-1} \\ 16642 &:= (((1 + 3)! / 5) - ((7 - (9 + 7)) - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 16643 &:= (1 \times (((3 \times 57) + 9) + 7)) \times (5! - 31) \\ 16644 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) + (((7! / 9) + (7^5)) - (3! + 1)) \\ 16645 &:= (1^3 - (5 - 7!)) + ((97 \times 5!) - 31) \\ 16646 &:= (1 - ((3! + 5) - (7! / 9))) + (((7^5) + 3) \times 1) \\ 16647 &:= ((13 - 5!) + (7 \times (97 - 5))) \times 31 \\ 16648 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 57)) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1) \\ 16649 &:= (1^3 - (5! + (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 16650 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 57)) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1) \\ 16651 &:= (((1 - (3 \times 57)) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3!)) - 1 \\ 16652 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7)) + (9 + 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\ 16653 &:= (((1 - (3 \times 57)) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3!)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16654 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5^3 \times 1))) \\ 16655 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 16656 &:= (((1^3 + 5)!) \times (7 + 9)) + (7! + (5! - (3 + 1)!)) \\ 16657 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) - (3! - 1) \\ 16658 &:= (1 - (3 \times (57 - 9))) + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 16659 &:= (((1 + 3)! + 5!) \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) + 531 \\ 16660 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5!) + ((797 \times 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 16661 &:= ((13 - 5!) - (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 16662 &:= ((1 - (3! + 5!)) - (7 + 9)) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1) \\ 16663 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + ((7 \times 97) + ((5^3!) - 1)) \\ 16664 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7! + (97 \times 5!))) - (3 + 1)! \\ 16665 &:= ((1 \times 3)!) + (5 + ((797 \times 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 16666 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5! + (3! + 1))) \\ 16667 &:= (1 + (((3! \times (5 - 7)) - 9) + (7^5))) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 16668 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5!)) - ((7 + 9) - (7^5))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 16669 &:= (1^3 - (5 - 7!)) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!) - 1) \\ 16670 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 57)) + 9) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 16671 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7!) - ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))) - 1 \\ 16672 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! + ((7 + 9) - (7^5)))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 16673 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 - 7!) - ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))) + 1 \\ 16674 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times 97) + (5 + (3 + 1)!)) \\ 16675 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5 + 7)) + (9 + 7)) \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1) \\ 16676 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 57) \times 97) + 5! - 31 \\ 16677 &:= (((1 + 3!) - (5 - 7!)) + (97 \times 5!)) - (3! - 1) \\ 16678 &:= (1 - 3) + (5! \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) + (5^3 \times 1))) \\ 16679 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5! - 7)) - (((97 - 5!) \times 3!) \times 1) \\ 16680 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((7 - 9) + ((7 \times 5!) - (3 + 1))) \\ 16681 &:= (1 \times 3! \times ((5 \times (79 \times 7)) + (5 \times 3))) + 1 \\ 16682 &:= (1 \times ((3 + (5 + 7!)) + ((97 \times 5!) - 3!))) \times 1 \\ 16683 &:= 1 \times (((3 - 5) \times 7) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1) \\ 16684 &:= 1 + (((3 - 5) \times 7) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1) \\ 16685 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((5 + 7!) + (97 \times 5!))) + (3! - 1) \\ 16686 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times 9) + (7! + (5 + 3 + 1))) \\ 16687 &:= (((1 + 3!) - (5 - 7!)) + (97 \times 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\ 16688 &:= ((13 - 5!) - ((7 + 9) - (7^5))) + (3 + 1) \\ 16689 &:= ((13 - 5!) - ((7 + 9) - (7^5))) + (3! - 1) \\ 16690 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5!) - (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 16691 &:= (((13 - 5!) + 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) + 3!)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16692 &:= (((13 - 5!) + 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) + 3!)) \times 1 \\16693 &:= ((13 - 5!) + 7) - (((9 - (7^5)) + 3!) - 1) \\16694 &:= (1 - (3! + 5!)) + (7 + 9 + (((7^5) - 3) - 1)) \\16695 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) - 79) \times 7 \times (53 \times 1) \\16696 &:= (1^{35}) \times (((7! / (9 + 7)) \times 53) + 1) \\16697 &:= (1^{35}) + (((7! / (9 + 7)) \times 53) + 1) \\16698 &:= (1 - (3^5)) \times (7 - ((97 - (5! / 3!)) - 1)) \\16699 &:= (1 + ((3! - (5 + 79)) + (7^5))) - 31 \\16700 &:= (1 - 3!) - (5! - ((7 + (9 + ((7^5) + 3))) - 1)) \\16701 &:= ((1 + 3)! - ((5! + (7 + 9)) - (7^5))) + 3! \times 1 \\16702 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) - (79 - (7^5))) - 31 \\16703 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) + (5! - (3 + 1)) \\16704 &:= 1 \times (((3 + (5! - 7)) \times (9 + 7)) \times ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\16705 &:= 1 + (((3 + (5! - 7)) \times (9 + 7)) \times ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\16706 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5! - (7 + 9))) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1) \\16707 &:= ((1 + 35) - 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\16708 &:= (1 - (3 + (57 + 9 - (7^5)))) - 31 \\16709 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5 \times 7)) + 9) + ((7^5) - (3 \times 1)) \\16710 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5 \times 7)) + 9) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1)) \\16711 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 57) \times 97) + 5!) + 3 + 1 \\16712 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 57) \times 97) + 5!) + 3 + 1 \\16713 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5!) + (7 + 9 + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)) \\16714 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5 + 7!) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3!))) - 1 \\16715 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + ((5 \times 7) + ((97 \times 5) \times (3 + 1)!)) \\16716 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! - (7 + 9)) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)) \\16717 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 + (97 - (5 \times 3))) + 1) \\16718 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) - 79) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1) \\16719 &:= ((1 - ((3! + 5) \times 7)) - 9) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1) \\16720 &:= ((1 - ((3! + 5) \times 7)) - 9) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1) \\16721 &:= ((1 + 3) - (57 + (9 - (7^5)))) - (3 + 1)! \\16722 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + ((5! + 7) \times ((97 + 5) + (3 + 1)!)) \\16723 &:= (13 - (57 + 9 - (7^5))) - 31 \\16724 &:= 1 \times ((3 - (5 + 79)) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1))) \\16725 &:= (1 + (3 - (5 + 79))) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1)) \\16726 &:= (1 + 3!) + (5 - ((79 - (7^5)) + 31)) \\16727 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((5 + 79) - ((7^5) - (3 - 1))) \\16728 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! + (7! - 975)) - (3 \times 1)) \\16729 &:= (1^3 - (57 - 9)) + ((7^5) - 31)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16730 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5! - 7) - ((9 + (7^5)) + (3 + 1)!)) \\16731 &:= ((1 - 3!) - ((5 - 7)^9)) \times (7 - 5 + 31) \\16732 &:= ((1 \times (35 - 79)) + (7^5)) - 31 \\16733 &:= ((13 - (5 + 79)) + (7^5)) - (3 \times 1) \\16734 &:= (1 + (3 - (5 \times (7 + 9)))) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1) \\16735 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 5) - (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1)!)) \\16736 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) - ((7 \times 9) - ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!)) \\16737 &:= 1 \times ((3 - (57 + 9)) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1))) \\16738 &:= 1 + ((3 - (57 + 9)) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1))) \\16739 &:= ((13 - (5 + 79)) + (7^5)) + (3 \times 1) \\16740 &:= ((1 + 35) \times (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! - 1)) \\16741 &:= (1^3 + 5) - ((79 - (7^5)) - (3! + 1)) \\16742 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5))) - (3 + 1) \\16743 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) \times 7) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\16744 &:= ((1 - 3)^{5-7+9+7}) + ((5! \times 3) \times 1) \\16745 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 + ((9 - 7) + (53 \times 1))) \\16746 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 + (9 - 7)) + (53 - 1)) \\16747 &:= (1 + ((3 - 5) - (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1) \\16748 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! + (7 \times (9 - 7))) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\16749 &:= (1 \times 3) - (57 + 9 - ((7^5) + (3! - 1))) \\16750 &:= (((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5))) + (3 + 1) \\16751 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((57 + 9 - (7^5)) - (3! + 1)) \\16752 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (57 + 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! - 1)) \\16753 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 - (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)) \\16754 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 - (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) + (3! + 1)) \\16755 &:= (1^3 - 5) - ((79 - (7^5)) - 31) \\16756 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((57 - 9) - ((7^5) - (3! \times 1))) \\16757 &:= (13 - 57) - ((9 - ((7^5) + 3)) \times 1) \\16758 &:= ((1 + 3) - 5) - (79 - ((7^5) + 31)) \\16759 &:= ((13 - 5!) + ((7 \times 9) + (7^5))) - (3 + 1) \\16760 &:= (1 - 3!) - ((5 \times 7) + (9 - (((7^5) + 3) - 1))) \\16761 &:= 1 + (((3! - (5 + 79)) + (7^5)) + 31) \\16762 &:= (1^3 - 579) \times (7 - (5 + 31)) \\16763 &:= 1 \times (3 + (5 \times (((7 - 9) + (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 + 1)))) \\16764 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) - (79 - (7^5))) + 31 \\16765 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5! - 79)) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1)) \\16766 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 57) + (9 + ((7^5) + 3))) + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16767 &:= ((13 - 5!) + ((7 \times 9) + (7^5))) + (3 + 1) \\ 16768 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5!)) + 7) \times ((9 - 7) + (5! + 3! \times 1)) \\ 16769 &:= ((1 + 3) - (57 + (9 - (7^5)))) + (3 + 1)! \\ 16770 &:= (1 - 3!) + (5 \times (7 + ((9 \times (7 + 5)) \times 31))) \\ 16771 &:= (13 \times (5! + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times (5! \times (3 - 1))) \\ 16772 &:= ((1 + 3)! - (57 + 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! + 1)) \\ 16773 &:= (1 - 35) - ((7 - (9 + (7^5))) + 3 - 1) \\ 16774 &:= (13 - 57) + (9 + (((7^5) + 3) - 1)) \\ 16775 &:= (1^3 - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3! + 1)) \\ 16776 &:= ((1 - 3)^5) + (7 - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 16777 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + (7^5)) - 3!) - 1) \\ 16778 &:= (1 + 3)! - (5 + ((79 - (7^5)) - 31)) \\ 16779 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) - 7) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3 - 1)) \\ 16780 &:= (((1 \times 3! + 5) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 16781 &:= (1 \times ((3! + 5) \times (7 - 9))) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1) \\ 16782 &:= ((1 \times ((3! + 5) \times (7 - 9))) + ((7^5) - 3)) \times 1 \\ 16783 &:= (1^{3579} \times (7^5)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 16784 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) - (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! + 1)) \\ 16785 &:= (13 - (57 + 9 - (7^5))) + 31 \\ 16786 &:= 13 - (((5 + 7) - 9) - ((7^5) - 31)) \\ 16787 &:= ((13 - 5!) + ((7 \times 9) + (7^5))) + (3 + 1)! \\ 16788 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! - ((7 \times 9) + (7^5))) - 31) \\ 16789 &:= (1 - (3! - (5 \times (7 - 9)))) + ((7^5) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 16790 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5 - 7)) - (((9 - (7^5)) - 3!) \times 1) \\ 16791 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 57)/9)) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1) \\ 16792 &:= (((13 + 5) + 7) - (9 - (7^5))) - 31 \\ 16793 &:= ((1 - 35) + 7) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 3 + 1) \\ 16794 &:= ((1 \times (35 - 79)) + (7^5)) + 31 \\ 16795 &:= (1^{357}) - ((9 - ((7^5) - 3)) + 1) \\ 16796 &:= (1 + (3 - 5)) - ((7 + 9) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 16797 &:= (1 + (3 - 5)) \times ((7 + 9) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 16798 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) - ((7 + 9) - ((7^5) - (3 + 1))) \\ 16799 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7) + 9) - (7^5))) - (3 + 1) \\ 16800 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5 - 7) - (9 - (7^5)))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 16801 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - ((5 - 7) + 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) + 1) \\ 16802 &:= (1^{3579}) \times (((7^5) - 3!) + 1) \\ 16803 &:= (1^{3579}) + (((7^5) - 3!) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16804 &:= 13 - (579 \times ((7 - 5) - 31)) \\ 16805 &:= (1^{3579}) \times ((7^5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 16806 &:= (1^{3579}) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1)) \\ 16807 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7) + 9) - (7^5))) + (3 + 1) \\ 16808 &:= (1^3) \times (((5 - 7) + (9 + (7^5))) - 3! \times 1) \\ 16809 &:= (1 - (35/7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 16810 &:= (((1 - 35) - 7)^{9-7}) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\ 16811 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) - (7 - (9 + (7^5)))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 16812 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 9) - (7^5))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 16813 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5))^{7+9}) \times ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 16814 &:= ((1 + (3 - 5))^{7+9}) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 16815 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 9) - (7^5))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 16816 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (5 + ((7 - 9) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1))) \\ 16817 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) - ((7 - 9) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 16818 &:= (1^{357}) \times (9 + ((7^5) + 3 - 1)) \\ 16819 &:= (1^{357}) + (9 + ((7^5) + 3 - 1)) \\ 16820 &:= (1^3 \times ((5 - 7) + (9 + (7^5)))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 16821 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 9) - (7^5))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 16822 &:= (((1 + 3) + ((5 - 7) + (9 + (7^5)))) + 3) + 1 \\ 16823 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) - (7 - (9 + (7^5)))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 16824 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) - ((7 - 9) - (7^5))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 16825 &:= (13 - (((5 - 7) - 9) - (7^5))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 16826 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5 - ((7 - 9) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1))) \\ 16827 &:= (1 + (3! + 5)) - ((7 - 9) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 16828 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57))/9) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1) \\ 16829 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57))/9) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 16830 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 57))/9) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1) \\ 16831 &:= (1^{3579} \times (7^5)) + (3 + 1)! \\ 16832 &:= (1 + 35) - ((7 + (9 - (7^5))) - (3! - 1)) \\ 16833 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 57)/9) + (7^5))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 16834 &:= (13 - (((5 - 7) - 9) - (7^5))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 16835 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5) + 7) + (9 + (7^5))) + 3 \times 1 \\ 16836 &:= 1 + 35 + ((7 - 9) + ((7^5) - (3! - 1))) \\ 16837 &:= (13 - (((5 - 7) - 9) - (7^5))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 16838 &:= (1^{3579}) \times ((7^5) + 31) \\ 16839 &:= (1^{3579}) + ((7^5) + 31) \\ 16840 &:= (((1 + 35) - (7 - 9)) + (7^5)) - (3! - 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 16841** := $((1 + 3)! + 5!) - ((79 - (7^5)) + 31)$
16842 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 + 797)) \times (5 - (3 - 1))$
16843 := $(1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) - 9) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
16844 := $(1 \times 3 + (5! - 79)) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1))$
16845 := $((1 \times 3!)/(5 + 7)) + (9 + ((7^5) - 31))$
16846 := $(1 + (35 + 7)) - (9 - ((7^5) + (3! - 1)))$
16847 := $1 \times 3 + ((5 \times 7) + (((9 + (7^5)) - 3!) - 1))$
16848 := $13 \times ((5 + 7) \times (((97 + 5) + 3!) \times 1))$
16849 := $((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1)$
16850 := $((1 \times (3 \times 57))/9) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!)$
16851 := $((1 + (3 + (5 \times 7))) + 9) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1)$
16852 := $((13 \times 5) - 7) - (9 - (((7^5) - 3) - 1))$
16853 := $((13 \times 5) - 7) - ((9 - ((7^5) - 3)) \times 1)$
16854 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)$
16855 := $1 \times (((3! - 5) + 7) + (9 + (7^5))) + 31$
16856 := $1 + (((3! - 5) + 7) + (9 + (7^5))) + 31$
16857 := $1 + ((3! \times 5) + (7 + 9 + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)))$
16858 := $((1 + (3! + 5)) \times 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
16859 := $(135 - 79) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1))$
16860 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5797)) - 531$
16861 := $1 + ((3 \times 5797) - 531)$
16862 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 - (7 - 9))) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)$
16863 := $(13 - 5) + ((79 + (7^5)) - 31)$
16864 := $(1 - (3 - ((57 + 9) + (7^5)))) - (3! + 1)$
16865 := $(1^3 + 57) + ((9 - (7 - 5))^{3! - 1})$
16866 := $((1 \times 3!) + 57) - 9 + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)$
16867 := $1 - ((3 - 57) - ((9 + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)))$
16868 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 + (9 - 7)) + (53 - 1))$
16869 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 + ((9 - 7) + (53 \times 1)))$
16870 := $1 \times (35 \times ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 53)) - 1))$
16871 := $1 + (35 \times ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 53)) - 1))$
16872 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) - (75 \times 31)$
16873 := $((13 + 5) + 79) + ((7^5) - 31)$
16874 := $1 + (((3!)/(5 + 7)) + (9 + ((7^5) - 3))) \times 1$
16875 := $((1 + 35) - 7) - (9 - 7) \times (5^{3+1})$
16876 := $(1^3) - (5 - (((79 + (7^5)) - 3!) \times 1))$
16877 := $((1 \times 3!) - 5) + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)$
16878 := $(1 - (3 - ((57 + 9) + (7^5)))) + (3! + 1)$
16879 := $((1 + 3) + 57) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 3 - 1)$
16880 := $1 - (((3 \times 5) - (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)) - (3 + 1)!)$
16881 := $((1^3)^5) \times (((79 + (7^5)) - 3!) + 1)$
16882 := $((1^3)^5) + (((79 + (7^5)) - 3!) + 1)$
16883 := $(1 \times 3 + (57 + 9)) + (((7^5) + 3!) + 1)$
16884 := $((1 + 35) + ((7 + 9) \times (7!/5))) + (3!! \times 1)$
16885 := $(1^3 + 5) + (((79 + (7^5)) - 3!) - 1)$
16886 := $(135 - ((7 \times 9) - (7^5))) + (3! + 1)$
16887 := $(1 - (3 - (5 + 79))) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1))$
16888 := $((1 + (357 \times 9)) + (7!/5)) \times (3 + 1)$
16889 := $((13 - 5) + 79) + (7^5) - (3! - 1)$
16890 := $(1^3 \times (5 \times (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
16891 := $((13 \times 5) + 7) + (((9 + (7^5)) + 3) \times 1)$
16892 := $(1 - 3!!) + (((5 + (79 + (7^5))) + 3!!) \times 1)$
16893 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) - (5! - (3 - 1))$
16894 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 - 79)) + ((7^5) + (3! + 1))$
16895 := $((1 + 3!)^5 - 7) + ((97 - 5) + 3 \times 1)$
16896 := $((1^3 \times 5) + 79) + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)$
16897 := $1 - (((3! + 5) \times ((7 - 9)^7)) \times ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
16898 := $((13 - 5) + 79) + (7^5) + (3 + 1)$
16899 := $1 \times (((3! + (5 + 79)) + (7^5)) + 3 - 1)$
16900 := $1 \times (((((3 + 5) \times 7) + 9)^{7-5}) \times (3 + 1))$
16901 := $1 + (((((3 + 5) \times 7) + 9)^{7-5}) \times (3 + 1))$
16902 := $((1 + (3 \times 5 \times 7)) - 9) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1))$
16903 := $(1 + (3! - 5)) + ((7 \times 9) + ((7^5) + 31))$
16904 := $((13 \times 5!) + (79 \times 7)) \times (5 + 3 \times 1)$
16905 := $(1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + (53 \times 1))$
16906 := $(1^{3!}) + (5 \times (7 \times (((97 \times 5) - 3) + 1)))$
16907 := $((1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 7))) - 9) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)$
16908 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 \times 7))) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3 + 1))$
16909 := $(1 - (((3! \times (5 - 7)) \times 9) - (7^5))) - (3! + 1)$
16910 := $1 \times (((3! - 5) + 7) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 31))$
16911 := $1 + (((3! - 5) + 7) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 31))$
16912 := $((1 \times (((3 - 5) + 7))!) - (9 - (7^5))) - 3! \times 1$
16913 := $((1 + 3!)^5 - (7^{9-7})) + (5 \times 31)$
16914 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! - (7 + 9))) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1)$

- 16915** := $(1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 7) + (9 + (7^5)))) - (3! + 1)$
16916 := $((1 + 3) - 5) + 79 + ((7^5) + 31)$
16917 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))$
16918 := $((((1 - 3) - 5) + 7) - (9 - (7^5))) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
16919 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 - 3!) - 1))$
16920 := $((13 \times 5) + (79 + (7^5))) - 31$
16921 := $((1 + 3^5) + 7!) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3 \times 1))$
16922 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! - 7)) - ((97 - 5!) \times (3!! + 1))$
16923 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 - ((9 + 7) - (5^3 \times 1)))$
16924 := $(1 \times (((3 - 5) + 7)!) - ((9 - (7^5)) - 3! \times 1)$
16925 := $1 \times 3! + ((5! \times ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5) - 3!)) - 1)$
16926 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (((79 \times 7) - 5) - (3 - 1))$
16927 := $1 \times 3! + ((5! \times ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5) - 3!)) + 1)$
16928 := $135 - ((7 + 9) - (((7^5) + 3) - 1))$
16929 := $(135 - (7 + 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
16930 := $(1 + 3!) + (5! - (7 - (9 + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1))))$
16931 := $(1 + 3!!) + (579 + ((7 + (5^{3!}) - 1))$
16932 := $(1 + 3!!) + (579 + ((7 + (5^{3!}) \times 1))$
16933 := $(1 + 3) - (57 \times ((9 \times (7 - 5!)) + (3!! \times 1)))$
16934 := $((((1 - 3 + 5) - (7 - 9)))! + ((7^5) + (3! + 1))$
16935 := $((1 + 3!) + 5!) + ((7 - 9) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1))$
16936 := $(1 - (((3 - 5) \times 7) \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1)$
16937 := $((13 \times 5) + ((7 \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3))) - 1$
16938 := $((13 \times 5) + ((7 \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3))) \times 1$
16939 := $((13 \times 5) + ((7 \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3))) + 1$
16940 := $1 \times (((3 + 5) + 7) \times 9) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
16941 := $(13 \times 57) + (9 \times (75 \times (3 + 1)!))$
16942 := $(1 \times (((3 - 5) + 7)!) + (9 + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1))$
16943 := $(135 + 7) - (((9 - (7^5)) - 3) \times 1)$
16944 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! + 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1)$
16945 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 - 9)) + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1))$
16946 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) + ((5! \times 3) - 1)$
16947 := $((1 + ((3 + 5) + 7)) \times 9) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1)$
16948 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 + 7) + 9)) + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1)$
16949 := $((1 \times (35/7)!) - 9) + ((7^5) + 31)$
16950 := $(1 + (35/7)!) - ((9 - (7^5)) - 31)$
16951 := $1 \times 3 + (((5 + 7) + (9 + (7^5))) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
16952 := $((1 \times 35) + 79) + ((7^5) + 31)$
16953 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 - 9)) + (((7^5) + 3) - 1)$
16954 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) + 79) + 75) - (3! + 1)$
16955 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (579 - (((7^5) + 3!) + 1))$
16956 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) + 79) + (75 - 3!)) + 1$
16957 := $((1 + (3! - 5))^7) - (9 - ((7^5) + 31))$
16958 := $((1 - 3!) + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 \times (7 + 5)) + 31)$
16959 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 \times 9) - (7 - 5!)) - (3 + 1)!)!$
16960 := $135 + (7 + 9 + (((7^5) + 3) - 1))$
16961 := $(135 + (7 + 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
16962 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) + (9 + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
16963 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((57 \times 97) + (5^3))) + 1$
16964 := $(1^3 - 5) \times (((7 \times 97) + 5!) - ((3! + 1)!)!$
16965 := $((1 + 35) - (7 - 9)) + (7^5) + ((3! - 1)!)!$
16966 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (79 + 75) + (3! - 1)$
16967 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 57) - 9) + (7^5))) - (3 - 1)$
16968 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) + 79) + 75) + (3! + 1)$
16969 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) + (7 + 9 + ((7^5) + 31))$
16970 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) + ((79 + (7^5)) - 31)$
16971 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 57) - 9) + (7^5))) + (3 - 1)$
16972 := $(1 + (3 \times 57)) - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3 - 1))$
16973 := $(1 \times (3!!/5)) + ((7 + 9 + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)$
16974 := $(1 + (3 \times 57)) - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3 + 1))$
16975 := $(135 - (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + 31)$
16976 := $(1 \times (3!! + 5)) - (((7!/9) - ((7^5) + 3)) - 1)$
16977 := $(1 + (3 \times 57)) - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3! + 1))$
16978 := $13 + (((57^{9-7}) \times 5) + 3!! \times 1)$
16979 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) \times (7 + 9) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1))$
16980 := $1 - (((3 - 57) \times 9) \times 7) \times 5 + 31)$
16981 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) + 9)) + ((7^5) - (3! \times 1))$
16982 := $((13 \times 5) + (79 + (7^5))) + 31$
16983 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) + (79 \times ((7! + 5!)/(3 + 1)!))$
16984 := $(1 \times (3 \times 57)) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3 \times 1))$
16985 := $(1 \times (3 \times 57)) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3 - 1))$
16986 := $((135 \times (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
16987 := $(1 + 3!) - (5 - (79 \times ((7! + 5!)/(3 + 1)!))$
16988 := $((1 + 3^5) - (7 \times 9)) + (7^{5!/(3+1)!})$

- 16989** := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((57^{9-7}) \times 5)) + (3 + 1)!$
16990 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + (7 \times 9) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1))$
16991 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) + (((7 \times 9) + ((7^5) - 3)) + 1)$
16992 := $((1 \times 3!) - (5 + 7)) \times (((9 + 7) - (5 + (3! + 1))))!$
16993 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) + 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))$
16994 := $13 + (((5 \times 7) \times (97 \times 5)) + 3! \times 1)$
16995 := $(1 - 3 + 57) \times (9 + (75 \times (3 + 1)))$
16996 := $(1 + 3)! + (((5 \times 7) \times (97 \times 5)) - (3 \times 1))$
16997 := $((1 - (3 - 5!)) + 79) + ((7^5) - (3! + 1))$
16998 := $135 + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) - (3! + 1))$
16999 := $(1 + ((3! + 5) \times 79)) + ((7 + 5!)^{3-1})$
17000 := $((1 + 3579) + (7! - 5!)) \times (3 - 1)$
17001 := $((((13 + 5) + 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) - 31$
17002 := $(1 - (3 - 5!)) + (79 + ((7^5) - (3 - 1)))$
17003 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) - ((7!/9) - ((7^5) + 31))$
17004 := $(13 \times ((5 + 7) + (9 \times (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1)$
17005 := $(1^{3!}) \times (5 \times ((7 \times (97 \times 5)) + (3! \times 1)))$
17006 := $(1^{3!}) + (5 \times ((7 \times (97 \times 5)) + (3! \times 1)))$
17007 := $(1 \times 35) + ((7! + (97 \times (5! + 3))) + 1)$
17008 := $1 \times (((3! + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (7^5)) - ((3! - 1)!))$
17009 := $(135 + ((7 \times 9) + (7^5))) + (3 + 1)$
17010 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 + 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! - 1))$
17011 := $(1^3) \times ((5! \times 79) + 7531)$
17012 := $(1^3 + (5! \times 79)) + 7531$
17013 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3! - 1))$
17014 := $((135 + 79) + (7^5)) - (3! + 1)$
17015 := $((135 + 79) + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1)$
17016 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5! + (7 \times 9)) - 7)) + 5 \times (3 + 1)!$
17017 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5!) \times (7 - 9))) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1)!)$
17018 := $((1 + 3) + (5! + (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!)$
17019 := $((1 + 3) + 57) \times 9 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1))$
17020 := $((1 + 3) \times 57) + ((9 + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)!)$
17021 := $(1 \times (3! + 5)) + ((7! / (9 + 7)) \times (53 + 1))$
17022 := $(1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + 5! \times (3! \times 1)$
17023 := $(135 + 79) + (((7^5) + 3) - 1)$
17024 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5! + 7) + 97)) \times ((5! / 3!) - 1)$
17025 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5797 - (5! + 3 - 1))$
17026 := $((135 + 79) + (7^5)) + 3! - 1$
17027 := $((135 + 79) + (7^5)) + (3! \times 1)$
17028 := $((135 + 79) + (7^5)) + 3! + 1$
17029 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5797 - 5!))) - (3 - 1)$
17030 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times ((7 \times 9) + 7)) + (5 \times (3 + 1))$
17031 := $(1 \times (((3^5) - 7) - (9 - ((7^5) - 3)))) \times 1$
17032 := $(1 \times (((3^5) - 7) - (9 - ((7^5) - 3)))) + 1$
17033 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5797 - 5!))) + (3 - 1)$
17034 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5797 - 5!))) + (3 \times 1)$
17035 := $1 \times ((3 \times (5797 - 5!)) + 3 + 1)$
17036 := $(1 + (3 \times (5797 - 5!))) + (3 + 1)$
17037 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5) + ((79 + (7^5)) + 31)$
17038 := $(1 + ((35 \times 7) - (9 - ((7^5) - 3!)))) \times 1$
17039 := $(1 + ((35 \times 7) - (9 - ((7^5) - 3!)))) + 1$
17040 := $((1^3 + 5)! \times (7 + 9)) + (7! + (5! \times (3 + 1)))$
17041 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + (79 + ((7^5) + 31))$
17042 := $(1 - (((3 - 57) \times 9) \times 7) \times 5) + 31$
17043 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5))) - (3! - 1)$
17044 := $(1 \times (3!^5)) + (7 + (((9 + 7) + 5)^3 \times 1))$
17045 := $((1 + 35) \times 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) + (3! - 1))$
17046 := $((1 + 3) \times 57) + (((9 + (7^5)) + 3) - 1)$
17047 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) + 7)^{9-7} - (5! - 3! \times 1)$
17048 := $((1 + 3) \times 57) + (((9 + (7^5)) + 3) + 1)$
17049 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) + ((5! / 3) - 1)$
17050 := $((1 + 3) - 57) \times 9 + (((7^5) + 3!) \times 1)$
17051 := $(1 \times (3^5 + 7)) - ((9 - ((7^5) + 3)) \times 1)$
17052 := $(1 \times ((357 - 9) \times 7)) \times (5 + 3 - 1)$
17053 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5))) + (3! - 1)$
17054 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + (7^5)) - 3!) - 1)$
17055 := $((1 + 35) \times 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3! - 1))$
17056 := $(1 + (3^5 + 7)) - (9 - (((7^5) + 3!) + 1))$
17057 := $1 \times ((3 \times (5 + 79)) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1)))$
17058 := $1 + ((3 \times (5 + 79)) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1)))$
17059 := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) + (9 + (7^5)) - (3 - 1)$
17060 := $(13 + (5! \times 7)) \times (9 + (((7 - 5) \times 3!) - 1))$
17061 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 - 9) + (7 \times (5 + 31))$
17062 := $((1 + (35 - 7)) \times 9) + (((7^5) - 3!) \times 1)$
17063 := $((13 + 5) + 7) \times 9 + (7^5) + 31$

- 17064** := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) + (9 + (7^5)) + (3 \times 1)$
17065 := $((13 + (5 \times (7 \times 97))) + 5) \times (3! - 1)$
17066 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) + ((7 + (9 + (7^5))) + ((3! - 1))!)$
17067 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 97)) + (5! \times (3 + 1))$
17068 := $((1 + 3) \times 57) + (9 + (7^5)) + (3 + 1)!$
17069 := $((1 + 3)! - (5! - 7!)) + (97 \times (5^3 \times 1))$
17070 := $(1 \times (3! \times 5)) \times ((79 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3) + 1))$
17071 := $(1 \times (((3^5 + 7) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3!))) - 1$
17072 := $(1 \times (((3^5 + 7) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3!))) \times 1$
17073 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7) \times 9) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1))$
17074 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3))) - 1$
17075 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3))) \times 1$
17076 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3))) + 1$
17077 := $(1 + (3 + 5)) + (7! + (97 \times ((5! + 3) + 1)))$
17078 := $((1 + 3)! + (5! + (7! / ((\sqrt{9})!))) + ((7^5) + ((3! - 1))!)$
17079 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + ((9 - 7) + 531))$
17080 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) \times (((7 - 9) \times 7) - ((5^3) + 1))$
17081 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) + ((7 \times 9) \times 7) - 5 \times 31$
17082 := $13 \times (((5! + 7) + 97) - 5) \times (3! \times 1)$
17083 := $((1 - 3!) - (5! - 7!)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) - 1)$
17084 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + ((7^5) - 31)$
17085 := $((1 - (3 - 5!)) - (7! / 9)) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1))!)$
17086 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7! / (9 + 7)) - (5 + 31))$
17087 := $((1 - 3579) + 7!) + ((5^3!) \times 1)$
17088 := $((1 + (((3!)^5 - 7!) / 9)) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)!$
17089 := $(1 + 3!!) + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times ((5! + 3) + 1))$
17090 := $((1 \times (3 - 5!)) + (7! - ((97 - 5!)^3))) \times 1$
17091 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1))!$
17092 := $(1 \times (35 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 31)$
17093 := $(1 + (35 \times 7)) + (9 + ((7^5) + 31))$
17094 := $((1 + (3!! + 5)) - (((7 \times 9) - 7!) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)$
17095 := $(13 \times 5) \times (((797 - 5) / 3) - 1)$
17096 := $((13 \times 5) + 7!) + 9 - (7 \times 5!) \times (3 + 1)$
17097 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + ((9 - 75) + ((3! \times 1))!))$
17098 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) - (79 \times (((7 - 5!) - 3!) + 1))$
17099 := $((1 \times 3 - 5)^7)^{9-7} - 5 + (3!! \times 1)$
17100 := $((1^3 + 5)! / (7 + 9)) \times (((7 + 5!) \times 3) - 1)$
17101 := $(1 + (357 - 9)) \times (7 \times (5 + 3 - 1))$
17102 := $((1 - 3!)^5 + 7!) \times 9 - 7 - ((5! + 3!) \times 1)$
17103 := $(1 - 3)^{5 - (7-9) \times 7-5} + 3!! - 1$
17104 := $(1 - 3)^{5 - (7-9) \times 7-5} + 3!! \times 1$
17105 := $(1 - 3)^{5 - (7-9) \times 7-5} + 3!! + 1$
17106 := $((1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1)$
17107 := $1 - ((3! - ((5! - 7) \times 9)) - ((7^5) + 3 - 1))$
17108 := $((1 + ((3 \times 57) + 9)) + (7^5)) + ((3! - 1))!$
17109 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (7 \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1)$
17110 := $((1 \times (3^5)) + (7 \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)$
17111 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + (7^5) - (3 + 1)$
17112 := $((1 \times 3!) \times ((5 + (7 \times 9)) \times (7! / 5!))) - (3 + 1)!$
17113 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) - 1)$
17114 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) \times 1)$
17115 := $(1 + ((3! + 5) + 7) \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
17116 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) \times ((7 \times 9) + 75) + (3 + 1)$
17117 := $((1 - 3!)^5 + 7!) \times 9 + (7 - ((5! + 3!) - 1))$
17118 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
17119 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) + 9)) + (7^5) + (3 + 1)$
17120 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5^3) - 1))$
17121 := $(1 - (3! - (5 \times (7 \times 9)))) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)$
17122 := $(1 + 3) + (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1))$
17123 := $((135 + 79) \times 7) + ((5^3!) \times 1)$
17124 := $((135 + 79) \times 7) + ((5^3!) + 1)$
17125 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 - (975 / (3 \times 1)))$
17126 := $((1^3 \times (5! + 79)) + (7^5)) + ((3! - 1))!$
17127 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9)) + (7^5))) - (3 + 1)!$
17128 := $((1 - 3!) + (((5 + 7!) - 9) - (7 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
17129 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) + (5! - (3 - 1))$
17130 := $(1 \times ((3! \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7! - 5!) \times 3))) \times 1$
17131 := $(1 \times ((3! \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7! - 5!) \times 3))) + 1$
17132 := $1 \times (3! + ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)))$
17133 := $1 + (3! + ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)))$
17134 := $1 + (((3^5) \times (7 + (9 \times 7))) + (5! + 3 \times 1))$
17135 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (97 + 5) \times 3! - 1$
17136 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (97 + 5) \times 3! \times 1$
17137 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (97 + 5) \times 3! + 1$
17138 := $((1 + 3^5) + (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1))!$

- 17139** := $(1 + 3)! + ((5 \times 7) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3 + 1))$
17140 := $((1 + 3^5) \times (7 + (9 \times 7))) + (5! / (3 - 1))$
17141 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) + 7)^{9-7} - (5! / 3! \times 1)$
17142 := $((13 - (5 - 7)) \times (9 \times (7 + 5!))) - (3 \times 1)$
17143 := $((1^3 \times 5) + ((79 \times 7) - 5)) \times 31$
17144 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9))) + (((7^5) - 3!) - 1)$
17145 := $((1^3 + 5)! / (7 + 9)) \times ((7 + 5!) \times 3) \times 1$
17146 := $((1^3 + 5)! / (7 + 9)) \times ((7 + 5!) \times 3) + 1$
17147 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 5) + (797 + (5^{3!} \times 1))$
17148 := $(1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! - (9 + (7 \times 5))) + 3! \times 1)$
17149 := $(1 \times (3 + (5 \times (7 \times 9)))) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!)$
17150 := $(1 + (((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9)) + (7^5))) - (3 - 1)$
17151 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5797) - (5! \times (3 - 1))$
17152 := $((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3) \times 1$
17153 := $((1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9))) + (7^5)) + (3 - 1)$
17154 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
17155 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9))) + (((7^5) + 3) + 1)$
17156 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9))) + (((7^5) + 3) + 1)$
17157 := $(13 + 5!) \times (((7 \times 9) + (7 \times 5)) + 31)$
17158 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9))) + (((7^5) + 3!) + 1)$
17159 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (((7 - 9) + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1))$
17160 := $((1^{3!} \times 5!) \times (7 + (97 + ((5! / 3) - 1)))$
17161 := $((1 \times 3) - 5!) - 7 - ((9 - 7) + 5)^{3-1}$
17162 := $(1 + 357) - (9 - ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
17163 := $(1 \times 3) - ((5! / (7 - (9 - 7))) \times (5 - 3! \times 1))$
17164 := $(1 \times 3! \times 57) + ((9 + ((7^5) + 3!)) \times 1)$
17165 := $(1 \times 3! \times 57) + ((9 + ((7^5) + 3!)) + 1)$
17166 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5! - 7) + ((97 - 5!) \times 3!)) + 1))$
17167 := $(1 + 3!) + ((579 - 7) \times (5! / (3 + 1)))$
17168 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5))) + ((3! - 1)!)$
17169 := $((1 - 3!)^5 + 7!) \times 9 - ((7 \times 5) + 31)$
17170 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 7) + 9 \times (7 + ((5 - 3) + 1))$
17171 := $((1^3 \times 5) \times 79) + ((7^5) - 31)$
17172 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (57 + 9)) + (7^5) - 31$
17173 := $13 \times ((5 \times ((797 - 5) / 3)) + 1)$
17174 := $(1 \times 3 + (5 \times 79)) + ((7^5) - 31)$
17175 := $(1 \times (((3 \times 5!) - (7 + 9)) + (7^5))) + (3 + 1)!$
17176 := $(1 \times 357 + 9) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)$
17177 := $(1 \times 357 + 9) + (((7^5) + 3) + 1)$
17178 := $((1 \times 3! + 5) + 7!) + (9 \times 75) \times (3 \times 1)$
17179 := $(1 \times (357 + 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))$
17180 := $((1 - 3!)^5 - 7) / 9 + (((7^5) + 3!) + 1)$
17181 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) + 7)^{9-7} + (5! / 3! \times 1)$
17182 := $(1 - (3^5)) \times ((7 - (9 + 75)) + (3! \times 1))$
17183 := $((1 \times (3! + (5 \times 7))) \times 9) + (((7^5) + 3!) + 1)$
17184 := $((1^{35}) - 7) \times ((9 + 7) - (5! \times (3 + 1)!))$
17185 := $((1^3 + 5)! \times (7 + 9)) + 7! + (5^{3+1})$
17186 := $1 \times (((357 - 9) + (7^5)) + 31)$
17187 := $1 + (((357 - 9) + (7^5)) + 31)$
17188 := $((1 + 3) \times 57) \times 9 + (((7! + 5) \times 3) + 1)$
17189 := $((1 + (3! + (5 \times 7))) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1)$
17190 := $((1^3 + 5)! / (7 + 9)) \times (((7 + 5!) \times 3) + 1)$
17191 := $1 - ((3! - (5 \times 79)) - (7^5)) + 3! \times 1$
17192 := $1 - ((3 \times 5) - ((7! - ((97 - 5!)^3)) - 1))$
17193 := $1 - ((3 - (5 \times 79)) - ((7^5) - (3! + 1)))$
17194 := $1 - ((3! - (5 \times 79)) - ((7^5) - (3 \times 1)))$
17195 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) - (3 - 1))$
17196 := $(1 - (3 - (5 \times 79))) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1)$
17197 := $(1 - (3 - (5 \times 79))) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)$
17198 := $(1 - (3 - (5 \times 79))) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1)$
17199 := $((1357 \times 9) + 7!) - (53 + 1)$
17200 := $(1 - 3) - (5 - ((7! - ((97 - 5!)^3)) \times 1))$
17201 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (57 + 9)) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1))$
17202 := $(1 \times (3! - 579)) \times ((7 + 5!) - (3! - 1))$
17203 := $(1^3 - 5) + ((7! - ((97 - 5!)^3)) \times 1)$
17204 := $(1 \times (3 - 5)) + ((7! - ((97 - 5!)^3)) - 1)$
17205 := $((1^{3!}) + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3)) - 1$
17206 := $((1^{3!}) + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3)) \times 1$
17207 := $((1^{3!}) + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3)) + 1$
17208 := $(1^3 + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3!)) - 1$
17209 := $(1^3 + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3!)) \times 1$
17210 := $(1^3 + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3!)) + 1$
17211 := $(1 + (3! \times (57 + 9))) + ((7^5) + (3! + 1))$
17212 := $(135 - 797) \times (5 - 31)$

$$\begin{aligned} 17213 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3) + 1 \\ 17214 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) \times ((7! + (97 - 5!)) + (3!! + 1)) \\ 17215 &:= (1 \times 3!!) - ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 17216 &:= (1 + (3 + (5 + 7!))) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1) \\ 17217 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7! - ((97 - 5!)^3)) + 1) \\ 17218 &:= (1 \times 3! + (5 + 7!)) - (((97 - 5!)^3) \times 1) \\ 17219 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times (7 + 9 + (7 + (5! - 3)))) - 1 \\ 17220 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + (((5 \times 7) + 97) \times ((5^3) \times 1)) \\ 17221 &:= 13 + (((5 \times 79) + ((7^5) + 3!)) \times 1) \\ 17222 &:= 13 + (((5 \times 79) + ((7^5) + 3!)) + 1) \\ 17223 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 17224 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 17225 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7!)) + (9 \times (75 + ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\ 17226 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7! - (5^3)) - 1) \\ 17227 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7! - (5^3)) \times 1) \\ 17228 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) - 7) \times (97 - (5! / (3! - 1))) \\ 17229 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 17230 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5 \times 79) + (7^5)) + 3 + 1) \\ 17231 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5797 - 53))) - 1 \\ 17232 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5797 - 53))) \times 1 \\ 17233 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5797 - 53))) + 1 \\ 17234 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (57 + 9)) + (7^5)) + 31 \\ 17235 &:= 1 - ((3! + 5!) - ((7! / 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1)))) \\ 17236 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5!) \times ((79 + 7) + (53 \times 1)) \\ 17237 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5! - 7)) - (((97 - 5!) \times 3!!) + 1) \\ 17238 &:= ((1 \times 3579) + 7!) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1) \\ 17239 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5! - 7)) - (((97 - 5!) \times 3!!) - 1) \\ 17240 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 53) - 1) \\ 17241 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 53) \times 1) \\ 17242 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 \times 9)) + ((7 \times 53) + 1) \\ 17243 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!)) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 17244 &:= ((1 + 3!))! + ((5! - 7) \times (97 + ((5 + 3!) \times 1))) \\ 17245 &:= 13 + (((5! \times 7) - (9 - (7 - 5!))) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 17246 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) - (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 17247 &:= (((13 \times 5) \times 7) - (9 - (7^5))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 17248 &:= ((1^{35}) + ((7! / 9) + (7^5))) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 17249 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times ((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) - 5)) + 3!!) - 1 \\ 17250 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5!)) - (7 + 9)) \times (7 - (53 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17251 &:= (1 + (3! \times ((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) - 5))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 17252 &:= (1 + (3! \times ((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) - 5))) + (3!! + 1) \\ 17253 &:= (((1 + (35/7)))! - 9) + 7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1) \\ 17254 &:= ((13 \times 57) \times 9) - (7! - ((5^{3!}) \times 1)) \\ 17255 &:= (1357 \times 9) + (7! + ((5 - 3) \times 1)) \\ 17256 &:= (1 \times (3! / (5 + (7 - 9)))) \times ((7 + 5) \times (3!! - 1)) \\ 17257 &:= ((13 \times 5!) + (79 - 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\ 17258 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5! - ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5^3))) + 1) \\ 17259 &:= (((13 \times 5) \times 7) - (9 - (7^5))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 17260 &:= (1 - (35/7)) \times (9 - (7! + ((5 - 3!!) - 1))) \\ 17261 &:= (1 + (3! \times 57)) - ((9 - (7^5)) - ((3! - 1)!!)) \\ 17262 &:= (1^3 \times (5 - 7)) \times (9 - (7! + (5 \times 3!! \times 1))) \\ 17263 &:= ((1 - ((3 - 57) \times 9)) + (7^5)) - 31 \\ 17264 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5!) - ((7! + (9 \times 75)) \times 3))) + 1 \\ 17265 &:= (((135 \times 7) \times 9) + 7!) + (5! \times 31) \\ 17266 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times 7)) + 9) + ((7^5) - (3! - 1)) \\ 17267 &:= (((13 - 5) \times 79) - 75) \times 31 \\ 17268 &:= (((1 \times 3! \times 579) + 7!) + 5!) \times (3 - 1) \\ 17269 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!))) - (3! + 1) \\ 17270 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 17271 &:= ((1 - 3) \times 5!) - ((7 + 9) - ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!!)) \\ 17272 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! + 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1))) \\ 17273 &:= 1 \times ((3!! \times 5) + (7! + (97 \times (5! - 31)))) \\ 17274 &:= (((1 \times 3!))! - ((5 - 7!) + ((9 - 7) - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17275 &:= (((1 - (3! + 5!)) + 7!) + (97 \times 5!)) + (3!! \times 1) \\ 17276 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times (5! \times (7 + (9 + 7)))) - 5)) + (3!! + 1) \\ 17277 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5797)) - (5! - (3! - 1)) \\ 17278 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5! + 7) \times (97 + ((5! / 3) - 1))) \\ 17279 &:= (((1 + (3 - 5)) + 7)!) - ((97 - 5!) \times 3!!) - 1 \\ 17280 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 79) - 75)! \times ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 17281 &:= (((1 + (3 - 5)) + 7)!) - ((97 - 5!) \times 3!!) + 1 \\ 17282 &:= (((1 \times 3!))! - (5! - 7!)) + ((97 \times 5!) + 3 - 1) \\ 17283 &:= (1 \times 3) - (((57 - (9 \times 7)) \times 5!) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 17284 &:= ((1 \times (3! \times 5!)) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + ((5 + 3!!) - 1) \\ 17285 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (5! + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!))) + (3! - 1) \\ 17286 &:= 1 \times (3! \times (((5! + 7) - 97) \times 5!) - (3!! - 1)) \\ 17287 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5! \times ((7 - 97) - (53 + 1))) \\ 17288 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) \times (7 - 9)) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1) \\ 17289 &:= (13 \times ((5 + 7975) / 3!)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

- 17290** := $(13 \times 5) \times (797 - 531)$
17291 := $(13 \times ((5 + 7975)/3!)) + 1$
17292 := $(13579 - 7) + (5! \times 31)$
17293 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5! \times (7 - 9)) + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1))$
17294 := $((((1 + 3!) \times 5) - (7 - 9)) + 7!) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1)$
17295 := $((1 + (35 \times (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times 5) + ((3! + 1)!)$
17296 := $13579 + (7 \times 531)$
17297 := $((((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (7 + 9 + (7^5))) - 3!) \times 1$
17298 := $((((1 - 35) \times 7) + (9 + (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!)$
17299 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7) + (9 + 7)) \times ((5^3) + 1))$
17300 := $(1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7!/(9 + 7))) - 5)) \times (3! - 1)$
17301 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - (5 \times 3!))) \times 1$
17302 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - (5 \times 3!))) + 1$
17303 := $13 \times ((579 + 753) - 1)$
17304 := $(1 + 3)! \times ((5! + 7) + (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 31)))$
17305 := $(1 \times 3! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!)) - (3! - 1)$
17306 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 \times (7 \times (9 + 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1}))$
17307 := $((1357 \times 9) + 7!) + (53 + 1)$
17308 := $((1 \times (3 + 5)) \times (7 \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)$
17309 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (5 + 79)) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1))$
17310 := $((1 - 3!) - 5) \times ((7 - 9) - (((7 + 5)^3) + 1))$
17311 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + ((7!/9) + ((7^5) - 31))$
17312 := $((1 - 3) - ((5 - 7)^9)) + (((7^5) - 3!) + 1)$
17313 := $(((((1 - 3)^5) \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) + (3! + 1)$
17314 := $(((((1 + (3 + 5)) - 7)^9) + (7^5)) - 3!) + 1$
17315 := $((((1 + (3 + 5)) - 7)^9) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)$
17316 := $(1 \times 3! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!)) + (3! \times 1)$
17317 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 - 97) + (5! \times (3! - 1)))$
17318 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 - 97) - 5!) + (3! + 1))$
17319 := $((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)$
17320 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) - ((9 + 7) \times (5 - ((3! - 1)!)!))$
17321 := $(1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1)$
17322 := $((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) + (7^5) - (3 - 1)$
17323 := $((((1 + (3 + 5)) - 7)^9) + (7^5)) + (3 + 1)$
17324 := $((1 - 3) - (((5 - 7)^9) - (7^5))) + 3! + 1$
17325 := $((1 - ((3 - 57) \times 9)) + (7^5)) + 31$
17326 := $((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) + (7^5) + (3 - 1)$
17327 := $((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) + (7^5)) + (3 + 1)$
17328 := $((1 + 3)! \times (5 - 7)) \times ((9 - (7 \times 53)) + 1)$
17329 := $(1 - (3!/5)) - (7 \times ((9 + (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!)!)$
17330 := $1 \times ((3 + 5!) + ((7! - ((97 - 5!)^3)) \times 1))$
17331 := $1 + ((3 + 5!) + ((7! - ((97 - 5!)^3)) \times 1))$
17332 := $((1 + 3) - ((5! + 79) - (7^5))) + (3! \times 1)$
17333 := $(1 + 3) - (((5! + 79) - (7^5)) - (3! + 1))$
17334 := $((1 + (35 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7! \times (5 - (3 - 1)))$
17335 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5! - (79 + 7)) \times 531)$
17336 := $((1 - 3!) + 5) + ((7!/9) + ((7^5) - 31))$
17337 := $((1^{35}) + (7!/9)) + ((7^5) - 31)$
17338 := $((((13 + 5) + 7!)/9) + (7^5)) - 31$
17339 := $(1 + ((3 \times 5797) - 53)) \times 1$
17340 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!) + (3! - 1)$
17341 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times 7) + (((9 + 7) + (5^3)) - 1)$
17342 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5 + 79)) + ((7^5) + 31)$
17343 := $(1 \times (3! - 579)) \times ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1))$
17344 := $(1 + ((3!/(5 + 7)) \times 9)) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1)$
17345 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) - 31$
17346 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + 5!) + (3! \times 1)$
17347 := $(1 - ((3 \times 57) + 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! - 1))$
17348 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (((79 \times 7) - 5) \times 31)$
17349 := $(1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! - 9) + (753 - 1))$
17350 := $(1 \times (((3! + 5) \times (7!/(9 + 7))) + 5)) \times (3! - 1)$
17351 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! + 5) - 3! \times 1$
17352 := $(1 + 35) \times ((7 \times (9 + 7) + 53)) - 1$
17353 := $((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (7!/9)) - ((7 \times 5)/(3! - 1))$
17354 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + (7!/9))) + (7^5) - (3 + 1)!$
17355 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! + 5) - (3 - 1)$
17356 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7!/9) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1))$
17357 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7!/9) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1))$
17358 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) + ((7!/9) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
17359 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! + 5) + (3 - 1)$
17360 := $(1^{35}) \times (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 \times 31))$
17361 := $(1^{35}) + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 \times 31))$
17362 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5797) - (5 \times 3!) + 1$
17363 := $(1^{3!}) + ((579 + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)!)$
17364 := $(1^{35}) + ((7!/9) + (((7^5) - 3) - 1))$
17365 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5797) + (5 - 31)$

- 17366** := $(1 + 3) + ((579 + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)!)$
17367 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((9 - 753) \times 1))$
17368 := $((1 \times 3!) + (579 + (7^5))) - (3 + 1)!$
17369 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) - (3! + 1)$
17370 := $(1 - (3 - 5)) + ((7!/9) + (7^{5/(3+1)!}))$
17371 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) - (3! - 1)$
17372 := $((1 + 3) - (5 - (7!/9))) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))$
17373 := $(13 \times (5! + 7)) + (97 + ((5^3!) \times 1))$
17374 := $(1 - 35) \times (7 \times (9 - ((75 + 3!) + 1)))$
17375 := $1 \times ((3 \times (5797 + 5)) - 31)$
17376 := $1 + ((3 \times (5797 + 5)) - 31)$
17377 := $((1 + 3)^5) \times (7 + ((9 - 7) \times 5)) - 31$
17378 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) + ((7!/9) + ((7^5) + 3))) - 1$
17379 := $((1 \times 3!) + 57) \times 9 + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)$
17380 := $(1 - ((3 - 579) - ((7^5) - 3))) - 1$
17381 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5797)) - (5 \times (3 - 1))$
17382 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 \times 9)) + (7! + (5 \times (3! \times 1)))$
17383 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) + (3! + 1)$
17384 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 5797) - (5 + 3))) + 1$
17385 := $(1 - 3 + 5797) \times (5 - (3 - 1))$
17386 := $(1 - 3 + (579 + ((7^5) + 3))) - 1$
17387 := $(1 - 3 + (579 + ((7^5) + 3))) \times 1$
17388 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (57 \times 9)) \times ((7!/5!) \times (3 - 1))$
17389 := $1 \times 3! + ((579 + (7^5)) - (3 \times 1))$
17390 := $1 - (((3! - (5797 + 5)) \times 3) - 1)$
17391 := $(1 + 3!) - (5 - (((7! + (97 \times 5!)) - 3!) + 1))$
17392 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5! - 7)) - (((97 - 5!) \times 3!) + 1)$
17393 := $13 + ((5 \times 79) \times (75 - 31))$
17394 := $(1^3 - 5) + ((7!/9) + ((7^5) + 31))$
17395 := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) \times (9 + ((7 - 5) \times 31))$
17396 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((579 + (7^5)) + 3 + 1)$
17397 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5797 - 5) + 3!) + 1)$
17398 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((579 + (7^5)) + 3!) \times 1)$
17399 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((579 + (7^5)) + 3!) + 1)$
17400 := $(1 \times 3!) \times ((5 \times ((7 - 9) + 7)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)))$
17401 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5797)) + (5 \times (3 - 1))$
17402 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5797 + 5))) - (3 + 1)$
17403 := $1 + ((3 \times (5797 + 5)) - (3 + 1))$
17404 := $((1 + 3!) - 5!) + ((7 - (9 - ((7^5) - 3))) + 1)$
17405 := $((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) + 7! + ((97 \times 5!) + (3! - 1))$
17406 := $((1 + 3)! + (579 + (7^5))) - 3 - 1$
17407 := $((1 + 3)! + (579 + (7^5))) - 3 \times 1$
17408 := $((1 + 3)! + (579 + (7^5))) - 3 + 1$
17409 := $((1^3!) - (5! + 7)) + (((9 + (7^5)) + 3!) - 1)$
17410 := $(1 \times (3 \times (5797 + 5))) + (3 + 1)$
17411 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5! + 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1)$
17412 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 + 79) - ((7^5) - 31)))$
17413 := $(1 + 3!) + (5 + (7! + (((97 \times 5!) + 3!) + 1)))$
17414 := $((1 + 3) + (579 + (7^5))) + (3 + 1)!$
17415 := $135 + (((79 - 7) \times 5!) \times (3 - 1))$
17416 := $((1 \times 3!) + (579 + (7^5))) + (3 + 1)!$
17417 := $((1 + 3!) + (579 + (7^5))) + (3 + 1)!$
17418 := $1 \times (3 \times ((5797 + 5) + 3 + 1))$
17419 := $1 + (3 \times ((5797 + 5) + 3 + 1))$
17420 := $1 + (((3! - 5!) + 7) + ((9 + ((7^5) - 3)) - 1))$
17421 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) + (((79 \times 7) + 5) \times 31)$
17422 := $((1 + 3!)^5 - 7) - ((97 - (5! \times 3!)) + 1)$
17423 := $((1^3 + 5!) \times ((7 + 9) \times (7 + (5 - 3)))) - 1$
17424 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5 - 797) \times (5 + 3! \times 1))$
17425 := $1 + ((3 + ((5! \times 7) - 975))^{3-1})$
17426 := $((1 \times (3 - 5!)) + (7 + 9)) + (7^5) + 3! \times 1$
17427 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 7) + ((9 + 7!) + 5))) \times (3 \times 1)$
17428 := $((1 + (3 \times 5797)) + 5) + 31$
17429 := $((1 + 3!)^5 + (7 \times ((97 - 5) - 3))) - 1$
17430 := $(13 + 5797) \times (5 - (3 - 1))$
17431 := $1 + ((3 \times (5797 + 5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
17432 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5 + (7!/(9 - 7))) + ((5^3!) + 1))$
17433 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5!) - (7 - 9) + ((7^5) + (3 + 1)!)$
17434 := $1 - ((3 + (5 \times (7 - 97))) \times ((5!/3) - 1))$
17435 := $((13 + 57) \times 9) + (7^5) - (3 - 1)$
17436 := $1 \times (((3 \times 57) \times (97 + 5)) - (3! \times 1))$
17437 := $1 \times ((3 \times (5797 + 5)) + 31)$
17438 := $1 + ((3 \times (5797 + 5)) + 31)$
17439 := $1 - ((3 - (57 \times ((97 + 5) \times 3))) + 1)$
17440 := $1 - (3 - ((57 \times ((97 + 5) \times 3)) \times 1))$
17441 := $(1 + (3! - ((5 \times (7 + 9)) - (7^5)))) - (3! + 1)$

- 17442** := $((1 \times 3)!) + ((5! + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5 - 3) \times 1)$
17443 := $(1^3) \times ((57 \times ((97 + 5) \times 3)) + 1)$
17444 := $(1^3) + ((57 \times ((97 + 5) \times 3)) + 1)$
17445 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((5! - 7!) - (9 - ((7 - 5) \times (3!! \times 1))))$
17446 := $(1 \times (((3 - 5) - 7) \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1)$
17447 := $(1 + 3) + ((57 \times ((97 + 5) \times 3)) + 1)$
17448 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 \times 7)) - (9 - (7^5)) + (3!! \times 1)$
17449 := $(((((1 - 3) \times 5) \times 7) - 9) + (7^5)) + (3!! \times 1)$
17450 := $((1 + (3! + 5!)) \times 7) - (((97 - 5!) \times 3!!) - 1)$
17451 := $(1 + 3) \times 579 + ((7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
17452 := $1 - (3! + (5! - ((7 \times (9^{7-5})) \times 31)))$
17453 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - (((((7 - 9)^7) \times 5) - 3!) \times 1)$
17454 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((57 + 9 - (7^5)) + (3! + 1)))$
17455 := $(1 + (3!! - ((5 \times (7 + 9)) - (7^5)))) + (3! + 1)$
17456 := $((13 - 5) - (79 - (7^5))) + (3!! \times 1)$
17457 := $(13 - 5) - (((79 - (7^5)) - 3!!) - 1)$
17458 := $((1 \times 35) \times (7 - 9)) + (7^5) + (3!! + 1)$
17459 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5 \times 7)) - (9 - ((7^5) - (3 + 1)!))$
17460 := $((1 \times 3)^5) \times (79 - 7) - (5 + 31)$
17461 := $(1^3) \times (((5 + 7) \times 97) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1$
17462 := $(1^3) + (((5 + 7) \times 97) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1$
17463 := $(1 \times 3!!) + (5 - ((7 \times 9) - ((7^5) - 3! \times 1)))$
17464 := $((1 \times (3!! \times (5 + 7))) + (97 - 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
17465 := $1 \times (35 \times ((79 \times 7) - (53 + 1)))$
17466 := $1 + (35 \times ((79 \times 7) - (53 + 1)))$
17467 := $((1 \times 3)! \times 5!) - (((7 \times 9) - (7^5)) - (3 \times 1))$
17468 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 57) - 9 + ((7^5) + (3! + 1))$
17469 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5797 - (5 - 31))$
17470 := $(13 - 5!) + (7 \times ((9^{7-5}) \times 31))$
17471 := $(135 + (7!/9)) + ((7^5) - 31)$
17472 := $((1^3 - 5!) - (79 \times 7)) \times (5 - 31)$
17473 := $(13 + ((5 + 7) \times (97 \times (5 \times 3)))) \times 1$
17474 := $13 + (((5 + 7) \times (97 \times (5 \times 3))) + 1)$
17475 := $1 + (3!! - (((5 + 79) - (7^5)) - 31))$
17476 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
17477 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 \times 7)) - (((9 - (7^5)) - 3!!) + 1)$
17478 := $((1 - 3)^5) - (((7 + 9) - (7^5)) - 3!!) - 1$
17479 := $((1 - 3)^5) - (((7 + 9) - (7^5)) - 3!!) \times 1$
17480 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + 7!)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5 + ((3! - 1)!))$
17481 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5797 + (5 \times (3! \times 1)))$
17482 := $(1 + 3) - ((57 - 9) - (((7^5) + 3!!) - 1))$
17483 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5 + 7) \times (97 \times (5 \times 3)))) - 1$
17484 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5 + 7) \times (97 \times (5 \times 3)))) \times 1$
17485 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5 + 7) \times (97 \times (5 \times 3)))) + 1$
17486 := $(1 + 3)! - ((57 + (9 - ((7^5) + 3!!))) - 1)$
17487 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (797 - 5!) + (3 \times 1)$
17488 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3! - 1))$
17489 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! + (7!/9)) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
17490 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((57 - 9) + 7) \times (53 \times 1))$
17491 := $((1 + 3!) + 5!) + ((7!/9) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1))$
17492 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5 - 7)) - ((9 - (7^5)) + (3 + 1)!)$
17493 := $(1 \times 357) \times ((9 \times (7 - 5)) + 31)$
17494 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + (7^5)) - 3!) - 1)$
17495 := $(1 - ((35 + 7) - (9 + (7^5)))) + (3!! \times 1)$
17496 := $((1 + 35) \times (7 + (9 - 7))) \times (53 + 1)$
17497 := $(1 - 3) + (57 \times (((97 + 5) \times 3) + 1))$
17498 := $((1 + ((3^5) \times ((79 - 75)!)) \times 3) - 1)$
17499 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5797 + 5) + 31)$
17500 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((79 \times 7) - 53)) \times 1$
17501 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((79 \times 7) - 53)) + 1$
17502 := $((1^3 - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 3!!)) \times 1$
17503 := $((1^3 - (5 \times 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 3!!)) + 1$
17504 := $(1 - 3) - (5 + ((7 + 9) - ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!))))$
17505 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (((7! + (9 \times 75)) \times 3) \times 1)$
17506 := $(1 + (3! \times 5!)) - (((7 + 9) - (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)$
17507 := $(1 + (3 \times 5797)) + (5! - (3! - 1))$
17508 := $1 \times ((3 \times 5797) + (5! - (3 \times 1)))$
17509 := $1 + ((3 \times 5797) + (5! - (3 \times 1)))$
17510 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5! \times (7 + 97)) - 5)) + ((3! + 1)!)$
17511 := $(1 + 3!!) + ((5 - 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) + (3! \times 1)))$
17512 := $(1^{35}) - (7 + (9 - ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1)))$
17513 := $1 \times ((3!! + 5!) + (7! + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!) - 1)))$
17514 := $1 + ((3!! + 5!) + (7! + (((97 \times 5!) - 3!) - 1)))$
17515 := $((135 \times 7) \times (9 - 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
17516 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7) + 975 \times (3 - 1)$
17517 := $(1^{3!}) + (((5 - 7) - (9 - (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!))$

$$\begin{aligned} 17518 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) - (9 - 7)) \times 531) \\ 17519 &:= (((1 - 3!)/5)^7) \times ((9 - (7^5)) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 17520 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + (7! - (9 \times 75))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 17521 &:= 1 - (3! \times (5! - (7! - (((9 + 7) \times (5^3)) \times 1)))) \\ 17522 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) - ((7 - 9) \times (7! + (5! \times 31))) \\ 17523 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + (((5 - 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) - 3!)) + 1) \\ 17524 &:= 13 \times ((5 - 7) + (9 \times (75 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 17525 &:= 1 - (3! - ((5 + (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1))) \\ 17526 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 7) - (9 - 7)) \times 531) \\ 17527 &:= (1 \times (3!! - 5)) + (7 - ((9 - ((7^5) + 3!)) - 1)) \\ 17528 &:= ((1^{3579}) + (7^5)) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 17529 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 \times 7) - (9 - 7)) \times 531) \\ 17530 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! - (5 + ((7 - 9) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1))) \\ 17531 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7))/9) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1))!) \\ 17532 &:= (1 \times (3!! - 5)) + ((7 + 9 + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1) \\ 17533 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) - ((7 - 9) - (((7^5) + 3!!) + 1)) \\ 17534 &:= (1 + ((3! - 5!) \times 7)) \times (9 - ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1))) \\ 17535 &:= (((1^{357}) \times 9) + (7^5)) + 3!! - 1 \\ 17536 &:= (((1^{357}) \times 9) + (7^5)) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 17537 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5) - (7 - (9 + (7^5)))) + ((3! \times 1))! \\ 17538 &:= ((1 + (3!! + 5)) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5! \times (3! + 1)) \\ 17539 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5 - (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + (3!! - 1))) \\ 17540 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + (5 - ((7 - 9) - ((7^5) + 3! \times 1))) \\ 17541 &:= ((1 + (35/7))!) + ((9 + (7^5)) + (3! - 1)) \\ 17542 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times (97 + 5)) - 3) + 1 \\ 17543 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (57 + ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3))) \times 1 \\ 17544 &:= (1 \times 3!!) - (5 - ((7 + 9 + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 17545 &:= (1 \times (3! \times (5 + (7 - 9)))) + ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1) \\ 17546 &:= ((1 + 35) - (7 + (9 - (7^5)))) + (3!! - 1) \\ 17547 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5797 + (53 - 1)) \\ 17548 &:= (1 + (3!! + (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)))) - (3 + 1)! \\ 17549 &:= (((1 + 3) - (5 - 7)) \times (975 \times 3)) - 1 \\ 17550 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5 \times 7) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3!!) - 1))) \\ 17551 &:= (13 - (((5 - 7) - 9) - (7^5))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 17552 &:= ((1 + 3!) - 5) \times (7 + ((9 + 7!) + (5! \times 31))) \\ 17553 &:= (((1 + (3 \times 5!)) \times (7 + 9)) + 75) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17554 &:= (1 \times (3!! + 5)) + ((7 + 9 + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1) \\ 17555 &:= (1 + (3!! + 5)) + ((7 + 9 + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17556 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1))!) \\ 17557 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5 + (7 - 9)))! + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1))!)) \\ 17558 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5) + 7) + (9 + (7^5)) + ((3! \times 1))! \\ 17559 &:= (((13 \times 57) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3)) - 1 \\ 17560 &:= (((13 \times 57) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3)) \times 1 \\ 17561 &:= (((13 \times 57) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3)) + 1 \\ 17562 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5 - 7)) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1) \\ 17563 &:= (13 \times (5! + (7 - (9 - 75)))) \times (3! + 1) \\ 17564 &:= (((1 \times 3!))! + (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + (7^5)) - 3!) - 1) \\ 17565 &:= 1 + ((3! \times (5 - 7)) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1)) \\ 17566 &:= (1 - 3) + (((5! \times (7 + 9)) + (7!/5)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 17567 &:= 1 \times ((3 \times 5!) + ((7! - ((97 - 5!)^3)) \times 1)) \\ 17568 &:= ((1 + 3) \times ((5 + 7) \times 9 + 75)) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 17569 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5))) + (3!! \times 1) \\ 17570 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5 \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5))) + (3!! + 1) \\ 17571 &:= (1^3 + (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + (7^5)) + 3!!) - 1) \\ 17572 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) \times 7) + ((97 + 5)^{3-1}) \\ 17573 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! + (7 \times (97 \times 5))) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 17574 &:= (1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1))! \\ 17575 &:= (1^3!) + ((5 - 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1)) \\ 17576 &:= ((1 \times (3! + (5 \times (7 - (9 - 7)))))) - 5^3 \times 1 \\ 17577 &:= (1^3 \times (5 + 7 + 9)) \times ((7 \times 5!) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 17578 &:= 1 + ((3 - (5! \times 7)) \times ((97 - (5! - 3)) - 1)) \\ 17579 &:= (1 \times (3!! - ((5 - (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 17580 &:= ((1 \times 3!))! + ((5 + 79) + ((7^5) - 31)) \\ 17581 &:= (((1 - 3!) - (5 - (7 \times 9))) + (7^5)) + (3!! + 1) \\ 17582 &:= (1 \times (3!! - ((5 - (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 17583 &:= (1 + 3!!) - ((5 - (7 \times 9)) - ((7^5) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 17584 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((((5 - 7) + 9))! + 75) - (3!! - 1)) \\ 17585 &:= (((1^3!) + 5))! + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) - (3! - 1)) \\ 17586 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times (7^{9-7})) - (53 + 1) \\ 17587 &:= (13 + 5) - (7 + ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1)) \\ 17588 &:= (1 \times (3!! - ((5 - (7 \times 9)) - (7^5)))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 17589 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + 797) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 17590 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5) \times (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) + 3!! \times 1) \\ 17591 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - 5) + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) + 3!! \times 1) \\ 17592 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((7 - 9) \times (7! - 5!)) + (3 + 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17593 &:= (((1+3!)^5) + (7 + ((9 \times 7) - (5 - 3!)))) + 1 \\ 17594 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5!) + (7 \times 9)) + (((7^5) + 3) + 1) \\ 17595 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 57)) + (9 + (7^5))) + 3!) - 1 \\ 17596 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 57)) + (9 + (7^5))) + 3!) \times 1 \\ 17597 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 57)) + (9 + (7^5))) + 3!) + 1 \\ 17598 &:= ((1+3)! + 57) - ((9 - ((7^5) + 3!)) + 1) \\ 17599 &:= ((1^3 + 5)!) + (((79 + (7^5)) - 3!) - 1) \\ 17600 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5!)) + 79) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 17601 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + 5) + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1) \\ 17602 &:= ((1 - 3!) + ((5! \times 7) - (9 - (7^5)))) - 31 \\ 17603 &:= (1 \times (3^5)) + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 17604 &:= 1 + (3^5 + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 \times 31))) \\ 17605 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 17606 &:= (1^{35}) + (79 + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)) \\ 17607 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 5) + (79 + (7^5))) - (3 + 1) \\ 17608 &:= ((1^3 + 579) - (7 + 5)) \times 31 \\ 17609 &:= 1 - ((3 - (5! + 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + ((5^3) + 1))) \\ 17610 &:= ((1 - (3! \times 5)) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5!/3))) - 1 \\ 17611 &:= (((1+3!)^5) + 797) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 17612 &:= ((1^3 + 5) + (79 + (7^5))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 17613 &:= 1 + 35 + (7 \times ((9^{7-5}) \times 31)) \\ 17614 &:= (13 - ((5 - 79) - (7^5))) + 3! \times 1 \\ 17615 &:= (13 - ((5 - 79) - (7^5))) + (3! + 1) \\ 17616 &:= (1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - ((9 - 7) \times (53 \times 1))) \\ 17617 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5) + (((7!/(9 - 7)) - 5) \times (3! + 1)) \\ 17618 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((57 \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!)) - 1) \\ 17619 &:= (((1+3!)^5) + 797) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1) \\ 17620 &:= ((1+3!)^5) + (797 + ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 17621 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((5! + 797) \times (5!/3! \times 1)) \\ 17622 &:= (((1^3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) + 3! - 1 \\ 17623 &:= (((1^3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 17624 &:= (13 - 5) \times ((7 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - (3 - 1)) \\ 17625 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5!) + ((7! + (9 \times 75)) \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 17626 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 17627 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + ((7^5) - 3!)) + 1 \\ 17628 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 + 9) - ((7 \times 5!) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 17629 &:= (1 - 3 + (5! - ((7 + 9) - (7^5)))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17630 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5 - (((7 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 17631 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5797) + (5! \times (3 - 1)) \\ 17632 &:= (1^3 \times 57) - (((9 - (7 \times 5))^3) + 1) \\ 17633 &:= (1 - (3 - ((5 \times (7!/(9 - 7))) - 5))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 17634 &:= (1^3) \times ((5! \times 7) - ((9 - ((7^5) - 3)) + 1)) \\ 17635 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) + (9 + 7)) \times 5! - (3! - 1) \\ 17636 &:= (1^3) + ((5! \times 7) - (9 - (((7^5) - 3) \times 1))) \\ 17637 &:= 1 \times ((3 + (5! \times 7)) - ((9 - ((7^5) - 3)) + 1)) \\ 17638 &:= 1 + ((3 + (5! \times 7)) - ((9 - ((7^5) - 3)) + 1)) \\ 17639 &:= (((1 - 3) - ((5 + 7) - (9 \times 7))) \times (5! \times 3)) - 1 \\ 17640 &:= (1 + 3)! \times ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 75)/(3 + 1))) \\ 17641 &:= (((1 - 3) - ((5 + 7) - (9 \times 7))) \times (5! \times 3)) + 1 \\ 17642 &:= ((13 - 5) \times (7 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5)))) + (3 - 1) \\ 17643 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5 + 79) + (7^5)) + 31) \\ 17644 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7) + 5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 17645 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) + (9 + 7)) \times 5! + (3! - 1) \\ 17646 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5 - 7) + 9) \times (7!/(5 - (3 \times 1)))) \\ 17647 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5 + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5!/3)) - 1)) \\ 17648 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5!)) + ((7 - (9 - (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 17649 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)))) + (3! - 1) \\ 17650 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + ((5! + (7 - 9)) + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)) \\ 17651 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + ((5! + (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 17652 &:= (13 + (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 75)) \times 3!)) - 1 \\ 17653 &:= (13 + (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 75)) \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 17654 &:= (13 + (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + 75)) \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 17655 &:= (13 + ((5 + 7) \times 97)) \times (5 \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 17656 &:= 1 + (3 \times ((5! \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + (5^{3!-1}))) \\ 17657 &:= 1 \times ((3! + ((5! + (7 + 9)) + (7^5))) - 3! \times 1) \\ 17658 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5) \times 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 17659 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3! + 1)) \\ 17660 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times (7^{9-7})) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 17661 &:= 135 + (((7 - (9 - (7^5))) + 3!) + 1) \\ 17662 &:= 1 - (3 \times (5 - ((7 + 975) \times 3! \times 1))) \\ 17663 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! + ((9 + 7) \times 53))) - 1 \\ 17664 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! + ((9 + 7) \times 53))) \times 1 \\ 17665 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! + ((9 + 7) \times 53))) + 1 \\ 17666 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5! \times 7) + 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 17667 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! + ((9 + 7) \times 53)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17668 &:= ((1 \times 3!) / 5) + (((7 - 9) + ((7^5) + 3!)) - 1) \\ 17669 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5! + (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 17670 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (5 \times ((7 \times (9 - 7)) + 5))) \times 31 \\ 17671 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times ((5! / 3) \times 1)) \\ 17672 &:= (13 + 5) + (7 \times ((9 + (7! - 5)) / (3 - 1))) \\ 17673 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + (7! + (9753 \times 1)) \\ 17674 &:= ((1 \times 3!) / 5) - (((7 - 9) - ((7^5) + 3!)) - 1) \\ 17675 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5! + ((797 + 5) \times 3)) - 1) \\ 17676 &:= ((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7 + 975)) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 17677 &:= (((13 \times 57 - (9 - 7!)) + 5!) \times 3) + 1 \\ 17678 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 + 975)) + (3 - 1) \\ 17679 &:= (((13 \times (57 + 9)) + 7!) - 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17680 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 + 975)) + (3 + 1) \\ 17681 &:= (((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 - (7! - 5))) \times 3) - 1 \\ 17682 &:= ((13 \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 - (7! - 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17683 &:= (((1 - (3 \times 57)) \times ((9 + 7) - 5!)) + 3) \times 1 \\ 17684 &:= (((1 - (3 \times 57)) \times ((9 + 7) - 5!)) + 3) + 1 \\ 17685 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5!) \times 7)) - ((9 - (7^5)) - (3 + 1)) \\ 17686 &:= 1 - (((3! \times 5) - (79 \times 75)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 17687 &:= (1 \times ((3! \times 5!) - (7! / 9))) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 17688 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5!)) + (7 \times (9 - (7 - 5!)))) \times (3 + 1)! \\ 17689 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) + ((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 17690 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) - 9) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 17691 &:= (1 - (3! - ((5 \times 7) \times (97 \times 5)))) + (3!! + 1) \\ 17692 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times (7^{9-7})) + (53 - 1) \\ 17693 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 5!) \times (7^{9-7}))) + (53 \times 1) \\ 17694 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5!)) \times (7^{9-7})) + (53 + 1) \\ 17695 &:= (((1^3!) + 5)! + ((7 \times (97 \times 5)) \times (3! - 1))) \\ 17696 &:= ((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (9 + (7 \times (5! - 31))) \\ 17697 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 + (79 \times 75)) - 31) \\ 17698 &:= (1 - ((3! - 5!) - 7)) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1) \\ 17699 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5! + 7)) + 9) + ((7^5) - 3!) \times 1 \\ 17700 &:= (((1 + 3) + (579 + 7)) \times 5) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 17701 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times (97 \times 5)) + 3!) - 1 \\ 17702 &:= ((13 + 5) \times 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1) \\ 17703 &:= (((1 + 3!))! + ((5! \times 7) + ((9 + 7) + 5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17704 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7! / 9) - (7! + 5)) / (3! - 1)) \\ 17705 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((7 - 9) \times 7!) + (5! + 31)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17706 &:= (((1 \times 3 + 5!) + 7) \times (9 + 7)) + ((5^3!) + 1) \\ 17707 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 57) + 9)) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 17708 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) + (((7 \times 9) + (7^5)) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 17709 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 7) - (97 - (5! + ((3! + 1)!)))) \\ 17710 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5 + 79))) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 17711 &:= (1 + 3!) + (5 \times (((7 \times (97 \times 5)) + 3) \times 1)) \\ 17712 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) + (3! + 1)) \\ 17713 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + ((7 \times 9) + (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 17714 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5)^7) - (97 - ((5^3!) - 1)) \\ 17715 &:= (((13 + 5!) + 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3)) - 1 \\ 17716 &:= (((13 + 5!) + 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3)) \times 1 \\ 17717 &:= (((13 + 5!) + 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3)) + 1 \\ 17718 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7!) - (9 - (7 \times 5!))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17719 &:= ((1 + 3)^5) + ((7! / (9 + 7)) \times (53 \times 1)) \\ 17720 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + (5! + (79 + (7^5)))) - 3! \times 1 \\ 17721 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 + 7!) - (9 - (7 \times 5!))) + 31) \\ 17722 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5!) \times (79 - 7)) + 5) \times (3 - 1) \\ 17723 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) - ((3! - 1)!))) \\ 17724 &:= ((1^3 \times 5) + 79) \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3!)) + 1) \\ 17725 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (57 - ((9 - 7) + (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!)))) \\ 17726 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (57 + 9)) + (7^5)) + (3!! + 1) \\ 17727 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5797 + 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 17728 &:= ((1 + (3!! + (5 \times (7 + 9)))) + (7^5)) + ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 17729 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 + (975 + 3))) - 1 \\ 17730 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7 + (975 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 17731 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 + (975 + 3))) + 1 \\ 17732 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) + (79 \times ((7! / 5!) \times 3))) + 1) \\ 17733 &:= 1 \times (3 \times (5797 + (5! - (3! \times 1)))) \\ 17734 &:= 1 + (3 \times (5797 + (5! - (3! \times 1)))) \\ 17735 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 - 7)^9)) + ((7^5) + 3!) \times 1) \\ 17736 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5797 + (5! - 3!)) + 1) \\ 17737 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5!) - (79 \times ((7 - 5!) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 17738 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - (((7 - 97) - 5!) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 17739 &:= (((1 - 3!) - ((5 - 7)^9)) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 17740 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times 7) - (9 - 7) \times (5! / (3! \times 1)) \\ 17741 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - (79 - ((7! / 5) + (3! - 1))) \\ 17742 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5797 + (5! - (3 \times 1))) \\ 17743 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - (79 - ((7! / 5) + (3! + 1))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17744 &:= (13 \times (((5 + 79) + 7) \times 5) \times 3) - 1 \\17745 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3!))) - 1 \\17746 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3!))) \times 1 \\17747 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3!))) + 1 \\17748 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 \times 7) + 9) + 7) \times (5! - (3 + 1)) \\17749 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5797 + 5!)) - (3 - 1) \\17750 &:= 1 + ((3 \times (5797 + 5!)) - (3 - 1)) \\17751 &:= (1^3) \times ((5797 + 5!) \times 3) \times 1 \\17752 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5! + ((7! - (9 - 7)) - (5! \times 3! \times 1))) \\17753 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5797 + 5!)) + (3 - 1) \\17754 &:= 1 + ((3 \times (5797 + 5!)) + 3 - 1) \\17755 &:= 1 + ((3 \times 5 \times (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1)) \\17756 &:= (((((1 + 3^5) - 7) - 9) + (7^5)) + 3!) + 1 \\17757 &:= (((((135 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) - 3) - 1) \\17758 &:= (((((135 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) - 3) \times 1) \\17759 &:= (((((135 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) - 3) + 1) \\17760 &:= (1^3) \times ((57 - 9) \times ((7 \times 53) - 1)) \\17761 &:= (1^3) + ((57 - 9) \times ((7 \times 53) - 1)) \\17762 &:= (1 + (((3 \times 57) - 97) \times 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\17763 &:= (((((135 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) + 3) - 1) \\17764 &:= (((((135 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) + 3) \times 1) \\17765 &:= (((((135 \times 7) + 9) + (7^5)) + 3) + 1) \\17766 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) + (((7 - 9)^7) \times 5)) \times 3! \times 1 \\17767 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - ((79 \times 75) \times 3))) - 1 \\17768 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - ((79 \times 75) \times 3))) \times 1 \\17769 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - ((79 \times 75) \times 3))) + 1 \\17770 &:= (1^3 - 5) + ((79 \times (75 \times 3)) - 1) \\17771 &:= (1^3 - 5) + ((79 \times 75) \times (3 \times 1)) \\17772 &:= (((1 \times 35) + 7!) + (9 + (7 \times 5!))) \times (3 \times 1) \\17773 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 \times 79) \times ((7!/5!) + 3 \times 1)) \\17774 &:= (1 + 3!) - ((5! \times (7 - 9)) - ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))) \\17775 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5 \times 79) \times ((7 - (5 \times 3)) - 1)) \\17776 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + ((7 - (9 - (7 + 5)))^{3+1}) \\17777 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 - ((975 + 3) - 1)) \\17778 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5 + (((79 \times 75) - 3) - 1)) \\17779 &:= (((1 + 3!) + 5) \times 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1) \\17780 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + (79 \times (75 \times (3 \times 1))) \\17781 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + ((79 \times 75) - 3)))) - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17782 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + ((79 \times 75) - 3)))) \times 1 \\17783 &:= 13 - (5 - ((79 \times 75) \times (3 \times 1))) \\17784 &:= ((13 + 5) \times ((7 - (9 - 7)))!) + ((5^3) - 1) \\17785 &:= ((1 - 3) \times (5! \times ((7 - 9) - 7))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\17786 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5!) - (7!/(9 - 7)))) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\17787 &:= (1^3 + 5!) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) + ((5^3) - 1)) \\17788 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 \times (7 - 5)) + 3)) + 1 \\17789 &:= (((1^3 + 5!) \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) + (3 - 1) \\17790 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5! - (79 \times 7)) - (5^{3! - 1})) \\17791 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + (5! + 7)) \times (9 + (7 + 5))) + (3 + 1) \\17792 &:= 13 + ((5 + ((79 \times 75) \times 3)) - 1) \\17793 &:= (13 + (5 + ((79 \times 75) \times 3))) \times 1 \\17794 &:= (13 + (5 + ((79 \times 75) \times 3))) + 1 \\17795 &:= ((1^3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 97) + (5^{3! - 1}) \\17796 &:= 1 - (3! + ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7) - 531))) \\17797 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) \times 7) + (9 + (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\17798 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5 \times ((7 \times 97) + (5! \times (3 + 1)!))) \\17799 &:= (13 - (5 - (79 \times 75))) \times (3 \times 1) \\17800 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5! \times 79) - (7! - 5)) + (3! - 1)) \\17801 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5 - 79 + (7! + 5!))/(3 - 1)) \\17802 &:= (((1 - 3) - (5! + 7)) \times (97 - 5!)) \times 3! \times 1 \\17803 &:= (1 - (3! \times 57)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\17804 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5! \times 79) - (7! - 5)) + (3! \times 1)) \\17805 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5)) + ((79 \times 75) \times (3 \times 1)) \\17806 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 + (((9 - 7)^5) \times 31)) \\17807 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 - (9 \times 7)) \times 5)) + (3! \times 1) \\17808 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5 + 7) \times ((97 + 5!) - (3! - 1))) \\17809 &:= (((1 - 35) - 79)^{7-5}) + ((3! + 1)!) \\17810 &:= (((1 - 3!) + (5! - 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 31) \\17811 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((57 - 9) \times ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\17812 &:= 1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7)^{9-7}) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!) \\17813 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((57 - 9) \times (7 \times 53)) - 1) \\17814 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((57 - 9) \times ((7 \times 53) \times 1)) \\17815 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((5! - 7)^{9-7}) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!) \\17816 &:= (((1 + 3!)! / 5) + (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1) \\17817 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + 7!) - (9 - (7! - (5! / (3 + 1)))) \\17818 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 + 9)) + (((7^5) + 3) \times 1) \\17819 &:= 1 - (((3 - 57) - 97) \times ((5! - 3) + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17820 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5! - (7 \times (97 + 5))) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 17821 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\ 17822 &:= ((1 \times (3!/5)) \times 7) + ((9 + ((7^5) - 3)) + 1) \\ 17823 &:= (((((1 + 3!)^5) - 7) + 9) + ((7!/5) + 3!)) \times 1 \\ 17824 &:= (((((1 + 3!)^5) - 7) + 9) + ((7!/5) + 3!)) + 1 \\ 17825 &:= (1^3 + (57 \times (9 - 7))) \times (5 \times 31) \\ 17826 &:= (1^{3!}) - ((5 - ((7 - (9 - 7)))!) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 17827 &:= (1 \times (((3!^5) + 7!) - (9 - 7!))) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 17828 &:= (1 + (((3!^5) + 7!) - 9)) + (7! - (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 17829 &:= (((((1 + 3!)!/5) + 7) + (9 + (7^5))) - (3 - 1)) \\ 17830 &:= ((1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + 5)) - 31 \\ 17831 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + (5 - 31) \\ 17832 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times ((5 + 79) \times 7)) + (5! \times 31) \\ 17833 &:= ((1 + ((3!/5) - 7)) \times (9 + 7)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\ 17834 &:= (((1 + 3!)!/5) + (7 + 9 + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1))) \\ 17835 &:= ((1 \times 3 + 5!) \times (7 - (9 - 7))) \times (5 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 17836 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! + (9 + 7!)) - (5!/(3 + 1))) \\ 17837 &:= 1 - (((3! - ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) - (7^5)) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 17838 &:= 1 - (((3! - ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) - (7^5)) - (3! + 1)) \\ 17839 &:= (((1^{3!}) + (5! - 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 17840 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) + (((7^5) + 3!) \times 1) \\ 17841 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7!) + ((9 + 7!) - (5!/(3! - 1))) \\ 17842 &:= (13 + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times 7)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\ 17843 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + 9)) + (7 - 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 17844 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 + ((7 \times 9) \times 7)) \times (5!/(3 \times 1))) \\ 17845 &:= ((1^3 - 5!) \times ((7 - 9) \times 75)) - (3! - 1) \\ 17846 &:= ((1^3 - 5!) \times ((7 - 9) \times 75)) - (3 + 1) \\ 17847 &:= (1 - (35 - 7)) \times (((9 \times 7) - 5) - (3! - 1)) \\ 17848 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - ((579 - 7!) + 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 17849 &:= ((1 \times (3! \times 5)) \times 79) + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) - 1) \\ 17850 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (5 \times ((7 - 97) + (5! \times (3! - 1)))) \\ 17851 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!)) \\ 17852 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) + (79 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 17853 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7! + (9 - (7 + 5))) + ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 17854 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5) + 79) \times ((75 \times 3) + 1) \\ 17855 &:= ((1 \times ((3! \times 5) - 7)) \times 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\ 17856 &:= ((13 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) \times ((7 - 5) \times 31) \\ 17857 &:= ((1 \times ((3! \times 5) - 7)) \times 97) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17858 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) \times ((79 \times (7 - 5!)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 17859 &:= (1^3 \times 5) + (79 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 17860 &:= (1^3 + 5) + (79 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)) \\ 17861 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! + (9 - 7)) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\ 17862 &:= 13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) + 5) - (3 + 1)! \\ 17863 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5 \times (7 \times 9))) \times (7 \times (5 + 3))) - 1 \\ 17864 &:= ((1 + (((3 - (5 - 7)))! \times 9)) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 17865 &:= (13 + 5!) + (((7!/9) + (7 + 5)) \times 31) \\ 17866 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + (((7! \times (9 - 7)) + 5) + (3! - 1)) \\ 17867 &:= (1 \times (((3!^5) + 7!) - 9)) + (7! + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 17868 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + (79 \times 75))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17869 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (((7! \times (9 - 7)) + (5 + 3!)) + 1) \\ 17870 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7! + (9 - 7)) + 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 17871 &:= (1 + ((3 \times 5) + 7)) \times ((97 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\ 17872 &:= (1 \times (3! \times 5)) + (((7 - 9)^7) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 17873 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5! + (7 + (9 + 7))) \times (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 17874 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5! + 7) + ((9 \times (7 - 5))^3)) - 1) \\ 17875 &:= (13 \times ((57 - (9 - 7)) \times 5)) \times (3! - 1) \\ 17876 &:= ((1 + 357) - 9) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 17877 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5! + 7) + ((9 \times (7 - 5))^3)) \times 1) \\ 17878 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + (7 + (9 + (7! + 5)))) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 17879 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7)) \times (5 \times 3)) - 1 \\ 17880 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7)) \times (5 \times 3)) \times 1 \\ 17881 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7)) \times (5 \times 3)) + 1 \\ 17882 &:= ((1 \times 3)^5) + (((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times (5!/3)) - 1) \\ 17883 &:= (1 + (((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7) \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17884 &:= ((1 + (((3 - (5 - 7)))! \times 9)) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 17885 &:= (1 - 3) + (((579 - 7) + 5) \times 31) \\ 17886 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - ((5! \times (7 - 9)) \times 75)) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 17887 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + 79) + ((7!/5) - (3! + 1)) \\ 17888 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! - (7 + 9)) \times ((7 + 5) + 31)) \\ 17889 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 - 9) + 7)) - (5! - (3 + 1)) \\ 17890 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 - 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times 31) \\ 17891 &:= ((1 + (((3 - (5 - 7)))! \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 3)) \times 1 \\ 17892 &:= (1 + 35) \times ((7!/9) - (7 \times ((5 + 3) + 1))) \\ 17893 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + (5 + 31)) \\ 17894 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - (7 - 9)) + ((7 \times 5) \times 31) \\ 17895 &:= ((1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + 7)) \times 5) \times (3 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17896 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! + (9 + 7!)) + (5!/(3 + 1))) \\ 17897 &:= (((1 + (3!! \times 5)) - (7 + (9 + 7))) \times 5) + (3! + 1) \\ 17898 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7! + (9 + 7)) + 5) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 17899 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (((7! - 9) + 7!) + 53) - 1 \\ 17900 &:= (1 + (3!! - 5)) \times (7 - ((97 - 5!) + (3! - 1))) \\ 17901 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5!)) \times ((7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 17902 &:= (13 - (((5 - 7)^9) \times (7 \times 5))) - 31 \\ 17903 &:= (((1 + (3!^5))/7) - 9) + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1) \\ 17904 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + ((7 + (9 + (7^5))) + 3!!)) + 1 \\ 17905 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 - (7 - 97))) + (5^{3 \times 1}) \\ 17906 &:= (((1 + (3!^5))/7) - 9) + (7^5) - (3 \times 1) \\ 17907 &:= 13 + ((5! + ((79 \times 75) \times 3)) - 1) \\ 17908 &:= (1 - (3^5)) \times (7 - ((97 - (5 \times 3)) - 1)) \\ 17909 &:= (((1 \times (3!^5)) + (7! \times (9 - 7))) + 53) \times 1 \\ 17910 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5^3)))) - 1 \\ 17911 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5^3)))) \times 1 \\ 17912 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5^3)))) + 1 \\ 17913 &:= ((1 + 3!) + ((5 \times (7!/9)) + ((7! - 5) \times 3))) + 1 \\ 17914 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5!)) - ((7!/9) + 7)) \times (5 - 31) \\ 17915 &:= (((1 + (3!^5))/7) - 9) + (7^5) + 3! \times 1 \\ 17916 &:= ((1 \times (3!! + (5 \times 79))) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 17917 &:= ((1 + 3) - (5! - (79 \times 7))) \times ((5!/3) + 1) \\ 17918 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 \times (7 + 9)) \times ((75 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 17919 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!/5) + ((79 \times 75) \times (3 \times 1))) \\ 17920 &:= (((1 + (3 + 5)) - 7)^9) \times (((7 + 5) \times 3) - 1) \\ 17921 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7!/9) \times (7 - 5)) - 3! \times 1) \\ 17922 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5797)) + 531 \\ 17923 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5797)) + 531 \\ 17924 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7! + (((9 \times 7) + 5) + ((3! + 1)!))) \\ 17925 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7!/9) \times (7 - 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 17926 &:= (((1 \times 3!!) + (5 \times 79)) + (7^5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 17927 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 + (97 + 5!)) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 17928 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5! - (79 - 7!)) + 5!) - (3!! - 1)) \\ 17929 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7!/9) \times (7 - 5)) + 3 - 1) \\ 17930 &:= (((1 + (3!^5))/7) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1) \\ 17931 &:= (1 + 3)! - ((5! + 7) \times (9 - (75 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 17932 &:= (1 - (((3^5) - 7!) + (9 \times (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 17933 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7!/9) \times (7 - 5)) + 3! \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17934 &:= (1 + (3!!/5!)) \times (((79 + 7!) + 5)/(3 - 1)) \\ 17935 &:= (1 \times ((3!^5) + (79 + 7!))) + ((5 + 3 - 1)!) \\ 17936 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - 3!! \times 1)) \\ 17937 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + ((79 + (7! \times (5 - 3))) + 1) \\ 17938 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5!) + 7) \times 9) + (7^5) + 3! \times 1 \\ 17939 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 17940 &:= (13 \times 5) \times (((7 \times 9) + 75) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 17941 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + (79 + (7^5))) + 31 \\ 17942 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + ((7 - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3)) - 1) \\ 17943 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((57 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - (3! + 1)) \\ 17944 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((57 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 17945 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - 97)) + (5! - (3! + 1)) \\ 17946 &:= (1 - 3 + ((57 \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 17947 &:= (1 + 3^5) + (7 \times ((9 + (7 \times (5! \times 3))) \times 1)) \\ 17948 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - ((5! + (79 \times 7)) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 17949 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - 97)) + ((5! - 3) \times 1) \\ 17950 &:= 1 \times (3! + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 17951 &:= 1 \times (3! + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) - (3! - 1)) \\ 17952 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! \times 7) - (9 \times 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 17953 &:= (((135 - 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 17954 &:= ((1 + ((3! \times 5) - 7)) \times 97) + ((5^3!) + 1) \\ 17955 &:= 1 \times (35 \times (((7 + 97) \times 5) - 3!) - 1) \\ 17956 &:= ((1 + 3) - ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) + 5))^{3-1} \\ 17957 &:= 1 + (((3 - ((5 \times 7) + 97)) - 5)^{3-1}) \\ 17958 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5 - 7!))) + ((97 - 5) \times 31) \\ 17959 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((57 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 17960 &:= (1 - 3 + ((57 \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5)) + (3! + 1) \\ 17961 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + (7^5)) - 31 \\ 17962 &:= 13 + ((57 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - 3! \times 1) \\ 17963 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5)/7) - ((9 \times 7) - ((5^3!) \times 1)) \\ 17964 &:= (1 + 35) \times ((79 \times 7) - (53 + 1)) \\ 17965 &:= (((135 - 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 17966 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - (753 + 1) \\ 17967 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - (753 \times 1) \\ 17968 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! \times 79) - ((7! - 53) + 1)) \\ 17969 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + (5! - (3! + 1))) \\ 17970 &:= ((13 \times 5) + (79 \times 75)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 17971 &:= 1 - (((3^5) \times 7) + 9) - ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17972 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! \times 79) - (7! - (53 \times 1))) \\
 17973 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) + ((7! \times (9 - 7)) + (5! - (3 \times 1))) \\
 17974 &:= (13 + (57 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5)))) + 3! \times 1 \\
 17975 &:= ((1 - (35 + 7)) - (9 - 75)) \times (3!! - 1) \\
 17976 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + (7^5) - (3!! + 1) \\
 17977 &:= 1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times ((9 + 75) \times (3 - 1))) \\
 17978 &:= (((((1 \times 3)!^5) - 7) + (9 + 7!)) + 5!) + ((3! + 1)!) \\
 17979 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) - (3 + 1)!) \\
 17980 &:= ((13 + 579) - (7 + 5)) \times 31 \\
 17981 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) + (79 \times ((75 \times 3) + 1)) \\
 17982 &:= (13 + 5) \times (7! - (9 \times ((75 \times 3!) - 1))) \\
 17983 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7)))) \times ((5 + 3) - 1) \\
 17984 &:= (((13 + 5) + 7!)/9) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)) \\
 17985 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (((5 - 7!) + 9)/7) \times 5) \times (3! - 1) \\
 17986 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((57 \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5) + (3! + 1)) \\
 17987 &:= (1 + (3579 + 7)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17988 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - 7) + (9 \times ((7 + (5^3)) \times 1)) \\
 17989 &:= 1 \times ((35 \times (((7 + 97) \times 5) - 3!)) - 1) \\
 17990 &:= 1 + ((35 \times (((7 + 97) \times 5) - 3!)) - 1) \\
 17991 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - (((7 - 9) - (7! - 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 17992 &:= 13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) - (5 + 3)) - 1 \\
 17993 &:= (((1 \times 3)!)! \times ((5! + 7) - (97 + 5))) - (3! + 1) \\
 17994 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times (5 \times ((7 + 9) \times 75)))) - 3!) \times 1 \\
 17995 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((57 \times 9) \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\
 17996 &:= (((1 + 3)! - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times 7))) \times 5!) - (3 + 1) \\
 17997 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times 5) \times ((7 - (9 - 7)) \times 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \\
 17998 &:= (((1 + 3)^5) + 7975) \times (3 - 1) \\
 17999 &:= ((1^3 + ((5! + 7) + (9 + 7))) \times 5!) + (3!! - 1) \\
 18000 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times (7^{9-7})) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

2.10 Numbers From 18001 to 20000

$$\begin{aligned}
 18001 &:= 1 + (3!! \times (5! - (((7 + 97) - 5) - 3) - 1)) \\
 18002 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times 5) \times ((7 - (9 - 7)) \times 5!)) + (3 - 1) \\
 18003 &:= (1 - 3) - (5 \times (((7 - 97) \times (5!/3)) - 1)) \\
 18004 &:= (((1 + 3)! - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times 7))) \times 5!) + (3 + 1) \\
 18005 &:= (13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) - (5 + 3))) \times 1 \\
 18006 &:= (13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) - (5 + 3))) + 1 \\
 18007 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 \times (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\
 18008 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (((7! \times (9 - 7)) + 5!) + 31) \\
 18009 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) + (((7 - (9 - 7)) \times 5) \times 3!! \times 1) \\
 18010 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + (5! \times (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1) \\
 18011 &:= ((1^3 \times 579) + (7 - 5)) \times 31 \\
 18012 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + (5! \times (7 + 9))) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1) \\
 18013 &:= 13 - (((5 \times (7 - 9)) \times 75) \times (3 + 1)!) \\
 18014 &:= 1 - (3!! - (((5! \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)) \\
 18015 &:= ((1 + 3)! + ((57 \times 9) \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\
 18016 &:= (1 - (3!! \times ((5 - 7) \times 9))) + ((7! + (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\
 18017 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5!) \times (79 + 75))) - (3 - 1) \\
 18018 &:= ((1^3 + 5)!) + (((79 \times 7) + 5) \times 31) \\
 18019 &:= 1 + ((3! + 5) \times (7 \times ((9 + (75 \times 3)) \times 1))) \\
 18020 &:= (1 - 3 + ((5! \times 7) + (9 \times 7))) \times (5!/3! \times 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18021 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5!) \times (79 + 75))) + (3 - 1) \\
 18022 &:= (1 + (((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) \times 7) \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \\
 18023 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5 \times 79)) + (7^5)) + 31 \\
 18024 &:= (1 + 3)! - (5! \times (((7 - 9) + 7) - (5 \times 31))) \\
 18025 &:= ((1 - (35 + 7)) - (9 - 75)) \times (3!! + 1) \\
 18026 &:= 1 + (35 \times (((7 + 97) \times 5) - 3! + 1)) \\
 18027 &:= (((1^3 - 5!) + (7!/(9 - 7))) + (5^3!)) + 1 \\
 18028 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 - (7 - (97 - 5!))) \times (3!! + 1)) \\
 18029 &:= 1 \times (((3 - ((5 - 7)^9)) \times 7) \times 5) + 3 + 1) \\
 18030 &:= (13 \times (5 \times 7)) - (((9 - (7 \times 5))^3) + 1) \\
 18031 &:= 13 + (((5! + 7) + 9) + 7) \times ((5^3) + 1) \\
 18032 &:= ((13 \times (5 \times 7)) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3)) + 1 \\
 18033 &:= (((1 \times 3^5) + 79) \times (7 \times (5 + 3))) + 1 \\
 18034 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) \times ((7! - (9 + 7!)) + (5! + 31)) \\
 18035 &:= (1 \times 35) + (((7 - 9) + 7) \times ((5 \times 3!!) \times 1)) \\
 18036 &:= (((1 - 3!!) + 5) + (7 \times 9)) + (7! + 5!) \times (3 + 1) \\
 18037 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + ((5^3) + 1))) \\
 18038 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 \times 9) + ((7 \times 5) - (3!! \times 1))) \\
 18039 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (((5! - 7) + 9) \times 7) + 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\
 18040 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + ((5^3) + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18041 &:= 1 \times ((3 - ((5 - 7)^9) - (7^5))) + (3!! - 1) \\ 18042 &:= (1 \times (3 + 579)) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 18043 &:= ((1 + 3) + ((57 \times 9) + (7^5))) + (3!! - 1) \\ 18044 &:= ((1 + (3! - 57)) + (9 \times (7!/5))) \times (3 - 1) \\ 18045 &:= 1 \times (3 \times 5 \times (((7 + 9) \times 75) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 18046 &:= 1 + (3 \times 5 \times (((7 + 9) \times 75) + 3 \times 1)) \\ 18047 &:= 1 + (((3! + 5) \times (7!/(9 + 7))) \times 5) + (3!! + 1) \\ 18048 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times (((5^{7-9+7}) - 5!) + 3 \times 1) \\ 18049 &:= (1 \times 3!!) - ((5! + (79 - (7^5))) - (3!! + 1)) \\ 18050 &:= ((1 + ((3! + 5) \times (7!/(9 + 7)))) \times 5) + (3!! \times 1) \\ 18051 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (5 \times (7! + (((9 - 7) \times (5 - 3!!)) - 1))) \\ 18052 &:= ((1 + 3!!) - 5) + ((7!/9) + ((7^5) - 31)) \\ 18053 &:= (((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) \times 5) - (3! + 1) \\ 18054 &:= (((1 \times 3 + (57 \times 9)) \times 7) \times 5) - (3! \times 1) \\ 18055 &:= ((1 + (3579 + 7)) \times 5) + ((3! - 1)!) \\ 18056 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5!) \times (((7 - 9) \times 75) + 3 - 1) \\ 18057 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!) + 3!) - 1) \\ 18058 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times (7 - (9 \times ((7!/5) - 3) - 1)) \\ 18059 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times ((97 + 5) + 3)) - 1 \\ 18060 &:= ((1 + 3!)!) + ((5 + 7) \times ((97 + 5!) \times (3! - 1))) \\ 18061 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times ((97 + 5) + 3)) + 1 \\ 18062 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (((5! \times 7) + (9 \times 7)) \times 5)) + (3 - 1) \\ 18063 &:= (1 + 3)! + (((57 \times 9) + (7^5)) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 18064 &:= (1 + 3)! + (5 \times (7! + ((9 - 7) \times (5 - (3!! + 1)))))) \\ 18065 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (((5 - 7)^9) \times 7) - (5 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 18066 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times ((5^{7-9+7}) - (5! - 3! \times 1)) \\ 18067 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 - 9) \times (7!/(5 + 3 \times 1))) \\ 18068 &:= (13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) - 5)) + (3 + 1)! \\ 18069 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((5 - (7! - (97 \times (5! - 3!)))) \times 1) \\ 18070 &:= 1 - (((3^5) - (7!/9)) \times ((7 \times (5 + 3)) + 1)) \\ 18071 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1) \\ 18072 &:= (1 \times 3!) \times ((5^{7-9+7}) - (5! - (3! + 1))) \\ 18073 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 18074 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5!) + (7! + 9))/(7 - 5) \times (3! + 1) \\ 18075 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5) + ((7! + 975) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 18076 &:= ((1 + (3! + (5! + 7)))^{9-7}) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 18077 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 + 79) \times 7) - 5) \times 31 \\ 18078 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - (5 - ((7!/9) + (7^5)))) - (3 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18079 &:= (((135 - 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) + ((3! - 1)!) \\ 18080 &:= ((1 + 3!!) - 5) + (((7!/9) + ((7^5) - 3)) \times 1) \\ 18081 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! \times 7) + ((9 + 7) + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 18082 &:= (1 - (3! + 57)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 18083 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5!) + (((7!/9) + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)) \\ 18084 &:= (((1 - (3 - 5)))!) + ((7!/9) + ((7^5) - (3 \times 1))) \\ 18085 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + (5 + (((7 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 \times 31))) \\ 18086 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5) + (((7!/9) + (7^5)) + 3 + 1)) \\ 18087 &:= (1 + ((3 + (5 \times 7)) \times 97)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 18088 &:= (1 \times (((3! - 5) + (7!/9) + (7^5))) + 3!! \times 1) \\ 18089 &:= (1^3) - (((57 \times 9) - 7!) + 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 18090 &:= (13 + (5! - 79)) \times (((7!/5)/3) - 1) \\ 18091 &:= ((1 + 3!) - ((5! - 7!)/(9 - 7))) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\ 18092 &:= (1^{3!}) + (((5 + (7!/9) + (7^5)) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 18093 &:= 1 \times ((3! - 57) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 18094 &:= (1 + (3! - 57)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 18095 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) + 3!!) - 1 \\ 18096 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) + 3!!) \times 1 \\ 18097 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times (5797 - 5)) + 3!!) + 1 \\ 18098 &:= 1 \times (3!! + ((5 + (7!/9) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))) \\ 18099 &:= ((13 + 5) + (7! + 975)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 18100 &:= (((13 \times (5! + 79)) \times 7) - (5 + 3)) - 1 \\ 18101 &:= (1 + 3!!) + ((5 \times 79) \times (75 - 31)) \\ 18102 &:= (((13 \times (5! + 79)) \times 7) - (5 + 3)) + 1 \\ 18103 &:= 1 - ((35 + 7) - ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 18104 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + (79 \times 75))) - 31 \\ 18105 &:= 1 - (((3 - 5!) - 7) \times (9 - ((7 - 5!) - (3 + 1)!))) \\ 18106 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 79) + 7) \times (5 + 3! \times 1) \\ 18107 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5!) \times (7 - 9)) + 7 \times (5 - (3 + 1)!) \\ 18108 &:= 1 \times (((3! + 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 18109 &:= 1 + (((3! + 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7))) + 5!) \times 3! \times 1 \\ 18110 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + ((579 + (7^5)) + 3 + 1) \\ 18111 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5!) - ((7 + 9) - ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1)) \\ 18112 &:= (1 + (3 + (5! \times 79))) + ((7 + 5) \times (3!! - 1)) \\ 18113 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 + 53) - 1) \\ 18114 &:= (1 - (3! - (5! \times (79 + (75 - 3)))) - 1 \\ 18115 &:= (1 - (3! - (5! \times (79 + (75 - 3)))) \times 1 \\ 18116 &:= (((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + (7!/9) + (((7^5) + 3!!) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 18117** := $((1 \times 3)! \times 5) + (7!/9) + ((7^5) + 3!) \times 1$
18118 := $(1 - 3) + (5! \times ((79 \times (7 - 5)) - (3! + 1)))$
18119 := $((1 + 3!)!) + ((5! + 7!) + ((9 + (7 - 5)) \times 3!)) - 1$
18120 := $((((1 \times 3)!)/(5 + (7 - 9))) \times 75) + ((3! - 1)!)$
18121 := $((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 - 9) + 7)) + (5! - (3 + 1))$
18122 := $1 - (((3! + 5) \times (7 - 9)) \times (7 + 5)) - 3! - 1$
18123 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times 7) - (97 - 5!))) \times (3! + 1)$
18124 := $1 - ((3 \times (5! - (7!/9))) - ((7^5) - 3) - 1)$
18125 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + 97) \times 53 - 1$
18126 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + 97) \times 53 \times 1$
18127 := $((1 \times (35 \times 7)) + 97) \times 53 + 1$
18128 := $(1 - 3) - ((5 - 79) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3! + 1)$
18129 := $(1^3) - ((57 \times 9) - (7! + 5)) \times (3 + 1)$
18130 := $(1 \times ((3^5 + 7) + 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) \times (3 - 1))$
18131 := $((1 + 3)! + (579 + (7^5))) + 3! + 1$
18132 := $(1^3 - ((57 \times 9) - (7! + 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
18133 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) - (5 + (3! \times 1))$
18134 := $1 + (3 - ((5 - 79) \times (7 \times 5)) \times (3! + 1))$
18135 := $(1 \times 3! + 579) \times (((7 \times 5) - 3) - 1)$
18136 := $((((1 - 3)^5) \times 79) + 7!) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
18137 := $((((1 - 3)^5) \times 79) + 7!) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
18138 := $(1^{35}) - (7 - ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1)))$
18139 := $((1^{3!}) - 5) + (((7 \times 9) \times ((7!/5) - 3!)) - 1)$
18140 := $(1 - (35/7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))$
18141 := $((1^{3!}) - 5) + (((7 \times 9) \times ((7!/5) - 3!)) + 1)$
18142 := $((1^{3!}) - 5) + ((7!/(9 - 7)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
18143 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5!) + (7 + 9 + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1))$
18144 := $((1 - ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1)$
18145 := $(1 + ((3!/5) \times (79 + (7 + 5)))) + ((3! + 1)!)$
18146 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5 \times 79) \times (7 \times 5))) - (3! - 1)$
18147 := $((1 \times 3!) - (((5 - 7) \times 9) \times (7!/5))) - (3 \times 1)$
18148 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5! - 7) \times (9 - (((7 + 5!) - 3) + 1))))$
18149 := $(1 \times (3! \times ((57 - (9 - 7))^{5-3}))) - 1$
18150 := $(13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) + 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
18151 := $(1 \times 3! \times ((5! - 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)$
18152 := $((((1 \times 3!) - (57 \times 9)) + 7!) + 5) \times (3 + 1)$
18153 := $((1 + 35) + (7! + 975)) \times (3 \times 1)$
18154 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) \times ((7 \times 97) - (53 \times 1))$
18155 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 7))) + (5 + (3! \times 1))$
18156 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5 - 7) \times 9) \times (7!/5)) - 3! \times 1$
18157 := $(1357 - \sqrt{9}) + ((7^5) - 3) - 1$
18158 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 79) - (7!/5)) - 31$
18159 := $((13 - 5) \times 79) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
18160 := $(1 + (3 - (5 \times (7 - 97)))) \times ((5!/3) \times 1)$
18161 := $(1 \times 3! + 5) \times (((7! - 9) - 75)/3) - 1$
18162 := $1 \times (3! - ((5 + 79) - (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)))$
18163 := $(1 + (3! - (5 + 79))) + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)$
18164 := $(1 + 3) \times (5 + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 - (3 \times 1))))$
18165 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) + ((7! + 9) + (7!/5)) \times (3 \times 1)$
18166 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! + (79 \times 75))) + 31$
18167 := $(1357 + 9) + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1)$
18168 := $(1 + 3)! \times ((5 + 7) - (9 - (753 + 1)))$
18169 := $1 + (((3 \times (57 - 9)) \times (7 + 5!)) - ((3! - 1)!)!$
18170 := $(1^3) \times ((5 \times 79) \times ((7 + (5!/3)) - 1))$
18171 := $(1^3) + ((5 \times 79) \times ((7 + (5!/3)) - 1))$
18172 := $(13 - 57) \times ((9 \times (7 - 53)) + 1)$
18173 := $(1 + (35 - 7)) + ((9 \times (7!/5)) \times (3 - 1))$
18174 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5 + 7 + 9)) \times (7 - (5 - (3 + 1)!))$
18175 := $(1357 + 9) + ((7^5) + 3 - 1)$
18176 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((7 + 97) \times 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
18177 := $((1 \times 3!)! - 5!) + (7 \times ((9^{7-5}) \times 31))$
18178 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) \times (((7 - 97) \times 5)/3) + 1$
18179 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) + (7 \times 9)) \times (7^{5-3+1})$
18180 := $(135 + (79 \times 75)) \times (3 \times 1)$
18181 := $1 \times ((35 + (7!/(9 - 7))) + ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
18182 := $1 + ((35 + (7!/(9 - 7))) + ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
18183 := $(1 - 3 + 5) \times ((7! + 9) + ((7!/5) + 3 + 1))$
18184 := $13 - ((5 \times 79) \times (7 - 53)) - 1$
18185 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 5) + ((7! - (9 \times 75)) \times (3 + 1))$
18186 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (5! \times (7 + 9))) - (7!/5)) \times (3! + 1)$
18187 := $((1 \times 3!)^5) + (7 + ((97 + 5)^{3-1}))$
18188 := $((1 + 3)! \times 57) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 3 + 1)$
18189 := $(1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! + (9 + ((7!/5) + 3! \times 1)))$
18190 := $((1 + 3)! \times 57) + ((9 + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)$
18191 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (5! - ((7^9-7) \times ((5! \times 3) - 1))))$
18192 := $((1 - 35) + (797 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)!$

$$\begin{aligned} 18193 &:= (1 + (3!! \times 5)) - (((7-9)^7) \times (5! - 3! \times 1)) \\ 18194 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 5)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 18195 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 - (9 \times 75)) - (3!! \times 1)) \\ 18196 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times ((7 + 97) \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 18197 &:= 1 \times (((3!!/5!) \times 79) - (7 - 5!)) \times 31 \\ 18198 &:= (13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) + 5)) + (3 + 1)! \\ 18199 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) - ((57 - (9 + (7^5))) - (3!! \times 1)) \\ 18200 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5! - 7) - (9 \times 7)) \times (53 - 1)) \\ 18201 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7!)/(9 - 7)) + ((5^3) + 1)) \\ 18202 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) - (5 - ((7!/9) + (7^5)))) + ((3! - 1)!) \\ 18203 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + (797 - 5!)) + (3!! - 1) \\ 18204 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times ((7 + 97) \times 5)) + (3 + 1) \\ 18205 &:= ((1 - 3!!) - (5 - (7! - (9 \times 75)))) \times (3! - 1) \\ 18206 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 5)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 18207 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 7) + (9 + 7))^{5-3 \times 1}) \\ 18208 &:= (1^3 + ((5! + (7!/9)) + (7^5))) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 18209 &:= ((1 - 3 + (57 + 97)) \times 5!) - 31 \\ 18210 &:= ((13 + ((5! - 7) \times 9)) + 7!) \times (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 18211 &:= (1 \times ((3! - (5 \times 7)) \times ((97 - 5) - 3!!)) - 1) \\ 18212 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! - 7)) \times (9 - (7 - (5 \times 31))) \\ 18213 &:= (1 \times ((3! - (5 \times 7)) \times ((97 - 5) - 3!!)) + 1) \\ 18214 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times (5! - 7)) + 9) + ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1) \\ 18215 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) - 5 \times (3! - 1) \\ 18216 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((57 \times 9) - 7) \times (5 + 3 + 1)) \\ 18217 &:= 1 + ((3! \times (5 + 7)) \times ((9 + 75) \times 3) + 1) \\ 18218 &:= 1 \times 3! + (5 + ((7 \times 9) \times (((7!/5) - 3!!) + 1))) \\ 18219 &:= 13 + (((5! + (7!/9)) + (7^5)) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 18220 &:= (((1 \times 3! + 5) \times (7 \times 9)) + (7^5)) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 18221 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) - ((7!/5) - 31) \\ 18222 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times ((7!/5) + 3 + 1))) \\ 18223 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5 + 7)) \times (97 + 5!)) - (3! - 1) \\ 18224 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times ((7 + 97) \times 5)) + (3 + 1)! \\ 18225 &:= ((1 \times 3) - ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7) + 5))^{3-1}) \\ 18226 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + (7^5)) - ((3! - 1)!) \\ 18227 &:= ((13 + 5) \times 79) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1) \\ 18228 &:= ((1^{35}) \times 7) \times ((9 + 75) \times 31) \\ 18229 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (797 + (5^{3+1})) \\ 18230 &:= (1 + (((3!^5) + 7!)/9) + ((7^5) - 3)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18231 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times 5!) - (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 18232 &:= 1 + (((3! \times 5!) - (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 18233 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times (5 + 7)) \times (97 + 5!)) + (3! - 1) \\ 18234 &:= (13 + 5) \times ((7 + 975) + 31) \\ 18235 &:= (1 - 3!) - (5 \times (79 - 7 - (5! \times 31))) \\ 18236 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((57 \times ((9 - 7) \times 5!))/3) - 1) \\ 18237 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + 79) + (7! + 5!) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 18238 &:= (1 - 3) - (5! \times ((7 - 9) - (75 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 18239 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + ((5! + 7!) + ((97 \times 5!) + (3!! - 1))) \\ 18240 &:= ((1^3 \times 5!) + ((7 \times 9) + 7)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!) \\ 18241 &:= (1 + 3!!) - (5! \times ((7! + 9) - (7! + 5 \times 31))) \\ 18242 &:= (((1 - 35) + (7!/(9 - 7))) + 5!) \times (3! + 1) \\ 18243 &:= ((1 \times 3!)!) + (((5 \times 7) - (9 - 7)) \times 531) \\ 18244 &:= (1 + 3) - (5! \times (7 - (9 + (75 \times (3 - 1)))) \\ 18245 &:= ((1^3 + 5)!) + ((7 - (9 - (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 18246 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (5! + 7)) \times 97) + ((5 \times 3!!) - 1) \\ 18247 &:= (1 - (3^5 + 7)) + ((9 + (7 + 5!))^{3-1}) \\ 18248 &:= (1^3 - 5) \times (7 - (9 + (7! - (5! \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 18249 &:= (1 - ((3 + 5) - (7!/9))) \times (7 - 5 + 31) \\ 18250 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + ((5 + (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1)) \\ 18251 &:= (1 + 3!!) + ((5 + (7 - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1)) \\ 18252 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) - ((5 \times 7) + 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 18253 &:= (((1^{3!})^5!) + ((7! \times \sqrt{9}) + 7)) + (5^{3!-1}) \\ 18254 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) + 5) - ((7 - 9) - (7^5)) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 18255 &:= (((1 + 3!) + (5! \times 79)) \times (7 - 5)) - (3!! - 1) \\ 18256 &:= ((13 - (5! \times (7 - 9))) \times 75) - (3!! - 1) \\ 18257 &:= (((1 \times 3!)!) - 5) + (7 + (9 + (7^5))) + (3!! - 1) \\ 18258 &:= ((1^{3!}) - (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5! - ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 18259 &:= (13579 + 7!) - (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 18260 &:= (((13 \times (5! + 79)) \times 7) + 5!) + 31 \\ 18261 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) + (9 + 7)) + (5^{3!-1}) \\ 18262 &:= (1 \times (3!! + 5!)) + (((7!/9) + 7) - 5) \times 31 \\ 18263 &:= (1 \times 35) + ((7 \times (9 + 75)) \times 31) \\ 18264 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times (97 + 5)) + ((3! \times 1)!) \\ 18265 &:= (1 - 3!!) + ((5! - 7) \times ((9 + 75) \times (3 - 1))) \\ 18266 &:= (((13 \times 5) - 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - 3 - 1 \\ 18267 &:= (((13 \times 5) - 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 18268 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 + 7) \times (9 \times 7)) + 5) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 18269 &:= (13 \times (5! - (7 \times 9))) + (((7^5) + 3!!) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

- 18270** := $((1+3)! + 5) \times 7 \times (97 - (5+3-1))$
18271 := $((1-3 + (57+97)) \times 5!) + 31$
18272 := $((1+3!)^5 + 7) + (9 \times (7+5 \times 31))$
18273 := $((13 \times 5) - 7) \times (9 \times (7 \times 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
18274 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + ((7^5) + (3!! + 1))$
18275 := $((1-3!) \times 5) \times (((7 \times 9) - 75) - 3!!) + 1$
18276 := $(1 + (3! + 5)) - ((79 - (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
18277 := $((13 \times 57) + 9) + (7^5) + 3!! \times 1$
18278 := $(1 \times ((3! + 5) + (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 + 5!) + ((3! - 1)!!)$
18279 := $(1 - (35 - 7)) \times ((9 + ((7 \times 5) - 3!!)) - 1)$
18280 := $((1-3!) \times 5!) - (((7!/9) - 7!) - (5!^{3-1}))$
18281 := $((1-3) \times 5) + ((7 \times \sqrt{9}) \times ((7 \times 5!) + 31))$
18282 := $((1+35) \times 7) \times \sqrt{9} + (7^5) + (3!! - 1)$
18283 := $1 - (3! - (((5+7-9)!) \times (7+5!)) \times (3+1)!!)$
18284 := $((13 \times 5!) - (79 - ((7^5) - 3))) - 1$
18285 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) \times ((7+9+7) \times (53 \times 1))$
18286 := $1 - (((3 - (5 \times 7)) + 9) \times (75 + ((3! \times 1)!!))$
18287 := $((1-3!!) + (5 \times (7!/9))) \times 7 + (5! \times 31)$
18288 := $(1 \times (3^5)) + ((7! + 975) \times (3 \times 1))$
18289 := $((1+3)! \times (5! + (7 - (9+7)))) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
18290 := $((1 \times 3) \times 57) - (9+7) \times (5! - (3-1))$
18291 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 7) + ((9 + (7^5)) + ((3! \times 1)!!))$
18292 := $1 - (3 \times (5 - (7! + ((9-7) \times 531))))$
18293 := $((1+3!) \times (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7^5) - (3!! - 1))$
18294 := $(1 \times (3!! + (5-7))) - ((9 - (7 \times 5))^3 \times 1)$
18295 := $((1 \times 3!!) + (57 - 9)) + (7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!)$
18296 := $((1 \times 3!!) + 57) - 9 + (7^5) + (3!! + 1)$
18297 := $(13 - 5!) \times ((7 - (9+7)) \times ((5!/3!) - 1))$
18298 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5! + 7)) + ((9 + (7^5)) + (3!! \times 1))$
18299 := $(1 - ((3+5) \times 79)) \times ((7-5) - 31)$
18300 := $(1 \times 357 + 9) \times ((7^{5-3}) + 1)$
18301 := $1 + (((3! \times ((5! - 7) \times 9)) - (7-5)) \times (3 \times 1))$
18302 := $(1 - 3!!) + ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1))$
18303 := $1 \times (((3!! + (5+7!)) \times \sqrt{9}) + (7!/(5!/(3+1)!!))$
18304 := $((13 - 57) \times (9+7)) \times (5 - 31)$
18305 := $(1 \times 35) \times ((7 + (97 \times 5)) + 31)$
18306 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! - 7)) \times 9 \times (7!/(5! \times (3! + 1)))$
18307 := $1 + (((3 \times (5-7)) \times (9 \times (7-5!))) \times (3 \times 1))$
18308 := $((1-3) \times (5! + 79)) \times (7 - (53 \times 1))$
18309 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! - 79)) + 7) \times ((5! \times 3) - 1)$
18310 := $((1 \times 3)! \times 5!) + (7 \times 9) + ((7^5) + ((3! \times 1)!!)$
18311 := $((1+3)! \times 579) + 7! - (5^{3+1})$
18312 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5! + 7!) + 975) - 31)$
18313 := $1 + (((3! \times 5) + 79) \times (7!/(5 \times 3! \times 1)))$
18314 := $1 \times (((3! + 5!) + 7)^{9-7}) + (5^{3+1})$
18315 := $((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + (7^5)) - 31$
18316 := $1 + (3!! + ((5 + (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 3!! \times 1)))$
18317 := $(1^{3!}) + (((5 - (7!/9)) \times (7 - (5!/3))) + 1)$
18318 := $(1 \times (357 \times 9)) + ((7! - 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
18319 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 - (7!/9)) \times (7 - (5 - 31)))$
18320 := $((1 + 3) + (57 \times (9 + 7))) \times (5!/3! \times 1)$
18321 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 \times ((9+7) \times 5)) + 31)$
18322 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7^5) - (3 + 1)!$
18323 := $1 \times 3 + (5 \times ((7 - (9 \times 7)) + (5! \times 31)))$
18324 := $((1+3!)^5 + 797) + (5! \times 3! \times 1)$
18325 := $((1^3 + 5)! + 79) + (7^5) + (3!! - 1)$
18326 := $((1^3 + 5)! + (79 + (7^5))) + (3!! \times 1)$
18327 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((579 + (7+5)) \times 31)$
18328 := $1 \times (((3-5) \times 79) \times ((7-5!) - 3)) \times 1$
18329 := $1 + (((3-5) \times 79) \times ((7-5!) - 3)) \times 1$
18330 := $1 + (((3-5) \times 79) \times ((7-5!) - 3)) + 1$
18331 := $((1 + (3 \times 57)) \times 9) + ((7^5) - (3+1)!)!$
18332 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((57 \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!)) - 1)$
18333 := $((1+3) \times 5) + 7 \times 97 \times (5+3-1)$
18334 := $1 - ((3! + 57) \times (9 - (75 \times (3+1))))$
18335 := $(1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) + ((7+5!)^{3-1})$
18336 := $(1+3)! \times (5! + (7 \times ((9 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1))))$
18337 := $13 - (((579 - 7!) - 5!) \times (3+1))$
18338 := $(13 \times (5! + (7-9))) + ((7^5) - (3 \times 1))$
18339 := $(1357 \times (9-7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
18340 := $(1 \times 35) \times ((7 \times 97) - (5 \times 31))$
18341 := $1 + (35 \times ((7 \times 97) - (5 \times 31)))$
18342 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7^5) - (3+1))$
18343 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7^5) - (3 \times 1)$
18344 := $((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + (7^5)) - (3-1)$
18345 := $(1 + ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + ((7^5) - (3-1))$

- 18346** := $(13 \times (5! + (7 - 9))) + (((7^5) + 3!) - 1)$
18347 := $(13 \times (5! + (7 - 9))) + (((7^5) + 3!) \times 1)$
18348 := $((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + (7^5)) + (3 - 1)$
18349 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7^5) + (3 \times 1)$
18350 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7^5) + (3 + 1)$
18351 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times (7 + 9 + (7 \times 5))) - (3 \times 1))$
18352 := $((1 + (3 + (57 \times 9))) + 75) \times 31$
18353 := $(13 \times 5!) - ((7 + 9) - (((7^5) + 3!) - 1))$
18354 := $(13 - (5! + 7)) \times ((97 - 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
18355 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)))) - (3! \times 1)$
18356 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)))) - (3! - 1)$
18357 := $(1 \times ((3 \times (5! \times (7 + 9 + (7 \times 5)))) - 3)) \times 1$
18358 := $1 - (3 + ((5! \times (7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5))) \times (3 \times 1)))$
18359 := $(1 + (3 \times (5! \times (7 + 9 + (7 \times 5)))) - (3 - 1)$
18360 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5! \times ((79 - (7!/5!)) \times 3)) \times 1)$
18361 := $((1 + 3!)! + ((5! \times ((79 - (7!/5!)) \times 3)) + 1)$
18362 := $(1 \times 3 + (5! \times ((7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)) + 3!))) - 1$
18363 := $(1 + (3 \times (5! \times (7 + 9 + (7 \times 5)))) + (3 - 1)$
18364 := $(1 + 3) - ((5! \times (7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5))) \times (3 \times 1))$
18365 := $(1 + (3 \times (5! \times (7 + 9 + (7 \times 5)))) + (3 + 1)$
18366 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) + 5)))) + (3! - 1)$
18367 := $(1 \times ((3! - 5!) + 7!)) + (((9 + 7) \times (5! + 3!)) + 1)$
18368 := $((1 + ((3! - 5!) + 7!)) + ((9 + 7) \times (5! + 3!))) + 1$
18369 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5! \times (7 + 9 + (7 \times 5))) + 3)) \times 1$
18370 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + (7^5) + (3 + 1)!$
18371 := $(1 - ((3 - (5 \times 79)) \times 7)) + ((5^3) + 1)$
18372 := $((1 \times (3 - 5!)) - 7) + (((9 + 7) + 5!)^{3-1})$
18373 := $1 \times ((3! + (5! \times 7)) + (9 + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)))$
18374 := $1 \times ((3! + (5! \times 7)) + ((9 + ((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
18375 := $1 + ((3! + (5! \times 7)) + ((9 + ((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
18376 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - ((7! - ((9 + 7) + (5^3)))) + 1)$
18377 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 - (7! - (((9 + 7) + (5^3)) \times 1))$
18378 := $(1 \times 3)! \times (((5 \times 7) - 97) + (5^{3-1}))$
18379 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 79) + (7! - (5! + 3!)))) - 1$
18380 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 79) + (7! - (5! + 3!)))) \times 1$
18381 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 + 79) \times 7) + 5) \times 31$
18382 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5! \times 7)) + ((9 + (7^5) + 3!)) \times 1$
18383 := $1 \times ((3! + ((5! + (7 + 9)) + (7^5))) + 3! \times 1)$
18384 := $(1 + 3)! \times (5 + (797 - (5 + 31)))$
18385 := $(1 + 3)! - ((5! \times ((7 - ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3)) - 1)$
18386 := $1 \times 3 + (((5 + 79) \times 7) + 5) \times 31$
18387 := $(1 - 3) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) + ((5^3) - 1))$
18388 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + (5^{3 \times 1})$
18389 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7!/9) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1))$
18390 := $(1^3 \times 5) \times ((79 \times 7) + (5^{3-1}))$
18391 := $((1^3) + ((5 \times 79) \times 7)) + ((5^3) \times 1)$
18392 := $((1 + 3) + (5 + 79)) \times ((7 \times (5 \times 3!)) - 1)$
18393 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - ((7 \times (9 + 7)) - ((5^3) \times 1))$
18394 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - (7 \times (9 + 7)) + (5^3) + 1$
18395 := $((1 + 3)^5) + (((7!/9) + ((7^5) + 3)) + 1)$
18396 := $(1 - (3! + ((5! - 7) \times 9))) \times (7 - (5^{3-1}))$
18397 := $((1 + 3)^5) + ((7!/9) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
18398 := $((1 + 3)! \times (57 + 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! + 1))$
18399 := $((1 + 3^5) + (7! + (9 + (7 \times 5!)))) \times (3 \times 1)$
18400 := $((1 + 3)^5 - 7) - 97 \times (5!/3! \times 1)$
18401 := $((1 \times (3!/5!))! + ((7 \times ((\sqrt{9})! + (7!/(5 - 3)))) - 1)$
18402 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (5! + (((7 + 975) \times 3) + 1))$
18403 := $(1 \times (3! + 5)) \times (7 \times ((9 + 7) \times (5 \times 3)) - 1)$
18404 := $(13 - 5!) \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) - (5! - 3)) + 1)$
18405 := $((1 + 3)! \times 579) + (7! - 531)$
18406 := $((13 + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1)$
18407 := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) - 9 \times (75 + 3) - 1$
18408 := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) - 9 \times (75 + 3) \times 1$
18409 := $((1 \times 35) \times 7) - 9 \times (75 + 3) + 1$
18410 := $(1 - 3!) \times (((5! - ((7!/9) \times 7)) + 5!) - 3) + 1$
18411 := $((1 \times 3)! - (5 \times (7 - (9 + 7)))) \times ((5! \times 3) + 1)$
18412 := $((13 + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3 - 1)$
18413 := $((13 + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
18414 := $(1 + (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 + (97 - 5)) \times 3! \times 1)$
18415 := $((13 \times 5!) + 79) + ((7^5) - 31)$
18416 := $((1 + 3)! + (5! + 7)) \times ((9 - 7) + 5!) - 3! \times 1$
18417 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + ((7 \times (9^{7-5})) \times 31)$
18418 := $((1 - ((3 - 5!) \times 79)) - (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
18419 := $((1 \times (3! \times (5! - 79))) \times 75) - 31$
18420 := $((1 + 3^5) + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 + 53) \times 1)$
18421 := $1 + ((3 + 57) \times ((97 + 5) \times 3) + 1)$

- 18422** := $((13 \times (5! + 7)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) \times (3 - 1)$
18423 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5) - ((7 - (97 \times 5)) \times 31)$
18424 := $1 + (3 \times ((5! + 7!) + (975 + (3! \times 1))))$
18425 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 + 9) - (753 \times 1))$
18426 := $((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (97 \times 5)) - 3 - 1$
18427 := $((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (97 \times 5)) - 3 \times 1$
18428 := $((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (97 \times 5)) - 3 + 1$
18429 := $(((((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (7 \times 9)) + (7^5)) + 3!) - 1$
18430 := $((1^{3!}) \times 5) \times ((79 + 7) + (5 \times 3! \times 1))$
18431 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 5!) + ((7^{9-7}) \times ((5! \times 3) - 1))$
18432 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! - ((7 \times 9) - 7)) \times (5! - (3 + 1)!))$
18433 := $(1 - ((3 - 579) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3))) \times 1$
18434 := $(1 - ((3 - 579) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3))) + 1$
18435 := $13 + ((5! - (7 - 9)) \times ((7 + 5!) + (3 + 1)!))$
18436 := $((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (97 \times 5)) + (3! \times 1)$
18437 := $((1 \times (3 + (5 \times 7))) \times (97 \times 5)) + (3! + 1)$
18438 := $((1 + 3!)! / 5!) \times ((7! / (9 \times 7)) + ((5! \times 3) - 1))$
18439 := $(((((1 + 3!) - 5)^7) \times ((\sqrt{9+7})! + 5!)) + 3!) + 1$
18440 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 \times (797 + (5^3))) \times 1)$
18441 := $((1 \times 3 + 5!) + (7! / 9)) \times (7 + (5! / 3!)) \times 1$
18442 := $(1 \times (3 - 57)) + (((9 + 7) + 5!)^{3-1})$
18443 := $((13 \times 5!) + 79) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)$
18444 := $((13 \times 5!) + 79) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1)$
18445 := $((1 \times 3^5) \times 79) - (753 - 1)$
18446 := $(1 + (3! - 57)) + (((9 + 7) + 5!)^{3-1})$
18447 := $(1 + 3!) + ((5! + 79) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1)))$
18448 := $(1 + 3) \times ((57 \times (9^{7-5})) - (3! - 1))$
18449 := $((1^3 \times (57 + 97)) \times 5!) - 31$
18450 := $((1 - (((3 - 5) - 7) \times 9)) \times 75) \times (3 \times 1)$
18451 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) + 5!)) + (3! - 1)$
18452 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5! - 7) - 9) + (7! - 531))$
18453 := $((1 - 3 + 5) \times (7! - 9)) + (7 \times (5! \times (3 + 1)))$
18454 := $(1 - 3) + ((5! \times (79 + 75)) - (3 + 1)!)$
18455 := $(1 \times 3! + ((57 + 97) \times 5!)) - 31$
18456 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5!) - 31)$
18457 := $((1 \times (3! \times 57)) \times 9) - (7 - 5) \times 3! + 1$
18458 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) - 7) - 97 \times (5! + (3! - 1))$
18459 := $((1 + 3) + 5) \times (((7 \times 97) + 5) \times 3) - 1$
18460 := $((1 + 3!) - 579) \times (((7 + 5!) + 3) \times 1)$
18461 := $(1 + (3!^5)) + ((7! + \sqrt{9}) + ((7! - (5! - 3!)) + 1))$
18462 := $((1 \times 3) \times (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + 5) - 3! \times 1$
18463 := $((1 + 3!) + 5!) + (((7! - (\sqrt{9})!) + (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 \times 1))$
18464 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 \times 7)) + (((9 + 7) + 5!)^{3-1})$
18465 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) - ((7 + 5) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
18466 := $(1 - 3) + (57 \times ((975/3) - 1))$
18467 := $(1 + (3 \times ((5! - 7) - 9))) \times ((7 + 53) - 1)$
18468 := $(1 \times (3 \times 57)) \times (9 \times (((7 - 5) \times 3!) \times 1))$
18469 := $(1 - ((3 \times (5! - 7!)) + 9)) + (7 \times 531)$
18470 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - ((7! \times (9 - 7)) - (5! + 3!)))) \times 1$
18471 := $1 \times (3 + (57 \times ((975/3) - 1)))$
18472 := $1 + (3 + (57 \times ((975/3) - 1)))$
18473 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 53) - 1$
18474 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 53) \times 1$
18475 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5 + 7!)) + ((9 \times 7) \times 53) + 1$
18476 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5! \times (7 - (9 + 75))) + 3 - 1)$
18477 := $((1 + 3) + 5) \times (((7 \times 97) + 5) \times 3) + 1$
18478 := $1 - (3 + ((5! \times (7 - (9 + 75))) \times (3 - 1)))$
18479 := $((1 - 3!) / 5) + (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5!) + ((3! + 1)!))$
18480 := $((1 - 3 + 57) \times (9 + 75)) \times (3 + 1)$
18481 := $13 + ((57 \times ((9 \times (7 + 5)) \times 3)) \times 1)$
18482 := $13 + ((57 \times ((9 \times (7 + 5)) \times 3)) + 1)$
18483 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) \times (7 + 9)) + (7! + ((5 - 3) + 1))$
18484 := $((1 + (3! + (5! \times (7 + 9)))) \times 7) - ((5 - 3) + 1)$
18485 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7! / 9) + (7^5) - (3 - 1)$
18486 := $13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) + 5) + (3 + 1)!)$
18487 := $(1 + (3! \times 57)) + ((9 \times (7! / 5)) \times (3 - 1))$
18488 := $(1 + (3 - (5! \times (7 - (9 + 75)))) \times (3 - 1)$
18489 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times 7! / 9) + (7^5) + (3 - 1)$
18490 := $((1 + (3! + (5! \times (7 + 9)))) \times 7) + ((5 - 3) + 1)$
18491 := $((1 - 35) - 7)^{9-7} \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1)$
18492 := $(1 + 3!) - (5 \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) - (5! \times 31)))$
18493 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5!) + 3! \times 1$
18494 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5!) + 3! + 1$
18495 := $((1 - (3! + 5)) + 7) \times 9 \times ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1)$
18496 := $((1 - 3!) + 5) + 7! + ((9 + 7) \times ((5! + 3!) + 1))$
18497 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times (79 + 75))) - (3! + 1)$
18498 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! + 7!) + (975 + 31))$
18499 := $((1 - 3!) + (5! \times (79 + 75))) + (3 + 1)!$

$$\begin{aligned}18500 &:= (((1 - 3!) \times (5 + 79)) + (7! + 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\18501 &:= ((1 + 3)! + (5! \times (79 + 75))) - (3 \times 1) \\18502 &:= (1 + (3!! + 5!)) \times (7 - (((9 + 7) \times (5 - 3!)) + 1)) \\18503 &:= ((1 + 35) \times (((7 + 97) \times 5) - 3!)) - 1 \\18504 &:= (13579 + 7!) - (5! - (3! - 1)) \\18505 &:= (13579 + 7!) - (5! - (3! \times 1)) \\18506 &:= (((1 + 35) - 7) + 9) \times (7 + (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\18507 &:= ((1 \times (3! + 579)) + (7 + 5)) \times 31 \\18508 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5!)) - (3! + 1) \\18509 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5 + (7! / (9 - 7))) + 5!)) - 3! \times 1 \\18510 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5!)) - (3! - 1) \\18511 &:= (13 - 5!) \times (((7 - (9 \times 7)) - (5! - 3)) \times 1) \\18512 &:= ((1 \times (((3! \times 5) \times 7) - 9)) + 7) \times (5! - 31) \\18513 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5 + (7! / (9 - 7))) + 5!)) - (3 - 1) \\18514 &:= (1 + (3 \times 579)) + ((7^5) - 31) \\18515 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) - 5! - (3!! \times 1) \\18516 &:= 1 + 35 + ((7! / 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 - 1))) \\18517 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((57 + 97) \times 5!)) + 31 \\18518 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 \times (9 - 7)) \times 5!) + 31) \\18519 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) + (((7 - 5!) \times 3!) - 1) \\18520 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) + ((7 - 5!) \times (3! \times 1)) \\18521 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5 + (7! / (9 - 7))) + 5!)) + 3! \times 1 \\18522 &:= ((1^3 + 57) - 9) \times (7 \times (53 + 1)) \\18523 &:= (((1 \times ((3^5) \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5))) + 3!) \times 1 \\18524 &:= (((1 \times ((3^5) \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5))) + 3!) + 1 \\18525 &:= 13 \times ((5 - (7 - 97)) \times ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\18526 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7!) + (9 + (7! / 5))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\18527 &:= ((1^3 \times 579) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3)) - 1 \\18528 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 579) \times (((7 + 5) - 3) - 1) \\18529 &:= ((1^3 \times 579) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3)) + 1 \\18530 &:= (1 + 3!!) + (5! + (((7 - 9)^7) - 5)^{3-1}) \\18531 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + 7) \times (5 + 3 + 1) \\18532 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) + (7! + ((9 \times 75) + ((3! + 1)!)) \\18533 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 - 9) + (7! / 5)) + 3!)) \times 1 \\18534 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 - 9) + (7! / 5)) + 3!)) + 1 \\18535 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - 7) - ((9 - (7^5)) - ((3! \times 1)!)) \\18536 &:= (13 \times ((5! + 7) + 97)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\18537 &:= (13 \times ((5! + 7) + 97)) + (5^{3! \times 1})\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18538 &:= ((1 + (3! + 579)) + (7 + 5)) \times 31 \\18539 &:= (13 + (57 \times (975/3))) + 1 \\18540 &:= 1 \times (((3 \times 579) + (7^5)) - 3) - 1 \\18541 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 579) + (7^5)) - 3) - 1 \\18542 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 579) + (7^5)) - 3) \times 1 \\18543 &:= (((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7!) + (9 \times (7 + 5!))) \times (3 \times 1) \\18544 &:= (1 + 3^5) \times (7 + (9 + ((7 + 53) \times 1))) \\18545 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5) \times ((7 + 975) - 3!)) + 1 \\18546 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1))) \\18547 &:= 1 + (((3 \times 579) + (7^5)) + 3) - 1 \\18548 &:= (13 \times 5!) + (((79 \times 7) - 5) \times 31) \\18549 &:= (1 + (3 \times 579)) + ((7^5) + 3 + 1) \\18550 &:= (1^3 \times 5) \times ((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (53 \times 1)) \\18551 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 579)) + (7^5)) + (3! + 1) \\18552 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 + 7) + 9) + (753 - 1)) \\18553 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\18554 &:= (((1 \times 3!!) \times 5) + (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times 5 - (3! \times 1) \\18555 &:= \sqrt{1 + 3} + (57 + ((9 + (7 + 5!))^{3-1})) \\18556 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5! \times 7) \times 9) - ((7^5) + 31)) \\18557 &:= (1^3 - (5! \times (7 - 9))) \times (75 + 3 - 1) \\18558 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5 - (3 \times 1))) \\18559 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) \times (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5) - 3!)) - 1 \\18560 &:= (1 \times ((3 + 5!) - 7)) \times (9 + (7 + (5! + (3 + 1)!))) \\18561 &:= (((1 + 3) - 5!) \times (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5) - 3!)) + 1 \\18562 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5! + (79 \times ((7 - 5!) - 3!))) \times 1) \\18563 &:= ((1 \times 357) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5 + 3!))) - 1 \\18564 &:= 13 \times (((5! - 79) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3!) - 1 \\18565 &:= ((1 \times 357) \times ((9 \times 7) - (5 + 3!))) + 1 \\18566 &:= ((1 + 3!)^5) + (79 + (7! / ((5 - 3) + 1))) \\18567 &:= (((1 \times (3!! \times 5)) + (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times 5) + (3! + 1) \\18568 &:= ((1^3 + 5) + (7 + 9)) \times ((7 \times 5!) + 3 + 1) \\18569 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + 5!) \times (((7 - (9 - 7)) - 5) - 31) \\18570 &:= (((13 + (5! + 7!)) + 9) + (7! / 5)) \times (3 \times 1) \\18571 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5 + (7! + 9)) - ((7^5) / (3! + 1))) \\18572 &:= (1 \times (3 - ((5 \times 79) - (7! - 5)))) \times (3 + 1) \\18573 &:= (135 + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5! - (3 + 1))) \\18574 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) - (3 - 1) \\18575 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (5! + (7 \times 97))) + (5! - (3!! + 1))\end{aligned}$$

- 18576** := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7!) + ((9 - 7) \times 5!) \times (3 + 1)!$
18577 := $13 \times (((5! - 79) \times (7 \times 5) - 3!) \times 1)$
18578 := $13 - ((5 \times 79) \times (7 - (53 + 1)))$
18579 := $((((1 + 3)! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) \times (7 \times 5) - 3!) \times 1$
18580 := $((1 - 3!) - (5! - (7! - (97 \times 5)))) \times (3! - 1)$
18581 := $((((1 + 3)! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) \times (7 \times 5) - (3 + 1))$
18582 := $(1 + ((3! \times 5) + 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) + 3 + 1)$
18583 := $13579 + (7! - (5 + 31))$
18584 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7! / (9 \times 7)) + ((5^3) - 1))$
18585 := $1 \times (35 \times (79 - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1))))$
18586 := $1 + (35 \times (79 - ((7 - 5!) \times (3 + 1))))$
18587 := $\sqrt{1+3} + ((5 \times (7 - (\sqrt{9})!)) \times (7 \times 531))$
18588 := $((((1 + 3)! + (5 \times 7)) \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
18589 := $((((1 + 3)^5 + 7) \times (9 \times (7 - 5))) + 31)$
18590 := $1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) - ((7 - 5!) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
18591 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) - ((7 - 5!) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
18592 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - ((7 - 5)^{3+1})$
18593 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! - (3! + 1)))$
18594 := $1 \times ((3!!/5!) \times ((7! - ((97 \times 5!)/3!)) - 1))$
18595 := $1 + ((3!!/5!) \times ((7! - ((97 \times 5!)/3!)) - 1))$
18596 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 5!) \times (7 + (9 + 7)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1)$
18597 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((5! \times 7) \times (9 + 7)) + (5! - 3)) \times 1)$
18598 := $(1 - 3) - (5! \times (((7 \times (97 - 5!)) + 3!) \times 1))$
18599 := $((1 - (3!! - ((5! \times 79) - 7!))) \times 5) - 3! \times 1$
18600 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 + (7 - 9))) + 7) \times (5! \times 31)$
18601 := $((1 + (3!^5)) - ((7 - 97) \times 5!)) + (3 + 1)!$
18602 := $((1 + 3!) - 579) \times (((7 + 5!) + 3) + 1)$
18603 := $1 \times (((3 \times 5!) - ((7 + 9) - 7)) \times (53 \times 1))$
18604 := $1 + (((3 \times 5!) - ((7 + 9) - 7)) \times (53 \times 1))$
18605 := $(1 \times 3!) - (5 \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times ((3! \times 1)!))))$
18606 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) + 7!) + ((9 + 7) \times ((5! + 3!) \times 1))$
18607 := $((1 - (3!! - ((5! \times 79) - 7!))) \times 5) + (3 - 1)$
18608 := $((1 - (3!! - ((5! \times 79) - 7!))) \times 5) + (3 \times 1)$
18609 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + (7 + 97)) + ((5^3) \times 1)$
18610 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((7 + (97 + (5^3))) + 1)$
18611 := $((1 - (3!! - ((5! \times 79) - 7!))) \times 5) + 3! \times 1$
18612 := $((1 + 3) + (57 \times 9)) \times ((7 + 5) + (3 + 1)!)$
18613 := $((1 \times 3!)! / 5) + ((7! / (9 - 7)) - 5) \times (3! + 1)$
18614 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + 7) - (5! - (3! + 1))$
18615 := $(1 + ((35 \times 7) + 9)) \times ((7!/5!) + 31)$
18616 := $(13579 + (7! - (5 - 3))) - 1$
18617 := $(13579 + (7! - (5 - 3))) \times 1$
18618 := $(13579 + (7! - (5 - 3))) + 1$
18619 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - (9 \times 7))) - ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
18620 := $((1 - 3 + 5!) \times 79) - (7 + 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
18621 := $(13579 + (7! + 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
18622 := $((13579 + 7!) + 5) - (3 - 1)$
18623 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 + 9) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1)!)$
18624 := $(1 + (((3 \times 57) - 9) - 7) \times 5) \times (3 + 1)!$
18625 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 + 9) - ((7!/5!) + (3!! - 1)))$
18626 := $13579 + (7! + (5 + 3 - 1))$
18627 := $13579 + ((7! + 5) + 3 \times 1)$
18628 := $1 + (3!! + ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5^3 \times 1))))$
18629 := $((1 - 3!) + 5) + (7! - (97 - (5!^{3-1})))$
18630 := $135 \times ((7 - 9) + ((7 \times 5) \times (3 + 1)))$
18631 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) \times (7 + 9) + (7! + (5! + 31))$
18632 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) + ((7 - 5!) \times (3! - 1))$
18633 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - (9 \times 7))) - ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
18634 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) - 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times 53) - 1)$
18635 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (((7!/9) - 75) \times 31)$
18636 := $(1 \times (3! - 5!)) + (((7 - (9 - 7))^5) \times 3! \times 1)$
18637 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (5^{7-9+7})) - (5! - (3! + 1))$
18638 := $1 - (3 + ((5 \times (((7 - 9)^7) - (5 \times 3!))) \times 1))$
18639 := $((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) + 5) - (3!! + 1)$
18640 := $((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) + 5) - (3!! \times 1)$
18641 := $(1 - (3 + 5)) - (((7 \times 9) - (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
18642 := $(1^3) - ((5 \times (((7 - 9)^7) - (5 \times 3!))) - 1)$
18643 := $((1 - 3!) + 5!) \times (7 + 9) + ((7^5) - 3)) - 1$
18644 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((79 + (75 + 3)) + 1)$
18645 := $1 - (3^5 + (((7 + 9) - 7!) + 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
18646 := $(1 - 3) - ((5 - 79) \times ((7!/5)/(3 + 1)))$
18647 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) \times ((7 \times 97) - (5 + 31))$
18648 := $((1 + 3!) \times (5 + 7)) \times ((97 + 5!) + (3! - 1))$
18649 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - (75 - (3 + 1))$
18650 := $((1 - (3! - (57 \times (9 \times 7)))) \times 5) + 3!! \times 1$
18651 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((57 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5))) - (3 + 1)!$
18652 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 - 79) \times ((7!/5)/(3 + 1)))$
18653 := $(13 \times (((5! - 79) \times 7) \times 5)) - 3) + 1$

- 18654** := $(1 \times 3)! \times (((5! + 79) \times (7 + 5)) + (3!! + 1))$
18655 := $(13 + (5 \times (7 + 97))) \times (5 \times (3! + 1))$
18656 := $(1^3) + ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 - 7) + 531))$
18657 := $((13 \times (((5! - 79) \times 7) \times 5)) + 3) - 1$
18658 := $(1 - (3^5)) + (((7 \times 9) \times 75) \times (3 + 1))$
18659 := $((1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7!) - 9) - (7 \times 53))) - 1$
18660 := $(1 \times (3 + 57)) \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1))$
18661 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) - (5! - 31)$
18662 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - (9 \times 7))) + ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
18663 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - (9 \times 7))) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)$
18664 := $((((1 + 3)^5) + 7!) + ((9 \times 7) \times 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)!$
18665 := $1 + (3!! + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1))$
18666 := $((1 \times ((3 + 5) \times 7)) + 97) \times ((5! + 3) - 1)$
18667 := $1 + ((3 \times ((5 + 7!) - (9 \times 7))) + (5! \times 31))$
18668 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (((57 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3! + 1))$
18669 := $1 \times (3!! + (579 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1))))$
18670 := $1 + (3!! + (579 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 + 1))))$
18671 := $((((1 \times 3)!)! + ((57 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5))) - (3 + 1))$
18672 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 - 79) \times ((7!/5) / (3 + 1)))$
18673 := $((1 + (3! + 5!)) \times 79) + (7! + (5 \times (3!! \times 1)))$
18674 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) + (7 - 531)$
18675 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5! + (((7 \times 975) - 3!!) \times 1))$
18676 := $(1 + (35 - 7)) \times ((9 \times 75) - 31)$
18677 := $((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - (9 \times 7))) + ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
18678 := $(1 \times 3) \times ((5! + (7 \times 975)) - (3!! - 1))$
18679 := $((((1 \times 3)!)! + ((57 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5))) + (3 + 1))$
18680 := $((1 \times 35) / 7) \times (9 + (7 + (5! \times 31)))$
18681 := $((((1^3!) - (5 - 7)^9) - ((7!/5) - 3! \times 1))$
18682 := $((((1 - 3!)^5) + (7! - 9)) + ((7^5) - 31))$
18683 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 - (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - 53)) + 1)$
18684 := $(1 \times 3)! \times ((5^{7-9+7}) - (5 + 3! \times 1))$
18685 := $(1 + 3579) + ((7! - 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
18686 := $((1 - 35) \times (7 - 97)) + ((5^3!) + 1)$
18687 := $(13 + (((57 \times 9) \times 7) \times 5)) + (3!! - 1)$
18688 := $((((1 \times 3)!)! - 5!) + ((7!/9) + ((7^5) + (3!! + 1))))$
18689 := $(((((1 + 3) - (5 - 7)))! - 97) \times (5 \times 3!)) - 1$
18690 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((57 \times (9 - 75)) + (3 + 1)!)!$
18691 := $(((((1 + 3) - (5 - 7)))! - 97) \times (5 \times 3!)) + 1$
18692 := $(1 + 3) \times (5! + (((7! - (97 \times 5)) - 3) + 1))$
18693 := $((1 - (((3^5) - 7!) / 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
18694 := $(1 - 3!!) \times ((5 \times (7 - ((9 + 7) - 5))) - (3! \times 1))$
18695 := $(1 - 3!) \times (((5 - 7)^9) \times 7) - (5 \times 31)$
18696 := $(1 \times 3!) \times (((5^{7-9+7}) - 5) - (3 + 1))$
18697 := $((1 - (((3^5) - 7!) / 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3! + 1)$
18698 := $(1 \times (3!! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - 7) - (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
18699 := $((((1 \times 3)!)! + ((57 \times 9) \times (7 \times 5))) + (3 + 1)!$
18700 := $1 + (3579 + (7! \times ((5 - 3) + 1)))$
18701 := $(1 \times (3!! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - 7) - ((5 + 3!) + 1)$
18702 := $(1 \times 3)! \times ((5^{7-9+7}) - (5 + 3 \times 1))$
18703 := $(1 \times (3!! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) - 7) - ((5 + 3!) - 1)$
18704 := $((1 - (((3! \times 5!) - 7!) + 9)) + 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))$
18705 := $(1 + (3!! \times 5)) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5! - (3 - 1)))$
18706 := $((1^3 \times (5! \times 79)) - (7 + 5!)) \times (3 - 1)$
18707 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) \times ((79 - 7) + 5)) - 3) - 1$
18708 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) \times ((79 - 7) + 5)) - 3) \times 1$
18709 := $((((1 \times 3)^5) \times ((79 - 7) + 5)) - 3) + 1$
18710 := $(((((1 \times 3)!^5) + 7) - 9) - 7!) \times 5 + ((3! + 1)!)!$
18711 := $1 \times ((3^5) \times (7 + 9 + ((7 + 53) + 1)))$
18712 := $1 + ((3^5) \times (7 + 9 + ((7 + 53) + 1)))$
18713 := $(1 + ((3 \times (5 \times 79)) + (7^5))) + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
18714 := $((1 \times 3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) - 5) - 31$
18715 := $((1 - (((3^5) - 7!) / 9)) \times 7) + 5 \times (3! - 1)$
18716 := $(1 + (3!! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + 7) - ((5 + 3!) + 1)$
18717 := $1 - (((3^5) - 7!) - (9 - (7 + 5!))) \times (3 + 1)$
18718 := $(1 - 3) - ((5 - ((7 - (9 - 7)^5)) \times 3! \times 1)$
18719 := $((1 - (3 - 5)) \times (7! - (9 - 7))) + (5 \times (3!! + 1))$
18720 := $(13 \times 5) \times ((7 \times 9) + ((75 \times 3) \times 1))$
18721 := $(1 \times 3!!) + (((5 \times (7 + 9)) \times (75 \times 3)) + 1)$
18722 := $(1^3!) + (((5! \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) - 3! \times 1)$
18723 := $1 \times 3 + ((5 \times (7 + 97)) \times (5 + 31))$
18724 := $(1 \times 3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) + (5 - 31)$
18725 := $(1 + ((3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) + 5)) - 31$
18726 := $1 + (35 \times (7 - (97 - (5^{3+1}))))$
18727 := $((1 + 3^5) + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 + 53) + 1)$
18728 := $((1 + (3!! \times 5)) + 7) + (((9 + 7) + 5) \times ((3! \times 1)!)!$
18729 := $((1 \times (3!! \times 5)) + (7! + 9)) + (7! \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
18730 := $((1 - (3! \times 5!)) + (7! + (9 + (7! - 5)))) \times (3 - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 18731 &:= (1 + (3! \times (5^{7-9+7}))) - (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 18732 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (((57^{9-7}) - 5!) - (3! + 1)) \\ 18733 &:= (13579 + 7!) + (5! - (3! \times 1)) \\ 18734 &:= (13579 + 7!) + (5! - (3! - 1)) \\ 18735 &:= (13579 + (7! + (5! - 3))) - 1 \\ 18736 &:= (13579 + (7! + (5! - 3))) \times 1 \\ 18737 &:= (13579 + (7! + (5! - 3))) + 1 \\ 18738 &:= ((13 + 5!)/7) - (((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!) + 1) \\ 18739 &:= (((13 + 5!)/7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 18740 &:= ((13 + 5!)/7) - (((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!) - 1) \\ 18741 &:= ((1 \times 3!) \times 5) + ((7! + (9 - (7 - 5))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 18742 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times (7!/9)) - (7 + 5!))) + 31 \\ 18743 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) + (((7 - (9 - 7))^5) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 18744 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((5 \times (7 + 97)) \times (5 + 31)) \\ 18745 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5! - ((7!/9 - 7) + ((5^3) - 1))) \\ 18746 &:= 13 \times ((5! + (7! + 9)) - (7 + (5! \times 31))) \\ 18747 &:= (1 + 3!) - (5! - ((7!/9 - 7) + ((5^3) + 1))) \\ 18748 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5^{7-9+7}) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 18749 &:= 1 - ((357 - (9 + (7! - 5))) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 18750 &:= ((1 - 3!)^5) \times (((7 - 97)/(5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 18751 &:= (1^{35}) \times (((((7 - 9) + 7)^5) \times 3!) + 1) \\ 18752 &:= (1^{35}) + (((((7 - 9) + 7)^5) \times 3!) + 1) \\ 18753 &:= (1 \times (3! - 579)) \times ((7 + 5!) + (3! \times 1)) \\ 18754 &:= 1 \times (((35 \times (79 \times 7)) + 5!) - (3! + 1)) \\ 18755 &:= ((1 - (3 - 57)) \times (9 + (7 - 5))) \times 31 \\ 18756 &:= (1^3) + (5 + (((7 - (9 - 7))^5) \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 18757 &:= 1 \times ((3! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + (7 + (5!/(3 + 1)))) \\ 18758 &:= (1^3 - (5 + 79)) \times ((7 - 5!) \times (3 - 1)) \\ 18759 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) + 5) + 3 + 1) \\ 18760 &:= 1 + (((3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) + 5) + 3 + 1) \\ 18761 &:= (1 - (((3 - (5 \times 79)) \times 7) \times 5)) + ((3! + 1))! \\ 18762 &:= (1 - 3 + 5!) \times (((7 \times 9) + 7) + 5!) - 31 \\ 18763 &:= (((1 - 3)^5) + (7 \times 97)) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1) \\ 18764 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (((((7 - 9) + 7)^5) \times 3!) - 1) \\ 18765 &:= 135 \times ((7!/(9 \times (7 + 5))/3) - 1) \\ 18766 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (((((7 - 9) + 7)^5) \times 3!) + 1) \\ 18767 &:= (((1 + 3!)! - 5!) - ((79 \times 7) - (5!^{3-1}))) \\ 18768 &:= ((1 - (3 - (5^{7-9+7}))) + 5) \times 3! \times 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18769 &:= 1 + (((3! \times ((5! - 7) - 9)) \times 7) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 18770 &:= (1^3) + (((5 \times 7) + 97) + 5)^{3-1} \\ 18771 &:= (1 + (3! \times (5^{7-9+7}))) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 18772 &:= (1 + (3 \times 5!)) \times (79 - (7 + (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 18773 &:= ((1 + 3!)! - (((5 + (7!/9)) - (7!/5)) \times 31)) \\ 18774 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) + (7! + 975)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 18775 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 \times 7) + (97 + 5))^{3-1}) \\ 18776 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) - 5) + 31 \\ 18777 &:= 1 - (((35 \times (7 - 97)) - (5^3)) - 1) \\ 18778 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7^5) + 3))) \times 1 \\ 18779 &:= (1 \times (((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7^5) + 3))) + 1 \\ 18780 &:= (1 \times 3 + 57) \times ((9 \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 18781 &:= (1^3) + (((5^{7-9+7}) + 5) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 18782 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 - 79) \times (7 + 5!)) + (3! + 1)) \\ 18783 &:= 1 \times ((3 - 5!) + ((7! - ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 18784 &:= 1 + ((3 - 5!) + ((7! - ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 18785 &:= 13 \times (((5 + 7) - 9) + ((7 - 5) \times (3! + 1))) \\ 18786 &:= 1 \times (((3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) + 5) + 31) \\ 18787 &:= (1 + ((3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) + 5)) + 31 \\ 18788 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times ((5! - 7) + 9)) \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 18789 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 18790 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5! + (7! - 97))) + ((5 \times 3!) + 1) \\ 18791 &:= ((1 + 3)! - 5) \times ((7 + (975 + 3!)) + 1) \\ 18792 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 7))) \times (53 + 1) \\ 18793 &:= ((1 - 3) \times ((5 - 79) \times (7 + 5!))) - (3 \times 1) \\ 18794 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5! + (7! - 97)))) + (5 \times (3! + 1)) \\ 18795 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 5!) + ((7 \times (9 \times 7)) \times 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 18796 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5!)) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) + (5^3)))) \times 1 \\ 18797 &:= ((1 + (3! + 5!)) \times (7 + ((9 + 7) + (5^3)))) + 1 \\ 18798 &:= (1 + ((3! + 5) \times 7)) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3! \times 1) \\ 18799 &:= ((1 - 3) \times ((5 - 79) \times (7 + 5!))) + (3 \times 1) \\ 18800 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((57 \times (9 - 75)) + 3 - 1) \\ 18801 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 18802 &:= (((1 + 3)! + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 \times 5)) + (3! + 1) \\ 18803 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 - (7!/9)) - ((7^5) + (3! + 1)))) \\ 18804 &:= (((135 + 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) + (3! - 1) \\ 18805 &:= (((135 + 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 18806 &:= (((135 + 7) \times 9) + (7^5)) + (3! + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18807 &:= ((1+3)+57) - ((9-(7 \times 5)) \times (3!!+1)) \\ 18808 &:= ((1 \times 3)!)! - (((57 \times 9) - 7!) + 5) \times (3+1) \\ 18809 &:= ((1+3)! \times 579) + (7! - (5! + (3!+1))) \\ 18810 &:= ((1+3)! \times 579) + (7! - (5! + 3! \times 1)) \\ 18811 &:= ((1+3)! \times 579) + (7! - (5^3 \times 1)) \\ 18812 &:= ((1+3)! \times 579) + (7! - (5! + 3+1)) \\ 18813 &:= ((1 \times 3)!^5) - (7! + ((9 - ((7^5) - 3!!)) + 1)) \\ 18814 &:= ((1 \times 3! \times 5) - 7) \times ((97 + (5! \times 3!)) + 1) \\ 18815 &:= (1 + (((3!^5) - 7!) - (9 - (7^5)))) - 3!! \times 1 \\ 18816 &:= ((1+3) \times ((5! + 7) + 97)) \times ((5!/3!) + 1) \\ 18817 &:= (((1+3)! \times (5+79)) + (7^5)) - (3! \times 1) \\ 18818 &:= (((1+3)! \times (5+79)) + (7^5)) - (3! - 1) \\ 18819 &:= (1 \times (((3+5) \times 7) + 97)) \times ((5! + 3) \times 1) \\ 18820 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((57 \times (9 - 75)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 18821 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5)) \times ((7 + (9 \times 7)) - ((5! \times 3!) - 1)) \\ 18822 &:= (1 + (3!! + ((57 \times 9) + 7!))) \times (5 - (3 - 1)) \\ 18823 &:= (((1+3)! \times 579) + 7) - 5! + ((3!+1)!) \\ 18824 &:= 13 \times ((5797 - 5)/(3+1)) \\ 18825 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((57 \times (9 - 75)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 18826 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5!)) + (((7!/9) \times 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 18827 &:= (((1+3)! \times (5+79)) + ((7^5) + 3)) + 1 \\ 18828 &:= (((1+3)! \times (5+79)) + (7^5)) + (3! - 1) \\ 18829 &:= (((1+3)! \times (5+79)) + (7^5)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 18830 &:= ((1-3) \times 5) \times (7 - (((9 \times 7) \times 5) \times 3! \times 1)) \\ 18831 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) \times (7 \times (97 - 5!))) - (3! \times 1) \\ 18832 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) \times (7 + (97^{5-3 \times 1})) \\ 18833 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 5!)) \times (7 \times (97 - 5!))) - (3 + 1) \\ 18834 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5!)) + (7!/9)) \times (7 + (5 + 31)) \\ 18835 &:= (1 - 3!) \times ((5! - 7) - ((97 \times 5!)/(3 \times 1))) \\ 18836 &:= ((13 - (5 \times (7 - 9))) \times (7 \times (5! - 3))) - 1 \\ 18837 &:= ((13 - (5 \times (7 - 9))) \times (7 \times (5! - 3))) \times 1 \\ 18838 &:= ((13 - (5 \times (7 - 9))) \times (7 \times (5! - 3))) + 1 \\ 18839 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (5^{7-9+7})) + (5! - 31) \\ 18840 &:= ((1 - ((3 - 57) - 97)) + 5) \times ((3! - 1)!) \\ 18841 &:= (1^3 + ((5! \times 79) - 7!)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 18842 &:= ((1+3!!) + (5! \times 79)) + (((7+5) \times 3!!) + 1) \\ 18843 &:= (((1 \times 3) - 5!) \times (7 \times (97 - 5!))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 18844 &:= (((((1+3)!)! - 5) + (7! + 9)) + 7!) + (5! \times 31) \\ 18845 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + ((5 \times (7!/9) \times 7)) - (5 + 31)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18846 &:= (((1 \times 3!) - 5!) \times 7) - (((9 - 7!) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 18847 &:= ((1 + (3! \times (5^{7-9+7}))) + 5!) - (3 + 1)! \\ 18848 &:= ((1^{3!}) - 5) \times ((7! - 9753) + 1) \\ 18849 &:= ((1 + (3! \times 5)) \times (7 + 97)) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\ 18850 &:= (1^3 + (5 \times (7 - (9 - 7)))) \times (5 + 3!! \times 1) \\ 18851 &:= ((1+3!)^5) + (7 + (97 \times ((5!/3!) + 1))) \\ 18852 &:= (((1+3)!)! + 5!) - (((7!/9) + 7) - 5!) \times (3 + 1) \\ 18853 &:= ((1+3!)^5) + ((7 + (9 \times 75)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 18854 &:= 135 - (((7+9) - (7!/5!)) \times 3!!) + 1 \\ 18855 &:= (((1+3) \times 57) \times 9) + ((7^5) - (3+1)) \\ 18856 &:= (((1+3) \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7^5) - 3)) \times 1 \\ 18857 &:= (((1+3) \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7^5) - 3)) + 1 \\ 18858 &:= (13 \times 5!) + (((79 \times 7) + 5) \times 31) \\ 18859 &:= (((13+5!) + 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!!)) - 1 \\ 18860 &:= (((13+5!) + 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!!)) \times 1 \\ 18861 &:= (((13+5!) + 7) - ((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!!)) + 1 \\ 18862 &:= (1 + 3!!) - (((5 - 7) \times 9) \times (7!/5)) + 3 \times 1 \\ 18863 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (5^{7-9+7})) + (5! - (3! + 1)) \\ 18864 &:= ((13 \times 5) + 79) \times ((7 + (5^3)) - 1) \\ 18865 &:= (1 \times 3! \times 5!) + (((7!/(9-7)) + (5^{3!})) \times 1) \\ 18866 &:= 1 - (35 \times ((79+7) - (5^{3+1}))) \\ 18867 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (579 - 7!)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 18868 &:= (1 + 3!!) - (((5 - 7) \times 9) \times (7!/5)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 18869 &:= (1 \times 3!!) + (5 + ((7!/(9-7)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1))) \\ 18870 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 - 9)) \times ((7 \times 53) - 1) \\ 18871 &:= (((1+3)!^{5+7-9}) + (7! + (5+3))) - 1 \\ 18872 &:= (1357 - 9) \times ((7+5) + 3 - 1) \\ 18873 &:= (((13 \times (5 \times 7)) + 9) \times 7) + (5^{3!}) \times 1 \\ 18874 &:= (((13 \times (5 \times 7)) + 9) \times 7) + (5^{3!}) + 1 \\ 18875 &:= (1 \times ((3+5) - 7) + 9) \times ((7+5!) + (3+1)!) \\ 18876 &:= (1 \times 3) \times ((579 - 7) \times (5 + 3! \times 1)) \\ 18877 &:= (1 + (3 + (57^{9-7}))) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) \\ 18878 &:= (1 + (3 + (57^{9-7}))) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1) \\ 18879 &:= (1 + (3 + (57^{9-7}))) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\ 18880 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) - 7) \times ((9+75) - (3+1))) \\ 18881 &:= 1 + (((3^5) - 7) \times ((9+75) - (3+1))) \\ 18882 &:= (1 + 3!!) + ((5! + 7) \times ((9+7) + (5! + (3! + 1)))) \\ 18883 &:= (((1+3) \times 57) \times 9) + ((7^5) + (3+1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18884 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5 \times (7 \times 9)) - 7!) + 5) \times (3 + 1) \\ 18885 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 57) - 9) + ((7^5) + (3!! - 1)) \\ 18886 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) - 7) \times ((9 + 7) \times 5)) + (3! \times 1) \\ 18887 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) + (7 - ((5! \times 3!) \times 1)) \\ 18888 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (((5 + 79) \times 75) - (3 + 1)) \\ 18889 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + 9)) + (7 + (5! \times 31)) \\ 18890 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (57 \times 9)) + ((7^5) + 31) \\ 18891 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5 \times (7!/9))) + ((7^5) - (3!! - 1)) \\ 18892 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5 - 797) + 5) \times (3 + 1)!) \\ 18893 &:= 1 - ((3 + 5) - ((7 \times 9) \times (75 \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 18894 &:= (1 \times (3!! - 579)) \times ((7 + 5!) + (3! + 1)) \\ 18895 &:= 1 + (((3! + (5! - 7!)/9) + 7!) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 18896 &:= 1 \times (((3 + 57) \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 18897 &:= 1 + (((3 + 57) \times 9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 + 1) \\ 18898 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 18899 &:= 1 + ((3 - 5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 18900 &:= ((13 + 57) \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) - (3! - 1)) \\ 18901 &:= (1^3 + ((5 + 79) \times (75 \times 3))) \times 1 \\ 18902 &:= (1^3 + ((5 + 79) \times (75 \times 3))) + 1 \\ 18903 &:= (1 - (3 - 5)) + ((7 \times 9) \times (75 \times (3 + 1))) \\ 18904 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times ((7 + 53) \times 1)) \\ 18905 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 + 79) \times (75 \times 3)) - 1) \\ 18906 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (((5 + 79) \times (75 \times 3)) \times 1) \\ 18907 &:= ((1 - 3!!) + ((5 \times (7!/9)) \times 7)) - (5 - 31) \\ 18908 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - 5) - (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1) \\ 18909 &:= (((1 - 3) - 57) \times 9) + (7! + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 18910 &:= ((13 \times 5) - (7 - 97)) \times (5! + 3 - 1) \\ 18911 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (57 + 9 + 7 - 5 + 3!!) - 1 \\ 18911 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (57 + 9 + 7 - 5 + 3!! \times 1) \\ 18913 &:= (1 - 3!!) - ((5 + 7) + (((9 - 7!) + 5!) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 18914 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - (((7 - 9) \times 7) \times 5!)) \times (3 - 1) \\ 18915 &:= (1 \times 3) \times (5! + ((7!/9) + (75^{3-1}))) \\ 18916 &:= (1 + 3!) + (((5! + 7) \times 9) + (7! + 5!)) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 18917 &:= (((1 - 3!!) + ((5 \times (7!/9)) \times 7)) + 5) + 31 \\ 18918 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) + ((9 - (7 - 5!)) \times 31) \\ 18919 &:= (1 + (357 \times (\sqrt{9}!))) + ((7^5) - 31) \\ 18920 &:= ((13 \times 5) \times (((7 \times 9) - 7) \times 5)) + 3!! \times 1 \\ 18921 &:= (1 \times 3 + (57 - 9)) \times ((7 \times 53) \times 1) \\ 18922 &:= 1 - (((3! - (5! - (7 \times 9))) \times 7) \times (53 \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18923 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 5!) + 7) + (9 + 7) \times (5! + (3! + 1)) \\ 18924 &:= (1 + 3)! + ((5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 7)) \times (53 + 1)) \\ 18925 &:= 1 - ((3 + (57 \times 9)) - (7! + (5!^{3-1}))) \\ 18926 &:= (13 \times (5 - (7 \times 9))) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 18927 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7!) - (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 18928 &:= ((1 + 3!) - (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 + (7 \times 5)) - 3!! \times 1) \\ 18929 &:= (13 \times 5!) + ((7!/9) + (((7^5) + 3) - 1)) \\ 18930 &:= ((1 \times 3) - (57 \times 9)) + (7! + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 18931 &:= (((1 \times (35 - 7)) \times 9) \times 75) + 31 \\ 18932 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times (7 + 5)) - (3! + 1)) \\ 18933 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 579) + ((7! - 5) + 3)) - 1 \\ 18934 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 579) + ((7! - 5) + 3)) \times 1 \\ 18935 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 579) + ((7! - 5) + 3)) + 1 \\ 18936 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (((5! \times 7) + 9) - (7 + (53 \times 1))) \\ 18937 &:= ((1 \times 3!) - (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + ((5 - 3!!) - 1)) \\ 18938 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5!)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5! + (3!! - 1))) \\ 18939 &:= (1 \times 3! + ((5 \times 7) \times 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 18940 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 79) \times (7 + 5)) - (3! - 1)) \\ 18941 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7!) + (5!/(3 + 1)!) \\ 18942 &:= (((1 + 3^5) - 7) + 9) \times 7 \times (5 + (3! \times 1)) \\ 18943 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7!) + (5 + 3 - 1) \\ 18944 &:= ((1 + (3 \times (5 + 79))) \times 75) - 31 \\ 18945 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7!) + (5 + 3 + 1) \\ 18946 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) - ((7!/5)/(3 + 1)) \\ 18947 &:= ((13 \times 5) + 7!) + (((\sqrt{9}^7) + 5!) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 18948 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5! \times 79)/(7 - 5)) - (3 \times 1)) \\ 18949 &:= (13 + ((5! \times 79) \times (7 - 5))) - (3 + 1)! \\ 18950 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5! - (7! - ((97 \times 5) - ((3! + 1)!))) \\ 18951 &:= ((1 \times 3 + ((5! \times 79) - 7)) \times (5 - 3)) - 1 \\ 18952 &:= (1 - ((3 \times 5!) + ((7 \times 9) - (7! + 5!)))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 18953 &:= (1^3 \times ((5! \times 79) \times (7 - 5))) - (3! + 1) \\ 18954 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times (5 + ((7 + 9) \times 7))) \times (53 + 1) \\ 18955 &:= ((1 + (3!! \times 5)) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times 5!)) - 3! \times 1 \\ 18956 &:= (1^3 + ((5! \times 79) \times (7 - 5))) - (3! - 1) \\ 18957 &:= (1 + (3 \times (5! + (7! - 9)))) - ((7 - 5!) \times 31) \\ 18958 &:= ((1 + (3!! \times 5)) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times 5!)) - (3 \times 1) \\ 18959 &:= (1^3 + ((5! \times 79) \times (7 - 5))) - (3 - 1) \\ 18960 &:= (1 \times (3 \times (5 \times 79))) \times (7 + ((5 + 3) + 1)) \\ 18961 &:= (1 - (3 \times 5!)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times ((5! + 3!!) \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 18962** := $((13 + (5! \times 79)) \times (7 - 5)) - (3 + 1)!$
18963 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! \times 79)) \times (7 - 5)) - (3 \times 1)$
18964 := $((135 \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) - (3 \times 1)$
18965 := $(1 \times (3 + ((5! \times 79) \times (7 - 5)))) + (3 - 1)$
18966 := $(1^3 + ((5! \times 79) \times (7 - 5))) + (3! - 1)$
18967 := $((1 + (3!! \times 5)) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times 5!)) + 3! \times 1$
18968 := $((1 \times 3!)! - ((5! + 7) \times ((9 + 7) - 5!))) + ((3! + 1))!$
18969 := $((1 \times 3 + (5! \times 79)) \times (7 - 5)) + (3 \times 1)$
18970 := $((135 \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) + (3 \times 1)$
18971 := $(135 \times (7 + 9)) + (((7^5) + 3) + 1)$
18972 := $1 \times ((3^5 + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 - 5) \times 31))$
18973 := $(135 \times (7 + 9)) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)$
18974 := $((1 - (3^5)) + (7 \times 9)) \times ((7 - (5! - 3!)) + 1)$
18975 := $((1 - (3 - 5)^7) \times 9) + ((7 + 5) - 3!! \times 1)$
18976 := $((1 + 3!)! + 5) \times 7 \times 97 + (5 - 3!! \times 1)$
18977 := $((1 + 3!)^5) - ((7 - 9) \times ((7 \times 5) \times 31))$
18978 := $1 + (3 + (((5! \times 79) + 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1))))$
18979 := $((1 - (3 - 5)^7) - ((9 - (7^5)) + 3! \times 1)$
18980 := $(13 \times ((57 + 9) + 7)) \times (5 \times (3 + 1))$
18981 := $((1 \times 3!) - 57) \times 9 + (7! + (5!^{3-1}))$
18982 := $((1 - (3 - 5)^7) - 9) + ((7^5) - (3 \times 1))$
18983 := $((1 + 3)! - (5 - 7!)) + (((9 - 7) - 5!)^{3-1})$
18984 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5797 + 531)$
18985 := $((1 \times 3! \times 5) \times 7) \times (9 + 7) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
18986 := $((1 + (3!! + 5!)) + ((7!/9 - 7) + (5^{3!}))) \times 1$
18987 := $((1 + (3!! + 5!)) + ((7!/9 - 7) + (5^{3!}))) + 1$
18988 := $((1 - (3 - 5)^7) - (9 - ((7^5) + 3 \times 1)))$
18989 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + ((9 - 7) - 5!))) - 3!! + 1$
18990 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((5 + 7) - 9)! \times (75 \times 31))$
18991 := $1 - (((3^5) - (7! + 9)) + (7!/5)) \times (3! - 1)$
18992 := $((1 + ((3 - (5 \times 7)) \times 9)) + 7!) - 5 \times (3 + 1)$
18993 := $1 \times (3^5 + (((7 - (9 - 7))^5) \times 3! \times 1))$
18994 := $((1 - 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 + 7!) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
18995 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 - (7 + (9 \times 7)))) \times ((5 \times 3!) - 1)$
18996 := $(1 + ((35 \times 79) \times 7)) - ((5! \times 3) \times 1)$
18997 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) - 7) + 9 \times (((7 + 5)^3) - 1)$
18998 := $1 - ((3! - (5! + 7)) \times ((9 - 7) + 5 \times 31))$
18999 := $1 \times (((3^{5-7+9}) + ((7^5) + 3!)) - 1)$
19000 := $((1 + 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) - 1)$
19001 := $((1^{3!} + 5!) + ((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5))) - 3!! \times 1$
19002 := $((1 + 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) + 1)$
19003 := $((135 - 7) + (97 \times 5)) \times 31$
19004 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) - (((7 \times (\sqrt{9})!) \times (7 - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
19005 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5 \times (7 + (9 \times (7 \times (5 \times (3 + 1))))))$
19006 := $((1 + (3 \times (5 + 79))) \times 75) + 31$
19007 := $((13 \times 5!) - 7) \times 9 + 7! - (5 \times (3 - 1))$
19008 := $(1^{35}) \times ((797 - 5) \times (3 + 1)!)$
19009 := $(1^{35}) + ((797 - 5) \times (3 + 1)!)$
19010 := $((13 + (5! \times 79)) \times (7 - 5)) + (3 + 1)!$
19011 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 + 7 + 9) \times ((7 \times 5!) + 31))$
19012 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 \times 7) \times (9 + (7 + 5!))) - (3! + 1))$
19013 := $(13 + 5!) + (((7!/9) \times 7) \times 5) - 3!! \times 1$
19014 := $((1 - 3!) + ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
19015 := $(1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + (5^{3!})) \times 1$
19016 := $(13 - 5) \times (((797 - 5) \times 3) + 1)$
19017 := $((13 \times 5!) + (79 \times 7)) \times (5 + 3 + 1)$
19018 := $((13 \times 5!) - 7) \times 9 + (7! + ((5 - 3) - 1))$
19019 := $((1 + (35 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) - (3 - 1))$
19020 := $((1^3 + 5!)! - (79 + 7)) \times (5 \times (3! \times 1))$
19021 := $1 + (((3!! \times 5) - ((79 + 7) \times 5)) \times 3! \times 1)$
19022 := $1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) - (7 \times (5^{3-1})))$
19023 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) - (7 \times (5^{3-1}))$
19024 := $(1 + 3) \times (5 + (((797 - 5) \times 3!) - 1))$
19025 := $((13 + 5) + 7) \times ((9 + 753) - 1)$
19026 := $(13 + 5) \times (7 \times ((97 + 53) + 1))$
19027 := $1 + (((3 \times (57 - 9)) + 7) \times (5! + (3! \times 1)))$
19028 := $(1 + 3) \times ((57 \times (9 + 75)) - 31)$
19029 := $1 - ((3 - ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 + 7) + 5!))) \times (3 + 1))$
19030 := $(1 + 3) - (((5 - 7) \times 9) \times (7 \times (5! + 31)))$
19031 := $(1^{3!}) + (((5! \times 79) + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1))$
19032 := $13 \times ((57 + (9 \times 75)) \times (3 - 1))$
19033 := $(13 + (5 \times (7 \times 97))) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
19034 := $(1 + (3^5 + (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 - 5) \times 31)$
19035 := $(13^{5+7-9}) + ((7^5) + 31)$
19036 := $1 \times (3! + (((5! \times 79) + (7 \times 5)) \times (3 - 1)))$
19037 := $1 \times (((35 - (7 + 9)) \times ((7!/5) - 3!)) - 1)$

- 19038** := $((1 \times 3)! - 5!) \times (7 - (((9 \times 7) - 5) \times (3 \times 1)))$
19039 := $(1 + ((35 - (7 + 9)) \times ((7!/5) - 3!))) \times 1$
19040 := $((1 \times 35) - 7) \times ((9 \times 75) + (3! - 1))$
19041 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + ((97 + 5!) \times 3!))) \times 1$
19042 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 + 7!) + ((97 + 5!) \times 3!))) + 1$
19043 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5 \times 7) \times 97)) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
19044 := $1 \times ((3 - ((57 + 9) + 75))^{3-1})$
19045 := $1 + ((3 - ((57 + 9) + 75))^{3-1})$
19046 := $((((1 \times 35) \times 7) + 9) \times 75) - (3 + 1)$
19047 := $13 + ((579 + (7 \times 5)) \times 31)$
19048 := $((((1 \times 35) \times 7) + 9) \times 75) - (3 - 1)$
19049 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7))) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1)$
19050 := $((((13 + 5) + 7) \times (9 + 753)) \times 1$
19051 := $((((13 + 5) + 7) \times (9 + 753)) + 1$
19052 := $((((1 \times 35) \times 7) + 9) \times 75) + (3 - 1)$
19053 := $(1 - ((3! \times 5!) - 7!)) - (((9 - 7!) + 5!) \times 3) + 1$
19054 := $((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + 5) \times (3! + 1)$
19055 := $(1 - ((3! \times 5!) - 7!)) - (((9 - 7!) + 5!) \times 3) - 1$
19056 := $(1 + ((3! \times 5!) + (7 - (9 - 75)))) \times (3 + 1)!$
19057 := $((1 \times 3)! \times (579 - 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
19058 := $((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + ((79 \times 7) + ((5^{3!}) \times 1))$
19059 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((5! + 797) \times (5!/3!)) - 1)$
19060 := $((1 + 3) - 5!) + (((7 \times 97) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)!)!$
19061 := $(1 - 3!) + (5 \times (((7!/9) \times 7) + 5) + 31)$
19062 := $((1 \times 3) \times ((5 - 7) \times 9)) \times (7 - (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
19063 := $((((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7) + (5! + ((3! + 1)!))$
19064 := $(1 + ((3^5 + 7) \times 9)) + (((7^5) + 3!) \times 1)$
19065 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((5! - 7) + (97 - 5)) \times 31)$
19066 := $((1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + (7^5)) + (3! \times 1)$
19067 := $(1 \times ((3 \times 57) \times 9)) + ((7^5) + (3! + 1))$
19068 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times (79 \times 7)) - (5!/3)) - 1)$
19069 := $((((1 + 3)! - (5 \times 79)) + 7!) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
19070 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) - ((7!/(5!/3)) + 1)$
19071 := $13 \times ((5 + 7) + (97 \times (5 \times (3 \times 1))))$
19072 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5)^7)) \times ((9 - 7) - (5! + 31))$
19073 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + (7!/9))) + ((7^5) + (3! \times 1))$
19074 := $((((1 \times 35) \times 7) + 9) \times 75) + (3 + 1)!$
19075 := $((((1 - 35) + 797) \times 5) \times (3! - 1))$
19076 := $((((1^{3!}) - 5) + 7)^9) - ((7 - 5!) + ((3! \times 1)!))$
19077 := $(1 \times 3) \times (((57 + 9 - 7) \times 5!) - (3! + 1))$
19078 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) + ((7 - 5!) - (3! \times 1))$
19079 := $((((1 \times (3^5)) + 7) - 97) \times 5!) + (3! - 1)$
19080 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 \times 79) + (7 \times (5^{3+1})))$
19081 := $(1 \times (((3 + 5) \times 7) + 97) \times 5!) + (3! + 1)$
19082 := $((((1 + 3)! + 5) \times 7) \times (97 - ((5 - 3) + 1))$
19083 := $((1 \times 3) - 5!) + ((7! - ((9 - 7) \times 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
19084 := $13 \times ((5 + 7) + ((97 \times (5 \times 3)) + 1))$
19085 := $1 - (((3! + 5) + ((7! + 9) - 7!)) \times (5 - 31))$
19086 := $(((((1 \times 3)! + 5!) \times 7) \times 9) + 7!) + (((5 - 3) + 1)!)$
19087 := $(1 + 3!) + (((5 + (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times 5!) + ((3! + 1)!))$
19088 := $((1 - (3^5)) + (7! + (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1)$
19089 := $1 - (((3 \times 5!) - 7!) - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)$
19090 := $(1 - (3! - 5!)) \times (7 + 9 + (75 \times (3 - 1)))$
19091 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) + (((7 - 5!) + 3!) + 1)$
19092 := $(1 - (((3 \times 5!) - 7!) - (97 - 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
19093 := $(1 - 3 + (5 \times (7 \times 9))) \times (7 + (53 + 1))$
19094 := $((((1 + 3)! - (((5! + 7) - 9) \times (7 - 5!)) - 3!)) \times 1$
19095 := $1 \times ((35 - (7 + 9)) \times ((7!/5) - (3 \times 1)))$
19096 := $1 \times ((3 - 5) \times ((7 - (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 31))$
19097 := $1 + ((3 - 5) \times ((7 - (9 \times (7 \times 5))) \times 31))$
19098 := $((1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 - 9)^7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
19099 := $((1 \times 3)^5 \times 79) - (7 \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
19100 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) \times ((7 \times (9 + (7 + 5!))) + 3 \times 1)$
19101 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7!/(9 + 7)) \times 5)) + 3!) - 1$
19102 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7!/(9 + 7)) \times 5)) + 3!) \times 1$
19103 := $((((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7!/(9 + 7)) \times 5)) + 3!) + 1$
19104 := $((1 \times 3!)! / 5! \times (7! - ((9 + 7) \times (5! - (3 + 1))))$
19105 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((5! - (7! - ((9 \times (7!/5!)) + 3!))) + 1)$
19106 := $((1 - (((3! + 5) - 7)!)) \times (9 - (7 \times 5!))) - (3! + 1)$
19107 := $((1 - (((3! + 5) - 7)!)) \times (9 - (7 \times 5!))) - 3! \times 1$
19108 := $((1 \times 3!) / 5 \times (7 + 9)) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)$
19109 := $((1 \times (35 \times ((79 + 7) + 5))) \times 3!) - 1$
19110 := $((1 - (3 + 5)) + (79 \times 7)) \times (5 \times (3! + 1))$
19111 := $((1 \times (35 \times ((79 + 7) + 5))) \times 3!) + 1$
19112 := $((1 \times ((3^5) - 7)) \times (9^{7-5})) - (3 + 1)$
19113 := $((13 - 5) \times 797) - 5 \times (3 \times 1)$
19114 := $(1 - 3) + ((5! + (7 - 9)) \times (7 + 5 \times 31))$
19115 := $(1 \times (35 \times (79 \times 7))) - (5! \times (3 - 1))$

$$\begin{aligned}19116 &:= ((1 \times (3 - 57)) \times ((9 - 7) - 5!)) \times (3 \times 1) \\19117 &:= (1 - (35 - (79 \times (7 \times 5)))) \times (3! + 1) \\19118 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) \times 79) \times (7 - ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\19119 &:= ((1 - (((3! + 5) - 7)!)) \times (9 - (7 \times 5!))) + 3! \times 1 \\19120 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) \times (7 - (97 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1) \\19121 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 579) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1) \\19122 &:= ((1 \times ((3^5) - 7)) \times (9^{7-5})) + 3! \times 1 \\19123 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + 797)) - ((5^3) \times 1) \\19124 &:= ((1357 + 9) \times 7) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)) \\19125 &:= ((1^{3!}) \times (5 \times ((7 \times 9)^{7-5}))) - ((3! \times 1)!) \\19126 &:= 1 - (3!! - ((5 \times (7 \times (9 \times 7))) \times (5 + 3 + 1))) \\19127 &:= (((1 + 3) \times 579) + (7^5)) + 3 + 1 \\19128 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 797) \times ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\19129 &:= (((1^{3!}) + 5!) + 7!) + (97 \times (5! + (3 + 1)!)) \\19130 &:= (1^3) \times (((5! \times (7 + 9)) - 7) \times (5 + (3! - 1))) \\19131 &:= (1^3) + (((5! \times (7 + 9)) - 7) \times (5 + (3! - 1))) \\19132 &:= (1 + 3) \times ((5! + (7! - (9 + 7))) - ((5! \times 3) + 1)) \\19133 &:= (1 + (3 - 57)) \times ((9 - (7 \times 53)) + 1) \\19134 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (57^{9-7})) - (5! \times (3 \times 1)) \\19135 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 7) \times 9) + (7! - ((5 + 3) \times 1)) \\19136 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) - (7 + 53)) - 1 \\19137 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) - (7 + 53)) \times 1 \\19138 &:= (((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) - (7 + 53)) + 1 \\19139 &:= ((1 \times (3!! \times 5)) - (79 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}) \\19140 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) - ((7 \times (5 + 3)) + 1) \\19141 &:= 1 \times ((3! \times (579 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\19142 &:= 1 + ((3! \times (579 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})) \\19143 &:= ((1 + 3!!) \times 5) - (((79 + 7) - (5^{3!})) + 1) \\19144 &:= ((1 + 3!!) \times 5) - (((79 + 7) - (5^{3!})) \times 1) \\19145 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5! - 7!)) / 9) \times (7 \times (5! / (3 + 1)!)) \\19146 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times 79) - 75 + (3 + 1)! \\19147 &:= (1 + (3 \times ((5 + 7!) + 97))) + (5! \times 31) \\19148 &:= (1 + (((3^5) - 7!) + 9)) \times (((7 - 5) - 3!) \times 1) \\19149 &:= (1 + (((3^5) - 7!) + 9)) \times ((7 - 5) - 3!) + 1 \\19150 &:= 13579 + 7! + 531 \\19151 &:= (((1 + 3!) - 5)^7) \times ((\sqrt{9 + 7})! + 5!) + (3!! - 1) \\19152 &:= (((1 + 3) + 5!) + ((7 \times 9) / 7)) \times (5! + (3 + 1)!) \\19153 &:= ((1 - (3! \times (57 - 9))) + 7!) + (5!^{3-1})\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19153 &:= ((1 - (3! \times (57 - 9))) + 7!) + (5!^{3-1}) \\19154 &:= (((1 - (3^5)) + (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - (5! - 3!))) + 1 \\19155 &:= ((1 \times (35 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5! \times 31) \\19156 &:= (1^3 + (57 \times (9 + 75))) \times (3 + 1) \\19157 &:= (((13 \times 5!) + 7) \times 9) + ((7! + (5 \times 3)) - 1) \\19158 &:= (((13 + 57) \times 9) - (7 + 5)) \times 31 \\19159 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 5!) - 7) - ((9 + 7) + 5!) \times (3! + 1) \\19160 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) - (7 \times 5))) - (3 - 1) \\19161 &:= 1 - (((3^5) - ((7! - 9) + (7 - 5))) \times (3 + 1)) \\19162 &:= (1 - (3 - 5!)) + (((7 \times 9) + 75)^{3-1}) \\19163 &:= -1 + 3^5 \times 79 - 7 \times 5 + 3 - 1 \\19164 &:= 1 \times 3^5 \times 79 - 7 \times 5 + 3 - 1 \\19165 &:= 13 + ((57 \times (9 + 75)) \times (3 + 1)) \\19166 &:= (1 + 3!) \times (((5 - 79)^{7-5}) / (3 - 1)) \\19167 &:= (1 \times 3 + 5!) + (((7 \times 9) + 75)^{3-1}) \\19168 &:= (1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) + ((7 - 5) - 31) \\19169 &:= (1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) + ((7 - 5) - 31) \\19170 &:= ((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times ((75 - 3) - 1)) \\19171 &:= (1 \times (35 - (7 + 9))) \times ((7! + 5) / (3! - 1)) \\19172 &:= (1^3) - (5 - (((7 \times 97) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)!)) \\19173 &:= 1 - (((35 - 7) \times 9) - (7! + 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\19174 &:= ((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) - (7 + ((5 \times 3) + 1)) \\19175 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times 79) - (7 + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\19176 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (7 + 9)) \times (75 - (3 + 1)!) \\19177 &:= 1 - (((3^5) - (7! + ((9 - 7) - 5))) \times (3 + 1)) \\19178 &:= ((1 - (3 \times 5!)) + (7! + 97)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\19179 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) + 7)) - (5^{3-1}) \\19180 &:= (1 \times 3! \times (5 \times 79)) + ((7^5) + 3 \times 1) \\19181 &:= (1 + (3! \times (5 \times 79))) + (((7^5) + 3) \times 1) \\19182 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) - (7! / (5! \times 3)))) - 1 \\19183 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) - (7! / (5! \times 3)))) \times 1 \\19184 &:= (((1 + 3) + 57) \times 9) \times (7 \times 5) - 31 \\19185 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times ((7 \times 97) - (5! - 3!))) \times 1 \\19186 &:= (1 - 3!!) + (5 \times (((797 \times 5) - 3) - 1)) \\19187 &:= (1 \times (((3^5) - 7!) \times ((9 + 7) - (5! / 3!)))) - 1 \\19188 &:= (13 \times (5! - 79)) \times ((7 + 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\19189 &:= ((1^3 - 57) + (9 \times 75)) \times 31 \\19190 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times 79) + (7 - ((5 \times 3) - 1))\end{aligned}$$

- 19191** := (((1 + 3) + 57) × 9) × (7 × 5) – (3 + 1)!
- 19192** := ((1 – 3!) × 5!) + ((7! – (97 – 5)) × (3 + 1))
- 19193** := (((1 + 3!)⁵/7) – 9) + (((7⁵) – 3!) × 1)
- 19194** := ((1 × (3 + 5)) × ((7!/(9 – 7)) – 5!)) – 3! × 1
- 19195** := ((1 × ((3⁵) × 79)) + (7 – (5 + 3))) – 1
- 19196** := ((1 × ((3⁵) × 79)) + (7 – (5 + 3))) × 1
- 19197** := ((1 × (3 + 5)) × ((7!/(9 – 7)) – 5!)) – (3 × 1)
- 19198** := (1 + (((3⁵) × 79) – (7 – (5 + 3)))) – 1
- 19199** := (((1³⁵) + 79)⁷⁻⁵) × 3) – 1
- 19200** := (((1³⁵) + 79)⁷⁻⁵) × 3) × 1
- 19201** := (((1³⁵) + 79)⁷⁻⁵) × 3) + 1
- 19202** := ((1 × (3 + 5)) × ((7!/(9 – 7)) – 5!)) + (3 – 1)
- 19203** := (1 × 3) – (5 × (((7 + 9) × 75) – ((3! + 1)!))
- 19204** := ((1 – (3⁵)) + (((7! – 9) + 7) + 5)) × (3 + 1)
- 19205** := ((1³ × 5) + 7!) – (((9 – 7) – 5!) × ((3! – 1)!))
- 19206** := (1 × (3 + 579)) × (7 – 5 + 31)
- 19207** := (1 + 3!) + (((5 × (7 + 9))⁷⁻⁵) × (3 × 1))
- 19208** := ((1 × 3 + 5) × ((7⁹⁻⁷)⁵⁻³)) × 1
- 19209** := (((1 – 3!) × (5 – 7)) + 9) × ((7!/5) + 3 × 1)
- 19210** := (1 – 3 + (((5! × 79) + 7) + 5!)) × (3 – 1)
- 19211** := (((1 + 3) + 57) × 9) × (7 × 5) – (3 + 1)
- 19212** := (((13 – 5!) – (7 × 9)) × (7 – 5!)) + 3) – 1
- 19213** := (((13 – 5!) – (7 × 9)) × (7 – 5!)) + 3) × 1
- 19214** := (((13 – 5!) – (7 × 9)) × (7 – 5!)) + 3) + 1
- 19215** := ((1 × 3) × ((5! + (7 × 9)) × 7)) × (5!/(3 + 1)!)
- 19216** := ((((((1 × 3!))! × 5) – 7) – 9) + 7) + (5^{3!×1}))
- 19217** := (1 + (3!! × 5)) + (7 – ((9 + 7) – (5^{3!}) × 1))
- 19218** := (((1 × 3)⁵) × 79) + (7 + ((5 × 3) – 1))
- 19219** := (((1 + 3) + 57) × 9) × (7 × 5) + (3 + 1)
- 19220** := (13 + ((5! – (7 + 9)) + 7)) × (5 × 31)
- 19221** := (1 × 3!) + ((5 × 7) × (((9 × 7) + 5!) × 3) × 1))
- 19222** := (1 × 3!) + (((5 × 7) × (((9 × 7) + 5!) × 3)) + 1)
- 19223** := (1 + (3! + ((5 × 7) × (((9 × 7) + 5!) × 3)))) + 1
- 19224** := ((1 + 3!!) – ((5 + 7) – (97 – 5))) × (3 + 1)!
- 19225** := ((1 – 3 + (5! + 7))⁹⁻⁷) + (5 × 3!! × 1)
- 19226** := (1 × ((3⁵) × 79)) – ((7 – 5) – 31)
- 19227** := (1 + ((3⁵) × 79)) – ((7 – 5) – 31)
- 19228** := (1 + 3) × (5 + ((7! + ((9 – 7) – 5!)) – ((3! – 1)!))
- 19229** := (1 × (((3⁵) × 79) + 7)) + (5³⁻¹)
- 19230** := 1 × (3! × (5 × ((7 × (97 – 5)) – (3 × 1))))
- 19231** := 1 + (3! × (5 × ((7 × (97 – 5)) – (3 × 1))))
- 19232** := (((1 × 3!) + ((5! + (7 × 9)) × (7 × 5))) × 3) – 1
- 19233** := (((1 × 3!))! × 5) – (7 – (((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) – 1))
- 19234** := ((1 × 35) – ((7 – 9)⁷)) × (5! – (3 – 1))
- 19235** := (((1 × 3!))! × 5) – (7 – (((9 + 7) + (5^{3!})) + 1))
- 19236** := 1 + (3!! – ((5 × 7) × ((9 – 7) – 531)))
- 19237** := 1 + ((35 × (7!/9)) – (7 × (53 – 1)))
- 19238** := (((1 + 3)! + (5! × (7!/(9 × 7)))) – 5) × (3 – 1)
- 19239** := (((1 + 3) + 57) × 9) × (7 × 5) + (3 + 1)!
- 19240** := ((1 + 3) + (5! × (7 + 9))) × ((7 + (5 – 3)) + 1)
- 19241** := (1 – (3 + 5)) + ((797 + 5) × (3 + 1)!)
- 19242** := ((1 + 3!))! – (5! + ((7 × (9 – 75)) × 31))
- 19243** := (1 + (((3! + 5!) × (7 × ((9 + 7) + 5))) + 3!)) × 1
- 19244** := (((1 × 3!))! – 5) + ((7 – 9)⁷⁺⁵) × (3 + 1)
- 19245** := (1 × (3 × 5)) × ((7! + (97 – 5))/(3 + 1))
- 19246** := (((1 + 3) + 57) × 9) × (7 × 5) + 31
- 19247** := ((1 + 3!) – ((5! – 7!) + 97)) + (5!³⁻¹)
- 19248** := (13 – 5) × ((797 + 5) × (3 × 1))
- 19249** := (1³⁵) + ((797 + 5) × (3 + 1)!)
- 19250** := (13 + 57) × (((97 – 5) × 3) – 1)
- 19251** := (((1 + 3)! × 57) + 9) + 7! × ((5 – 3) + 1)
- 19252** := (((1 × 3!) × 5!) – 7) × (9 + ((7 + 5) + 3!)) + 1
- 19253** := ((1 + ((3⁵) × 79)) + (7 × (5 + 3))) – 1
- 19254** := ((1 × (3⁵) × 79) + ((7 × (5 + 3)) + 1)
- 19255** := (1 + 3) + ((579 + (7!/5!)) × 31)
- 19256** := (1 × 3!) + ((5 × 7) × (((9 × 7) + 5!) × 3) + 1))
- 19257** := 1 × (3 × ((5! + 797) × ((5 + 3) – 1)))
- 19258** := 1 + (3 × ((5! + 797) × ((5 + 3) – 1)))
- 19259** := ((13 – 5!) × ((7 – 97) × (5 – 3))) – 1
- 19260** := (13 – 5!) × ((7 – 97) × ((5 – 3) × 1))
- 19261** := (1 – 3!!) – ((5 – (7!/9)) × ((7 + 5) + (3 + 1)!))
- 19262** := ((1 × 3!))! + ((5! + 7) × (9 – ((7 – 5!) – (3 + 1)!))
- 19263** := ((1 × 3!) – (5! – 7!)) – ((9 × 7) – (5!³⁻¹))
- 19264** := ((1 × 35) × (7 + 97)) + ((5^{3!}) – 1)
- 19265** := ((1 × 35) × (7 + 97)) + ((5^{3!}) × 1)
- 19266** := ((1 × 35) × (7 + 97)) + ((5^{3!}) + 1)
- 19267** := (((1 + 3⁵) × 79) + 7) – ((5 × 3) + 1)

- 19268** := $((1 + 3^5) \times 79) + 7) - (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
19269 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) + ((7 + 5) \times (3! \times 1))$
19270 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times ((7 \times 9) + 7)) \times (53 \times 1))$
19271 := $((1 + 3!)! + 5!) + (((7 + 9) \times (7 \times (5! + 3!))) - 1)$
19272 := $((1 \times 3^5) + (7!/9)) \times ((75/3) - 1)$
19273 := $((1 + 3) \times 57) \times (9 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1})$
19274 := $((1 + 3!)^5 + (7!/(9 - 7))) - (53 \times 1)$
19275 := $(1 + 3)! + ((579 + (7!/5!)) \times 31)$
19276 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 79) \times ((7 - 5)/(3 - 1))$
19277 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 79) + ((7 - 5)/(3 - 1))$
19278 := $(1 \times (3! + 57)) \times ((97 + 5) \times (3 \times 1))$
19279 := $(1 \times 357) \times ((9 \times (7 - 5)) \times 3) + 1$
19280 := $((1 \times 3!)! - (((5 \times 79) - 7!) + 5) \times (3 + 1))$
19281 := $(135 \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) + 5!)) - (3 + 1)!$
19282 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) - (7 - (((9 \times 7) + (5^{3!}) + 1))$
19283 := $((1 - 3!)! + ((579 \times 7) - 5!)) \times 3! - 1$
19284 := $((1 - 3!)! + ((579 \times 7) - 5!)) \times 3! \times 1$
19285 := $((1 - 3!)! + ((579 \times 7) - 5!)) \times 3! + 1$
19286 := $(1 - 35) + ((7 + 9 + 7) \times (5! + 3! \times 1))$
19287 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 79) + (7!/5!) - 31$
19288 := $((1 + 3) - ((5 - 7!) + (97 + 5!))) \times (3 + 1)$
19289 := $((1 + 3)! \times (5! + (7 \times 97))) + (5! - (3! + 1))$
19290 := $((1 \times 3) - (5 \times ((7 - 9)^7))) \times (5 \times 3! \times 1)$
19291 := $1 - (((3 - (5! + (7^{\sqrt{9}}))) \times 7) + 5) \times 3! \times 1)$
19292 := $((1 + 3) + (57 - 9)) \times (7 \times (53 \times 1))$
19293 := $(1 - (3 + 57)) \times (9 - (7!/(5 \times 3) \times 1))$
19294 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 79) + (7 + (5 + (3! \times 1)))$
19295 := $((1 \times 3^5) \times 79) + (7 \times ((5 \times 3) - 1))$
19296 := $((1 \times 3^5) + (7 \times (9 \times 7))) + 5! \times (3 + 1)!$
19297 := $((1 + 3!)^5 + ((7!/(9 - 7)) - ((5 \times 3!) \times 1))$
19298 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 79) + 7) + (5 \times (3 \times 1))$
19299 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) + (((7 \times 97) + 5!) \times (3 + 1))!$
19300 := $((1 - (3! - (5 \times 797))) - 5!) \times (3! - 1)$
19301 := $(1 \times 35) \times (79 \times 7) - (53 + 1)$
19302 := $(1 \times 35) \times (79 \times 7) - (53 \times 1)$
19303 := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + (7 + ((9 + 7) \times (5! \times (3! \times 1))))$
19304 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) - ((7 - 5!) + (3! \times 1))$
19305 := $(13 \times (5 \times (7 + (97 - 5)))) \times (3 \times 1)$
19306 := $(1 - 3 + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) - 5)) \times (3! + 1)$
19307 := $(1 \times (((3 - 5!) + 7!) - (9 + 7))) + (5! \times ((3! - 1))!)$
19308 := $((1 + 3!)! - ((5 \times 7) + 97)) + (5!^{3-1})$
19309 := $(1 - (35 - (7! - 97))) + (5!^{3-1})$
19310 := $(1 - (3! + 5)) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
19311 := $(1 \times 3) - (5! + (((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)))$
19312 := $((1 \times 3) \times (5! \times 7)) + (9 + (7^5)) - (3 + 1)!$
19313 := $((1 - ((3 + 5) \times (7 + 9))) + 7!) + (5!^{3-1})$
19314 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) - (7 - 97) + ((5^{3!}) - 1)$
19315 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) - ((7 - 5!) - (3! - 1))$
19316 := $(1^3 - (5! - ((7! - 97) + 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
19317 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) - ((7 - 5!) - (3! \times 1))$
19318 := $(13 \times (5 - 7)) \times ((9 - 753) + 1)$
19319 := $(1 \times ((35 \times 79) \times 7)) - (5 + 31)$
19320 := $(1 \times 35) \times (((7 \times 9) + 75) \times (3 + 1))$
19321 := $((135 - 7) + 9) + (7 - 5)^{3-1}$
19322 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times 79) + (7!/(5!/3)) - 1$
19323 := $(1 \times (3 \times 57)) \times (9 + ((7 \times (5 \times 3)) - 1))$
19324 := $((1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) + 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!)$
19325 := $(1 \times 3!)! + (5 + (((7 - (9 - 7)))! \times 5) \times 31))$
19326 := $(1 + (35 \times (79 \times 7))) - (5!/(3 + 1))$
19327 := $(1 + 3!) + (5! \times (79 + (75 + (3! + 1))))$
19328 := $((1 - 3!)! + 5) - (7 - 9)^7 \times (5! + 31)$
19329 := $(135 \times ((7 + (9 + 7)) + 5!)) + (3 + 1)!$
19330 := $1 \times ((35 \times (79 \times 7)) - (5^{3-1}))$
19331 := $1 + ((35 \times (79 \times 7)) - (5^{3-1}))$
19332 := $(1 \times (3 - 57)) \times ((9 - 7) - ((5! \times 3) \times 1))$
19333 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) \times 7) + (9 + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1))$
19334 := $((1 + 3^5) \times 7) - (((97 - 5!)^3) + 1)$
19335 := $(13 - (5! \times (7 \times (97 - 5)))) + (3 - 1)$
19336 := $(1 \times (3! - (5! - ((7! - 97) + 5)))) \times (3 + 1)$
19337 := $((1^{3!}) - (5! - 7)) + (9 + 7!) + (5! \times ((3! - 1))!)$
19338 := $13 + ((57975/3) \times 1)$
19339 := $(13579 + 7!) + (5! \times (3! \times 1))$
19340 := $(1 - 3!) \times (5! - (((797 \times 5) + 3) \times 1))$
19341 := $((1 \times 35) \times (79 \times 7)) - ((5 \times 3) - 1)$
19342 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5) + ((7 \times (9 + 7)) + (5^{3! \times 1}))$
19343 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) \times (((7 + 9) \times (7!/5!)) - (3! - 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 19344 &:= (((1^{35}) + 7!) - 97) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!) \\ 19345 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (5! - (((797 \times 5) + 3) + 1)) \\ 19346 &:= (1 + (35 \times (79 \times 7))) - (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 19347 &:= ((1 - 3 \times 5) - (79 - 7!)) + (5!^{\sqrt{3+1}}) \\ 19348 &:= (1 - (35 \times 79)) \times ((7 - (5 \times 3)) + 1) \\ 19349 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times 79) + ((7!/5!) + 31) \\ 19350 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + ((7!/(5 + 3)) \times 1) \\ 19351 &:= (1 + (3! \times 5)) + ((7 + (9 + 7)) \times (5! + 3!! \times 1)) \\ 19352 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5)) - 3! \times 1) \\ 19353 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) + ((5 - 3!) - 1) \\ 19354 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) - (5/(3! - 1)) \\ 19355 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5)) \times (3! - 1) \\ 19356 &:= (1 + (35 \times (79 \times 7))) + ((5 - 3!) + 1) \\ 19357 &:= 13 \times (((5 - 7) \times (9 - 753)) + 1) \\ 19358 &:= (((1 + 3!)^5) - 7!) + ((9 \times (7 \times 5!)) + 31) \\ 19359 &:= (1 + 3) + (((5 \times 79) \times 7) \times ((5 + 3) - 1)) \\ 19360 &:= (1 - 3!) - (5 \times (7 - (97 \times ((5!/3) \times 1)))) \\ 19361 &:= (13 + 5) + (7! - (97 - (5!^{3-1}))) \\ 19362 &:= (1 + (35 \times 79)) \times (((7 - 5) \times 3) + 1) \\ 19363 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 \times (7 - 975)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19364 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 - 7) \times 97) - 5) + ((3! + 1)!) \\ 19365 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) + (5 + 3!) - 1 \\ 19366 &:= (1 + (35 \times (79 \times 7))) + (5 \times (3 - 1)) \\ 19367 &:= (13 - 5!) \times (((7 - 97) \times (5 - 3)) - 1) \\ 19368 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((5 - 7) \times (9 \times (7 + 531))) \\ 19369 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (79 \times 7)) + ((5 \times 3) - 1) \\ 19370 &:= ((1 + (35 \times 79)) \times 7) + ((5 + 3) \times 1) \\ 19371 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) - (7! - 9)) \times 7) + 5 \times 31) \\ 19372 &:= ((1 - 3 + (5! + 7!)) - ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19373 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times (5 + 797)) + ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 19374 &:= ((1 + (3 \times 5 \times 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) + 5!)) - (3 + 1)! \\ 19375 &:= ((1 \times ((3 \times 57) - 9)) - 7) \times (5^3 \times 1) \\ 19376 &:= (((1 + (3 - (5 \times (7 + 9)))) + 7!) - 5!) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19377 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (57^{9-7})) - (5! - (3 \times 1)) \\ 19378 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + ((7 - 9) + 7)) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 19379 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times (57^{9-7})) - (5! - (3! - 1)) \\ 19380 &:= (1 \times 3!) - ((57 + (9 - 7!)) - (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19381 &:= (1 \times 3!) + ((5 + ((7 - (9 - 7)))!) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 19382 &:= (1 + 3!) + ((5 + ((7 - (9 - 7)))!) \times (5 \times 31)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19383 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5! + ((7 \times 9) \times 75)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19384 &:= ((1 \times 3)! - ((5 \times (7 + 9)) - (7! - 5!))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19385 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) + (97 \times 5!) - (3 + 1)! \\ 19386 &:= (1 + ((3! \times 5) + (7 + (9 + 7)))) \times ((5! \times 3) - 1) \\ 19387 &:= (1 - 3!) - (57 - (9 + (7! + (5!^{3-1})))) \\ 19388 &:= 13 + ((5^{79-75}) \times 31) \\ 19389 &:= 1 \times (3!! + ((5! + 7) \times (((9 + 7) + 5) \times (3! + 1)))) \\ 19390 &:= ((1 - 3) - (57 - 9)) + (7! + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19391 &:= (1 \times ((35 \times 79) \times 7)) + (5 + 31) \\ 19392 &:= (((1 \times 3) - (5 \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! + 5!)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19393 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - 31) \\ 19394 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) + (5!/3) - 1 \\ 19395 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 79) \times 7) + (5!/3) \times 1 \\ 19396 &:= (1 \times 35) - (79 - (7! + (5!^{3-1}))) \\ 19397 &:= ((1 - (3 + 5!)) + 79) + (7! + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19398 &:= ((1 - (3^5)) + (7!/9)) \times ((7 + 53) + 1) \\ 19399 &:= (1 - (3! \times 5)) + (((7! - (9 \times 7)) - 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19400 &:= (1 - (3 - (5 + 7))) \times (97 \times ((5!/3!) \times 1)) \\ 19401 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! - ((5 \times 7) + 9)) - 7) \times (5 + (3 + 1)!) \\ 19402 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) - 7) + (97 \times 5!) - (3! + 1) \\ 19403 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (57 + 9)) \times (7^{5-3})) - 1 \\ 19404 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) \times 7) \times (((9 \times 7) \times 5) - (3! + 1)) \\ 19405 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - (((7 - (97 \times 5!)) + 3!) - 1) \\ 19406 &:= (1 + (((3 + 57) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5^3))) \times 1 \\ 19407 &:= (1 + (((3 + 57) \times (9 \times 7)) + (5^3))) + 1 \\ 19408 &:= ((13 \times 5) + 7!) - (97 - (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19409 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (79 \times 7)) + (53 + 1) \\ 19410 &:= (1 \times 3)! \times (((57 + 9) \times (7^{5-3})) + 1) \\ 19411 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 + ((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!))) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19412 &:= 1 \times ((35 + 7!) - ((9 \times 7) - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!!))) \\ 19413 &:= (1 - 3!!) \times (((5 + 7) + 9) - 75)/(3 - 1) \\ 19414 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5 + ((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!))) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19415 &:= (1 \times ((3 \times 5!) - 7)) \times ((9 - (7 - 53)) \times 1) \\ 19416 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 579) + (7! + (5! \times (3 + 1))) \\ 19417 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3! \times 1)) \\ 19418 &:= (((1 \times 3)! \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + ((7^5) + (3!! + 1)) \\ 19419 &:= (((1 \times 3!)^5) + 7) + (((97 \times 5!) - 3) - 1) \\ 19420 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5!)) + (7! + (97 + (5!^{3-1}))) \end{aligned}$$

- 19421** := $((1 \times 3!)^5 + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) - (3 - 1))$
19422 := $((13 + 5) \times ((7 \times 97) + 5!)) + ((3! + 1)!)!$
19423 := $(1 + 3) - ((5 + ((7 + 9) - 7!)) - (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)!))$
19424 := $((1 - 3 \times 5) + (7 - 9)) + 7! + (5!^{3-1})$
19425 := $((135 \times 79) + 7!) + (5! \times 31)$
19426 := $(1 \times 3) - (5 + (((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)))$
19427 := $((13 + 5!) \times 7) + (((9 + 7) + 5!)^{3-1})$
19428 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7!) - (9 \times 7)) - ((5^3) \times 1))$
19429 := $(1 \times 3)! - (5 + (((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)))$
19430 := $((1 - 3!) - 5!) + (7 \times (9 \times 75)) \times (3! - 1)$
19431 := $((1 - 3) - (5 - 7!)) - ((9 - 7) - (5!^{3-1}))$
19432 := $((1^{35}) - ((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!))) \times (3 + 1)$
19433 := $(((((1 - 3!)^5) + 7!) - 9) + ((7^5) + 3!)) \times 1$
19434 := $(((((1 - 3!)^5) + 7!) - 9) + ((7^5) + 3!)) + 1$
19435 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((9 \times 7) + (5! + 3)))) - 1$
19436 := $(1 \times 3 + 5) - (((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
19437 := $(13 + (579 + (7 \times 5))) \times 31$
19438 := $((1 \times (3 + 5!)) \times (79 \times (7 - 5))) + (3 + 1)$
19439 := $((1^{35}) + (7! - (9 - 7))) + (5!^{3-1})$
19440 := $((1 - 3!) + (5 \times 7)) \times 9 \times ((75 - 3) \times 1)$
19441 := $(1 \times (3! + (5! \times (7 + 9)))) + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1)$
19442 := $(1 + (3! + (5! \times (7 + 9)))) + ((7^5) - 3! \times 1)$
19443 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5) - (((7 \times 9) - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
19444 := $((1 + 3) + 5!) + (((7 + (9 + 7)) \times 5!) \times (3! + 1))$
19445 := $((1 \times 3) \times (((5 - 7) + 9)!) + ((7! + 5) - 3! \times 1))$
19446 := $(13 + 5) - (((7 \times 9) - 7!) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)$
19447 := $(1 - 3!) - ((5! - ((7 \times 9) + (7! - 5!))) \times (3 + 1))$
19448 := $((1^{3!}) + ((5 + 7!) + (9 - 7))) + (5!^{3-1})$
19449 := $(1 - ((3 + 5) - (7 + 9))) + (7! + (5!^{3-1}))$
19450 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) + ((7!/5)/(3 + 1))$
19451 := $(1 + (((3 + 5) - (7 - 9)) + 7!)) + (5!^{3-1})$
19452 := $(1 \times ((3! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + (7 + 5))) + ((3! \times 1)!)!$
19453 := $(1 + (3 - 5!)) + (((7!/9) \times 7) \times 5) - 31$
19454 := $(1 + (3! + (((5 - (7 - 9))!) + 7))) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)!$
19455 := $((1 + 3!)! + (((5! \times (7 - 9)) + (7! + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)))$
19456 := $(1 - ((3 \times 5!) - (((7 \times 9) + 7!) + 5!))) \times (3 + 1)$
19457 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 + 7!))) + (((9 - 7) + 5)!) - (3! - 1)$
19458 := $(1 - 3 + ((5^{7-9+7}) + 5!)) \times 3! \times 1$
19459 := $(1 \times 3) - (((5 - 7)^9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3 \times 1))$
19460 := $((1 + 3) \times 5) \times (7 \times ((9 \times (7 + 5)) + 31))$
19461 := $((1 \times (3^5)) \times ((7!/9)/7)) + ((5!/3!) + 1)$
19462 := $(13 + (57 \times 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times (3! \times 1)))$
19463 := $((1 \times 3!)!/5) + ((7! \times \sqrt{9}) + (7! - (5! + (3! + 1))))$
19464 := $(1 \times ((3 - 5!) + ((7 \times 9) + (7! - 5!)))) \times (3 + 1)$
19465 := $((1 + (3 + 5)) + (7 + 9 + 7!)) + (5!^{3-1})$
19466 := $((1 \times (3 + (5! + 7!))) - 97) + (5!^{3-1})$
19467 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) \times (79 + (75 + 3))) - 1$
19468 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) \times (79 + (75 + 3))) \times 1$
19469 := $((1 + (3 + 5!)) \times (79 + (75 + 3))) + 1$
19470 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((79 \times (7 - 5)) + (3! + 1))$
19471 := $((1 + (3! \times ((57^{9-7}) - 5))) + 3!) \times 1$
19472 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times ((5 \times 7) - 9)) + (753 - 1)$
19473 := $((1 \times 35) + 7!) - 9) + (7 + (5!^{3-1}))$
19474 := $(13 - 5!) \times (((7 - ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 3) + 1)$
19475 := $(1 + (3! \times (57^{9-7}))) - (5 \times (3 + 1))$
19476 := $(1 - 3) \times (((5 - 7) \times (9 + 7!)) + (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
19477 := $(1 + 3!) + (5 \times (((7!/9) \times 7) + (5 - 31)))$
19478 := $(1 + 35) - (((7 - 9) - 7!) - (5!^{3-1}))$
19479 := $((1 \times 3!)/5) + 7) \times ((9 + 7) + (5! - (3! + 1)))$
19480 := $(1 - (((3 \times 5 \times 79) - 7!) - (5^{3!}))) - 1$
19481 := $(1 - (((3 \times 5 \times 79) - 7!) - (5^{3!}))) \times 1$
19482 := $(1 - (((3 \times 5 \times 79) - 7!) - (5^{3!}))) + 1$
19483 := $(1 - (3! - 57)) - (9 - (7! + (5!^{3-1})))$
19484 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + ((7 \times 9) \times (7!/5!)) + 31$
19485 := $(1 \times (((3 \times (5 \times 7)) \times (9 \times 7)) - 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)$
19486 := $(1 - 3) + ((57 - 9) + (7! + (5!^{3-1})))$
19487 := $(1 \times 3 + 5!) - (((79 - 7!) + 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
19488 := $(1 \times 3!) \times ((57^{9-7}) + (5 - (3! \times 1)))$
19489 := $1 - ((3! \times ((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 7))) \times (5! - (3 + 1)))$
19490 := $((1 \times 3)! \times ((5! - (7 \times 9))^{7-5})) - (3 + 1)$
19491 := $(1 \times 3) \times (5! + ((797 \times (5 + 3)) + 1))$
19492 := $((1 + 35) + (7 + 9)) + 7! + (5!^{3-1})$
19493 := $(1 \times 3! \times (57^{9-7})) + (5 - (3! \times 1))$
19494 := $((1 \times 3) - 5) \times (7 - (9753 + 1))$
19495 := $(1 \times 3! \times (57^{9-7})) - (5 - (3! \times 1))$
19496 := $(1 \times 3! \times (57^{9-7})) - ((5 - 3!) - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 19497 &:= ((1 + 3!))! + ((5! + (7 \times 9)) \times (75 + 3 + 1)) \\ 19498 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times ((5! - (7 \times 9))^{7-5})) + (3 + 1) \\ 19499 &:= 1 \times 3! + (((57 \times 9) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3)) - 1) \\ 19500 &:= (13 + ((5! + (7 + 9)) + 7)) \times ((5^3) \times 1) \\ 19501 &:= (1 - ((3! - 57) - 9)) + (7! + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19502 &:= (1 - (3^5)) + (((7 + 9 + 7!) - 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19503 &:= ((1 + 3!) + 5!) + (((7!/9) + (7!/5!)) \times 31) \\ 19504 &:= (((1 + 3) - (57 - (9 + 7!))) - 5!) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19505 &:= (1 \times 3! \times ((57^{9-7}) + (5 - 3))) - 1 \\ 19506 &:= (13 + (57 \times (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 3)))) - 1 \\ 19507 &:= (13 + (57 \times (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 3)))) \times 1 \\ 19508 &:= (13 + (57 \times (9 \times ((7 \times 5) + 3)))) + 1 \\ 19509 &:= (1 \times (3 + 57)) + (9 + (7! + (5!^{3-1}))) \\ 19510 &:= (1 \times ((35 \times 79) \times 7)) + (5 \times 31) \\ 19511 &:= (1 \times (3 + 5)) + ((7! + (9 \times 7)) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19512 &:= (1 - 3) \times (5 - (7 + (9753 + 1))) \\ 19513 &:= (13 + (57 + 9)) \times (7 + (5! \times (3 - 1))) \\ 19514 &:= (1 \times (3! \times (57^{9-7}))) + (5 \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19515 &:= (1 + (3 + ((5 \times (7!/9)) \times 7))) - (5! - 31) \\ 19516 &:= (1 - 3 + (5 \times ((79 \times 7) + 5))) \times (3! + 1) \\ 19517 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times ((57^{9-7}) + 5)) - (3! + 1) \\ 19518 &:= ((1 \times 3)! \times ((5! - (7 \times 9))^{7-5})) + (3 + 1)! \\ 19519 &:= (((1 - 3!) + 5) + (79 + 7!)) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 19520 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5! + (7 \times ((9 \times 75) + (3! - 1)))) \\ 19521 &:= (13 \times 5) + (((7! + 9) + 7) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19522 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - 7!) + (9 + ((7^5) - 31)) \\ 19523 &:= (((1 - 3 \times 5) + 7!) + 97) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 19524 &:= (1^3 \times (((57^{9-7}) + 5) \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 19525 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5 \times 7) \times 9) \times (7 - 5)) \times 31 \\ 19526 &:= 1 - (3! + (5! - (7 - ((9 - 7!) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 19527 &:= 1 \times 3 + ((5 + 79) + (7! + (5!^{3-1}))) \\ 19528 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) - ((7! - 9) - ((7^5) - (3 + 1)!)) \\ 19529 &:= 1 - ((3!/5) - ((7 - ((9 - 7!) + 5!)) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 19530 &:= (1^3 + (57 + 97)) \times ((5^3) + 1) \\ 19531 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - 7!) - ((9 - ((7^5) - 3)) + 1) \\ 19532 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - 7!) - ((9 - (7^5)) + 3 \times 1) \\ 19533 &:= ((1 + (3!^5)) - 7!) - ((9 - ((7^5) - 3)) - 1) \\ 19534 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) - ((7 \times 5) + 31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19535 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) - (((7 - 5)^{3!}) + 1) \\ 19536 &:= (1 - 3) \times ((57 + 9) \times (7 - (5 \times 31))) \\ 19537 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) - (((7 - 5)^{3!}) - 1) \\ 19538 &:= (((1^{35}) + 7!) + 97) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 19539 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) - ((7 + 53) + 1) \\ 19540 &:= ((1 \times (3 \times (5 + 7)))/9) \times (7! - (5 \times 31)) \\ 19541 &:= ((1 \times 3!)^5) - (((7! + 9) - (7^5)) - (3! + 1)) \\ 19542 &:= (1 - 3) + ((5 \times ((7!/9) \times 7) - 5) - 31) \\ 19543 &:= (((1 \times 3!) + 5!) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 19544 &:= (((1 + 3)! - 5!) + ((7! - (9 \times 7)) + 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19545 &:= (((13 - 5) + 7!) + 97) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 19546 &:= (1 + (35 \times (7!/9))) - ((7 \times (5 + 3)) - 1) \\ 19547 &:= (1 \times 3 + (5! + (7! - (9 + 7)))) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)) \\ 19548 &:= (1 - 3 + 5) \times (((7 \times 9)/7) \times ((5 + 3!) - 1)) \\ 19549 &:= (1 + (3!^5)) - ((7! - 9) - ((7^5) - 3) - 1) \\ 19550 &:= ((1 + ((3!^5) - 7!)) + 9) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1) \\ 19551 &:= ((1 + ((3!^5) - 7!)) + 9) + (((7^5) - 3) + 1) \\ 19552 &:= 1 + (3 \times (5797 + (5! \times (3! \times 1)))) \\ 19553 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5! + 7!) - (9 - 7)) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19554 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times (5 - 79)) + 7!) - 5 \times 3! \times 1 \\ 19555 &:= ((13 + 5) + 7!) + (97 + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19556 &:= ((1 + 3)! - 5) + ((7! + 97) + (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19557 &:= (13 + 5!) - ((7 + (9 - 7!)) - (5!^{3-1})) \\ 19558 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 - (7 + 9)) \times 7) \times (5! + (3! + 1))) \\ 19559 &:= 1 + (((3!^5) - (7! - 9)) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1)) \\ 19560 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5 \times (((7 + 975) - 3) - 1)) \\ 19561 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times 579) + 7!) + (5!^{3+1}) \\ 19562 &:= 1 + (((3^5) \times 79) + (7 \times (53 - 1))) \\ 19563 &:= ((1 - 3!) - 5!) + (((7! + 9) - 7) - 5!) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19564 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5! \times 79)) + ((7 - 5) \times ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 19565 &:= (13 \times 5) \times ((7!/9 + 7) - ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 19566 &:= ((1^3 + 5) \times (79 + (7!/5))) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 19567 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) - (7 - (5 - 31)) \\ 19568 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times 79) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1)) \\ 19569 &:= ((1 - (3! - 579))^{7-5}) - 31 \\ 19570 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (((5! - 7!) - 9) + ((7!/5) + (3! + 1))) \\ 19571 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times (7!/9)) + (7 - (5 + 31)) \\ 19572 &:= (1 + 3!) \times ((5 + 7) \times ((9 + (75 \times 3)) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 19573** := $1 - ((3! + ((5 + 7) + ((9 - 7!) + 5!))) \times (3 + 1))$
19574 := $((13 \times (5 \times 7)) \times 9) + (((7! + 5!) \times 3) - 1)$
19575 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) \times ((7 \times (97 - 5)) + 31)$
19576 := $((1 - 3!) - (5! - (7!/9))) \times ((7!/5!) + 3) + 1$
19577 := $(1 \times 3!) - (5! - (7 \times (97 \times (5 + (3 + 1)!))))$
19578 := $((13 \times 5!) - 79) + (7! + 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
19579 := $1 \times 3 + ((5! + 7!) + ((9 + 7) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!)))$
19580 := $((13 - 5!) \times ((7 - ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 3)) - 1$
19581 := $((13 - 5!) \times ((7 - ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 3)) \times 1$
19582 := $((13 - 5!) \times ((7 - ((9 \times 7) + 5)) \times 3)) + 1$
19583 := $((1 \times (3^5 + (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 - 5)^{3!})) - 1$
19584 := $((1 \times 3!) + ((5 + 7) + (9 + 75))) \times (3 + 1)!$
19585 := $((1 \times (3^5 + (7 \times 9))) \times ((7 - 5)^{3!})) + 1$
19586 := $((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) - ((7 + (5 + 3)) - 1)$
19587 := $1 - ((3! \times 5) + ((7 + ((9 - 7!) + 5!)) \times (3 + 1)))$
19588 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) \times (((7 + 9) \times 7) + (53 + 1))$
19589 := $(1^{3!}) - ((5! - (7! + (97 - 5!))) \times (3 + 1))$
19590 := $(1 \times ((3! \times (57^{9-7}) + 5!)) - (3 + 1)!$
19591 := $((1 + 3!) + 5!) + (((7 - (9 - 7))^5) \times 3! \times 1)$
19592 := $((1 - ((3 \times 5!) - 7!)) + 97) + 5! \times (3 + 1)$
19593 := $((1 - 3!) - 5) + (((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1)$
19594 := $((1^{35}) \times ((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5))) - 3! \times 1$
19595 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5! - (7! + (97 - 5!))) \times (3 + 1))$
19596 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((7 \times 97) - 5!)) + 31$
19597 := $((1 + 3!)! - (((5 - 7!) + ((9 \times 7) + 5!)) \times 3)) + 1$
19598 := $1 - (3 - ((5 \times (7 \times (9 + 7))) \times (5 \times (3! + 1))))$
19599 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) + (\sqrt{7+9} \times ((7! - 5!) - (3 + 1)!))$
19600 := $((1 - 3) - ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) + 5))^{3-1}$
19601 := $((13 + ((57^{9-7}) + 5)) \times 3!) - 1$
19602 := $((13 + ((57^{9-7}) + 5)) \times 3!) \times 1$
19603 := $((13 + ((57^{9-7}) + 5)) \times 3!) + 1$
19604 := $((1 - 3!) - (5 \times 7)) \times ((97 - (5! + 3)) \times 1)$
19605 := $(1^3) + ((5 \times (7!/9)) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1))$
19606 := $((1^{35}) \times ((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5))) + 3! \times 1$
19607 := $((1 + 35) + (79 \times (7 \times 5))) \times (3! + 1)$
19608 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (57^{9-7})) + (5! - (3! \times 1))$
19609 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (57^{9-7})) + (5! - (3! - 1))$
19610 := $1 + (3 + ((5 \times (((7!/9) \times 7) - 5)) + 31))$
19611 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (57^{9-7})) + (5! - (3 \times 1))$
19612 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5 \times (((7!/9) \times 7) - 5)) + 31)$
19613 := $((1 + 3!) \times ((5 \times (7!/9)) + 7)) - (5 + 31)$
19614 := $((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) + ((7 + (5 + 3)) - 1)$
19615 := $(1 + (35 \times (7!/9))) + (7 + ((5 + 3) - 1))$
19616 := $(1 + 3) \times (((579 + (7! + 5)) - 3!) \times 1)$
19617 := $(1^{35}) - (((7 + 9) - 7!) + 5!) \times (3 + 1)$
19618 := $(1^{35}) - ((7 \times 9) - ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1)))$
19619 := $((1 - (3 - 5))^7) \times 9 - ((7 - 5)^{3! \times 1})$
19620 := $(1 + 3) \times ((579 + (7! + 5)) - (3! - 1))$
19621 := $(((((1 \times 3!)! / (5 + 7)) \times ((9 \times 7) \times 5)) + 3!) + 1$
19622 := $(13 + (5 \times (7!/9))) + (((7^5) + 3) - 1)$
19623 := $(((((1^{3!}) - 5) + 7)^9) - ((7 + 5) \times (3! - 1)))$
19624 := $(((((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) - (7 \times 9)) + ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!)))$
19625 := $(1 + (3 + 5)) - (((7 + 9) - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
19626 := $(1 \times 3!) \times ((5 \times (7 \times 97)) - (5! + 3 + 1))$
19627 := $((1 + 35) \times 79) + ((7^5) - (3 + 1)!)$
19628 := $((1 + 3) + ((5 \times ((7 + 9) \times 7)) \times 5)) \times (3! + 1)$
19629 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times (7!/9) - (7 - (5 + 31))$
19630 := $1 \times ((3! + (5 \times 7)) \times ((9 + 7) + (5 + 3!) - 1))$
19631 := $((1 - (3! - 579))^{7-5}) + 31$
19632 := $((1^{3!})^5) + (((7!/9) \times 7) \times 5) + 31$
19633 := $((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) + (7 - (5 - 31))$
19634 := $(13 + 5) - (((7 + 9) - (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
19635 := $1 \times ((3! + 5) \times (7 \times (975 - 3! \times 1)))$
19636 := $1 + ((3! + 5) \times (7 \times (975 - 3! \times 1)))$
19637 := $((13 \times 5!) + 79) \times (7 + 5) - 31$
19638 := $1 + 35 + (((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 - 1)$
19639 := $1 - (3! \times ((5! - ((7 \times (97 \times 5)) - 3)) - 1))$
19640 := $(1^3 - (5! + (((7 + 9) - 7!) - 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
19641 := $(1^3) + (5 \times ((7 + 975) \times (3 + 1)))$
19642 := $((13 + 5!) - (7!/9)) \times ((7 - 53) \times 1)$
19643 := $(((((1 \times 35) \times (7!/9)) + 7) + 5) + 31$
19644 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + ((7! + (9 + 7)) - 5!))) - ((3! - 1)!)$
19645 := $((1 + 3!) + (5 \times (7!/9))) + ((7^5) + 31)$
19646 := $(1 + 3!) + (5! + ((79 + 7!) + (5!^{3-1})))$
19647 := $((1 + 3)^5) + (7! + (97 \times 5)) \times (3 \times 1)$
19648 := $(13 - (5! - ((7! - (9 + 7)) - 5))) \times (3 + 1)$
19649 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) + ((7!/9) \times 7)) \times 5 - 31$

- 19650** := $(1 - ((3! - 5!) - (7 + 9))) \times (75 \times (3 - 1))$
19651 := $((((1 - 3 + 5)^7) \times 9) + 7) - ((5!/3) - 1)$
19652 := $((13 + 5!) \times 7) - (((9 - (7 \times 5)) \times 3!!) - 1)$
19653 := $(1 - 35) + (7! + (97 \times (5! + 31)))$
19654 := $((1 - 35) - 7) + (9 \times 75) \times 31$
19655 := $((1 - (3 - 5!)) + 7!) + (97 + (5!^{3-1}))$
19656 := $((1 + 3) - (5 - 79)) \times (7 \times (5 + 31))$
19657 := $(1 - (((3! - 5) - 79) \times (7!/5!)) \times 3!) \times 1$
19658 := $(1 - (((3! - 5) - 79) \times (7!/5!)) \times 3!) + 1$
19659 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 - (7 - ((9 - 7!) + 5!))) \times (3 + 1))$
19660 := $1 \times (3 + (((5! + 7!) + 97) + (5!^{3-1})))$
19661 := $1 + (3 + (((5! + 7!) + 97) + (5!^{3-1})))$
19662 := $(1 - (((3! - 5) - 79) \times (7!/5!))) \times 3! \times 1$
19663 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (7 \times ((97 + 5) \times (3 + 1)))$
19664 := $(1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3)) - 1$
19665 := $(1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3)) \times 1$
19666 := $1 \times 3 + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3) + 1$
19667 := $1 \times 3! + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3) - 1$
19668 := $1 \times 3! + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3) \times 1$
19669 := $13 \times (((5! + 79) \times 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1)!))$
19670 := $1 \times ((3 \times (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3)) - 1)$
19671 := $1 \times ((3 \times (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3)) \times 1)$
19672 := $((1 + (3! - (5! - 7!))) - 9) \times (7 - 5 + 3 - 1)$
19673 := $(1 + (3 + 5)) - ((7 + 9) - ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1)))$
19674 := $((1 - (3! - ((5! \times 79) \times (7 - 5)))) + 3!!) - 1$
19675 := $((1 - (3 - 5))^7) \times 9 - (7 - 5 + 3! \times 1)$
19676 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 + (7 - 9)) + 7!) - (5! + 3 + 1))$
19677 := $((1 - 3) - (5! \times ((7 \times (97 - 5!)) - 3))) - 1$
19678 := $(1 - 3!) - (((57 - 9) - 75)^3 \times 1)$
19679 := $((1 + 3 - 5)^{7 \times 9}) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
19680 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (((5 \times 79) \times (7 - 5)) \times (3 + 1)!)$
19681 := $((1^{35})^{7 \times 9}) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
19682 := $(1 + 3) + ((579 \times 7) + (5^{3! \times 1}))$
19683 := $((1 \times 3)^{5-7+(9-7) \times 5}) \times (3 \times 1)$
19684 := $((1 \times (3 - 5!)) - 7) - 9) \times (7 - (5 \times 31))$
19685 := $((1 + 3)! + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3)) - 1$
19686 := $(1 \times 3!) + (((5 + 7) - (9 + 7)) \times (5! - ((3! + 1)!)))$
19687 := $((1 + 3)! + (((5! - 7) \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times 3)) + 1$
19688 := $((1^{35} + 7!) + (97 \times (5! + 31))$
19689 := $((1 + 357) \times (9 - (7 - 53))) - 1$
19690 := $(((((1^{3!}) - 5) + 7)^9) + (7 + 5)) - (3! - 1)$
19691 := $((1 - (3 - 5))^7) \times 9 + (7 - 5 + 3! \times 1)$
19692 := $1 - (((3! - (5 \times 7)) \times 97) \times (5 + 3 - 1))$
19693 := $((1 + 3!) + (5! \times 79)) \times (7 - 5) + (3!! - 1)$
19694 := $((13 - (5! \times (7 - 9))) \times 75) + (3!! - 1)$
19695 := $(13 \times 5) \times ((7! / (9 + 7)) - (5 + (3! + 1)))$
19696 := $((1 + 3) - (5! - 7!)) \times (((9 - 7) + 5) - (3 \times 1))$
19697 := $1 - (((35/7)! - 9) - 7!) + 5) \times (3 + 1)$
19698 := $(1 \times 3! + (5 + 7!)) + (97 \times (5! + 31))$
19699 := $((13 \times 5!) + 79) \times (7 + 5) + 31$
19700 := $(((((1^{3!}) - 5) + 7)^9) + (7 + 5)) + (3! - 1)$
19701 := $((1 \times 35) \times ((7! / 9) + 7)) - (5! + (3 + 1)!)$
19702 := $(1 - (3 + 5!)) - ((7 \times (9 - (7 + 5!))) \times (3 + 1)!)$
19703 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5! + 7!) - (97 - (5!^{3-1}))$
19704 := $((1 - 3 + 5)^7) \times 9 + (7 + (5 \times 3)) - 1$
19705 := $((1 - 3 + 5)^7) \times 9 + (7 + (5 \times 3)) \times 1$
19706 := $(1 - 3 + 5!) \times ((7 + (9 + (7 + 5!))) + (3 + 1)!)$
19707 := $((1 \times 3!) + (5 + 7 + 9)) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
19708 := $(1^3) \times (((5 + (7! + (9 - 7))) - 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
19709 := $(1^3) + (((5 + (7! + (9 - 7))) - 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
19710 := $(1 + ((3! + (5 \times 7)) \times (9 + 7))) \times (5 \times (3! \times 1))$
19711 := $((1 + (3 \times 5)) + ((7! / 9) \times 7)) \times 5 + 31$
19712 := $(1 \times ((3! + 5) \times 7)) \times ((9 - 7)^{5+3 \times 1})$
19713 := $1 \times ((3!! / 5) + (((7! / 9) \times 7) \times 5) - 31)$
19714 := $1 \times (((35 \times 79) \times 7) + ((5! \times 3) - 1))$
19715 := $1 + (((35 \times 79) \times 7) + ((5! \times 3) - 1))$
19716 := $(1 - ((3 - 5) \times 79)) \times (7 + (5! - (3 \times 1)))$
19717 := $(1 + ((35 \times 79) \times 7)) + ((5! \times 3) + 1)$
19718 := $((1 - 3) \times (5 - 7)) \times (9 + (7! - 5!)) + 3) - 1$
19719 := $(1 - (3 - (5 \times (7 \times 9)))) \times (7 \times (5 + 3 + 1))$
19720 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 57) - 97) \times (5 + (3 + 1)!)$
19721 := $(13 \times (5! - 79)) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3 - 1)$
19722 := $(1 + ((3^5) \times 79)) - (7 - 531)$
19723 := $(1 + (3! \times (5 - (7 - 9)))) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1))$
19724 := $((1 + 3!)^5 + 7) + ((97 \times 5!) / (3 + 1))$
19725 := $((1 \times 3!)! + ((5 \times 7) \times ((9 \times 7) + (5! \times (3 + 1))))$
19726 := $(1 \times 3!) + ((5! + (7! / 9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3! \times 1))$
19727 := $((1 + 3!) + 5) \times 7) \times 97) + (5 + 31)$

- 19728** := $((1 \times (3 - 5)) - ((7 + 9) - (7 \times 5!))) \times (3 + 1)!$
19729 := $(1 + ((3! \times (57 - 9)) + 7!)) + (5!^{3-1})$
19730 := $(1 + 3!) + (5! + (((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 \times 1))$
19731 := $(1 + 3!) + (5! + (((7!/9) \times (7 \times 5)) + 3 + 1))$
19732 := $((13 - 5!) + 7!) \times (9 - (((7 - 5) \times 3) - 1))$
19733 := $((((1 + 35) + 7!)/9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3! + 1)$
19734 := $((1 \times 3!) \times (57^{9-7})) + (5! \times (3 - 1))$
19735 := $((((1 + 35) + 7!)/9) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3! - 1)$
19736 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 - 7) + 9)! - (75 + 31))$
19737 := $((((13 \times 5!) - 7) - (9 - 7!)) - 5) \times (3 \times 1)$
19738 := $((1 + (35 + 7!))/9) \times (7 \times 5) - (3 - 1)$
19739 := $((1 \times 3!)! + (((5 \times 7) \times 97) + (5^{3!}))) - 1$
19740 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((5! - 7!) + ((975 - 3) \times 1))$
19741 := $(1 + 3) + ((5! - (7 \times 9)) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1)))$
19742 := $(13 - ((5 - 7) \times ((9 + 7!) - 5!))) \times (3 - 1)$
19743 := $((((1^{3!} - 5) + 7)^9) + ((7 + 5) \times (3! - 1)))$
19744 := $((1 + (35 + 7!))/9) \times (7 \times 5) + (3 + 1)$
19745 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((5 - (797 \times 5)) + 31)$
19746 := $((((1^{3!} - 5) + 7)^9) + (((7 - 5)^{3!}) - 1))$
19747 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (7 \times 9) + (((7^5) - 3) \times 1)$
19748 := $(1 + 3) \times (57 - (((9 - 7!) + 5!) + 31))$
19749 := $((1 + 35) - 7) \times ((9 \times 75) + (3! \times 1))$
19750 := $((1 \times 3!)! \times 5) + (7 \times 9) + ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!))$
19751 := $13 - ((5 - (7 \times 9)) - ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1)))$
19752 := $((1 \times 3!)! + 5!) - (7 + ((9 - 7) \times 5)) \times (3 + 1)!$
19753 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 + 975) \times 3) \times 1)$
19754 := $((1 + 3!)^5) + (((7 + 975) \times 3) + 1)$
19755 := $((1 - (3! + 5)) + (7!/(9 - 7))) \times (5 + 3!) - 1$
19756 := $((1 - (3! + 5)) + (7!/(9 - 7))) \times (5 + 3!) \times 1$
19757 := $((1 + 35) \times (79 \times 7)) - (5! + 31)$
19758 := $((1 - (3 \times (5! - 7!))) + 9) + (7! - (53 - 1))$
19759 := $(1 - 3!) + ((5! - (7 - 9)) \times (7 + 5 \times 31))$
19760 := $((1 - 3) \times 5) \times ((7 + 97) \times (5 - (3 + 1)!))$
19761 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 + (7! + (9 + 7))) - 5!)) - (3 \times 1)$
19762 := $(1 \times ((3^5) \times 79)) - ((7 - 5!) \times (3! - 1))$
19763 := $((1 + 3^5) \times (((7 + 9) - 7)^{5-3})) - 1$
19764 := $(1 + 3) \times (5 - 79 + (7! - (5^{3-1})))$
19765 := $((1 + 3^5) \times (((7 + 9) - 7)^{5-3})) + 1$
19766 := $((1 + 3) \times ((5 + (7! + (9 + 7))) - 5!)) + (3 - 1)$
19767 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) + ((7! - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1))$
19768 := $((1 + 3!) - (5 \times (7 + 9))) \times (7 - (5! \times (3 \times 1)))$
19769 := $((1 \times (357 + 9)) + 7) \times (53 \times 1)$
19770 := $((1 - (3! + (5 + 7!))) + (97 \times 5!)) \times (3 \times 1)$
19771 := $((1 \times (3 - 5)) + 7!) - (((9 - 7!) + 5!) \times (3 \times 1))$
19772 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 + (7! + (9 + 7))) - 5!) + 3 - 1)$
19773 := $(1 \times ((3! \times 57) - 9)) + (7! + (5!^{3-1}))$
19774 := $(1 + 3) + (5 \times ((797 \times 5) - 31))$
19775 := $(1 - 3!) \times ((5 - 7!) + (((9 \times 7) \times 5!)/(3! + 1)))$
19776 := $(1 + 3!) \times (((5! \times 7) - (9 + 7)) \times ((5 - (3! - 1)!))!)$
19777 := $(1 + 3!) + (5 \times ((797 \times 5) - 31))$
19778 := $(13 + (5^{79-75})) \times 31$
19779 := $(1 + 3) + ((5 + (7!/9)) \times ((7 \times 5!)/(3 + 1)!))$
19780 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5! + 7!) - 97) - (5! - (3 - 1)))$
19781 := $((1 \times 3!) + 5) + ((7 - (9 - 7!))!) \times (5! + 31)$
19782 := $((1 - 3!) - 5) + ((7! - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1))$
19783 := $1 + ((3 + (57 + 97)) \times ((5^3) + 1))$
19784 := $((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + (7! - (9 + 7)) + (5! \times ((3! - 1)!))$
19785 := $1 + ((3 + ((5! + (7! - 97)) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
19786 := $((1 + 35) - 797) \times (5 - 31)$
19787 := $(1 - (3!/5!)) + ((7! - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1))$
19788 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7!) - (97 - 5)) - (3! \times 1))$
19789 := $1 + (((3! - (5! - 7!)) + (9 + (7 + 5))) \times (3 + 1))$
19790 := $(1 \times 3!) - ((5! - (7! - (9 - (7 \times 5)))) \times (3 + 1))$
19791 := $((1 + (35 \times (7 \times 9))) - 7) \times ((5 + 3) + 1)$
19792 := $(1 - (3! - 5)) + ((7! - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1))$
19793 := $1 - ((3! - (5! + 7)) + (9 - ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1))))$
19794 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5! - ((79 \times (7!/5!)) \times 3!)) + 1)$
19795 := $(1 - 3!) \times (((5 - 7!) - 9) + ((7 \times 5) \times 31))$
19796 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5! - ((79 \times (7!/5!)) \times 3!)) - 1)$
19797 := $((1 + 3!) \times 5!) + (79 + ((7^5) + 31))$
19798 := $(1 - 3) \times ((5! - (7! - 9)) - (7! - (53 - 1)))$
19799 := $((1 \times 3! + 5) \times ((7 - (9 - 7)) \times (5! \times 3))) - 1$
19800 := $(1^3) \times ((57 + 9) \times (75 \times (3 + 1)))$
19801 := $(1^3) + ((57 + 9) \times (75 \times (3 + 1)))$
19802 := $((1 - 3) - 5) + 7! + (9 + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 \times 1)))$
19803 := $1 \times (3! + (5 + ((7! - (97 - 5)) \times (3 + 1))))$
19804 := $1 - ((3 \times ((5 + 7!) - ((97 \times 5!) + 3!))) \times 1)$
19805 := $1 - ((3 \times ((5 + 7!) - ((97 \times 5!) + 3!))) - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 19806 &:= 1 + (((3 + 5!) - 7) + (9 + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 19807 &:= (1 \times 3) - ((5 + ((79 - 7!) + 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19808 &:= ((1^{35}) \times (7! + (9 + ((7! - 5!) \times 3)))) - 1 \\ 19809 &:= (((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times ((7!/9) + 7)) - (5 + 31) \\ 19810 &:= (1 \times 3)! - ((5 + ((79 - 7!) + 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19811 &:= (1 \times (3 - 5!)) + ((7! - ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19812 &:= (((1 \times 35) \times 7) + 9) \times ((75 + 3) \times 1) \\ 19813 &:= (((1 - 3 + 5)^7) \times 9) + (7 + (5! + 3)) \times 1 \\ 19814 &:= ((1 + 3^5) \times 79) + (7 + 531) \\ 19815 &:= 1 \times ((3 - 5!) + (((7 \times 9) + (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 19816 &:= 1 + ((3 - 5!) + (((7 \times 9) + (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 19817 &:= ((1 + (3 + 5)) \times ((7 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) - 3)) - 1 \\ 19818 &:= (((1 \times 3) \times 5!) + 7) \times ((9 \times (7 - 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 19819 &:= ((1 + 35) \times (79 \times 7)) - (5! - 31) \\ 19820 &:= 135 + (((7!/9) + 75) \times 31) \\ 19821 &:= (((((13 \times 5!) - 7) + (9 + 7!)) + 5) \times 3) \times 1 \\ 19822 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) - (((79 - 7!) + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19823 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5! - 7)) + 9) \times (7 + (5 + 31)) \\ 19824 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 19825 &:= (((1 \times 3!)! + (57 + 9)) + 7) \times (5 \times (3! - 1)) \\ 19826 &:= (13 + 5) + ((7! + 9) + (((7! - 5!) \times 3) - 1)) \\ 19827 &:= (1 \times 3!) + (579 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 - 1))) \\ 19828 &:= 1 + (3!) + (579 \times ((7 \times 5) - (3 - 1))) \\ 19829 &:= (1 - ((3 - 5!) \times 79)) - (7! - (5^{3! \times 1})) \\ 19830 &:= ((135 \times (7^{9-7})) - 5) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 19831 &:= (1 - 3!) + ((57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) \times (3! \times 1)) \\ 19832 &:= 1 \times 3 + (5 - (((79 - 7!) + 5) \times (3 + 1))) \\ 19833 &:= ((1 - 3) - 5) - (((7 - 9)^7) \times (5 \times 31)) \\ 19834 &:= ((13 - 5) + 7!) + (((9 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3) - 1 \\ 19835 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 5!) + (79 \times ((7 \times 5) \times (3! + 1))) \\ 19836 &:= ((1 - 3 + 5) \times 7!) - (9 \times (7 - 531)) \\ 19837 &:= (1 + ((3 + 5) + 7!)) + (((9 + 7!) - 5!) \times 3) + 1 \\ 19838 &:= 13 \times (((5 + 7) + 97) \times ((5 \times 3) - 1)) \\ 19839 &:= ((1 \times 3) \times 5) - (((79 - 7!) + 5) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19840 &:= (1^3 - 5) \times (((79 - 7!) + 5) - 3) - 1 \\ 19841 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - 9)) - ((7 + 5!) - (3 + 1)!) \\ 19842 &:= ((1 + 3!) + (5 \times 79)) + (7! + (5! \times (3! - 1)!)) \\ 19843 &:= ((1 + 3) \times 579) + ((7^5) + 3! \times 1) \\ 19844 &:= (1 + 3) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 75)) \times 31) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19845 &:= (((1 - 3) - 5) \times (7 \times 9)) \times (7 - (53 - 1)) \\ 19846 &:= (1 \times 3!) - (((5 \times 7) - (9 \times 75)) \times 31) \\ 19847 &:= (((1 + (3!/5)) \times (7 + 9)) + (7^5)) + 3! \times 1 \\ 19848 &:= (1 + 3)! \times (((5! \times 7) + (9 + 7)) - (5 \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 19849 &:= (1 + 3) + ((5 \times (7 \times 9)) \times (7 \times (5 + 3 + 1))) \\ 19850 &:= (((1 - 3!) - 5) \times (7 - ((9 + 7) \times 5!))) + (3! \times 1) \\ 19851 &:= ((1 + 3) + (5 \times 7)) \times ((97 \times 5) + (3 + 1)!) \\ 19852 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 - 79 + 7!)) - ((5 + 3!) + 1) \\ 19853 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 - 79 + 7!)) - ((5 + 3!) \times 1) \\ 19854 &:= ((1 + 3) \times (5 - 79 + 7!)) - ((5 + 3!) - 1) \\ 19855 &:= ((1 + 3)! \times 5!) + (((7 \times 97) \times 5) \times (3! - 1)) \\ 19856 &:= 1 \times (((3 - (5 + 79)) + (7! + 5)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19857 &:= (13 - 5!) + ((7 \times (97 - 5)) \times 31) \\ 19858 &:= (((1^{3!} - 5) + 7)^9) + (7 \times (5 \times (3! - 1))) \\ 19859 &:= ((1 + ((35 - 7) \times 97)) + 5!) \times (3! + 1) \\ 19860 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7!) - (9 + 75)) + 3 + 1) \\ 19861 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 - (79 - 7!))) - (5 - 3)) - 1 \\ 19862 &:= (1 - (3 \times (5! - 7!))) + ((9 + 7!) + (53 - 1)) \\ 19863 &:= (1 + (3 + 5)) \times (((7 \times (9 \times (7 \times 5))) + 3) - 1) \\ 19864 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 - (79 - 7!))) - (5 - 3!)) - 1 \\ 19865 &:= (((1 + 3) \times (5 - (79 - 7!))) - (5 - 3!)) \times 1 \\ 19866 &:= ((1 - ((3! - (5! - 7)) \times (9 \times 7))) - 5!) \times (3 \times 1) \\ 19867 &:= (1^3) + ((5 \times (7! - (97 \times (5 + 3!)))) + 1) \\ 19868 &:= ((1^{3!} - 5) \times ((7 - 9) + 75) - ((3! + 1)!)) \\ 19869 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + (((5 + 7!) - (97 + 5)) \times (3 \times 1)) \\ 19870 &:= 1 \times 3! + ((5 \times (7! - (97 \times (5 + 3!)))) - 1) \\ 19871 &:= (1 \times 3! \times ((57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3!)) - 1 \\ 19872 &:= (((1^3 + 5)! + (7 + 9)) \times (7 + (5 \times (3 + 1)))) \\ 19873 &:= (1 \times 3! \times ((57 \times ((9 \times 7) - 5)) + 3!)) + 1 \\ 19874 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) - ((7 - 5!) \times 3!)) - 1 \\ 19875 &:= 1 \times (((3^5) \times 79) - ((7 - 5!) \times 3!)) \times 1 \\ 19876 &:= ((1 + 3^5) + ((7 \times 9) \times 75)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19877 &:= 1 + (((3^5) \times 79) - ((7 - 5!) \times 3!)) + 1 \\ 19878 &:= (((1 \times (3 + 5)) + (7!/9)) \times (7 \times 5)) - (3 - 1) \\ 19879 &:= ((1 \times 35) \times ((79 \times 7) + (5 \times 3))) - 1 \\ 19880 &:= ((1 + 3!) \times 5) \times ((79 \times 7) + ((5 \times 3) \times 1)) \\ 19881 &:= (1 \times 3 + ((5 - ((7 - 9)^7)) + 5))^{3-1} \\ 19882 &:= (((1 + 35) \times (79 \times 7)) + 5) - 31 \\ 19883 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5! - 7) \times (9 + 7)) \times (5 + 3! \times 1)) \end{aligned}$$

- 19884** := $((1 - (3 - (5 \times 797))) \times 5) - 31$
19885 := $(1 + 3!) - ((5 - (79 \times (7!/5!))) \times (3! \times 1))$
19886 := $1 - (((3 - (5 \times 797)) + 5) \times (3! - 1))$
19887 := $(1 + 3)! + ((5! + (7 \times 9)) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 + 1)))$
19888 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7!) + (9 - (75 + 3!))) - 1)$
19889 := $(1 + 3)! + (5 \times (7! - (97 \times ((5 + 3!) \times 1))))$
19890 := $((1 + 3!)!) + ((57 + 9) \times (75 \times (3 \times 1)))$
19891 := $((1 \times 3! \times 57) \times 9) + (((7^5) + 3!) \times 1)$
19892 := $((1 \times 3! \times 57) \times 9) + (((7^5) + 3!) + 1)$
19893 := $((1 \times (3! + 5!)) + (7!/9)) \times ((7 \times 5) - 3!) - 1$
19894 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) \times (7 \times (((97 + 5) - 3) - 1))$
19895 := $((1 \times (3^5)) - (7 \times 9)) - 7) \times (5! - (3! - 1))$
19896 := $(1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7!) + (9 - (75 + 3!))) + 1)$
19897 := $((1^{3!}) - 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7!) - 5) - 3! \times 1$
19898 := $1 \times (((35 \times ((7!/9) + 7)) + 53) \times 1)$
19899 := $((1^{3!}) + ((5! - 7) \times (9 + 7))) \times (5 + (3! \times 1))$
19900 := $((1 - 3!) \times 5) \times ((7 - 9) - (75 + (3!! - 1)))$
19901 := $1 \times (3! + (5 \times ((797 \times 5) - 3! \times 1)))$
19902 := $((13 + 57) \times 9) + (7 + 5) \times 31$
19903 := $1 + (3! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5) \times 3!) - 1)$
19904 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 - 79 + 7!) + ((5 + 3!) - 1))$
19905 := $((1 - ((3 - (5 \times 797)) \times 5)) - 3!) \times 1$
19906 := $((1 - ((3 - (5 \times 797)) \times 5)) - 3!) + 1$
19907 := $1 - (((3 - (5 \times 797)) \times 5) + 3 + 1)$
19908 := $(1 \times 3! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5) \times 3!) \times 1$
19909 := $(1 \times 3! \times (((5 \times 79) \times 7)/5) \times 3!) + 1$
19910 := $(1 - (3 - 57)) \times ((9 - 7) + ((5! \times 3) \times 1))$
19911 := $((1 + 3) \times (5 + (7! + (9 - 75)))) - (3! - 1)$
19912 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 - 79 + 7!) + ((5 + 3!) + 1))$
19913 := $((13 \times (5! + 7)) \times 9) + ((7! + (5 \times 3)) - 1)$
19914 := $(1 + 3) + (5 \times ((797 \times 5) - (3 \times 1)))$
19915 := $(1 \times 35) \times (((79 \times 7) + (5 \times 3)) + 1)$
19916 := $((1^{3!}) - 5) \times ((7 \times 9) - 7!) + 5) + (3 \times 1)$
19917 := $((1 + 35) \times 79) \times 7) + 5) + (3 + 1)$
19918 := $1 - (((3 - (5 \times 797)) \times 5) - 3!) - 1)$
19919 := $(1 \times 3!!) - ((5! \times (((7 \times (9 + 7)) \times 5) - 3!!)) + 1)$
19920 := $(1 \times (3 \times 5)) \times (797 + 531)$
19921 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 \times 797) \times 5)) - (3 - 1)$
19922 := $1 \times 3! + (((5 + 7!) + (9 - 75)) \times (3 + 1))$
19923 := $1 \times 3 + (5! \times (((7 \times 9) + 7) + 5!) - (3 + 1)!))$
19924 := $1 \times 3 + (((5 \times 797) \times 5) - (3 + 1))$
19925 := $(1 - 3 + ((5 \times 797) \times 5)) + (3 - 1)$
19926 := $(1 \times 3!) + (5! \times (7 + (9 + (75 \times (3 - 1)))))$
19927 := $((1 + 3)! - 5) + ((79 \times (7!/5!)) \times (3! \times 1))$
19928 := $((1 + 35) \times 79) \times 7) + (5 \times (3 + 1))$
19929 := $(13 \times (5 + 7 + 9)) \times (75 - (3 - 1))$
19930 := $((1^{35}) + (797 \times 5)) \times (3! - 1)$
19931 := $((1 + 3)! - 5) \times (((7 + (9 \times 7)) \times (5 \times 3)) - 1)$
19932 := $((1 + 3) \times (5! - (7! + (9 \times 7)))) \times (5 - (3! \times 1))$
19933 := $(1 \times ((3 + (5 \times 797)) \times 5)) - (3! + 1)$
19934 := $(1 + ((3 + (5 \times 797)) \times 5)) - (3! + 1)$
19935 := $13 + (((5 \times 797) \times 5) - 3) \times 1$
19936 := $(1 + 3) \times ((5 + 7!) - ((97 - 5) - 31))$
19937 := $1 - (3 - ((5! + 7) \times (9 - (7 - (5 \times 31)))))$
19938 := $(1 - 3) + (5 \times ((797 \times 5) + 3 \times 1))$
19939 := $(1 + (3 \times (5 - 7))) - ((9 - (7 \times 5!)) \times (3 + 1)!))$
19940 := $((1 + 3)! + ((5 + 7!) - (9 + 75))) \times (3 + 1)$
19941 := $(1 + 3) + (((5 + (79 \times (7!/5!))) \times 3!) - 1)$
19942 := $1 \times 3! + ((5! + (7 + 97)) \times (5! - 31))$
19943 := $((1 \times (3^5 + (7 + 9))) \times 7) \times (5 + 3! \times 1)$
19944 := $((1 + 35) \times (79 \times 7)) + 5) + 31$
19945 := $(1 + ((3 + 5) \times (7 \times 9))) + (7! + (5^{3-1}))$
19946 := $((1 - ((3! - (5 - 7)) \times (9 - (7 \times 5!)))) \times 3) - 1$
19947 := $(1 \times ((3 + (5 \times 797)) \times 5)) + (3! + 1)$
19948 := $(1 + ((3 + (5 \times 797)) \times 5)) + (3! + 1)$
19949 := $((1 \times 3)^5) \times 79) + (753 - 1)$
19950 := $((135 + 7) - 9) \times (75 \times (3 - 1))$
19951 := $1 + (((3! - (5! - 7!)) + 9) + 7!) \times (5 - (3 \times 1)))$
19952 := $(1^{3!}) \times ((5 + ((7 \times 9) + (7! - 5!))) \times (3 + 1))$
19953 := $((1 - 3) - 5!) + 7!) + ((97 \times 5) \times 31)$
19954 := $(1 \times 3!) - (((5! - 7!) - 9) - (7! + 5)) \times (3 - 1)$
19955 := $(13 \times 5) \times ((7 \times (97 - 53)) - 1)$
19956 := $1 + (((357 \times 9) - 7) + 5!) \times 3!) - 1)$
19957 := $(1^{35}) + (((7! - 9) - (7!/5!)) \times (3 + 1))$
19958 := $1 + (((357 \times 9) - 7) + 5!) \times 3!) + 1)$
19959 := $((1 \times 3!) + (57 \times 9)) + (7! + (5^{3-1}))$
19960 := $(1 \times ((3! + (5 \times 797)) \times 5)) + (3! - 1)$
19961 := $((1 + 3)! + 5) + ((7! + ((9 \times 7) - 5!)) \times (3 + 1))$

$$\begin{aligned} 19962 &:= 1 + (((3! + (5 \times 797)) \times 5) + (3! \times 1)) & 19983 &:= ((1 + 3!)! + (5! + ((7 \times 9) + ((7! - 5!) \times (3 \times 1)))) \\ 19963 &:= (1^3 - 5 + 7)^9 + (7 \times (5! / (3 \times 1))) & 19984 &:= (((1^{35}) \times 7!) - (9 + (7 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19964 &:= (((1 + 3) - 57) + 9) + (7! - 5) \times (3 + 1) & 19985 &:= (1 + ((35 - (7! - 9)) \times (7 - (5 + 3!)))) \times 1 \\ 19965 &:= 1 + ((35 \times (7! / 9)) + (7 \times (53 - 1))) & 19986 &:= ((1 \times 3!)! + ((5! + (7^{9-7})) \times (5! - 3! \times 1))) \\ 19966 &:= (((1 + 3)! \times ((5! \times 7) - 9)) - 7) + (5 + (3 + 1)!) & 19987 &:= (1 \times 3! + 5) \times (79 \times ((7 + (5 \times 3)) + 1)) \\ 19967 &:= (1 + ((3!^5) / (7 + 9))) \times ((7 \times 5) + 3! \times 1) & 19988 &:= (((1 - 3)^5 + 7!) - ((9 + 7) - 5)) \times (3 + 1) \\ 19968 &:= ((1 \times (3 + 5)) - (7 + (9 - (7 \times 5!)))) \times (3 + 1)! & 19989 &:= (1 \times (3!^5)) + ((7 + 9 + 7) \times 531) \\ 19969 &:= (((1 + 3) + (5 \times 797)) \times 5) + (3 + 1)! & 19990 &:= (1 + (357 \times 9)) + ((7^5) - 31) \\ 19970 &:= (1 - 3!) \times (5! - ((7 \times (97 \times 5)) + (3!! - 1))) & 19991 &:= (1 \times (3 \times 5!)) + (((7! / 9) \times (7 \times 5)) + 31) \\ 19971 &:= (((1^{3!}) - (5 - 7))^9) + ((7! / 5) - 3!! \times 1) & 19992 &:= (((1 \times 35) - 7) \times (97 + 5)) \times (3! + 1) \\ 19972 &:= (13 - 5) + (7 \times ((97 - 5) \times 31)) & 19993 &:= (((1^3 + 5)! + 79) \times 7) + (5!^{3-1}) \\ 19973 &:= ((1 + 3) + 5) + (7 \times ((97 - 5) \times 31)) & 19994 &:= (1 - 3) \times (((5 + 79) \times ((7 - 5!) - 3!)) - 1) \\ 19974 &:= ((1 - ((3! + 5) \times (7 \times 9))) + 7!) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) & 19995 &:= (1 - 3!) + (((5 \times (7 + 9)) + (7! - 5!)) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19975 &:= (((1 \times 3)^5) \times (7 + 9)) + ((7^5) - ((3! \times 1)!)) & 19996 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5)) \times (((79 + 7!) - 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19976 &:= ((1 \times 3!) + 5) \times (7! + (((9 + 7) - 5!) \times 31)) & 19997 &:= (1 \times (3! - 5)) + (((79 + 7!) - 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19977 &:= (1 + 3) \times (((5 + 7!) + (9 - 7)) - 53) + 1 & 19998 &:= (1 + (3! - 5)) + (((79 + 7!) - 5!) \times (3 + 1)) \\ 19978 &:= (13 + 5!) + (((7! / 9) + 7) \times 5) \times (3! + 1) & 19999 &:= ((13 - (5! + (7! / 9))) + 7!) + ((5^{3!}) + 1) \\ 19979 &:= ((1 + ((3 - 5) \times (7^{\sqrt{9}}))) + 7!) + ((5^{3!}) - 1) & 20000 &:= (1 + 3) \times (5 + (7! - ((97 - 53) + 1))) \\ 19980 &:= 1 \times (3 \times 5 \times ((7! + 9) - (7 \times 531))) & & \\ 19981 &:= 1 + (3 \times 5 \times ((7! + 9) - (7 \times 531))) & & \\ 19982 &:= ((1 \times 3) - 5) \times (((7 - 9) \times 7!) + (5! - 31)) & & \end{aligned}$$

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to T.J. Eckman, Georgia, USA (email: jeek@jeek.net) in programming the script to develop these representations.

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